

**The International Rice Research Institute
Annual Report 1968**

THE INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE **Annual Report 1968**

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The International Rice Research Institute was established jointly by The Rockefeller Foundation and the Ford Foundation in cooperation with the Republic of the Philippines. It was incorporated in 1960 and dedicated in 1962 when the research program began. This annual report, the seventh to be published by the Institute, presents a detailed account of the work done in 1968.

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* Arrived during year.

** Left during year.

† Arrived and left during year.

‡ On study leave March to Dec., 1968.

∅ On study leave since Aug., 1968.

‡ On study leave since July, 1968.

Director's Introduction

During 1968, the Institute made a strong effort to identify new genetic lines of rice from its breeding program that would have all the advantages of IR8 and IR5 and none of their disadvantages. Although none of the selections were pure enough or had been sufficiently tested to allow them to be named in 1968, enough promising materials were identified to give us confidence that one or two new varieties will be named in 1969.

Each year the Institute staff tests more than 40,000 genetic lines from many different crosses. In fact, since the Institute started its research program more than 1,500 crosses have been made. It is only a matter of time before outstanding varieties will be developed and identified which have the high yield potential and fertilizer responsiveness of IR8, but with superior grain quality and increased resistance to the major diseases and insect pests.

Among other things being developed by the Varietal Improvement Department are varieties adaptable to deep water, high-yielding Basmati types, and early-maturing varieties (100 days from seed to seed).

The outstanding contribution of the Agronomy Department during 1968 was to identify and test several promising herbicides, or combinations of herbicides, that would effectively control weeds in transplanted rice. Trifluralin and MCPA; and α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene and the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D; applied once every 4 days after transplanting gave highly satisfactory control of weeds, grasses, sedges and various broad-leaved species. All three of these chemicals, including the MCPA or 2,4-D, can be applied in a granular form. This eliminates the problems connected with purchasing and maintaining spraying equipment. Also, these chemicals are less costly than handweeding, and two of the three chemicals mentioned are already on the market in the Philippines and hence available to farmers.

The Agronomy Department continued to work with upland rice. In 1967 excellent yields were obtained, but in 1968 the rainfall was quite uneven and lower in total amount. As a result yields were extremely low. This simply shows that rice has low tolerance to drought and in regions where rainfall is highly unpredictable, it would be preferable under upland conditions to plant crops other than rice, such as sorghum, millet, soybeans and maize.

The Agronomy Department has been attempting to increase total annual rice production by growing four crops a year. During 1968, four crops of the variety Taichung (Native) 1 yielded a total of 22,400 kg/ha. This is the highest total annual production of rice yet obtained at the Institute. An early-maturing selection from the IR8 line produced 22,000 kg/ha and another variety which we call "dwarf Peta" yielded 21,800 kilograms. All of these yields were obtained in 365 days or less.

The Agronomy Department continues to conduct a few experiments on farmers' fields and in one in Calamba, IR8 yielded 10,474 kg/ha. This is the highest yield yet obtained on replicated plots in the Philippines. Every effort was made to keep the cash inputs as low as possible, and this high yield was obtained by spending a total of ₱456 for insect and weed control, and for fertilizers. This is of course the cash outlay and does not involve the cost of labor, other than that of weeding. Ten tons of rice should sell for approximately ₱3,300. It would indeed give a farmer a good

labor income from only one crop, and of course, if he has irrigation water, he can grow one or two additional crops during the year.

The most striking contribution of the Entomology Department during 1968 was the further proof that a high degree of immunity to planthopper and leafhopper attack exists in several varieties from India and that this quality is rather simply inherited and can be readily transmitted to improved but susceptible varieties. For example, the variety Mudgo from India is resistant to the brown planthopper, which causes extensive direct damage and is also the vector of the grassy stunt virus disease of rice. Planthoppers caged with this variety live no more than 4 days and do not multiply sufficiently to maintain their population. When Mudgo is crossed with IR8, which is a highly susceptible variety, the progeny in the F₂ generation show a 3:1 segregation, that is, there are three resistant plants to one susceptible. Although the genetics of this have not yet been carefully studied, it appears to be a straight Mendelian ratio indicating that a single dominant gene is responsible for the resistance. If there are modifying genes, their influence must be slight.

A similar study is being carried out with the green planthopper, also a vector of virus diseases. A variety called Pankhari 203 from India has strong resistance to the green leafhopper. The resistance can be incorporated into a susceptible variety in a similar way as is the resistance to the brown planthopper. Preliminary evidence indicates that soon we shall be able to develop improved varieties that have strong resistance to both the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper. This will indeed be a great boon to farmers who now must either spend large amounts of money for insecticides to control these pests or must suffer the yield losses that result from their attacks.

There was widespread evidence obtained this year to indicate that the brown planthoppers on the Institute's field were beginning to develop resistance to diazinon, the chemical which originally gave good control. The Institute has been using this chemical for about 3 years and with a new generation of brown planthoppers every 15 to 20 days, obviously many generations have occurred. We are now testing several new chemicals for insect control on rice and some of them look highly promising.

The Chemistry Department continued to study the protein content of rice grain and the distribution of the essential amino acids. It was mentioned in the 1967 report that quite a few varieties averaged more than 13.5 percent protein in the brown rice (the average protein content of brown rice is about 8 percent). Several of these selections have been crossed with varieties with a good plant type, such as IR8. Very preliminary information indicates that there is some possibility that high-yielding, nitrogen-responsive varieties of rice can be developed that have protein contents averaging 10 percent rather than less than 8 percent. The protein content of rice is strongly influenced by environment and, generally speaking, as yield goes up the protein content goes down. It may take another 2 years to determine for certain whether a significant and consistent high protein level can be introduced into rice varieties through plant breeding.

As mentioned in the 1967 report, the Agricultural Engineering Department has developed a new type of mechanical thresher. During 1968 this piece of equipment was further improved and widely tested. It has proved to be quite successful from the standpoint of acceptance by selected farmers, principally because it is simple to operate, has few mechanical troubles, and can thresh wet rice. Three commercial companies in the Philippines have constructed models after the Institute design, and

some of these manufactured models are now being shipped to other cooperating countries for trial.

The Engineering Department continues to work on equipment for wet land preparation, but it may be several years before something significant will come from the program. Work was started in 1968 on a mechanical stripper for harvesting rice.

The Multiple Cropping program of the Institute was expanded during 1968 because of the increasing awareness of the need and opportunity for growing food crops the year round in tropical Asia. Essentially all the land in the Multiple Cropping experimental area was planted to rice during the monsoon season and to several other crops during the remainder of the year. Among the more successful crops in rotation with rice are soybeans, sweet potatoes, sweet corn, cow peas and sorghum. The program received a grant from The Rockefeller Foundation enabling the construction of a small building for multiple cropping which will have a classroom for training, offices, storerooms, and workrooms for the staff and trainees. It is expected that a multiple cropping training program for the Philippines and Southeast Asia will be underway by June, 1969.

The Rice Production Training Program continued unabated and at an international level. A group of 35 scholars from nine countries were in residence at the Institute from early June until early December, 1968. The largest group was from India; other countries represented included Pakistan, Ceylon, South Vietnam, Indonesia, the United States, Malaysia, Laos, and the Philippines.

The spread of Institute varieties continued throughout Asia and in certain other parts of the world. For example, Pakistan is now growing more than one million acres of IR8 and India may have a total of five million acres. Burma has an estimated 400,000 acres and the Philippines has more than one million acres. Undoubtedly, in the world there were at least 10 million acres of IR8 being grown in 1968, and if you estimate conservatively an additional profit of U.S. \$60 per acre, the calculated increased income for rice farmers in 1968 is \$600,000,000. During 1968 the expenditures of the Institute was somewhat over 1½ million dollars which shows that there is a rather high pay-off on the investment made by the foundations and other organizations supporting the research program.

Staff Changes

Mrs. Merry Lee San Luis was appointed as Editor of the Institute on July 1, 1968, replacing Mr. Edward A. Jackson who resigned in 1967.

Trustees

Dr. Noboru Yamada, the regional rice information specialist of the Food and Agriculture Organization in Bangkok, was elected a trustee of the Institute for the 4-year period beginning January 1, 1968.

Dr. Yoshiaki Ishizuka's 4-year term expired on December 31, 1967.

Finances

As has been true previously, the major portion of the operating costs of the Institute was shared equally by the Ford and Rockefeller foundations. The sum received during 1968 from the two foundations for the Institute's central program amounted to \$1,544,550, which included \$300,000 provided by The Rockefeller Foundation in terms of manpower services and their travelling expenses.

Other funds received by the Institute in 1968 are listed below:

1. From the Ford Foundation for support of rice research and for the training of scientists and extension workers, as follows:

West Pakistan	\$ 80,000
Ceylon	147,660
Philippines	40,890

The Foundation also provided \$80,000 to support the training and cooperative research program of the Institute.

2. From The Rockefeller Foundation, to support the training and cooperative program of the Institute, \$93,000, and to support the accelerated research and training program on cropping systems for tropical areas, \$76,800.

3. From the United States Agency for International Development, a total of \$104,216.99. Of this amount \$54,677.34 was for support of a research project entitled "Research on Farm and Equipment Power Requirements for Production of Rice and Associated Food Crops in the Far East and South Asia"; \$32,494.65 was for the acceleration of the rice research program in India; and \$17,045 was a contribution toward the training program of the Institute. Furthermore, the Agency for International Development has given the Institute a \$400,000 grant toward the cost of expanding the Institute's training and consultation services; the grant was made available for the period July 1, 1968 to June 30, 1969.

4. From the National Institutes of Health, \$65,127.25 for the screening of rice varieties with respect to their amino acid content, particularly as regards lysine and threonine, and to study the genetic characteristics of the lysine-rich varieties.

5. From the National Science Foundation, \$5,750 to support a research project entitled "The Description and Preservation of the World's Rice Germplasm."

6. From the National Science Development Board, P44,493 (\$11,408.46), to support the studies on the "Insecticide Residue Problems of Rice Production with Emphasis on Gamma-BHC."

7. From the Imperial Chemical Industries, Ltd., \$10,000 to support research on minimal tillage techniques, and on the use of non-selective herbicides for tropical rice production.

8. From the Stauffer Chemical Company, \$5,000 as its contribution toward the general research program of the Institute.

9. From Union Carbide Asia, Ltd., \$5,000 to assist the rapid dissemination of the Institute's research findings, particularly in the field of entomology.

10. From the J. R. Geigy S. A., \$5,000 to partially support the insecticide program of the Institute.

11. From the Esso Research and Engineering Co., \$4,305.92, a contribution toward the fertilizer research work of the Institute.

12. From the International Potash Institute, \$2,400 as its contribution toward the soil fertility studies of the Institute.

13. From the Eli Lilly and Co. (ELANCO), \$2,000 to partially support the Institute's weed control research program.

14. The Bio-Products Dow Chemical International, \$1,537.30 to help support the weed and grass control research of the Institute.

Crop Weather-1968

Fig. 1. Weekly rainfall curve (3-point moving average) for College, Los Baños, Laguna.

The weather during the 1968 dry season (January through May) was normal compared to recent averages. During the wet season (June through November) there were a few deviations from the normal. Figures 1 and 2 show the curves for rainfall and solar radiation recorded by the Philippine Weather Bureau station at College, Laguna, located about 700 meters from the Institute farm. From January to November 30, 1968, the rainfall amounted to 1,263 mm as compared to 1,769 mm for the 19-year mean (1959-1967).

At the beginning of the wet season, at which time the land is usually being prepared, the rainfall was normal compared to the long-term average. The abnormally low rainfall during the monsoon season greatly reduced the yields of rainfed, upland rice (nonflooded). In fact, the yield data were so variable that they are not recorded in this report.

The total solar energy received during the ripening period (April and May) of the 1968 dry season crop was 1,411 g-cal cm^{-2} lower than that of 1967 and 2,973 g-cal cm^{-2} lower than the long-term average. This had no appreciable significance, however, and the high-yielding varieties produced

good grain yields. The amount of solar energy received during the critical period of the 1968 wet-season crop (September to November) – when most of the varieties were in the grain development stage – was higher than that received during the same months in 1967. The other significant aspect of the 1968 crop weather was the low frequency of typhoons during the wet season. The first typhoon, “Didang”, which occurred on July 23-25 with a maximum wind velocity of 61 km/hr did not cause damage to the rice because most of the crop was newly transplanted. Two other minor typhoons, “Huaning” and “Nitang”, occurred on August 18-20 and September 27-29, respectively, both with a maximum velocity of only 40 km/hr. The low frequency of typhoons and slightly higher solar energy received during the ripening period of the 1968 wet-season crop resulted in high grain yields varying from 6,000 to 7,000 kg/ha in many of the experiments.

Fig. 2. Solar radiation curve (3-point moving average) for College, Los Baños, Laguna.

*The general climatic and soil environment at the Institute was described in the 1965 Annual Report and the crop weather for 1966 and 1967 were described in the annual reports for those years.

Plant Physiology

Studies on the varieties of improved plant type showed that their physiology differs from that of the traditional tropical indica varieties. The improved variety IR8 has a steady high growth rate from the seedling stage to harvest whereas the traditional variety Peta has a high growth rate at the early stages followed by a low growth rate after flowering, resulting in low yields. IR8 can produce more dry matter than Peta with the same leaf area index, and has a larger optimum leaf area index and a higher maximum crop growth rate. It seldom exceeds its optimum leaf area index; consequently, it can respond to high levels of nitrogen without showing a noticeable decline in grain yield. These results explain some of the differences in the response to nitrogen of IR8 and Peta.

Detailed analysis of the yield components of improved varieties indicated that the number of grains per unit area is an adequate measure for evaluating growth performance. The model yield components of transplanted IR8 are given in this report.

Detailed studies were also made on the tillering performance of rice varieties as affected by nitrogen nutrition.

Studies on photosynthesis showed a higher photosynthetic rate for the varieties tested than those reported so far in the literature.

The experiments on photoperiod showed that long photoperiods after panicle initiation can delay panicle exertion, a delay mainly in development and elongation. Temperatures between 21 and 32 C during photoinductive cycles did not affect panicle initiation.

Salinity studies dealt with the different kinds of the salt and their effect on potassium supply. It appears that the antagonism between sodium and potassium in the rice plant occurs only when the potassium supply is relatively high.

Work on zinc deficiency centered on factors affecting zinc uptake and on correcting zinc deficiency. Dipping of rice seedlings in zinc oxide suspension was found to provide an effective and economical way of correcting zinc deficiency.

Growth Rate and Plant Characters of Rice Varieties in Relation to their Response to Nitrogen

Previous studies of the growth rate of both the japonica and the leafy, tropical indica varieties of rice have shown that a high growth rate at the early stages is followed by a low growth rate at the later stages, and vice-versa. Since most of the grain carbohydrates are actually photosynthesized after flowering, varieties with a high dry matter production during the later stages generally give high yields. It has been established that the high growth rate of the tall, leafy, tropical indica varieties in the early stages tends to result in excessive vegetative growth, which in turn causes mutual shading and subsequently a lower growth rate.

On the other hand, rapid seedling growth is considered a desirable trait of tropical rice varieties, particularly when combined with early maturity. It enables the young plants to become fully established before weeds become a problem. Obviously, too, it is associated with heavy tillering capacity. The new dwarf variety, IR8, with its stiff straw and short, erect leaves, offers a good opportunity for studying the relationship between the growth rate at the different physiological stages and the yield of the new tropical varieties now being developed. As the studies reported in this section will show, the modern plant types appear to behave quite differently from the traditional tropical indica varieties.

Seedling growth and grain weight

Pre-germinated seeds of 14 varieties with different grain weights were grown in the greenhouse and in a darkroom for 10 and 20 days.

As shown in Fig. 1, the dry weight of shoots in the 10-day experiment seems to be well correlated with grain weight: the heavier the grain weight, the larger the shoot weight. This suggests that early growth rate in rice varieties depends largely on the reserve nutrients in the seeds. A comparison of seedling growth in the light vs. dark and clay vs. sand treatments indicated that (a) the seedlings grown in the light had a faster growth rate than those grown in the dark and (b) the clay-grown seedlings had a faster growth rate than the quartz-grown seedlings only in the light. This

Fig. 1. Relationship between shoot weight and grain weight under various conditions.

indicates that nutrient supply may have an effect on growth only in conjunction with photosynthesis.

In the 20-day experiment, the relationship between shoot weight and grain weight was less exact, but there was a close relationship between shoot weight and leaf blade weight (Fig. 2). This suggests that leafiness becomes the dominant factor at the later stages of seedling growth.

Plant height was well correlated with shoot weight (Fig. 3). However, seedling height was not necessarily correlated with plant height at harvest, there being a large variation in plant height at harvest among seedlings of similar sizes (Fig. 4). This indicates that rapid seedling growth is not necessarily associated with the tall, leafy varieties at later stages.

Early vegetative growth and LAI

IR8 and Peta were grown on the Institute farm at 30 x 30 cm and 100 x 100 cm spacing and in combination with three levels of added nitrogen. The plants of the Peta population were supported with bamboo stakes whenever there was danger of lodging.

As shown in Fig. 5, Peta is leafier than IR8. At the early growth stages when the leaf area index (LAI) is small, the growth rate of the crop was almost a linear function of the LAI, and was

20-Day Experiment

Fig. 2. Relationship of shoot weight to grain weight and to leaf blade weight.

Fig. 3. Relationship between shoot weight and height of 20-day-old seedlings.

Fig. 4. Relationship between plant height of 20-day-old seedlings and at harvest.

Table 1. Photosynthetic rate of isolated leaves of IR8 and Peta at low and high light intensities.

Variety	Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Photosynthetic rate mgCO ₂ /100cm ² /hr		N content of leaf blade (%)
		10 K Lux	60 K Lux	
IR8	0	18.2	44.1	4.16
	100	21.1	49.8	6.24
	(mean)	19.7	47.0	5.20
Peta	0	23.1	49.5	4.63
	100	23.4	43.8	5.28
	(mean)	23.3	46.7	4.96

independent of variety (Fig. 6). At the 100 x 100 cm spacing, a close relationship between LAI and growth rate existed at all growth stages, largely because of the reduced mutual shading at the wide spacing.

Photosynthetic rate of isolated leaves

The photosynthetic activity of a population (P_1) per unit land area is a product of the leaf area index (A), the light-receiving coefficient (f), and the photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area under

Fig. 6. Leaf area index and crop growth rate.

light-saturated condition (P_0). Thus,

$$P_1 = A \times f \times P_0$$

The leaf area index (A) can be changed by such cultural practices as increasing the plant density and fertilization; the light-receiving coefficient (f) is affected by LAI and such varietal characters as leaf erectness; and the photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area is controlled by varietal characters and nutrition at a given stage.

To find out what factor (s) is dominant in determining P_1 , it is necessary to separate P_0 from A and f.

The photosynthetic rate of IR8 and Peta per unit leaf area are about the same (Table 1). This implies that when the P_1 's of the two varieties are to be compared, P_0 is no longer a determining factor, and thus P_1 is determined by A and by morphological characters. This conclusion offers a basis for evaluating plant type in the determination of P_1 or dry matter production.

The photosynthetic rate of leaves is affected by nitrogen nutrition. The higher the nitrogen content, the higher the photosynthetic rate (see Fig. 14).

Plant type, optimum LAI, and maximum CGR

Up to 8 weeks after transplanting, the dry weight of Peta was heavier than that of IR8 at the 30 x 30 cm spacing; at later growth stages, this situation

Fig. 5. Dry weight and LAI of IR8 and Peta at successive stages of growth (100 kg/ha N).

Table 2. Crop growth rate (CGR), mean leaf area index (LAI), and nitrogen content of the leaf blade of IR8 and Peta at different nitrogen levels and spacings, IRRI, 1966 wet season.

Variety	Spacing (cm)	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	4th-6th week*				8th-10th week*			
			CGR**	Mean† LAI	NAR††	N%‡	CGR	Mean LAI	NAR	N%
IR8	30 x 30	0	49	1.15	43	3.70	118	2.93	40	2.39
		50	71	1.60	44	3.85	136	3.14	43	2.50
		100	92	1.91	48	4.40	191	5.76	33	2.68
Peta	30 x 30	0	74	1.37	54	3.34	105	3.38	31	2.22
		50	104	2.26	46	3.60	127	4.72	27	2.28
		100	127	2.56	50	3.87	137	5.76	24	2.36
IR8	100 x 100	0	13	0.18	72	4.00	36	0.69	52	3.38
		50	14	0.20	70	4.29	43	0.79	54	3.56
		100	15	0.23	65	4.66	47	1.00	47	3.78
Peta	100 x 100	0	14	0.20	70	3.64	50	0.98	51	2.96
		50	20	0.26	77	3.68	47	1.25	38	2.78
		100	16	0.35	46	4.00	60	1.41	43	3.14

* After transplanting.

** g/sq m/week.

† Mean of LAI's at the start and end of the 2-week period.

†† Net assimilation rate.

‡ Nitrogen content of leaf blades.

was reversed (Fig. 5). However, the LAI of Peta was always larger than that of IR8 and reached about 8 at flowering. This indicates that mutual shading in the Peta population became serious and this reduced the efficiency of dry matter production per unit leaf area.

To study the quantitative relationship between plant type and optimum LAI, data were collected from the population 8 and 10 weeks after transplanting.

Crop growth rate (CGR) is defined as the increase in dry matter in grams per square meter per week, and net assimilation rate (NAR) as:

$$\text{NAR} = \frac{\text{CGR (Y)}}{\text{Mean LAI (F)}} = \frac{Y}{F} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the NAR is considered as a measure of leaf efficiency for dry matter production. From Table 2 and Fig. 7, it is obvious that the NAR decreased with the increase in mean LAI. In other words, the NAR is dependent on the mean LAI which determines the average light intensity in the leaf layers of a population. It is also logical to assume that the higher NAR values for the 100 x 100 cm spacing than for the 30 x 30 cm spacing are partly due to higher nitrogen content because the photosynthetic rate of a leaf is a function of

Table 3. Some plant characters of IR8 and Peta at flowering (100 kg/ha N), 1966 wet season.

Variety	Height (cm)	Mean leaf openness	Leaf blade ratio *	K **
IR8	121	22.1	0.56	0.40
Peta	196	34.2	0.46	0.51

* Leaf blade to leaf-sheath-plus-culm ratio (in weight).

** Light extinction coefficient measured at 10 weeks after transplanting.

Fig. 7. Relationship between net assimilation rate (NAR) and mean leaf area index (LAI).

Fig. 8. Optimum leaf area indices of IR8 and Peta.

	Opt. LAI	Max. CGR
IR8	7.91	206 g/sq/m/week
Peta	5.94	135

These results show that IR8 can produce more dry matter with the same LAI, and has a larger optimum LAI and a larger maximum CGR. These results explain also why IR8 and Peta differ in their response to nitrogen.

With increasing levels of nitrogen, Peta tends to exceed its optimum LAI, resulting in a decrease in the amount of dry matter it produces. On the other hand, IR8 seldom exceeds or, when it does, only to a small extent, its optimum LAI. Con-

its nitrogen content, other factors not being limiting. Thus, the NAR measured in this experiment is considered a function of the mean LAI and the nitrogen content of the leaves.

Nevertheless, as shown in Fig. 7, there is linear relationship between NAR and mean LAI (F):

$$NAR = a - b F \quad (2)$$

By rewriting equation (1):

$$Y = NAR \times F \quad (3)$$

From equations (2) and (3), the following parabolic equation between CGR and mean LAI was obtained:

$$Y = a F - b F^2 \quad (4)$$

By this mathematical manipulation, it seems justified to fit data on CGR and LAI into a parabolic equation with the help of the least square method.

As shown in Fig. 8, the relationship between mean LAI and CGR can be expressed by a parabolic equation.

$$IR8 : Y = 52.1 F - 3.29 F^2 \quad (5)$$

$$Peta : Y = 45.3 F - 3.81 F^2 \quad (6)$$

The optimum LAI was obtained by the equation:

$$\frac{d Y}{d F} = 0$$

Substituting the optimum LAI into equation (5) and (6) gave the maximum CGR for each variety. The following data summarize the above calculations.

sequently, it can respond to higher levels of nitrogen without showing a noticeable decline in grain yield. This appears to be the physiological basis of the nitrogen responsiveness of IR8.

Since there is no significant difference in the photosynthetic rate of isolated leaves between the two varieties, it can be concluded that the increased optimum LAI of IR8 is the overall result of the improvement in plant type. Therefore, some plant characters of the two varieties that are related to dry matter production were investigated.

As shown in Table 3, IR8 is much shorter than Peta, and has a larger leaf blade ratio. It also has more erect leaves as expressed by mean leaf openness, resulting in lower light extinction coefficient value. These characters are believed to increase the photosynthetic activity of the population and to maintain a better balance between photosynthesis and respiration.

Maximum recorded LAI and grain yield in the wet season

Figure 9 shows the relationship between the maximum recorded LAI (usually recorded at flowering) and grain yield in the wet-season crop. It is during the wet season when the average solar radiation is low (averaging about 300 g-cal cm²/day during the ripening period) and mutual shading is a serious problem.

To obtain information on the relationship between maximum recorded LAI and grain yield, data were analyzed from various field experiments conducted at the Institute in the 1966 and 1968 wet seasons.

In the case of IR8, grain yield increased with increasing LAI until the LAI reached about 5. Beyond this value, grain yield became almost constant. It appears that the higher LAI did not result in decreased grain yield, i.e., excessive LAI did not have a detrimental effect on the grain yield of IR8.

On the other hand, there was an optimum LAI at which Peta achieved its maximum grain yield. Beyond the LAI of 5.5, the grain yield decreased sharply. In other words, the grain yield of Peta increased with increasing LAI up to 5.5, then detrimental mutual shading set in, and grain yield decreased with increasing LAI.

Conclusion

This experiment appears to indicate that the dominant factor which determines the growth rate of rice varieties varies with the growth stage. At the seedling stage, the grain weight largely influences the growth rate; subsequently, leafiness or leaf area index becomes the dominant factor. When the LAI increases and mutual shading becomes more serious, the growth rate is determined by plant type. IR8, typical of the improved varieties, has a bigger optimum LAI and a higher efficiency of dry matter production than Peta, a tall leafy tropical variety.

IR8 has relatively heavy grain weight, 25.2 g/1,000 grains dried at 105 C, which brings about vigorous seedling growth. This early growth rate continues at later stages. In other words, IR8 has a steadily high growth rate from the seedling stage to harvest, whereas Peta has a high growth rate at the early stages followed by a low growth rate after flowering.

It appears that the high growth rate of IR8 throughout its life is the result of a combination of increased optimum LAI and moderately early maturity. It is logical to consider the whole story of seedling vigor, mutual shading, and high growth rate at later growth stages in terms of plant type and maturity. When a variety is leafy with droopy leaves, and as a result its optimum LAI has a low value, mutual shading sets in at relatively early stages and the growth rate becomes slower at later stages. On the other hand, when a variety has erect leaves (and the resulting value of the optimum LAI is high) and is relatively early maturing, there is

Fig. 9. Relationship between maximum leaf area index and grain yield of IR8 and Peta, 1966 and 1968 wet seasons.

little chance for mutual shading to become detrimental and the growth rate continues to be high from the seedling stage to maturity.

The optimum LAI of the rice plant varies with growth stage and the amount of solar energy received by the rice population. The reported optimum LAI's at around the booting stage range from about 6 in Japan, and from 5 to 6 in the Philippines. As shown in Fig. 9 and in equations (5) and (6), the optimum LAI's are about 6 for Peta and 8 for IR8. The improvement of plant type resulted in increased optimum LAI. Besides bringing about increased resistance to lodging, this also is an important factor constituting the physiological basis for the nitrogen responsiveness of the improved variety. (It is important to bear in mind that the tall Peta plants were tied up to prevent lodging, otherwise different results might have been obtained.)

IR8 has a distinctly higher optimum LAI than Japanese varieties under comparable solar radiation. It can be predicted from empirical and theoretical considerations that IR8 may have an even bigger optimum LAI in the dry season when climatic conditions are more favorable than in the wet season.

It is also striking that a large LAI did not have any noticeable adverse effects on the grain yield of the wet-season crop. This may have been due partly to the increased optimum LAI. Thus, it may be said that with an improved variety, mutual shading is no longer a serious problem in rice growth as it is with leafy indica varieties. As a result, IR8 can yield up to 10,000 kg/ha with increasing nitrogen applications under good management and favorable climatic conditions.

Varietal difference in photosynthetic rate of rice varieties

The concept of plant type has provided a useful guide in the program of breeding for high-yielding varieties. Not much information is available, however, about the photosynthetic rate of rice varieties per unit leaf area. It is possible that the improvement in plant type is associated with increased photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area.

In addition, a variety with a high photosynthetic rate could be used in the breeding program.

Since it appears that improvement in plant type has achieved the goal of developing high-yielding varieties, and that few further improvements can be expected along this line, this other approach – increasing the photosynthetic rate per unit leaf area – might offer a possible breakthrough in breeding for higher yielding varieties.

Thus, the purpose of this study was twofold: to verify whether the new high-yielding varieties are associated principally with plant type, and to find varieties with high photosynthetic rates.

In our study, the values found for photosynthetic rate were much higher than those reported so far in the literature. The reported values are 10 to 30 mg CO₂/100 cm²/hr. On the other hand, the values found in the present study ranged from 35 to 60 mg CO₂/100 cm²/hr. These findings led to a reexamination of some of the basic relationships in the photosynthesis of the rice plant.

Some relationships in the photosynthesis of isolated leaves

Light-photosynthesis curve. As shown in Fig. 10, photosynthetic rate increased with increasing light intensity up to about 50 K Lux. In this example, the maximum photosynthetic rate was 51 mg CO₂/100 cm²/hr. The shape of the curve remained similar to that reported so far in the literature.

Fig. 10. Relationship between light intensity and photosynthetic rate.

Fig. 11. Diurnal change in apparent photosynthetic rate of isolated leaves.

Air flow rate, mean CO₂ concentration in a leaf chamber, and apparent photosynthetic rate. Apparent photosynthetic rate increased with increasing air flow rate or increasing carbon dioxide concentration in a leaf chamber (data are omitted). Because of this relationship, the measured photosynthetic rate was standardized against 300 ppm of the mean carbon dioxide concentration in the leaf chamber.

Time of sampling. When sampling took place several hours after sunrise, the plants often showed signs of wilting. They visibly recovered when placed in a darkroom or under shade for some hours but their photosynthetic rates remained low, contrary to what was expected.

Figure 11 shows the diurnal change in apparent photosynthetic rate. The plants sampled early in the morning or late in the evening showed consistently high values and those sampled in mid-day showed low values. This variation in photosynthetic rate is probably related to the water supply of the plant. This indicates that sampling should be done early in the morning to obtain the maximum activity of photosynthesis of isolated leaves. In addition, early morning sampling gives more consistent results than mid-day sampling. In this experiment, the plants were sampled at around 6 a.m.

Fig. 12. Relationship between nitrogen content and photosynthetic rate.

Fig. 13. Relationship between chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate.

Method of mounting leaf samples in a leaf chamber. A leaf blade was separated from the sheath and placed in a small tube. This operation was accomplished in water to allow for a continuous flow of water in the tissues. The small

Fig. 14. Distribution of photosynthetic rate of rice varieties at 60 K LUX.

tube containing the leaf blade was placed in a leaf chamber.

Nitrogen content, chlorophyll content, and photosynthetic rate. As shown in Figs. 12 and 13, the higher the nitrogen or chlorophyll content, the higher the photosynthetic rate. A high nitrogen content was accompanied by a high chlorophyll content.

Varietal differences

Photosynthetic rate of 50 varieties. Fifty rice varieties from the world collection of the Institute were grown with 0 and 100 kg/ha N on the Institute experimental field in the 1967 dry season. The photosynthetic rate was measured about 30 days after transplanting.

The photosynthetic rate of the varieties ranged from 34.5 to 62.1 with an average of 46.6 mg CO₂/100 cm²/hr at 60 K Lux (Fig. 14 and Table

Fig. 15. Relationship between nitrogen content and photosynthetic rate of 50 rice varieties.

Fig. 16. Relationship between chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate of 50 rice varieties.

Fig. 17. Relationship between leaf thickness and photosynthetic rate of 50 varieties.

4). Most values fell in the range of from 40 to 55 mg CO₂/100 cm²/hr. It is obvious from these findings that varietal differences exist in the photosynthetic rate of rice varieties.

Nitrogen content, chlorophyll content, leaf thickness, and photosynthetic rate. As already shown in Figs. 12 and 13 there are close relationships between photosynthetic rate and nitrogen or chlorophyll content within the same variety. Leaf thickness is considered as one of the factors that affect the absorption of light by a leaf.

Figures 15, 16 and 17 show the relationships between photosynthetic rate and nitrogen and chlorophyll contents and leaf thickness. There are loose correlations between photosynthetic rate and nitrogen content, chlorophyll content, or leaf thickness. A low photosynthetic rate is associated with low nitrogen content, low chlorophyll content, and low leaf thickness values. A high photosynthetic rate is associated with high nitrogen content, high chlorophyll content, and high leaf thickness values. However, there is a large variation

Table 4. Photosynthetic rate, nitrogen content, chlorophyll content and leaf thickness of some rice varieties.*

Expt. no.	Variety	Country or location	Photosynthetic rate (CO ₂ mg/100cm ² /hr)		Nitrogen content (mg/cm ²)	Chlorophyll content** (mg/cm ²)	Leaf thickness (mg/cm ²)
			10 K Lux	60 K Lux			
1	Caloro II	Australia	14.0	38.2	177	0.59	3.90
2	H4	Ceylon	16.4	44.9	219	0.53	4.65
3	Pokkali	Ceylon	18.6	43.6	225	0.55	4.35
4	Pachchai Perbunal	Ceylon	17.9	51.8	223	0.73	4.95
5	PI 163540	Colombia	20.9	44.1	201	0.71	4.30
6	CI 8308	Colombia	20.4	50.4	230	0.77	4.50
7	Gambiaka Sebela	Egypt	22.7	49.3	209	0.52	4.40
8	Araby	Egypt	20.9	43.4	164	0.45	3.55
9	Nahda	Egypt	18.6	44.0	210	0.60	4.40
10	T 141	India	19.2	62.1	195	0.61	3.65
11	GEB 24	India	21.8	47.6	172	0.57	3.80
12	Basmati	India	22.2	52.7	225	0.62	4.65
13	Jhona 349	India	20.6	47.9	189	0.74	3.70
14	ADT 27	India	18.3	47.0	216	0.59	4.40
15	BJ 1	India	24.3	55.6	180	0.60	4.10
16	Sigadis	Indonesia	29.6	47.5	201	0.57	4.05
17	Peta	Indonesia	23.3	46.7	184	0.58	3.70
18	Bengawan	Indonesia	18.6	45.0	192	0.51	4.05
19	IR8	IRRI	19.7	47.0	203	0.62	3.90
20	IR5	IRRI	20.9	44.5	177	0.60	3.65
21	3558	Italy	18.3	42.3	179	0.56	3.50
22	P Rossi	Italy	17.7	44.6	234	0.66	4.45
23	Stripe 136	Italy	20.4	43.7	226	0.53	4.80
24	Yabami 15	Italy	18.3	46.0	193	0.73	3.85
25	Fujisaka 5	Japan	20.5	42.6	190	0.61	4.05
26	Daikoku	Japan	19.7	39.9	201	0.66	4.10
27	Hoyoku	Japan	13.7	34.5	172	0.57	3.45
28	Tankai Rotan	Malaysia	22.6	49.2	219	0.60	3.75

continued on the next page

Table 4. continued

Expt. no.	Variety	Country or location	Photosynthetic rate (CO ₂ mg/100cm ² /hr)		Nitrogen content (mg/cm ²)	Chloro-phyll content** (mg/cm ²)	Leaf thickness (mg/cm ²)
			10 K Lux	60 K Lux			
29	Donabaru	Nigeria	24.4	52.7	191	0.61	3.90
30	Suwedee	Nigeria	22.7	51.1	203	0.60	4.15
31	Dikwee	Nigeria	20.9	49.0	205	0.57	4.10
32	BPI 76(1)	Philippines	21.2	47.1	220	0.51	4.25
33	Milfor (62)	Philippines	18.6	44.5	224	0.38	4.30
34	Wagwag	Philippines	17.5	42.1	194	0.50	3.85
35	81 B25	Surinam	18.5	44.9	181	0.64	3.45
36	SML-Apura	Surinam	18.8	45.4	181	0.47	3.70
37	SML-Kapuri	Surinam	20.2	40.3	185	0.56	3.55
38	SML-Temerin	Surinam	19.8	47.3	212	0.51	4.20
39	Dee-geo-woo-gen	Taiwan	22.6	53.0	202	0.67	3.95
40	Taichung (Native) 1	Taiwan	21.8	45.2	214	0.62	4.10
41	Tainan 3	Taiwan	11.9	35.3	220	0.55	4.15
42	Chianung 242	Taiwan	16.8	43.8	200	0.61	4.35
43	Leb Mue Nhang 111	Thailand	21.6	57.8	208	0.50	4.00
44	Leuang Yai 36	Thailand	17.7	47.2	227	0.60	4.50
45	Nang Mai	Thailand	18.2	46.2	181	0.45	3.80
46	Siam 29	Thailand	19.6	45.6	195	0.53	3.75
47	CP 231	U.S.A.	20.8	55.0	250	0.50	4.80
48	Belle Patna	U.S.A.	16.5	40.2	196	0.53	4.05
49	Nato	U.S.A.	19.7	54.3	242	0.49	4.70
50	Blue Bonnet	U.S.A.	16.7	46.2	223	0.56	4.60
	Min.		11.9	34.5			
	Max.		29.6	62.1			
	Mean		19.7	46.6			

* Mean values of 0 and 100 kg/ha N.

** Relative values.

in photosynthetic rate within the same range of these factors. A comparison of these relationships within a variety and between varieties suggests that there are other factors which control the photosynthetic rate of the rice plant. The photosynthetic process can be considered as consisting of two parts, namely, the diffusion of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere to the chloroplast, and the efficiency of the chloroplast in the assimilation of carbon dioxide. The first process may be mainly concerned with the anatomical structure of the plant and the second one may be largely dependent on the micro-structure of the chloroplast and

its biochemical activity. To understand the factors responsible for varietal differences in photosynthetic rate, a study is underway on the photosynthetic rate of chloroplasts isolated from different rice varieties.

Analysis of Yield Components of Improved Varieties

In the 1967 wet season and 1968 dry season, various field experiments were conducted to find out how spacing and nitrogen application affect

the grain yield and yield components of improved low- and high-tillering varieties. Below is an analysis of the grain yields from these experiments in terms of yield components.

The data were collected from the experiments listed in Table 5. Five varieties were used in all the experiments, with two of them, IR8 (V5) and IR154-45-1-3-3 (V2), being used as examples in the analysis of yield components. The varietal characteristics of these varieties were described in the 1967 Annual Report.

Panicle number per square meter vs grain yield

Grain yield was closely related to panicle number per square meter up to about 350 to 400 per sq m; beyond this, grain yield was not necessarily related to panicle number (Fig. 18). The dry-season crop produced more panicles than the wet-season crop and the increased number of panicles was associated with increased grain yield. The direct-seeded crop produced a much larger number of panicles than the transplanted crop but this increase did not bring about the increased grain yields. This was because the increase in the number of panicles was accompanied by a decrease in the number of grains per panicle (Fig. 19).

Panicle number per square meter vs number of grains per panicle

The number of grains per panicle is inversely related to the number of panicles per square

Fig. 18. Relationship between panicle number per square meter and grain yield.

Fig. 19. Relationship between panicle number per square meter and number of grains per panicle.

Table 5. Sources of data used in analyzing yield components.

Expt. no.	Year	Season	Planting method	Nitrogen application (kg/ha)	Spacing (cm) or seeding rate (kg/ha)
1	1967	Wet	Transplanting	0, 100	10 ² , 20 ² , 30 ² , 40 ² , 50 ²
2	1968	Dry	Transplanting	0, 100	10 ² , 20 ² , 30 ² , 40 ² , 50 ²
3	1967	Wet	Transplanting	0, 30, 60, 90, 120	20 ²
4	1968	Dry	Transplanting	0, 30, 60, 90, 120	20 ²
5	1968	Dry	Transplanting	0, 100, 150, 200, 250	10 ² , 20 ²
6	1968	Dry	Direct-seeding	130	50, 100, 200

Fig. 20. Relationship between total number of grains per square meter and grain yield.

meter, i.e., the more panicles per square meter, the fewer grains per panicle. For example, the wet-season crop tended to produce a larger number of grains per panicle than did the dry-season crop which had a larger number of panicles per unit area of land. The direct-seeded crop produced a much smaller number of grains per panicle than did the transplanted crop, which produced fewer panicles per square meter.

Total number of grains per square meter vs grain yield

Since the number of panicles per square meter and the number of grains per panicle tend to compensate for each other, neither of them can be an adequate measure of grain yield under diverse cultural conditions. For instance, close spacing can bring about more panicles per square meter but this increase would be accompanied by a decrease in the number of grains per panicle. However, the product of the panicle number per square meter and the grain number per panicle, i.e., the total number of grains per square meter, is closely related to grain yield. As shown in Fig. 20 there is a linear relationship between total number of grains per square meter and grain yield. This linear relationship is independent of season and method of planting. The dry-season crop produced more grains per square meter than the wet-season crop,

and this increase resulted in increased grain yield.

This linear relationship indicates that (1) the total number of grains per square meter determined grain yield and (2) two other yield components, filled grain percentage and grain weight, did not affect grain yield.

Filled grain percentage and 1,000-grain weight

As shown in Fig. 21, the percentage of filled grains and the 1,000-grain weight remained fairly constant regardless of the total number of grains per square meter. Therefore, roughly speaking, in the dry and wet seasons, the relationship between grain yield and the yield components can be reduced from:

$$\text{Grain yield} = \text{panicle number/m}^2 \times \text{grain number/panicle} \times \text{filled grain \%} \times \text{grain weight}$$

to:

$$\text{Grain yield} = \text{total number of grains/m}^2 \times K,$$

where K corresponds to the gradient in Fig. 20.

When grain yield is relatively low, panicle number per square meter can be a good measure of growth performance, but when the yield increases, the total number of grains per square meter is more reliable for comparing growth performance under different cultural practices. When transplanting and direct seeding are compared, total number of grains per square meter is the adequate

Fig. 21. Relationship between total number of grains per square meter and filled grain percentage and grain weight.

Fig. 22. Relationship between total number of grains per square meter and grain yields of two varieties.

measure for evaluating growth performance, as panicle number per square meter will give less information.

Model yield components of transplanted IR8

Table 6 gives a rough idea of the yield components of transplanted IR8 in the wet- and dry-season crops.

Comparing different varieties

Since grain yield is approximately the product of total number of grains per square meter and grain weight, and grain weight is mainly a varietal character and is not changed much by cultural practices under natural conditions, it (grain weight) becomes an important factor in comparing different varieties. This relationship is shown in Fig. 22. The variety V2 has a smaller grain weight than V5. Consequently, V2 needs more grains to obtain the same grain yield as V5. There is a tendency for a variety of smaller grain weight to produce a larger number of grains per square meter.

Effects of Nitrogen Nutrition on Tillering Performance

In 1967, the concept of relative tillering rate (RTR) was introduced to study the effects of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium supply on the tillering performance of the rice plant. Of these nutrients, nitrogen is the most dominant in

Table 6. The model yield components of transplanted IR8.

Grain yield component	Wet	Dry
Grain yield (kg/ha)	6,163	9,244
Panicle number/sq m	250	375
Grain number/panicle	100	100
Total grain number/sq m	25,000	37,500
Filled grain (%)	85	85
1,000 grain weight (g)	29	29

controlling the tillering performance of the rice plant in farmer's fields.

There are contradicting opinions as to whether the concentration of nitrogen in the plant or the rate of nitrogen uptake per day is related to the tillering performance of the rice plant. Furthermore, rice varieties have large varietal differences in tillering ability, the nature of which has not been understood well. To better understand these matters an experiment was conducted to study (1) the relationship between nitrogen nutrition and tillering performance, and (2) varietal differences in tillering performance. The rice plant was grown at different nitrogen levels using the standard water culture technique, and the necessary data were collected every week from 2 weeks after transplanting.

Change in tiller number as affected by N levels in culture solution

As shown in Table 7 the initiation of tillering was accelerated by increased concentration of nitrogen; also, the higher the nitrogen supply, the larger the tiller number at any time. This clearly shows that nitrogen supply controls the tillering rate of the rice plant unless other factors such as spacing and light become limiting.

Total N uptake vs N concentration

At the early growth stages of the rice plant, tillering is not related to the nitrogen concentration in the plant (Table 8 and Fig. 23). The data indicate that the rice plant started tillering when the total nitrogen uptake became more than 10 mg per plant or the dry weight became more than 300 mg per plant. In other words, the size of the main tiller determined the initiation of tillering.

When the main tiller is too small, the surplus carbohydrate it produces is consumed mainly for

Table 7. Effects of nitrogen concentration in culture on tiller number of IR8.

N level (ppm)	Weeks after transplanting									
	0	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	No. of tillers									
1	1	1	1	2.2	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.7	3.7
5	1	1.2	1.7	4.1	6.4	8.8	11.5	13.3	13.9	12.8
25	1	1.2	2.5	3.7	6.7	12.1	17.9	22.6	30.2	31.8
50	1	2.5	4.2	10.9	16.9	24.6	35.3	42.7	47.0	48.6
100	1	2.4	4.8	11.6	19.2	27.9	37.2	44.7	51.6	56.6

Table 8. Total nitrogen uptake (mg/plant), nitrogen content of leaf blade, dry weight vs tiller number.

N level (ppm)	Item	Weeks after transplanting				
		0	2	3	4	5
1	N% in L.B.*	3.20	4.81	3.67	3.18	3.63
	N mg/plant	0.43	4.44	5.85	21.0	29.0
	Dry weight (g)	0.02	0.13	0.19	0.85	1.03
	Tiller no.	1	1	1	2.2	3.3
5	N% in L.B.	3.20	4.81	4.36	4.25	3.48
	N mg/plant	0.43	5.39	12.0	—	107
	Dry weight	0.02	0.15	0.33	0.90	3.63
	Tiller no.	1	1.2	1.7	4.1	6.4
25	N% in L.B.	3.20	4.91	4.42	4.80	4.50
	N mg/plant	0.43	6.16	12.7	36.6	113
	Dry weight	0.02	0.16	0.37	0.90	3.94
	Tiller no.	1	1.2	2.5	3.7	6.7
50	N% in L.B.	3.20	5.13	4.09	4.46	4.45
	N mg/plant	0.43	11.1	18.9	132	396
	Dry weight	0.02	0.31	0.70	3.51	10.8
	Tiller no.	1	2.5	4.2	10.9	16.9
100	N% in L.B.	3.20	4.97	4.57	4.76	4.32
	N mg/plant	0.43	10.5	23.7	158	353
	Dry weight	0.02	0.27	0.62	3.87	10.8
	Tiller no.	1	2.4	4.8	11.6	19.2

* Leaf blade

Fig. 23. Relationship between tiller number, nitrogen content of leaf blade and total nitrogen uptake.

its own growth and is not sufficient for the production of new tillers. However, when the main tiller becomes about 300 mg, the surplus carbohydrate can support not only its own growth but also the production of tillers.

Tiller number vs RTR

Relative tillering rate is defined as:

$$RTR = \frac{dN}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{N}$$

where N refers to number of tillers and t, to time.

Therefore, RTR is the mean tillering rate per tiller.

When RTR was plotted against the nitrogen content of the leaf blade, the RTR tended to be smaller at the same nitrogen content when the tiller number was large. This suggests that when the tiller number increases, mutual shading within the hill retards tiller production.

To test the above possibility, RTR was plotted against tiller number. Figure 24 indicates that RTR is dependent on the total tiller number present; the larger the tiller number, the smaller the RTR. This relationship indicates that mutual shading within the hill is an important factor affecting tillering rate. It has been established that light is required for tiller development.

Thus, RTR is determined not only by nitrogen content but also by the total number of tillers present.

Nitrogen content of leaf blade and straw vs RTR

The preceding studies have made clear that (1) RTR is independent of the nitrogen content of the plant until the total nitrogen uptake increases to more than 10 mg per plant, and (2) RTR tends to become smaller when the total tiller number is large. These factors were considered when the relationship between RTR and the nitrogen content of the plant was sought. As shown in Figs. 25 and 26, linear relationships exist between RTR and nitrogen content of the leaf blade or leaves. The figures indicate that the nitrogen concentration in the plant controls tillering rate after the

Fig. 24. Effects of total tiller number on RTR.

Fig. 25. Relationship between RTR and nitrogen content of leaf blade.

Fig. 26. Relationship between RTR and nitrogen content of leaves.

plant has reached a certain growth stage. Figure 25 shows that RTR becomes zero when the nitrogen content of the leaf blade is about 2 percent.

Another experiment was conducted to test further if the nitrogen content of the leaf blade is related to tiller production. The plants were grown in 1 ppm and 50 ppm N culture solutions for certain periods and then transferred to 50 ppm

and 0 ppm N culture solutions, respectively.

In both treatments the tiller number increased when the nitrogen content of the leaf blade was over 2 percent (Fig. 27). Tillering stopped when the nitrogen content of the leaf blade decreased to below 2 percent. The experiment demonstrated that the nitrogen content of the plant is an internal factor which is related to tiller production.

Varietal differences

It is well known that there are varietal differences in the tillering ability of the rice plant, as shown in the example in Fig. 28.

To study such differences, a high-tillering variety, IR8, and a low-tillering selection,

Fig. 27. Effects of supply and stoppage of nitrogen on tillering.

IR154-45-1-3-3, were grown in culture solutions with different nitrogen supply.

As shown in Fig. 29, within the same variety, RTR is a linear function of the nitrogen content of the leaf blade. When low- and high-tillering varieties are compared, however, nitrogen content is not the only important factor causing differences in tillering performance. The fact that, at the same nitrogen content, the high tillering variety had a high RTR, suggests that other factors such as hormones control the tillering habit of different varieties.

Salinity problems in rice nutrition

In a previous study of the effect of high concentrations of salt on rice growth, sodium chloride was used as the test salt (1967 Annual Report). Under natural conditions, the kinds of salt differ from one place to another in salt-affected areas. It is, therefore, necessary to know the effects of different kinds of soil or mixtures of them on rice growth. On the other hand, under weakly saline conditions, the presence of the sodium ion could be beneficial to rice growth if there is a poor supply of potassium, i.e., the partial replacement of sodium by potassium is involved in this problem.

The 1968 experiment included studies on the effects of a) different kinds of salt on rice growth, and b) potassium supply on rice growth in the presence or absence of a moderate concentration of sodium chloride.

Effects of sodium, calcium, and magnesium chlorides on rice growth

The same soil culture technique used in last year's experiment was used to study the effects of sodium, magnesium, and calcium chlorides on rice growth (Fig. 30). The toxicity of high concentrations of calcium chloride appears to be a little less than that of sodium and magnesium chlorides. The panicle weight of the plants in the sodium and magnesium series was reduced to half that of the control at about $7,100 \text{ u mhos cm}^{-1}$.

Potassium requirement of the rice plant in the absence or presence of sodium chloride

The plants were grown at different potassium levels in the presence or absence of 1,000 ppm NaCl.

Fig. 28. Tillering performance of low- and high-tillering varieties grown in culture solution.

Fig. 29. Relationship between RTR and nitrogen content of leaf blades of two varieties.

Potassium deficiency symptoms started to appear about 1 month after transplanting at low potassium levels (1 and 2 ppm K). Later, the plants with 5 and 10 ppm K also developed slight symptoms of potassium deficiency. In the absence of sodium chloride, orange-yellowish discoloration started with the lower leaves from the tips going downward. The leaves became droopy, with some of them showing a few brown spots and others drying up. In the presence of sodium chloride, the leaves remained erect, were greener, and did not have brown spots (Fig. 31).

Fig. 30. Effects of sodium, calcium, and magnesium chlorides on panicle weight.

Generally, when the potassium content was less than 1 percent, typical, easily identifiable symptoms of potassium deficiency developed.

It is interesting to note that IR8 does not develop tiny brown spots on its leaves similar to those caused by iron toxicity even when potassium deficiency becomes severe. Although some reports say that the appearance of small brown spots is characteristic of potassium deficiency, this has not been the case with IR8. Therefore, with this

variety, one would not confuse iron toxicity and potassium deficiency symptoms.

As shown in Table 9 and Fig. 32, sodium can partially replace potassium at low potassium levels. This seems important in weakly saline areas where frequently the sodium content of the plant is high. The presence of sodium chloride decreased the potassium content of the plant when there was a high supply of potassium. It appears that antagonism between sodium and potassium in the rice plant occurs only when the potassium supply is relatively high. When the supply is limited, sodium can partially replace potassium. With these considerations, the relatively high sodium content of the plant can be beneficial to rice nutrition under weakly saline conditions.

Zinc deficiency of the rice plant

Observations of the visible symptoms on the rice plant and the results of simple greenhouse experiments have shown that zinc deficiency occurs on calcareous soils at Pant Nagar, Uttar Pradesh, India, and at Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, West Pakistan (1967 Annual Report).

In 1968, the work on zinc was continued by (1) conducting greenhouse experiments on the occurrence of zinc deficiency and how to cure it, (2) studying some factors affecting zinc uptake by the rice plant, and (3) conducting a field experiment at the Kala Shah Kaku Rice Experiment Station to confirm the existence of zinc deficiency and assess several methods of zinc application.

Table 9. Effects of a moderate concentration of sodium chloride on the growth and potassium requirements of the rice plant.

Potassium supply (ppm)	Dry weight shoot (g)		Nutrient content of shoot (%)			
			K		Na	
	No NaCl	1,000 ppm NaCl	No NaCl	1,000 ppm NaCl	No NaCl	1,000 ppm NaCl
1	9.0	15.7	0.33	0.30	0.14	1.63
2	16.0	21.8	0.56	0.56	0.15	1.76
5	24.2	30.4	0.76	0.77	0.12	1.39
10	31.7	38.5	1.23	0.92	0.10	1.24
50	33.4	36.3	1.18	1.11	0.12	1.37
100	39.9	36.7	1.51	1.34	0.09	1.03
200	47.7	44.2	2.75	1.80	0.10	0.98

Fig. 31. Effects of sodium chloride on rice growth at low supply of potassium.

Fig. 32. Relationship between potassium contents of leaves and shoot weight in the absence and presence of NaCl.

Effects of cellulose on zinc deficiency

When zinc deficiency was reproduced several times in the greenhouse using soil from the Kala Shah Kaku station, the soil, without added zinc, did not consistently produce severe symptoms of zinc deficiency.

Field experience has shown that the disorder is usually found in low-lying patches, and that drainage alleviates the problem. This suggests that the disorder is associated with highly reducing conditions in submerged soils, and that, the addition of organic matter may aggravate it.

Table 10 and Fig. 33 show that (1) the addition of cellulose to the problem soil aggravated the disorder and markedly retarded plant growth and (2) the addition of zinc counteracted partially the effects of the cellulose. These results indicate that the application of cellulose affected not only the

availability of zinc and/or the uptake of zinc by the rice plant but also other factors retarding plant growth. These results were confirmed by several repeated experiments.

Comparison of methods of zinc application

Different methods of zinc application were compared to select those that are easy and safe to use and inexpensive. Cellulose was added to all the pots to make certain that zinc deficiency was present. The control plants (no zinc added) started showing characteristic zinc deficiency symptoms about 2 weeks after transplanting. Three weeks after transplanting, the plants which received zinc either in the nursery bed, in the pots after transplanting or those dipped in ZnO suspension before transplanting started showing slight zinc deficiency symptoms in their lower leaves. The presence of cellulose caused the zinc deficiency symptom to persist.

The dry weight and zinc content data shown in Table 11 indicate that all the methods tested were highly effective in correcting the deficiency. The advantage of the nursery bed application is that it eliminates the possibility of zinc salt affecting microbiological or chemical changes in the soil through which plant growth might be improved.

A field experiment was conducted at the Kala Shah Kaku Rice Farm in Lahore, West Pakistan, to verify the results of the greenhouse experiments and to evaluate different methods of zinc application.

The experiment consisted of 16 treatments, including nursery bed application, mainfield

Fig. 33. Effects of cellulose on appearance of zinc deficiency of the rice plant (O.M. stands for cellulose).

Table 10. Effects of cellulose on the appearance of zinc deficiency, dry weight, and zinc content on Kala Shah Kaku soil*

Treatment		Dry weight (g/pot)	Zn content (ppm)	Symptoms
Zn (ppm)	Cellulose (%)			
0	0	7.7	14	Moderate
10	0	12.7	27	None
0	0.5	2.2	10	Very severe
10	0.5	5.9	20	Very slight

* The plants were harvested 5 weeks after transplanting.

Table 11. Effects of methods of zinc application on the appearance of zinc deficiency, dry weight, and zinc content on Kala Shah Kaku soil.*

Method of zinc application	Zinc applied (ppm)		Dry weight (g/pot)	Zn content (ppm)	Symptoms
	Nursery	Main pot			
None	0	0	0.8	9	Very severe
Nursery application	100	0	3.1	12	Very slight
Main-pot application	0	10	2.9	22	Very slight
Dipping of seedlings in ZnO suspension	0	0	3.4	13	Very slight

* The plants were harvested 4 weeks after transplanting.

application, dipping of seedlings in 1 percent ZnO suspension, foliar spray, and topdressing at the time of symptom appearance (Table 12).

Zinc deficiency symptoms were observed in the nursery bed when no zinc sulfate was added. The effects of zinc application on rice growth became apparent about 2 weeks after transplanting. Foliar application and topdressing of zinc sulfate caused a remarkable recovery in plant growth within a week following application.

Grain yield data showed a striking difference between the no-zinc plots and those in which zinc was applied.

All the methods of zinc application tested proved effective, resulting in grain yield increases of 1 to 2.5 ton/ha. When the occurrence of zinc

deficiency can be anticipated, the dipping of seedlings in ZnO suspension is the most economical. The amount of ZnO required by this treatment is 100 g/ha, which costs only 12 US cents. The nursery bed application is also highly economical. Assuming that the area required for the nursery bed is about one-twentieth that of the main field, the rate of 100 kg/ha Zn in the nursery bed corresponds to 5 kg/ha Zn for the main field.

Factors affecting zinc uptake by the rice plant

Total and available zinc content of the soil. Neither the total zinc nor the available zinc content of the soil was related to the plant zinc

content (Table 13). Surprisingly, the problem soils appeared to contain an adequate amount of zinc.

Effects of nitrogen, bicarbonate ion concentrations, and pH of culture solutions on Zinc-65 uptake and distribution in the rice plant. Since the disorder has reportedly become more apparent with the introduction of improved varieties which are heavily fertilized, the effects of nitrogen nutrition on zinc uptake by the rice plant were studied using radioactive zinc. The effects of bicarbonate ion and pH were studied also, because high concentrations of bicarbonate ion in submerged soils result from additions of organic matter. Furthermore, the problem soils were alkaline.

The absorption of Zinc-65 by the rice plant, both in concentration and in total uptake, in-

creased with increasing concentrations of nitrogen in the culture solution (Table 14). Obviously the greater supply of nitrogen promoted plant growth. This suggests that when plant growth is improved as a result of fertilization, the zinc requirement of the rice plant is also increased. This requirement may not be met by soils with low available zinc content. The pH only slightly affected the absorption of Zinc-65, as measured by concentration or by total uptake. High concentrations of the bicarbonate ion, however, remarkably altered the distribution of Zinc-65 in the roots and tops. A much higher relative amount of Zinc-65 was found in the plant roots in the presence of 50 m.M. bicarbonate ion than in the case of any other treatment. This immobilization of zinc in the roots may be one of the reasons why the application of cellulose aggravates zinc deficiency.

Table 12. Treatment of zinc deficiency of the rice plant at the Kala Shah Kaku Rice Farm, West Pakistan.*

Plot no.	Zinc application (kg/ha)			Organic matter (ton/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
	Nursery	Field			
		Incorporated	Surface-applied		
1	0	0	—	0	4315
2	0	0	—	5	4159
3	0	10	—	0	5982
4	0	10	—	5	6147
5	0	100	—	0	6516
6	0	100	—	5	6855
7	100	0	—	0	5253
8	100	0	—	5	4968
9	100	10	—	0	6170
10	100	10	—	5	6020
11	Dipping seedlings in 1% ZnO suspension		—	0	5858
12**	Foliar spray (10 kg/ha)		—	0	5713
13	0	—	10	0	6008
14	0	—	100	0	6915
15**	0	—	10	0	5690
16**	0	—	100	0	6170

* All plots were fertilized with 168 kg/ha N, 67 kg/ha P₂O₅, 67 kg/ha K₂O.

** Applied about 2 weeks after transplanting, when the deficiency symptoms were noticed.

Table 13. pH, total and available zinc content of soils, and plant zinc content.

Country	Expt. no.	Soil	pH	Total Zn (ppm)	Available Zn* (ppm)	Plant Zn (ppm)
India	5	Lateritic	5.3	23	3.4	46
	10	Usar	10.4	75	3.1	12
	13 **	Calcareous	8.3	75	4.3	8
	15	Regur	7.8	82	4.3	29
	18	Lateritic	5.1	110	3.1	20
Pakistan	2 †	Calcareous	7.9	99	—	10
	6	Calcareous	8.6	75	—	11
	7	Calcareous	8.6	92	—	12

* 0.1 HC1 extractable.

** Pant Nagar, India.

† Kala Shah Kaku, West Pakistan.

Table 14. The effects of pH, nitrogen, and bicarbonate ion concentrations of culture solutions on the absorption of Zn-65 by the rice plant.*

Nitrogen (ppm)	Bicarbonate** (m.M)	Dry weight (g/pot)		cpm/0.1 g dry matter		Total cpm x 10 ³ /plant		Total
		Top	Roots	Top	Roots	Top	Roots	
pH 5								
20	0	19.3	4.2	581	8037	11.2 (25)†	33.8 (75)	45.0
40	0	37.5	6.2	1376	13250	51.6 (39)	82.2 (61)	133.8
80	0	48.7	5.3	1778	26950	86.6 (38)	142.9 (62)	229.5
pH 8								
20	0	18.3	4.0	705	—	12.9	—	—
40	0	38.0	6.0	1069	17790	40.6 (28)	106.8 (72)	147.4
80	0	54.3	6.6	1350	20970	73.3 (35)	134.4 (65)	211.7
40	10	38.2	8.3	1199	16510	45.8 (25)	137.0 (75)	182.8
40	50	39.4	6.3	698	24360	27.5 (15)	153.5 (85)	181.0

* Measurement of radioactivity was made 6 hours after Zn-65 was added to culture solutions.

** Bicarbonate was added as NaHCO₃.

† Figures in parentheses show the relative amount of radioactivity on the top and root portions.

Mobility of Zinc-65 absorbed via roots and a lower leaf of the rice plant. Table 15 shows the mobility and distribution of Zinc-65 when it is absorbed through the roots or through the 5th leaf from the top. When zinc was absorbed through the roots, a distinctly higher amount went to the upper leaves. A similar trend was also found when zinc was absorbed through the lowest leaf. These experiments may explain why brown discoloration starts with the lower leaves.

Response to Photoperiod

Panicle emergence

BPI-76, a photoperiod-sensitive variety, requires a minimum of eight photoinductive cycles before panicle initiation can occur. Additional short photoperiods are necessary for the panicle primordium to develop further and emerge; otherwise, the primordium will revert to its vegetative character, become dormant and produce a vegetative branch, or will develop into a small panicle but will never exert from the flag leaf sheath. Observations have indicated a definite effect of photoperiod on the subsequent development of the panicle. To study this effect, an experiment was conducted using BPI-76.

The plants were grown for 30 days under a 24-hour photoperiod (non-inductive photoperiod) and then given 10 and 15 ten-hour photoinductive cycles. After the photoinductive treatments, the two sets of plants were divided into six groups per set and given 10, 12, 13, 14, 16 and 24 hours of photoperiod until flowering.

As shown on Table 16, all plants given photoinductive cycles initiated panicle primordium and all had panicle exertions except at the 24-hour photoperiod when three plants out of 10 did not exert panicles. The longer the photoperiod after panicle initiation, the greater was the delay in panicle exertion.

When the plants were given five cycles more than the minimum requirement, the subsequent photoperiods had very little effect on panicle exertion although those subjected to the 10-hour and 12-hour photoperiods flowered significantly earlier than the other treatments. Apparently, the five extra cycles are enough to produce the necessary stimulus for the normal elongation of

Table 15. Mobility and distribution of Zn-65 absorbed through the roots and through a leaf.

Leaf no. *	cpm/0.1 g dry matter	
	pH 5	pH 8
Through the roots		
1	4745	5192
2	2144	2039
3	985	1814
4	659	509
5	925	606
Through the 5th leaf from the top		
1	1050	1197
2	435	919
3	844	498
4	269	599
5	115931	111280

* Counted from the top on the main culm.

Table 16. Effect of photoperiods on panicle emergence (average of 10 plants).

Number of 10-hr cycles	Photoperiod after inductive cycles (hours)	Days from treatment to flowering	Leaf number of flowering
10	10	39	12
	12	53	12
	13	60	12
	14	62	12
	16	67	12
	24	70 *	12
15	10	38	12
	12	44	12
	13	46	12
	14	47	12
	16	46	12
	24	46	12

* Average of seven plants.

LSD (.01) for 10 cycles = 3.8

LSD (.01) for 15 cycles = 1.5

Table 17. Effect of photoperiods after panicle initiation on the lengths of the panicle and the first internode, and on the panicle-internode ratio. These data from 10 plants are given in centimeters.

Treatment		Photoperiods (hours)					
		10	12	13	14	16	24
10 Photoinductive cycles	Panicle	23	31	43	44	47	51 *
	Internode	30	35	26	27	20	15 *
	P/I ratio	0.76	0.89	1.65	1.63	2.35	3.40
15 Photoinductive cycles	Panicle	23	28	29	29	29	26
	Internode	30	37	37	38	40	38
	P/I ratio	0.77	0.76	0.78	0.70	0.73	0.68

* Average of seven plants.

10 Photoinductive cycles

LSD (.05) for panicle = 5.3

LSD (.05) for 1st internode = 6.6

15 Photoinductive cycles

LSD (.05) for panicle = 1.2

LSD (.05) for 1st internode = 2.4

the internodes and the eventual exertion of the panicle.

The panicle primordia of the treated plants were all initiated at the same time or at the same leaf stage as evidenced by the fact that the leaf number of the main culm at flowering time was the same for all plants. The delay in flowering was mainly a delay in development and elongation.

The lengths of the panicle and the first internode were not greatly affected by photoperiod after panicle initiation if the plants were given 15 photoinductive cycles, except at the 10-hour photoperiod (Table 17). The plants that received only 10 photoinductive cycles generally showed an increase in panicle length with the increase in photoperiod. The internodes at the 16- and 24-hour photoperiods were shorter than those at the 10- to 14-hour photoperiods. This shows the effect of photoperiod after panicle initiation.

Whether the effect of photoperiod is directly related to internode elongation and panicle length or indirectly to the degree of development of

panicle primordium, which then controls the elongation of the panicle and internodes, is not clear. The degree of development of the panicle primordium may be the factor controlling the length of the panicle and that of the first internode.

The panicle length-internode length ratio tended to be higher with longer photoperiods in the case of plants receiving 10 photoinductive cycles. The present data show that when the panicle was greatly elongated, the first internode suffered a great reduction in length. Some plants grown at a 24-hour photoperiod after the 10 photoinductive cycles did not exert panicles since the first internode was much shorter than normal or even shorter than the leaf sheath. The increase in panicle length was due to the increase in length of the panicle axis, resulting in a decrease in the grain density of the panicle.

Effect of temperature during photoinduction

The rice plant may respond simultaneously to

temperature and photoperiod but the degree varies according to variety. Temperature affects both the photoperiod-sensitive and photoperiod-insensitive varieties. Generally, high temperature accelerates heading and low temperature delays it.

Although there have been many published studies on the effect of temperature on the flowering response of the rice plant, the question still remains as to whether temperature affects photoinduction or panicle initiation since the previous studies have been based on either the growth of the panicle or on the time of flowering.

To answer the above question, an experiment was conducted using the variety BPI-76. The plants were grown under a 24-hour photoperiod for 45 days after which they were given 14 photoinductive cycles (10 hours each) with the following night temperatures: 21, 27, and 32 C. The plants were again subjected to the 24-hour photoperiod after the treatment.

Table 18 shows that plants given photoinductive cycles at 27 C flowered 38 days after treatment while those given photoinductive cycles at 21 C flowered 52 days after treatment or a

Fig. 34. Effect of temperatures during photoinduction on panicle development.

Fig. 35. Effect of temperatures during photoinduction on subsequent leafing intervals.

difference of 14 days. At 32 C there was also a delay in flowering when compared to the 27 C treatment which was the optimum.

Since the leaf number on the main culm of plants in all treatments was the same before and at flowering, the plants must have been photoinduced at the same time regardless of the temperature during photoinduction. The vegetative primordia were converted to reproductive primordia at the same time or at the same morphological stage regardless of temperature.

The subsequent development and elongation of the panicle primordia differed in the three treatments, with high temperature accelerating the process (Fig. 34). Leaf development was also accelerated by high temperatures (Fig. 35). Optimum panicle development and leaf development of the main culm occurred at 27 C. The delay in panicle exertion of plants given photoinductive cycles at 21 C and 32 C was mainly caused by the slow leafing interval.

Although the plants were under the same temperature conditions during the period of

Table 18. Effect of temperature during photoinduction.

Temperature	Days from treatment to flowering	Leaf number at flowering (main culm)
21 C	52	14.0
27 C	38	14.0
32 C	44	14.0

panicle development and elongation, those that had been subjected to high temperatures during photoinduction (14 short days) had a more rapid panicle growth. The effect of the temperature treatment was apparent in the growth of the panicle and leaves long after completion of the treatment.

This study would indicate that temperature during the dark period has little effect on photoinduction or panicle initiation. However, it affects the subsequent development of the panicle primordium.

Internode Elongation

Response to increasing water depth

Large areas in Thailand and Pakistan are planted to floating rice. The water in these areas is usually more than 1 meter deep and remains at a high level for long periods. In the Philippines, as in areas

around Laguna de Bay, the water depth may reach 1 meter for several weeks. Varieties used in these areas should have a good plant type and still retain the ability to elongate rapidly if necessary.

Several crosses have been made by the Varietal Improvement Department using floating rice varieties from Thailand and the short, stiff-strawed varieties. The response of the parents and selected lines to increasing water depth were studied.

The seedlings were sown in clay pots containing soil and sufficient fertilizer. Thirty-five days after transplanting, the plants were transferred to a water tank and the water level was adjusted to 10 cm above the soil level. The water level was increased by 10 cm every fifth day until the water depth was 110 cm.

The increase in culm length as a result of the treatment is shown in Table 19. Among the parents, CP231 x SLO-17 showed the least response while both floating varieties gave a large response. Selections from crosses, with CP231 x SLO-17 as one of the parents, gave very low responses, i.e., these lines may not do well under deep water conditions. Crosses of Leb Mue Nahng with Taichung (N) 1 or IR95 showed the greatest response. In some cases the response was greater than that of the floating parent variety.

Although the water depth used was just over a meter, the test showed that it is possible to breed for short, stiff-strawed varieties which still retain the ability to elongate under deep water conditions. Apparently, the height of the plant and the ability to elongate are separate characters of the plant.

Table 19. Response of selected varieties and lines to increasing water. The relative heights were obtained from the Varietal Improvement Department.

Variety and line	Relative height classification	Control	Treated	Difference
Parents				
CP231 x SLO-17	Short	91	93	2
Pingaew 56	Tall	164	196	32
Selected Lines				
IR435-3	Interm.	97	119	22
IR435-14	Interm.	91	108	17
IR435-17	Interm.	111	127	16
IR435-28	Interm.	92	113	21

Continued on the next page

Table 19 continued

Variety and line	Relative height classification	Control	Treated	Difference
Parents				
Leb Mue Nahng	Tall	167	215	48
Taichung (N) 1	Short	73	107	34
Selected Lines				
IR439-1-37-1	Interm.	75	105	30
IR439-1-44-1	Interm.	59	82	23
IR439-2-2-1	Short.	59	85	26
IR439-2-7-1	Interm.	86	106	20
Parents				
CP231 x SLO-17	Short	91	93	2
Leb Mue Nahng	Tall	167	215	48
Selected Lines				
IR441-2-2	Interm.	97	114	16
IR441-5	Tall	113	137	24
IR441-10	Tall	83	103	21
IR441-16	Short	94	109	15
Parents				
Peta/2 x T(N) 1	Short	67	106	39
Leb Mue Nahng	Tall	167	215	48
Selected Lines				
IR442-1-11-1	Short	88	127	39
IR442-1-12-1	Short	75	132	58
IR442-1-20-1	Short	58	118	60
IR442-1-25-2	Interm.	67	129	63
IR442-1-39-3	Interm.	68	120	52
IR442-1-62-3	Interm.	87	134	48
IR442-2-8-1	Interm.	75	114	38
IR442-1-12-2	Interm.	75	108	33
IR442-2-32-2	Interm.	81	131	50
IR440-8	Interm.	99	121	23
Peta	Tall	128	157	29
IR8(68)	Short	64	101	37
IR5-47-2	Interm.	87	125	38
IR11-288-3-1-2	Short	62	99	37

Cereal Chemistry

The integrated study of the relationship between the properties of the rice grain and its processing, eating, and nutritive values this year emphasized: (a) the influence of parboiling on the physicochemical properties of the rice grain of seven varieties and selections of rice, (b) the nature of rice hemicelluloses and their relation to the alkali test, (c) the improvement of the protein content of rice through crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties, and (d) the physicochemical nature of rice proteins. A study of the metabolism of protein by varieties differing in grain protein level was initiated.

Effect of Parboiling and Variety on Grain Properties

Parboiling and grain properties

Rough rice of seven varieties and selections differing in amylose content was parboiled to study the effect on the properties of the grain. To parboil, the rough rice was soaked in water until saturation, after which it was steamed and dried slowly. The process had no effect on the 100-grain weight, protein content, and amylose content (as measured by iodine colorimetry and potentiometric titration) of the brown rice.

That the starch granules underwent gelatinization on parboiling was verified by the loss of birefringence under polarized light and by the amorphous x-ray diffraction pattern (Fig. 1) of the flour. Starch corrosion by 2.2*N* hydrochloric acid was greater in parboiled than in raw rice (Table 1). The intrinsic viscosity of the whole rice powder of the waxy selection, IR253-16-1-1-2, did not change following parboiling, thus indicating very little degradation of starch during the process.

Parboiling increased the translucency of the grain in all varieties and even the waxy selection, IR253, became translucent. Three tests showed that endosperm hardness was increased also. The values for the breaking and crushing hardness, as measured with a Kiya-type tester, were higher for all parboiled samples than for the raw samples. The head rice yields at 4 percent milling (the point at which 4 percent bran by weight has been removed) were at least 99 percent of the total milled rice in all parboiled samples, while the average for the raw rice samples was 75.3 percent. The percentage passing through an 80-mesh screen after 40 seconds in a Wig-L-Bug amalgamator was significantly reduced, thus indicating that parboiled rice has greater resistance to disintegration than raw rice.

Parboiling drastically reduced the extractability of protein in all samples by an average of 45 percent. Although this was true for all four protein fractions, the globulin fraction showed the largest reduction – 65 percent. Similar amino acid compositions were found in the residual protein of both raw and parboiled brown rice following serial extraction of the protein fractions.

A histochemical investigation showed a fusion of adjoining starch granules in parboiled, but not in raw, endosperm. In addition, the protein bodies in parboiled endosperms were less distinct. Parboiling then, evidently causes the expansion and subsequent cohesion/adhesion of the gelatinized starch and protein particles into a solid matrix. This information would help to explain the improved translucency and increased hardness of the grain and the reduced extractability of protein following parboiling.

The cooking and pasting properties of the seven raw and parboiled samples were also compared. The cooking water of the raw samples showed more dissolved solids and a deeper blue color following the addition of iodine than that of the

Table 1. A comparison of properties of raw and parboiled rice (mean of seven varieties).

Property	Treatment	
	Raw	Parboiled
Four-day lintnerization loss (% of milled-rice flour)	60.7	77.5
Brown rice hardness (Kiya Tester)		
Breaking (kg)	5.4	9.6
Crushing (kg)	8.9	15.4
Head rice yield (% of milled rice)	75.3	99.8
Percentage passing through an 80-mesh sieve after disintegration	89.0	48.8
Cooking water (cooking test)		
Solids (%)	9.9	5.5
Blue value (600 $m\mu$), absorbance	0.31	0.19
Elongation ratio (cooked/raw)	1.44	1.14
Protein fractions (% of dry wt)		
Albumin	1.00	0.58
Globulin	1.18	0.41
Prolamin	0.29	0.16
Glutelin	4.95	2.83
Extraction efficiency (%)	74.1	41.8

Fig. 1. X-ray diffractogram of brown rice of raw, 65°C water-soaked, and parboiled IR8 rice.

parboiled samples. The parboiled grains tended to expand girthwise more than did the raw grains. This tendency was more apparent in the samples presoaked in the cooking water for 2 hours before heating (Fig. 2).

Parboiling influenced the amylograph curves of an 11-percent aqueous suspension of brown rice powder. The gelatinization temperatures of the samples with 2.0 percent (waxy) and 7.5 percent amylose were shifted to lower values, but the samples with higher amylose contents showed little change. The peak viscosity changed drastically in the highest (27%) amylose sample, IR8, from 1,010 to 120 Brabender units. Samples with less than 25 percent amylose showed less change. These results may be related to the observed *in situ* retrogradation of amylose in which the starch-iodine-blue test showed that the amylose of the gelatinized high-amylose rice samples was less extractable than that of the lower amylose samples. The retrogradation of the gelatinized amylose, which prevents the swelling of the granules during heating in the amylograph bowl, can thus explain the suppressed amylogram of

parboiled IR8. This retrogradation may also explain the fainter iodine staining of starch in slices of parboiled IR8 rice as compared with that of the raw rice.

The changes in grain properties during storage of the raw and parboiled samples were also studied. The amylograph viscosities of parboiled rice did not change, whereas those of the recently harvested raw samples increased with age. The starch became more insoluble in water but its amylose content did not change significantly during storage for either raw or parboiled samples. These results are in agreement with a previous 2-year storage study of rough and milled rice and rice starch of the IR8 variety.

The endosperm showed an increasing disarrangement of the starch and protein particles following parboiling and cooking (Fig. 3). In laboratory-parboiled samples, adjoining starch granules were fused together through the endosperm. A parboiled rice sample from Burma, however, showed starch gelatinization of only the surface cells. A cross-section of the cooked rice grain

Fig. 2. Effect of a 2-hour presoaking on the swelling properties of raw and parboiled rices.

showed that the endosperm contents were very disorganized and cell walls were difficult to discern.

Variety and grain properties

Waxy rices have a compact arrangement of compound starch granules in the endosperm, whereas nonwaxy rices that are somewhat opaque have a loose arrangement of the starch granules. The endosperm of a breeding line containing 8 percent amylose was examined histologically since it showed a tombstone-white appearance intermediate between that of waxy and nonwaxy endosperms. The histological examination revealed a compact arrangement of the starch granules. Presumably, the cause of opacity in these low-amylose and waxy endosperms is related to the low content of amylose and not to a loose packing of the starch granules.

To explain the varietal differences in elongation during the cooking of presoaked milled rice, a

histological examination of the endosperm of selected varieties was undertaken. No general differences could be detected between those varieties which greatly expand lengthwise and those which predominantly expand girthwise during cooking.

The properties of the starch fractions and aminogram of an opaque, nonwaxy (30% amylose) Thai variety, Khao Long 258-22-33, were determined. The amylopectin and amylose fractions showed properties similar to those of other nonwaxy samples. The lysine content of this variety was 4.04 percent of the brown rice protein and it had a normal protein level of 6.12 percent. No unusually high-lysine rice sample has yet been identified.

Varietal screenings were made on samples obtained from Bulgaria and South Korea. The milled rice of three varieties from Plovdiv, Bulgaria, had 7.0 to 9.8 percent protein and 24.3 to 27.3 percent amylose, both on a dry weight

basis. They all had low gelatinization temperatures. Of the five varieties from South Korea, one was waxy and four were nonwaxy, amylose contents ranging between 20.5 to 24.2 percent. All five had low gelatinization temperatures. Their protein levels ranged from 5.7 to 8.4 percent.

Rice Hemicelluloses

Hemicelluloses are polysaccharides of high molecular weight which are composed mainly of pentose units (L-arabinose and D-xylose) although hexoses (D-galactose, D-glucose, and D-mannose) are frequently found in association with them. Aside from cellulose, the hemicelluloses probably constitute the least studied carbohydrate fraction of the rice grain. Because of their uneven distribution in the rice grain, both bran-polish and milled rice fractions of IR8 were used as sources of hemicelluloses for this study. Hemicelluloses extracted during the alkali test of IR8 and BPI-76 milled rices are also being studied.

Bran-polish hemicelluloses

A 0.2 percent recovery of the crude water-soluble hemicelluloses was obtained from bran-polish by water extraction, heating, and a bleaching-earth treatment. Further purification by α -amylase digestion of starch and trichloroacetic acid precipitation of protein gave a 60-percent recovery of a purified preparation containing 11% protein, 38% arabinose, 19% xylose, 27% galactose, 7% uronic acid, and trace amounts of glucose. The overall recovery was 0.12 percent of the bran. The oxidation of this preparation with hydrogen peroxide did not result in gelation.

Alkali-soluble hemicelluloses were extracted from water-washed bran-polish. The pretreatment involved boiling, cooling, starch digestion with α -amylase at 55 C, and washing with ethanol. The crude extract (26% yield) was extracted with 0.5*N* sodium hydroxide under nitrogen, neutralized with acetic acid, treated with trichloroacetic acid, dialyzed, and lyophilized. A 3-percent yield of fibrous, fairly water-soluble brown powder was obtained. The overall extraction from bran-polish was 0.78 percent. The oxidation of the hemicellulose did not result in gelation. The hemicellulose preparation had 7% protein (as glutelin), 33% arabinose, 30% xylose, 10% galactose and 8%

uronic acid (pectin). It was devoid of mannose, but showed a faint reaction for polyphenolic compounds. The residual bran still contained large amounts of arabinose, xylose, and galactose, thus indicating an incomplete extraction of all hemicelluloses. Part of the alkali-extracted hemicellu-

A

B

C

Fig. 3. Cross section of rice endosperm: (A) raw, (B) parboiled, and (C) cooked. Stain: Hematoxylin.

lose became insoluble upon neutralization with acetic acid and was therefore discarded. It corresponded to the classical hemicellulose A. The portion which remained in solution corresponded to hemicellulose B. A minor fraction which precipitated upon lowering the pH to 3.7 with trichloroacetic acid contained mannose.

Further characterization work was done on the alkali-soluble bran-polish hemicellulose preparation. The preparation was fractionated in a DEAE cellulose column (borate form, pH 9.2). Gradient elution with increasing borate molarity from 0.01 to 0.65*M* showed a continuous elution of carbohydrate material between 0.1 and 0.45*M*. To obtain distinct peaks, the subsequent columns were eluted stepwise with one liter each of 0.1*M*, 0.3*M*, and 0.5*M* borate buffer followed by 0.25*N* sodium hydroxide. The peaks obtained with 0.3 and 0.5*M* borate showed tailing and were probably not homogeneous. Only about 70 percent of the carbohydrates applied to the column could be recovered. Uronic acid was evaluated by the carbazole test since only the neutral sugars were recovered from the acid hydrolysates of the fractions in the presence of ion-exchange resins. A rechromatography of the sodium hydroxide peak yielded traces eluted with 0.3 and 0.5*M* borate in addition to the main sodium hydroxide peak which still contained traces of glucose and uronic acid.

The alkali-soluble hemicelluloses and their fractions contained equal amounts of arabinose and xylose, while the water-soluble hemicelluloses contained twice as much arabinose as xylose (Table 2). The 0.25*N* sodium hydroxide fraction differed from the three borate fractions in that it had a lower arabinose-xylose ratio (0.9), a higher protein content (24%), and showed traces of glucose and uronic acid. This fraction is probably heterogeneous, but was not eluted out of the DEAE column with 0.1*N* sodium hydroxide. Viscosity was measured in Ubbelohde dilution viscometers in 0.05*N* sodium hydroxide at 25 C at concentrations between 0.1 and 0.4 percent. The sodium hydroxide fraction was more stable in the alkaline solvent (0.1*N* sodium hydroxide) than were the borate fractions. Only the latter showed a drop in viscosity following overnight storage.

Preliminary studies on the sodium hydroxide

fraction showed that the protein and carbohydrate fractions may be separated by disc electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel. A study of the action pattern of xylanase and/or arabinosidase on these hemicellulose preparations will provide information on the nature of the arabinans and xylans.

Milled-rice hemicelluloses

IR8 milled rice flour was extracted twice with distilled water at 4 C. The combined extracts were heated to 90 C for 35 minutes, treated with bleaching earth, dialyzed, and lyophilized. There was a 66-percent recovery of the crude preparation. Portions of this preparation were subjected to α -amylase hydrolysis followed by a trichloroacetic acid treatment to give an overall recovery of 0.01% of a purified preparation containing 10.5% protein (Lowry), 9.5% pectin, 18% arabinose, 10% xylose, 12% galactose, and 40% glucose. It did not stain blue with iodine.

Essentially the same method was used for the preparation of the alkali-soluble hemicelluloses of milled rice as that used for bran. The overall recovery of the purified preparation was 0.1%. The hemicellulose contained 25% arabinose, 23% xylose, 8% galactose, 23% glucose, 7% uronic acid, and 14% protein. The hemicellulose A precipitate contained mostly glucose and traces of arabinose and xylose. The precipitate from the trichloroacetic acid treatment showed the same sugar composition — primarily glucose.

All the DEAE fractions of the milled-rice alkali-soluble hemicelluloses had a 1:1 ratio of arabinose to xylose and contained glucose and protein (Table 2). The carbohydrate recovery averaged 72 percent.

Preliminary studies were made on the hemicellulose solubilized during the alkali test on IR8 and BPI-76 milled rice. The resulting supernatant was separated by centrifugation, neutralized with glacial acetic acid, and recentrifuged. The hemicellulose in the neutralized supernatant was precipitated with ethanol. The preparation was subjected to α -amylolysis and trichloroacetic acid treatment, and then dialyzed. A paper chromatography of the hydrolysates revealed mostly arabinose and xylose in a ratio of approximately 1:1 and smaller amounts of glucose and galactose in both samples.

Table 2. Composition and intrinsic viscosity of fractions of bran-polish and milled rice alkali-soluble hemicelluloses obtained by DEAE-cellulose chromatography.

Solvent	Wt (%) of eluted carbohydrates	Composition (wt %)					Uronic acid	[η] (ml/g)
		Arabinose	Xylose	Galactose	Glucose	Protein		
Bran-polish								
0.1M borate	4-9	40	40	20	-	0	-	
0.3M borate	34-35	46	46	8	-	<1	-	154
0.5M borate	18-26	38	38	21	-	2.8	-	184
0.25M sodium hydroxide	28-38	32	35	9	+	24	+	114
Milled rice								
0.1M borate	9-12	28	27	8	24	13	-	1
0.3M borate	23-30	26	24	5	22	23	-	98
0.5M borate	9-13	21	20	6	20	33	-	160
0.25M sodium hydroxide	23-26	19	18	5	22	13	23	62

Improvement of the Protein Content of Rice

In the cooperative project with the Varietal Improvement Department on the improvement of the protein content of rice, brown rice of F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 plants from crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties were analyzed for crude protein. The F_2 seeds from F_1 plants showed protein contents as high as those of the high-protein parents (Table 3). Most of the plants saved were the progeny of F_2 plants showing relatively high protein contents. In addition, plants from a few of the low-protein lines showing good traits were saved. The balance, 361 plant lines, were discarded because of low protein contents and/or undesirable plant characteristics. Many of the F_4 brown rice from the 1,290 individual F_3 plants (representing 253 F_3 plant lines classified as "high protein") which had been saved had as high a protein level as the F_2 parental plants. Most of the F_3 lines and almost all of the F_3 plants saved possessed the dwarf height characteristic of IR8. Some of the lines showing high protein content (F_3 and F_4 caryopses) were dwarf lines with a reasonably good plant type.

Protein analyses of F_3 brown and hand-milled rices confirmed previous findings that the degree

of reduction of protein content during milling is lower when the pre-milling protein level is high (Table 4). It would thus appear that much of the increased protein is in the milled rice fraction, and not in the bran alone.

Single brown rice analysis was undertaken to determine the variability of protein content within a panicle. Using Peta and the high-protein lines, results showed that the top (or earlier) grain tended to have lower protein levels than the bottom (or late-produced) grain. The maximum difference obtained within a panicle was 5.4 per cent of the dry weight.

The Varietal Improvement Department conducted yield trials on 71 of the high-protein selections during the dry and wet seasons of 1968. Their yields were generally lower than those of IR8, Peta, IR5, and BPI-76. However, the protein of caryopses of these varieties grown in the dry season ranged from 7.8 to 12.9% with a mean level of 10.6%, as compared with 8.0% for IR8, 7.0% for IR5, and 6.6% for Peta. Similar results were obtained from the wet-season crop. Further trials with those high-protein varieties which were highly photosensitive were discontinued since high-protein progenies with good plant types were already available from the crosses between IR8 and these high-protein varieties.

Table 3. Protein levels of brown rice from crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties and of the two parents.

Cross no.	No. of lines	No. of plants	Brown rice protein (% wet basis)					
			Cross		IR8 parent		High-protein parent	
			Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
IR1100 (IR8 x Rikuto Norin 20)								
F ₂	-	6	9.8-17.6	13.3	9.1-11.0	10.0	-	14.3
F ₃	-	46 *	6.4-14.6	10.8	8.1- 9.9	8.8	8.4-10.0	9.5
F ₄	46	202	5.8-15.3	10.8	6.2- 8.6	7.8	-	12.9
IR1101 (IR8 x Omirt 39)								
F ₂	-	1	14.5-16.5	15.3	9.1-11.0	10.0	-	12.8
F ₃	-	44 *	7.0-12.9	10.0	6.3- 8.7	7.5	8.7- 9.9	9.8
F ₄	44	208	6.8-14.3	10.0	7.5- 9.5	8.8	10.4-12.9	11.7
IR1102 (IR8 x Santo)								
F ₂	-	6	10.0-14.3	12.7	9.1-11.0	10.0	-	13.8
F ₃	-	32 *	7.0-11.2	8.7	7.1- 8.6	8.0	8.1- 9.9	9.0
F ₄	32	156	7.4-13.0	9.4	8.4- 8.5	8.4	12.8-13.6	13.1
IR1103 (IR8 x Chow-sung)								
F ₂	-	1	14.9-16.9	16.0	9.1-11.0	10.0	-	14.6
F ₃	-	47 *	6.8-12.8	9.7	7.0- 8.0	7.7	7.3- 9.3	8.6
F ₄	47	251	7.2-14.0	10.1	8.0- 8.7	8.3	9.8-11.6	10.8
IR1104 (IR8 x Crythroceros Korn)								
F ₂	-	8	11.9-17.8	14.6	9.1-11.0	10.0	-	13.5
F ₃	-	50 *	6.9-12.3	10.1	7.4- 9.2	8.1	8.7-10.8	9.7
F ₄	50	260	5.4-13.8	10.3	7.8- 8.5	8.2	11.7-13.2	12.2
IR1105 (IR8 x Chok-jye-bi-chal)								
F ₂	-	8	11.4-18.8	15.1	9.1-11.0	10.0	-	15.4
F ₃	-	34 *	7.5-15.2	10.7	7.5- 9.0	8.0	10.2-12.7	11.7
F ₄	34	213	7.6-15.2	11.1	8.6-12.3	10.1	14.2-14.6	14.5

* Selected from 614 plants on the basis of high protein content and/or plant type.

The Spies and Chambers method for tryptophan assay gave low values for brown rice, even after defatting. Turbid solutions were obtained, and blank values were high – particularly for the red-pericarped samples. Alkaline hydrolysis at 100 C using barium hydroxide for 16 hours and the subsequent work-up resulted in improved values

for tryptophan using the Spies and Chambers method. Bran pigments were destroyed during hydrolysis. A recently developed method for evaluating tryptophan in corn based on the Opienska-Blauth reagent is being tested. This method requires neither a blank for each sample nor a dark reaction. However, it cannot be used

for red-pericarped samples.

Among the recent methods developed for lysine assay in corn is a colorimetric assay based on the reaction of 2-chloro-3,5-dinitropyridine with the *epsilon*-amino lysing group and the subsequent colorimetric assay of the resulting derivative. The applicability of this method for rice is being tested.

Three of the varieties classified as high-protein in the world collection were analyzed to determine the changes in protein quality brought about by an increase in protein level. The milling of high-protein brown rice in the McGill mill gave an 8% recovery of bran-polish in contrast to about 10% for low-protein samples. A protein analysis of the two milling fractions showed that 91% of the brown rice protein was in the milled rice and 9% was in the bran-polish fraction. The brown rice

samples had a mean protein level of 15.0% wet basis, whereas the milled rice had 14.8% and the bran-polish had 16.2%. These results are in agreement with previous findings that high-protein rices are harder to mill and have a more uniform protein distribution than low-protein samples. The fat content of the bran-polish averaged 23.0 percent.

Protein fractions of the brown and milled high-protein rice were extracted by percolation. Gluten formed 80% of total protein in brown and about 91% in milled rice. The albumin-globulin fraction was 15% in brown and 6% in milled rice, and prolamin was 5% in brown and 3% in milled rice. This distribution gradient in the protein fractions is reflected in the aminogram of milled rice and bran-polish. The two amino acids most affected were lysine and glutamic acid. Bran-polish protein had, on the average, 16.0% glutamic acid

Table 4. Protein content of F₃ brown and hand-milled rices from plants of crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties.

Cross no.	No. of plants	Protein content (wet basis)*					
		Brown rice			Milled rice		
		Overall range	Range of plant means	Overall mean	Overall range	Range of plant means	Overall mean
IR1100, IR8 X Rikuto Norin 20	18	8.0-13.4	9.7-12.3	11.1	7.4-12.7	7.9-12.5	10.6
IR1101, IR8 X Omirt 39	5	9.2-12.0	10.1-11.5	11.1	8.4-11.3	9.0-11.1	10.4
IR1102, IR8 X Santo	1	10.5-11.8	---	11.2	10.4-11.0	---	10.8
IR1103, IR8 X Chow-sung	4	10.2-13.0	11.1-12.7	11.7	10.3-12.5	10.5-12.4	11.5
IR1104, IR8 X Crythroceros Korn	5	10.2-11.6	10.6-11.2	11.0	9.4-11.6	9.9-11.4	10.8
IR1105, IR8 X Chok-jye-bi-chal	8	8.6-14.3	10.1-13.6	12.4	8.7-13.5	8.8-13.3	12.1
IR8 (Control)	12	7.0-10.3	7.4- 9.7	8.7	6.3- 9.7	6.5-9.4	8.1

* Three analyses of 6 grains each per plant, except IR8 milled rice, with only two analyses.

and 5.75% lysine, whereas milled rice protein had 21.5 and 3.32%, respectively. Because of the more even distribution of protein in these high-protein rices, the brown rice aminogram is similar to that of milled rice. The glutamic acid and lysine contents of the brown rice protein were 21.1 and 3.53%, respectively.

The rice hull has been reported to contain 1 to 3 percent protein, but the aminogram of its protein is not available in the literature. Therefore, the aminogram of the hulls and brown rice of three local varieties was determined. The hull protein showed higher values for alanine, glycine, lysine, proline, and valine, and lower values for arginine, glutamic acid, isoleucine, methionine, and tyrosine than did the brown rice protein. Since hull protein constitutes only 5 to 8 percent of the protein of rough rice, its effect on the rough rice aminogram is very slight compared with that of brown rice. Rough rice protein, for example, has a lysine content 0.14 percent higher than that of brown rice.

Because of the increasing area being planted to IR8, an investigation of the effect of replacing traditional varieties with this improved variety on the protein level of rice grown in farmers' fields was made to test the prevalent belief that yield and protein content are inversely correlated. Analyses of IR8 and traditional varieties grown in the Institute indicated that the high-yielding IR8 has a protein level comparable to that of the traditional varieties. An arrangement has been made with the Statistics Department whereby samples of IR8 and local varieties collected from farmer cooperators in the province of Laguna will be analyzed for protein content.

With the increase in the importance of IR8 as a rice variety in Asia, the nutritive value of its protein as compared with that of local varieties should be verified by actual rat feeding experiments. An amino acid analysis indicated that IR8 has the same lysine content as other varieties with the same protein level. Since techniques of protein quality evaluation have improved in recent years, a cooperative project was recently initiated with Dr. R. Bressani of the Institute of Nutrition for Central America and Panama (INCAP), Guatemala City, to study exhaustively the quality of rice protein. Three samples of milled rice were sent to INCAP - Intan, with 5.7 percent protein and two

IR8 samples with 7.3 and 9.7 percent protein, respectively. The moisture content of the samples was 12 percent. Three types of PER assays are planned: (1) at the same protein and calorie level as found in the normal diet, (2) using a fixed amount of rice and correcting only for the calorie level, and (3) at levels of protein varying from 1 to 7 or 8 percent in the diet.

Studies of Rice Protein

Soluble proteins

Studies on the various protein fractions of rice were continued. Preliminary work was done on the amylases of mature and germinating rice grain. Total amylases were assayed by observing the reaction of reducing sugars formed with the Somogyi reagent. The bran-polish of mature IR8 grain had a higher total amylase activity than the milled rice fraction. Phosphate buffer (0.1*N*), pH 7.0 was a better amylase extractant than 5 percent sodium chloride for both milled rice and bran-polish. The amylase activity of the phosphate buffer extract was about four times that of the salt extract for bran-polish. The activity of the milled rice extracts was improved by increasing the salt concentrations up to 3 percent sodium chloride after which it declined. Corresponding increases in salt concentrations in bran extracts lowered the amylase activity. Amylase activity may thus be presumed concentrated in the albumin fraction.

In whole-grain and milled rice extracts of mature grain, β -amylase was readily detected, but α -amylase could not be found by the assay method employed. For α -amylase assays, β -amylase was inactivated by heating the extracts for 5 minutes at 70 C. In the β -amylase assays, α -amylase was inactivated by adjusting the pH to 3.4 (ice bath) at least 10 minutes before the assay.

Agar-gel electrophoresis and immunoelectrophoretic analyses were applied to the bran-polish extracts. The agar-gel electrophoresis at pH 8.2 of the buffer extract and the subsequent amylase assay of the gel revealed one fast-migrating amylase band. No such band could be detected with the salt extract. Three precipitin lines were obtained with the phosphate buffer extract and only two with the salt extract (Fig. 4). Immune sera were prepared from rabbits injected with a rice protein preparation by Dr. R. Djurtoft of the

Technical University of Denmark in Copenhagen. A gel filtration on Sephadex G-100 of the buffer extract showed that the bran amylase was heterogeneous. Two broad peaks of amylase activity were obtained.

The changes in the protein fractions during germination were studied also. After the second day of germination a rapid drop in the glutelin and globulin fractions coincided with an increase in the level of non-protein N per grain (Fig. 5). A constant level of albumin and prolamins was noted.

Increases in the activities of both α - and β -amylases were noted after the fourth day of germination. Disc electrophoresis showed two amylase bands in extracts of germinating rice which were not detectable in the mature grain. Further study of the amylases is in progress.

Prolamin

Prolamin preparations were obtained from defatted brown and milled IR8 rices which had been previously extracted with water and a 5-percent salt solution. Aqueous ethanol at a 70-percent alcohol concentration extracted slightly more prolamins than did 60 percent ethanol. The recovery of prolamins was higher from brown rice protein than from milled rice. Previous studies have shown that brown rice protein has a higher content of prolamins than milled rice protein. The dialyzed prolamins recovered was 0.2 to 0.3 percent of the total protein. The preparations were very hygroscopic and contained carbohydrates, mainly glucose. The nature of the carbohydrate fraction is under study.

Glutelin

A comparison of three methods of extracting glutelin from IR8 milled rice was undertaken. The Lindner method involved the extraction of protein with sodium hydroxide (0.015*N*) and the precipitation of glutelin-prolamins by acidification of the extracts. This precipitate was washed several times with 5 percent sodium chloride and the prolamins were extracted with 60 percent ethanol. A modified Lindner procedure involved the extraction of the protein by percolating 0.015*N* and 0.01*N* sodium hydroxide solutions through a column of rice. Osborne's method consisted of extracting albumin, globulin, and prolamins with water, 5 percent sodium chloride, and 60 percent

Fig. 4. Immuno-electrophoretic patterns of bran protein extracted with phosphate buffer, and with 5% sodium chloride.

Fig. 5. Changes in the protein fractions during germination of IR8 grain.

ethanol, respectively, before extracting the glutelin with 0.05*N* sodium hydroxide. The glutelin preparations were purified by dissolution in alkali and precipitation with hydrochloric acid. Some of the preparations extracted directly from milled rice with alkali (without prior extraction of the other protein fractions) showed abnormally high lysine content values of 6.0 and 6.7 percent. The other preparations had lysine contents of 3.42 to 3.94 percent. The glutelin prepared by Osborne's method had a higher N content than those of the other preparations.

The intrinsic viscosity of the glutelin preparations ranged from 12 to 20 ml/g in 0.1*N* sodium hydroxide at 25 C. Ultracentrifugation in an alkaline solution revealed only the 1.3 to 1.6 S peak for glutelins extracted with 0.015*N* alkali. Those extracted with 0.05 or 0.1*N* sodium hydroxide showed two peaks with $S_{20,w}$ values of 1.4 to 2.3 and 4 to 6, respectively. Preliminary light-scattering data indicated that one of the glutelin preparations had a molecular weight of 3×10^6 .

Protein metabolism

In the Institute's intensive breeding program, lines are being produced which are essentially isogenic except for a single property, such as protein content, amylose content, resistance to rice blast disease, or resistance to stem borer attack. Such plant materials are ideal for studying the biochemical basis for the differences among these properties in plants, since the normal environmental and varietal differences have been minimized.

The first project, the study of protein metabolism, was initiated this year since lines differing in protein content will shortly become available from the Varietal Improvement Department. The higher protein content of some varieties possibly results from a higher rate of synthesis and/or a slower rate of breakdown of protein during grain development. Protein synthesis, in turn, is affected by a number of factors, including the level of enzymes along the synthetic pathway, the availability of amino acids, and the level of ribonucleic acid.

Preliminary experiments were made on three varieties, Peta, IR8, and A₂ torzs with a low, intermediate, and high protein level, respectively. Planting dates were adjusted so varieties would flower simultaneously. The plants were grown in pots in concrete beds under continuous flooding. The overall protein-synthesizing and hydrolytic activities were assayed during grain development at 4-day intervals using intact and homogenized brown rice. Samples were kept in an ice bath during the preparation. The capacity to synthesize protein was determined by measuring the amount of radioactivity incorporated into the grain protein after the incubation of intact, hull-free grains with a complete mixture of amino acids containing leucine-U-¹⁴C. Proteolytic activity was estimated by the rate at which a crude homogenate of brown rice could break down added protein. Assuming that differences in the ability to synthesize protein are found, the synthesis of ribonucleic acid will be assayed by allowing brown rice to incorporate adenosine triphosphate-¹⁴C from a mixture containing the three other nucleotides — guanosine, cytidine, and uridine triphosphates. Ribonuclease was estimated on the basis of the ability of the homogenates to break down added ribonucleic acid. It was found that the ribonuclease activity in the rice grain was much lower than in corn. Proteolytic activity also seemed to be low. These preliminary experiments provided the bases for the selection of a standardized method of assay which will later be applied on the isogenic lines differing in protein level.

Varietal Improvement

The breeding program was considerably expanded during the year. Six pedigree nurseries with a total of 41,577 rows selected from 324 different crosses were grown. A total of 55 F₂ populations were planted and over 4,000 plant selections were made from them for growing in pedigree rows. Some of the important new crosses were between IR8 and six high-protein varieties. Several F₃ pedigree rows from these crosses were of reasonably good plant type and had as high a protein content as 12 percent. In the same experiment the protein content of the IR8 check rows varied from 7.9 to 9.1 percent.

Observational and replicated yield trials were grown twice during the year. Several lines of good plant type yielded as well as IR8 and in addition showed resistance to several diseases and insects and possessed grains of improved milling and cooking quality. These promising lines are being tested in the rice growing countries of Asia and South America, and it is hoped that one or two of them will be found suitable for release as new varieties. Pure seed programs for several promising selections were started.

In 1968 over 12,000 samples of seeds of Institute breeding lines were sent to 183 individuals and organizations in 79 countries. A large number of varieties and lines were sent to various cooperating countries to determine their adaptability, resistance to various diseases, reaction to low temperatures and/or performance under conditions of deep water. In addition, special nurseries of breeding lines were sent to the cooperating countries for field tests for resistance to bacterial leaf blight, blast, and the tungro virus.

Genetic studies to determine the allelic relationships of various dwarfs and semidwarfs and to ascertain the inheritance pattern of photoperiod sensitivity were continued. Cytological investigations of the causes of sterility in the sterile indica x indica crosses were continued, and new studies on the sterile indica x bulu hybrids were initiated.

Varietal Testing and Improvement

World collection

The number of cultivated varieties of *Oryza sativa* maintained in the Institute world collection now totals 11,057 accessions, of which 226 were received during the year. Of this total, 652 accessions were grown during the year and morphologic-agronomic data were taken on them in the field and in the laboratory. New accessions are grown in at least one wet and one dry season for proper description and classification and are regrown from time to time for maintaining viable seeds.

A varietal catalogue which describes 8,628 accessions is nearing completion.

Viability is maintained by placing a 250-gram seed sample of each accession in a cold room maintained at 1 to 4 C. The moisture content of stored rice is gradually reduced to below 7 percent during storage by placing samples in sealed glass bottles (2-gallon capacity, with 12-cm diameter screwcaps) containing silica gel. Seed samples of 12 accessions are placed in each bottle along with 600 grams of activated silica gel. The silica gel is replaced every 6 months with reactivated silica gel.

The moisture content of the rough rice at the start of the storage period usually varies from 11 to 13 percent, or the approximate moisture content reached in the air-conditioned seed room which is maintained at about 25 C. After several changes of silica gel, the moisture content is reduced to about 6 percent.

An experiment to determine the viability of stored materials over a period of years was started in April 1963. Seeds of the varieties Peta, Siam 29 and Chianan 8 were placed in air-sealed metal cans and stored in the cold storage room housing the world collection. Each can contained 1,500 grams of rough rice and 500 grams of silica gel. The cans were opened every 6 months and a small seed sample withdrawn for determining the percentage of germination. Reactivated silica gel was added each time the cans were opened. In 1967, the metal cans were replaced by 2-gallon glass bottles with metal screwcaps similar to those used for storing the world collection. At present about 1 kilogram of rough rice remains in each bottle. The amount of silica gel placed in each bottle is 600 grams.

At the start of the experiment, the moisture

content of the rough rice ranged from 12.29 to 13.83 percent. In July 1968, the moisture content ranged from 3.08 to 6.33 percent and the percentage of germination from 83.8 for Chianan 8 to 95.4 for Siam 29. The germination percentage of Peta was 91.2. A total of 500 seeds were used to determine the germination percentage of each sample.

During the year, over 5,000 seed samples of accessions from the world collection were sent to 147 organizations located in 60 countries.

Breeding program

The breeding program was expanded considerably, with larger numbers of F_2 populations and pedigree rows being grown during the year than in any previous year. Similarly, the number of breeding lines grown in the observational and replicated yield trials was also larger than in previous years. The seed purification and multiplication programs were expanded to involve many new selections.

The main breeding objectives as outlined in the previous reports were continued. As some of the insects such as the brown planthoppers and the green leafhoppers act as vectors of rice viruses besides causing direct damage to the rice plant, the problem of breeding for resistance to these insects received considerable emphasis. The breeding for high protein content is another breeding objective which received attention during the year. The crosses of six high-protein varieties with IR8 were screened in early segregating generations and the selection for high protein content appeared to be effective.

F₂ populations. A total of 55 F_2 populations of new crosses were grown during the year. From these populations over 4,000 plant selections were made for growing in pedigree rows. Over 700 F_2 backcross populations from 35 different backcross combinations were grown and over 4,600 plant selections made for growing in pedigree rows. Some of the important new crosses and backcrosses were between IR8 and six high-protein varieties, and between Peta/3 x Taichung (Native) 1 and Thailand varieties such as Leuang Hawm, Gam Pai, Khao Khian, Khao Selti, Khao Poodhat, Nahng Suwon, Khao Med Lek, Leuang Pratahn and Khao Dawk Mali. IR8 x Intan is another promising cross of which F_2 bulk populations and F_3 pedigree rows were grown.

Pedigree nurseries. pedigree nurseries were sown in November and December 1967 and in February, May, July and August 1968. The number of pedigree rows grown during this period totaled 41,577. Of this number, 2,080 rows consisted of parental check varieties spaced every 20th row.

The pedigree lines grown during the year were selected from 324 different crosses made at the Institute. The large number of crosses involved gives some idea as to the genetic diversity of the Institute's breeding program.

It is essential that a wide range of genetic diversity be developed within the improved plant-type material. This diversity includes wide differences in resistance to diseases and insects, leaf characteristics such as toughness and rate of senescence, degree of resistance to cold, extremely wide variations in grain size and shape, and milling and cooking properties.

Eighty of the more promising crosses grown in pedigree rows are listed in Table 1. These crosses represent over 65 percent of the total number of selections grown.

The Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 backcrosses to Peta made up only 701 rows but aside from the Peta/7 x Taichung (Native) 1 combination, intensive selection has been discontinued. Many extremely promising lines were obtained from this series of backcrosses. They range in maturity from 10 days earlier to 15 or more days later than IR8. Most of these lines are resistant to tungro and are more resistant to grassy stunt than IR8. They have excellent plant type and sturdy stems but are not highly resistant to the bacterial diseases.

Recently, lines of the Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 backcrosses have been found which do not show the white belly characteristic of the grain which is so prominent on IR8 grains. Some of these clear-grain lines are being tested extensively at the Institute and elsewhere. The better Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 backcross lines are considered to be outstanding as parent material.

Intan, a variety closely related to Peta, was crossed with IR8. F₃ pedigree lines from this cross were grown in the August nursery and included many good long-grain types which do not have white belly. Some of these lines tend to show lower amylose content than the Peta hybrids. They offer much promise as parent material and as possible commercial varieties. Their only serious

Table 1. Leading crosses grown in pedigree nurseries, IRR1, November 1967 to August 1968.

IR No.	Cross	No. of pedigree rows grown
IR95	Peta/2 x T(N)1	24
IR262	Peta/3 x T(N)1	36
IR400	Peta/4 x T(N)1	51
IR482	Peta/5 x T(N)1	45
IR564	Peta/6 x T(N)1	78
IR658	Peta/7 x T(N)1	467
Total		701
IR1093	IR8 x Intan	122
IR577	IR8 x Sigadis	132
IR578	IR8 x [Sigadis x T(N)1]	248
IR930	IR8 x (MCVA x 1-geo-tze) (IR 12-178)	518
Total		1020
IR662	IR8 x [IR4-253 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1)]	401
IR783	IR8/2 x [IR4-253x (B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1)]	72
IR790	IR400 x [(IR8 x IR4-253) x (B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1)]	244
Total		717
IR758	IR8/2 x Dawn	275
IR759	IR8 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	286
IR879	IR8/2 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	103
IR782	IR8 x [Dawn x T(N)1]	347
IR643	IR8 x (81B-25 x Dawn)	480
IR749	IR8/2 x (81B-25 x Dawn)	668
IR880	IR8/3 x (81B-25 x Dawn)	220
Total		2379
IR626	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	464
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	
IR751	IR8/2 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	1345
IR875	IR8/3 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	585
Total		2394

IR no.	Cross	No. of pedigree rows grown	IR No.	Cross	No. of pedigree rows grown
IR533	(CP-SLO/2 x Sigadis) x [Peta/3 x T(N)1]	141	IR748	IR8 x (Dawn x Pankhari 203)	174
IR661	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	506	IR877	IR8/2 x (Dawn x Pankhari 203)	254
IR594	IR8 x (CP-SLO x BPI-76)	82	Total		3831
IR593	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4	611	IR627	IR8 x Wagwag	251
IR755	IR8 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4		IR752	IR8/2 x Wagwag	319
IR773	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4)		IR881	IR8/3 x Wagwag	154
IR874	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4	838	IR793	Wagwag/2 x IR8	143
IR878	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4		Total		867
Total		2178	IR1154	IR8/2 x Zenith	1127
IR754	IR8/2 x [Nahng Mon S-4 x T(N)1]	172	IR666	IR8 x Yukara	273
IR835	IR262 x Leuang Hawm	51	IR568	Yukara x T(N)1	270
IR841	IR262 x Khao Dawk Mali	338	IR667	IR8 x [Yukara x T(N)1]	692
IR1113	IR262/2 x Khao Dawk Mali	126	IR781	IR8/2 x [Yukara x T(N)1]	1477
IR810	IR8 x Khao Dawk Mali	56	IR934	IR8/3 x [Yukara x T(N)1]	613
IR838	IR262 x Khao Tah Haeng 17	247	IR583	IR8 x FF 33	168
IR1109	IR262/2 x Khao Tah Haeng 17	23	IR800	Ch. 242/2 x FF 36	143
IR844	IR262 x Puang Nahk 16	342	IR672	(Peta x PI 215936 x Ch. 242	51
IR1108	IR262/2 x Puang Nahk 16	11	IR450	Ch. 242/2 x Peta	87
Total		1366	IR744	Ch. 242/2 x Pankhari 203	103
IR848	IR262 x (Cp-SLO x Gam Pai)	336	Total		3877
IR789	IR8 x Muey Nahng 62M	309	IR159	Basmati 370 x T(N)1	126
IR887	IR8/2 x Muey Nahng 62M	236	IR520	Basmati 370/2 x T(N)1	75
IR933	IR8/2 x Muey Nahng 62M		IR 1001	IR8 x T-3 Basmati	68
Total		881	Total		269
IR574	IR8 x (CP 231 x Dima)	294	IR579	IR8 x Tadukan	463
IR822	IR8/2 x Pankhari 203	1942	IR532	[Peta/3 x T(N)1] x TKM-6	1151
IR932	IR8/3 x Pankhari 203	131	IR580	IR8 x TKM-6	527
IR854	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x [Peta/3 x T(N)1]	519	IR747	TKM-6/2 x T(N)1	138
IR825	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x [Peta/6 x T(N)1]	811	Total		2279
			IR528	[Peta/3 x T(N)1] x ADT-27	223

IR No.	Cross	No. of pedigree rows grown
IR570	IR8 x ADT-27	100
Total		323
IR1005	IR8 x (BPI-76 x T. 176)	121
IR586	IR8 x (BPI-76/2 x T. 172)	333
IR591	IR8 x (FB-24 x T. 172)	150
Total		604
IR589	IR8 x (H-105 x Dgwg)	305
IR474	Sukanandi x T(N)1	215
IR478	CP-SLO x Sukanandi	199
Total		414
IR435	CP-SLO x Pingaew 56	24
IR441	CP-SLO x Leb Mue Nahng	60
IR439	T(N)1 x Leb Mue Nahng	63
IR442	[Peta/2 x T(N)1] x Leb Mue Nahng	282
Total		429

drawback is their lack of resistance to the bacterial diseases.

Another selection which showed an excellent grain type of lower amylose content than IR8 was a dwarf line from the cross IR8 x (Mong Chim Vang A x I-geo-tze). The Mong Chim Vang A x I-geo-tze parent line (IR12-178-2-3) was resistant to grassy stunt, the grains did not show white belly, and the amylose content was 24 to 26 percent compared with 30 percent or more for IR8. Many good plant-type lines combining grassy stunt resistance, intermediate amylose content, and absence of white belly have been selected from this cross.

Selections from Sigadis x Taichung (Native) 1 backcross (IR305) continue to show promise. Some of the better lines are higher tillering and shorter in height than IR8. They are also more resistant to the bacterial leaf diseases and blast. These lines have yielded well in variety and fertilizer yield trials. While they may not develop into commercial varieties, they provide another valuable parental source.

IR8 and a Peta/4 x Taichung (Native) 1 line were crossed with the F₁ plant of a cross between IR4-253 (H-105 x Dee-geo-woo-gen) and an advanced generation selection from B589A4-18-1/2 x Taichung (Native) 1. Excellent lines combining IR8 plant type with good long grains were obtained. It was anticipated that bacterial leaf blight resistance would be obtained as B589A4-18 possessed resistance. However, the B589A4-18-1/2 x Taichung (Native) 1 selection used did not carry resistance to the disease. H-105 appears to have a high level of resistance to the brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens*) and the lines selected from the crosses with IR8 and Peta/4 x Taichung (Native) 1 mentioned above will be tested for resistance to the insect.

The variety Dawn has been used extensively as a blast-resistant parent. Over 2,300 rows of selections from crosses involving Dawn were grown. In addition to blast resistance, these lines show promising plant traits such as slow senescence, tough leaves, and non-pubescent plant parts. Many lines of excellent grain shape and appearance as well as lower amylose content have been found in these crosses.

IR8 was crossed with a line from Peta/3 x Dawn which was resistant to blast, tungro, and grassy stunt, and also with an 81B-25 x Dawn line. In both combinations, one backcross to IR8 was made. Many promising blast-resistant selections were made and a total of over 1,700 lines were grown and studied.

An early maturing Peta/5 x Belle Patna line was crossed with IR8 followed by one and two backcrosses to IR8. A total of 2,394 lines were grown from these combinations. Early maturity was lost in most cases but excellent long slender grain types of good plant-type were obtained. These lines have performed very well in yield trials. Also, they appear to have tougher leaves and more resistance to grassy stunt than IR8.

The selection CP231 x SLO-17 (Acc. No. 6993) has been used in many crosses. It has a relatively short height which is easily recovered from its hybrids. CP-SLO has a tough leaf which has been transmitted to many hybrid lines. As demonstrated by IR127-80-1-10 (CP-SLO x Sigadis), clear or translucent grains have been found in many lines from crosses involving CP-SLO. The cross IR661 [IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)] appears to be an outstanding combination. Lines that are earlier maturing than IR8 and have excellent plant type and grain characteristics are being found. Aside from resistance to bacterial leaf blight, tungro, blast, and the brown planthopper, the better IR661 lines combine most of the improved traits mentioned in this and previous annual reports.

Another outstanding combination is IR8 x (CP-SLO x Nahng Mon S-4). It appears that some of these lines possess resistance to grassy stunt derived from CP-SLO. Many lines from this cross have excellent grains with clear texture. Some lines are resistant to blast under Los Baños conditions.

Several Thailand varieties have combined well with IR8 and Peta/3 x Taichung (Native) 1 lines. They include Nahng Mon S-4, Leuang Hawm, Khao Dawk Mali, Khao Tah Haeng 17, Puang Nahk 16, Gam Pai and Muey Nahng 62M. Khao Dawk Mali, a variety rated as having excellent cooking properties in Thailand, has a rather low amylose content and a relatively high gelatinization temperature. These traits have been recovered in many of the hybrid lines grown. Leuang Hawm, an aromatic Thailand variety, is being used to transfer aroma to improved plant-type lines.

Muey Nahng 62M and Gam Pai were being used to combine the waxy gene with improved plant type. Lines 14 to 20 days earlier maturing than IR8 have been selected from the Muey Nahng 62M cross. Muey Nahng 62M has been reported to be resistant to gall midge in Thailand.

Variety Pankhari 203 from India, which is highly resistant to tungro, was used as a parent in several crosses. Over 4,000 selections from Pankhari 203 crosses were grown. Pankhari 203 did not combine well with IR8 (sterility in F₁) but after one backcross to IR8, some good plant types were obtained.

Only occasional lines from the IR8/2 x Pank-

hari 203 backcross showed the low tungro infection of Pankhari 203. These lines will have to be tested further to substantiate this reaction to tungro. Both IR8 and Pankhari 203 are susceptible to grassy stunt and, in most cases, plant types of the hybrid lines were inferior to IR8.

Except for the possible tungro-resistant lines, most of the Pankhari 203 lines will be discarded as they do not show the promising plant types being obtained from several other crosses.

The variety Wagwag crossed with IR8 gave many promising plant-type lines resembling Wagwag in grain size, shape, and appearance. Further testing is needed to evaluate the disease resistance of these lines. However, they should make good parent material. Some photoperiod-sensitive lines were saved from the Wagwag crosses. Both IR8 and Wagwag have high amylose content.

Zenith continues to be a promising source of resistance to bacterial leaf blight and blast. F₃ lines of the cross IR8/2 x Zenith (IR1154) were sent to Indonesia, Ceylon, Malaysia, Thailand, and East Pakistan to determine their reaction to bacterial leaf blight as well as to low temperatures. The results have not yet been received.

Crosses between japonica varieties and IR8 may offer much promise in the development of improved varieties for sub-tropical and temperate regions. If the vigor of IR8 can be combined with the cold resistance, tough leaves, and other desirable traits of japonica varieties from temperate regions, sturdier strawed varieties capable of utilizing higher rates of nitrogen could result. The F₁ generation of the cross Yukara (japonica) x Taichung (Native) 1 was crossed with IR8, and many of the resulting F₁ plant were backcrossed to IR8.

A large number of lines from the Yukara crosses have been sent to East Pakistan, Indonesia, Ceylon, and Korea for determining cold resistance.

Stem borer-resistant, improved plant-type lines were developed by crossing IR8 and Peta/3 x Taichung (Native) 1 with TKM-6. The [Peta/3 x Taichung (Native) 1] x TKM-6 lines (IR532) were not as sturdy strawed as IR8. IR8 x TKM-6 lines (IR580) appeared to be sturdier but in some cases they had inferior grain types (opaque endosperm). It is possible that lines suitable for release as a commercial variety will be developed from the

Table 2. Yield data of lines grown in observational yield trials.

IR no.	Cross	No. of lines grown		Yield range (kg/ha)					
		Dry season	Wet season	Dry season			Wet season		
				Highest	Lowest	Mean	Highest	Lowest	Mean
IR95	Peta/2 x T(N)1	18	8	8486	6588	7537	6764	4319	5542
IR262	Peta/3 x T(N)1	25	10	8280	6604	7442	5873	4997	5435
IR400	Peta/4 x T(N)1	11	14	9457	7288	8373	6151	3541	4846
IR482	Peta/5 x T(N)1	9	12	8388	6796	7592	5640	1912	3776
IR564	Peta/6 x T(N)1	7	9	7908	6426	7167	6061	4927	5494
IR658	Peta/7 x T(N)1	4	19	7340	7181	7261	6815	2441	4628
IR305	Sigadis/2 x T(N)1	7	—	8416	7833	8125	—	—	—
IR442	(Peta/2 x TN1) x Leb Mue Nahng	47	41	8442	5653	7048	5977	1911	3944
IR506	IR8 x [B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1]	7	—	9024	6442	7733	—	—	—
IR644	IR8/2 x [B589A4- 18-1/2 x T(N)1]	11	—	9707	7938	8823	—	—	—
IR533	[(CP-SLO)/2 x Sogadis] x [Peta/3 x T(N)1]	7	—	8254	5864	7059	—	—	—
IR594	IR8 x (CP-SLO x BPI-76)	6	5	7444	6200	6822	4807	3553	4180
IR579	IR8 x Tadukan	6	—	7891	6958	7425	—	—	—
IR157	L. Yai 34 x T(N)1	16	9	9554	6698	8126	5770	4325	5048
IR481	L. Yai 34/2 x T(N)1	7	—	7994	6680	7337	—	—	—
IR160	Nahng Mon S-4 x T(N)1	38	7	8112	5720	6916	5897	3862	4880
IR480	Nahng Mon S-4/2 x T(N)1	8	3	7128	5698	6413	5341	5043	5192
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	5	4	5412	4928	5171	6202	3602	4902
IR626	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	—	6	—	—	—	6122	4377	5250
IR751	IR8/2 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	3	11	5612	5002	5307	5550	3167	4359
IR875	IR8/3 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	—	6	—	—	—	4524	2124	3324
IR577	IR8 x Sigadis	—	7	—	—	—	6037	4556	5297
IR578	IR8 x [Sigadis x T(N)1]	—	22	—	—	—	6505	3770	5138
IR580	IR8 x TKM-6	—	18	—	—	—	6349	4294	5322
IR586	IR8 x (BPI-76/2 x T. 172)	—	11	—	—	—	5249	3142	4196
IR589	IR8 x (H-105 x Dgwg)	—	17	—	—	—	5798	4137	4968
IR593	IR8 x (CP-SLO x BPI-76)	—	5	—	—	—	6038	4500	5269
IR661	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	—	13	—	—	—	6111	3553	4832
IR532	[Peta/3 x T(N)1] x TKM-6	—	19	—	—	—	5906	3382	4644
IR874	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x Nahng Mon S-4)	—	6	—	—	—	6057	3022	4540
IR8	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen	11	14	8618	6799	7709	6389	5253	5821

TKM-6 crosses.

Sukanandi, a bulu variety from Indonesia, was crossed with Taichung (Native) 1 and CP-SLO. A series of rather promising dwarf lines possessing many of the traits of bulu varieties have been developed and are being tested in several countries. Bulu varieties possess tough leaves, are cold-resistant, and do not shatter.

The IR442 lines from the cross [Peta/2 x Taichung (Native) 1] x Leb Mue Nahng, a deep-water variety from Thailand, continue to show promise. The floating trait of Leb Mue Nahng has been successfully combined with the dwarf gene in this cross. Some of the CP-SLO x Leb Mue Nahng lines (IR441) combine the floating trait with the tough leaf of CP-SLO. Lines from the cross Chianung 242/2 x Leb Mue Nahng may possess both the tough leaf and the floating trait. If this be the case they will be crossed with the better IR442 lines to further improve the strains and make them suitable for growing in areas with one-half to one meter of flood water.

Observational yield trial

Totals of 569 and 621 promising selections were grown in non-replicated, observational 6-row, 5-meter-long yield trial plots in the dry and wet seasons, respectively. Most of the selections were hybrid lines taken from pedigree rows. Data were obtained on yield, agronomic traits, disease resistance, and the milling and cooking quality of their grains. Some of the important crosses and the number of lines from each cross which were grown in the observational yield trial are listed in Table 2. The table also shows the highest and the lowest yielding lines of each cross as well as the average yield of all the lines from each cross. In the dry season 67 entries yielded over 8,000 kg/ha. IR8 was in 11 of these entries and averaged 7,709 kg/ha. In the wet season 95 entries yielded over 5,500 kg/ha. IR8 was in 14 of these entries and averaged 5,821 kg/ha.

All of the high-yielding lines were semidwarf and resembled IR8 in plant type. Some of them had excellent grains and a few showed high levels of resistance to several diseases.

In addition to the two main observational yield trials grown during the year, 392, 145, and 533 selections were grown in unreplicated plots seeded

in November 1967 and February and May, 1968, respectively. The incidence of grassy stunt in these plantings was so high and the general growing conditions so poor that reliable yield data were not obtained. Therefore, these plantings will be discontinued in 1969.

Replicated yield trials

A dry-season yield trial of 189 entries and a wet-season trial of 162 entries were grown in replicated 6-row plots 5 meters long. A 30 x 15 cm spacing with a single plant per hill was used in both experiments. The same land area was used for the two experiments which were transplanted on January 18 and July 26, using 20-day-old seedlings. A total of 120 kg/ha nitrogen was applied to the dry-season experiment and 90 kg/ha to the wet-season experiment. Basal nitrogen applications of 90 and 70 kg/ha were made on the dry- and wet-season crops. Nitrogen topdressings were made 25 and 45 days after transplanting using 30 kg/ha rates in the dry season and 20 kg/ha rates in the wet season.

In the dry-season experiment 92 entries yielded over 8,000 kg/ha, with 24 of them, including 19 IR8 line selections, producing over 9,000 kg/ha. IR8 occurred four times in the trial and averaged 9,071 kg/ha. The highest yielding entry was an IR8 line selection which gave 9,812 kg/ha, and one plot of this entry yielded over 10,000 kg/ha. Five other IRRI dwarf selections yielded over 9,000 kg/ha. IR5 and Taichung (Native) 1 yielded 8,503 kg/ha and 8,663 kg/ha, respectively (Tables 3 and 4). All the entries which yielded over 8,000 kg/ha were semidwarf improved plant-type selections.

Yields in the wet-season experiment were reduced by wind damage including lodging caused by heavy rains during the ripening period. The highest yielding entry was IR8 which occurred six times in the trial and averaged 5,900 kg/ha. Eleven other semidwarf selections from different crosses yielded over 5,500 kg/ha. Forty-nine selections yielded over 5,000 kg/ha.

The promising selections entered in the two yield trials are listed in Table 3. This table also shows the number of selections and the yields (lowest, highest, and mean) of the selections of each cross. The yields of IR8, IR5, Taichung (Native) 1 and three popular Philippine varieties are also given in the table for comparison.

The highest total production from two crops

Table 3. Yield data on lines grown in yield trial.

IR no.	Cross	No. of lines grown		Yield range (kg/ha)					
		Dry season	Wet season	Dry season			Wet season		
				Highest	Lowest	Mean	Highest	Lowest	Mean
IR593	IR8 x [(CP-SLO) x Nahng Mon S-4]	—	7				5445	3707	4576
IR160	Nahng Mon S-4 x T(N)1	4	4	8504	7289	7896	5355	4190	4773
IR589	IR8 x (H-105 x Deege-woo-gen)	—	2	—	—	—	5550	4881	5216
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	1	4	—	—	4872	5268	4970	5119
IR533	[(CP-SLO)/2 x Sigadis] x [Peta/3 x T(N)1]	—	5	—	—	—	5754	4445	5100
IR643	IR8 x (Dawn x 81B-25)	—	4	—	—	—	5233	4649	4941
IR586	IR8 x (BPI-76/2 x T. 172)	—	10	—	—	—	4404	2988	3696
IR578	IR8 x [Sigadis x T(N)1]	2	3	8706	7572	8139	5370	4387	4879
IR127	(CP-SLO) x Sigadis	—	5	—	—	—	5560	2654	4107
IR661	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	1	3	—	—	8008	5562	4111	4837
IR305	Sigadis/2 x T(N)1	12	5	9512	8133	8823	5911	3967	4939
IR667	IR8 x [Yukara x T(N)1]	—	3	—	—	—	5371	4422	4897
IR503	[Peta/3 x T(N)1] x B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1]	7	6	8301	5882	7092	5295	5323	4809
IR506	IR8 x [B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1]	8	9	9190	6082	7636	5733	3681	4707
IR253	Gam Pai/2 x T(N) 1	4	3	8951	8143	8547	4761	2706	3734
IR532	[Peta/3 x T(N)1] x TKM-6	27	19	9097	7089	8093	5240	3481	4361
IR39	Peta x T(N)1	1	1	—	—	8930	—	—	5410
IR95	Peta/2 x T(N)1	5	2	8887	7925	8406	5159	2373	3767
IR262	Peta/3 x T(N)1	5	3	8424	7603	8014	5270	3669	4470
IR400	Peta/4 x T(N)1	3	2	8577	8031	8304	4875	4059	4467
IR8							9071		5915
IR5							8505		4498
Peta							6503		2603
T(N)1							8663		4022
BPI-76-1							6724		2722
C4-63							7478		3774

was obtained with IR8 and it amounted to 15,917 kg/ha.

In addition to yield, data on agronomic traits, disease resistance, and milling and cooking quality of the grains were obtained on all the entries included in the yield trials. Detailed information on 38 entries is given in Table 4. The data on tungro reaction was obtained from greenhouse tests by

the Plant Pathology Department and represent the percentage of tungro-infected seedlings after being fed upon by viruliferous green leafhoppers. The readings for bacterial leaf blight resistance were obtained by the flag leaf puncture method and those for bacterial leaf streak were based on field observations at Los Banos. The data on blast resistance represent the seedling reaction to blast in the

Table 4. Agronomic, disease, and quality data on selected varieties and lines grown in replicated yield trials at two planting dates (December 1967 and June 1968), IRR1.

IRRI acc. no.	Variety or selection	Grain yield (kg/ha)		Maturity (day's seedling to harvest)		Mean plant height (cm)		Mean no. panicles/plant		Mean lodging (%)		Disease		Seed dormancy (%)	Milled rice yields (%)		Gelatination temperature	Amylose (%)		Protein (%)		
		Dec.	June	Dec.	June	Dec.	June	Dec.	June	Dec.	June	Dec.	June		Dec.	June		Dec.	June	Dec.	June	Dec.
		Tungro		Blast		Bact. Bact.		Head		Total		Dec.		June		Dec.		June				
105	Taichung (Native) 1	8663	4022	130	115	102	107	15	0	95	93	S	MR	S	9	55.4	72.5	L	28.8	8.5	11.8	
35	Peta	6503	2603	140	135	150	162	13	100	100	24	S	S	S	87	35.6	64.9	I	32.1	8.3	9.8	
	C4-63	7478	3774	131	123	115	129	13	0	95	66	S	MR	MR	100	64.3	71.2	H/HI	28.0	8.5	10.6	
9915	BPI-76-1 (Bicol)	6724	2722	131	125	125	140	11	50	100	89	S	S	MR	76	66.1	70.6	HI	29.0	8.4	11.8	
10321	IR5	8505	4775	144	134	120	130	13	60	100	75	S	S	MR	89	53.8	69.6	HI/I	31.1	9.2	9.2	
	IR5-81-3-2-3, Peta x Tangkai Rotan	8114	4555	132	130	110	129	13	0	30	45	S	R	S	100	71.0	73.2	I	31.4	7.8	9.7	
10320	IR8	9071	5919	135	127	85	99	13	0	0	71	S	S	S	80	52.8	72.1	L	31.3	9.6	9.6	
	IR6-1-3-1, Siam 29 x Deep-geo-woo-gen	6946	3283	128	117	103	111	14	0	66	86	S	S	R	67	61.7	71.2	L	30.1	8.9	12.0	
	IR6-156-3-3	7734	3702	120	123	92	106	13	0	75	96	S	S	MR	40	46.7	71.8	L	29.0	9.7	11.5	
	IR39-14, Peta x T(N)1	8792	5381	132	123	90	99	14	0	0	86	S	S	MR	60	57.8	72.8	I	29.4	8.4	10.5	
	IR95-42-11-2-2, Peta/2 x T(N)1	8413	5159	145	132	105	117	14	85	100	42	S	S	S	100	53.6	74.6	I	30.6	9.7	9.7	
	IR95-43-2-4	7560	2373	153	134	105	103	15	0	100	50	S	S	MR	95	42.0	71.5	I	27.0	9.2	12.6	
	IR262-43-9-11, Peta/3 x T(N)1	8424	3930	130	114	85	96	14	0	100	44	S	S	R	100	50.1	74.2	I/L	28.8	7.5	10.4	
	IR400-5-12-10-2, Peta/4 x T(N)1	8296	4059	126	112	86	97	16	0	10	41	S	S	R	95	41.4	72.4	L	28.8	8.6	10.3	
	IR400-2-5-3-3-2	8577	4875	145	137	95	99	13	0	13	48	S	S	MR	100	56.3	68.2	I	13.5	8.1	9.8	
	IR127-80-1-10 (CP231 x SLO-17) x Sigadis	8780	5560	125	123	97	115	11	0	0	17.0	R	HR	MR	10	63.2	72.8	H	21.2	10.0	10.0	
	IR140-136 (CP231 x SLO-17) x Mas	6396	4173	125	123	98	120	12	0	7	28	S	R	MR	82	63.0	70.8	H	22.4	8.4	9.1	
	IR253-16-1-1-2 Gam Pai/2 x T(N)1	8463	2706	131	119	115	128	13	50	100	36	S	S	MR	91	46.9	69.1	I	Waxy	8.1	11.5	
	IR253-4-1-2-1	7525	4463	132	129	125	103	12	0	70	31	S	S	R	93	48.6	74.7	I	Waxy	10.4	10.4	
	IR305-3-17-1-3	8794	3967	136	123	87	102	16	0	0	33	MR	S	R	67	50.9	73.4	L	29.4	8.5	10.5	
	IR305-4-12-1-3	8432	5911	137	127	83	93	17	0	0	90	R	MR	R	45	66.4	75.4	L	29.4	8.3	10.4	
	IR305-4-20-3-3	9212	4995	136	125	88	103	16	0	0	86	MRS	R	R	68	49.7	74.6	L	29.7	9.2	11.3	
	IR532E239 [Peta/3xT(N)1]xTKM-6	4534		119		103	17		100	33		MR	S	R	94	49.7	71.2	I	30.2	10.4	10.4	
	IR532E257	4122		119		106	13		85	53		MR	S	R	81	42.5	69.8	I	28.0	10.6	10.6	
	IR532E576	5240		127		114	15		60	64		MR	MR	R	81	56.3	71.4	I	30.9	9.2	9.2	
	IR578-84-5	8706	5370	134	125	96	106	14	0	0	61	R	S	R	59	50.2	74.0	I/L	30.0	9.5	9.9	
	IR8 x [Sigadis x T(N)1]																					

blast nursery. Brown rice grains from both crop seasons were analyzed for protein content by the Cereal Chemistry Department.

Seed Purification and Multiplication

In addition to producing breeder seed of IR8 and IR5 in the dry season, several promising selections were planted for seed multiplication. Eighteen of these selections came from [Peta/3 x Taichung (Native) 1] x TKM-6 cross (IR532), four from Nahng Mon S-4 x Taichung (Native) 1 (IR160) and one each from Gam Pai/2 x Taichung (Native) 1 (IR253), CP-SLO x Mas (IR140), BPI-76 x (CP-SLO x Peta) (IR298), Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 (IR39), Peta/2 x Taichung (Native) 1 (IR95), and Peta/4 x Taichung (Native) 1 (IR400). The area planted to each selection varied from one-sixteenth to one-fourth of a hectare. These plantings provided an opportunity to see the performance of these selections under field conditions. Moreover, enough seed was available at the end of the season for testing the selected lines of this group on a large scale.

Seven of the IR532 lines, namely, IR532-1-218, IR532E233, IR532E239, IR532E257, IR532E420, IR532E423, and IR532E576, were considered promising and were included in the multiplication program in the wet season. Six additional lines of this cross – IR532-1-33, IR532E160, IR532E210, IR532E213, IR532E230 and IR532E527 – were included in this program. At least one-fourth of a hectare was planted to each of these 13 selections, and progeny-row plots of each of these lines were grown to start the seed purification program. Head row blocks of three waxy lines from Gam Pai/2 x Taichung (Native) 1, namely, IR253-16-1-2, IR253-16-1-1-2, and IR253-4-1-2-1, were grown along with a bulk seed increase. One-tenth to one-twelfth of a hectare was planted with bulk seed only of the following selections:

IR160-25-1-1, Nahng Mon S-4 x Taichung (Native) 1
IR160-44-1-2, Nahng Mon S-4 x Taichung (Native) 1
IR480-5-9-3-3, Nahng Mon S-4/2 x Taichung (Native) 1
IR140-136, (CP231 x SLO-17) x Mas
IR127-80-3-6-1, (CP231 x SLO-17) x Sigadis
IR127-80-1-10, (CP231 x SLO-17) x Sigadis
IR286-1-8-2-1, Peta x [Dawn x Taichung (Native) 1]
IR506-110-2-1, IR8 x [B589A4-18-1/2 x Taichung (Native) 1]
IR5-81-3-3-3, Peta x Tangkai Rotan

International Cooperative Variety Testing Program

An important part of the international program of the Institute is the supplying of seeds of breeding lines and varieties requested by cooperators and interested organizations and individuals in the various rice-growing countries.

During the year, over 12,000 samples of seeds of Institute breeding lines were sent to 183 organizations and individuals in 79 countries. A large number of breeding lines were sent to co-operators in Burma, Ceylon, Colombia, India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, and Pakistan. IRRI rice breeders maintain close cooperation with rice breeders in each of these countries through a free exchange of ideas and breeding materials. Rice breeders from many countries who come to the Institute as research fellows and scholars select lines from Institute breeding nurseries and yield trial plots and take the materials home with them at the conclusion of their training programs. Frequently, they make crosses between the varieties from their home countries and Institute breeding lines during their training program and take the F_1 and F_2 seeds with them.

A large collection of varieties and lines were sent to various cooperating countries to determine their adaptability, resistance to various diseases, low temperatures and/or performance under conditions of deep water. During the year, several hundred lines including those from the IR8/2 x Zenith cross were sent to East Pakistan, Ceylon, Malaysia, and Indonesia to determine their reaction to bacterial leaf blight. Over 800 lines were sent to Thailand to test their resistance to the tungro virus under field conditions in that country.

A nursery of 154 Institute breeding lines from 13 different crosses in which one of the parents was blast-resistant was prepared. The lines included in this nursery had been found to be resistant under Los Baños conditions. Twelve resistant parent varieties and nine breeding lines from Thailand were also included in the nursery. Seed samples of the lines and varieties from this nursery were sent to Ceylon, Colombia, Guyana, India, Indonesia, East Pakistan, and Thailand. These lines and varieties have been planted in these countries and blast readings will be taken. Since

these countries presumably have different races of blast fungus, the reaction of the lines and varieties to races different from those prevalent at Los Banos will be determined. It is hoped that improved plant-type lines with a broad spectrum of resistance to blast will be detected.

Breeding for High Protein Content

The breeding program aimed at evolving high-yielding varieties with high protein content is being carried out under a grant to the Institute from the National Institute of Health, U.S.A. The F₂ and F₃ generations of the hybrid populations of crosses between IR8 and six high-protein varieties were grown in 1968. Brown and milled rice grains from 1,290 individual F₃ plants were saved for analysis by the Cereal Chemistry Department. These plants were selected from 253 F₃ lines, most of which showed high protein content in the previous generation. As shown in Table 5, the F₃ plants grown from high-protein F₂ plants (11 percent or above) averaged 11.9 percent while F₃ plants produced from low-protein F₂ plants (10 percent or below) averaged 8.8 percent in protein content. These figures represent only a part of the

1,290 plants saved as the rest of the data is still being analyzed. As indicated in Table 6, much of the increase in protein content is retained in the milled rice.

The yield potential of these lines is not known. Most of the plants saved were from rows carrying the semidwarf trait of IR8. At least some of the lines showing higher than average protein content were rated as having reasonably good plant-type.

The protein content of most of the entries grown in replicated yield trials and in observational yield trials was also determined. A comparison of data from the wet and dry season crops showed that protein content was lower during the dry season. The average yields and protein content of the hybrid lines of four crosses are summarized in Table 7. Most of these lines were high-yielding and averaged over 9 percent protein. Sixty-six individual good plant-type Peta x Taichung (Native) 1 backcross lines with a mean yield of 5,001 kg/ha averaged 9.1 percent in protein content (Table 8). The average protein content of 30 individual plots yielding over 5,500 kg/ha was 9.9 percent and of 7 plots yielding over 6,000 kg/ha, 10.2 percent.

Rough rice samples from a variety-fertilizer experiment conducted at The Maligaya Rice

Table 5. Protein content of F₃ and F₄ brown rice grains from IR8 x high-protein varieties.*

Cross	Protein content (wet basis)							
	11% or over in F ₃ brown rice grains				10% or below in brown rice grains			
	F ₃ grains		F ₄ grains		F ₃ grains		F ₄ grains	
No. of plants	Ave. protein content (%)	No. of plants	Ave. protein content (%)	No. of plants	Ave. protein content (%)	No. of plants	Ave. protein content (%)	
IR8 x Rikuto Norin 20	9	12.1	30	12.1	7	7.8	40	8.6
IR8 x Omirt 39	9	11.7	20	11.6	9	7.5	25	8.7
IR8 x Santo	1	11.2	6	12.4	7	7.1	39	8.7
IR8 x Chow Sung	10	11.6	50	11.9	4	7.1	29	9.0
IR8 x Crythroceros								
Korn.	12	11.3	43	11.7	5	8.1	3	9.0
IR8 x Chok-jye-bi-chal	12	13.1	88	11.9	6	7.4	33	9.2
Average		11.8		11.9		7.5		8.8
Total	53		237		38		169	

* The protein content of the parent variety check rows were: IR8, 7.8 (dry season) and 8.7 (wet season); Rikuto Norin 20, 9.5 and 12.9; Omirt 39, 9.8 and 11.4; Santo, 8.8 and 13.1; Chow Sung, 9.8 and 10.8; Crythroceros Korn., 9.7 and 12.2; and Chok-jye-bi-chal, 10.0 and 14.5.

Table 6. Comparative protein content of brown and milled rice of F₃ and F₄ caryopsis from crossed plants of IR8 x high-protein varieties.

	Protein content (% wet basis)		
	F ₃ caryopsis	F ₄ caryopsis	
		Brown rice	Brown rice
High-protein plants (11% or over)	11.8	11.9	10.9
Low-protein plants (10% or below)	7.5	8.8	8.3
IR8		8.7	8.1

Table 7. Average yield and protein content (wet basis) of hybrid lines, IRR1, 1968 wet season (observational yield trial).*

IR No.	Cross	Average		
		No. of lines	Yield (kg/ha)	Protein content
IR532	[Peta/3 x T(N)1] x TKM-6	19	4284	10.3
IR580	IR8 x TKM-6	18	5325	9.1
IR751	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	11	4598	10.9
IR661	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	13	4977	8.8

* 30 plots averaging over 5,500 kg/ha averaged 9.9% protein (range 8.5-11.3%).
7 plots averaging over 6,000 kg/ha averaged 10.2% protein (range 9.4-11.0%).

Experiment and Training Center in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, by the Agronomy Department was milled by the Varietal Improvement Department and analyzed for protein content by the Cereal Chemistry Department. The protein content of both the brown and milled rice of four improved varieties (IR8, IR5, IR532E576 and C4-63) and Peta increased substantially as the fertilizer rates increased (Table 9). Likewise, head and total milled rice yields tended to increase with higher levels of nitrogen.

Table 8. Average yield and protein content (wet basis) of hybrid lines IRR1, 1968 wet season (observational yield trial).

IR No.	Cross	Average		
		No. of lines	Yield (kg/ha)	Protein content
IR265	Ch. 242/2 x (PI 215936 x Mo. R-500)	12	4509	8.2
IR95	Peta/2 x T(N)1	8	5308	9.3
IR262	Peta/3 x T(N)1	10	5555	8.9
IR400	Peta/4 x T(N)1	14	5266	9.3
IR482	Peta/5 x T(N)1	7	4461	8.9
IR564	Peta/6 x T(N)1	9	5450	9.3
IR658	Peta/7 x T(N)1	18	5435	8.9

Breeding Program with TKM-6

The variety TKM-6 from India was found to be highly resistant to stem borers by Institute entomologists, and resistant to bacterial leaf blight and the tungro virus by Institute plant pathologists. Because of its insect and disease resistance and good grain quality, TKM-6 was considered a potentially good parent for the breeding program. In late 1965, plant breeders crossed TKM-6 with a dwarf selection from Peta/3 x Taichung (Native) 1. An F₂ population was grown in March 1966 and selected plants were saved to form an F₃ bulk population which was planted in November 1966. A total of 255 promising plants were selected from this F₃ bulk population and planted to F₄ pedigree rows in May 1967. The F₅ and F₆ pedigree lines were grown in pedigree nurseries planted in November 1967 and May 1968. The selection for plant type, disease reaction, grain quality, and maturity date was continued.

A part of the hybrid material emanating from the above cross was also evaluated cooperatively by the Entomology Department. The entomologists made many panicle selections from the F₃ bulk populations grown by the Varietal Improvement Department and grew several F₄ bulk populations in March 1967. The over 600 F₅ plant selections made from these populations were planted in August 1967 in two-row plots which were replicated twice. One replication was pro-

Table 9. Protein content (wet basis) of brown and milled rice, rough rice and milling yields from a fertilizer experiment, Maligays Center, 1968 wet season.

Variety	Nitrogen rate (kg/ha)					
	0	30	60	90	120	150
Improved varieties*						
Protein content						
Brown	7.09	7.52	8.01	8.36	8.47	9.48
Milled	6.22	6.58	7.25	7.43	7.74	8.47
Rough rice, kg/ha	3854	4406	5180	5206	5710	5337
Head rice, kg/ha	2090	2469	2989	3083	3438	3261
Total milled rice, kg/ha	2666	3061	3634	3629	4042	3777
Peta						
Protein content						
Brown	7.07	7.40	8.10	8.70	8.87	8.03
Milled	6.20	6.70	6.65	7.50	7.80	7.63
Rough rice, kg/ha	4110	4334	4280	4572	4539	4745
Head rice, kg/ha	2085	2306	2455	2773	2728	2918
Total milled rice, kg/ha	2879	3022	3019	3200	3256	3386

* Average of four varieties (IR8, IR5, C4-63 and IR532E576).

tected with insecticides while the other was not. In the unprotected plots, entomologists classified the selections as to the degree of stem borer resistance, while in the protected plots, plant breeders classified the lines as to plant type, disease reaction, and other agronomic traits. Sixteen promising lines good plant type and of a low level of stem borer infestation were harvested and then grown as a part of the seed multiplication program. Single plant selections from the above pedigree nursery were grown in January 1968 in F₆ pedigree rows in two replication – one protected, and the other unprotected. Again, the material was studied jointly by the entomologists and plant breeders and selections from this nursery numbering 621 were grown in the pedigree nursery of the Varietal Improvement Department in June 1968. All lines were then evaluated for grain dormancy, threshability, and resistance to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, blast, and the tungro virus. Data on grain texture, size and shape, milling recovery, amylose content and gelatinization temperature were also obtained.

The yielding ability of the lines of this cross was tested in the observational and replicated yield

trials grown in December 1967 and June 1968. Twenty-seven lines, 17 from the Entomology Department nursery and 10 from the Varietal Improvement Department nursery, were included in the dry-season yield trial. At least four lines yielded as well as IR8. The wet-season yield trial planted in June 1968 included 19 lines from this cross. The average yield of these lines was much lower than those of IR8 and other high-yielding entries (Table 3) mainly because most of the lines lodged badly.

During the 1968 dry season, lines of this cross which were included in the seed multiplication program were evaluated on a field scale. The seeds of three of the more promising lines, namely IR532E239, IR532E257 and IR532E576, were distributed to cooperators of the Philippine Agricultural Productivity Commission for testing in 13 provinces of the Philippines during the wet season. The Agronomy Department carried out fertility trials with these lines at four locations in the Philippines during the 1968 wet season. The Varietal Improvement Department again multiplied the seeds in the 1968 wet season and at the end of that season enough seeds were available for

sending to other countries for testing under local conditions. Seeds of IR532E576 which appeared to be one of the best lines were sent to Burma, Colombia, Ceylon, India, Indonesia, and Pakistan for large-scale testing. Small samples of this selection have been sent to many other countries. At the end of the 1969 dry season, data on the international performance of IR532E576 will become available. Meanwhile, the purification of seed of several lines which was started in the 1968 wet season is being continued; if any of the lines are recommended for cultivation, breeder's seed will be made available.

The promising lines of this cross have the following main features: They are moderately resistant to bacterial and virus diseases, and some lines are resistant to blast under Los Banos conditions. Their level of resistance to stem borers is not as high as that of TKM-6 but is considerably better than that of the other commonly cultivated varieties. They have fine grains of clear texture with high amylose content and are dry cooking. Their maturity period varies from 20 to 25 days earlier to a few days later than that of IR8. Most of them have good plant types with good early vegetative vigor. However, all of them have weak stems and may lodge with heavy nitrogen fertilization.

IR580, a cross between IR8 and TKM-6, was subsequently handled in the same manner. The lines of this cross have somewhat sturdier stems but the grain quality is generally poor.

Genetic and Cytogenetic Studies

Allelic relationships of dwarfs and semidwarfs

In the Institute's breeding program, the recessive gene in Taiwan's semidwarf varieties [Dee-geo-woo-gen, I-geo-tze and Taichung (Native) 1] has served as the principal source of short plant stature. Another promising source of semidwarfism came from the CP231 x SLO-17 selections (Acc. 6993 and sister lines). Samples of several other sources of semidwarfism and dwarfism were taken from the Institute's world collection in an attempt to broaden the genetic base of potential breeding material. The following 10 short-statured lines were included in this genetic study.

Strain	Culm length (cm)	Origin	Parentage
Daikoku dwarf (d_1)	28	Japan	
Ai-yeh-lu dwarf	35	China	
Fanny semidwarf	47	France	
FF36	43	Taiwan	[(Chianung 242 x Taichung (Native) 1) x Tainan 3]
IR273	45	IRRI	(CP231 x SLO-17) / 2 x Taichung (Native) 1 F ₄
Intermediate dwarf	69	U.S.	
Long-grain dwarf	66	U.S.	
Taichung (Native) 1	58	Taiwan	Dee-gwo-woo-gen x Tsai-yuan-chung
IR8	63	IRRI	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen
Acc. 6993	67	U.S.	CP231 x SLO-17

The 10 short-statured selections were intercrossed. Each line was also crossed with two tall tropical varieties, BPI-76-1 and Peta.

Among the F₁ hybrids and parents grown in the 1967 wet season, most of the F₁ plants originating from dwarf x dwarf, dwarf x semidwarf, and semidwarf x semidwarf crosses exceeded in height the tall parent involved in the crosses. But only a few of these hybrids were almost as tall as the tall tropical varieties. On the other hand, the crosses between a tall parent and a short-statured line produced F₁ hybrids which were shorter than the tall parent, indicating the incomplete dominance of tallness.

Sixty-four F₂ populations and their parents were grown in the 1968 dry season. About 200 plants were included in each F₂ sample. The cool temperatures which prevailed in the first part of the crop season adversely affected the full expression of the height genes. For instance, the average culm length of Peta plants reached only 114 cm, while the culm length of BPI-76-1 was only 83 cm.

From crosses among the dwarfs and semidwarfs, the F₂ distributions indicate that the following groups of strains can be recognized as having non-allelic gene or genes for short stature.

1. Daikoku dwarf and Ai-yeh-lu dwarf.
2. Fanny semidwarf.
3. Intermediate semidwarf and Long-grain semidwarf.
4. Accession 6993 and IR273.
5. FF36, Taichung (Native) 1, IR8 and IR273.

The F₂ data from dwarf x tall and semidwarf x tall crosses indicate that:

1. The dwarf stature in Daikoku and Ai-yeh-lu lines is controlled mainly by a single recessive gene and probably involves genes of the modifying type (modifiers).

2. Semidwarfism in the Fanny strain is conditioned by genes of a polygenic-additive nature.

3. The intermediate and long-grain semidwarfs carry a number of recessive alleles for short stature.

4. FF36 has the recessive gene from Taichung (Native) 1 (originally from Dee-geo-woo-gen) and other modifiers for short height. This recessive gene is also present in IR8.

5. The IR273 line combines the polygenic-additive genes from Acc. 6993 and the recessive gene from Taichung (Native) 1.

In addition to the above generalized postulates, most of the F₂ populations from dwarf x dwarf and dwarf x semidwarf crosses involving non-allelic genes did not produce segregates which were as tall as Peta. On the other hand, the dwarf x semidwarf crosses frequently yielded extremely short F₂ progenies. Similarly, the semidwarf x semidwarf crosses involving non-allelic genes produced very few tall segregates. Crosses involving the intermediate and long-grain semidwarfs frequently produced a few F₂ plants which belong to the dwarf class.

In contrast to the above, crosses between Peta and the Ai-yeh-lu dwarf or either one of the U.S. semidwarfs (intermediate or long-grain) produced segregates which were taller than Peta. The above three short-statured selections tended to produce relatively taller segregates in their crosses with other semidwarfs.

The diverse F₂ distributions found in the 64 crosses suggest that:

1. Tall plant height is generally dominant over short stature, but the dominance is incomplete in nearly all cases.

2. A complex of height genes is involved in the crosses. These genes vary in their degree of dominance, magnitude of effect, and level of heritability. The modifiers also differ in the direction of effects (enhancing or depressing).

3. The Fanny semidwarf, FF36, Acc. 6993 and Taichung (Native) 1, appear to have in common several negative modifiers (for short stature) which

could explain the failure to recover tall segregates in their F₂ samples.

4. The expression of height genes could be markedly affected by the different genes for maturity which were also segregating in these crosses, especially those genes for extreme earliness carried by the dwarfs and some of the semidwarfs.

Inheritance of photoperiod sensitivity

Observations made on F₂ samples of three photoperiod-sensitive x sensitive crosses were given in the 1967 Annual Report. The remaining three crosses from this series were planted in late May under natural daylength and they involved Podiwi-A (8) of Ceylon as the common parent. The other parents were BPI-76, Siam 29 and Raminad Strain 3. The four parents were also included in the field planting.

The mean duration from seeding to heading ranged among the parents from 133 days for BPI-76, 166 days for Siam 29, 184 days for Raminad Strain 3, and 188 days for Podiwi-A (8). The parental populations of about 100 plants each headed within a period of 6 to 8 days.

The three F₂ populations showed different distribution curves but indicated three common features.

1. All of the F₂ plants could be classified as photoperiod-sensitive under a natural daylength.

2. The total range of F₂ distribution was related to the magnitude of difference between the parents concerned.

3. Only a few F₂ plants flowered later than the Podiwi parent, whereas the earliest F₂ plants headed at the same time as BPI-76.

The above observations are similar to those made on the 1967 wet-season crop. The field data again suggest that the major photoperiod-sensitivity gene (*Se*) in the four parents may belong to a multiple allelic series or a complex locus. In order to have a fuller description of the genes concerned, it appears necessary to use controlled photoperiods and vegetative tillers of the same plant so that concurrent determination of genes controlling the components of photoperiod sensitivity (the critical photoperiod and the optimum photoperiod) could be made.

Cytological study of sterility in indica x indica and indica x bulu hybrids*

Studies on the sterility of intervarietal crosses were continued in 1968. Twelve indica x indica, eight indica x bulu, and one bulu x bulu crosses involving 10 indica and 2 bulu varieties were used. The spikelet fertility of the parent varieties ranged from 51.5 percent in TKM-6 to 90.3 percent in IR8. Among the F₁ hybrids, fertility ranged from 21.1 percent in Boegi imba x Basmati 370 to 85.1 percent in Pankhari 203 x Basmati 370.

All the parent varieties showed essentially normal chromosome behavior at meiosis except for a low frequency of univalents (0.9 to 2.8%) in three parent varieties, 2 IR's (1.5%), laggards (1.5%), and a bridge (1.5%) in three other varieties.

The hybrids exhibited a wide range of chromosomal aberrations.

At diakinesis and metaphase I, the following abnormalities with their corresponding frequency were observed in some of the hybrids: 1 to 2 IV's (0.3-4.2%), 2 to 4 I's (0.2-4.3%), a ring-of-four chromosomes (0.3-0.7%), 2 III's (0.8%), 1 III + 1 I (0.2%-1.0%) and a persistent nucleolus at metaphase I (0.2%). At anaphase I and telophase I, laggards (0.4-2.6%), a bridge without fragment

(0.2-0.9%), and a bridge with fragment (1.0%) were also observed in some hybrids.

There was no significant difference in kind and frequency of the abnormalities observed between the indica x indica and indica x bulu hybrids. Although some abnormalities observed in the hybrids were not found in the parents, their frequency was too low to account for the observed sterility. Furthermore, there was no association between sterility and kind or frequency of abnormalities observed, e.g., the most sterile hybrids had only 2.8 and 0.6 percent abnormalities at diakinesis – metaphase I and anaphase I – telophase I, respectively. The most fertile hybrids had 2.3 and 0.6 percent abnormalities at the same stages. The data suggest that sterility in indica x indica and indica x bulu hybrids may not be due to chromosomal aberrations alone. These observations and conclusions are similar to those on the indica x japonica hybrids. As in the indica x japonica hybrid, sterility could be attributed to more complex factors such as genic imbalance in addition to chromosomal aberrations.

* A cooperative project between IRRI and the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines.

Plant Pathology

*The broad spectrum of resistance to the blast disease of several rice varieties was confirmed by additional tests in the Philippines and in various countries participating in the International Blast Nursery program. Experiments were initiated to determine whether rice varieties possess horizontal (field) resistance to blast. Many more new pathogenic races of the fungus were characterized in the Philippines, and the presence of many and new races in the Institute blast nursery was demonstrated. These and other experiments substantiated the concept that great variability exists in *Pyricularia oryzae*.*

The varietal resistance to the bacterial blight disease of selected varieties was further investigated. Experiments showed that bacterial blight is not transmitted through seed. Many varieties were found resistant to the bacterial streak disease. Information was also gathered on the virulence of the bacterial strains, bacteriophages, host range, etc. of bacterial streak.

*Two new vectors which transmit the tungro virus were found. The morphological features of the virus transmitters and non-transmitters of both *Nephotettix apicalis* and *Nephotettix impiciceps* were studied in detail. The extensive host range of tungro virus was also determined, with the wild rices appearing to be perhaps the most important virus reservoir during the off-season. Strains or biotypes of the tungro virus vector which can persist and develop on resistant varieties were isolated. Resistance to the tungro virus seemed to be distinct at the seedling and mature plant stages of rice varieties.*

A mass screening method for grassy stunt disease was developed, and several thousand varieties and breeding lines were tested, with not one proving to be highly resistant. The transmission of grassy stunt was investigated in detail.

Fig. 1. Some resistant and susceptible varieties from the International Blast Nurseries, 1963-1968.

Rice Blast Disease

Varietal resistance

The screening for resistance to the rice blast disease in the International Uniform Blast Nurseries (IBN) during the last several years has so far yielded 159 test results in 24 countries. This is the first time that rice varieties have been tested over such a wide geographic area and for many seasons, and it has made possible a more comprehensive assessment of varietal reaction to the blast disease. The test varieties showed a full range of reaction from very resistant to very susceptible. Some showed a broad spectrum of resistance, susceptible only in very few of the tests, while others showed only a few resistant reactions.

Of the first set of 258 varieties tested in the IBN, 18 were found to be most resistant and 2 most susceptible (Fig. 1). These resistant varieties are generally considered to be the most useful available sources of resistance to blast. The data in Fig. 1, as well as results of numerous artificial inoculations made in Japan, the United States, and the Philippines showed the variety Tetep to be the most resistant. Many other varieties are resistant in specific countries or geographic regions of Asia, such as Japan-Korea, Southeast Asia, and India-Pakistan.*

A second set of 321 varieties (referred to as "BRWCV Set" in the 1967 Annual Report) selected from over 8,000 entries in the Institute blast nursery has so far been subjected to 49 tests in 10 countries. Some of those considered as highly resistant are also listed in Fig. 1. This set of varieties will be tested further in the IBN.

Since even the most resistant varieties were susceptible in one or more readings, it was generally assumed that resistance in these varieties was due to major genes. The IBN data are not detailed enough to indicate whether these varieties also possess some type of horizontal (field) resistance. For instance, the varieties in the blast nurseries with partly dead leaves are usually considered susceptible. This susceptibility, however, may have resulted from numerous type 3 lesions due to the very heavy inoculum in the nurseries. The type 3 reaction may be considered as a type of horizontal resistance in the field. Therefore, some of the

highly resistant varieties may also have some type of field resistance.

Horizontal (non-race-specific or field) resistance to blast

When varietal resistance is due to major genes and when a pathogenic race exists which can heavily infect the variety, it is feared that such resistance will break down after the variety has been extensively cultivated. It also was shown recently that the blast fungus is highly variable and can produce new races with high frequency. Experiments were therefore initiated to seek the horizontal or non-race-specific type of resistance, with which a certain degree of resistance is maintained regardless of the pathogenic races. However, as horizontal resistance is polygenic, intangible, and difficult to assess in most cases, separation of field resistance from major gene resistance usually requires repeated tests over a long period and in various geographic areas. An international cooperative study should prove useful.

There are two types of varietal reaction to blast which are tangible and may be considered as field resistance: (1) The small-lesion type (type 3), which is common in the blast nursery. This type of lesion produces few conidia (estimated at 15 to 50 each day for a few days) as compared to many in large lesions (4,000 - 6,000 each day for more than 2 weeks, Fig. 2). (2) The few-lesion type, in which typical lesions (type 4) are produced, but their number on each seedling is small in contrast to the 50 to 100 or more lesions on susceptible varieties.

The small-lesion type of reaction, however, is in most cases controlled by major genes, as many of the varieties produce large lesions and become susceptible in subsequent tests. Whether varieties possess such reaction but are non-race-specific, i.e., field-resistant, can only be determined by repeated tests over wide geographic areas.

The few-lesion type of reaction in many cases is due to the low population of the specific race(s) present in the nursery. Many varieties reacted this way in the early blast nursery tests but became very susceptible in the later tests as the population of the specific race(s) increased. To determine

* The results are published in detail in the *International Rice Commission Newsletter* 13 (3): 22-30, 15 (3): 1-10, 17 (in press).

Fig. 2. Conidia released from a typical blast lesion collected in one night on agar media.

whether this type of reaction is due to a low population of pathogenic race(s) or to field resistance, the fungus on these few lesions may be isolated and cultured to increase the conidial population, and then artificially inoculated on the varieties. If the variety consistently produces only a few lesions in spite of repeated inoculations, it may possess field resistance.

Small-lesion type of resistance. A group of 441 varieties showing the small-lesion type of reaction in the early tests in the blast nursery was again tested. After the first repeated test, only 301 varieties remained resistant (type 3 or better). Of this total, 265 (there were not enough seeds for the other 36) were again tested and 218 remained resistant. These varieties will be tested further in the IRRI blast nursery, in other cooperative nurseries in the Philippines and, in the near future, in the International Blast Nursery. Unless extensively tested, there is no way of determining whether this reaction (Type 3) can be attributed to major genes or to field resistance.

Small number of lesions by artificial inoculation. Many varieties showing typical but few

lesions were found in the blast nursery. The fungi in these leaf lesions were isolated, cultured, and artificially inoculated with heavy inoculum to the varieties at the seedling stage. Variety Khao-teh-haeng 17 (susceptible to most races known in the Philippines) was included in each inoculation for comparison. Preliminary results (Fig. 3,A) seemed to show that some of these varieties have fewer lesions than Khao-teh-haeng 17, although the fungi were isolated from them. Two of these varieties, however, have as many lesions as Khao-teh-haeng 17. Apparently, this scarcity of lesions in the blast nursery was due to the low population of the races which attacked the two varieties. It is also interesting to note that the varieties with fewer lesions were also those which were found to be more resistant in the IBN tests. Whether these varieties also possess this few-lesion type of field resistance is yet to be confirmed.

In another set of experiments, the varieties Tetep and Khao-teh-haeng 17 were included in the artificial inoculations with the fungus isolated from the other varieties. Again, in many cases, more lesions were found on Khao-teh-haeng 17

Fig. 3.A. Numbers of blast lesions developed by artificial inoculation on leaves of variety Khao-teh-haeng 17 (KTH 17) and on those of original varieties, from which the fungus was isolated.

than on the original varieties; in some cases, the original varieties showed as many lesions as Khao-teh-haeng 17. In all cases, however, Tetep had the fewest lesions (Fig. 3,B), and these were mostly of type 3. As mentioned earlier, Tetep is the most resistant variety found so far in the IBN. More significant differences were found by comparing the number of type 4 lesions found among the varieties.

When varieties produce only a few lesions even with the fungus isolated from them, i.e., pathogenic to the varieties, and many lesions are produced on the susceptible control variety, Khao-teh-haeng 17, in the same inoculation, it is possible that these varieties possess some kind of field resistance. Previous studies at the Institute have shown that in a culture, even that from a single conidium, several races may be present. Some of the races may not infect the varieties from which the culture originated, hence, the lesions would be few. Whether these varieties possess some kind of field resistance, whether they will be resistant in

the field where the inoculum occurs repeatedly, and whether this type of resistance in leaves also exists in panicles, require further investigation. The reasons for the varying number of lesions on Khao-teh-haeng 17 in different inoculations are not definitely known. In some cases, the variability was due to the concentration of the conidial suspension used in the inoculation since some isolates produced fewer conidia in culture although, in most of the cases, this was adjusted to a similar concentration. Also, it might have been partly due to the fluctuating environmental conditions in the greenhouse which cannot adequately be controlled.

Small number of lesions in blast nursery. Eight rice varieties from the blast nursery were selected to study the rate of blast disease development by counting the number of lesions observed every other day on the seedlings in 50-cm rows from the time the disease first appeared. The susceptible check variety, Tjeremas, was planted in parallel 10

Fig. 3.B. Numbers of blast lesions (type 3 and 4) developed by artificial inoculation at the same times on leaves of varieties Khao-teh-haeng 17, on Tetep, and on the original varieties from which the fungus was isolated.

Fig. 3.C. Number of blast lesions observed on four more resistant varieties and their neighboring susceptible checks in blast nursery (100 seedlings).

cm away from each of the varieties for comparison. The results showed that all the 8 selected resistant varieties had much fewer lesions than the neighboring check variety. The data from four of the eight varieties together with the check variety are plotted in Fig. 3.C to illustrate these differences in lesion number. The number of lesions (both type 3 and type 4) was counted on the basis of 100 seedlings.

Superficially, it appears as if the eight varieties have considerable field resistance. However, the small number of lesions on the varieties was prob-

ably the result of the inability of many of the races present in the blast nursery to infect these varieties (major gene resistance). Since there are numerous fungus races and almost all the rice varieties have resistance to a few or many of them, it is difficult to separate horizontal resistance from resistance due to major genes. Nevertheless, these resistant varieties greatly reduce the effective inoculum, thus minimizing disease epidemics.

Pathogenic races in the IRRI blast nursery

It is generally assumed that several races of the blast fungus may be present in rice fields. However, the number of these races, their relative population, seasonal changes, etc. have not been investigated in detail. A study of these aspects was conducted with samples collected from the Institute blast nursery. A total of 363 samples was collected monthly and monoconidial cultures were obtained during a period of 21 months. Each isolate was inoculated to 8 international and 12 Philippine differential varieties so that both the international race groups and the Philippine races to which they belong could be identified. The 363 isolates were differentiated into 37 international race groups, of which 22 were new. Of the 60 Philippine races, 34 were new. More races would have been detected had more samples been taken.

The number of races, as indicated by the samples, varied from 3 to 14 each month with an average of about 9. The composition of races differed each month, and the race groups in any two months were not similar. The relative population of the races detected in each month also varied; a race may have a high frequency (percentage of total isolates) in one month but a low one in other months. A few races were present in most of the months, such as IA-109 (20 in 21 months) and P-8 (19 in 21 months), and showed high frequency; hence they were considered as the prevailing or major races. Other races occurred only periodically, and many were detected only once during the entire period. These changes are illustrated in Fig. 4.

The relatively large number of races detected was probably due to the presence of a very susceptible variety and of several hundred other varieties in the blast nursery. We believe that most of the new races are being produced by the fungus

Fig. 4. Races of *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. detected in IRR1 blast nursery each month from August 1966 to May 1968 and their relative population (based upon Philippine differentials).

in the blast nursery rather than by air-borne conidia from outside. A larger number of races than those detected may actually have been produced.

New pathogenic races in the Philippines

Up to 1967, 88 races have been characterized by the Philippine differential varieties and 49 races by the international differential varieties in the Philippines. In 1968, 28 new Philippine races and 18 new international races were identified. Their designated numbers and varietal reactions are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Variation in pathogenicity from single cells

Our early studies have shown that many pathogenic races may be differentiated among conidia produced on single lesions, and may be produced by subcultures from a single conidium. Of 50 sub-

cultures tested, one culture (L-2-36), however, did not change in pathogenicity. The variability and stability of the fungus were further investigated.

Variation in pathogenicity among subcultures of single cells. Single hyphal tips of two germinating conidia from culture I-42 (a variable culture) were isolated from both the apical and basal cells of each of the conidia. These were designated as A-a (Conidia A, apical cell), A-b (Conidia A, basal cell), B-a and B-b. They were cultured and 15 to 20 of them were further isolated from each of the subcultures. These were grown and the conidia collected and inoculated on the international and Philippine differential varieties.

Based on the international differential varieties, the 20 single hyphal-tip isolates of A-a were separated into 3 races, and the 17 A-b isolates into 7 races, the 17 B-a isolates into 2 races, and the 15 B-b isolates into 5 races.

Table 1. New races of *Pyricularia oryzae* in the Philippines based upon international differentials.

International race number	International differentials								Number of isolates
	P.I.231128 (Raminad Str. 3)	Zenith	P.I.201902 (NP-125)	Usen	P.I.180061 (Dular)	Kanto 51	C.I.8970(s)	C.I.1561 (Caloro)	
IA-66	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	R	2
IA-67	S	R	S	S	S	S	R	S	9
IA-68	S	R	S	S	S	S	R	R	1
IA-97	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	3
IA-121	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	1
IA-124	S	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	1
IB-61	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	1
IC-26	R	R	S	R	R	S	S	R	1
IE-1	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	1
IF-2	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R	1
IF-3	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	1

Table 2. New physiologic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* (identified in 1968) based upon Philippine differentials.

Philippine race number	Differential varieties												No. of isolates
	Katakara Da-2	C.I.5309	Chokoto Co25	Wag-wag Paikantao	Peta	Raminad Str. 3	Taichung T.C.W.C.	Lacrosse	Sha-tiao-tsau (s)	Khao-teh-haeng	17		
P-89	S	S	S S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	3
P-90	S	S	S S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	S	4
P-91	S	S	S S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	1
P-92	S	S	S S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	5
P-93	S	S	S R	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	S	1
P-94	S	S	S S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R	S	1
P-95	R	R	R R	S	R	R	S	S	S	R	S	S	1
P-96	R	R	R R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	1
P-97	R	R	R R	S	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	1
P-98	R	R	R R	S	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	S	1
P-99	R	S	S S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	2
P-100	S	S	S R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	1
P-101	R	R	S R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	1
P-102	R	R	R S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	1
P-103	R	S	S S	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	1
P-104	R	S	S S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	1
P-105	R	S	R R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	11
P-106	R	S	S R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	14
P-107	R	S	S R	S	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	2
P-108	R	S	S R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	1
P-109	R	S	S R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	1
P-110	R	R	S R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	1
P-111	S	S	S R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	2
P-112	S	S	S R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	4
P-113	S	S	S R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	R	S	4
P-114	S	S	S S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	1
P-115	S	S	S R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	1
P-116	S	S	S R	R	R	R	S	S	R	S	R	S	1
P-117	R	S	S R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	2
P-118	R	S	R R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	1

Based on the Philippine differential varieties, the 20 A-a single hyphal-tip isolates were separated into 7 races, the 17 A-b isolates into 8 races, the 17 B-a isolates into 8 races, and the 15 B-b isolates into 8 races (Table 3).

This further indicates that the fungus may produce new races not only from a single conidium, which is three-celled, but also from single hyphal tips isolated from single apical or basal cells on the conidium. Among the races, ID-9 or the original race, P-23, still dominated the population, i.e., it had a higher frequency. A total of 9 international race groups and 19 Philippine races was separated from the single hyphal tip isolates of the two conidia.

Variability and stability of monoconidial subcultures. Two isolates, I-281 and L-2-36, were studied further. Forty-one monoconidial subcultures from I-281, when inoculated on the international and Philippine differential varieties, were separated into 3 international race groups and 4 Philippine races as follows: by international differentials: IA-65 (25 subcultures), IC-1 (914), and ID-1 (2); by Philippine differentials: P-85 (23), P-84 (15), P-37 (2), and P-86 (1).

Twenty-six monoconidial subcultures of L-2-36, which was known to be stable, were further tested on the two sets of differentials. All

of the subcultures had the same reaction and were identified as IA-109 or P-8.

The available results seem to show that certain isolates, such as L-2-36, are quite stable in pathogenicity. Some are variable but the frequency in which they produce new races is low, such as I-281, while others, such as I-43, are very variable.

Variability in single lesions was further studied using Lesion No. 5. When inoculated to the two sets of differentials the 24 monoconidial cultures isolated from the lesion were separated into 6 race groups: IA-65, IA-67, IA-68, IA-124, IB-1 and IC-3. Eleven of the 24 monoconidial cultures belonged to IA-65, 9 to IA-67, and one each to the 4 other race groups. Based on the Philippine differentials, the 24 cultures were separated into 12 races: P-58 (1 culture), P-86 (1), P-89 (2), P-90 (4), P-91 (1), P-92 (3), P-111 (1), P-112 (4), P-113 (4), P-114 (1), P-115 (1), and P-116 (1).

The variations in pathogenicity from the single lesions, single conidium and single cells so far studied are summarized in Fig. 5.

Bacterial Blight Disease

Further screening for resistant varieties

A total of 607 varieties were further tested for their reaction to bacterial blight in addition to the

Table 3. Differentiation of pathogenic races from single hyphal tips of germinating conidia.

Single hyphal tip isolate	Races differentiated	
	International race group	Philippine races
A-a (20 isolates)	ID-9 (16), IA-10 (2) ID-1 (2)	P-106 (10), P-105(5), P-99 (1), P-107 (1), P-109 (1), P-110 (1), P-111 (1)
A-b (17 isolates)	ID-9 (9), IA-4 (2) IA-105 (2), IA-109 (1) IB-41 (1), ID-13 (1) IF-1 (1)	P-23 (6), P-105 (3), P-106 (2), P-13 (2), P-2 (1), P-9 (1), P-21(1), P-22(1)
B-a (17 isolates)	ID-9 (14), IA-105 (3)	P-23 (10), P-8 (1), P-9 (1), P-19 (1), P-21 (1), P-33 (1), P-68 (1), P-106 (1)
B-b (15 isolates)	ID-9 (9), IC-9 (3) IC-1 (1), ID-10 (1) ID-13 (1)	P-23 (6), P-105 (3), P-2 (1), P-10(1), P-19 (1), P-106 (1), P-107 (1), P-108 (1)

Fig. 5. Relative population of pathogenic races originating from single lesions, single conidia and single cells of *P. oryzae* (L-1 to L-5 from single lesions, L-1-43 to L-2-42 and I-281 from single conidia, A-a to B-b from apical or basal cells of conidia).

7,000 varieties screened in 1965 and 1966. Of these, 132 were found to be highly resistant in the field by inoculation of the flagleaf with isolate B-15. These varieties will be tested against other strains to confirm their resistance.

Since varietal reaction varies with different strains of the bacterium and was affected by temperature during the conduct of the experiment, the resistant varieties selected from the early tests were further tested against 10 strains of the organism to confirm their resistance (Table 4).

Reaction of Japanese varieties to the Philippine strains

There are a number of Japanese varieties that generally are known to be resistant, moderately resistant, and susceptible to bacterial blight. To better understand the interaction of rice varieties and the bacterial strains, some of the Japanese varieties were inoculated with virulent, intermediate, and weak Philippine strains. The results (Table 5) showed that these varieties reacted similarly to the Philippine strains. They further indicate that most of the Philippine strains are similar to the most virulent strains of Japan (Type I or A).

Transmission through seed

Rice seeds harvested from diseased fields are often contaminated or infected with the bacterium. In temperate regions, this is not considered important in transmitting the disease to the next planting. In the tropics, however, recent reports have indicated a high percentage of seed contamination and disease transmission to the seedlings.

Our preliminary experiments have indicated that it is difficult to isolate and positively identify the bacterium from naturally infested seeds, either by planting the seeds on agar medium or by the dilution plate method, because of the very high frequency of other bacterial contaminations. Ordinary hot-water treatment, or even surface-sterilization with chemicals, failed to remove all the contaminants. About 80 yellowish colonies grown from diseased seeds proved to be non-pathogenic, i.e., were not *X. oryzae*. A convenient method for studying the problem is by completely sterilizing the seeds with higher water temperature and artificially inoculating them with the bacterial suspension.

Preliminary experiments have also indicated that the bacterium cannot be recovered from artificially inoculated seeds 2 to 3 weeks after being kept outdoors during summer. This finding led to the study on the viability of the bacterium at

Table 4. Reaction of selected resistant varieties to 10 strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Disease scales 0 to 9, resistant to susceptible).

Variety	Acc no.	B ₂	B ₆	B ₁₃	B ₁₅	B ₃₈	B-75	B-77	B-57	B-59	B-23
Zenith	131	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	2	3	2
TKM 6	237	3	4	1	4	2	3	3	3	4	2
Wase Aikoku 3	525	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
M. Sungsong	755	0	0	1	1	1	2	3	1	3	1
Keng Chi-ju	1540	2	3	4	3	2	3	3	2	3	3
Early Prolific	1766	2	3	3	2	1	3	2	2	2	2
Early Prolific	1768	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Early Prolific	1769	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	1	4	1
Early Prolific	1772	4	3	3	5	4	4	5	4	5	2
Lacrosse x Zenith	2001	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	3	1
x Nira	2097	2	4	5	2	3	2	3	2	2	2
P.I. 162319	2396	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
3 Baifufugoya	2773	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	0
P.I. 209938	2856	3	4	3	3	5	3	3	2	3	1
Tainan-iku 512	2993	3	5	4	4	6	3	1	4	3	3
Giza 38	3086	2	4	4	5	1	2	3	3	4	4
Balilla	3098	3	3	5	4	4	3	2	4	3	3
BJ 1	3711	3	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	2
Sigadis	4095	2	4	2	5	3	3	3	3	3	2
Semora Mangga	4181	0	0	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	1
Tainan 9	6883	3	5	4	3	3	4	4	5	4	3
221c/BC11/Br/62/2	7608	3	2	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	1
DZ-78	8555	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	2
DZ-60	8558	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0
DD-96	9647	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	1
DV-29	8816	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	2
DV-52	8828	2	1	2	1	1	3	3	2	2	0
Dv - 2 (ck)	8806	6	8	8	6	9	7	6	9	7	3
JC - 70 (ck)	9114	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	7

Table 5. Reaction of resistant (R), moderately resistant (M) and susceptible (S) Japanese varieties to virulent (V), intermediate (I), and weak (W) strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the Philippines. (Disease scale 0, 1-9; 0, 1 are most resistant, 9 most susceptible. The disease reading was made after 30 days).

Variety	Average reaction to Philippine strains					
	B-2 (V)	B-6 (V)	B-15 (V)	B-57 (V)	B-59 (I)	B-23 (W)
Kidama (R)	6	6	6	6	7	6
Kogane-maru (R)	9	8	—	9	9	9
Norin 27 (R)	—	6.5	6.5	—	—	—
Norin 35 (R)	—	—	5	5	—	—
Norin 12 (M)	6	6.5	6.5	5	5	4
Norin 13 (M)	5	6	7	7	5	4
Norin 18 (M)	5	6	7	7	6	3
Sasahigure (M)	—	5	5	—	—	—
Aichi-asahi (S)	—	6.5	6	7	5	4
Jikkoku (S)	—	6.5	6.5	—	—	—
Kin-maze (S)	5	6.5	6.5	6	7	5
Norin 39 (s)	5	6	7	6	5	3
Norin 51 (S)	7	7	7	7	6	4
Zenith R (ck)	4	3	4	4	4	2
Tsao-tsuan (M ck)	8	9	8	8	9	6
JC-70 (S ck)	9	9	9	9	9	5

Fig. 6.A. Longevity of *X. oryzae* on seeds stored in flasks at different temperature conditions.

Fig. 6.C. Longevity of *X. oryzae* on rice hulls at different temperatures.

Fig. 6.B. Longevity of *X. oryzae* on rice grains (brown rice) at different temperatures.

Fig. 6.D. Longevity of *X. oryzae* from different sources at different temperatures.

Fig. 7. Infection and killing of rice seedlings by cutting roots in suspension of *X. oryzae*. Seedlings at left are not infected, the roots are not cut, even though they are similarly inoculated with the bacterial suspension.

various temperatures. Infected leaves, rice hull, and brown rice were kept at 24, 28, 32, 34, and 36 C, and some of them at 4 C and at -30C. The results (Fig. 6A, B, C, D) showed that the bacterium quickly lost its viability at higher temperatures. At about 32 C the bacterium lost its viability within 30 days. At 4 C, all the inoculated seeds produced bacterial colonies after several months. At -30 C, the bacterium was readily isolated from infected leaves after 18 months. In the tropics, rice seeds are often exposed to 30 to 32 C or higher for a considerable period, particularly when these were starting to dry up after harvest. It is doubtful that the bacterium on or in the seeds can remain viable up to the next planting if the interval between harvest and the next planting is more than 30 days.

Experiments also indicated that seedlings from inoculated seeds and seeds grown on inoculated soil or mineral-culture solution are not infected unless the root is injured or cut (Fig. 7).

The above experiments suggest that in the tropics, infected or contaminated seeds hardly transmit the bacterial blight disease.

Effect of shading and plant age on disease development

Previous results have shown that varieties susceptible to bacterial blight have a higher reducing sugar content than those resistant to the disease.

Two preliminary experiments showed that rice plants grown in reduced light (partly shaded) developed smaller lesions than those exposed to full sunlight. The plants in both cases were treated in total darkness for 2 to 3 days before they were exposed to the two light conditions.

In the experiments on plant age in relation to lesion development, young seedlings (10 days after germination) even of resistant varieties such as Zenith were severely infected or died from needle inoculation. It was inferred that these young seedlings contained large amounts of sugar from the decomposition of starch in seeds.

All these experiments suggest that the sugar content of the leaves is closely related to the development of the disease.

Bacterial Leaf Streak

Varietal resistance

More than 600 indica- and japonica-type varieties and 49 wild rice species and strains have been screened for resistance to the bacterial leaf streak disease using S-103, a virulent strain of the bacterium. The results are summarized in Table 6. Most of the varieties were moderately resistant, and a number of them showed highly resistant reaction. As a group, wild rice is more resistant to the disease than the cultivated forms.

The varieties found to be resistant (Scales 1 and 2) among those tested are listed below for possible use by breeders.

The following varieties have reaction Scale 1:

1. DZ-60 (IRRI Acc. No. 8558)
2. *Oryza perennis* (100192)
3. *Australian spontanea* (100944)
4. *Australian spontanea* (101146)
5. *Australian spontanea* (101147)
6. *Australian spontanea* (101148)

The following varieties have reaction Scale 2:

- | | |
|----------------------------------|--|
| 1. Milbuen 5(3) (2 entries) (49) | 21. DD-96 (2 entries) (8647) |
| 2. Hsinchu 56 (77) | 22. DD-100 (8649) |
| 3. Ch 242 (87, 7114) | 23. DD-113 (8657) |
| 4. Bluerosse (551) | 24. Ctg. 1118 (8712) |
| 5. Norin 37 (2556) | 25. DV-52 (2 entries) (8828) |
| 6. Hashikalmi (3397) | 26. DV-29 (2 entries) (8816) |
| 7. Charmock (Aus.) (3685) | 27. DV-57 (8831) |
| 8. NP-97 (3700) | 28. DV-68 (8833) |
| 9. Bmt. 53 R3540 (4132) | 29. DV-98 (8845) |
| 10. Huan-sen-goo (4619) | 30. DV-150 (8876) |
| 11. Pi 4 (6733) | 31. JW-107 (9129) |
| 12. DNJ-142 (8426) | 32. <i>Oryza glaberrima</i> (100140) |
| 13. DJ-65 (8485) | 33. <i>O. glaberrima</i> (100143) |
| 14. DZ-192 (8518) | 34. <i>O. perennis</i> (100211) |
| 15. DZ-179 (8520) | 35. <i>O. breviligulata</i> (100927) |
| 16. DZ-153 (8538) | 36. <i>Australian spontanea</i> (101145) |
| 17. DZ-74 (8556) | 37. <i>Oryza rufipogon</i> (101448) |
| 18. DZ-39 (8564) | |
| 19. DL-10 (8597) | |
| 20. DD-89 (8644) | |

As reported earlier, there was a very high correlation between the disease scales based on artificial inoculation and the visual field scales, particularly when virulent strains were used in the inoculation (Table 7). This is understandable since there are many virulent strains in the field.

Plant age and disease development

Both artificial inoculation and field observations indicated that plants become more resistant to

bacterial blight at the later growth stage. This increase in resistance was more significant in some varieties than in others.

Eight resistant, moderately resistant, and susceptible rice varieties were inoculated with 8 virulent and weak isolates of the bacterium at the age of 22, 39 and 57 days, and the sizes of the lesions produced were measured. In all cases, the 57-day-old plants produced significantly smaller lesions, averaging less than one-half the size of those on the younger plants. The difference in the production of lesions between 22- and 39-day-old varieties was not always significant. As indicated in the foregoing, the resistance may increase further when the plants become older.

In another experiment, a few varieties and selections were grown to observe the development of the bacterial blight disease in the field. The disease began to appear 4 to 6 weeks after transplanting, when the leaves of the plants among the hills were in contact with each other. Under favorable conditions in the wet season, the disease became more serious and the susceptible varieties looked completely yellow by the 7th and 8th weeks. In the 9th and 10th weeks, the flag leaves which appeared were, however, almost intact, and since these leaves dominated the field, the plants looked healthy green and remained so until harvest. At the same time, the younger plants of the same varieties were heavily infected. This type of adult plant resistance was particularly significant in such varieties as IR8, IR5 and BPI-76-1. In other varieties, e.g., Peta and C-18, such resistance was less pronounced. The disease is most intense when favorable climatic conditions (high moisture and wind or rain-storm) coincide with the more susceptible age of the plants. The tolerance to the disease at the later growth stage may also be considered as a type of resistance and may be utilized in breeding for resistance.

Relative virulence of the strains in the Philippines

Preliminary inoculation experiments using two susceptible varieties, Pah Leud 29-8-11 and Peta, indicated marked differences in virulence among the 150 isolates obtained in the Philippines. The results of the experiment in which eight selected strains were inoculated to 16 rice varieties with various degrees of resistance are shown in Fig. 8.

Table 6. Varietal resistance to bacterial leaf streak of indica and japonica varieties and wild rice species and strains. (Test strain: S-103.)

Reaction (scale)	Number of varieties per reaction group									Total no. varieties
	Resistant			Intermediate			Susceptible			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Indica varieties	1	30	62	61	110	65	52	26	5	412
Japonica varieties	0	5	15	22	37	24	14	9	0	126
Wild species and strains	5	6	7	8	9	7	7	0	0	49
Others	0	0	4	7	13	21	16	16	1	78
Total	6	41	88	98	169	117	89	51	6	665

Table 7. Scales for rating varietal reaction to bacterial leaf streak in greenhouse inoculation and field visual observation.

Scale	Greenhouse inoculation	Field observation		
0	No lesion	No lesion	} Field	
1	< 1 mm	Sporadic and few lesions		} looks
2	1-2 mm	Very few lesions per plant		
3	2-5 mm	Few lesions per plant but all over the field	} green	
4	6-10 mm	Generally few lesions but some plants heavily infected		
5	11-20 mm	Many lesions per plant all over the field		
6	21-30 mm	Many lesions, some leaf tips yellow	} Field	
7	31-40 mm	Leaf tips yellow		} looks
8	41-60 mm	Whole parts of leaves yellow, leaves drying		
9	> 60 mm	Leaves drying	} yellow	

Isolates S-103 and S-107 were the most virulent, S-1, S-64, S-115, and S-101 had intermediate virulence, and S-20 and S-95 were the least virulent (weak strains).

The resistant varieties were more resistant to all isolates while the susceptible ones produced larger lesions to all isolates although there were variations within each group. There were no distinct differences in the reaction of the varieties to different isolates. There seemed to be no distinct pathogenic races as in the case of the blast fungus, i.e., those varieties that are resistant to the most virulent strains would be expected to be resistant to other strains.

Pathogenicity patterns

To better understand the interaction of varieties and strains, 25 isolates of the bacterium of different virulence and 6 rice varieties with various

degrees of resistance were selected to study the pathogenicity patterns of the organism or the reaction types of the varieties. Various patterns and reaction types were observed; these may, however, be summarized into four major types (Fig. 9). Type I, represented by isolate S-78, showed high virulence and a distinct reaction among the resistant, moderate and susceptible varieties; Type II, represented by isolate S-95, had intermediate virulence; Type III, represented by isolate S-95, had very weak virulence; and Type IV, represented by S-94, did not show any marked difference in reaction among the varieties. These pathogenicity patterns are similar to that of the bacterial blight organism.

Bacteriophage population in irrigation water

To obtain information on the fluctuations of the bacterial population in the water of irrigation

Fig. 8. Reaction of 16 rice varieties to 8 isolates of *X. translucens* f. sp. *oryzae*.

Resistant	Susceptible
1- Charnock (Aust.)	9- Paikan-tao
2- N.P. - 97	10- NP-137
3- Norin 22	11- Taichung-ti-chio-wu-chien
4- Milbuen 3	12- Peta
5- Milketan 20	13- Ya-yiu-tsai
6- CI-73385	14- Kam-bau-ngan
7- Kung-shan-wu-shen-ken	15- Mamoriaka
8- Unblatuzi Valley Sugar Co.	16- Nhta-10

Fig. 9. Reactions of resistant, intermediate and susceptible varieties to strains of *X. translucens* f. sp. *oryzae*.

canals and of fields during rice-growing seasons, the bacterial population was taken by means of bacteriophage counts. Water from three sites was sampled: the large canal leading to the IRRI Experimental Farm, the rainfed reservoir of the same

Farm, and the drainage canal leading out of the Farm. The samples were taken at about 1-week intervals. The results showed that the water in the drainage canal had the highest bacterial population - 6,000 to 7,000 plagues per ml of water were counted from August to October. The water in the reservoir had the next highest count, while that in the large irrigation canal had the lowest. However, the fluctuation in population was greater in the water of the large canal; occasionally more plagues were detected in this canal than in the reservoir during the early months. A summary of these results into a monthly-average basis from April 1967 to February 1968 is shown in Fig. 10 A.

The phage population was also counted in four field plots, two each of a more resistant variety, Hsinchu 56, and a susceptible variety, Pah Leud 29-8-11. One plot of each variety was inoculated by spraying the bacterial suspension on leaves 1 month after transplanting. Phage plague counts were made at approximately weekly intervals. The results (Fig. 10,B) showed that: (1) the phage

Fig. 10,A. Bacterio-phage plague counts for *X. translucens* f. sp. *oryzae* in irrigation water, IRRI Experimental Farm (monthly average from weekly counts).

Fig. 10,B. Bacterio-phage counts for *X. translucens* f. sp. *oryzae* in field water under resistant and susceptible varieties.

population is much higher in the water in the susceptible varieties than that in the more resistant varieties with or without inoculation, (2) the phage population increased rapidly after inoculation for a period of about 5 weeks, after which it declined to a level similar to that of uninoculated plots, (3) the phage population increased rapidly 4 or 5 weeks after transplanting (without inoculation), and (4) the phage population was generally higher in field water than in the water of the large irrigation canal and in the water reservoir of the Farm. The reason for the dip in July is not known; perhaps it was due to season.

New phages and lysotypes

As reported earlier (1964), six phages (Sp-1 to Sp-6) and 16 lysotypes of the 84 isolates of the streak organisms were found in the Philippines. These phages and the bacterial isolates stored in a deep freezer were tested again for their inter-

reactions. Several single-plague reisolations were made from each of the original phages. These single-plague reisolates differed from the original phages in their reaction to the host bacterial isolates. For instance, a re isolate from Sp-1 phage, designated as Sp-1-1, lysed the bacterial isolates S-20, S-24, and S-51, all of which were not lysed by the original Sp-1. Also, the bacterial isolates S-43 and S-81 were lysed by Sp-1 but not by Sp-1-1. A new type of phage, therefore, seemed to have appeared. All the original six phages, except Sp-3, produced this new type. Nine such new phages were found and designated as Sp-1-1, Sp-1-2, Sp-2-1, Sp-2-2, Sp-2-3, Sp-4-1, Sp-5-1, Sp-6-1, and Sp-6-2. It appears that the phages are variable and new ones may be produced in the old cultures.

Besides those produced by the old cultures, many new phage isolations were made. A number of these were classified as new and differed in their reaction to bacterial strains. Based upon 20 host strains, 18 more new phages were characterized and designated as Sp-7 to Sp-24. Altogether, there are 33 known phages of the streak organism. The details will be presented separately from this report.

The ability of the 33 phages to lyse the 20 test bacterial isolates varied from 1 to 14, mostly 5 to 8. The 20 bacterial isolates sensitive to the 33 phages varied from 2 to 28, mostly 10 to 15. At least three bacterial isolates in combination, S-74, S-73 and S-77, were required to detect the presence of all phages.

The study suggested the variability and complexity of the bacterium-phage interaction which are generally used for detecting other phages and which in turn indicate the presence of the bacterium causing the streak disease.

Host range

None of the 13 species in 10 genera of gramineous weeds and 10 varieties of sorghum, corn, millet and wheat were infected by artificial inoculation, even after the leaves were pricked with a needle.

All the 49 species and strains of wild rice, however, can serve as alternative hosts. The degree of infection varied greatly among species and strains, as shown below:

Oryza spontanea (IRRI Acc. No. 100910) - disease scale 6

<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i>	(100912)-7	<i>Oryza perennis</i>	(100602)-5
"	(100916)-4	"	(100606)-5
"	(100917)-6	"	(100930)-4
"	(100918)-6	<i>Oryza breviligulata</i>	(100117)-7
"	(100945)-4	"	(100119)-6
"	(100946)-7	"	(100120)-4
<i>O. perennis balunga</i>	(101156)-3	"	(100929)-4
"	(101173)-3	"	(100931)-3
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	(101512)-7	"	(100940)-6
"	(101508)-7	"	(101252)-4
"	(101507)-5	<i>Oryza glaberrima</i>	(100128)-5
"	(101510)-7	"	(100136)-5
<i>Oryza perennis</i>	(100194)-6	"	(100137)-5
"	(100195)-4	"	(100977)-5
"	(100196)-6	"	(100932)-3
"	(100208)-5	"	(100152)-3
		"	(100139)-3

Others with scales 1 and 2 are listed under varietal resistance.

Tungro Disease

Varietal resistance to tungro disease

The search for sources of resistance to the tungro disease was continued, with a total of 3,990 varieties and breeding lines being tested by the previously described mass screening method.

Resistant varieties. Of the 596 varieties tested, 44 were classified as resistant while the rest were either intermediate or susceptible to the disease. Seven of these 44 resistant varieties have been reported in previous annual reports. The following 10 varieties and lines showed less than 30 percent infected seedlings in at least two tests:

Basmati 370 (IRRI Acc. No. 4895)
 Seratus hari T/36 (5346)
 Urang-Urangan 89 (6016)
 Basmati 37 (6448)
 Tsou-yuen (7315)
 221b/210/2/1/1/2(7589)
 221c/53/1/2/1 (7596)
 221/BC11/11/3 (7606)
 268b/Pr/2/2/2 (7624)
 Padi Kasalle (8261)

Resistance of IR breeding lines. A total of 2,930 selections of 101 IR lines was tested. About 11 percent of these selections were classified in the resistant group while the rest were either intermediate or susceptible to the disease (Table 8).

New vectors

In 1967, *Nephotettix apicalis* insects collected

Table 8. Reaction of IR lines to the tungro disease as determined by the mass screening test.

Line and parents	No. of selections showing infection (%)		
	0 – 30	31 – 60	61 – 100
IR 159, Basmati 370 x T(N)1	5	5	1
IR 506, IR8 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1)	5	20	25
IR 532, (Peta/3 x T(N)1) x TKM 6	3	40	66
IR 580, IR8 x TKM 6	10	35	12
IR 626, IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	7	12	4
IR 644, IR8/2 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1)	2	6	7
IR 658, Peta 7 x T(N)1	2	16	1
IR 661, IR8 x (CP231 x SLO-17) x Sigadis	5	4	7
IR 644, IR8 x IR5-273-1-2	2		2
IR 665, IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	2	4	5
IR 748, IR8 x (Dawn x Pankhari 203)	4	17	7
IR 751, IR8/2 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	4	4	3
IR 756, IR8/3 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x T(N)1)	2	1	1
IR 781 IR8/2 x (Yukara x T(N)1)	3	6	5
IR 822, IR8/2 x Pankhari 203	125	609	254
IR 854, (IR 8 x Pankhari 203) x IR262-43-8-11	21	108	42
IR 874, IR8/2 x (CP - SLO/2 x Nahng Mon s-4)	3	1	2
IR 877, IR8/2 x (Dawn x Pankhari 203)	61	165	13
IR 1154, IR8/2 x Zenith	6	88	50
Other 81 IR lines	15	150	397
Total (101 lines, 2,930 selections)	326	1,586	1,018

from the provinces of Camarines Norte, Camarines Sur, Laguna, and Nueva Ecija, all in the Philippines, were found to be capable of transmitting the tungro virus at the rate of 12, 9, 16 and 11 percent respectively. The results were confirmed in a further study (Table 9). The percentage of active transmitters varied not only among localities where the insects were collected but also among samples collected in the same locality. A higher percentage of active transmitters was obtained when, in addition to the acquisition feeding, a daily reacquisition feeding was provided. For the daily acquisition feeding, the insects was used for inoculation during the daytime and confined on diseased plants for the rest of the day.

Some of the "active" individuals were selected and mated through several generations to produce a colony with a high percentage of active transmitters. The percentage of tungro disease-transmitting leafhoppers of *N. apicalis* has now reached about 55. The search for other possible leafhopper and planthopper vectors of the tungro disease, besides *N. impicticeps* and *N. apicalis*, was continued. The 10 species of leafhoppers or plant-

hoppers used in the study were identified by Dr. T. Ishihara of Ehime University, Japan, and Dr. M. S. K. Ghauri of the Commonwealth Institute of

Table 9. Percentage of male *Nephotettix apicalis* insects transmitting the rice tungro virus.

Insects collected from	No. of infective insects/no. tested	Percentage of active transmitters
Bay, Laguna	0/113	0
	1/104	0.96
	2/100	2.00
	3/112	2.68
Los Baños, Laguna	6/72	8.33
	13/88*	14.77
	25/92	27.17
	45/100*	45.00
Pila, Laguna	1/35	2.86
	2/40	5.00
	3/30	10.00
	4/40	10.00
Total	105/921	11.40

* Daily reacquisition feeding in addition to 4-5 days acquisition feeding was provided.

Entomology, London, as *Balclutha viridis* (Mats.), *Cicadulina bipunctella* (Mats.), *Exitianus capicola* Stal., *Hecalus* sp., *Macrosteles fascifrons* (Stal.), *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal.), *Nisia atrovenosa* Lethierry, *Recilia (Inazuma) dorsalis* (Motsch.), *Tettigella spectra* (Dist.) and *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath.

The only successful transmission of the disease from infected to healthy plants was obtained with the leafhopper *R. dorsalis*. About 6 percent of the field population of this species used transmitted the disease. Several field collections of this insect transmitted the "S" and "M" strains of tungro. The percentage of "active" transmitters for all collections ranged from 4 to 8. For the other 9 species, tests involving 112 to 664 insects of each species failed to show any disease transmission.

Morphology of *N. apicalis* and virus transmission

General morphology. The morphological similarities and deviations from typical morphological characteristics of *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps* have accounted for the difficulties encountered in distinguishing between these two species. However, the morphological features of the insects of both species collected in the Philippines and examined at the Institute generally agreed with the characteristics described by Ishihara. But there were deviations in the arrangement of the teeth or spines on the aedeagus as well as in the number of teeth. The teeth are generally arranged in two rows but in some cases, one to four teeth are arranged irregularly or appear somewhat in one row either on one side or on both sides of the outer area of the two main rows of teeth on the aedeagus. Furthermore, the arrangement of teeth in each of the two main rows may not be symmetrical. Therefore, the number of teeth in each of the two main rows may not be identical. The existence of teeth in addition to those in the two main rows and the asymmetrical arrangement of the teeth in the two main rows have been observed in both *N. apicalis* (Figs. 11 and 12) and *N. impicticeps* (Figs. 13 and 14). The number of teeth on the aedeagus varies from 10 to 23, mostly 14 to 17 for *N. apicalis* and from 4 to 10, mostly 7 to 8 for *N. impicticeps*.

Based on the present results, the following key

Fig. 11. Portion of aedeagus of *Nephrotettix apicalis* showing teeth on each side of the two main rows of teeth.

is proposed for distinguishing between *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps*.

Aedeagus without elongated paraphyses and hardly constricted below the paraphyses. Style straight.

1. Vertex with a submarginal black band. Tegminal spots often present and confluent along the claval suture. Aedeagus with a total of 10 to 23, mostly 14 to 17 teeth *N. apicalis*
2. Vertex without submarginal black band. Tegminal spots present or absent; if present, not confluent to claval suture. Aedeagus with a total of 4 to 10, mostly 7 to 8 teeth *N. impicticeps*

Attempts have been made to separate the active transmitters of *N. apicalis* on the basis of their minor morphological features such as location of tegminal spots, length of aedeagus, arrangement of teeth on aedeagus, and number of teeth. The results are summarized as follows:

Tegminal spots. The collected samples showed that the tegminal spots may or may not be confluent to the claval suture. The insects could be grouped into three categories according to the location of the spots. The spots of the majority of the insects examined were confluent to the suture (Table 10). The spots of the other insects were either not confluent to the suture or only one of the two spots was confluent to the suture. However, the frequency distribution of the active trans-

mitters by the location of the spots seemed to be identical with that of the insects that did not transmit the virus. Therefore, the location of the spots cannot be used as a criterion for determining the transmissive ability of the insect.

Length of aedeagus. The length of the aedeagus of the 100 non-active *N. apicalis* transmitters examined varied from 0.45 to 0.62 mm with an average of 0.52 mm. The range of the length of the aedeagus of 73 active transmitters was from 0.41 to 0.67 mm with an average of 0.51 mm. The frequency distribution of both active and non-active transmitters by the length of the aedeagus was similar. Since their differences are not statistically significant, the active and non-active transmitters cannot be separated by the length of their aedeagal shafts.

Arrangement of teeth on aedeagus. As mentioned earlier, the arrangement of teeth on the aedeagus may not always be symmetrical. This means that either the number of teeth on each of the two main rows may not be identical or there

Fig. 13. Portion of aedeagus of *Nephrotettix impicticeps* showing one tooth on the left side of the two main rows of teeth.

Fig. 12. Portion of aedeagus of *Nephrotettix apicalis* showing asymmetrical arrangement of the teeth.

Fig. 14. Portion of aedeagus of *Nephrotettix impicticeps* showing asymmetrical arrangement of teeth.

Table 10. Frequency of tungro virus transmitters of male *Nephotettix apicalis* by location of tegminal spots.

Location of spots	Nonactive transmitters (%)	Active transmitters (%)
Spots confluent to claval suture	86.8	88.0
One spot confluent to claval suture	3.8	2.7
Spots not confluent to claval suture	9.4	9.3
Total no. of examined insects	106	75

may be more than two series of teeth on the aedeagus. The 171 insects examined (98 non-active transmitters and 73 active transmitters) can be grouped on the basis of symmetrical teeth and asymmetrical arrangement. The insects in the first group can be further divided according to the number of teeth per series, which varied from 6 to 10; those in the latter group, according to the number of series, which varied from 2 to 4. The majority of the insects, regardless of whether they were active or non-active transmitters, had asymmetrically arranged teeth. There seemed to be no striking difference between the active and non-active transmitters in the arrangement of teeth.

Number of teeth. The number of teeth on the aedeagus of the *N. apicalis* insects examined varied from 10 to 23 with an average of 15.96. About 82 percent of the insects examined had 14 to 17 teeth. The number of teeth varied from 10 to 22 with an average of 15.60 for the active transmitters and from 12 to 23 with an average of 16.23 for the non-active transmitters. The difference was not statistically significant.

Virus transmissible ability of *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps*

The tungro virus transmissible ability of *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps* were compared. Transmissible ability refers to the percentage of active transmitters, retention period of infectivity, effect of daily acquisition feeding on both the percentage of active transmitters and the virus retention period in the insect, and effect of length of acquisition feeding on infectivity. The most active *N. apicalis* colony obtained so far was used. The results are

summarized as follows:

Percentage of active transmitters. As mentioned earlier, the percentage of active transmitters of *N. apicalis* varied greatly among the samples collected from different localities. It even varied among the samples collected from the same locality. However, even with the most active colony, the percentage of active transmitters of *N. apicalis* was significantly lower than that of *N. impicticeps* (Table 11).

As has been known since 1965, the percentage of infective insects of *N. impicticeps* increases as the acquisition feeding period is increased up to 4 days. In the case of *N. apicalis*, the percentage of infective insects may or may not increase proportionally with the length of the acquisition feeding period. This depends on the activity of the insects. For instance, if a colony with a low percentage of active transmitters is used, the percentage of infective insects may remain similar even if the length of the acquisition feeding period varies from 1 to 4 days. However, the results in Table 11 show that the percentage of infective insects of both *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps* was increased when, in addition to the acquisition feeding period, the insects were given a daily reacquisition feeding period. Therefore, the effects of daily acquisition feeding on the infectivity of both species are basically similar.

Virus retention period. One of the reasons for concluding that the tungro virus does not persist in *N. impicticeps* is that the infective insects do not retain their infectivity. The longest virus retention period obtained was 5 days. It was found that the tungro virus also does not persist in *N. apicalis* (Fig. 15). The longest retention period obtained in

Table 11. Comparison of the average percentage of tungro virus transmitters between *Nephotettix apicalis* and *N. impicticeps*.

<i>Nephotettix</i> sp.	Percentage of infective insects		
	Acquisition feeding only	With daily reacquisition feeding	LSD 5%
<i>N. impicticeps</i>	69.40	83.67	11.09
<i>N. apicalis</i>	17.39	30.13	11.67
LSD 1%	12.69	17.69	

N. apicalis was 3 days, i.e., shorter than that in *N. impicticeps*. The infective *N. apicalis* insects also gradually lost their infectivity with time after the termination of acquisition feeding. However, the insects could become re-infective if they were again given access to a virus source. In some cases, the previously non-infective *N. apicalis* insects became infective after the second acquisition feeding. It seems that the virus persistence of *N. apicalis* did not differ fundamentally from that of *N. impicticeps* but the retention period of *N. apicalis* was shorter than that of *N. impicticeps*.

Insect infective days. The percentage of active transmitters is often used to compare the transmissible ability or efficiency of two or more groups or species of insects. However, this criterion does not entirely explain the activity of the transmitters. The retention period, i.e., the length of time during which the insects remain infective after acquisition feeding, can be used as an additional basis for determining the differences in transmissible ability between groups of insects. The retention period of a non-persistent group is relatively short especially in the case of the tungro virus. A daily acquisition feeding period is often given to the insects to increase their infectivity. In such a case, the retention period cannot be determined. Therefore, "insect infective days" or "infective days" for short, is a new term proposed to indicate the number of days that the insect is infective during a given period. Consequently, an average number of "insect infective days" during a given period can be obtained to specify the transmissible activity of the infective insects of each group for comparison. The "insect infective days" can be further converted to percentage of infective days, i.e., the number of infective days divided by the total number of days tested expressed in percent. Actually, if (a) only one acquisition feeding is provided to the insects, (b) the daily transmission pattern of the insect is consecutive, and (c) the infectivity of the insects is tested by daily serial transmission method during a given period, the average retention period would be equal to the average number of "insect infective days." Nevertheless, the term "insect infective days" can also be applied to compare the transmissible ability of infective insects of the persistent group between two or more groups if the daily transmission pattern is intermittent. One insect may transmit

Fig. 15. Comparison of tungro virus retention period between *Nephotettix apicalis* and *N. impicticeps*.

the disease almost every day while another may transmit it only occasionally during the same period. They may not differ in their virus retention period but they would differ strikingly in their disease transmission activity. In selecting a highly active insect colony for virus inoculation, it would be better to focus not only on the high percentage of active transmitters but also on the large number of "insect infective days."

The number of insect infective days with and without daily acquisition feeding during a period of 4 days after the termination of acquisition feeding of *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps* are compared in Fig. 16. The average number of insect infective days of *N. apicalis* was 1.06, which means that not only did the majority of the infective insects transmit the disease for only 1 day but also that the infective insects transmitted the disease for only 1.06 days during a period of 4 days. Actually, four healthy seedlings were exposed to individual in-

Fig. 16. Comparison of insect infective days of tungro virus between *Nephrotettix apicalis* and *N. impicticeps*.

fective insects at the rate of one seedling per day. An average of only 1.06 seedlings were infected, with the other 2.94 seedlings remaining healthy. The insect infective days of *N. impicticeps* was 1.38; this was significantly higher than that of *N. apicalis*. Since the tungro virus does not persist in *N. impicticeps* and in *N. apicalis* and less than 50 percent of the insects remain infective on the following day, the theoretical number of infective days should be less than 2.0 but greater than 1.0. With additional daily acquisition feeding, the number of insect infective days of both species increased. This explains why the daily acquisition

feeding is a practical way of increasing or maintaining the infectivity of the insects. The number of insect infective days were 1.28 and 2.70 for *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps*, respectively, with daily acquisition feeding during a 4-day period. The difference in infective days between the species is statistically significant, indicating that *N. impicticeps* can transmit the disease more often than *N. apicalis* during a given period.

Based on the above results, the virus-vector interaction of *N. apicalis* does not differ fundamentally from that of *N. impicticeps*, but the percentage of active transmitters, the virus retention period, and the number of insect infective days with or without daily acquisition feeding of *N. apicalis* are lower than those of *N. impicticeps*. Therefore, *N. apicalis* is less efficient than *N. impicticeps* in transmitting the tungro virus.

Morphological features of *N. impicticeps*

Several morphological features of *N. impicticeps* insects such as tegminal spots, mandible, maxilla, aedeagus, and number of teeth of the male adults were examined after the insects were tested individually for their transmission of the tungro virus.

Tegminal spots. Although the majority (69.6%) of the 382 insects examined did not have tegminal spots, the number of spots of those which had them varied from one to two since, in some cases, there was only one spot on either one of the tegmina. The frequency distribution of active transmitters by their number of tegminal spots was almost identical with that of the insects which did not transmit the disease. In other words, neither the absence nor the number of tegminal spots can be used as a basis for classifying the active and non-active transmitters in an insect colony. Among the active transmitters, the degree of tungro virus transmission in terms of average number of insect-infective days of those insects with two tegminal spots seemed to be slightly higher than that of the insects without tegminal spots. Further studies are needed to verify this finding.

Mandible. The tip portion of the mandible with its tooth-like projections can be seen under a high-power microscope (Fig. 17). However, there were no obvious differences between active and non-active transmitters. The length of the mandible varied from 0.58 to 0.67 mm. About one-half of

the 174 mandibles examined were 0.61 to 0.63 mm long. The frequency distribution of the active transmitters according to the length of the mandible seemed to be similar to that of the non-active transmitters. At least, the average length of the mandible of the active transmitters (0.6275 mm) did not differ significantly from that of the non-active transmitters (0.6210 mm).

Maxilla. The length of the maxilla varied from 0.69 to 0.80 mm. About 70 percent of the 162 maxillae examined were 0.72 to 0.76 mm long. The frequency distribution of the active transmitters by the length of the maxilla seemed to deviate slightly from that of the non-active transmitters: the length of the maxilla of about 75 percent of the active transmitters ranged from 0.73 to 0.78 mm whereas that of about 80 percent of the non-active transmitters was from 0.71 to 0.76 mm. However, the average length was 0.7433 mm for the active transmitters and 0.7425 mm for the non-active transmitters. The difference is not statistically significant.

Aedeagus. The length of the aedeagus varied from 0.43 to 0.57 mm. About 60 percent of the 374 aedeagus examined were 0.47 to 0.50 mm long. The frequency distribution of the active transmitters by the length of the aedeagus seemed to be similar to that of the non-active transmitters. The averaged lengths of the aedeagus were 0.4896 and 0.4892 mm for the active and non-active transmitters, respectively. The difference is not statistically significant.

Number of teeth The number of teeth on the aedeagus varied from 4 to 10. Seventy percent of the 376 aedeagus examined had 7 to 8 teeth. The majority of the active transmitters (69.4%) and of the non-active transmitters (75.9%) had 7 to 8 teeth. The average numbers of teeth were 7.40 and 7.46 for the active and non-active transmitters, respectively. The difference is not statistically significant. The frequency distribution of the active transmitters by the number of teeth was similar to that of the non-active transmitters.

Transmissive ability The ability of the insects differing in morphological features to transmit the tungro disease was compared. The insects were grouped according to the number of infective days out of a test period of 4 consecutive days. The average figures for the various morphological features (Table 12) did not differ strikingly. There-

Fig. 17. Tip portions of mandible of *Nephrotettix impicticeps* in different views showing the tooth-like projections.

Table 12. Morphological features of *Nephrotettix impicticeps* with different tungro virus transmission activities.

Morphological feature	No. of insect-infective days				
	0	1	2	3	4
Length of mandible (μ)	621.0	626.8	630.0	625.0	
Length of maxilla (μ)	742.5	742.8	743.8	745.7	
Length of aedeagus (μ)	489.2	488.2	486.4	491.6	495.4
Number of teeth	7.46	7.31	7.44	7.56	7.33

fore, these morphological features may not be the factors that determine the tungro virus transmissive ability of *N. impicticeps*.

Resistance to the virus and to the vector

Four rice varieties - Taichung (Native) 1, IR8, Kai Lianh Hsung Ting, and Pankhari 203 - were selected to demonstrate the difference between varieties

Table 13. Comparison of susceptibility of four rice varieties to the tungro disease.

Variety	Number of inoculated seedlings	Percentage of infected seedlings		
		Range	Average	Arcsin $\sqrt{x}$
Taichung (Native) 1	565	64-100	94.00	80.76
IR8	606	50-100	83.67	68.00
Kai Lianh Hsung Ting	623	11-48	19.38	25.54
Pankhari 203	682	0-17	5.46	11.99
L S D 1 %				5.93

resistant to the tungro virus and those resistant to the virus vector, *Nephotettix impicticeps*. Seedlings of the same age were transplanted in pots, and four pots of each variety were inoculated in the same cage by the mass screening method. The test was repeated six times. The percentage of infected seedlings varied among the varieties (Table 13), and the difference between any two varieties was statistically significant. The susceptibility to tungro disease was in descending order as Taichung (Native) 1 and IR8. Based on the present arbitrary grouping system, Taichung (Native) 1 and IR8 were classified in the susceptible group since their percentages of infected seedlings were more than 60 while Kai Lianh Hsung Ting and Pankhari 203 were included in the resistant group because their percentages of infected seedlings were less than 30.

The above rice varieties were further tested for their effect on the life span of adult *N. impicticeps* insects. From several tests, a total of 100 adult insects were confined on seedlings of each variety. The results (Fig. 18) showed that the average life span of the insects feeding on Taichung (Native) 1 and Kai Lianh Hsung Ting was almost the same. The life span of the insects feeding on IR8 was slightly longer than that of the insects feeding on Pankhari 203. However, the average life span of the insects feeding on IR8 or Pankhari 203 was significantly shorter than that of the insects feeding on either Taichung (Native) 1 or Kai Lianh Hsung Ting. If both Taichung (Native) 1 and Kai Lianh Hsung Ting are considered as varieties susceptible to *N. impicticeps*, then, IR8 and Pankhari 203 are resistant varieties.

There are four possible combinations of resistance to the insect vector and resistance to the virus, namely (1) resistant to the vector and resistant to the virus, (2) resistant to the vector but

susceptible to the virus, (3) susceptible to the vector but resistant to the virus, and (4) susceptible to the vector and susceptible to the virus. Pankhari 203, IR8, Kai Lianh Hsung Ting, and Taichung (Native) 1 could be respective examples of each of the four combinations. Resistance to the virus may not always be correlated to resistance to the insect vector, or vice versa.

Colonies of *N. impicticeps* breeding on resistant rice varieties and virus transmission

Pankhari 203 and IR8 have been shown to be highly resistant to the vector of the tungro virus, *N. impicticeps*. *N. impicticeps* has been found to live longer on Taichung (Native) 1 than on Pankhari 203 or IR8. The ability of the insect to survive and perpetuate on these resistant varieties may be determined not only by their relative life span but also by their oviposition and the viability of their eggs on different varieties. One hundred pairs of male and female *Nephotettix impicticeps* insects were caged on Pankhari 203. After 5 days, only four pairs survived. There were maintained on Pankhari 203 through several generations. After three generations, the average life span of the adults on Pankhari 203 and Taichung (Native) 1 were 16.1 and 18.0 days, respectively. On the average, the males lived for about 2 weeks and the females, about 3 weeks. The average number of eggs laid per female for a 10-day period was 16.8 on Pankhari 203 and 45.3 on Taichung (Native) 1. The percentages of eggs which hatched on Pankhari 203 and Taichung (Native) 1 were 56.3 and 82.1, respectively. These findings indicate that (1) some individuals of *Nephotettix impicticeps* can survive and complete their development on Pankhari 203, and (2) besides the life span of the

Fig. 18. Life span of adult *Nephotettix impicticeps* when fed on seedlings of 4 rice varieties in test tubes.

adults, the number of eggs laid and the percentage of those which hatched may also be used as a basis for comparing the resistance to insects of rice varieties. Similar results were obtained with IR8. In the F₂ generation of the surviving population, the average number of eggs deposited per female for a 10-day period on IR8 was 11.2 and the percentage of hatching was 38.3. The life span of the adults on IR8 was about the same as that on Taichung (Native)1.

Preliminary results showed that those insects reared from Pankhari 203 transmitted the tungro virus to Pankhari 203 at a higher percentage than those from ordinary colonies.

Host range

Studies on the host range of the "S" strain of the tungro virus were conducted in the greenhouse with *N. impicticeps*. The tests included representatives of 26 genera in 8 tribes in the graminæ. Sixty-three species and varieties or selections, including those described in the 1964 Annual Report, were used in several of the tests. The plants were identified by Prof. J. V. Pancho of the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines in Los Baños, Laguna, and the classification conformed to that of Bor (Grasses of Burma, Ceylon, India and Pakistan, Vol. 1, 767 pp., 1960).

From 50 to 200 viruliferous insects were caged for 1 week or more on five plants in each clay pot, depending on the size of the plants. The plants were observed for symptoms of tungro for at least 1 month after caging. Although 63 species and varieties in the graminæ were tested, only the *Oryza* spp. and certain small grains or weeds developed symptoms of the disease. Thirteen species had one or more infected plants (Table 14). At first most of these plants produced symptoms similar to those of the control, Taichung (Native) 1, but as the plants grew further, the leaf discoloration disappeared. No disease symptoms appeared on the common weed, *Echinochloa colonum* (L.) Link, which was reported earlier to be a symptom-less host of the tungro virus transmitted by *N. impicticeps*. The irregular appearance of symptoms on these hosts or the recovery of the virus from symptom-less hosts was again noticed. For instance, several other inoculations on *Ischaemum rogosum* and *Sorghum vulgare* did not reveal any disease symptoms on the plants.

Since large numbers of *N. apicalis* insects have been found on wild grass species, especially *E. colonum*, studies were also initiated to determine if this plant could be infected with the virus by allowing *N. apicalis* to feed on it. In five experiments, no disease symptoms appeared on 115 plants caged with 3,462 insects previously fed on

Table 14. Host range of the tungro disease of rice.

Species	No. plants infected/ no. plants inoculated
Tribe Andropogoneae	
<i>Ischaemum rogosum</i> Salisb.	2/133 (virus recovered)
<i>Sorghum vulgare</i> Pers. var. Darso	3/106 (virus recovered)
Tribe Fragrosteae	
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Beauv.	2/103
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i> (L.) Beauv.	1/58
Tribe Oryzae	
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (L.) var. Taichung (Native)1	16/20 (virus recovered)
<i>O. rufipogon</i> Griff.	8/9 (virus recovered)
<i>O. officinalis</i> Wall.	6/6 (virus recovered)
<i>O. ridleyi</i> Hook	4/4 (virus recovered)
<i>O. barthii</i> Chev.	7/9 (virus recovered)
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Wartz	1/19
Tribe Paniceae	
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	2/67 (virus recovered)
<i>Setaria glauca</i> Beauv. var. Proso	3/138 (virus recovered)
Tribe Triticaceae	
<i>Triticum vulgare</i> Vill. var. Fiorello	2/55

diseased plants. Attempts to recover the virus from *E. colonum* to rice with *N. apicalis* and *N. impicticeps* also failed. Young adults of *N. apicalis* survived and oviposited better on *E. colonum* than on Taichung (Native) 1. This plant species, however, is not a suitable host of *N. impicticeps*.

Except for the *Oryza* spp., all the plants tested were poor hosts of the leafhopper, *N. impicticeps*, and therefore, virus recovery trials were difficult to conduct. The average survival time of the insect was less than 3 days on most of the plants. However, the tungro virus was recovered in the infected plants of *Setaria glauca*, *Sorghum vulgare*, *Ischaemum rogosum* and *Paspalum scrobiculatum*. It was also possible that some plants without symptoms were infected with the disease. However, the practical significance of these hosts which serve as virus reservoir in the disease cycle appeared doubtful since most of the plants tested were poor hosts of the virus and its leafhopper vector, *N. impicticeps*. The dependence of *N. impicticeps* upon cultivated rice (*Oryza sativa*) and other *Oryza* species makes them the most important hosts of the disease in the transmission cycle.

Inheritance of tungro resistance in respect to plant age

In developing isogenic lines resistant to tungro, many crosses were made between varieties Pank-

hari 203 and IR8 and Taichung (Native) 1. Resistant progenies were backcrossed to IR8 and Taichung (Native) 1. The seedlings from each backcross generation were inoculated with the tungro virus and transplanted for observation and selection. Many of the seedlings which showed symptoms of the disease and were identified as susceptible recovered and looked healthy at the later growth stage. On the other hand, those seedlings which did not show any symptoms and were considered healthy became diseased at a later growth stage. Such changes were not observed in IR8. This seems to suggest that different genes for resistance are involved, and resistance at the seedling stage and at the adult stage may have to be considered separately in a genetic analysis of tungro resistance.

Grassy Stunt Disease

Antibiotics treatment

The grassy stunt disease was previously assumed to be caused by a virus because of its type of disease syndrome and its transmission by the brown plant-hopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal). Recently diseased specimens were sent to Hokkaido University, and ultrathin sections of the specimens were prepared and examined by Dr. E. Shikata. The electron micrographs demonstrated that the

mycoplasma-like bodies were present in the tissue. It is suspected that these bodies are caused by the mycoplasma-like organism, as in the case of the yellow dwarf disease.

Mycoplasma-like organisms are sensitive to antibiotics and diseased plants treated with antibiotics may be cured temporarily. However, if applying antibiotics would have a remarkable effect on the symptom expression of a diseased plant or on the infectivity of the vector by the mechanism of partial elimination of the causal agent, this would help to verify the nature of the causal agent by mycoplasma-like organism as well as to develop a possible means of control.

Four tetracyclines, namely, tetracycline (achromycin), chlortetracycline (aureomycin), dimethyl chlortetracycline, and oxytetracycline (terramycin) provided by Dr. E. Shikata were prepared at concentrations of 10, 50, 100, and 200 ppm and applied to plants infected with grassy stunt either by the root-dipping method or by foliage spray. The roots were dipped for 15, 24 and 48 hours. A total of 20 foliage sprays were applied at a frequency of three sprays a week. Four plants were used for each treatment. The treated plants were observed up to 13 weeks after the antibiotics were applied. There were no apparent differences in symptoms of diseased plants between the treated and untreated controls. However, the application of a high concentration of the compounds and the long dipping period resulted in a high yield percentage of dead plants.

Three tetracyclines at a concentration of 30 ppm were applied to healthy Taichung (Native) 1 seedlings by the root-dipping method. The durations of dipping were 1, 2, and 3 days immediately before or after seedling inoculation by viruliferous insects. For those inoculations made before treatment, 133 seedlings were used for each treatment, and for those made after treatment, 57 seedlings were used for each treatment. The average percentages of infected seedlings of the four inoculations made after treatment, were 83.7, 87.8, 86.7, and 85.0 for tetracycline, chlortetracycline, dimethyl chlortetracycline, and water (which served as the control), respectively. For inoculations made before treatment, the corresponding percentages were 87.1, 93.3, 91.9, and 95.4. The results did not show a significant reduction in the percentage of infected seedlings as a result of treatment with

any one of the three tetracyclines. There also was no striking difference among the three different dipping periods. Although this does not disprove the mycoplasma nature of the causal agent, the application of tested tetracyclines for grassy stunt disease control was not successful.

Assuming that *N. lugens* feeds on moist filter paper, viruliferous insects can be treated with tetracycline to determine the effect of the compound on the causal agent by testing the infectivity of the insects. Insects were confined in test tubes in which filter paper with various concentrations of tetracycline were placed. One day later, the surviving insects were transferred individually to healthy Taichung (Native) 1 seedlings to test their infectivity. The percentages of infective insects were 30.0, 36.7, 28.6, 24.1, and 21.4 for 0, 100, 200, 300, and 400 ppm tetracyclines, respectively. The corresponding average numbers of insect-infective days out of a period of 4 days were 3.27, 2.82, 2.91, 3.05, and 3.50. The result was not striking enough to indicate the reduction of infectivity of the insects by treatment with tetracycline.

Field dissemination

Except for a few cases, the incidence of grassy stunt disease in farmer's fields was generally much lower than that on the Institute farm, especially in the past 2 years. However, a severe case of plant damage due to *N. lugens*, commonly known as "hopper burn," was not limited to the Institute farm. Hence, disease incidence is not directly correlated to the population of the insect in the field, but should be determined by several factors such as activity and efficiency of the vector, availability of virus source and host susceptibility. To investigate the transmissible ability of *N. lugens* in farmer's fields, the insects were collected from various localities, including the area where "hopper burn" occurred. Immediately after they were collected the insects were tested individually to determine how many in the field population were infective. The insects were then confined on diseased plants for acquisition feeding. After an incubation period of 10 days, the insects were tested again for their ability to transmit the disease. Because of natural mortality of the insects, the number which survived was usually small after acquisition and incubation. The insects were

Table 15. Grassy stunt active transmitters of *Nilaparvata lugens* collected from different localities in the Philippines.

Insects collected from	No. of infective insects/no. tested		
	Field population	Field population after acquisition	F ₁ generation after acquisition
Muñoz, Nueva Ecija	0/35	6/8	31/62
Cabanatuan, Nueva Ecija	0/18	1/4	31/81
IRRI farm*	110/341		57/186
Tungtungin, Los Baños, Laguna**	2/86	18/80	20/90
Calo, Bay, Laguna**	0/230	3/15	26/111
Dila, Bay, Laguna**	0/200	50/98	44/143
San Juan, Lumban, Laguna	0/13	0/10	1/37
Bago, Negros Occidental*	83/273		24/75

* Grassy stunt disease present in farm.

** "Hopper burn" present in field.

reared in separate cages, and the first generation were tested for their transmissible ability after acquisition feeding. The results are shown in Table 15. Except for the insects collected from Tungtungin, as will be discussed later, the insects taken from fields where the grassy stunt disease did not occur were not infective regardless of the location of the field or of the occurrence of "hopper burn." However, some insects collected from the field where the disease occurred, e.g., the IRRI farm and the field in Boga, were infective. The percentage of infective insects of a field population varied among the insect samples. If the insects were sampled from diseased hills, the percentage of the infective ones was much higher than that of the insects collected from healthy hills in the same field. Two out of 86 insects collected from a field having no diseased hills in Tungtungin were infective. A possible explanation is the migration of the insects from the diseased field since Tungtungin is adjacent to the IRRI farm. However, the percentage of infective insects of a field population seems directly related to the incidence of the disease in the field.

The non-infectivity of the insects collected from fields where no disease occurred does not mean that the insects cannot transmit the disease. After acquisition feeding, some of them became infective and their progenies were also capable of transmitting the disease although the transmissible ability of *N. lugens* varied. Consequently, the low

incidence of grassy stunt disease in farmer's fields would be due primarily to the availability of source of causal agent in a locality and the migration of infective vectors rather than the inability of the insect to transmit the disease.

Transmission

Active transmitter. *N. lugens* is the only known vector of the disease. The percentage of active transmitters in a field population varied among localities (Table 15). However, except for the extreme cases, it was often in the range of 20 to 40 percent. The extreme cases could be lower than 3 percent or higher than 50 percent. Both nymphs and adults were able to transmit the disease. There were no consistent differences in the percentage of active transmitters between male and female adults, between insects of dark brown and light brown color, or between macropterous (long-winged) and brachypterous (with short or abbreviated wing) forms. However, the macropterous insects are suspected as being more capable of spreading the disease.

The percentage of active transmitters of an insect colony could be increased by selecting the active females and males for every successive generation. The highest percentage of active transmitters obtained after four generations was 82. But the percentage of increase of the active transmitters decreased gradually in successive genera-

Fig. 19. Daily serial transmission of grassy stunt infective *Nilaparvata lugens*.

tions when the selection of active parents was suspended.

Incubation period. Results of the daily serial transmissions (Fig. 19) indicated that the causal agent in the vector had a definite incubation period since not a single insect could become infective immediately after acquisition feeding. The incubation period varied from 5 to 28 days among individual insects. The average was 10.59 days, and the incubation period of about 80 percent infective insects was shorter than 11 days.

Retention period. Once the insects become infective, they often retain their infectivity for practically the rest of their lives. The longest retention period obtained was 40 days after acquisition feeding or 30 days after the insect became infective. However, a few infective insects retained their infectivity for only a few days and became non-infective until their death.

The retention of infectivity was not altered by insect moulting. The insects could acquire the

causal agent at the nymph stage and could become infective at the adult stage after two moultings without access to another diseased plant.

Transmission pattern. The hourly or daily transmission pattern of the infective insects is more of the intermittent than the consecutive type because more than 60 percent of the infective insects failed to transmit the disease consecutively at hourly or daily intervals. Except at 34 and 37 to 40 days after acquisition feeding, there was not a single day during which all the infective insects transmitted the disease (Fig. 18). The maximum percentage of infective insects in a single day was only about 86.

Disease-transmitting days. The average number of disease-transmitting days from the time the insects become infective until their death was 0.8068. In other words, the infective insects transmitted the disease for about 80 percent of the total number of days during the period. The average number of disease transmitting days during

Table 16. Percentage of grassy stunt-infected seedlings from various inoculation feeding periods.

Treatment	No. of seedlings inoculated/day	Inoculation feeding period (hours)	Infected seedlings (%)
I	2	6	28.0
		18	68.6
II	2	8	42.3
		16	60.6
III	1	24	72.6
IV	0.5	48	78.5

the period from 10 days after acquisition feeding until death was 0.7162. This means that when healthy seedlings were exposed to infective insects at the rate of one a day from 10 days after acquisition feeding until their death, an average of about 72 percent of the exposed seedlings became infected. The rest remained healthy.

Transovarial passage. No infective nymphs were obtained from eggs of infective females, indicating that there was no transovarial passage of the causal agent.

Inoculation feeding. To determine the time required by the insects to inoculate the seedlings, viruliferous insects were confined individually on healthy seedlings for 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 minutes. About 100 insects were used for each test. No positive transmission was obtained from an inoculation feeding period of 8 minutes or shorter. However, 2 and 3 percent infected seedlings were obtained from inoculation feeding periods of 9 and 10 minutes, respectively. Nine minutes may not be the minimum inoculation feeding period but it was the shortest inoculation feeding period during which positive transmission was obtained.

Viruliferous insects were also confined individually on healthy seedlings for inoculation feeding periods of 1 to 24 hours. About 400 insects were used for each treatment. The percentages of infected seedlings were 8.9, 9.5, 12.7, 17.8, and 33.4 for inoculation feeding periods of 1, 2, 4, 12, and 24 hours, respectively, indicating that the former percentage is correlated with the latter. Within 24 hours, the longer the inoculation feeding period, the higher the percentage of positive transmission.

Attempts were made to inoculate a larger number of seedlings per day by the same insect colony in order to develop a mass screening method for varietal resistance to grassy stunt. One or two seedlings were exposed to the insects for different periods each day. The percentages of infected seedlings varied according to the length of inoculation feeding period (Table 16). The highest percentage of infection was obtained from a 2-day inoculation feeding period but on the least number of seedlings inoculated per day among the treatments. Although the number of seedlings inoculated can be doubled by inoculating two sets of seedlings a day, the variation in infection should be eliminated in determining the varietal resistance. Considering both the percentage of infection and the number of seedlings inoculated per day, the inoculation feeding period of 1 day was applied in the mass screening method.

Starvation. Four groups of viruliferous insects were tested to determine the effect of starvation on the uniformity of seedling inoculation. The insects in the first group were starved for 2 hours before they were used for inoculation. The insects in the second and third groups were starved for 2 hours every other day. The fourth group was not starved to serve as the control. The treatments did not show any striking differences in percentage of infected seedlings.

Place of inoculation. Although brown plant-hoppers often confine themselves to the basal portion of rice plants, positive transmission can be obtained by confining the viruliferous insects on the leaf blade of the plant. When viruliferous individuals were confined alternately on the leaf blade and leaf sheath of rice seedlings, no significant difference in percentage of infected seedlings was obtained.

Transmission through seed

The transmission of grassy stunt disease through seeds was determined by observing seedlings grown from seeds harvested from diseased plants. A total of 2,411 seedlings were obtained from 6,110 discolored seeds and 5,488 seedlings from 7,015 non-discolored seeds. None of the total of 7,889 seedlings from 13,125 seeds harvested from diseased plants of several varieties developed symptoms. Hence, the disease apparently is not transmitted through seeds.

Fig. 20. Comparison of life span of *Nilaparvata lugens* after being fed on healthy and grassy stunt diseased plants for 15 days.

Life span of viruliferous insects

To determine the effect of the causal agent of grassy stunt on the life span of *N. lugens*, nymphs of the same colony were confined separately on healthy and diseased plants for 15 days. The insects were then transferred to healthy seedlings of Taichung (Native) 1 in test tubes. A total of 160 insects for each treatment from several tests were observed. The maximum life span obtained from both non-viruliferous and viruliferous insects was 45 days. However, the average life span of non-viruliferous insects (20.44 days) was significantly longer than that of viruliferous insects (16.06 days) (Fig. 20).

Among the viruliferous insects, the average life spans of 164 non-infective insects and 130 infective insects were 17.45 and 15.36 days, respectively. The LSD at 5 percent level was 1.86.

Mass screening method

A mass screening method for testing varietal resistance to the grassy stunt disease has been

developed. The method is a modification of that for testing tungro resistance, after taking into consideration the features of the vector-causal agent interaction. It consists of:

(1) An insect rearing procedure from which a new batch of insects is available at a constant interval.

(2) Diseased plants are provided to the insects at nymph stage. The insects are used for inoculation 10 to 11 days after acquisition feeding.

(3) Seedlings to be tested are transplanted to pots (19 seedlings per pot) and at the 2- to 3- leaf stage (11-13 days old) are subjected to inoculation.

(4) Seedlings are inoculated in cage. Each cage holds 16 pots (304 seedlings). The seedlings are exposed to viruliferous insects at 4 to 6 insects/seedling for 24 hours.

(5) The insects on the seedlings in the cages are gently disturbed to ensure their even distribution on every seedling.

(6) After inoculation, the seedlings are removed out of the cage for symptom development.

The insects left in the cage are ready for next inoculation after the number of insects has been adjusted.

To evaluate the accuracy of the method, 319 entries of Taichung (Native) 1 were used to test the reproducibility of results obtained by the method. Among the entries, the percentage of infected seedlings varied from 33.3 to 100 percent with an average value of 75.8 percent. The difference between two cages during a period of 10 days varied from 0.3 to 21.3 percent. The variation among dates for a period of 10 days was from 60.5 to 89.0 percent. Therefore, varieties which showed low percentage of infected seedlings in the preliminary screening test should be confirmed by further testing.

Varietal resistance

A total of 2,320 entries from 1,119 rice varieties and 11 selections of IR lines were tested for their resistance to the grassy stunt disease by the above-described method. Of 1,130 varieties and selections, 73 percent were definitely susceptible to the disease since their percentages of infected seedlings were higher than 60 in the preliminary screening test. The results of repeated tests of 299 varieties with percentages of infected seedlings less than 60 in the preliminary test indicated that not one of the test varieties was highly resistant to the disease because all the varieties showed more than 60 percent infection. However, four varieties with the lowest average percentages of infected seedlings (56-60%) from three tests were Pagey tinyagen dayket likwet, Mitao, Gendjah Banten, and Gowai 84.

The following Philippine Seed Board varieties were also tested for their resistance to grassy stunt disease: Azucena, Bengawan, BPI-76, Dinalaga, FB-121, IR5, IR8, Manarez, Seraup Kechil 36 str. 482, and Tjeremas. The average percentages of infected seedlings of these varieties from four tests ranged from 84 to 96 percent.

Reaction of Oryza spp. In searching for a source resistant to the grassy stunt disease, the following *Oryza* species were artificially inoculated: *O. alta*, *O. australiensis*, *O. breviligulata*, *O. latifolia*, *O. nivara*, *O. punctata*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa f. spontanea*, and *O. spontanea* (Australia). The result showed that all these species were not immune or highly resistant to the disease.

Likewise, they are hosts of the causal agent of the disease. However, *O. australiensis* and *O. sativa f. spontanea* seemed to be less susceptible than the other species tested.

Virus Disease in East Pakistan

A plant disorder which has been particularly observed in IR8 and other IRRI pedigree entries appeared during the Boro season in the Comilla-Dacca regions of East Pakistan. It was characterized by marked leaf yellowing and slight stunting. An investigation to determine the cause of the disease was conducted at Dacca from February 27 to May 28, 1968.

Field observations

A survey to determine the incidence of the disorder was made on 197 IRRI pedigree entries which were transplanted at the Comilla District Sub-station Farm in early December, 1967. The first reading taken on March 5 indicated that no entry was completely free from the disease. About 75 percent of the 7,082 hills observed were diseased. The second reading taken a month later showed that the disease incidence was significantly reduced as many of the plants recovered. Of the 6,738 surviving hills, only 31 percent remained diseased. Except for six entries which did not show any reduction or an increase in the percentage of diseased hills, the other 191 entries showed a decrease of from 3 to 81 percent. Entry 62444 recovered completely from about 28 percent diseased hills. Entry 60137 showed a remarkably high percentage of recovery as evidenced by the reduction of the diseased hills from 97 percent to 16 percent. The recovery of diseased plants might be related to the warm weather since the period from December to February of this year had the lowest temperature.

Symptoms

In March; the symptoms of the diseased plants were found to be similar. Two major symptoms were leaf yellowing and various degrees of stunting. In April, the symptoms of the individual diseased plants were found to differ. The diseased plants could be separated and grouped by symptom as follows:

- A. Diseased plants showing yellowing
 - a. Plant stunted

Table 17. Retention period of the tungro virus in *Nephotettix impicticeps* in East Pakistan.

Days after acquisition feeding	No. of infective insects/no. tested	Percentage of infective insects
1	25/45	55.6
2	11/39	28.2
3	4/35	11.3
4	1/30	3.3
5	0/28	0
6	0/28	0
7	0/28	0
8	0/28	0

1. Leaves without stripes

2. Leaves with stripes

b. Plants not stunted

B. Diseased plants showing no yellowing

1. Plants stunted

2. Plants stunted with leaf galls

3. Plants stunted with profuse tillers and narrow leaves.

Diseased plants under each of the above groups were not limited to one variety or one IRRI pedigree entry.

Fertilizer experiment

Fifty diseased plants of IR8 and Taipei 177 were taken from the field at Comilla and transplanted in pots. About 80 percent of them recovered from yellowing after they received complete fertilizer. In contrast, the control plants did not recover.

Transmission study

Forty-five *Nephotettix impicticeps* insects collected locally were fed for a day on infected Taichung (Native) 1 plants which showed yellowing and stunting. The insects were then transferred individually to healthy Taichung (Native) 1 seedlings at 4- to 5-leaf stage. About 56 percent of the inoculated seedlings developed symptoms 8 to 15 days after inoculation. The causal agent of the disease could be transmitted by either the nymph or the adult insect. The results obtained from daily

serial transfers of viruliferous *N. impicticeps* insects to healthy Taichung (Native) 1 seedlings (Table 17) indicated that the percentage of infective insects decreased gradually with time following acquisition feeding. The longest retention period obtained was 4 days. Fifteen of the 28 surviving insects had previously been infective, indicating that the virus does not persist in the vector.

Attempts have been made to transmit the causal agent of diseased plants with stripes and diseased plants with galls by several species of insects (*Thaia oryzivora*, *Inazuma dorsalis*, *N. impicticeps*, *Cicadulina bipunctella*, *Macrosteles* sp. and 4 unidentified cicadellids). No positive transmission was obtained.

Starch accumulation test

A total of 110 diseased hills of IR5, IR8, IR9-60, and Muktuswar sampled from fields at Kodda, Comilla, and Mohannadpur, Dacca, were iodine tested for the accumulation of starch in the leaf blade. Only 15 percent of the sampled hills gave positive reaction.

From the above information, it can be concluded that the disease which appeared in East Pakistan might at that time not have been caused by a single factor since a high percentage of the plants recovered from the disease either in the field or in pots with complete fertilizer. However, at least 8 percent of the diseased hills were infected by a virus. Based on symptomatology, vector species, and virus-vector interaction, the disease is similar, if not identical, to the tungro disease in the Philippines. The results constitute the first experimental evidence of the existence of hitherto unreported virus disease of rice in East Pakistan. No positive results have been obtained on the nature of the diseased plants showing stripes on leaves and galls that resemble the stripe and black-streaked dwarf diseases of the rice plant reported in Japan, respectively.

Soil Chemistry

The themes of this report are manganese equilibria in flooded soils, chemical analysis of submerged soils, temperature of flooded soils and the growth of rice, remedies for physiological disorders of rice, liming of acid rice soils, and water regime in rice soils.

Manganese equilibria in flooded soils appeared to be regulated by complex oxides of manganese rather than by their ideal counterparts.

Chemical analysis of the solutions of flooded soils revealed (a) the superiority of gas chromatography to titration for the assay of carbon dioxide, and (b) no significant changes in the concentration of boron but a decrease in that of zinc during 6 weeks of submergence.

A regime in which the soil temperature decreased progressively from 35 C at flooding and planting to 20 C at harvest produced the best chemical environment and the highest yield of rice; a constant temperature of 20 C, the worst chemical milieu and the lowest yield. A constant temperature of 30 C was slightly inferior to the falling temperature regime but considerably superior to the rising regime (15-30 C). The adverse effects of unfavorable soil temperature were most severe in the Akiuchi soil from Korea and least in Maahas clay, and ideal lowland rice soil.

Delaying submergence of the soil until a week before panicle primordia initiation was the simplest and most effective remedy for suffocation disease on two problem soils from Taiwan. Liming a strongly acid ferralitic soil did not benefit rice. Two years of continuous submergence did not depress the yield of rice on three widely differing soils.

Manganese Equilibria in Flooded Soils

In studies of the chemical and electrochemical changes in flooded soils reported earlier (1964, 1965, and 1967 Annual Reports), it was observed that soils well supplied with native or added manganese had more positive redox potentials, lower concentrations of water-soluble Fe^{++} , and lower partial pressures of CO_2 than other soils. The attempts to explain these observations (1964 Annual Report) were extended and refined by (a) the application of new theoretical concepts and (b) equilibration studies of reduced soils in the laboratory.

It is now proposed that (a) the higher potentials of flooded manganiferous soils are due to the presence of complex oxides of manganese and iron whose apparent standard free energies of formation are considerably less than those of their ideal counterparts, (b) the lower concentrations of water-soluble Fe^{++} in these soils stem from the presence of solid solutions of Fe_3O_4 and Mn_3O_4 rather than the hydrated Fe_3O_4 associated with reduced ferruginous soils, and (c) the lower partial pressures of CO_2 derive from the precipitation of MnCO_3 . Thermodynamic proof of these concepts and a discussion of their implications for rice culture follow.

Redox potential and complex oxides of manganese

The redox potentials of flooded manganiferous soils, though more positive than those of other soils, are not high enough to be associated with the pure oxides MnO_2 , Mn_2O_3 , or Mn_3O_4 . This may be due to either the absence of true equilibria between the oxidized and reduced species or the presence of more stable forms of these oxides. The criterion for thermodynamic equilibrium is the constancy of E_0 of the system whose presence is suspected, in spite of variations in Eh, pH, activity of water-soluble Mn^{++} , and P_{CO_2} . This test revealed the presence of distinct equilibria at different stages of submergence in (a) a synthetic medium of sand, MnO_2 , and organic matter incubated anaerobically (Table 1) and (b) 16 flooded lowland rice soils. The systems and their observed E_0 's (extracted from Table 1) along with the corresponding theoretical values are as follows:

Dominant system	Duration (weeks)	E_0 (volts)	
		Observed	Theoretical
$\text{MnO}_2 - \text{Mn}^{++}$	1 - 4	0.79	1.23
$\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Mn}^{++}$	3 - 8	1.12	1.45
$\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{Mn}^{++}$	3 - 8	1.44	1.82
$\text{MnO}_2 - \text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3$	1 - 5	0.50	1.01
$\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{MnCO}_3$	8 - 10	0.65	0.97
$\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{MnCO}_3$	8 - 10	0.68	1.10

The observed E_0 's are considerably lower than those of the ideal systems. The lower E_0 's indicate the presence of more stable oxides. This may be ascribed to the strong tendency of Mn to form non-stoichiometric complex oxides whose apparent standard free energies of formation are considerably less than those of their ideal counterparts. These energies of formation are compared below with the experimental values for the synthetic medium and the soils.

Solid Species	Standard free energy of formation (Kcal per mole at 25 C)		
	Ideal	Sand + MnO_2 (observed)	Soils (observed)
MnO_2	-111.1	-130.9	-126.8 to -134.1
Mn_2O_3	-212.3	-227.2	-223.2 to -232.3
Mn_3O_4	-306.2	-323.6	-321.3 to -331.9
MnCO_3	-194.3	-193.7	-193.7 to -194.1

Table 2 shows the influence of soil properties on the apparent standard free energies of the hypothetical oxides, derived from E_0 's of the systems whose presence was recognized. These figures indicate that (a) the apparent standard free energies are considerably lower than the theoretical values; (b) the oxides present in Soil 4 are apparently considerably more reactive than those even in the sand - MnO_2 medium; (c) $\Delta F^0_{\text{MnO}_2}$ decreases as the manganese content of the soil declines; and (d) $\Delta F^0_{\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3}$ and/or $\Delta F^0_{\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4}$ may differ for two soils even though $\Delta F^0_{\text{MnO}_2}$ may be the same (cf. Soils 7 and 10, 17 and 26, 28 and 14).

These observations are compatible with the hypothesis that the manganese oxides involved in redox equilibria in soils that undergo reversible oxidation-reduction are complex oxides of manganese and iron whose composition and solid state vary with the environment in which they are formed and whose apparent standard free energies

Table 1. Influence of changes in pH, Eh, P_{CO_2} , and Mn^{++} concentration of the aqueous phase of a mixture of quartz sand, organic matter, MnO_2 , and water incubated anaerobically on the E_0 values and on the value of the expression, $pH + \frac{1}{2} \log Mn^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log P_{CO_2} = K$.

Weeks incu- bated	pH	Eh (mv)	P_{CO_2} (atm.)	Mn^{++} (ppm)	E_0^1 *	E_0^2	E_0^3	E_0^4	E_0^5	E_0^6	K
0.5	6.08	20	0.35	84	0.64	0.90	1.16	0.38	0.41	0.42	4.20
1	6.65	110	0.14	156	0.80	1.10	1.41	0.50	0.55	0.58	4.69
2	6.40	112	0.30	342	0.78	1.08	1.38	0.49	0.52	0.54	4.73
3	6.69	110	0.14	325	0.79	1.12	1.45	0.50	0.56	0.57	4.85
4	6.81	87	0.08	200	0.80	1.12	1.45	0.49	0.55	0.59	4.79
5	6.78	95	0.06	124	0.81	1.12	1.44	0.50	0.56	0.60	4.65
6	6.70	127	0.07	75	0.82	1.12	1.43	0.52	0.59	0.63	4.48
7	6.71	120	0.05	86	0.82	1.12	1.43	0.52	0.59	0.63	4.49
8	6.59	160	0.07	76	0.84	1.14	1.44	0.55	0.61	0.65	4.40
10	6.60	192	0.05	67	0.88	1.17	1.47	0.58	0.66	0.69	4.36
15	6.58	178	0.05	74	0.86	1.16	1.46	0.57	0.64	0.68	4.35

* $E_0^1 = Eh + .0295 \log Mn^{++} + .118 pH$

$E_0^2 = Eh + .059 \log Mn^{++} + .177 pH$

$E_0^3 = Eh + .089 \log Mn^{++} + .236 pH$

$E_0^4 = Eh + .059 pH$

$E_0^5 = Eh - .059 \log P_{CO_2} + .059 pH$

$E_0^6 = Eh - .089 \log P_{CO_2} + .059 pH$

of formation are much less than those of their ideal counterparts.

Figure 1 shows the stability areas of the oxides of manganese assumed to be present in manganese soils. The diagram is based on the following apparent standard free energies of formation in kcal per mole at 25 C:

$\Delta F^0_{MnO_2} = -127,$ $\Delta F^0_{Mn_2O_3} = -225$

$\Delta F^0_{Mn_3O_4} = -322,$ $\Delta F^0_{MnCO_3} = -194$

It may be used to interpret manganese transformation in reduced soils. The Eh of the solutions of flooded soils high in manganese is usually 0.1 to 0.2 volt at a pH of 6.5-7.0, and P_{CO_2} is 0.05 to 0.1 atm. In this region, the stable solid phases are MnO_2 (at Eh's higher than 0.17 volt), Mn_2O_3 , and

$MnCO_3$. If the activity of Mn^{++} and/or P_{CO_2} increases, the $MnCO_3 - Mn^{++}_{aq}$ boundary will move left, enlarging the $MnCO_3$ area and excluding Mn_2O_3 and Mn_3O_4 . The situation will be reversed if Mn^{++}_{aq} or P_{CO_2} decreases. For soils low in manganese (in which the less reactive forms of the manganese oxides are involved), the $MnO_2 - Mn^{++}$ boundary will be depressed 0.1 to 0.2 volt, narrowing the Mn^{++}_{aq} area.

Diagrams like this may be useful in the study of manganese availability even in aerobic soils if E_0 's peculiar to each soil are used. Variations in the thermochemical properties of manganese oxides and the possible role of $MnCO_3$ may account for some of the difficulties encountered in relating manganese availability in upland soils to pH, Eh, or total manganese content.

Table 2. Influence of soil properties on the apparent standard free energies of formation of the species of MnO_2 , Mn_2O_3 , and Mn_3O_4 assumed to be present in flooded soils to which no fresh organic matter was added.

Soil no.	Texture	pH	O.M. (%)	Mn (%)	Fe (%)	ΔF^0		
						MnO_2	Mn_2O_3	Mn_3O_4
						(kcal per mole at 25C)		
0		Sand + Manganese dioxide				-130.9	-225.9	-322.4
4	clay	6.9	2.0	0.24	0.91	-125.0	-221.3	-319.0
7	clay	5.9	3.3	0.33	1.67	-127.7	-225.9	-324.5
27	clay	6.6	2.0	0.31	1.60	-127.7	-224.5	-323.6
10	clay	5.4	1.5	0.20	1.67	-127.7	-226.8	-326.4
3	clay	5.7	1.3	0.36	0.79	-128.6	-227.7	-323.6
17	clay	7.0	1.8	0.15	1.03	-129.1	-229.1	-328.0
26	clay loam	7.7	1.5	0.06	0.30	-129.2	-226.7	-324.1
9	sandy loam	6.0	4.0	0.05	0.21	-133.6	-236.0	-337.0
28	clay	4.7	3.2	0.05	2.91	-134.0	-236.0	-338.4
14	clay	4.6	2.8	0.06	2.13	-134.1	-234.6	-335.4
1	fine sand	7.6	2.3	0.03	0.18	-136.0	-236.9	-337.4
23	sandy loam	5.7	8.0	0.03	0.47	-136.5	-237.4	-338.4
39	silt loam	5.8	3.4	0.02	1.30	-136.9	-236.5	-336.1
24	sandy loam	5.3	3.8	0.01	1.32	-137.2	-238.3	-340.2
21	clay	4.6	4.1	0.02	2.78	-137.4	-238.3	-339.3
18	sandy loam	5.6	6.0	0.005	0.27	-138.3	-238.8	-340.7

Manganous carbonate in flooded soils

A remarkable feature of Table 1 is the relative constancy of the value of the expression, $pH + \frac{1}{2} \log Mn^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log P_{CO_2} = K$, during the last 10 weeks of submergence when redox criteria indicate the presence of $MnCO_3$. This is additional proof of the presence of solid phase $MnCO_3$. The higher value of K (4.4) compared with the theoretical value (4.1) indicates that the $MnCO_3$ present in the synthetic medium of sand, MnO_2 and organic matter, incubated anaerobically, is more soluble than $MnCO_3$ precipitated *in vitro*, as was noted earlier for a submerged manganese-rich soil (1964 Annual Report). In view of the role of $MnCO_3$ in regulating PCO_2 and the concentration of Mn^{++} in flooded soils after the peak of water-soluble Mn^{++} , the specific problem was studied in the laboratory.

Samples of four reduced soils high in manganese or low in iron were taken at three intervals of submergence and equilibrated with 1-100% CO_2 - N_2 mixtures, and pH and Mn^{++} activity determined. Table 3 shows the remarkable constancy of the value of the expression, $pH + \frac{1}{2} \log$

$Mn^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log P_{CO_2} = K$, over the 4-15 week period of submergence for each soil. As before, the values of K exceed the theoretical value. This confirms the greater solubility of the species of $MnCO_3$ present in flooded soils.

Implications for rice culture

The presence of native or added manganese oxides in flooded soils should (a) retard the decrease of redox potential, (b) depress the concentration of water-soluble Fe^{++} both by retarding the reduction of iron and decreasing the activity of Fe_3O_4 in the solid solution, $(Fe, Mn)_3O_4$ and (c) lower the concentration of CO_2 .

These properties of manganese render MnO_2 a fruitful amendment for flooded soils in which excess organic reduction products, Fe^{++} , or CO_2 , are factors retarding the growth of rice.

Chemical Analysis of Flooded Soils

Because chemical analysis is one of the main tools in the theoretical study of flooded soils and the

Fig. 1. Stability areas of the hypothetical manganese oxides, $Mn(OH)_2$, and $MnCO_3$, relative to a Mn^{++aq} activity of 10^{-4} , and a P_{CO_2} of 0.1 atm at a total pressure of 1 atm, at 25C, for flooded soils high in manganese.

diagnosis of soil problems, a constant effort is made to improve and simplify analytical procedures by examining and modifying procedures developed for other media.

The studies on the determination of CO_2 and H_2S were continued and the methods for the assay of boron, sulfate, and zinc in flooded soils tested.

Partial pressure of CO_2

The gas chromatographic method of determining CO_2 in the solutions of flooded soils (1967 Annual Report) was compared with the titration method and found to be more reliable, especially for acid soils. As suspected earlier (1964, 1967 Annual Reports), organic acids and their salts (which are known to be more stable in acid soils) inflate P_{CO_2} values derived from methyl orange alkalinity and pH. This is clear from the values exceeding 1 atm in the Korean silt loam and Louisiana clay, 2 weeks after flooding (Table 4).

H_2S by the sulfide ion electrode

The sulfide ion electrode which was sensitive and accurate in solutions of sodium sulfide (1967

Annual Report) proved disappointing with solutions of flooded soils, apparently because at the pH values of flooded soils (6.5 - 7.0) the electrode was operating at the limit of its sensitivity. Despite this drawback, in a study of four problem rice soils, the electrode showed that the concentration of H_2S was least in the Akiuchi soil from Korea (on which a physiological disorder attributed to H_2S occurs) and highest in the "straighthead" soil from Texas, although none of the concentrations exceeded 0.05 ppm.

Polarographic assay of SO_4^{--}

The polarographic method of Khan and Webster (Soil Sci. 105, 1968) was tested with the solutions of seven widely differing soils. The precision ranged from 3.4 percent for the soil with 102 ppm SO_4^{--} to 7.2 percent for one with 22 ppm SO_4^{--} . The mean recovery of added SO_4^{--} (100.3% to 94.2%) followed the same pattern.

This method seems suitable for submerged soil solutions with more than 45 ppm SO_4^{--} .

Kinetics of water-soluble boron and zinc in flooded soils

In view of the recent observations of boron toxicity (Annual Report 1965) and zinc deficiency (1967 Annual Report) on certain rice soils, the curcumin method for boron and atomic absorption spectrophotometry for zinc were applied to the study of the kinetics of these two elements in some representative rice soils.

Table 5 shows no significant changes in the concentrations of water-soluble boron during the 1-5 week period of submergence. It is noteworthy that Shuchia silt loam (a soil on which a physiological disorder of rice occurs) had the highest concentration of boron. The concentrations of zinc were highest in the strongly acid soil from Vietnam and lowest in the two sandy soils (the sandy loam from Korea and Casiguran sandy loam) and in Pila clay loam, a calcareous soil, during the 1-5 week period of submergence.

Soil Temperature and the Growth of Rice

Soil temperature can influence the growth of rice on flooded soils through its effects on (a) the metabolic activity of the roots and (b) anaerobic soil metabolism. As there are abundant data on the

Table 3. Values of the expression $\text{pH} + \frac{1}{2} \log \text{Mn}^{++} + \frac{1}{2} \log P_{\text{CO}_2} = \text{K}$ for four reduced soils equilibrated with different P_{CO_2} 's at three intervals of submergence.

Soil no.	Texture	pH	O.M. (%)	Mn (%)	k for weeks submerged		
					4	8	15
3	clay	5.7	1.3	0.36	4.59	4.56	4.59
4	clay	6.9	2.2	0.24	4.50	4.46	4.47
26	clay loam	7.7	1.5	0.06	4.35	4.38	n.d.
27	clay	6.6	2.0	0.31	4.40	4.37	4.35

influence of temperature on nutrient and water uptake by rice in culture solutions but very little on its influence on the chemical environment in flooded soils, studies on the effects of soil temperature on the chemical kinetics of flooded soils and the growth of rice, begun in 1967, were continued. This section describes a follow-up of the earlier constant temperature study and a new experiment involving different temperature regimes.

Influence of different constant soil temperatures on the growth of rice

Temperature markedly affects metabolic processes in flooded soils and consequently the availability of nutrients and the generation of toxic substances. The earlier study (1967 Annual Report) suggested that the unfavorable effects of a constant low temperature (15 C) were low availability of N and P and high concentrations of CO_2 in the early stages in some soils and the late buildup of toxic concentrations of Fe^{++} and CO_2 in other soils. The adverse effects of a high soil temperature (45 C) appeared to be associated with high initial concentrations of NH_3 , Fe^{++} , CO_2 , and reducing substances.

To test these hypotheses, immediately after the first harvest, the soils, while still submerged, were treated with 50 ppm each of N, P, and K, and 20-day-old IR5 seedlings planted in them. Fertilizer N, P, K, it was believed, would offset the unfavorable effect of low temperature on nutrient release, while prolonged submergence would produce a milieu low in Fe^{++} , organic reducing substances, and CO_2 . The substantially higher yields of straw at 15 C and 45 C than in the first

experiment (Table 6) indicate a more favorable chemical environment for rice roots in the second experiment. Chemical kinetics of the soils confirmed this. Chemical kinetics also indicated that the poor growth of rice in Louisiana clay at 15 C was due to the persistence of high concentrations of Fe^{++} and CO_2 and the death of plants at 45 C in the Korean silt loam to an inexplicable resurgence of high concentrations of Fe^{++} , CO_2 , and reducing substances.

These results show that a substantial component of the adverse effects of too low or too high a soil temperature on the growth of rice is the chemical environment dependent on bacterial activity. The remarkably good vegetative growth and grain yield on Maahas clay (an ideal lowland rice soil) at 15 C and the substantial straw yield at 45 C confirm this (Table 6).

Soil temperature regime and the growth of rice

The previous constant temperature study revealed that 25 to 35 C was optimum for rice, while 15 and 45 C were injurious, largely for chemical reasons. Although these experiments demonstrated the tremendous influence of soil temperature on the chemical milieu of rice roots relative to root physiology, the treatments did not reflect adequately the temperatures obtained under field conditions during the rice-growing season. Therefore the influence of four soil temperature regimes on the chemical kinetics and the growth of rice on light soils was studied. The regimes correspond to those obtaining in Korea, in the tropical highlands, in the tropical lowlands, and in Taiwan during the second crop. The soils included an Akiuchi soil from Korea and a soil from Taiwan on

Table 4. Comparison of the gas chromatographic (GLC) and titration methods of determining PCO_2 of seven flooded soils at five intervals of submergence.

Weeks submerged	Method	Silo silt loam pH 8.1	Pila clay loam pH 7.6	Maahas clay pH 6.6	Tungshan silt loam pH 5.8	Casiguran sandy loam pH 4.9	Korea silt loam pH 4.8	Luisiana clay pH 4.7
Partial pressure of carbon dioxide in atm.								
0	GLC	0.04	0.008	0.01	0.17	0.02	0.05	0.02
	Titration	0.06	0.008	0.03	0.13	0.16	0.13	0.11
2	GLC	0.21	0.40	0.23	0.27	0.34	0.30	0.57
	Titration	0.27	0.50	0.27	0.38	0.68	1.45	1.13
4	GLC	0.21	0.31	0.13	0.26	0.37	0.25	0.46
	Titration	0.24	0.44	0.17	0.29	0.42	0.44	0.56
6	GLC	0.16	0.32	0.11	0.31	0.38	0.27	0.24
	Titration	0.18	0.38	0.17	0.33	0.47	0.43	0.35
8	GLC	0.16	0.31	0.12	0.26	0.34	0.20	0.20
	Titration	0.16	0.40	0.15	0.28	0.43	0.25	0.24

Table 5. Kinetics of boron and zinc in the solutions of nine flooded soils.

Soil	pH	O.M. (%)	Element	Weeks submerged				
				0	1	2	3	5
Acid sulfate clay (VietNam)	3.6	9.6	B	.30	.48	.40	.52	.57
			Zn	.65	.70	.65	.59	.44
Sandy loam (Korea)	5.5	1.6	B	.26	.25	.20	.21	.20
			Zn	.56	.14	.08	.05	.06
Shuchia silt loam	7.8	2.1	B	.24	.80	.77	.78	.81
			Zn	.16	.16	.11	.10	.10
Pila clay loam	7.6	1.5	B	.36	.32	.34	.34	.25
			Zn	.10	.13	.11	.10	.10
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	B	.29	.42	.36	.41	.39
			Zn	.12	.13	.09	.09	.05
Sandy loam (Texas)	6.2	1.5	B	.46	.29	.26	.29	.22
			Zn	.41	.19	.12	.10	.08
Keelung silt loam	7.7	7.6	B	.58	.24	.28	.30	.26
			Zn	.14	.23	.10	.09	.08
Casiguran sandy loam	4.9	5.3	B	.74	.22	—	.26	.20
			Zn	.22	.10	.09	.10	.07
Luisiana clay	4.7	3.2	B	.24	.22	.24	.27	—
			Zn	.29	.65	.25	.10	.09

Fig. 2. Influence of temperature regime on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ in the Korean silt loam.

which suffocation disease occurs. Pertinent details of these soils are in Table 7, and the temperature regimes in Table 8.

Ten-kilogram portions of each soil were mixed in the air-dry state with 0.2 percent of chopped straw and 1 percent of fresh *Glyricidia sepium* leaves along with 50 ppm each of N, P, and K. They were placed in four tanks of water fitted with thermoregulators, and the temperature treatments started after submerging the soils with water at the appropriate temperature. Twenty-day-old IR5 seedlings were planted immediately.

Temperature regime markedly influenced the chemical changes in these soils and the growth of IR5. Generally, the chemical and electrochemical changes associated with the anaerobic metabolism of the soils proceeded at the rates shown below:

$$35 \rightarrow 20\text{C} > 30\text{C} > 20\text{C} > 15 \rightarrow 30 \rightarrow 25\text{C}$$

There were, however, severe soil-temperature interactions, and these were reflected in the growth and yield of the rice plants.

pH changes. The differential influence of temperature regime was most apparent in the acid soils and least in the nearly neutral soils (Table 9).

Luisiana clay attained the favorable pH of 6.5 within 4 weeks of submergence in the high-initial-temperature treatment (35 → 20 C); at the low initial temperatures, it took 8 weeks. Maahas clay showed no significant differences.

Kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺. Temperature regime profoundly influenced the kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺. In all soils, the regimes with a high initial temperature hastened and shortened the peak of Fe⁺⁺, but the effects were most pronounced in the acid soils as illustrated by the kinetics of Fe⁺⁺ in the Korean silt loam, pH 4.8 (Fig. 2). These low and early peaks of Fe⁺⁺ at the high initial temperatures meant (a) a low overall Fe⁺⁺ concentration and (b) an absence of the harmful effects of excess iron at the critical stage of panicle primordia initiation.

A low initial temperature retarded the solubilization of iron in the early stages only to produce a massive buildup 6 to 8 weeks after submergence in all the acid soils except Casiguran sandy loam. In this soil, as was observed earlier (1967 Annual Report), low temperature did not prevent the early buildup of high concentrations while high initial temperatures markedly depressed them (Fig. 3). The concentrations of Fe⁺⁺ declined more slowly in the continuously low temperature treatment (20 C) than in the 15 → 30 → 26 C regime. The opposite was true in the initially higher temperature regimes: the decline was faster in the 35 → 20 C than at a constant temperature of 30 C.

Fig. 3. Influence of temperature regime on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ in Casiguran sandy loam.

Table 6. Influence of soil temperature on the growth and yield of rice on seven submerged soils in two seasons.

Soil	pH	O.M. (%)		First crop				Second crop			
				15C	25C	35C	45C	15C	25C	35C	45C
				(g per pot)				(g per pot)			
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	straw	27	95	77	0.5	110	107	126	51
			grain	17	93	81	0	44	83	80	3.0
Luisiana clay	4.6	3.2	straw	1.0	35	16	—	3.8	173	160	27
			grain	0	37	15	—	0	130	145	0
Pila clay loam	7.6	1.5	straw	1.2	42	33	—	58	114	112	14
			grain	0	27	36	—	0	79	72	0.2
Casiguran sandy loam	4.8	4.0	straw	4.7	64	63	28	79	66	93	68
			grain	0.9	83	94	39	0	73	87	8.6
Tungshan silt loam	5.8	3.4	straw	—	0.4	1.7	—	20	64	105	17
			grain	—	0	0	—	0	37	99	0
Marilao clay loam	4.7	1.3	straw	—	21	17	—	32	95	107	16
			grain	—	27	18	—	0	66	70	0
Korean silt loam	4.8	2.8	straw	0.1	21	31	—	11	72	93	—
			grain	0	31	41	—	0	53	57	—

(-) dead

Table 7. Soil properties.

Soil	pH (1:1)	O.M. (%)	Total N (%)	Active Fe (%)	Active Mn (%)
Casiguran sandy loam	4.9	5.3	0.27	0.35	0.005
Korean (1) silt loam	4.8	2.8	0.18	0.48	0.003
Korean (2) sandy loam	4.8	1.6	0.09	0.41	0.001
Albay sandy loam	5.9	4.0	0.21	0.75	0.026
Pila clay loam	7.7	1.5	0.09	0.95	0.053
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	0.13	2.18	0.163
Keelung silt loam	7.9	6.9	0.43	2.30	0.065
Luisiana clay	4.8	3.2	0.19	3.30	0.048

Table 8. Temperature regimes

Week	Temperature treatment (C)			
	1*	2**	3†	4††
0-1	15	20	30	35
1-2	17	20	30	35
2-3	19	20	30	35
3-4	21	20	30	35
4-5	23	20	30	35
5-6	24	20	30	33
6-7	25	20	30	32
7-8	26	20	30	30
8-9	27	20	30	28
9-10	28	20	30	27
10-11	29	20	30	26
11-12	30	20	30	25
12-13	28	20	30	24
13-14	27	20	30	23
14-15	26	20	30	22
15-16	25	20	30	20

* Korean regime.

** Tropical highlands.

† Tropical lowlands.

†† Taiwan second crop regime.

The temperature effects on Fe^{++} kinetics were most pronounced in the Korean silt loam and least in Maahas clay.

Kinetics of water-soluble Mn^{++} . The pattern of Mn^{++} kinetics was roughly parallel to that of Fe^{++} but the influence of temperature was much less severe, as was noted in the earlier experiment (1967 Annual Report).

Kinetics of water-soluble NH_4^+ . The changes in concentration at NH_4^+ are difficult to interpret because of the complications caused by cation exchange reactions and differential plant uptake. But the kinetics of NH_4^+ in Keelung silt loam (Fig. 4) in which the growth of rice was negligible confirms the earlier finding that a high temperature markedly accelerates the release of NH_4^+ . A temperature of 35 C for the first weeks of submergence enabled the release of more NH_4^+ than a constant temperature of 30 or 20 C for many more weeks.

Kinetics of NO_3^- . The behavior of NO_3^- was most unusual. Regardless of temperature regime, soil, and initial nitrate content, after 2 weeks of submergence, the concentration of NO_3^- -N was less than 1 ppm. It is interesting to note that low temperature did not retard denitrification.

Kinetics of water-soluble P. High initial temperatures produced concentrations of water-soluble P which tended to be higher than those in the low-temperature treatments. The lowest concentration of P for a given soil was in the 20 C treatment (Table 10). The effect of temperature was least in Maahas clay (as it was for Fe^{++}).

Kinetics of SO_4^{--} . The two temperature regimes with a high initial temperature favored the reduction of SO_4^{--} in all soils, but low temperature retardation was most pronounced in the Korean silt loam and least in Casiguran sandy loam (Table 11).

Growth and yield of rice. Temperature regime markedly influenced the growth and yield of rice but the effects varied with the soil (Table 12).

On the acid soils (except Louisiana clay), the 35 → 20 C regime gave the highest grain yield, with 30 C coming a close second; 20 C was by far the worst. The better growth and yield of rice on these

Fig. 4. Influence of temperature regime on the kinetics of water-soluble NH_4^+ in Keelung silt loam.

Table 9. Influence of soil temperature on pH kinetics in three flooded soils.

Soil texture	Temperature regime *	pH at weeks submerged					
		0	2	4	6	8	10
Louisiana clay, pH 4.8, O.M. 3.2%	15→28	5.15	5.18	5.75	6.15	6.48	6.61
	20	5.24	4.90	5.95	6.20	6.48	6.61
	30	5.32	6.20	6.40	6.44	6.60	6.75
	35→27	5.47	6.25	6.50	6.41	6.64	6.75
Korean silt loam, pH 4.8, O.M. 2.8%	15→28	4.56	4.80	4.76	5.05	5.43	6.20
	20	4.51	4.82	5.05	5.36	5.89	6.18
	30	4.39	5.40	6.30	6.12	6.17	6.10
	35→27	4.35	6.00	6.32	6.22	6.25	5.90
Maahas clay, pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%	15→28	6.24	6.90	6.82	6.68	6.80	6.86
	20	6.19	7.00	6.84	6.65	6.82	6.77
	30	6.49	6.92	6.75	6.65	6.70	6.76
	35→27	6.24	6.90	6.80	6.74	6.67	6.78

* Up to the 10th week.

Table 10. Influence of temperature regime on the kinetics of water-soluble P in three flooded soils.

Soil	Temperature regime *	Weeks submerged			
		4	6	8	10
Casiguran sandy loam, pH 4.9, O. M. 5.3%	15 → 28	2.7	1.6	1.1	1.4
	20	2.4	1.2	1.1	0.9
	30	3.5	1.2	1.1	0.8
	35 → 27	3.9	2.3	1.0	0.9
Korean silt loam, pH 4.8, O. M. 2.8%	15 → 28	1.1	0.4	0.5	0.5
	20	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.2
	30	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.3
	35 → 27	1.6	0.8	0.2	0.1
Maahas clay pH 6.6, O. M. 2.0%	15 → 28	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.4
	20	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.1
	30	0.6	0.6	0.3	0.1
	35 → 27	0.8	0.6	0.3	0.2

* Up to the 10th week.

Table 11. Influence of temperature regime on the kinetics of water-soluble SO_4^{--} in three flooded soils.

Soil	Temperature regime *	Weeks submerged			
		2	4	6	8
Casiguran sandy loam, pH 4.9, O.M. 5.3%	15 → 26	125	0	0	0
	20	50	0	0	0
	30	3	0	0	0
	35 → 30	0	0	0	0
Korean silt loam, pH 4.8, O.M. 2.8%	15 → 26	700	710	450	0
	20	900	850	295	0
	30	625	0	0	0
	35 → 30	175	0	0	0
Maahas clay pH 6.6, O.M. 2.0%	15 → 26	438	20	0	0
	20	205	5	0	0
	30	0	0	0	0
	35 → 30	0	0	0	0

* Up to the 8th week.

soils in the 35 → 20 C and 30 C treatments can be correlated with (a) a better supply of P and N (Table 10 and Fig. 4), (b) much lower overall concentrations of water-soluble Fe^{++} due to hastening and shortening of the peaks (Figs. 2 and 3) and (c) increased uptake of water and nutrients. The higher grain yield in the 35 → 20 C treatment than at 30 C may be ascribed partly to the more rapid decline in concentration of Fe^{++} referred to under kinetics of water-soluble iron. The chemical reasons for the very poor growth and yield at 20 C are (a) excess iron (and associated retarding factors) and (b) low P supply. The adverse effects of low temperature were most pronounced in the Korean silt loam. The soil built up a concentration of 620 ppm Fe^{++} at a temperature of 20 C compared with a peak of 280 at 35 → 20 C (Fig.2). Thus the physiological disorder of rice, known as *Akiuchi*, frequently attributed to a high temperature in late summer, may in fact be due to low soil temperature. Also, Fe^{++} rather than H_2S appears to be the chief injurious factor.

The response to temperature regime was least in Maahas clay. Is it a coincidence that, in this soil, temperature hardly affected (a) pH changes (Table 9), (b) the release of P (Table 10), (c) water-soluble Fe^{++} (peak values ranged from 67 to 83 ppm), and (d) reducing substances (peaks: 15.2 - 20.0 m.e./l)? Maahas clay produced 143 g of straw and 108 g of grain at 20 C; 140 g of straw and 119 g of grain at 15 → 30 → 25 C. These yields are not significantly different from those of the best temperature regime in this experiment although 20 C and 15 → 30 → 25 C proved injurious on other soils. This confirms the earlier observation (1967 Annual Report) that the ill effects of an unfavorable soil temperature are largely chemical.

As emphasized earlier (1967 Annual Report), results from a greenhouse study in which the roots are subjected to one temperature regime and the tops, to a radically different one, must be used cautiously in interpreting the behavior of rice under field conditions. But one thing is clear: a

soil temperature of 35 to 30 C during the first 8 weeks of submergence produced a more desirable chemical environment for rice roots than either 20 C or 15 → 30 C.

Physiological Disorders of Rice

Several physiological disorders of rice are attributed to the accumulation, in the root zone of the plant, of the products of anaerobic soil metabolism. If reduction products cause these disorders, measures to minimize their concentration should improve the growth of rice on these problem soils. Such measures include (a) delaying planting until after the peaks of water-soluble Fe^{++} , CO_2 , organic acids, and reducing substances and their concentrations have been reduced to innocuous levels, (b) providing internal drainage to remove the water-soluble toxins, (c) retarding soil reduction with MnO_2 , and (d) delaying submergence until a week before panicle primordia initiation to give a medium that is virtually free of reduction products in the vegetative phase and the anaerobic environment necessary in the reproductive phase (1966 Annual Report). These measures were tested in a replicated greenhouse experiment on four problem soils (an Akiochi soil from Korea, two soils from Taiwan on which suffocation disease occurs, and a "straighthead" soil from Texas).

The air-dry soils were mixed with 0.2 percent of chopped straw and 1 percent of *Glyricidia sepium* (to simulate incorporation of stubble and weeds). Fifty parts per million each of N, P, and K were added and the soils placed in 16-liter pots fitted with tubes for sampling the soil solution. The treatments were: (1) submerged throughout (control), (2) submerged for 4 weeks before planting, (3) submerged throughout, with internal drainage at 1 cm per day, (4) submerged throughout plus 1 percent crystalline MnO_2 , and (5) field capacity for 7 weeks after transplanting, followed by submergence till harvest. One 2-week-old IR5 seedling was planted in each of the 80 pots on the same day.

These treatments markedly influenced the chemical and electrochemical changes and the growth of rice on all soils but the effects were most pronounced in Tungshan silt loam and Keelung silt loam (the two problem soils from

Taiwan). The treatment means averaged for soils are in Table 13, and the individual treatments in Table 14.

Table 13 shows that, on the average, late submergence was by far the best treatment, and submergence plus drainage, the worst. The addition of MnO_2 improved vegetative growth considerably but did not increase the grain yield. Presubmergence produced no overall benefit. But there were marked interactions of the treatments with soils (Table 4).

Late submergence which produced such a dramatic yield increase in Tungshan silt loam and Keelung silt loam gave no response on the silt loam from Korea and depressed yield on the soil from Texas. MnO_2 increased the yield of both straw and grain on Tungshan silt loam and Keelung silt loam substantially but had hardly any favorable effect on the soils from Korea and Texas. Presubmergence was decidedly beneficial on Tungshan silt loam, lethal on Keelung silt loam, and indifferent on the two other soils. The submerged treatment with 1 cm drainage per day was uniformly the worst. The chemical and electrochemical kinetics of the soils throw some light on these responses.

The benefits of late submergence, presubmergence, and MnO_2 in Tungshan silt loam can be correlated with the more favorable chemical environment brought about by these treatments: the redox potentials were higher, the electrolyte concentration and the partial pressure of CO_2 lower, and the concentration of reduction products as exemplified by water-soluble iron (Fig. 5) considerably lower than in the submerged treatment (the control). The adverse effects of internal drainage, despite the sharp decrease in electrolyte content, P_{CO_2} , and gross concentration of reduction products may be due to the lower redox potentials in this treatment (Fig. 6). (A moderate amount of internal drainage, contrary to popular belief, depressed Eh because pH increased following the loss of CO_2 .) At low potentials, some bacteria apparently produce substances which, even at low concentrations, are toxic to rice.

The responses on Keelung silt loam cannot be explained so easily. The benefits of late submergence and MnO_2 addition clearly indicate that the physiological disorder of rice on this soil is caused by soil reduction. The markedly adverse

Table 12. Influence of soil temperature regime on the growth and yield of IR5 in the greenhouse.

Soil	Temperature regime (C)	Tiller number	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Days from sowing to flowering
Casiguran sandy loam pH 4.9, O.M: 5.3%	15 → 30 → 25	55	92	123	94
	20	52	88	124	95
	30	96	135	164	95
	35 → 20	72	127	168	93
Korean silt loam pH 4.8, O.M: 2.8%	15 → 30 → 25	14	40	58	113
	20	7	31	34	116
	30	27	53	64	100
	35 → 20	26	86	90	95
Korean sandy loam pH 5.5, O.M: 1.6%	15 → 30 → 25	8	36	64	112
	20	13	40	50	114
	30	32	54	67	95
	35 → 20	27	45	69	93
Albay sandy loam pH 5.9, O.M: 4.0%	15 → 30 → 25	43	100	144	93
	20	42	92	86	95
	30	57	113	132	88
	35 → 20	78	141	161	87
Pila clay loam pH 7.6, O.M: 1.5%	15 → 30 → 25	66	113	94	94
	20	70	100	76	99
	30	84	127	80	91
	35 → 20	74	105	78	87
Maahas clay pH 6.6, O.M: 2.0%	15 → 30 → 25	78	140	119	95
	20	70	143	108	95
	30	81	147	116	89
	35 → 20	75	139	116	88
Keelung silt loam pH 7.7, O.M: 7.6%	15 → 30 → 25	3	2	0.3	113
	20	4	1	0.0	—
	30	9	15	2.0	126
	35 → 20	16	24	2.6	115
Luisiana clay pH 4.8, O.M:3.2%	15 → 30 → 25	36	87	102	97
	20	23	55	53	99
	30	41	106	117	94
	35 → 20	22	74	66	93

effects of presubmergence and drainage in spite of the favorable chemical environment they brought about are difficult to explain. Perhaps, a stable, toxic bacterial metabolite of unknown identity was involved.

The absence of a response to treatments designed to depress the concentration of reduction products in the soils from Korea and Texas indicate that there was no serious soil reduction problem under the conditions of this experiment.

Fig. 5. Kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ in Tungshan silt loam as affected by five treatments.

At the high soil temperature of this experiment (25-35 C), the metabolism of these soils is apparently different from that under the conditions in which Akiochi is observed on the silt loam from Korea or straighthead, on the soil from Texas. Chemical analyses of the soil solution confirmed this: the concentrations of toxic substances, except CO₂, were well within acceptable limits. The negative response to drainage on these two soils with low cation exchange capacity was, no doubt, partly due to loss of nutrients, notably N (Table 15).

The results of this experiment clearly indicate that delaying submergence until panicle primordia

Table 13. Growth and yield data averaged for soils.

Treatment	Height (cm)	Tiller no.	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)
1. Submerged (S)	97	31	58	57
2. Presubmerged plus (S)	77	39	60	52
3. (S) plus drainage	98	32	49	41
4. (S) plus MnO ₂	106	40	78	56
5. Late submergence	116	56	106	86

initiation is the best and simplest remedy for the physiological disorder of rice on Tungshan silt loam and Keelung silt loam, the problem soils from Taiwan.

Fig. 6. Kinetics of solution Eh in Tungshan silt loam as affected by five treatments.

Table 14. Influence of five treatments on the growth, yield, and maturation of IR5 on four problem soils.

Treatment	Height (cm)	Tiller number	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Maturation (days)
Tungshan silt loam, pH 5.8, O.M. 3.4%					
1. Submerged (S)	74	13	27	28	156
2. Presubmerged + (S)	86	21	38	49	148
3. (S) + drainage	92	20	24	21	140
4. (S) + MnO ₂	102	22	41	46	140
5. Submerged late	106	71	124	87	
Keelung silt loam, pH 7.7, O.M. 6.9%					
1. Submerged (S)	86	11	18	29	152
2. Presubmerged + (S)	0	0	0	0	—
3. (S) + drainage	81	11	22	15	144
4. (S) + MnO ₂	92	37	56	37	144
5. Submerged late	112	57	117	93	127
Silt loam from Korea, pH 4.8, O.M. 2.8%					
1. Submerged (S)	113	52	90	89	121
2. Presubmerged + (S)	109	73	106	85	121
3. (S) + drainage	107	52	76	64	123
4. (S) + MnO ₂	114	50	115	67	123
5. Submerged late	122	59	109	87	127
Silt loam from Texas, pH 7.5, O.M. 1.8%					
1. Submerged (S)	115	50	96	83	122
2. Presubmerged + (S)	113	61	95	74	121
3. (S) + drainage	113	48	74	63	122
4. (S) + MnO ₂	115	52	99	72	122
5. Submerged late	123	34	72	75	122

Table 15. Influence of five treatments on the kinetics of water-soluble NH₄⁺ in the sandy loam from Texas

Treatment	Weeks				
	2	4	5	7	9
(ppm NH ₄ ⁺ -N)					
1. Submerged (S)	89	85	55	6	7
2. Presubmerged + (S)	90	76	39	5	3
3. (S) + drainage	35	14	7	0	0
4. (S) + MnO ₂	79	74	44	4	4
5. Submerged late	7	3	2	0	1

Table 16. Straw yield as affected by CaCO₃ application, duration of presubmergence, and P application. (Total of three replicates, in g.)

Phosphorus (ppm)	CaCO ₃ (tons/ha)									Phosphorus means
	0			2.7			6.0			
	Presubmergence (weeks)									
	0	3	6	0	3	6	0	3	6	
0	120	97	139	92	126	162	107	138	178	128.8
25	261	322	290	309	285	326	266	325	290	297.1
50	276	339	311	275	321	348	266	315	370	313.4
CaCO ₃ means	239.4			249.3			250.6			
Presubmergence means				219.1 (0)						
				252.0 (3 weeks)						
				268.2 (6 weeks)						
LSD 18.18 (5%)										
24.28 (1%)										

Table 17. Influence of three levels of lime on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe⁺⁺ in flooded Luisiana clay.

CaCO ₃ (tons/ha)	Soil pH	Weeks submerged					
		0	2	4	6	8	10
		(ppm Fe ⁺⁺)					
0	4.9	0.6	311	284	228	237	187
5.7	5.6	0.3	284	185	139	143	127
12.0	6.6	0.7	128	98	91	94	94

Liming of Rice Soils

Lowland rice does not grow well on strongly acid soils. The adverse factors are probably aluminum toxicity immediately after flooding, iron toxicity after the soil has undergone reduction, and low phosphate availability in the early stages of submergence. The spontaneous increase in pH of acid soils, when flooded, normally reduces the severity of these problems. But because benefits of liming acid rice soils have been reported, an experiment was conducted to compare the effects of lime with those of presubmergence and phosphate application.

The soil was Luisiana clay (pH 4.7, O.M: 3.2%, active Fe: 2.9%, and active Mn: 0.05%). The periods of presubmergence were 0, 3, and 6 weeks; the levels of lime were 2, 2.7 and 6.0 tons/ha; and the levels of phosphate were 0, 25 and 50 ppm P as superphosphate. These treatments were combined factorially and tested over a basal dressing of 50 ppm K, and 0.2% chopped straw and 1% fresh *Glyricidia sepium* leaves. The lime, P and K were mixed with the soil immediately prior to planting 20-day-old IR8 seedlings. The yield data are in Table 16.

Phosphate and presubmergence of the soil individually and in combination improved the

Table 18. Influence of four water treatments on the yield of IR5 (averaged for 3 soils).

Water treatment	Feb.-June, 1968		July-Nov., 1968		Mean (1968)		Mean (1967-68)	
	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain
(g per drum of 4 hills)								
1. Dry fallow no msd*	449	368	250	312	350	340	331	330
2. Dry fallow with msd	367	319	251	299	309	309	308	290
3. Flood fallow no msd	468	376	250	286	359	331	340	326
4. Flood fallow with msd	485	328	267	323	376	326	349	315

* Midseason soil drying.

growth and yield of IR8 (Table 16). The combination of 50 ppm P with 6 weeks presubmergence gave the highest yield. Lime, at the levels used, produced no significant effect on the chemical changes in the soil or on yield.

A repetition of the experiment with the levels of CaCO_3 increased to 5.7 and 12 tons /ha confirmed the marked response to P but showed none to lime. Presubmergence, this time, depressed yield.

A third experiment with the same soil, with a basal dressing of P, revealed no response to either the earlier application of lime or to presubmergence. Although lime depressed the concentrations of water-soluble Fe^{++} (Table 17), it did not benefit rice apparently because the Fe^{++} levels without lime were not too high.

Liming this acid ferralitic soil did not benefit rice because the spontaneous increase in pH on flooding was rapid and high enough to preclude toxic concentrations of water-soluble Fe^{++} .

Water Regime in Rice Soils

Because of the current interest in year-long rice culture on the same land, the water-management studies in large drums begun in 1967 (1967 Annual Report) were continued. The yield data for the third and fourth successive seasons and the averages for the four seasons are in Table 18.

These data (obtained with a strongly acid clay, a nearly neutral clay, and a calcareous clay loam) show no deleterious consequences of continuous soil submergence but indicate the injurious effects of mid-season soil drying, especially if the soils are dried between crops.

Soil Microbiology

Tropical rice soils are characterized by the occurrence of intensive microbial activity. The soil on the surface, a few millimeters thick, is aerobic and the microorganisms which undertake atmospheric nitrogen fixation, nitrification, and microbial photosynthesis are active. Nitrogen-fixing microorganisms were found to be important in maintaining the fertility of paddy soils if the environmental conditions are favorable. The rice plant seems to have a mechanism for nitrogen fixation. A large number of nitrifying bacteria was found on the surface soil particularly when ammonium nitrogen was applied. The fate of applied nitrogen appeared to be greatly influenced by microbial transformations. Most of the rice root area is exposed to the reduced anaerobic environment where various anaerobic and facultative anaerobic metabolisms occur simultaneously during the period of plant growth. The anaerobic bacteria play an important role in the transformation of inorganic and organic soil materials. Gamma-BHC, which has been considered a persistent insecticide, is biodegradable in tropical soils under anaerobic conditions. The pathway of diazinon degradation under submerged soil conditions is characteristically different from that under upland soil conditions.

Nitrogen Fixation

In many areas of the countries of Southeast Asia, chemical fertilizers are not yet commonly used, so that the growth and yield of rice depend on the natural fertility of the soil. The continuous supply of nitrogen, despite its use over the years by rice crops, is claimed to be due to the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by microorganisms in paddy soils. This is yet to be proven unequivocally.

The role of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms in the maintenance of the fertility of paddy soil was studied by: (1) investigating, under greenhouse conditions, the effect of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms on the rice plant and on soil fertility, (2) examining, using the N^{15} method, the effect of some environmental factors on nitrogen fixation, and (3) looking into the application of the acetylene reduction method in the nitrogen fixation studies in paddy soils.

Effect of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms on the rice plant and on soil fertility

The extent of occurrence and abundance of total algae and blue-green algae in flooded Maahas clay at different growth stages of the rice plant under greenhouse conditions are shown in Fig. 1. These stages were transplanting, maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and maturity (designated as 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively). There was a bigger number of algae in the surface layer (0-2 cm) of the soil than in the lower layer (2-7 cm), and in the soil exposed to light (L) than in that kept in the dark (D). The presence of nitrogen fertilizer and of plants seemed to inhibit or depress the growth of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae, probably due to increased competition with other nitrogen-fixing algae under these conditions. The algal population was highest at maximum tillering.

In contrast, the *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* populations showed no significant change during

Fig. 1 Algal population during the rice-growing period. L - Light; D - Dark. Depth of soil: 0-2 cm; 2-7 cm. Stage of rice: 1, transplanting; 2, maximum tillering; 3, panicle initiation; 4, maturity.

Table 1. Nitrogen fixation under various soil treatments.

Pretreatment*	Incubated in light		Incubated in dark	
	Atom % excess N ^{15**}	Estimated amount of fixed N (kg/ha/month)	Atom % excess N ^{15**}	Estimated amount of fixed N (kg/ha/month)
P K L † No plant	.395	32.0	.038	3.2
P K D †† No plant	.493	32.8	.020	1.2
P K L IR8	.459	32.6	.026	1.9
P K D IR8	.514	36.0	.006	0.5
P K L Peta	.517	38.1	.047	3.4
P K D Peta	.410	27.2	.027	1.8
N P K L No plant	.043	5.7	.048	4.6
N P K D No plant	.020	2.0	.000	0.0
N P K L IR8	.075	6.4	.017	1.5
N P K D IR8	.070	5.1	.024	1.8
N P K L Peta	.151	13.3	.031	2.5
N P K D Peta	.089	5.6	.000	0.0

* Treatment of Maahas clay soil in greenhouse pots from which soil samples were obtained 2 months after transplanting IR8 and Peta.

** Determined after incubation of soil in glass tubes for 1 month in the greenhouse.

† L - Light (good growth of indigenous algae).

†† D - Dark (no algal growth observed).

plant growth and among treatments. Most of the *Azotobacter* counts were in the range of 1.9×10^5 in the 0-2 cm layer of the soil and $0.5-4 \times 10^5$ per g dry soil in the 2-7 cm area. The *Clostridium* counts were 2.8×10^5 per g dry soil in both 0-2 and 2-7 cm areas. Some bacteria which may neither be *Azotobacter* nor *Clostridium* but which could grow in the media used were included in the counts. The nitrogen-fixing activities of these bacteria are currently being identified and tested. The *Clostridium* counts after the samples were heat-treated at 80 C for 20 minutes showed that more than 50 percent of the bacteria were in the resting stage, probably as spores. The bacteria at this stage would not be active unless some energy source for them, i.e., organic materials, is supplied.

The tubes used in estimating the number of blue-green algae present in the soil were cultured further and the number of genera was counted. Of 308 isolated, 267 belong to the *Nostoc* genus, 38 to the *Anabaena*, 1 to the *Stigonema*, 1 to the *Tolypothrix* and 1 to the *Scytonema*.

The capacity for nitrogen fixation of the soil in each pot was examined 2 months after transplanting. The soil samples obtained from the pots

were incubated in test tubes at 30 C. One set was illuminated while another was kept in the dark. The data (Table 1) showed that a significantly higher amount of nitrogen was fixed in the test tubes incubated with light than in those incubated without light regardless of the pre-treatments. The results suggest that the soil has a great capacity for fixing atmospheric nitrogen if the conditions are favorable for the growth of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms. In this case, the microorganisms are most likely photosynthetic, probably nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae since not much nitrogen fixation was observed in the tubes incubated in the dark regardless of the pre-treatments.

The addition of ammonium fertilizer (500 ppm N) remarkably depressed the amount of molecular nitrogen fixed by the soils. However, the soil samples incubated in the light showed good algal growth, although the major algal flora might have been non-nitrogen-fixing algae. The data in Fig. 1 show that there were fewer counts of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae in the pots with added ammonium fertilizer as compared to the total algae. In addition, it is known that nitrogen fixation is inhibited when ammonium nitrogen is

Table 2. Effect of algae on the growth and yield of rice.

Treatment	IR 8						Peta							
	Height at harvest (cm)	Max. tiller no.	No. of panicle	Straw weight (g)	Total N (g)	Grain weight (g)	Total N (g)	Height at harvest (cm)	Max. tiller no.	No. of panicle	Straw weight (g)	Total N (g)	Grain weight (g)	Total N (g)
First crop – Maahas clay soil. (Dec. 6 – April 1)														
P K L*	104	9	9	53.8	.4	31.4	0.4	133	13	11	73.6	.3	42.5	.4
P K D**	115	9	8	58.1	.4	30.3	0.3	136	12	9	68.9	.3	35.7	.4
N P K L	127	62	62	224.2	3.5	149.3	2.8	171	62	63	334.3	3.3	291.8	3.6
N P K D	127	38	39	196.4	4.5	90.9	1.8	174	59	59	374.2	3.8	302.6	4.5
Second crop – Maahas clay soil. (April 17 – August 10)														
P K L	122	15	15	43.3	.3	46.3	.6	161	25	22	108.6	.5	53.3	.5
P K D	123	15	15	44.5	.3	47.1	.6	162	18	18	107.1	.4	57.4	.5
N P K L	125	24	22	64.4	.3	66.0	.9	168	20	19	88.7	.5	41.7	.4
N P K D	134	25	27	83.6	.7	80.7	1.2	169	22	20	122.7	.6	45.2	.4

* L – Light (profuse growth of indigenous algae).

** D – Dark (no algal growth observed).

Table 3. Effect of inoculation of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae on the growth and yield of rice (Maahas clay soil, April 19 – August 10).

Treatment	IR 8						Peta							
	Height at harvest (cm)	Max. tiller no.	No. of panicles	Straw Weight (g)	Total N (g)	Grain Weight (g)	Total N (g)	Height at harvest (cm)	Max. tiller no.	No. of panicles	Straw Weight (g)	Total N (g)	Grain Weight (g)	Total N (g)
N*–L**	122	29	26	93.4	.6	71.2	.9	190	38	30	180.4	.7	78.3	.7
N–D†	137	22	20	91.2	.5	81.6	1.0	186	30	29	203.3	.7	93.4	.8
T††–L	125	26	24	91.8	.5	78.0	1.0	190	39	34	190.5	.7	73.4	.7
T–D	135	20	20	78.1	.5	78.3	1.0	189	29	26	182.6	.7	89.0	.8

* N – *Nostoc muscorum*.

** L – Light (good algal growth).

† D – Dark (no algal growth).

†† T – *Tolypothrix tenuis*.

added to cultures of nitrogen-fixing organisms, and that the ammonium nitrogen is preferentially assimilated.

The foregoing experiment indicated that the soil in each pot kept in the light without nitrogen fertilizer could fix atmospheric nitrogen at the rate

of about 30 kg/ha N while that kept in the dark could fix only very small amounts of nitrogen. The large amount of nitrogen fixed in the former could be explained by the large population of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae in the soil. Even with a much smaller population of microflora, the soil

pre-treated in the dark has a remarkable potential for fixing large amounts of atmospheric nitrogen once it is exposed to sunlight for a certain period.

The growth and yield of IR8 and Peta in each treatment are shown in Table 2. Indigenous algal growth (in light treatments) did not result in any significant increases in plant height, in straw and in grain yield. However, algal growth had a slight effect on the tiller and panicle number of Peta except in the second crop which was treated with NPK. Since the total nitrogen uptake did not differ in the light and dark pre-treatments, the increase in the number of tillers and panicles might have been due to some excretion products of algae rather than to nitrogen-fixation. Similar results were obtained from the pot experiment in which the soil was inoculated with the nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae, *Nostoc muscorum* and *Tolypothrix tenuis*. As shown in Table 3, the algae growing in the light stimulated tillering and increased the panicle number, but the total nitrogen uptake of the plant did not significantly differ in the soil with the inoculated algae growing and in that without algal growth.

The insignificant effect of nitrogen-fixing algae in spite of the large potential of the soil to fix nitrogen in the light suggests that the fixed nitrogen was immobilized in the soil, perhaps as micro-

bial bodies or in the organic fraction of the soil. Table 4 shows the total nitrogen content of the soil after the second crop. A larger amount of nitrogen remained in the soils which were kept in the light than in those kept in the dark. These results suggest that the soil exposed to light fixed nitrogen through the activities of photosynthetic nitrogen-fixing microorganisms, while that in the dark fixed nitrogen in the presence of organic materials, probably through the activities of heterotrophic nitrogen-fixing bacteria. The enrichment of nitrogen during the period of the experiment may partly explain the better growth of the second rice crop. The experiment is being repeated using Buenavista soil which is low in nitrogen.

To find out if algae have a stimulating effect on tillering, the amount of oxygen which had dissolved in flood water was determined. The results showed that the pots which showed algal growth had more dissolved oxygen in flood water (Table 5). In greenhouse studies using Buenavista soil, algal growth in flood water was found to increase the dissolved oxygen content. The algae, like the higher plant forms, release molecular oxygen during photosynthesis. The increase in dissolved oxygen brought about by the growth of algae in the soil surface and in flood water was confirmed in the pot experiment in which the plants were

Table 4. Total nitrogen content of Maahas clay soil after two croppings*.

Treatment	Replication			Mean
	Pot 1	Pot 2	Pot 3	
P K L** No plant	.113	.101	.113	.109
P K D† No plant	.100	.098	.095	.096
P K L IR8	.102	.103	.110	.105
P K D IR8	.092	.090	.085	.089
P K L Peta	.112	.110	.108	.110
P K D Peta	.104	.102	.102	.103
N P K L No plant	.146	.126	.131	.134
N P K D No plant	.107	.118	.111	.112
N P K L IR8	.104	.116	.096	.105
N P K D IR8	.124	.091	.115	.108
N P K L Peta	.117	.124	.117	.119
N P K D Peta	.106	.107	.115	.109

* The soil used in the greenhouse experiment was taken from an area planted to coconuts adjacent to the IRRI experimental farm. Total N content of the soil; 0.098%.

** L - light.

† D - dark.

Fig. 2. Oxygen concentration of the flood water of Buenavista soil in a day. D - Dark (no algae); L - Light (good growth of algae); Plant - IR8 at 46 days after transplanting.

inoculated with nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae (Table 6). There is no information available on whether such an increase in oxygen concentration in flood water would definitely affect plant growth. The total amount of dissolved oxygen during the growth stage of the rice plant may not differ much since algae, like the higher plant forms, also consume oxygen during the night. The concentration of dissolved oxygen in flood water during the night was much less with than without algal growth (Fig. 2).

Effect of some environmental factors on nitrogen fixation

The conditions in the paddy field vary with time and place depending on the macro- and micro-environments. The effect of submergence and pre-submergence of rice soils on nitrogen fixation was therefore examined using Maahas clay and the following pretreatments: field capacity, submerged (no pre-submergence), 2-week pre-submergence, 4-week pre-submergence and 6-week pre-submergence. In the light, flooding the soil proved beneficial to nitrogen fixation (Table 7). The amount of nitrogen fixed in the flooded soil decreased as the period of pre-submergence was prolonged, in spite of the better algal growth in the soil surface and in the water. This indicates that, during the earlier

period of plant growth, the blue-green algae are more active in nitrogen fixation, or that there is a bigger population of blue-green algae than of other microorganisms which do not fix nitrogen. Interestingly, in the light, even under anaerobic conditions, appreciable amounts of nitrogen were fixed in the soil, suggesting that the photosynthetic nitrogen-fixing bacteria (*Chlorobium*, *Chromatium* and *Rhodospirillum*) may be important in paddy fields.

Both nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae and photosynthetic bacteria seemed to be less active in nitrogen fixation in the soil presubmerged for 6 weeks. Regardless of the soil treatment, no significant nitrogen fixation occurred in the dark, indicating that, under these particular experimental conditions, non-photosynthetic nitrogen-fixing bacteria such as *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* were not active nitrogen-fixers. However, in the presence of rice roots or rice plant residues, these bacteria might play a significant role in nitrogen fixation. Consequently, an experiment on this aspect is in progress.

The effect of various nitrogen fertilizers on nitrogen fixation was also examined. The presence of ammonium nitrogen greatly affected the fixation of molecular nitrogen by soil microorganisms both in the dark and in the light. An almost com-

Table 5. Oxygen content of flood water with and without algae*.

Treatment	Light**			Dark†		
	Plant stage					
	I	II	III	I	II	III
	Dissolved oxygen (ppm)					
P K – No plant	3.3	7.4	5.3	2.7	4.0	2.0
P K – IR8	3.3	6.7	5.5	2.9	3.7	1.7
P K – Peta	3.3	6.3	2.8	2.8	4.2	1.3
N P K – No plant	3.5	4.9	6.5	3.3	3.7	2.0
N P K – IR8	3.4	7.1	6.5	2.8	3.6	4.6
N P K – Peta	3.6	5.7	7.5	3.0	3.3	3.3

* Oxygen contents were analyzed at 10-20 a.m. on August 20 (I), September 2 (III), and October 17 (III), 1968.

** Good growth of indigenous algae in flood water and soil surface.

† No algal growth observed.

Table 6. Oxygen content of flood water inoculated with pure cultures of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae*.

Species, treatment	Light**		Dark†	
	Plant stage			
	II	III	II	III
	Dissolved oxygen (ppm)			
<i>Nostoc muscorum</i>				
No plant	5.1	9.1	2.3	5.6
IR8	5.1	7.2	2.0	4.0
Peta	3.7	7.1	2.2	4.8
<i>Tolypothrix tenuis</i>				
No plant	5.3	6.0	2.0	5.3
IR8	4.5	6.8	2.0	4.8
Peta	4.8	5.4	2.3	4.5
Control (indigenous algae)				
IR8	7.0	12.2	2.0	5.0
Peta	5.4	6.3	1.8	4.0

* Oxygen contents were analyzed at 10-20 a.m. on August 20 (II) and September 24 (III), 1968.

** Good growth of inoculated algae in flood water and soil surface.

† No algal growth observed.

plete inhibition of nitrogen fixation was observed when nitrogen was applied to the soil at the rate of 160 ppm (Table 8). The growth of algae was luxuriant in the soil that was illuminated and that received ammonium nitrogen but the amount of nitrogen fixed was not appreciable. The small amount of nitrogen fixed could partly be attributed to the stimulation of the growth of non-

nitrogen-fixing algae by the ammonium fertilizers, thus giving the nitrogen-fixing microorganisms stiff competition. The main reason, however, is the inhibitory effect of ammonium nitrogen on the nitrogen-fixing enzymes of the microorganisms. However, in the presence of organic material, such as rice plant residues in the natural environment, and where immobilization and mineralization occur simultaneously, nitrogen fixation in the soil may not be greatly influenced by the application of nitrogen fertilizers.

Application of the acetylene reduction method in nitrogen fixation studies in paddy soil

The nitrogen-fixing enzymes in microorganisms were recently known to reduce acetylene and convert it to ethylene. This acetylene reduction method was applied in the assay of the nitrogen-fixing activity in microbial systems. Isotope N^{15} nitrogen gas has been commonly used in studies on nitrogen fixation, but this technique is time-consuming and expensive. On the other hand, the acetylene reduction method is more sensitive, practical and economical. This section discusses (a) the method as well as the test used for determining the nitrogen-fixing capacity of soils, (b) different species of microorganisms, and (c) plant crops and insects. A typical gas chromatogram of acetylene and ethylene determination with the flame ionization detector, Porapak R column, carrier gas 25 ml nitrogen/minute is shown in Fig. 3. Most of the microorganisms so far examined which could grow

Table 7. The effect of soil submergence on nitrogen fixation.

Soil pretreatment	Condition of nitrogen fixation			
	Light *		Dark **	
	Aerobic	Anaerobic	Aerobic	Anaerobic
Atom % excess N ¹⁵				
No presubmergence				
Field capacity	0.126	0.124	0.004	0.003
Flooded	1.379	0.194	0.003	0.001
2-week presubmergence	0.617	0.419	0.004	0.004
4-week presubmergence	0.717	0.346	0.006	0.004
6-week presubmergence	0.349	0.065	0.003	0.001
Estimated amount of fixed nitrogen in a month (kg/ha)				
No presubmergence				
Field capacity	10.5	10.3	0.3	0.2
Flooded	114.9	17.2	0.2	< 0.1
2-week presubmergence	51.4	34.9	0.3	0.3
4-week presubmergence	51.5	28.8	0.5	0.3
6-week presubmergence	29.1	4.7	0.2	< 0.1

* Good algal growth.

** No algal growth.

Table 8. Effect of ammonium N fertilizer on nitrogen fixation.

Fertilizer	Level of N application (ppm)	Atom % excess N ¹⁵	
		Incubation in light	Incubation in dark
No fertilizer	0	0.150	0.100
Ammonium sulfate	80	0.042	0.036
	160	0.009	0.000
Ammonium chloride	80	0.005	0.015
	160	0.000	0.000
Urea	80	0.024	0.043
	160	0.000	0.000

in the N-free media reduced acetylene to ethylene. A result of the C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay with nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae is shown in Table 9.

Fresh plants of rice, broccoli, sorghum, soybean, spinach, sweet corn and sweet potato were taken from the field. The tops and roots of each crop were tested for their ability to reduce acetylene to ethylene. The rhizosphere soil was used as control. Of these crops, only rice and soybean could produce ethylene (Table 10); interestingly this is the first report on the ability of the rice

plant to reduce acetylene to ethylene. Soybean nodules are known to possess a nitrogen-fixing system in addition to the acetylene-reducing system. The reduction of acetylene and the production of ethylene by the tops and roots of rice plants suggest the possibility that nitrogen-fixing microorganisms inhabit the root surface (rhizosphere) and the leaf surface (phyllosphere) of the rice plant. When the roots of Peta at the heading stage were retested for ethylene formation after careful washing, it was found that they produced

Table 9. Ethylene formation by nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae.

Species	nmole C ₂ H ₄ /day/mg dry material
<i>Nostoc entophyllum</i>	3809
<i>Nostoc muscorum</i>	532
<i>Tolypothrix tenuis</i>	581
BGA-1	360
BGA-5	1953
BGA-6	1009
BGA-7	1194
BGA-10	2296
BGA-14	854
BGA-16	343
BGA-17	755
BGA-22	1416

Table 10. Ethylene formation by some crops.

Plant	Plant part	Amount of C ₂ H ₄ produced (mμmole/day/g fresh material)
Rice (IR8)	Tops	4.2
	Roots	0.7
	Control*	0.0
Rice (Peta)	Tops	1.4
	Roots	5.1
	Control*	0.0
Broccoli	Tops	0.0
	Roots	0.0
	Control*	0.0
Sorghum	Tops	0.0
	Roots	0.0
	Control*	0.0
Soybean	Tops	0.0
	Roots	402.5
	Control*	0.0
Sweet Corn	Tops	0.0
	Roots	0.0
	Control*	0.0
Spinach	Tops	0.0
	Roots	0.0
	Control*	0.0
Sweet Corn	Tops	0.0
	Roots	0.0
	Control*	0.0
Sweet Potato	Tops	0.0
	Roots	0.0
	Control*	0.0

*Control used was rhizosphere soil of corresponding plant.

Fig. 3. Gas chromatogram of ethylene (C₂H₄) and acetylene (C₂H₂).

Table 11. Ethylene formation by rice (Peta) roots.*

Sample	Condition	Incubation		
		Time (days)		
		1	2	3
mμmole C ₂ H ₄ /day/g fresh weight				
Roots	Dark	0	92	266
	Light	0	92	280
Control**	Dark	0	0	5
	Light	0	0	5

* The plant samples were taken at the heading stage.

** The controls were the rhizosphere soil.

more ethylene than the rhizosphere soil (Table 11). This acetylene reduction-ethylene formation ability of plants will be further studied using aseptic conditions and techniques. Nevertheless,

the existing data suggest that the rice plant has a mechanism for fixing atmospheric nitrogen. This may partly explain why the rice plant can grow without fertilizer for a long period. It might be mentioned here, too, that the rice stem borer and the brown leafhopper, when tested, did not have the ability to reduce acetylene to ethylene.

Nitrogen Transformation

The maintenance of the natural fertility of the soil in the rice-growing areas for many years could also be explained by the continuous mineralization and

Fig. 4. Population of nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria during the rice-growing period. (D - Dark, L - Light, Depth of soil - 0-2 cm, 2-7 cm.)

economic preservation of soil organic nitrogen under flooded conditions. A number of microorganisms in the soil mineralize the soil organic nitrogen although the inorganic nitrogen is immobilized simultaneously. The results obtained at the Institute in the previous year suggested the intensive transformation of nitrogen fertilizers in the flooded rice soils in the tropics. There are indications that nitrification can occur in the oxidized layer where it is denitrified, but this still needs to be positively proven. Following is a discussion of the results of studies on (1) the population of nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria, and (2) the fate of inorganic and organic nitrogen under flooded soil conditions.

Nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria in flooded soils

The population of nitrifying bacteria in flooded soil under greenhouse conditions is shown in Fig. 4. A large number of such bacteria was found in the surface layer (0-2 cm) of the flooded soil. The *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrobacter* counts were usually much higher in soils with than without ammonium fertilizer. The rice plant, particularly at the later growth stage, seemed to have a stimulative effect on the number of nitrifying bacteria in the soil. In

the lower layer, the soil without added nitrogen had fewer nitrifying bacteria than the soil with added nitrogen. On the other hand, there was no significant difference in the number of denitrifying bacteria among the treatments. The results also indicated a tendency for the population to increase in the lower soil layer during the experimental period. Although the size of the microbial population is not necessarily related to the extent of microbial activities, the large number of microflora reflects the large potential for microbial activity in the process of nitrogen oxidation and reduction in flooded rice soils.

Fate of inorganic and organic nitrogen in the flooded soil

In order to simplify the environmental factors in the studies on nitrogen transformation, the experiments were carried on under laboratory conditions. Results of laboratory studies on the transformation of inorganic nitrogen supplied as ammonium sulfate and organic nitrogen supplied as lysozyme in flooded Maahas clay soil incubated at different temperatures indicated that, the higher the temperature, the more added inorganic nitrogen is lost and also the more active net mineralization of lysozyme is obtained if the soil was not

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature and presubmergence on the nitrogen transformation in the flooded Maahas clay soil.

presubmerged (Fig. 5). The presubmerged soil, however, showed a much faster loss of ammonium nitrogen but less net mineralization as compared to the non-presubmerged soil. These could be explained by either the denitrification of nitrogen following nitrification or the immobilization of inorganic nitrogen by the microorganisms under flooded soil conditions, or perhaps by both. The fate of nitrogen in flooded Maahas clay soil is presently being studied using N^{15} techniques.

Pesticide Residue

The extensive occurrence of insect pests, weeds, and microbial diseases in tropical countries requires the greater usage of chemicals for their control. However, the toxicity of these pesticides often extend to organisms other than those it is expected to control. This persistence of the pesti-

cides may cause the contamination of the water supply, soil, and crops. Extensive studies have been conducted on pesticide degradation in upland soils, but not in lowland rice soils.

Table 12. Effect of glucose on γ -BHC biodegradation in submerged Maahas clay soil.

Treatment	Time of incubation (day)			
	0	15	30	50
	$\mu\text{g } \gamma\text{-BHC} / 20 \text{ g soil}$			
γ -BHC	705	547	332	169
γ -BHC + glucose (0.25%)	639	548	176	69

Table 13. Degradation of γ -BHC in Maahas clay soil under different conditions.

Soil condition	% γ -BHC decomposed by microorganisms*				
	Time of incubation (days)				
	0	3	7	10	15
Submerged	0.0	30.0	47.6	58.3	63.2
Aerobic	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Anaerobic	0.0	28.9	51.5	54.9	61.8

* Values were obtained by:

$$\frac{(\text{amount in sterilized soils} - \text{amount in nonsterilized soils})}{\text{initial concentration of } 204 \mu\text{g } \gamma\text{-BHC per } 20 \text{ g soil}} \times 100$$

Table 14. Effect of combined oxygen* on γ -BHC decomposition in flooded soil.

Treatment	Time of incubation (days)				
	0	3	7	10	15
	$\mu\text{g } \gamma\text{-BHC remaining} / 20 \text{ g soil}$				
Control	120	65	49	28	17
0.5% O.M.**	120	55	34	14	2
0.5% Na_2SO_4	120	59	43	40	13
0.5% MnO_2	120	61	45	44	26
0.5% $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	120	120	111	112	113

* All compounds were added in powdered form and mixed well with the soil before flooding.

** Rice straw.

Fig. 6. Degradation of γ -BHC in four Philippine soils under upland and flooded conditions.

Of the many synthetic organic pesticides, the chlorinated hydrocarbons have been widely used in agriculture and have been reported as persistent pesticides. Recently, organic phosphate and carbamates have increasingly been used as pesticides. Previous work on γ -BHC and diazinon residues showed that the microorganisms in paddy soils play an important role in the degradation of these insecticides. This report covers studies made on (1) γ -BHC degradation in rice soils, (2) γ -BHC biodegradation by a bacterial isolate, and (3) fate of diazinon in rice soils.

γ -BHC degradation in rice soils

The degradation of γ -BHC was investigated using four different kinds of Philippine soils incubated under upland and flooded conditions. The results are shown in Fig. 6. Under upland soil conditions (at field capacity) very little or no γ -BHC was degraded during the incubation period. On the other hand, under flooded conditions, a large amount of the γ -BHC added disappeared in a

month. The extent of γ -BHC degradation depended on the kind of soil, and, it seems, on the organic matter content of the soil. A higher organic matter content showed a more rapid γ -BHC degradation. The effect of glucose on the degradation of γ -BHC is shown in Table 12. Although there was a lag period of 2 weeks because of the large amount applied, almost 90 percent of the γ -BHC added disappeared after 50 days in the presence of glucose, whereas only 75 percent was decomposed in the control. These results show that the addition of organic materials favors the biodegradation of γ -BHC. It is not known whether the stimulating effect of organic materials is due to the enhancement of the growth of γ -BHC-degrading microflora or to the lowering of the reduction potential. The degradation of γ -BHC appeared to occur only under anaerobic conditions (Fig. 6). This was confirmed by another experiment in which the degradation of γ -BHC was observed in flooded Maahas clay soil kept under different conditions of aeration: aerobic, by in-

cubating the soil on a shaker; submerged, by letting the soil stand; and anaerobic, by incubating the soil under nitrogen gas. As shown in Table 13, no γ -BHC biodegradation occurred under an aerobic condition. Under submerged and anaerobic conditions, however, more than 60 percent of the γ -BHC added was degraded in 15 days. Available data showed that the molecular oxygen in the soil disappeared in one day after the soil was flooded. The molecular oxygen could be an inhibitor of the microbial degradation of γ -BHC, and the degradation proceeds only in its absence. Besides molecular oxygen, combined oxygen such as nitrate and manganic oxide also inhibited the degradation of γ -BHC. In aerobic soils or under upland soil conditions, the persistence of γ -BHC is explained not only by the presence of molecular oxygen but also of nitrate and other combined oxygen of oxidized compound (Table 14). The addition of rice straw was found to enhance γ -BHC degradation.

The effect of temperature on γ -BHC degradation is shown in Table 15. Each soil sample was presubmerged for a month at room temperature to avoid the effect of a change in pH and oxidation-reduction potential during the experiment under different temperatures. The data clearly indicate a positive relationship between the bacterial activity of γ -BHC and temperature, suggesting that γ -BHC residue is less of a problem in the tropical than in the temperate areas.

γ -BHC biodegradation by a bacterial isolate

A number of γ -BHC degrading bacteria in rice soils have been isolated in our Department. The most active of these bacteria was used for further biochemical studies of γ -BHC metabolism. The resting cell suspension of the anaerobic bacterium quickly decomposed γ -BHC and, in the process, a less stable unknown compound was detected in the gas chromatogram. Gamma-pentachlorocyclohexene (γ -PCCH) has been suggested as an immediate intermediate of γ -BHC degradation in other biological systems and in soils. In an experiment, the bacterium active in γ -BHC degradation degraded γ -PCCH faster than γ -BHC (Table 16). No other compound appeared in the gas chromatogram during the degradation of γ -PCCH. The results seemed to indicate that γ -PCCH is an intermediate of γ -BHC degradation. However, the R_f value in the

Table 15. Effect of temperature on γ -BHC degradation in flooded Maahas soil.*

Temperature (C)	Time of incubation (days)				
	0	3	7	10	15
	μ g γ -BHC remaining/20 g soil				
20	154	151	142	131	98
24	154	142	132	124	81
30	154	134	119	111	61
35	154	117	95	72	47

* Samples with 5 cm water layer above soil surface were incubated for 1 month at 30 C before adding γ -BHC to eliminate the effect of changes in pH and redox potential.

Table 16. Biodegradation of γ -BHC and γ -PCCH.*

Time of incubation (min)	γ -BHC remaining (ppm)**	γ -PCCH remaining (ppm)**
0	2.7	19.2
30	2.7	13.7
60	2.4	10.1

* Total volume of reaction mixture: 40 ml (10 ml cell suspension + 30 ml γ -BHC in phosphate buffer); Total N of reaction mixture: 35.2 mg.

**The values represent the biological degradation by living cells after subtracting the chemical degradation of the control (dead cells).

thin layer chromatogram (TLC) of the unknown product and the R_t (retention time) in the gas chromatogram of the same product differed from those of γ -PCCH, suggesting that the compound might differ from γ -PCCH (Table 17, 18).

To verify if the unknown compound is a derivative of γ -BHC, and to estimate its amount, ring-labeled C^{14} - γ -BHC was used. The radioautogram shown in Fig. 7 indicates that there was radioactivity in the unknown compound and that the compound is a metabolite of γ -BHC. A considerable amount of radioactivity was recovered from the region on the TLC containing the unknown compound and, eventually most of the γ -BHC was degraded to a metabolite not extractable by hexane (Table 19). This metabolite is probably a further breakdown product of the unknown compound.

Fig. 7. Radioautographic representation of γ -BHC and its metabolite produced by a soil bacterium under anaerobic conditions.

The effect of nitrate as a form of combined oxygen on the biodegradation of γ -BHC by the bacterium (Table 20) was also determined. As with the results obtained in the soil experiment, nitrate inhibited the bacterial degradation of γ -BHC in a way similar to the inhibition by molecular oxygen. Nitrate could be an inhibitor of the dechlorination process. It is interesting to note that potassium sulfate and potassium chloride stimulated the degradation of γ -BHC (Fig. 8), probably due to the lowering of the oxidation-reduction potential by the salts. Since the bacterium could also degrade DDT to DDD (Table 21), a process by which one

chlorine is removed, the unknown compound produced during γ -BHC degradation could be a compound equivalent to γ -pentachlorocyclohexane ($C_6H_7Cl_5$) instead of γ -pentachlorocyclohexene ($C_6H_5Cl_5$).

Fate of diazinon in rice soils

Studies to identify the degradation compound of diazinon in submerged Maahas clay soil showed that a hydrolysis product of diazinon, 2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxy pyrimidine, accumulated to a greater extent in nonsterilized soil than in sterilized soil (Fig. 9). A reversible relationship between diazinon level and amount of hydrolysis product was observed. The results suggest the active participation of the soil microflora in the degradation of diazinon to its hydrolysis product. Available data on diazinon degradation under upland soil conditions showed very small amounts of the metabolite in the soil, but a fairly large amount of diazinon was mineralized to CO_2 . Under submerged soil conditions, however, about 43 and 20 percent of the diazinon applied were converted to the hydrolysis product in non-sterilized and sterilized soils, respectively, and very small amounts of CO_2 were recovered.

The distribution of radioactivity in submerged soils with ring-labeled diazinon after 30 days of incubation is shown in Table 22. Only diazinon was identified in the hexane fraction. Most of the radioactivity in the chloroform-diethyl ether fraction was located at the R_f position of 2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxy pyrimidine — a metabolite detected from the flooded soils with added

Table 17. Gas chromatographic data comparing the retention times of γ -BHC and the unknown substances produced during γ -BHC and α -BHC biodegradation.

Column condition		Actual retention time (min)				
Packing and size	Operating temp., C	γ -BHC	α -BHC	γ -PCCH	Unknown peak of γ -BHC	Unknown peak of α -BHC
5% QF-1 on 60-80 Chromosorb W 5 feet x 1/8 inch, Pyrex glass	165	3.61	2.53	1.31	1.31	0.92
5% DC-200 on 60-80 Chromosorb G 5 feet x 1/8 inch, Pyrex glass	165	7.41	6.04	2.54	2.16	1.87

Table 18. Comparison of R_f of γ -BHC, γ -PCCH and of the unknown metabolite formed during the degradation of γ -BHC by a soil bacterium.*

Distance from the spotting site (cm)	Authentic γ -BHC	Authentic γ -PCCH	Unknown metabolite
1 - 5	-	-	-
5 - 9	-	-	+
9 - 11	+	-	-
11 - 15	+	+	-

* Signs (+) and (-) indicate the presence and absence of each compound.

Table 19. Distribution of radioactivity at R_f of γ -BHC and the unknown product on the chromatoplate of the hexane extract of bacterial cells exposed to ring-labeled C^{14} -BHC.

Time of incubation (hours)	Living		Dead	
	γ -BHC	unknown	γ -BHC	unknown
	cpm/ml reaction mixture			
0	56,240	40	58,520	0
2	12,200	9,960	50,920	200
4	5,780	6,230	49,280	160
6	3,790	4,120	48,760	200
24	20	80	40,560	0

Table 20. Effect of nitrate on γ -BHC degradation.*

Time of incubation (hours)	Amount of γ -BHC* (ppm)	
	Control	with 0.2% KNO_3
0	3.5	3.7
2	1.8	3.2
4	1.3	3.7
8	0.3	3.4
24	0.0	2.1

* Total volume of reaction mixture: 40 ml (10 ml cell suspension + 30 ml γ -BHC in phosphate buffer); total N of reaction mixture: 28.2 mg.

Fig. 8. Effect of some potassium salts on the biodegradation of γ -BHC and formation of the unknown intermediate.

diazinon. However, direct cleavage at the phosphorus-oxygen-pyrimidine bond should result in the formation of diethyl thiophosphate in addition to the pyrimidinyl moiety. Diethyl thiophosphate may be further degraded or metabolized by some soil microflora, leading to the formation of ethanol, inorganic phosphate and sulfate.

From the foregoing, it appears that the major step in the degradation of diazinon in flooded soils is hydrolysis which results in the formation of

Fig. 9. Formation of 2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxy pyrimidine from C¹⁴ diazinon in submerged Maahas clay.

Table 22. Distribution of radioactivity recovered from different fractions 30 days after C¹⁴-diazinon application to submerged Maahas clay.

Treatment	C ¹⁴ O ₂	Hexane	Chloroform-diethyl ether	Water	Soil bound	Total radioactivity recovered	Initial radioactivity
cpm / 20 g soil							
Nonsterilized	60	28,000	85,000	4,000	81,000	198,060	197,000
Sterilized	0	75,000	45,000	2,000	68,000	190,000	221,000

Table 21. Conversion of p, p'-DDT to DDD by the γ -BHC-degrading bacterium under anaerobic conditions.*

Time of incubation (hours)	DDT (ppm)	DDD (ppm)
0	8.5	0.0
4	6.3	2.4
24	0.0	6.9

* Total volume of reaction mixture: 25 ml (5 ml cell suspension + 20 ml γ -BHC in phosphate buffer); total N of reaction mixture: 21.6 mg.

2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxy pyrimidine. Under submerged conditions wherein the bulk of the soil microflora is anaerobic, the hydrolysis product tends to accumulate and persist in large quantities without being oxidized. The accumulation of the hydrolysis product, however, should not pose a serious problem since the compound is far less toxic than the parent molecule based on the available data on the anticholine activity.

Agronomy

Agronomy research continued to be directed toward management practices and their immediate application to rice production.

New yield records for replicated experiments were established during the year with a 10,474 kg/ha yield from an IR8 crop grown with cultural practices within the reach of many Asian farmers, a 3-crop annual production of 19,632 kg/ha using IR400-28-4-5 [Peta/4 x Taichung (Native)1], and a 4-crop annual production of 22,419 kg/ha with Taichung (Native)1 and 22,012 kg/ha with IR8 (40).

Soil fertility studies emphasized the fertilizer requirements of direct-seeded, flooded rice. Transplanted and direct-seeded rice were compared with respect to stand establishment, weed control practices, and effect on varietal type.

Studies on the time of harvesting flooded rice were initiated during the year and information was obtained on the effects of nitrogen level and time of harvest on the grain yield and milling quality of rice.

Weed control in rice was an important part of the Agronomy program. The first agronomic evidence of the efficacy of granular α,α,α -trichloroethyl styrene for the selective control of annual grasses in transplanted rice was obtained at the Institute. Another new accession, CP53619, gave excellent weed control in transplanted flooded and non-flooded, upland rice. The remarkable performance of granular 2,4-D isopropyl ester illustrates its potential for low-cost weed control in transplanted rice. Low-rate combinations of molinate/bromoxynil and molinate/2,4-D appeared promising for post-emergence weed control in direct-seeded, flooded rice. Activated-charcoal coatings protected germinating rice seeds from injury by several pre-emergence herbicides applied before seeding and made it possible for these otherwise toxic herbicides to be used effectively in broadcast rice.

Experiments were continued on no-tillage techniques for broadcast and transplanted rice, on sources and rates of fertilizer phosphorus, on water management, and on the agronomic aspects of production resource management for transplanted rice.

Continuous Rice Cropping

Studies of the continuous growing of rice on the same land were continued in 1968. From the farmer's standpoint this experiment has little practical value, but it does give the Institute an opportunity to fully evaluate some of the improved early-maturing varieties or genetic lines. Also, it affords a chance to test the capability of soil under good management to withstand intensive, continuous, one-crop cultivation. A total of 5 days was used for land preparation for the four crops grown during the year. Figure 1 shows the lines tested and Table 1 gives the schedule of operations and the grain yields obtained. Taichung (Native) 1 yielded the most grain for one crop

(8,212 kg/ha), and for four crops (22,410 kg/ha) in 365 days. IR8 (40) had the second highest 4-crop total yield of 22,012 kg/ha in 365 days. Calculated on a production-per-day basis, Taichung (Native) 1 yielded 61 kg/ha/day and IR8 (40), 60 kg/ha/day. IR262-43-8-11 produced 21,777 kg/ha in four crops in 359 days, or an average of 66 kg/ha/day.

Date-of-planting Experiment

The date-of-planting experiment (see 1962-1967 Annual Reports) was redesigned in 1968. Since no significant grain yield differences had been found among the three spacings (15 x 15 cm, 25 x 25 cm, and 35 x 35 cm) used in previous years, a

Table 1. Continuous rice-cropping experiment (4 crops a year). IRRI, 1967-1968.

Crop	Transplanted	Harvested	Seedling age (days)	Field duration (days)	Crop duration (days)	Grain yield* (kg/ha)	Productivity based on field duration (kg/ha/day)
IR 262-43-8-11							
1st	Nov. 12, '67	Feb. 9, '68	21	90	111	4440	
2nd	Feb. 11, '68	May 7, '68	23	87	110	7501	
3rd	May 9, '68	Aug. 5, '68	24	89	113	5768	
4th	Aug. 7, '68	Nov. 3, '68	23	89	112	4068	
				355			
		Land preparation		4			
		Total		359		21,777	66
Taichung (Native) 1							
1st	Oct. 11, '67	Jan. 10, '68	26	92	118	3558**	
2nd	Jan. 12, '68	April 16, '68	30	96	126	8212	
3rd	April 9, '68	July 18, '68	26	91	117	7011	
4th	July 20, '68	Oct. 8, '68	23	81	104	3638	
				360			
		Land preparation		5			
		Total		365		22,419	61
IR8 (40)							
1st	Oct. 11, '67	Jan. 10, '68	26	92	118	3075*	
2nd	Jan. 12, '68	April 16, '68	30	96	126	7999	
3rd	April 19, '68	July 18, '68	26	91	117	6758	
4th	July 20, '68	Oct. 8, '68	23	81	104	4180	
				360			
		Land preparation		5			
		Total		365		22,012	60

* At 14% moisture, average of 2 replications and 2 samples per replication.

** 10% virus.

Table 2. Mean grain yield and yield components of four rice varieties for four nitrogen levels and the solar radiation totals during the last 45 days before harvest. Date-of-planting experiment, IRR1, 1968.

Harvest month	Duration (days)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Total tillers at harvest (no./sq m)	Panicle (no./sq m)	Unfilled grains (%)	Solar energy* (g-cal cm ⁻²)	Duration (days)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Total tillers at harvest (no./sq m)	Panicle (no./sq m)	Unfilled grains (%)	Solar energy* (g-cal cm ⁻²)
IR8												
May	123	7981	440	420	9	19,764	119	5392	410	390	19	19,659
June	126	6693	440	430	17	17,891	126	3514	365	335	31	17,309
July	121	5028	385	370	20	16,152	131	2494	405	320	39	16,031
August	118	4638	345	340	29	13,814	132	1661	295	265	43	12,910
September	124	4724	340	320	17	14,009	132	2435	290	265	38	14,021
October	117	5471	345	330	14	14,265	127	2607	255	220	32	14,917
November	119	4956	295	280	22	13,381	121	2561	290	280	29	13,339
December	118	4607	251	235	13	11,951	124	3796	290	275	24	11,667
IR5												
May	127	6954	420	395	21	19,575	117	5530	360	340	7	19,566
June	139	5566	420	405	28	16,413	127	4853	295	285	6	16,823
July	140-143	5210	380	355	26	14,536	124	3161	300	275	17	16,298
August	137	4525	335	320	27	12,781	122	3239	260	235	13	13,727
September	138	4894	330	315	26	14,132	127	2942	245	230	22	14,008
October	127	4737	320	310	18	14,917	117	3253	245	235	15	14,265
November	125	4389	310	305	21	13,404	118	3654	250	240	12	13,430
December	124	4236	330	315	23	11,667	118	3477	195	180	10	11,951
Milfor-6(2)												

* 45 days before harvest.

Fig. 1. Four rice varieties or selections were grown in the field in the four-crops-a-year continuous rice rotation experiment. IR8 (40) and Taichung (Native) 1 produced 22,000 and 22,400 kg/ha, respectively. IRRI, 1967-1968.

uniform 20 x 20 cm spacing was adopted in 1968. IR5 was added to the three previous test varieties, IR8, Milfor-6(2), and H-4, and the following nitrogen levels were used: 0, 30, 90, and 120 kg/ha. All nitrogen was applied before the last harrowing and was incorporated thoroughly with a comb harrow. In all plots 30 kg/ha P_2O_5 was applied at planting.

Among eight harvests of the four test varieties, the highest grain yield obtained was 9,345 kg/ha in the May harvest of IR8 (Fig. 2). IR8 also gave the highest peak yield in all harvest months, except in September when IR5 obtained a peak yield equal to that of IR8.

As the solar radiation received during the last 45 days before harvest decreased from about 20,000 g-cal cm^{-2} for the May harvest to 13,000

Fig. 2. Nitrogen response of four varieties as affected by month of harvest. Date-of-planting experiment, IRRI, 1968.

g-cal cm⁻² for the August harvest, the nitrogen response of both IR8 and IR5 decreased. Even so, Fig. 2 shows that these improved varieties had better nitrogen response than the traditional varieties represented by H-4, a tall indica variety from Ceylon, and Milfor-6(2), a lodging resistant variety of medium height.

During the wet, cloudy season the highest grain yields were obtained in the October and November harvests. The growth characteristic and yield component data presented in Table 2 help to explain the experimental results. As the solar energy during the 45 days preceding harvest decreased, both the total number of tillers and the number of panicles per square meter decreased for all varieties. Since the IR5 plant is taller and leafier than the IR8 plant, it had a slightly lower panicle density and a higher percentage of unfilled grains and therefore gave lower yields than did IR8 at most solar energy levels.

Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Management

Effect of plant type and nitrogen level on the growth and yield of rice

Experiments were continued in the 1968 dry and wet seasons to study the nitrogen response and the growth characteristics of indica varieties with improved plant types and of Peta, a tall, tropical indica variety.

Dry season. The lines tested are given in Table 3. The highest yield obtained (8,141 kg/ha) in the 1968 dry season was lower than those obtained in the 1966 and 1967 dry seasons (1966 and 1967 Annual Reports) due to the heavy stem borer infestation which was not adequately controlled by applications of diazinon at the recommended rates. The average grain yield of all lines combined increased as the level of nitrogen increased. As in the 1967 dry season, IR400-5-12-10-2 [Peta/4 x T(N)1] gave total yields similar to those of IR8. Of the new selections tested, IR305-3-17-2 [Sigadis/2 x T(N)1] showed the most promise and will be tested further.

Wet season. The lines tested in the 1968 wet season were the same as those used in the dry season. Table 4 shows that IR400-5-12-10-2 gave the highest grain yield and had yields similar to those of IR8 at all levels of nitrogen. As in the dry

season, IR305-3-17-2 showed promise in terms of growth characteristics and grain yield.

Nitrogen response of promising rice selections

Several promising Institute-developed selections were compared with IR8 and Peta under five nitrogen levels in the 1968 wet season. The amount of rainfall during the August to November period was 630 mm while it was 1,171 mm during the same period in 1967. The solar energy values during the ripening period (October-November) were higher by about 1,177 g-cal cm⁻² than those in the same period in 1967. These environmental differences accounted for the higher grain yields of several selections in 1968. The highest grain yield, 6,937 kg/ha, was obtained with IR593-3-17 [IR8 x (CP 231 x SLO 17) x Nahng Mon S-4] (Table 5).

IR305-4-12-1-3 [Sigadis/2 x T(N)1] had a grain-straw ratio and grain yield similar to those of IR8. It was 9 cm shorter, had 75 tillers and 75 panicles per square meter more, and fewer filled grains, hence, lower weight per panicle, than IR8. This selection showed enough merit to be tested further.

IR532E576 [TKM-6 x (Peta/3 x T(N)1)] was slightly taller and had more tillers and panicles per square meter and more filled grains per panicle than IR8, but its 100-grain weight and thus, weight per panicle and yield, was lower than that of IR8.

IR8 had the greatest straw strength at maturity and Peta the least at 40 and 80 kg/ha N (Table 6). The calculated straw strength of IR532E576 was less than half that of IR8 (Table 6), primarily because of its thinner and slightly longer culm. This straw weakness explains why IR532E576 lodged after a light rain just prior to harvest. On the other hand, IR8 and IR593-3-17 did not lodge at any growth stage or nitrogen level. IR532E576 thus may not yield as well as IR8 in the normal wet season (June through November) during which several typhoons usually occur.

Nitrogen response of Surinam varieties

An experiment was conducted to compare the nitrogen response of some promising varieties from Surinam with certain of the Institute's high yielding varieties or selections. The results from the 1968 late dry season test (Table 7) indicated that

Table 3. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of indica rice, IRR1, 1968 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*											N-level (mean)			
	IR154-61-1	IR400-5-12-10-2	T(N)1	BPI-76-1	IR8	C4-63	IR160-27-4-1	IR5	Peta	IR253-16-1-2	IR262-7-1-1-2		IR305-3-17-2	IR95-41-11-2-2	IR5-114-3-1-2
0	3360	3443	3830	2851	3561	3711	3465	4260	5036	3403	4070	3531	4429	4656	3829
30	4654	4975	5587	4394	5069	4849	4382	5102	5402	4578	4455	4755	5682	5094	4927
60	4813	6493	6449	5231	5510	5893	5137	6375	6127	5068	5491	6903	6451	6797	5910
90	5353	7197	6973	6117	6995	6785	6180	6989	5859	5667	6626	7428	7691	7469	6666
120	6016	7966	6588	5842	7831	6935	6737	7173	5595	6041	7062	7859	8141	7771	6968
Mean	4839	6015	5885	4887	5793	5635	5180	5980	5604	4951	5541	6095	6479	6357	
Duration (days):	111	114	114	114	121	121	122	128	135	111	114	121	130	137	

* Average, 3 replications.

Analysis of variance:

Nitrogen level (N)**

Variety (V)**

Nitrogen mean in the same variety**

Variety mean in the same nitrogen level**

s.e.

LSD (5%)

CV (X)%

11

9

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Table 4. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of indica rice, IRR1, 1968 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*											N level (Mean)			
	IR154-61-1	IR400-5-12-10-2	IR262-7-1-1-2	T(N)1	IR160-27-4-1	IR253-16-1-2	IR8	IR305-3-17-2	IR5	BPI-76-1	C4-63		IR95-42-11-2-2	IR5-114-8-1-2	Peta
0	3743	3890	3788	4352	3811	3751	4002	3801	3925	3186	4422	4775	4281	2971	3907
20	4197	4433	4327	4493	4100	3893	4492	4253	4231	3493	4569	5050	4723	2729	4213
40	4383	4928	4578	4616	4406	4229	5111	4419	4618	3826	4871	5365	4814	2427	4464

60	4436	4826	4655	4611	4899	3477	5405	5133	4138	3903	4128	5544	4984	2634	4484
80	4957	5875	4533	4918	5477	2525	5731	5419	4132	4025	4019	5795	5378	2329	4651
Mean	4343	4771	4376	4598	4539	3575	4948	4605	4209	2687	4402	5306	4836	2618	4344

* Average, three replications.

Analysis of variance:

Nitrogen level (N)**	s.e.	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Variety (V)**	96	266	14
N x V***	90	248	8
Nitrogen mean in the same or different variety**	305	598	
Variety mean at the same nitrogen level**	283	555	

the Surinam varieties have no apparent grain yield advantage over IR8, but in general have better grain quality.

The highest yield among the Surinam lines was 7,520 kg/ha produced by SML Apura. This variety was about 40 cm taller than IR8, lodged heavily at the highest nitrogen level, and had a similar panicle density, but a higher percentage of unfilled grains (33%) than IR8 (19%). The 100-grain weight and growth duration of SML Apura and of IR8 were similar.

Nitrogen response experiments in a farmer's field

Studies of varietal difference in response to nitrogen were continued on farmer's fields under management practices economically feasible for the average rice farmer. The experiments were conducted in cooperation with the Institute's Experimental Farm Department.

Dry season. In an experiment conducted at Calamba, Laguna, Philippines, using the lines listed in Table 8, the nitrogen levels were varied from 0 to 150 kg/ha. The pest control measures adopted were those that a farmer might use and so were less elaborate than those at the Institute farm. An IR8 grain yield of 10,474 kg/ha at 150 kg/ha N was the highest obtained thus far in any replicated experiments conducted by the Institute. It is interesting to note that this yield occurred using management practices requiring a modest cash input of only P456/ha*.

All other lines tested gave significantly lower grain yields than IR8 (Table 8).

Wet season. The varieties and selections used were the same as in the dry season except that the selection IR532E239 [TKM-6 x (Peta/3 x T(N)1] was added. The increase in the yield of all varieties resulting from the addition of up to 50 kg/ha of nitrogen (Table 9) was significant except in the case of C4-63. As in the dry season, IR8 gave the highest grain yield (6,082 kg/ha) and its average yield at all nitrogen levels was significantly higher than those of all other lines included in the experiment. This high yield was also obtained with management practices which required low (P373/ha) cash inputs. The results from these experiments in a farmer's field demonstrate that

*P3.90 = US \$1.

Table 5. Effect of nitrogen level on the growth characteristics, grain yield, and yield components of promising rice selections. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Variety or selection	Duration (days)	Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers at harvest (no./sq m)	Panicles	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains (% panicle)	Unfilled grains (% panicle)	Panicle length (cm)	100-grain weight (g)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Grain-straw ratio
IR8	125	0	85	156	152	114	13	10	22.6	2.8	3.5	4130	1.0
		20	87	187	186	109	12	10	21.8	3.0	3.3	4834	1.0
		40	90	170	170	110	18	14	22.4	2.8	3.4	5839	1.1
		60	95	207	207	112	15	13	22.4	3.1	3.5	5866	0.9
		80	97	234	230	102	14	13	21.0	3.0	3.4	6133	1.0
		Mean (N level)	91	191	189	109	14	12	22.0	2.9	3.4	5360	1.0
IR593-3-17	125	0	82	166	166	101	19	16	20.8	2.7	3.1	4435	1.2
		20	92	190	190	120	13	10	21.7	2.9	3.7	5554	1.3
		40	88	169	169	100	10	9	20.4	2.8	3.0	5121	1.0
		60	92	230	230	96	10	9	20.6	3.0	3.1	5899	1.1
		80	94	232	232	121	8	6	21.7	3.0	3.8	6937	0.9
		Mean (N level)	90	197	197	108	12	10	21.0	2.9	3.3	5589	1.1
IR532E576	120	0	90	189	188	126	36	22	25.6	1.9	2.8	3737	0.9
		20	96	229	228	117	23	16	26.2	2.0	2.9	4673	0.9
		40	98	233	217	140	34	19	27.1	2.0	2.9	4838	1.0
		60	101	264	257	120	24	18	25.4	2.1	2.7	5027	0.8
		80	107	286	279	131	37	22	25.9	2.0	3.1	5268	0.8
		Mean (N level)	98	240	234	127	31	19	26.0	2.0	2.8	4709	0.9
IR305-4-12-1-3	131	0	76	223	223	82	9	9	23.3	2.8	2.2	4670	1.0
		20	81	252	243	97	7	6	22.7	3.0	3.6	5352	1.0
		40	84	252	252	85	12	12	23.4	2.9	2.6	5369	1.0
		60	82	271	271	92	11	10	22.9	2.8	2.6	5815	1.0
		80	85	330	330	83	10	10	23.1	2.9	2.1	6011	1.0
		Mean (N level)	82	266	264	88	10	9	23.0	2.9	2.6	5441	1.0
Peta	144	0	148	163	163	88	69	44	25.1	2.6	2.9	3936	0.5
		20	152	189	188	83	40	33	24.4	2.5	2.7	3120	0.4
		40	149	182	181	89	44	33	24.1	2.7	2.8	2985	0.4
		60	151	169	168	81	55	41	23.4	2.6	2.6	3091	0.3
		80	157	143	142	95	49	33	25.1	2.6	2.9	2112	0.3
		Mean (N level)	151	169	168	87	51	37	24.4	2.6	2.7	3049	0.3

high yields and profits can be obtained from cultural practices which require cash inputs within the reach of many Asian farmers.

Nitrogen response of indica rice

Cooperative soil fertility experiments were conducted to (a) establish the nitrogen response curves of selected indica types in several locations during the dry and wet seasons, and (b) to determine the yield potential of some semi-dwarf indica varieties and selections under a wide variety of soil and climatic conditions.

Each variety or selection was included because of its desirable plant type, with Peta, or the best available local variety, serving as the check. In the dry season, the nitrogen rates ranged from 0 to 150 kg/ha incorporated just before planting, plus 30 kg/ha topdressed at the time of panicle initiation. In the wet season the highest nitrogen rate applied at planting time was 130 kg/ha with 20 kg applied at panicle initiation. All plots were treated uniformly with 60 kg/ha P_2O_5 .

A split-plot design with three replications was used. The nitrogen treatments served as the main plot with the varieties as subplots. All varieties were planted at 20 x 20 cm spacing in an 18-sq m plot. No levees were constructed between varieties within the main plot.

Tests at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center. Table 10 shows the grain yields of 12 indica lines in the 1968 dry season-N-response experiment at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Central Luzon. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that, without added nitrogen, only IR95-42 gave a yield significantly higher than Peta, the control variety, while IR400-4, IR262-7, and BPI-76 (Maligaya selection) yielded significantly less than Peta. The yields of the other varieties and selections were similar to that of Peta without added nitrogen. The addition of up to 150 kg/ha N did not significantly influence the grain yield of Peta, but at 180 kg/ha it lodged severely and gave yields significantly lower than when no nitrogen was applied. The yields of all the other varieties increased significantly with the application of each additional 30 kg/ha up to 150 kg/ha N. For most lines, an application exceeding 120 kg/ha N did not result in any further significant yield increases. The optimum nitrogen level seems to be 90 kg/ha during the dry season.

Table 6. Effect of nitrogen level on the straw strength of indica varieties and selections. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Variety or selection	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Straw strength at maturity	
		P_1/E^* (without leaf sheath)	P_2/E^{**} (with leaf sheath)
IR8	0	19	96
	40	15	82
	80	15	83
	Average	16	87
IR532E576	0	9	46
	40	6	31
	80	6	28
	Average	7	35
Peta	0	4	11
	40	22	8
	80	2	8
	Average	3	9
IR593-3-12	0	17	57
	40	14	45
	80	11	49
	Average	14	50
IR305-4-12-1-3	0	13	31
	40	7	22
	80	12	23
	Average	11	25

$$* P_1/E = \frac{0.121 \times (d_2^4 - d_1^4)}{L^2}$$

$$** P_2/E = \frac{0.121 \times (d_3^4 - d_1^4)}{L^2}$$

Data taken from 50 tillers per replication and 3 replicates per treatment.

d_1 = inside stem diameter of 2nd internode (mm)

d_2 = outside stem diameter of 2nd internode (mm)

d_3 = diameter of the stem including the leaf sheath (mm)

L = stem length (cm)

The variety means showed that, except for BPI-76, all the varieties and selections were superior to Peta. The highest total mean yield of 7,408 kg/ha was obtained with IR5-114.

An evaluation of the daily productivity of individual varieties at a uniform nitrogen level showed that at 90 kg/ha N, the most promising varieties were IR253-16 (60 kg/ha/day), T(N)1 (57 kg/ha/day), and IR8 (49 kg/ha/day). At its best nitrogen level (60 kg/ha N), Peta produced only 39 kg/ha/day.

Table 7. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of some Surinam and other high-yielding indica varieties, IRRI, February 15 through July 3, 1968.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*										
	IR8	IR5	C4-63	Taichung (N)1	IR262-7-1-1-2	SML Apura	SML Alupi	SML Kapuri	SML Temerin	SML Galibi	Mean
0 + 0	5233	5489	5221	5007	4947	5401	4821	5277	4785	4518	5070
15 + 20	6099	6029	5860	5258	5421	6382	5297	5838	5248	4600	5603
50 + 20	7213	6339	6411	6715	5540	7028	5378	6372	5559	5316	6187
85 + 20	6964	5547	6371	6501	6187	7520	5064	5964	6274	4895	6129
120 + 20	8119	5740	6318	7816	6025	6329	5581	5088	4720	5789	6153
Mean (variety)	6726	6829	6036	6259	5624	6532	5228	5708	5317	5024	5828
Duration (days)	130	145	130	119	125	135	146	138	134	140	

* Average, 2 replications.

Analysis of variance:	s.e.	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Nitrogen level (N)*	164	642	13
Variety (V)**	125	357	7
2 V means at same N**	280	799	—
2 N means at same or different V**	442	982	—

Table 8. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of indica rice. Calamba, Laguna, Philippines, 1968 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture					Mean
	IR8	IR5	IR262-7-1-1-2	IR400-5-12-10-2	C4-63	
0	5928	5150	5029	4782	4874	5152
30 + 20	6418	6518	6739	6636	6835	6629
80 + 20	10196	8128	8818	8842	7950	8786
130 + 20	10474	8209*	8787	9026	7822	8863
Mean (variety)	8256	7001	7346	7324	6873	
Duration (days)	126	130	117	117	117	

* Includes one replication damaged by rats.

Analysis of variance:	s.e.	LSD (5%)	CV(X)%
Nitrogen level (N)**	316	1424	14
Variety (V)**	135	405	5
N X V	270	611	—

Cash inputs:	Cost (P/ha)
Diazinon (3x), 6 kg/ha a.i.	150
Foidol, 0.04%	27
MCPA, 0.8 kg/ha a.i.	22
Handweeding, (1x)	80
Nitrogen, 150 kg/ha	177
	P 456

Table 9. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of indica rice. Calamba, Laguna, Philippines, 1968 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture						Mean
	IR8	IR400-5-12-10-2	IR5	C4-63	IR532-E239	IR262-7-1-1-2	
0	3416	3216	3824	3857	3215	3348	3479
25	5332	4398	4447	4778	4531	4229	4619
50	5843	5736	4906	5031	5037	5007	5260
75	6082	5618	5515	5074	5254	4937	5413
Mean (variety)	5168	4742	4673	4685	4509	4380	
Duration (days)	123	114	128	123	120	114	

Analysis of variance:

	s.e.	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Nitrogen level**	93	419	6.9
Variety (V)**	123	366	7.5
N x C n.s.	350		

Cash inputs:

	Cost (P/ha)
Diazinon, (3x) 6 kg/ha a.i.	150
Folidol, 0.04 (2x)	54
Weed control	80*
Nitrogen, 75 kg/ha	88
	P 372

* Estimate.

In the wet season, the yields of all the varieties tested generally increased with the addition of 60 kg/ha N (Table 11). The highest yields were obtained from IR532E576 which outyielded IR8 at all nitrogen levels. The 1968 wet season was unusual because the rainfall was lower than normal during the reproductive and ripening stages of the rice crop and because no serious typhoon occurred. The yield of Peta was therefore higher than in the two previous wet seasons (1966 and 1967 Annual Reports) with its best yield, 4,745 kg/ha, obtained at 150 kg/ha N. All the improved varieties or selections, except BPI-76, IR262-43-8-11, and IR253-16-1-2, gave yields similar to that of Peta (4,110 kg/ha) without added nitrogen.

An analysis of the protein content of the brown rice of six lines indicated that, on the average, it increased from 7.2 to 9.5 percent as the nitrogen level was increased from 0 to 150 kg/ha (Fig. 3). BPI-76 showed the highest mean protein content, 9.9 percent, while IR5, IR8, IR532E576, C4-63, and Peta showed protein contents between 8 and

8.2 percent. The highest value obtained was 11.2 percent from BPI-76 at 150 kg/ha N.

Experiments at the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station. Tables 12 and 13 show the grain yields obtained from the nitrogen response experiments during the 1968 dry and wet seasons, respectively, at the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station near Naga City in the Philippines.

The high CV(X) (33%) of the dry season was attributable to drought-induced soil cracking during the flowering stage of most varieties, which caused a wide range of maturity dates within a variety. The ANOV, however, showed some trends. Generally, there were no significant yield differences among the test varieties without added nitrogen. The application of 60 kg/ha N significantly increased the yields of all test varieties, except Peta, over those at the 0 kg/ha N level (Table 12) and these yields increased with added nitrogen up to the 150 kg/ha N level. A significant yield increase was obtained in Peta with the addition of 120 kg/ha N. The highest yield (6,929

Table 10. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of different varietal types, IRRI-BPI Cooperative Fertility Experiment, Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Philippines, 1968 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*												
	IR5-114	IR95-42-11-2-2	IR8	IR253-16-1-2	T(N)1	IR5	MIFB 3221-1	IR400-5-12-10-2	C4-63	IR262-7-1-1-2	BPI-76 (Maligaya Selection)	Peta	Mean
B + PI**													
0	5191	5459	4990	3638	4094	4805	3696	3326	3826	3287	3280	4376	4164
30+30	7057	6865	5623	4605	4845	5321	5102	4729	4815	4188	3749	5228	5177
60+30	7913	7009	7228	6420	6079	5993	5401	5005	5063	4742	4575	4483	5826
90+30	7958	6652	6894	6979	6387	6277	5905	5595	5833	5708	5239	4300	6144
120+30	7882	6866	7112	6965	6767	6066	6187	6313	6146	6055	5347	4737	6370
150+30	8449	7633	7343	7152	6615	6078	6331	7049	5967	6181	5127	3148	6423
Mean (variety)	7408	6748	6532	5960	5798	5757	5437	5336	5275	5027	4553	4378	
Duration (days)	154-160	154-160	145	118-124	118-124	145	154	126	126	126	145	146-154	
Productivity (kg/ha/day)†	55	49	54	60	57	45	38	44	44	41	34	39††	

* Average, three replications.

** B + PI = Basal + panicle initiation.

† Based on field duration at 90 kg/ha total N.

†† Based on field duration at 60 kg/ha total N.

Analysis of variance:	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Nitrogen level (N)**	448	15
Variety (V)**	348	9
2 variety means at same N	853	
2 nitrogen means at same or different V	931	

kg/ha) was obtained with Taichung (N)1 at 150 kg/ha N.

During the 1968 wet season the grain yields of all test lines, except Peta, increased significantly up to the 90 kg/ha N level (Table 13). The highest grain yield (6,652 kg/ha) was obtained with IR8 at 150 kg/ha N. Without added nitrogen, IR8, IR532E576, IR532E239, and IR253-16-1-2 gave significantly higher grain yields than Peta.

Nitrogen response experiment at the Central Philippine University. The nitrogen-response experiment at the Central Philippine University in the Western Visayas involved six varieties and five levels of added nitrogen (0 to 150 kg/ha). Table 14 shows the grain yields of five of the varieties; that of the sixth variety, Peta, was not included since

the plants matured late, were affected by drought and infested with rats. Of these five varieties, only four were statistically analyzed since the IR5 plots without added nitrogen were also damaged by drought and rats. The ANOV showed a highly significant difference among nitrogen levels and varieties. At 150 kg/ha N, IR400-5 and IR8 gave yields of 10,153 and 9,890 kg/ha, respectively. The yields of IR262-7 and C4-63 increased up to the 120 kg/ha N level and then decreased with additional nitrogen. Generally, IR400-5, IR8, and IR262-7 yielded significantly better than did C4-63.

All plots without added nitrogen matured much later than those with nitrogen additions.

Table 15 shows the highly efficient use of

Fig. 3. Effect of nitrogen levels on the protein content of brown rice. IIRRI-BPI (Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center) cooperative fertilizer experiment, 1968 wet season.

nitrogen by nitrogen-responsive varieties. At 150 kg/ha N, the average grain production of IR400-5 was 97 kg/ha/day. Even at this high nitrogen level, the net return per peso invested can be as high as P6.60.*

Of the new selections tested in replicated field experiments, only IR400-5, which yielded over 10,000 kg/ha, has equalled the yield performance of IR8. This selection, therefore, merits further testing.

Effect of varietal type, season, nitrogen level, and insect and weed control on grain yield

Since the maximum yields of nitrogen-responsive, early maturing, short, stiff-strawed rice varieties can be realized only with improved cultural practices, efforts were continued to determine the optimum levels of management practices for two varietal types of rice. Field experiments were conducted at the Institute farm during the 1968 dry

and wet seasons.

Dry season. Five levels of nitrogen - 0, 70, 100, 130, and 160 kg/ha; 8 cumulative levels of diazinon - 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 applications of 2.0 kg/ha a.i./application; and 4 levels of weeding - no-weeding, 1 handweeding, MCPA + 1 handweeding, and MCPA + 2 handweedings - were used. A fractional replicated design with 8 blocks of 16 plots each was used.

For the plots receiving added nitrogen, 30, 60, 90 and 120 kg/ha N as ammonium sulfate, was incorporated into the soil at the final harrowing, with an additional 40 kg/ha N applied at panicle initiation. Diazinon was applied at 2, 10, and 30 days after transplanting, at panicle initiation, booting, heading, and 15 days after heading. The time of handweeding was the same as in the previous experiments (1967 Annual Report).

IR8 gave the highest grain yield, 8,572 kg/ha with a nitrogen application of 160 kg/ha. Weeds were controlled by one application of MCPA followed by two handweedings. Six diazinon applications were used to control insects. The highest grain yield of H-4 was 7,848 kg/ha at 130 kg/ha N with the same weeding treatments and five diazinon applications.

The ANOV for grain yield showed a highly significant difference between the varieties, nitrogen levels, weeding levels, and accumulated diazinon levels. It also showed a significant interaction between variety and nitrogen.

IR8 and H-4 gave similar grain yields without added nitrogen (Table 16), while their yields increased with added nitrogen up to 130 kg/ha N (although H-4 had a lower rate of increase). The further addition of nitrogen did not increase the yield of IR8 and decreased that of H-4. At all nitrogen levels the yield of IR8 was higher than that of H-4.

The ANOV showed a highly significant difference among weeding levels, but no significance in the variety x weeding interaction. Weeding increased the grain yield of both IR8 and H-4 (Table 17). The yield with MCPA spray followed by one handweeding did not differ significantly from that with one handweeding alone, but the

*This calculation assumes that the cost/kg of nitrogen as Urea (45% N) is P1.20, rough rice is P0.36/kg, and 1/6 of the increase in yield attributable to fertilizer nitrogen is deducted for added harvesting cost.

Table 11. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of different varietal types. IRRRI-BPI cooperative fertility experiment, Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1968 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture												
	IR532 E576	IR5-114	IR532 E239	IR532-1 33	IR532 E257	IR5	IR8	C4-63	Peta	BPI-76 (Maligaya selection)	IR262-43-8-11	IR253-16-1-12	Mean
B + PI**													
0	4010	4089	3939	4565	4177	3987	3737	3682	4110	2697	2508	2624	3677
10+20	4867	4861	5038	4709	4750	4528	3914	4314	4334	3471	2820	2311	4160
40+20	5797	5816	4939	5352	5488	5471	4642	4813	4280	4133	3529	3782	4837
70+20	5583	5501	5646	5713	5312	5223	4983	5035	4572	4333	4299	3162	4947
100+20	6144	6599	5731	5631	5505	5383	5948	5365	4539	4258	4429	4136	5222
130+20	5914	5760	5864	5279	5443	5099	5264	5071	4745	3648	4560	4059	5059
Mean (variety)	5386	5288	5193	5192	5112	4949	4749	4713	4430	3757	3691	3346	
Duration (days)	123-126	133	123-126	123	123-126	133	123-126	123	133	123	108	108-113	

* Average, three replications.

**B + PI = Basal + panicle initiation.

Analysis of variance:	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Nitrogen level (N)**	354	14
Variety (V)**	316	10
N X V n.s.	—	—

Table 12. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of different varietal types. IRRRI-BPI cooperative fertility experiment, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur, Philippines, 1968 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*												
	T(N)1	IR5-114	IR253-16-1-2	IR8	IR400-5 12-10-2	C4-63	IR95-42-11-2-2	IR5	BPI-76-1	IR262-7-1-1-2	MIFB 322-1	Peta	Mean
B + PI**													
0	3780	3788	3729	3469	3669	3659	3380	2927	3334	3171	2623	3176	3392
30+30	5451	5275	5303	5689	5153	5378	5916	5223	5310	4712	4422	4257	5174
60+30	5961	6310	5943	5662	5444	5484	5700	5613	5289	4313	4360	3768	5321
90+30	6313	6652	5542	5754	5696	6163	4922	6122	5807	5439	5001	4488	5658
120+30	6929	6801	6309	6267	5987	6234	5856	5790	5899	5278	5662	3350	5864
150+30	6387	5580	5829	5670	6403	5256	5830	5760	5535	4866	5217	2415	5396
Mean (variety)	5804	5734	5443	5418	5392	5362	5267	5239	5196	4630	4543	3576	
Duration (days)	131-138	149-154	131-138	135-153	131-135	131-144	138-159	143-159	131-138	131-132	144-156	149-159	

* Average, 3 replications.

** B + PI = Basal + panicle initiation.

Analysis of variance:	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Nitrogen (N)**	620	33.2
Variety (V)**	459	13.6
2 variety means at the same N	1124	
2 nitrogen means at the same or different V	1241	

Table 13. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of different, varietal types. IRR-BPI cooperative fertility experiment, Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur, Philippines, 1968 wet season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*												
	IR8	IR5-114	IR532 E257	IR532 E576	IR532 E239	IR5	C4-63	IR253-16-1-2	IR262-43-8-11	BPI-76	Peta	IR400-5-12-10†	Mean ††
B + PI**													
0	5117	4025	3991	4547	4477	4532	3840	4473	3426	4005	3815	3198	4204
10+20	5251	5466	4786	4846	4669	5185	4101	4493	3840	4159	4141	3500	4812
40+20	5684	6091	5603	5258	4938	5953	4862	4929	4120	4111	4046	4984	5054
70+20	6499	6462	6175	5853	5887	5587	5383	5049	5107	4927	4101	4894	5548
100+20	6296	6469	6227	6051	5887	5575	5356	4741	5500	4622	3150	6116	5443
130+20	6652	5559	6289	5266	5798	4744	5162	4183	5840	4506	3062	5628	5188
Mean (variety)	5917	5679	5512	5304	5276	5263	4784	4645	4606	4388	3719	4720	
Duration (days)	125-137	132-138	125-130	122-130	125-130	137-138	122-124	116-122	108-115	122-138	132-138	108-115	

*Average, three replications.

** B + PI = Basal + panicle initiation.

† One replication.

†† Excluding IR400-5-12-10.

Analysis of variance (excluding IR400-5)

	LSD (5%)	CV (X)%
Nitrogen level (N)**	493	18
Variety (V)**	324	10
2 N means at same or different V	902	—
2 V means at same N	794	—

yield with MCPA spray followed by two handweeding was significantly higher than that with one handweeding.

The ANOV for grain yield showed a highly significant difference among accumulated diazinon levels but no interaction between variety and diazinon. The only increase in grain yield resulted from 8 or more kg/ha a.i. diazinon, but there were no significant differences between the grain yields at the 10 to 14 kg/ha a.i. level (Table 18).

A multiple regression analysis was made on the grain yield (Y) of each variety with the following independent variables: nitrogen - 0, 70, 100, 130, and 160 kg/ha (X_1), and diazinon - 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 kg/ha (X_2). This analysis showed that both nitrogen and diazinon affected the grain yield of IR8.

$$\hat{y} = 1848 + 27.99X_1 - 0.055X_1^2 - 297.70X_2 + 81.05X_2^2 - 3.36X_2^3; R^2 = 0.75$$

For H-4, only nitrogen significantly affected the grain yield.

$$\hat{y} = 2220 + 29.65X_1 - 0.11X_1^2 - 282.46X_2 + 66.90X_2^2 - 2.94X_2^3; R^2 = 0.43$$

The relatively smaller R^2 value for H-4 indicates that factors other than nitrogen and diazinon were also responsible for the yield variation.

The following regression equations were worked out for each of the two varieties on the basis of grain yield data from the 1968 dry season.

For IR8:

$$\hat{y} = 1855 + 25.12X_1 - 0.037X_1^2 - 28.38X_2^2 - 1.03X_2^3,$$

and for H-4:

*Significant at 5% level.

**Significant at 1% level.

Table 14. Effect of nitrogen level on the grain yield of different varietal types. IRRI-CPU Cooperative Fertility Experiment, Central Philippine University, Iloilo, Philippines, 1968 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*					Mean †
	IR400-5-12-10-2	IR8	IR262-7-1-1-2	C4-63	IR5	
B + PI**						
0 + 0	5540	6194	5613	5088	††	5609
30 + 30	7542	7402	6589	6384	6199	6979 (6823)
60 + 30	9137	8350	8267	7469	7763	8306 (8197)
90 + 30	9363	8997	9867	8207	8181	9108 (8923)
120 + 30	10153	9890	9029	7475	8230	9137 (8955)
Mean (variety)	8347	8167	7873	6925	(6075)	
Duration (days)	118-124	131-133	118-124	124-131	131-133	

* Average, three replications.

**B + PI = Basal + panicle initiation.

† Data in parentheses refer to the average including IR5.

†† Flowered late and suffered from water shortage and also from rat damage.

Analysis of variance: (excluding IR5)

Nitrogen level (N)**
Variety (V)**
N x V^{n.s.}

LSD (5%) CV (X) %

746 10
600 10
—

$$\hat{y} = 2022 + 29.52X_1 - 0.10X_1^2 + 21.97X_2^2 - 1.01X_2^3,$$

where

$\hat{y}$ = Estimated grain yield (kg/ha),

X_1 = Nitrogen application (kg/ha), and

X_2 = Diazinon application (kg/ha a.i.)

Using these equations, the expected grain yield, gross income, net income, and cost-return ratio for each variety were computed for different combinations of nitrogen and diazinon levels (Table 19). The cost and return analysis indicates that an investment in nitrogen application was more profitable than one in diazinon in terms of gross and net return and benefit-cost ratio for both varieties, possibly because of the high cumulative diazinon levels in the experiment.

The net profit and benefit-cost ratio of 70 kg/ha N with no added diazinon was the same for both IR8 and H-4. As inputs were added, the net profit increased in both varieties except at the 160 kg/ha N level at which the net profit of H-4 was

lower than that at the 130 kg/ha N level, with the diazinon application being the same.

Although the gross income increased with increased investment, the benefit-cost ratio was higher at lower investment levels. The cost and

Table 15. Effect of nitrogen level on the productivity of four rice varieties. IRRI-CPU (Central Philippine University, Hoilo City) Cooperative Fertility Experiment, 1968 dry season.

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha/day) at 14% moisture*			
	IR400-5-12-10-2	IR8	IR262-7-1-1-2	C4-63
B + PI**				
0	50	52	50	43
30 + 30	72	63	63	58
60 + 30	87	71	79	67
90 + 30	89	76	94	74
120 + 30	97†	84	86	67

* Based on field duration.

**B + PI = Basal + panicle initiation.

† Highest productivity reported from any replicated experiment with an indica rice.

Table 16. Grain yield (kg/ha) at five levels of nitrogen, IRRI 1968 dry season.*

Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (kg/ha)**		
	IR8	H-4	Mean
0	2860	2805	2832
70	4300	3980 b	4140
100	5042	4324 bc	4683
130	5704 a	4949	5327 d
160	5788 a	4454 bc	5121 d
Mean (variety)	5028	4280	

*Mean grain yields for each variety at 0 and 70 N are the average of 8 insect and weed control treatments and the rest are of 16 insect and weed control treatments.

**Means in one column with the same letters are not significantly different from each other.

Analysis of variance:	LSD (0.05)	CV (X) %
Variety**	250	15
Nitrogen**		
N x V		

return analysis shows that IR8 gave a higher return than H-4 at all management levels except at 70 kg/ha, when both varieties gave the same return. A net profit of almost ₱1,800/ha was possible from IR8, whereas the maximum from H-4 was ₱980/ha.

Wet season. The dry-season experiment was repeated during the wet season using the same varieties and insect - and weed-control treatments. The nitrogen levels were 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha and were applied at planting, except for 10 kg/ha applied as topdressing at panicle initiation.

The ANOV for grain yield indicated a highly significant difference between the two varieties and highly significant linear interactions between variety and nitrogen, thus showing that the effect of nitrogen on the two varieties differed (Fig. 4). With IR8, a significant grain yield increase was obtained with one weeding, while there was no significant increase due to weeding with H-4 (Fig. 5).

The grain yields of both varieties increased significantly with increasing cumulative diazinon levels, but the grain yields differed significantly between varieties only at the 6 and 8 kg/ha a.i. levels (Fig. 6).

The effect of different diazinon levels on brown

Table 17. Grain yield (kg/ha) at four levels of weeding (average of 16 treatment combinations). IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Weeding level	Grain yield (kg/ha)		
	IR8	H-4	Mean
No weeding	4527	3575	4051
1 handweeding (HW)	4907	4347	4627
MCPA + 1 handweeding	5304	4469	4887
MCPA + 2 handweedings	5376	4727	5052
Mean (variety)	5028	4280	

Analysis of variance:	LSD (0.05)	CV(X)%
Variety**	250	15
Weeding**	351	
V X W ^{n.s.}		

Table 18. Grain yield (kg/ha) at eight cumulative diazinon levels (average of 8 treatment combinations). IRRI, 1968 dry season.

No. of diazinon applications	Grain yield (kg/ha)		
	IR8	H-4	Mean
0	4078	3553	3815
1	3689	3544	3618
2	4290	3437	3864
3	3940	3602	3772
4	5461	4566	5014
5	5986	5201	5593
6	6133	5045	5589
7	6651	5288	5970
Mean (variety)	5028	4280	

Analysis of variance:	LSD (0.05)	CV (X)%
Variety**	250	15
Diazinon**	500	—
V X D ^{n.s.}		

Table 19. Cost and return analysis for IR8 and H-4 at different management levels. IRRI, 1968 dry season.*

Variety	Management level		Computed yield (kg/ha)	Increased yield over control (kg/ha)	Gross income over control (₱)	Extra expense over control (₱)	Net income over control (₱)	Benefit-cost ratio
	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Diazinon (kg/ha a.i.)						
IR8	0	0	1855	—	—	—	—	—
	70	0	3432	1577	631	77	554	8.2
	100	0	3997	2142	857	110	747	7.8
	130	0	4495	2640	1056	143	913	7.4
	0	8	3144	1289	516	200	316	2.6
	0	12	4162	2307	923	300	623	3.1
	70	8	4721	2866	1146	277	869	4.1
	100	8	5285	3430	1372	310	1062	4.4
	100	12	6304	4449	1780	410	1370	4.3
	130	14	7232	5377	2151	493	1658	4.4
	160	14	7663	5808	2323	526	1797	4.4
H-4	0	0	2022	—	—	—	—	—
	70	0	3598	1576	630	77	553	8.2
	100	0	3974	1952	781	110	671	7.1
	130	0	4170	2148	859	143	716	6.0
	0	8	2911	889	356	200	156	1.8
	0	12	3440	1418	567	300	267	1.9
	70	8	4487	2465	986	277	709	3.6
	100	8	4863	2841	1136	310	826	3.7
	100	12	5392	3370	1348	410	938	3.3
	130	14	5704	3682	1473	493	980	3.0
	160	14	5720	3698	1479	526	953	2.8

* N @ ₱1.10/kg as urea; diazinon a.i. @ ₱25.00/kg as Basudin 10 G; palay (rough rice) @ ₱0.40/kg.

planthopper infestation was measured at the hard dough stage 20 days after heading. IR8 showed a higher percentage of infested tillers than H-4 at no or low levels of applied diazinon (Fig. 7), but at 8 kg/ha a.i. diazinon or more there was no significant difference in percentage of infested tillers between varieties.

Fertilizing flooded rice with anhydrous ammonia under two planting methods.

Previous experiments at the Institute have demonstrated that high yields can be obtained from broadcast plantings if adequate management levels, such as the use of herbicides to minimize early weed competition, proper water management, and adequate snail and algae control are maintained. During the 1968 dry and wet seasons, IR5 was added to the previous experiments to study the nitrogen fertilization of flooded broadcast and transplanted rice. A strip block design was used

with variety and nitrogen level as the main plots and method of planting as the subplot.

Dry season. Nitrogen (anhydrous ammonia) was applied by a portable anhydrous ammonia applicator 3 and 5 days before transplanting and broadcasting, respectively, at a 15-cm depth at rates varying from 0 to 120 kg/ha at 30-kg increments. Pregerminated seeds were broadcast on the mud surface at a 100-kg/ha seeding rate and 12-day-old "dapog" seedlings were transplanted at 25 x 20 cm spacing. The stands of IR8 under the broadcast and transplanted methods at 120 kg/ha N are shown in Fig. 8. Unlike in the 1967 dry season, there was a linear grain yield response to 120 kg/ha N in both broadcast and transplanted IR8 (Fig. 9). A similar result was also obtained with transplanted IR5. Broadcast IR5 gave a positive grain yield response up to 90 kg/ha N (Fig. 9).

The differences in grain yield due to nitrogen level and method of planting were highly signifi-

Fig. 4. Effect of nitrogen levels on the grain yield of IR8 and H-4 (average of 8 diazinon and 4 weeding levels). IRRI, 1968 wet season.

cant, but there was no significant yield difference between varieties. When broadcast, IR8 yielded higher than IR5 at all added nitrogen levels. At over 60 kg/ha N, IR5 lodged from 28 to 90 percent when broadcast but only from 40 to 45 percent when transplanted. IR8, however, did not lodge under either planting method at any nitrogen level. When broadcast, the total number of tillers and panicles of IR8 increased with added nitrogen, giving a higher total of tillers and panicles per square meter than when transplanted (Table 20) and consequently, higher grain yields. The larger number of panicles under the broadcast method was not accompanied by a proportionate increase in grain yield since there were fewer total and filled grains per panicle, and therefore, lower panicle weight (Table 20).

With an increase in nitrogen level, the 100-grain

weight increased slightly, but the differences between planting methods were not significant. Averaging all nitrogen levels, the mean 100-grain weights for IR8 were 2.9 and 2.8 g for the broadcast and transplanted methods, respectively.

The effects of nitrogen level and method of planting on the yield components of IR5 were similar to those of IR8 (Table 21). With added nitrogen, the higher panicle density with the broadcast method did not result in an increase in the IR5 grain yield.

Wet season. The nitrogen rates varied from 0 to 100 kg/ha at 25-kg increments. There was no significant varietal grain yield difference at any nitrogen level, but, unlike in the dry season, when the yields of both varieties were averaged, the transplanted treatments gave significantly higher values than the broadcast treatments (Fig. 10) at all nitrogen levels. This difference is due to the lodging (up to 84%) of broadcast IR8. Transplanted IR8 did not lodge.

Although IR5 lodged heavily under both planting methods, the lodging was more serious when

Fig. 5. Effect of levels of weed control on the grain yield of IR8 and H-4 (average of 5 nitrogen and 8 diazinon levels). IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Table 20. Effect of nitrogen (anhydrous ammonia) level and planting method on the yield components of IR8. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Planting method and N applied (kg/ha)	No./sq m at harvest		Panicle weight (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains (no./panicle) (%)		100-grain weight (g)
	Tiller	Panicle					
Broadcast							
0	624	609	1.2	54	6	17	2.8
30	676	618	1.4	51	11	18	2.9
60	644	630	1.4	64	9	12	2.8
90	644	619	1.6	66	10	13	2.8
120	619	672	1.5	64	10	14	3.0
Mean	656	630	1.4	60	9	15	2.9
Transplanted							
0	290	283	1.9	69	10	13	2.6
30	392	321	1.9	72	17	19	2.8
60	361	353	2.0	74	12	14	2.8
90	381	372	2.0	76	12	14	3.0
120	437	422	2.1	84	10	11	2.8
Mean	372	350	2.0	75	12	14	2.8

Table 21. Effect of nitrogen (anhydrous ammonia) level and planting method on the yield components of IR5. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Planting method and N applied (kg/ha)	No./sq m at harvest		Panicle weight (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains (no./panicle) (%)		100-grain weight (g)
	Tiller	Panicle					
Broadcast							
0	544	519	1.4	71	13	15	2.7
30	598	577	1.8	82	21	20	2.5
60	626	615	1.9	88	20	19	2.7
90	735	719	1.9	85	16	16	2.8
120	736	701	2.0	88	28	24	2.7
Mean	647	626	1.8	83	20	19	2.7
Transplanted							
0	347	314	2.1	89	29	18	2.6
30	376	366	1.9	87	27	24	2.6
60	368	352	2.1	90	19	17	2.7
90	460	454	2.1	95	22	19	2.7
120	437	422	2.2	103	22	18	2.7
Mean	398	382	2.1	93	22	19	2.7

Fig. 6. Effect of cumulative levels of diazinon on the grain yield of IR8 and H-4 (average of 5 nitrogen and 4 weeding levels). IRRI, 1968 wet season.

broadcast.

As in the dry season, the total number of tillers and panicles of IR8 was higher when broadcast than when transplanted (Table 22).

These results indicate that the differences in grain yield between broadcast or transplanted rice vary with variety and season. Under the reduced solar energy of the wet season, and with the increased plant density of the broadcast method, the crop becomes susceptible to lodging.

Time of nitrogen application for flooded rice

Results from the 1967 experiments demonstrated that split applications of nitrogen offer no advantage if the variety is lodging-resistant, and is grown on a heavy clay soil such as Maahas clay. The initial nitrogen, however, should be thoroughly incorporated into the soil during land preparation and the soil kept continuously flooded. IR5, which may lodge in a highly fertile soil, may res-

pond to split applications of nitrogen.

Field experiments were conducted in two locations during the 1968 dry and wet seasons using N^{15} -labelled ammonium sulfate. IR5 was the variety used, but IR8 was also included for comparison, although the nitrogen applied to IR8 was not labelled. The two locations used were the Institute farm (Maahas clay soil, 6.0 pH, 2% O.M., 0.14% total N, CEC 45 meq/100 g soil, montmorillonite predominant clay mineral) and the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (Maligaya clay soil, 6.9 pH, 1.5% O.M., 0.08% total N, CEC 36 meq/100 g soil, montmorillonite predominant clay mineral). The experiment at Maligaya was conducted in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry.

Totals of 120 and 80 kg/ha were applied in the dry and wet seasons, respectively, in single or multiple doses before final harrowing or during selected growth stages. In the basal application, nitrogen was incorporated into the soil. All top-dressings were made when the fields were flooded

Fig. 7. Effect of diazinon level on the percentage of hills infected by brown planthopper in IR8 and H-4. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Fig. 8. Broadcast IR8 yielded significantly higher than transplanted IR8 when both were fertilized with anhydrous ammonia applied 15 cm deep. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Fig. 9. Effect of level of nitrogen as anhydrous ammonia (applied at 15-cm depth) and methods of planting on the grain yield of two rice varieties. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Table 22. Effect of nitrogen (anhydrous ammonia) level and planting method on the yield components of IR8. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Planting method and N applied (kg/ha)	No./sq m at harvest		Panicle weight (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains		100-grain weight (g)
	Tiller	Panicle			(no./panicle)	(%)	
Broadcast							
0	393	380	1.6	71	12	14	2.7
25	403	397	1.7	72	11	13	2.6
50	383	373	1.7	86	10	10	2.6
75	400	393	1.8	78	14	15	2.8
100	400	380	1.7	80	14	15	2.9
Mean	396	385	1.7	77	12	13	2.7
Transplanted							
0	240	230	2.9	103	6	6	2.7
25	262	255	2.8	104	11	10	2.7
50	305	296	2.5	98	14	12	2.7
75	298	292	2.5	76	11	13	2.7
100	332	320	2.4	82	12	13	2.7
Mean	287	279	2.6	93	11	11	2.7

Table 23. Effect of time of nitrogen application on the grain yield and some yield components of IR 8 and IR 5 in Maahas clay, IRR1, 1968 dry season.

Treat- ment number	Time of application				IR 8				IR 5							
	*	**	†	††	$\bar{X}$	Grain yield† (kg/ha)	Panicle weight (no/sq m)	Panicle weight (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain-straw ratio	Grain yield† (kg/ha)	Panicle weight (no/sq m)	Panicle weight (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain- straw ratio	Mean grain yield (kg/ha)
1	0	0	0	0	0	3832	250	2.1	16	1.2	4090	250	2.4	18	1.0	3961
2	120Δ	0	0	0	0	6854 ab	425	3.3	6	0.9	7570 a	400	3.2	14	0.8	7212
3	0	60Δ	0	0	0	7638 a	400	2.9	14	1.2	6696 ab	350	3.2	22	0.8	7167
4	0	0	60Δ	60Δ	0	6642 abc	450	2.4	13	1.4	4802	325	3.0	21	0.7	5722
5	0	0	0	60Δ	60Δ	5498 d	475	2.3	9	1.2	5848 c	300	2.9	13	1.0	5673
6	90Δ	0	30Δ	0	0	7712 a	400	2.6	10	1.1	7366 ab	325	2.8	20	0.8	7539
7	90Δ	0	0	0	30Δ	6408 bcd	375	2.3	6	1.1	6352 bc	325	2.8	12	0.8	6380
8	0	40	40	40	0	6302 bcd	350	2.6	14	1.3	7022 ab	325	3.3	29	0.8	7162
9	0	0	40	40	40	6248 bcd	375	2.4	10	1.4	6510 abc	325	3.3	15	1.0	379
10	0	40	40	0	40	7124 ab	350	3.3	7	1.2	7338 ab	300	3.2	15	1.0	7231
11	60	0	30	30	0	7560 a	400	2.6	8	1.1	7374 ab	325	3.1	21	1.0	7467
12	60	0	0	30	30	5721 cd	375	2.6	4	1.1	6538 abc	350	2.5	13	1.0	6129
						Mean (variety)										6544

* Last harrowing.
 ** Maximum tillering stage.
 † Panicle initiation stage.
 †† Booting stage.
 $\bar{X}$ Heading stage.

Δ N¹⁵-labelled (NH₄)₂SO₄ applied to IR5 only.

† Means marked with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 24. Effect of time of nitrogen application on the grain yield and some yield components of IR8 and IR5 in Maligaya soil, Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Nueva Ecija, 1968 dry season.

Treat- ment * number	Time of application				IR8				IR5						
	**	†	††	‡	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance† (5%)	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle Unfilled grain (%)	Grain-staw ratio	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance† (5%)	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle Unfilled grains (%)	Grain- staw ratio	Mean grain yield (kg/ha)
1	0	0	0	0	4869	e	375	13	1.1	5088		350	16	0.9	4978
2	120Δ	0	0	0	8363	bc	525	11	0.8	7465	de	475	11	0.7	7914
3	0	60Δ	0	0	9024	ab	450	16	1.0	8279	ab	450	23	0.8	8652
4	0	0	60Δ	0	7712	cd	425	14	1.3	7070	de	350	21	1.2	7391
5	0	0	0	60Δ	5397	e	400	10	1.1	6790	e	400	8	1.1	6094
6	90Δ	0	30Δ	0	9268	a	550	13	1.0	7607	bcd	525	16	0.8	8438
7	90Δ	0	0	30Δ	8444	b	500	8	0.9	7429	de	500	7	0.7	7936
8	0	40	40	0	8374	bc	425	18	1.1	7585	cd	400	23	1.0	7980
9	0	0	40	40	7389	d	400	17	1.4	7082	de	350	24	1.3	7236
10	0	40	0	40	9021	ab	425	10	1.2	8501	a	425	12	1.0	8761
11	60	0	30	0	8563	ab	475	11	1.1	8196	abc	450	15	0.9	8380
12	60	0	0	30	7339	d	500	10	0.9	7558	cd	500	10	0.8	7448
Mean (variety)					7814		450	13	1.1	7388		425	16	0.9	

* Last harrowing.

** Maximum tillering stage.

† Panicle initiation stage.

†† Booting stage.

‡ Heading stage.

† Means marked with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Δ N¹⁵-labelled (NH₄)₂SO₄ applied to IR5 only.

Fig. 10. Effect of levels of nitrogen as anhydrous ammonia (applied at 15-cm depth) and methods of planting on the grain yield of two rice varieties. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

to a depth of 5 cm. As in the earlier studies, a split plot design was used with variety as the main plot and time of nitrogen application as the subplot, with three replications of all treatments.

Dry season. Table 23 shows the grain yields and some yield components from the experiment at the Institute. The highest yield (7.7 mt) of IR8 resulted from treatment 6 - a split application, two-thirds at planting and one-third at panicle initiation. The lowest yield among the treated plots was recorded with treatment 5 - a split application at the booting and heading stages. All the nitrogen plots gave significant yield increases over the no-nitrogen control plots.

For IR5, the highest yield was 7,570 kg/ha obtained from treatment 2 - nitrogen applied entirely before the last harrowing. This yield, however, was only slightly higher than that from treatment 6 which was the highest also for IR8. Other than in the control, the lowest yield of IR5 was obtained from a split application of nitrogen at panicle initiation and booting (treatment 4). The yield difference between the control and treatment 4 was not significant because at the early

Table 25. Effect of time of nitrogen application on the utilization of added fertilizer (N^{15}) by the grain and straw of IR5. IRRI and Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Nueva Ecija, 1968 dry season.

Treatment number	Time of N application					Utilization of added nitrogen (%)					
	*	**	†	††	‡	IRRI			Maligaya		
	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	(kg/ha)	Grain	Straw	Total	Grain	Straw	Total
2	120 $\overline{\mp}$	0	0	0	0	23	10	33	15	9	24
3	0	60 $\overline{\mp}$	60 $\overline{\mp}$	0	0	31	18	49	27	14	41
4	0	0	60 $\overline{\mp}$	60 $\overline{\mp}$	0	26	25	51	35	13	48
5	0	0	0	60 $\overline{\mp}$	60 $\overline{\mp}$	35	22	57	44	20	64
6	90 $\overline{\mp}$	0	30 $\overline{\mp}$	0	0	27	12	39	20	11	31
7	90 $\overline{\mp}$	0	0	0	30 $\overline{\mp}$	23	17	40	27	14	41
	Mean					28	17	45	28	14	42

* Last harrowing.

** Maximum tillering stage.

† Panicle initiation stage.

†† Booting stage.

‡ Heading stage.

$\overline{\mp}$ N^{15} -labelled ammonium sulfate applied.

growth stages, Maahas clay could not supply adequate nitrogen to the control for greater tiller production and the number of potential panicles was therefore reduced.

The yields of IR8 and IR5 under the same treatments were not statistically different except in treatment 4 in which IR8 gave over 1,800 kg/ha more grain than IR5. Accounting for this difference were the significantly greater number of panicles, higher grain-straw ratio, and lower percentage of unfilled grains of IR8. IR5 had a slightly greater panicle weight, but it was not enough to compensate for its low number of panicles and higher percentage of unfilled grains.

Higher mean yields were obtained at the Maligaya Center than at the Institute. The control plot at Maligaya gave about 1,000 kg/ha more grain than that at the Institute farm. For the first time at Maligaya a grain yield of over 9,000 kg/ha was obtained when IR8 yielded 9,268 kg/ha, about 2,000 kg/ha more than the highest yield from the Institute farm (7,712 kg/ha) (Table 24). The higher yields from Maligaya may be attributed to higher solar radiation and longer sunshine hours in that location, especially during the later growth stages. During the last 3 months of the crop growth (April, May, and June), the solar radiation recorded at Maligaya (14,800, 16,500 and 14,100 g-cal cm⁻²) was consistently higher than that at the Institute farm.

Statistical analysis shows that treatments 6, 3, 10 and 11 were better as a group than treatments 4, 9, and 12. In both varieties topdressings at booting and heading (treatment 5) gave the lowest yields among the nitrogen treatments.

The results from Maligaya indicate a fast rate of nitrogen exhaustion in the soil. Topdressed nitrogen can apparently sustain the plants for only a short period, possibly because of its rapid uptake by the plants in metabolic processes made more efficient by the high solar energy of the dry season. Preliminary results also indicate that ammonium fixation is higher in the Maligaya soil than in the Maahas clay soil.

The yield components tend to show that treatments without a basal application of nitrogen had significantly fewer panicles than those with basal application. The treatments with delayed nitrogen topdressing had the least number of panicles.

Data on dry matter production and nitrogen

uptake (not shown here) indicate a drastic response to each topdressing with a tendency to balance uptake with nutrient supply. There was an increase in the dry matter and nitrogen contents of the plant after each nitrogen topdressing. At harvest, the plants which had the most recent topdressings (treatments 4, 5, 9, 10) had the highest nitrogen content, and therefore, protein content, in both grain and straw while those with basal applications of nitrogen (treatment 2, 6, 7, 11) had greater amounts of dry matter at harvest. More nitrogen, however, was removed from the soil at harvest in the late-application treatments.

In both locations, treatment 5 - topdressing at booting and heading - showed the highest utilization of added nitrogen (Table 25). At the Institute farm, early applications (treatments 2, 6) showed a higher proportion of fertilizer nitrogen in the grain than did late applications. At Maligaya, more of the fertilizer nitrogen was found in the grain in treatments with nitrogen topdressings at panicle initiation and beyond.

The considerable difference in total utilization of nitrogen in treatment 2 at the Institute and at Maligaya shows the low level of nitrogen in the Maligaya crop, especially at the later growth stages. Nitrogen utilized earlier probably was returned to the soil in the dead leaves.

Wet season. The wet season experiment had the same design and similar cultural practices as the dry season test.

Table 26 shows the yields of IR8 and IR5 at the Institute farm. A split application of nitrogen, two-thirds at planting and one-third at panicle initiation (treatment 6) gave the highest mean grain yield of the two varieties. However, this treatment was significantly better than only two other treatments - treatment 1, the no-nitrogen control and treatment 5, split application at booting and heading. No significant difference was found among the rest of the treatments.

At the Maligaya Center (Table 27), a split application of nitrogen did not produce a marked increase in IR8 yield over a single application. Yields tended to increase in treatments with basal applications while topdressing at the later growth stages (treatment 5 - booting and heading) gave a 4,463 kg/ha grain yield, the lowest obtained excluding the control. Apparently the Maligaya soil

Table 26. Effect of time of nitrogen application on the grain yield of IR8 and IR5 grown under flooded conditions. IRR1, 1968 wet season.

Treatment number	Time of N application					Grain yield (kg/ha)		Mean (kg/ha)	Statistical significance [‡] (5%)
	*	**	†	††	⧘	IR8	IR5		
	(kg/ha)								
1	0	0	0	0	0	4157	4347	4252	ab
2	80 [△]	0	0	0	0	5599	5102	5350	ab
3	0	40 [△]	40 [△]	0	0	5711	5375	5543	ab
4	0	0	40 [△]	40 [△]	0	5543	5147	5345	ab
5	0	0	0	40 [△]	40 [△]	5381	5213	5296	b
6	60 [△]	0	20 [△]	0	0	5839	5600	5719	a
7	60 [△]	0	0	0	20 [△]	5623	5380	5502	ab
8	0	27	27	27	0	5431	5227	5330	ab
9	0	0	27	27	27	5449	5730	5590	ab
10	0	27	27	0	27	5663	5639	5651	ab
11	40	0	20	20	0	5791	5265	5528	ab
12	40	0	0	20	20	5670	5335	5503	ab

* Last harrowing.

** Maximum tillering stage.

† Panicle initiation stage.

†† Booting stage.

⧘ Heading stage.

[‡] Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level using the Duncan's multiple range test.

[△] N¹⁵-labelled (NH₄)₂SO₄ applied to IR5 only.

Table 27. Effect of time of nitrogen application on the grain yield of IR8 and IR5 grown under flooded conditions. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Nueva Ecija, 1968 wet season.

Treatment number	Time of N application					IR8		IR5		Mean (kg/ha)
	*	**	†	††	⧘	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance (5%)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance [‡] (5%)	
	(kg/ha)									
1	0	0	0	0	0	3758	e	3670	d	3714
2	80 [△]	0	0	0	0	5537	ab [*]	4425	bc	4981
3	0	40 [△]	40 [△]	0	0	5223	bc	4376	bc	4799
4	0	0	40 [△]	40 [△]	0	5487	ab	4779	abc	5133
5	0	0	0	40 [△]	40 [△]	4463	d	4478	abc	4470
6	60 [△]	0	20 [△]	0	0	5784	a	4921	ab	5353
7	60 [△]	0	0	0	20 [△]	5601	ab	4615	abc	5108
8	0	27	27	27	0	5125	bc	4316	c	4721
9	0	0	27	27	27	5328	abc	4998	a	5163
10	0	27	27	0	27	4926	cd	4435	bc	4680
11	40	0	20	20	0	5847	a	4817	abc	5832
12	40	0	0	20	20	5493	ab	4981	a	5237
	Mean (variety)					5214		4568		

* Last harrowing.

** Maximum tillering stage.

† Panicle initiation stage.

†† Booting stage.

⧘ Heading stage.

[‡] Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level using the Duncan's multiple range test.

[△] N¹⁵-labelled (NH₄)₂SO₄ applied to IR5 only.

has a relatively inadequate supply of nitrogen available to sustain the crop long after planting. This deficiency limited such factors for high grain yield as tiller number, panicle number, and number of grains. Topdressing made at the later stages helped only a little, if at all, to increase yield.

With IR5, significantly higher yields were obtained when nitrogen was applied in multiple doses than when all of it was applied at planting. Presumably, split applications caused less mutual shading, minimal leaching losses, and delayed lodging. This yield response was not observed in the more fertile, less sandy Maahas soil at the Institute farm.

These results indicate that with lodging-susceptible varieties, nitrogen applications should be delayed to avoid excessive vegetative growth and delay lodging as long as possible, particularly if the soil is fertile. With a lodging-resistant variety, the application of nitrogen at planting will increase the number of panicles and enhance the grain yield. At the Institute farm a split application of nitrogen did not increase the yields of IR8 or IR5 significantly over the application of nitrogen entirely at planting. Splitting the application of nitrogen resulted in a higher grain yield for IR5 only at Maligaya. Nitrogen topdressings at the booting and heading stages increased the yields of IR8 and IR5 to a limited extent only.

Long-term fertility experiment

The objective of the 1968 experiment and the treatments used were the same as in previous years. The results reported here are from the 8th and 9th crop in this series.

Dry season. Without any fertilizer the average grain yield of the three indica varieties (IR8, early short Peta, and early tall Peta) was 4,245 kg/ha. The average yield of IR8 was about 1,000 kg/ha more than that of early tall Peta (IR 262-43-8-1). None of the three indicas showed any response to phosphorus and/or potassium (Table 28).

Wet season. During the wet season, the response to nitrogen was significant, but not to phosphorus, and/or potassium (Table 20).

Sources and rates of fertilizer phosphorus for flooded rice

The third season of this study continued to assess

the efficiency for flooded rice of urea-ammonium phosphate materials containing various rates of N and P to evaluate the relative efficiency of different sources of fertilizer phosphorus as an alternative to using superphosphate for flooded rice.

The study was conducted in the 1968 dry season on Buenavista clay soil (described in the 1966 and 1967 Annual Reports). A randomized complete block arrangement was used, and all of the phosphorus, potassium, and 120 kg/ha of the fertilizer nitrogen was applied before the last harrowing. An additional 30 kg/ha N was topdressed at the panicle initiation stage. The uniform nitrogen level for all treatments supplied by urea-ammonium phosphate was supplemented with superphosphate (40% P_2O_5) in order to obtain 90 and 120 kg/ha $P\oplus O_5$.

Nitrogen application increased the rough rice yields by about 2,300 kg/ha. The application of phosphorus with nitrogen further increased the grain yield (Fig. 11).

All the urea-ammonium phosphate fertilizers and superphosphate proved equally effective in increasing grain yield, indicating that any of the phosphates in N:P combinations used in this study are effective for flooded rice and can be used as alternatives to superphosphate under these soil and climatic conditions (Fig. 11). The cost relationships are satisfactory, too.

Time of harvesting flooded rice

The yield ceiling of rice has been raised by the introduction of high-yielding varieties in tropical Asia and as the supply of rice on the market increases, milling quality becomes more important. Although it is generally thought that flooded rice can be harvested about a month after heading, there is too little evidence that this is the optimum practice as far as grain yield and milling quality are concerned. A study was therefore conducted to determine the effect of harvesting time on grain quality and yield, and to study the influence of nitrogen on grain quality. Four varieties and three nitrogen levels were used. The varieties were IR8, IR5, C4-63 (an improved variety developed by the U.P. College of Agriculture), and Sigadis (a tall and lodging-susceptible variety from Indonesia). The levels of nitrogen were 0, 60, and 120 kg/ha during the dry season, and 0, 30, and 60 kg/ha during the wet season. The varieties were harvested 15 times

Table 28. Effect of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of IR8, early short Peta (IR 262-43-8-11) and early tall Peta (IR 262-43-8-1), Long-term fertility experiment IRR1, 1968 dry season (8th crop).

Fertilizer treatment (kg/ha)			Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	Early short Peta (IR 262-43-8-11)	Early tall Peta (IR262-43-8-1)	Mean
B + PI**						
0	0	0	4434	3841	4462	4245
100 + 40	0	0	9691	8222	5316	7743
0	30	0	4598	4208	4496	4434
0	0	30	4590	3647	4423	4220
100 + 40	30	0	9782	8322	5524	7876
100 + 40	0	30	9871	8192	5454	7839
100 + 40	30	30	9621	8220	5367	7736
100 + 40†	30	30	9497	8772	6844	8205
Mean (variety)			7761	6616	5236	
Duration (days):			128	109	109	

* Average, four replications.

** Basal + panicle initiation.

† Compost + inorganic.

Analysis of variance:	s.e.	LSD (5%)	CV(X)%
Treatment combinations**	244	689	} 7
Variety (V)**	86	243	
Fertilizer treatment (T)**	140	390	
V x F			

Table 29. Effect of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of IR8, early short Peta (IR 262-43-8-11), and early tall Peta (IR 262-43-8-1). Long-term fertility experiment, IRR1, 1968 wet season (9th crop).

Fertilizer treatment			Grain yield (kg/ha) at 14% moisture*			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	Early short Peta IR262-43-8-11	Early tall Peta IR262-43-8-1	Mean (treatment)
0	0	0	3422	3016	3334	3258
60	0	0	4722	4776	4722	4740
0	30	0	3690	3502	3265	3486
0	0	30	3372	3218	3363	3318
60	30	0	4736	4852	4737	4775
60	0	30	4554	4760	4734	4683
60	30	30	4876	4835	4709	4807
60	30	30**	4876	4556	5026	4819
Mean (variety)			4281	4190	4236	
Duration (days)			122	111	111	

* Average, four replications.

** Compost + inorganic.

Analysis of variance:	s.e.	LSD (5%)	CV(X)%
Treatment combination**	168	475	8
Variety (V)	59	—	
Fertilizer treatment (F)**	97	274	
V X F*			

Fig. 11. Effect of sources and rates of fertilizer phosphorus on the grain yield of flooded IR8. Soil: Buenavista clay, Bulacan, Philippines, 1968 dry season.

at 2-day intervals starting from 16 days after heading. The heading date was considered to be the day when about 50 percent of the heads had emerged.

Dry season. The grain yields of IR8, IR5, and C4-63 were similar, while that of Sigadis was significantly lower due to its susceptibility to lodging at high nitrogen rates. The grain yields rapidly increased with time until they reached a plateau 32 to 34 days after heading (Fig. 12). Generally, the grain yields of the four varieties

were low when harvested early due to low 100-grain weights and high percentages of unfilled grains (Fig. 13). The yields, particularly that of Sigadis, started to decrease at 38 days after heading. The yield reductions at late harvest dates were due primarily to grain shattering and, in the case of Sigadis, to lodging.

Although maximum yields were obtained at 32 or 34 days after heading, there was no significant difference among the yields from 24 to 44 days after heading. Averaging all varieties however, only

Fig. 12. Effect of time of harvest on the grain yield of IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Fig. 13. Effect of time of harvest on percentage of unfilled grains and weight of 100 grains in IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

the grain yields obtained between 28 and 38 days after heading did not differ among themselves. The four varieties could thus be harvested as early as 28 days or as late as 38 days after heading without significant yield losses.

Generally, the moisture content of the grain decreased as the grain yield increased (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Effect of time of harvest on the moisture content of the grain and the grain yield of IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

The decrease was very rapid at early maturity, slowed down at optimum maturity (32 to 34 days after heading), and was somewhat irregular at late maturity due to the frequent rains which occurred at this stage.

The total milled rice appeared to be positively correlated with the 100-grain weight and bushel weight. The low milling recovery at early harvest, as shown in Fig. 15, was due to a low 100-grain weight (Fig. 13) and a high percentage of green kernels (Fig. 16). As the 100-grain weight increased and the percentage of green kernels decreased, the percentage of total milled rice increased, but levelled off at about 26 days after heading. The highest total milled rice was obtained with C4-63, followed by Sigadis, IR8, and IR5, in that order (Fig. 15). The low milling recovery of IR5 (66%) was very closely related to its low bushel weight while the milling recovery of C4-63 at optimum maturity was about 70 percent.

The average head rice yields of IR5 and Sigadis were 34 and 35 percent, respectively, which were significantly lower than that of IR8 (43%) which in turn was significantly lower than that of C4-63 (55%). At optimum maturity, however, the head

Fig. 15. Effect of time of harvest on percentages of total milled rice and head rice of IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IIRI, 1968 dry season.

Fig. 16. Effect of time of harvest on percentages of green kernels and chalky kernels in IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IIRI, 1968 dry season.

rice yields of the four varieties were 40, 44, 52, and 62 percent, respectively (Fig. 15). In absolute value, the grain yields of 5,806, 5,622, 5,629, and 4,906 kg/ha of IR8, IR5, C4-63 and Sigadis, respectively, gave corresponding head rice yields of 2,497, 1,911, 3,096 and 1,717 kg/ha, thus demonstrating the superior milling quality of C4-63 over the other varieties. The low head rice yields of IR8, IR5, and Sigadis were related to their inherently chalky grains, quite unlike the clear, hard and translucent grains of C4-63.

The four varieties showed an almost identical trend with respect to time of harvest. When harvested early, the head rice yields were low due to the presence of a large quantity of light-green, chalky and immature grains which were easily pulverized during hulling and polishing. The yields increased as the quantity of such grains decreased, but began to fall at 30 to 32 days after heading due to prolonged exposure to alternate wetness by dew and dryness by sunshine which caused the grains to crack crosswise. The decrease of head rice yields at late maturity was very dramatic in Sigadis and IR5, gradual in IR8, and almost insignificant in C4-63. The pronounced decrease of head rice yield in Sigadis was associated with a sudden increase in the percentage of chalky kernels during late maturity (Fig. 16). Low light penetration resulting from lodging and the sudden drying of the wet grains after harvest may have contributed to breakage.

Although maximum head rice yields occurred between 28 and 30 days after heading, regardless of variety, there was no significant difference among the head rice yields between 24 and 34 days after heading.

The effect of nitrogen on head rice yields was highly significant although there was an interaction between the effects of variety and nitrogen (Fig. 17). In chalky varieties such as IR8, IR5, and Sigadis, the addition of nitrogen significantly increased head rice yields by reducing the percentage of chalky kernels by 1 to 3 percent. In a non-chalky variety such as C4-63, nitrogen had no significant effect on either the head rice yield or the percentage of chalky kernels.

These results indicate that, regardless of variety and nitrogen level, rice can be harvested between 28 and 34 days after heading for maximum grain and head rice yields. Lodging varieties, however,

Fig. 17. Effect of nitrogen levels on milling qualities of IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IRR1, 1968 dry season.

Fig. 18. Effect of time of harvest on the grain yield of IR8, IR5, C4-63, and Sigadis. IRR1, 1968 wet season.

should be harvested earlier.

Nitrogen applications of up to 120 kg/ha improve the milling quality of chalky varieties, but

have no effect on the milling quality of non-chalky varieties.

Wet season. Probably because of the higher amount of solar radiation it received during the later growth stages, IR5 gave a higher yield than IR8. The actual yields were IR8, 4,190; IR5, 4,957; C4-63, 3,462; and Sigadis, 3,298 kg/ha.

With respect to time of harvest, the grain yields of the four varieties showed a trend almost identical to that in the dry season (Fig. 18). The maximum grain yields were obtained at 34 and 36 days after heading for both C4-63 and Sigadis. The grain yield decrease, due to grain shattering after the maximum yield was attained, was more rapid with C4-63 and Sigadis, which also suffered yield losses as a result of lodging.

Weed Competition and Weed Control in Transplanted Rice

Effect of varietal type and planting method on rice and weed competition

An experiment conducted at the Institute during the 1967 dry season showed that grassy weeds reduced the grain yield of rice by 90 percent, while broadleaved weeds did not reduce the yield.

In 1968, field experiments were conducted to study the effects of plant type, method of planting, and time of emergence of different kinds of weeds on the grain yield of rice. IR8 and H-4 were used, representing two contrasting plant types, the first being short and lodging-resistant and the second, tall and lodging-susceptible. The two planting methods used were transplanting at a spacing of 25 x 25 cm and broadcasting at a rate of 100 kg/ha seeds. Early and late weed emergence were compared by kinds of weeds, and a standard weed-free condition was included for comparison. Weed communities were manipulated by broadcasting grassy weed seeds and by eliminating the weeds either by hand or by using chemicals at appropriate times. Since the natural communities of broadleaved weeds and sedges were adequate, it was not necessary to sow them. A splitplot design was used with varieties as the main plots, methods of planting as the subplots, and weed communities by kinds of weeds and their periods of competition with the rice as the subplots. The treatments were replicated four times.

Dry season. Nitrogen was applied at 120 kg/ha

Table 30. Effects of weed competition and weed densities on the grain yield of IR8 rice variety under two methods of planting. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Weed community	Weed weight* (g/sq m)				Grain yield (kg/ha)			
	Broad-cast	Trans-planted	Mean	Statistical significance at 5% level**	Broad-cast	Trans-planted	Mean	Statistical significance at 5% level**
1. Early-grass (G)	356	574	465	a	4663	3240	3952	c
2. Early-sedges (S) + broadleaf (BL)	50	94	72	c	6119	7632	6876	ab
3. Early - G+S+BL	662	479	571	a	2742	3612	3177	c
4. Late - G	202	245	224	b	5305	6817	6061	b
5. Late - S+BL	59	62	61	c	6700	7245	6972	ab
6. Late - G+S+BL	157	211	184	b	5767	6517	6142	ab
7. Weed-free	14	42	28	c	7059	7321	7190	a

* Determined at the heading stage of grassy weeds.

** Any two treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level.

Table 31. Effects of weed competition and weed densities on the grain yield of IR8 under two methods of planting. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Weed community	Weed weight* (g/sq m)				Grain yield (kg/ha)			
	Broad-cast	Trans-planted	Method (mean)	Statistical significance at 5% level**	Broad-cast	Trans-planted	Method (mean)	Statistical significance at 5% level**
1. Early grass(G)	325	285	305	a	700	1738	1219	a
2. Early-sedge(S) + broadleaf (BL)	250	110	180	b	3848	4756	4302	b
3. Early - G+S+BL	540	330	435	c	0	1408	704	a
4. Late - G	15	0	8	d	4633	4849	4741	b
5. Late - S+BL	70	25	48	d	4484	5089	4786	b
6. Late - G+S+BL	70	40	55	d	4294	4530	4412	b
7. Weed-free	0	0	0	d	5032	4839	4936	b

* Determined at the heading stage of grassy weeds.

** Any two treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

for both IR8 and H-4. Method-of-planting grain yield means, as affected by early sedge and broad-leaved weed competition or by late-emerging mixed-weed communities, were not significantly different from those obtained under weed-free conditions. Significantly lower mean yields, however, resulted from early competition by mixtures of grasses, of sedges and broadleaved weeds or of early or late competition by grasses alone (Table 30). Competition was most serious when a mixed-weed community, including grasses, was present

during the early growth stages of the crop. Grain yield data corresponded inversely with weed-community densities as measured by weed weights. The decreased weights of late-emerging grasses in IR8, or mixed communities including them, might indicate successful competition of the well-established IR8 plants, since some suppression of weed competition can be expected from such a heavy-tillering variety about a month after transplanting. The similarities of early- and late-emerging sedge and broadleaved-weed weights

showed that successively germinating natural populations of these weeds were quite uniform in size in this season and that the effects of crop competition on them were negligible.

H-4 lodged severely because of heavy fertilization. Consequently, the yield results were highly variable and are not reported here.

Wet season. Nitrogen was applied to IR8 at 60 kg/ha at planting time but, to avoid lodging, none was applied to H-4.

Method-of-planting grain yield means, as affected by weed competition at two times of weed emergence, did not differ significantly among themselves. The grain yield data for IR8 as affected by kinds of weeds and their times of emergence showed a trend similar (Table 31) to that of the dry season. Compared with the weed-free treatment, early grass competition, with or without sedges and broadleaved weeds, reduced grain yield. Late emergence of weeds, including grasses, did not reduce the grain yield. The grain yields and weed weights were similar for broadcast and transplanted IR8.

For H-4, the grain yield difference between the two planting methods as affected by weed competition at two times of weed emergence was highly significant; hence, statistical analyses are presented separately for each method of planting. (Table 32).

Weed weights and grain yields were lower in transplanted than in broadcast H-4 rice and lodg-

ing was severe under both planting methods, without added nitrogen. The lower weed densities in transplanted H-4 may have indirectly made additional nitrogen available to the rice crop which caused early lodging and lower grain yields.

Weed densities (weights) were generally less for H-4 than for IR8, especially when transplanted. This difference may indicate that H-4, the taller variety, was the more successful competitor with weeds.

Considering the broadcast method, an analysis of grain yield shows that weeding produced a greater grain yield in IR8 than in H-4, thus indicating that weed control gives a higher yield return with a variety of an improved plant type than with one of a poor plant type.

Screening of herbicides

The screening of herbicides for transplanted rice was continued during the 1968 wet season under the timing and water management conditions described in previous annual reports. Table 33 summarizes the ranked results of the effect of chemicals on yield or weed control. The results of the 20 best treatments based on low to no toxicity to the rice crop and low weed weights are listed along with those of an untreated control. Several new chemicals are reported here for the first time, while others appear in new combinations. Such herbicides as OCS 21799 at 1 and 2 kg/ha a.i. and

Table 32. Effects of weed competition and weed densities on the grain yield of H-4 under two methods of planting. IIRI, 1968 wet season.

Weed community	Weed weight* (g/sq m)				Grain yield (kg/ha)				
	Broad-cast	Statistical significance at 5% level**	Trans-planted	Statistical significance (mean) at 5% level**	Broad-cast	Statistical significance at 5% level**	Trans-planted	Statistical significance (mean) at 5% level**	
1. Early grass (G)	290	a	125	a	208	1736 a	2102	a	1914
2. Early sedge (S) + broadleaf (BL)	120	b	55	bc	88	4188 d	2732	ab	3460
3. Early G+S+BL	330	a	110	ab	220	652 b	1980	a	1316
4. Late - G	35	d	10	c	22	4484 d	4166	c	4325
5. Late - S+BL	50	cd	25	c	38	4831 d	3266	bc	4048
6. Late - G+S+BL	105	bc	35	c	70	3118 c	3206	bc	3162
7. Weed-free	0	d	0	c	0	4082 d	2825	ab	3454

* Determined at the heading stage of grassy weeds.

** Any two treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 33. Rank of herbicides in a screening test evaluating grain yield and weed control under four conditions of testing. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Early application (4 DAT)				Late application (16 DAT)			
		Weed weight		Grain yield		Weed weight		Grain yield	
		Drained (g/sq m)	Flooded (g/sq m)	Drained (kg/ha)	Flooded (kg/ha)	Drained (g/sq m)	Flooded (g/sq m)	Drained (kg/ha)	Flooded (kg/ha)
OCS 21799 (WP)	2.0	75	40	5776	5438	135	35	5053	5047
CP 53619 (L)	4.0	15	75	5164	5414	230	20	4897	5621
Trifluralin/MCPA BE (L)	0.7/0.4	120	15	5122	5278				
Propanil (L) fb MCPA (L)	3.0+0.8					50	25	5224	5162
2,4-D IPE (G)	0.8	140	40	5003	5536				
MSMA (G) + MCPA (G)	5.0+0.8	150	60	5448	5222	135	60	5229	5173
2,4-D IPE (G)	1.6	35	30	5327	4477				
MSMA (G) + 2,4-D (G)	5.0+0.8	80	25	5316	4888	240	55	4562	5538
Nitrofen (G)+2,4-D IPE (G)	2.0+0.8	130	20	5729	5376	260	70	3974	5228
MSMA (G) + MCA	2.5+0.8	230	95	5061	4874	145	55	4810	4297
Nitralin/MCPA (G)	1.5/0.68	40	45	5061	4977				
Dichlobenil/CNP (G)	0.75/3.5	305	25	5032	5663	230	75	4332	4922
OCS 21693/21799 (G)	4.0/2.0	100	95	4406	5247	305	40	4515	5091
OCS 21693/21799 (G)	4.0/1.0	160	30	4683	5823	135	75	3856	4626
Propanil/CHCH (L)	1.5					95	160	4948	4832
Propanil (G)	3.0	100	85	4887	5147	245	130	4049	5084
DCPA (WP) + MCPA (L)	1.0+0.8	100	65	5159	5683	325	55	2953	5138
OCS 21799 (WP)	1.0	20	30	5567	4984	455	80	3034	5130
DCPA (WP)+MCPA (L)	1.0 + 0.8	220	55	5114	4594	260	85	4315	5143
CP 53619 (L)	2.0	60	30	5009	5539	980	55	3203	4327
Untreated control		215	135	3802	5698	355	160	2775	4480

CP 53619 at 2 and 4 kg/ha a.i. appeared at least twice among the 20 best treatments. Trifluralin/MCPA-butyl ester, granular 2,4-D isopropyl ester, granular MSMA + 2,4-D or MSMA + MCPA, DCPA + MCPA granular propanil and liquid propanil/CHCH also gave encouraging results.

Effect of granular α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene and other herbicides on the IR8 grain yield

Weeds in rice fields consist mainly of grasses, although broadleaved weeds and sedges are also common. A field experiment conducted at the Institute during the 1968 dry season tested the effects on these weeds of applications of α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene (TCE-styrene) and other herbicides in granular or liquid form at appropriate rates and times to a 15-sq m plot of transplanted IR8 in which 2.5 to 5 cm of standing water was maintained until crop maturity. The design used was a randomized complete block with four replications. *Echinochloa crusgalli* (L.) Beauv. seeds were sown at 2 kg/ha shortly after transplanting to

insure uniform weed densities among the plots at each site. Standard chemical and handweeding methods were included for comparison.

Figure 19 shows the remarkable contrast typical of the first experiment between the untreated plots and those treated with TCE-styrene. The density of *E. crusgalli* in the control plots of this experiment was higher than usually found in farmers' fields, but applications of TCE-styrene at rates of 1.0 and 2.2 kg/ha a.i. gave excellent grass

* The following abbreviations are used in the text and tables of this and the succeeding sections on weed control: AE - allyl ester; ae - acid equivalent; a.i. - active ingredient; BEE - butoxyethanol ester; DAS - days after seeding; DAT - days after transplanting; DBS - days before seeding; EC - emulsifiable concentrate; EE - ethyl ester; EHE - 2-ethyl-hexyl ester (iso-octyl ester); fb - followed by; G - granular; g/l - grams per liter; IOE - iso-octyl ester (2-ethyl ester); IPE - isopropyl ester; K - potassium (salt); LSG - leaf stage of grassy weeds; OPDA - N-oleyl-1,3-propylenediamine (salt); WP - wettable powder; WSL - water-soluble liquid; WSP - water-soluble powder. "+" between two herbicide names indicates that they were applied separately at about the same time (e.g. MSMA (G) + MCPA (G)). "/" between two herbicides indicates that they were formulated on the same carrier or mixed together and applied as a single treatment (e.g. Nitralin/MCPA (G)).

Fig. 19. A dramatic difference in grain yield was observed between a weedy control and a plot treated with α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene. With just one application of this granular herbicide, IR8 yielded 5.7 metric tons per hectare more than the control which was covered by a thick stand of *Echinochloa crusgalli*.

control and a grain yield increase of over 5.5 ton/ha (Table 34). These results constitute the first agronomic evidence of the efficacy of α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene for the selective control of annual grasses in transplanted rice. Except at the highest rate, TCE-styrene appeared ineffective on annual broadleaved weeds and sedges. Applications

of other herbicides, including pyriclor/2,4-D; molinate followed by MCPA; CP29037; EPTC*/2,4-D; trifluralin**/MCPA; N-oyleyl-1; 3-propylenediamine salt of 2,4-D, and the ethyl ester of MCPA resulted in grain yields similar to those produced on plots treated with TCE-styrene at rates of 1 or 2 kg/ha a.i.

Based on the early observations from the first experiment, a second experiment was carried out in the late 1968 dry season using granular TCE-styrene at rates of 1 kg/ha a.i. or less with the potassium salt of MCPA or the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D applied at the same time. The experimental procedures, plot size, and experimental design were similar to those of the first experiment. Toxicity ratings and degrees of weed control were recorded by arbitrary visual scoring. Weed survival in treated plots was observed and compared with the untreated control.

An examination of the control plots 2 weeks after transplanting showed that the predominant weeds present on the Institute's experimental

*ethyl N, N-dipropylthiolcarbamate.

** α , α , α -trifluoro, 2,6-dinitro-N, N-dipropyl-p-toluidine.

Table 34. Effect of granular α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene and other herbicides on the grain yield of transplanted IR8, IIRRI, 1968 dry season.

Herbicide treatment*	Herbicide application		Grain yield at 14% moisture* (kg/ha)	Statistical significance at 5% level**
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAT)		
Molinate (G) fb MCPA	3 fb 0.8	1-2 LSG fb 25	7698	
Pyriclor (EC) fb MCPA	0.2 fb 0.8	1 DBT fb 25	7610	
Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2 / 0.5	4	7566	
MCPA fb HW	0.8	25 fb 40	7469	
EPTC/2,4-D (EC)	2.0 / 1.0	4	7438	
Trifluralin/N CPA (liquid)	0.75 + 0.5	4	7334	
TCE-styrene (G)	2.2	4	7323	
CP 29037 (EC)	3	4	7138	
TCE-styrene (G)	1.0	4	7134	
2,4-D OPDA (EC)	0.8	4	7075	
MCPA EE (WP)	0.8	4	6966	
Handweeding	2X	25 fb 40	6534	
Propanil (EC) fb MCPA	3.0 fb 0.8	2-3 LSG fb 25	6279	
Molinate (EC) fb Pyriclor (EC)	1.0 fb 0.1	1-2 LSG	6254	
HE 314/propanil (EC)	3	2-3 LSG	6107	
TCE-styrene (G)	0.45	4	5797	
Unweeded check	—	—	1624	

* Average, four replications.

** Any two means falling opposite the same line are not statistically different at the 5% level. CV(X)% = 11

Table 35. Control of annual grasses, broadleaved-weeds and sedges by granular herbicides and their effects on the grain yield of transplanted IR 8 rice. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate of application (kg/ha a.i.)	Time of application	Weed count* (no/sq m)				Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance** (5%)
			Grasses	Broad-leaves	Sedges	Total		
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	0.75+0.8	1-2 LSG	1	28	0	29	6798	
EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2.0/0.8	3 DAT	0	55	5	60	6794	
TCE-styrene (G)+MCPA	0.75 + 0.8	3 DAT	0	11	1	12	6715	
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-DIPE	1.0 + 0.5	1-2 LSG	1	43	1	45	6650	
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	1.0 + 0.8	1-2 LSG	4	49	0	53	6640	
Pyriclor† 2,4-D (G) IPE	0.2 / 0.5	3 DAT	4	43	10	57	6574	
Propechlor/2,4-D (G)	2.5 / 0.5	3 DAT	2	23	4	29	6530	
TCE-styrene (G)+2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	1-2 LSG	1	37	1	39	6508	
TCE-styrene+2,4-D IPE	1.0 + 0.5	3 DAT	4	49	1	54	5419	
Nitrofen (G) + 2,4-D IPE	2.0 + 0.5	3 DAT	8	18	1	27	6416	
TCE-styrene (G) fb MCPA	1.0 fb 0.8	3 + 25 DAT	4	251	0	255	6335	
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	3 DAT	4	59	1	64	6242	
Trifluralin/MCPA (EC)	0.7 + 0.4	3 DAT	9	185	14	208	6144	
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	1.0 + 0.8	3 DAT	10	15	1	26	6103	
MCPA fb Hand weeding	0.8	25 + 25 DAT	18	153	0	171	5958	
TCE-styrene (G)	1.0	3 DAT	0	646	0	646	5841	
Untreated control	—	—	69	639	228	936	5107	

* 40 days after transplanting.

** Any two means falling opposite the same line are not statistically different at the 5% level. CV (X) = 6.5%

† 2, 3, 5-trichloro-4-pyridinol.

fields were *Echinochloa crusgalli* (L.) Beauv., *Monochoria vaginalis* (L.) Presl., *Cyperus iria* L., and *C. difformis* L.

Applications of granular α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene (TCE-styrene) at rates as low as 0.75 kg/ha a.i. with MCPA or 2,4-D isopropyl ester applied at the same time, gave similar grass and sedge control and better broadleaved weed control than TCE-styrene alone at 1.0 kg/ha a.i. (Table 35). The additions of phenoxy acid herbicides not only increased the weed control spectrum of TCE-styrene, but also appeared to have augmented its grass-controlling ability. Since the weed control resulting from the applications made 3 days after transplanting was equivalent to that at the one- or two-leaf stage of grass weeds (8-10 days after transplanting), it appears that TCE-styrene has a wide latitude with respect to time of application. This leeway would give a grower time to make a late application of herbicide, if necessary, and still obtain effective weed control.

Figure 20 shows the post-emergence activity of

TCE-styrene/2,4-D on annual weeds in flooded transplanted rice. Granular formulations of EPTC/2,4-D, as well as granular propachlor (2, chloro-N-isopropylacetanilide), pyriclor (2,3,5-trichloro-4-pyridinol), and nitrofen (2,4-dichlorophenyl 4-nitrophenyl ether), when applied with 2,4-D isopropyl ester, gave yields similar to those produced by TCE-styrene applied with MCPA or 2,4-D or by trifluralin/MCPA applied 3 days after transplanting.

In the second experiment the relation between grain yield and weed count was determined 40 days after transplanting. The correlation coefficient between total weeds and yield was $r = -0.87^{**}$ ($\hat{y} = 6572.3 - 1.46X$). The association between the dry weight of weeds by kind (grasses, broadleaved weeds, and sedges) and grain yield was examined. The results showed that the grasses were apparently most influential in the reduction

**Significant at 1 percent level.

Fig. 20. A significant difference in grain yield was observed when granular α -2,2,2-trichloroethyl styrene was applied with liquid 2,4-D isopropyl ester at the 1- to 2-leaf stage of grasses, demonstrating the post-emergence activity of TCE-styrene on *Echinochloa crusgalli*.

of grain yield, followed by the broadleaved species and then by the sedges (Fig. 21). This observation indicates the importance of controlling grassy weeds in flooded rice. Weed control and toxicity ratings made 2 weeks after transplanting revealed that most of the granular herbicides tested had low

toxicity to rice and provided good weed control (Table 36).

A third experiment was conducted at the Institute farm during the 1968 dry season to test various combinations of granular EPTC/MCPA and other herbicide treatments for transplanted rice. The experimental design and procedures were the same as in the two previous experiments except, contrary to the usual practice, seeds of *E. crusgalli* were not sown after transplanting because previous observations indicated that a high natural population of this weed already existed.

As shown in Table 37, applications of granular EPTC and MCPA at varying rates did not result in significantly different yields. The highest mean grain yield was obtained from plots treated with EPTC/MCPA (G) at 1.75/0.8 kg/ha a.i. The natural weed population was high and all EPTC/MCPA-treated plots yielded significantly more grain than the control plots. Trifluralin/MCPA applied as granules gave significantly lower grain yields than EPTC/MCPA at 1.85/0.8 kg/ha a.i. because the granular herbicides were applied 5 days after transplanting, when some grassy weeds had already

Table 36. Weed control and toxicity ratings of herbicide treatments in transplanted IR8. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate of application (kg/ha a.i.)	Time of application	Weed control rating*	Toxicity rating**
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	0.75 + 0.8	1-2 lsg	1.2	1.0
EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2.0/0.8	3 DAT †	1.0	1.0
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	0.75 + 0.8	3 DAT	1.0	1.7
TCE-styrene (G) † 2,4-D IPE	1.0 + 0.5	1-2 lsg	1.0	1.0
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	1.0 + 0.8	1-2 lsg	1.0	2.5
Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2 / 0.5	3 DAT	1.0	1.2
Propachlor/2,4-D (G)	2.5 / 0.5	3 DAT	1.2	1.7
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	1-2 lsg	1.0	1.5
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-D IPE	1.0 + 0.5	3 DAT	1.2	1.5
Nitrofen (G) + 2,4-D IPE	2.0 + 0.5	3 DAT	1.0	1.0
TCE-styrene (G) fb MCPA	1.0 fb 0.8	3 + 25 DAT	2.2	1.5
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-D IPE	0.75 + 0.5	3 DAT	1.0	1.5
Trifluralin / MCPA (EC)	0.7 / 0.4	3 DAT	2.0	1.0
TCE-styrene (G) + MCPA	1.0 + 0.8	3 DAT	1.0	2.5
MCPA fb Hand weeding	0.8	25 + 35 DAT	4.0	1.0
TCE-styrene (G)	1.0	3 DAT	2.5	1.5
Untreated control	—	—	4.5	1.0

* Weed control rating (2 weeks after transplanting): 1 - excellent, 2 - good, 3 - fair, 4 - poor, 5 - no control.

** Toxicity rating: 1 - no toxicity, 2 slight toxicity, 3 - moderate toxicity, 4 - severe toxicity, 5 - toxic.

Fig. 21. Correlation and linear regression between weed weight by kinds of weeds and the grain yield of IR8, IIRI, 1968 dry season.

Fig. 22. A difference was evident in the stand of IR8 in an untreated control (top) and in a plot treated with herbicides nitralin + 2,4-D isopropyl ester (bottom). Weed control experiment in transplanted rice. IIRI, 1968 wet season.

sprouted. Trifluralin is a pre-emergence herbicide and it did not control the sprouted grassy weeds effectively. Applications of granular TCE-styrene, applied either with 2,4-D or followed by MCPA, produced grain yields similar to those given by

applications of EPTC/MCPA granules.

A fourth experiment was conducted at the Institute during the 1968 wet season and included several herbicides, mostly in granular formulations. Three rice varieties, IR8, IR5, and C4-63, and a new selection, IR532E239, were used for grain yield comparisons and to determine whether or not any of the promising herbicides were toxic to any of these improved varieties or the selection. IR5, C4-63, and IR532E239 all lodged excessively and their grain yields were highly variable, so the only yield data reported here are those of IR8, which did not lodge. Figure 22 shows the stand of IR8 with and without weed control. None of the chemicals used was toxic to any of the test varieties or to the selection.

Only EPTC/MCPA, TCE-styrene/2,4-D, nitralin/2,4-D, and 2,4-D isopropyl ester treatments gave significantly higher IR8 grain yields than the untreated control (Table 38), although all herbicide treatments gave higher actual grain yields. A plot treated with nitralin+2,4-D isopropyl ester 4 days after transplanting provided adequate weed control and yielded significantly better than the untreated control. Of all the herbicides, granular TCE-styrene provided the best grass control as indicated by the low grassy weed weight at the heading stage of the rice crop.

In two separate experiments conducted at the Institute during the 1968 dry season, several herbicides which had shown promise in the herbicide screening test of the 1967 wet season were tested. Optimum cultural practices were used.

In the first of these experiments the highest grain yield (9,407 kg/ha) was obtained from the plots sprayed with CP 29037 4 days after transplanting, while the lowest yield (4,588 kg/ha) was obtained from the untreated control (Table 39). Many other herbicides, including granular molinate, EPTC/2,4-D, trifluralin/MCPA, pyriclor/2,4-D, and TCE-styrene, gave grain yields which were not significantly different from that of the best treatment. Although some rice injury symptoms appeared after the application of CP 50144, they apparently did not significantly affect the yield.

In the second experiment, several granular and liquid herbicides were applied as pre- and early

* α,α,α -trifluoro, 2,6-dinitro-N, N-dipropyl-p-toluidine.

Table 37. Effect of various combinations of granular EPTC/MCPA and other herbicide treatments on the grain yield of transplanted IR8. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Herbicide treatment*	Rate of application (kg/ha a.i.)	Time of application	Grain yield* (kg/ha)	Statistical significance** (5%)
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.75 / 0.8	5 DAT	7295	a
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.5 / 0.8	5 DAT	7033	ab
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.5 / 0.4	5 DAT	6546	ab
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.5 / 0.6	5 DAT	6400	ab
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.75 / 0.6	5 DAT	6300	ab
EPTC/MCPA (G)	2.0 / 0.6	5 DAT	6200	ab
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.75/0.4	5 DAT	6093	ab
EPTC/MCPA (G)	2.0/0.4	5 DAT	5905	ab
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-D	1.0 + 0.5	5 DAT	6784	ab
TCE-styrene (G) fb MCPA	1.0 fb 0.8	5 + 25 DAT	6763	ab
TCE-styrene (G) fb MCPA	1.5 fb 0.8	5 + 25 DAT	6709	ab
Trifluralin/MCPA (EC)	0.7 / 0.4	5 DAT	5377	ab
Trifluralin/MCPA (G)	0.7 / 0.4	5 DAT	5261	b
Hand weeded	—	25 + 35 DAT	6404	ab
Untreated control	—	—	3400	c

* Average, three replications.

** Any two treatment means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. CV(X) = 16%

post-emergence treatments on transplanted IR8. CP 29037 applied 4 days after transplanting (pre-emergence to grasses) or at the 2- to 3-leaf stage of grassy weeds (post-emergence) again gave excellent weed control and high grain yields. As in previous experiments, granular herbicides such as EPTC/2,4-D, trifluralin/MCPA, propachlor, pyriclor/2,4-D, and TCE-styrene were among the best treatments. Other herbicides not included in earlier experiments, but which showed promise in this experiment, were nitratin [4-(methylsulfonyl)-2,6-dinitro-N, N-dipropylaniline] sprayed 4 days after transplanting and granular propanil applied at the 2- to 3-leaf stage of the grasses (Table 40).

Other weed control experiments concerned primarily with testing granular herbicides for transplanted rice were conducted in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry, using essentially the same procedures as those previously described.

In the field experiment conducted during the 1968 dry season at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, located in the principal rice-growing region of the Philippines, weed control with granular herbicides resulted in dramatic increases in grain yield ranging from 3.7 to 5.2 mt/ha (Table 41). The mean grain yield of all

treated plots was significantly higher than that of the untreated control. Grain yield differences among the plots treated with the various granular herbicides were not significant.

In the field experiment conducted at the Visayas Rice Experiment Station in Iloilo, the differences in grain yield among the plots treated with the various granular herbicides were not significant. Grain yields from all the treated plots were, however, significantly higher than that of the untreated control (Table 42).

In tropical Asia, about 80 percent of the area planted to rice is rainfed. Herbicides which require the removal of field water for effective weed control are unacceptable to most Asian farmers since the uncertainty of the amount and distribution of rainfall makes them reluctant to remove the flood water. Under tropical conditions, granular herbicides, which can be broadcast directly into the water, should be highly acceptable to farmers growing transplanted rice.

Of the herbicides tested by the Institute's Agronomy Department in 1968, the following gave excellent weed control: nitrofen + 2,4-D IPE, nitrofen followed by MCPA, EPTC/2,4-D, EPTC/MCPA, and trifluralin/MCPA. Granular formulations of nitrofen, trifluralin/MCPA, and

Table 38. Control of annual grasses, broadleaves and sedges by granular herbicides and their effects on the grain yield of transplanted IR8 rice. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate of application (kg/ha a.i.)	Time of application	Weed weight at heading (g/sq m)				Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance at 5% level
			Grasses	Broad-leaves	Sedges	Total		
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.75/0.7	4	53	6	0	59	5011	
TCE-styrene (G)	0.75 + 0.5	4	21	30	0	51	4816	
+ 2,4-D IPE								
Nitralin (WP)	1.5 + 0.5	4	84	12	0	96	4790	
+ 2,4-D IPE								
2,4-D IPE (EC)	0.8	4	105	0	0	105	4788	
Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2/0.5	4	148	76	0	224	4677	
CP 50144 (G)	1.5	4	6	94	0	100	4588	
Propachlor/2,4-D (G)	2.5/0.5	4	44	22	0	66	4504	
Nitrofen (G)	2.0 + 0.8	4	68	57	0	125	4525	
+ MCPA (WSL)								
Trifluralin/MCPA (G)	0.7/0.4	4	117	76	0	192	4260	
MCPA fb handweeding	0.8 MCPA	28 fb 38	50	0	0	50	4200	
Unweeded control		—	211	60	0	271	3838	

* Any two treatment means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at 5% level.

EPTC/MCPA are now available in the Philippines at prices competitive with the cost of 100 man-hours of labor, which is generally considered necessary for one handweeding of 1 hectare of transplanted rice.

Granular TCE-styrene is another selective grass herbicide which, when applied shortly after transplanting with either MCPA or 2,4-D, provided good control of all kinds of weeds in transplanted rice. Granular formulations of TCE-styrene with the 2,4-D isopropyl ester will soon be tested further in the Philippines as well as in other tropical rice-growing countries.

Early application of phenoxy acid herbicides

In an experiment conducted during the 1966 dry season, 2,4-D isopropyl ester, 2,4-D amine, and 2,4-D sodium salt, applied at 4 days after transplanting (pre-emergence of grasses) gave adequate weed control and yields similar to that given by a selective grass herbicide, nitrofen. This test was conducted with H-4, the tall, tropical indica variety from Ceylon, which was transplanted in the field as 21-day-old wet-bed seedlings.

Additional experiments were conducted during the 1968 dry and wet seasons to evaluate the performance and weed selectivity of several formulations of 2,4-D and MCPA applied 4 days after transplanting to dapog (11-day-old) and wet-bed (21-day-old) IR8 seedlings.

Dry season. An emulsifiable-concentrate formulation of isopropyl ester of 2,4-D, an ethyl ester formulation of MCPA, and an ethyl-hexyl ester formulation of MCPA all gave yields similar to those produced by applying granular EPTC/2,4-D and molinate followed by a potassium salt of MCPA (Table 43). The phenoxy acetic acid herbicides worked equally well on dapog regular 21-day-old seedlings. A single application of 2,4-D isopropyl ester at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. produced outstanding results and appeared superior to any of the other 2,4-D formulations, including the various ethyl hexyl ester formulations. The rates of MCPA ethyl ester and 2,4-D isopropyl ester were different and hence not comparable.

Wet season. In the 1968 wet season a granular formulation of 2,4-D isopropyl ester was tried for the first time in an Institute experiment. The base

of the granules was volcanic ash from Sicily. All the treated plots gave significantly higher grain yields than the untreated controls (average of 2 seedling-types).

Unlike the dry-season results, the grain yields obtained from dapog-grown seedlings of IR8 in the wet season were significantly higher than those from the 21-day-old wet-bed seedlings (Table 44). This difference was not due to herbicide treatment, since in the untreated control the dapog-grown seedlings gave significantly higher yields than those grown by the wet-bed method.

The highest grain yield resulted from the application of the granular 2,4-D isopropyl ester and was significantly higher than that of the 2,4-D isooctyl ester treatment. Liquid 2,4-D isopropyl

ester and MCPA ester both gave grain yields similar to that of the best treatment and that of the previous standard Institute treatment (MCPA spray followed by one handweeding).

These results suggest that short-chain alkyl esters of 2,4-D or MCPA, such as the ethyl or isopropyl esters, formulated as granules, emulsifiable concentrates, or wettable powders, may be more selective and active as pre-emergence herbicides in transplanted rice than the long-chain esters (e.g., ethyl hexyl ester of 2,4-D) and the amine and alkali-metal salts of these compounds.

Figure 23 shows the stands of IR8 after application of granular 2,4-D isopropyl ester and a wettable powder of MCPA-ethyl ester at 4 days after transplanting. Some formulations of 2,4-D and

Table 39. Effect of early application of herbicide on the grain yield of IR8. IRR1, 1968 dry season.

Treatment	Herbicide applied		Grain yield*
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAT)	
1. CP 29037 (EC)	3.0	4	9407
2. Molinate (G) fb MCPA (WSL)	3.0 fb 0.8	8 fb 25	9256
3. Handweeding (2x)	—	20 + 35	9062
4. Molinate (G)	3.0	8	8961
5. EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2.5/1.0	4	8845
6. EPTC (G)	3.0	4	8768**
7. MCPA (WSL) fb 1 HW	0.8	20 fb 35	8719
8. Trifluralin/MCPA (EC)	0.7/0.4	4	8296
9. MCPA-Ksait (WSL)	0.8	4	8207
10. Nitrofen (G) fb MCPA (EC)	2.0 fb 0.8	4 fb 25	8158**
11. EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2.0/0.8	4	8108
12. Trifluralin/MCPA (G)	0.7/0.4	4	8043**
13. Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.4/0.5	4	8037**
14. Pyriclor fb MCPA (EC)	0.2 fb 0.8	4 fb 25	7993
15. CP 50144 (G)	3.0	4	7969
16. Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2/0.5	4	7895**
17. Nitrofen (G)	0.2	4	7849†
18. 2,4-D IPE (EC)	0.8	4	7841**
19. TCE-styrene (G)	1.75	4	7656
20. Pyriclor (EC)	0.2	4	7293**
21. Nitrofen (G) fb 2,4-D (EC)	2.0 fb 0.8	4 fb 25	7183
22. Dicamba/MCPA (EC)	0.5	4	7073**
23. Dicamba (EC)	1.0	4	7025
24. Untreated control	—	—	4588

* Average, four replications. Any two treatment means opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

** One value computed as missing plot.

† Two values computed as missing plot.

Table 40. Effect of pre-and early post-emergence herbicides on the grain yield of IR8. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Herbicide treatment	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Timing	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance* at 5% level
1. CP 29037 fb MCPA	3 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	8339	
2. Pyriclor/2,4-D fb pyriclor /2,4-D	(.2/.54)+(.1/.27)	4 fb 18 DAT	8272	
3. Nitrain fb MCPA	2 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	8237	
4. Propachlor fb MCPA	3 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	8236	
5. CP 29037	3	2-3 LSG	8222	
6. CP 29037 fb MCPA	3 + .8	2-3 LSG fb 25 DAT	8066	
7. TCE-styrene (G)	1	4 DAT	8032	
8. Pyriclor/2,4-D fb MCPA	(.2/.5)+.8	4 fb 25 DAT	8028	
9. Nitrain (WP)	2	4 DAT	8020	
10. Pyriclor/2,4-D fb MCPA	(.2/.5)+.8	2-3 LSG fb 25 DAT	7902	
11. MCPA fb HW	.8	25 fb 35 DAT	7840	
12. CP 54040	3	4 DAT	7793	
13. Molinate fb MCPA (G)	3 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	7780	
14. CP 29037 (EC)	3	4 DAT	7734	
15. EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2/.8	4 DAT	7684	
16. Pyriclor/2,4-D fb Pyriclor/2,4-D	(.15/.4)+(.1/.27)	4 fb 18 DAT	7654	
17. Trifluralin /MCPA (G)	.7/.4	4 DAT	7636	
18. CP 54040 fb MCPA	3 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	7616	
19. TCE-styrene fb MCPA	1 + .8	2-3 LSG fb 25 DAT	7614	
20. Pyriclor (EC) fb MCPA	.2 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	7579	
21. Pyriclor/2,4-D	.2/.5	2-3 LSG	7564	
22. TCE-styrene fb MCPA	1 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	7525	
23. Propanil (G)	3	2-3 LSG	7445	
24. CP 50144 (G)	3	4 DAT	7304	
25. Propanil (G) fb MCPA	3 + .8	2-3 LSG fb 25 DAT	7272	
26. Propachlor (G)	3	4 DAT	7267	
27. TCE-styrene	1	2-3 LSG	7226	
28. Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	.2/.5	4 DAT	7005	
29. Pyriclor/2,4-D fb Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	(.1/.27)+(.1/.27)	4 fb 18 DAT	6920	
30. CP 50144 fb MCPA	3 + .8	4 fb 25 DAT	5902	
Weedy check			6373	

* Any two treated means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5-percent level.

MCPA, when applied early (pre-emergence of weeds), gave total weed control without injury to dapog or wet-bed seedlings and provided significantly higher grain yields than the untreated control, thus comparing favorably with other successful herbicide treatments. These findings further suggest the desirability of using granular formulations of the low-cost herbicides for weed control in transplanted rice. Such a development could dramatically change the weed control practices in rice throughout tropical Asia.

Use of chemicals in lieu of land preparation in flooded rice

Experiments conducted in 1967 showed that,

under certain field conditions, high yields can be obtained from broadcast-seeded rice without land preparation (plowing and harrowing) through the use of a suitable herbicide combination sprayed before planting (1967 Annual Report).

During 1968, further field experiments were conducted at the Institute to develop no-tillage chemical procedures for transplanted or direct-seeded rice that might replace land preparation.

Transplanted rice

Dry season. Herbicides were applied at different rates and in various combinations as substitutes for land preparation before wet-bed rice seedlings were transplanted. The herbicides were sprayed

Table 41. Effect of early application of granular herbicides on the grain yield of IR8. IRRI-BPI Cooperative Weed Control Experiment, Maligaya Rice Research & Training Center, 1968 dry season.

Herbicide treatment*	Rate of application (kg/ha a.i.)	Time of application (DAT)	Grain yield** (kg/ha)	Statistical significance†† (5%)
Nitrofen (G) fb MCPA	2 fb 0.8	3 fb 22	8060	
EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2 / 0.8	3	7792	
Molinate† (G) fb MCPA	3 fb 0.8	7 fb 22	7692	
Trifluralin/MCPA (G)	0.7 / 0.4	3	7609	
TCE-styrene (G) fb MCPA	1.52 fb 0.8	3 fb 22	7473	
EPTC/2,4-D (G)	1.75/ 0.7	3	7354	
MCPA fb handweeding	0.8 (MCPA)	22 fb 35	7018	
Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2 / 0.5	3 fb 22	6590	
Untreated control	—	—	2878	

* Average of 6 replications.

** Average of 4 replications.

† (S-ethyl hexahydro-1H-azepine-1-carbothioate).

†† Any two means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level. CV (X) = 16%.

Table 42. Effect of early application of herbicides on the grain yield of transplanted IR8. IRRI-BPI Cooperative Weed Control Experiment, Location: Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Iloilo, 1968 wet season.

Herbicide treatments	Rate of application (kg/ha a.i.)	Time of application (DAT)	Grain yield* at 14% moisture	Statistical significance** at 5% level
Handweeding (2x)	—	25 + 40	6924	
Trifluralin/MCPA (G)	0.7/0.4	3	6831	
TCE-styrene (G)	1	3	6792	
Nitrofen (G) + 2,4-D	2 + 0.5	3	6778	
EPTC/MCPA (G)	1.75/0.7	3	6725	
MCPA fb handweeding	—	25 + 40	6649	
TCE-styrene (G) fb MCPA	1 fb 0.8	3 fb 25	6579	
TCE-styrene (G) + 2,4-D IPE	1 + 0.5	3	6572	
Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2/0.5	3	6108	
Untreated control	—	—	4328	

* Average of 4 replications.

** Any two means following opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level. CV (X)% = 9

Table 43. Grain yield (jg/ha) of transplanted IR8 obtained after early applications of phenoxy-acids and other herbicides to dapog (11-day-old) and regular (21-day-old) seedlings. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Treatment (by rank)	Application		Seedling type		Treatment mean	Statistical significance at 5% level*
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAT)	Regular	Dapog		
MCPA-K (WSL) fb HW	0.8	25 & 35	7080	7491	7286	
Molinate (G) fb MCPA-K	3.0 & 0.8	4 & 25	6891	6972	6932	
EPTC/2,4-D (G)	2.0 / 0.8	4	7201	6124	6663	
2,4-D-IPE (EC)	0.8	4	6108	7124	6616	
2,4-D-IPE (EC) fb same	0.8 & 0.8	4 & 25	6652	6246	6449	
MCPA-EE (WP) fb same	0.7 & 0.7	4 & 25	5676	6908	6292	
MCPA-EE (WP)	0.7	4	4966	5919	5443	
Pyriclor/2,4-D (G)	0.2 / 0.5	4	4737	5464	5101	
2,4-D-OPDA (EC) fb same	0.6 & 0.6	4 & 25	4438	5132	4785	
2,4-D-IOE (G)	0.8	4	3506	4899	4203	
2,4-D-OPDA (EC)	0.625	4	3896	4480	4188	
2,4-D-EHE (G)	0.8	4	4278	2548	3913	
2,4-D-EHE (G) fb same	0.8 & 0.8	4 & 25	3980	3539	3759	
2,4-D-IOE (G) fb same	0.8 & 0.8	4 & 25	4729	2666	3698	
Trifluralin/MCPA (G)	0.7 / 0.4	4	2902	3463	3182	
Untreated controls			1640	2173	1906	
Seedling-type mean			4918	5134		

* Any two means falling within the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 44. Grain yield (kg/ha) of transplanted IR8 obtained after early application of phenoxy acids to dopog (11-day-old) and regular (21-day-old) seedlings. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Treatment (by rank)	Application		Seedling type		Treatment mean	Statistical significance at 5% level*
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAT)	Regular	Dapog		
2,4-D-IPE (G)**	0.8	4	5150	5671	5410	
MCPA-EE (WP)	0.7	4	4958	5809	5384	
2,4-D-IPE (EC)	0.8	4	4711	6047	5379	
MCPA (WSL) fb handweeding	0.8	25 fb 35	4670	5809	5240	
2,4-D IOE (G)	0.8	4	4390	5401	4896	
Untreated controls			2668	3977	3322	

* Any two means falling within the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

onto weedy plots from which transplanted rice had been harvested more than 2 months earlier. Treatments included MCPA applied at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. 11 days before transplanting (DBT), followed by (fb) such systemic herbicides as pyriclor or dalapon sprayed at 8 DBT. These combinations were then followed by contact herbicides such as paraquat, MSMA, or PCP in oil applied at 5 DBT. Transplanted control plots were prepared using normal tillage practices (plowing and harrowing) followed by two successive handweeding at 14 and 39 days after transplanting (DAT).

The application of chemicals such as pyriclor at 2.0 kg/ha a.i. and combinations of MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. fb dalapon at 3 kg/ha a.i. fb paraquat at 1 kg/ha a.i. resulted in grain yields similar to that of the transplanted control, and gave good weed control. There were no significant differences between the yields on plots treated with paraquat and pyriclor at their lowest and highest rates, but pyriclor at 3 kg/ha a.i. was toxic to the rice plant (Table 45).

Wet season. Applications of herbicides at different rates and combinations were substituted for land preparation during the 1968 wet season. The herbicides were sprayed onto randomly distributed weedy plots before planting. Herbicide combinations included dalapon at 3 kg/ha a.i. and MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. at 8 DBT followed by paraquat, MSMA, or PCP in oil at 3 DBT. The transplanted control plots were plowed, harrowed, and handweeded twice at 14 and 35 DAT.

The chemical combinations of MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. + dalapon at 3 kg/ha a.i. + paraquat at 1 kg/ha a.i. and of dalapon at 3 kg/ha a.i. + paraquat at 1 kg/ha a.i. gave grain yields similar to that of the transplanted control plot (Table 46).

In the experimental field which was not plowed or harrowed, infestation by a perennial grass (*Paspalum scrobiculatum*) was heavy. This grass, which normally confines its growth to the levees of the Institute farm, grew profusely in the experimental plots and was not effectively controlled by any of the herbicide treatments. Thus, where perennial grasses are present, no-tillage techniques may not be feasible for more than two successive crop seasons in the same field. The possibilities of eliminating or minimizing land preparation in flooded transplanted rice through the use of chemicals, however, merits further testing.

Fig. 23. Granular 2,4-D isopropyl ester and MCPA ethyl ester wettable powder when applied 4 days after transplanting dapog-grown IR8 seedlings provided total weed control until crop maturity and yielded over 2,000 kg/ha more than the untreated control. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Broadcast rice

Dry season. A project similar to that for transplanted rice was undertaken in broadcast rice during the 1968 dry season. An experimental site was chosen which contained weedy plots with about 60 percent grasses and where transplanted rice had been harvested more than 2 months earlier. The herbicide combinations included MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. applied 11 days before seeding (DBS) followed by systemic herbicides such as pyriclor, dalapon, or MSMA sprayed 8 DBS and then followed by paraquat or PCP in oil 5 DBS. Broadcast control plots were prepared by normal tillage practices (plowing and harrowing) followed by two handweeding at 25 and 40 days after seeding (DAS), respectively. A blanket spray of MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. was given to all but the

Table 45. Effects of some herbicides substituted for land preparation (no tillage) on the grain yield of transplanted IR8, IRR1, 1968 dry season.

	Unplowed pre-planting treatment	+ post-planting treatment	Weed control rating*	Weed weight** (g/sq m)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance at 5% level†
1.	Plowed + harrowed	1 HW (14DAT) + MCPA 0.8+1 HW (39 DAT)	1.0	27	7090	
2.	Pyriclor 2.0	Pyriclor 0.2+2,4-D 0.5 kg/ha a.i. (5 DAT)	3.0	246	7010	
3.	MCPA 0.8 + Dalapon 3.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	1.5	56	6860	
4.	Pyriclor 3.0	"	2.0	184	6494	
5.	MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 1.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	1.5	174	6422	
6.	MCPA 0.8 + paraquat 3.0	"	2.3	96	6345	
7.	MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 1.0	"	2.5	112	6338	
8.	Dalapon 3.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	2.3	66	6140	
9.	Plowed + harrowed only	"	2.5	118	6126	
10.	PCP oil 5.0	Pyriclor 0.2/2,4-D 0.5 kg/ha a.i. (5 DAT)	7.3	134	6053	
11.	MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 2.0	"	1.0	212	6009	
12.	MCPA 0.8 + MSMA 8.0 E paraquat 1.0	"	1.0	72	5849	
13.	MCPA 0.8 + PCP oil 5.0	"	3.3	156	5822	
14.	Pyriclor 1.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	3.8	262	5773	
15.	MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 3.0	"	1.5	74	5770	
16.	Pyriclor 1.0	"	7.3	317	5770	
17.	MCPA 0.8 + paraquat 1.5	"	6.3	272	5736	
18.	Paraquat 1.5	"	5.5	268	5602	
19.	Paraquat 3.0	"	4.0	236	5462	
20.	Paraquat 2.0	"	6.3	384	5090	
21.	MCPA 0.8 + paraquat 2.0††	"	6.5	324	5070	
22.	MSMA 8.0	"	8.5	226	4873	
23.	MSMA 8.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	4.3	228	4801	
24.	MCPA 0.8 + MSMA 8.0	"	7.3	356	4680	

* 1 - complete control, 10 - no control (14 DAT).

** 55 DAT.

† Any two means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

†† Weed species present in replications 1 and 2 was different from that in 3 and 4 and the chemical (paraquat 2.0) was not effective against this weed species.

Table 46. Results of an experiment involving the substitution of herbicides for land preparation in transplanted IR8 rice, IRR1, 1968 wet season.

	Pre-planting treatment	Post-planting treatment	Weed control rating*	Weed weight** (g/sq m)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance at 5% level†
1.	Plowed + harrowed	1 HW + MCPA 0.8 + 1 HW	1.0	18	4952	
2.	MCPA 0.8 + Dalapon 3.0 + paraquat 1.0	Pyriclor 0.2/2,4-D	1.5	140	4395	
3.	MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 1.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	3.2	176	3755	
4.	Dalapon 3.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	5.5	384	3695	
5.	Plowed + harrowed only	-	2.5	134	3528	
6.	Pyriclor 2.0	Pyriclor 0.2/2,4-D	3.2	249	2990	
7.	MCPA 0.8 + PCP oil 5.0	"	9.5	792	2679	
8.	MCPA 0.8 + MSMA 8.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	7.2	538	2194	

* 1- complete control, 10 - no control (14 days after transplanting).

** 55 days after transplanting.

† Any two means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 47. Effect of some herbicides substituted for land preparation (no tillage) on the grain yield of broadcast IR8, IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Unplowed pre-planting treatment	+ post-planting treatment	Weed control rating	Weed weight** (g/sq m)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance at 5% level††
1. Plowed + harrowed	1 HW (25 DAS) + MCPA 0.8 kg/ha (35 DAS) + 1 HW (40 DAS)	1.0	14	6654	
2. Dalapon 3.0 + paraquat 1.0	MCPA 0.3 kg/ha (35 DAS)	2.0	213	5695	
3. Plowed + harrowed only	No weeding	3.5	86	5692	
4. MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 1.0 + paraquat 1.0	MCPA 0.8 kg/ha (35 DAS)	2.0	152	5261	
5. MCPA 0.8 + MSMA 8.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	2.0	486	4592	
6. MCPA 0.8 + dalapon 3.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	2.0	310	4424	
7. MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 3.0	"	3.0	694	3743	
8. Pyriclor 2.0	"	5.7	1011	3142	
9. MCPA 0.8 + paraquat 2.0	"	6.0	615	3109	
10. MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 2.0	"	6.2	615	3109	
11. Pyriclor 1.0 + paraquat 1.0	"	5.2	738	2969	
12. Paraquat 2.0	"	6.2	748	2913	
13. MCPA 0.8 + paraquat 1.5	"	5.5	676	2747	
14. PCP oil 5.0	"	8.5	354	2640	
15. MCPA 0.8 + paraquat 3.0	"	5.7	707	2611	
16. Pyriclor 3.0	"	6.0	908	2437	
17. Pyriclor 1.0	"	6.5	820	2374	
18. MSMA 8.0 $\bar{x}$	"	9.5	1108	2040	
19. MSMA 8.0 + paraquat 1.0 $\bar{x}$	"	4.2	783	1957	
20. MCPA 0.8 + MSMA 8.0 $\bar{x}$	"	9.2	760	1856	
21. MCPA 0.8 + PCP oil 5.0 $\bar{f}$	"	10.0	109	1730	
22. Paraquat 3.0	"	7.2	932	1700	
23. MCPA 0.8 + pyriclor 1.0 $\bar{f}$	"	7.0	586	1694	
24. Paraquat 1.5	"	8.2	1034	765	

* 1 - complete control, 10 - no control (14 DAS).

** 55 days after transplanting.

† Average, four replications.

†† Any two means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

$\bar{x}$ Average, three replications.

$\bar{f}$ Average, two replications.

control plots at 35 DAS (Table 47).

Such combinations of chemicals as dalapon at 3 kg/ha a.i. + paraquat at 1 kg/ha a.i. and MCPA at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. + pyriclor at 1 kg/ha a.i. + paraquat at 1 kg/ha a.i. gave grain yields similar to that of the control plots. No significant differences in grain yield resulted from paraquat and pyriclor applications at their lowest and highest rates, but pyriclor was toxic to the rice at 3.0 kg/ha a.i. Figure 24 shows the stand of IR8 when transplanted and broadcast on a field without land preparation. Weed control was excellent when MCPA, dalapon, and paraquat were applied in succession,

thus showing the feasibility of no-tillage techniques in both transplanted and broadcast rice.

Weed Control in Direct-Seeded Rice

Herbicide evaluation in broadcast flooded rice

Direct-seeding is faster and easier than transplanting and yields are similar (1967 Annual Report). However, weed competition is more severe in broadcast rice. It is difficult to handweed broadcast rice because it is nearly impossible to distinguish the young grasses from the rice seedlings and, of course, mechanical weeding is impossible.

Fig. 24. Applications of MCPA, dalapon, and paraquat at 11, 8, and 5 days, respectively, before transplanting (DBT) or 11, 8, and 5 days before broadcasting (DBS) IR8 in a field with no land preparation gave similar grain yield to the standard method of land preparation. IIRRI, 1968 dry season.

Effective combinations of chemical and cultural methods of weed control, however, have made direct-seeding highly practical in developed countries where the scarcity and high cost of labor had encouraged mechanization.

Chemical weed control is difficult in direct-seeded rice because few herbicides are available that will kill the weeds without injuring the crop during some stage of its growth. MCPA and 2,4-D are economical and effective for sedge and broad-leaved weed control when used correctly, but molinate and propanil, the only selective grass herbicides commercially available for direct-seeded rice, have serious cost and usage limitations in Asia.

A preliminary experiment was conducted to compare the selectivity and performance of eight herbicides not previously tested in direct-seeded

rice at the Institute and several new formulations and mixtures of herbicides with nitrofen, monate, and propanil, which were earlier found promising (1966 Annual Report). These herbicides were applied at selected rates and times to 15 sq plots after pre-germinated IR5 rice seeds were broadcast onto puddled soil at 100 kg/ha. The experimental area received 60 kg/ha of nitrogen ammonium sulfate during final harrowing (DBS), and 5 kg/ha of dry *Echinochloa crusgala* seeds were sown 2 DBS and lightly incorporated into the soil surface by raking, to insure a uniform initial weed stand among the plots. The soil of the plots was kept saturated with water but not flooded until 3 DAS, when 2 to 3 cm of standing water was added prior to the herbicide applications. This water level was maintained until crop maturity in all plots except those treated with liquid propanil formulations, which required drainage before application and reflooding the next day. All but eight treatments (which were either too toxic to the rice plant or were applied at incorrect rates or times) yielded higher than the untreated control. The grain yield performances of the 12 best treatments are shown in Table 48. The yield data were not statistically analyzed because these preliminary treatments were replicated only twice. The following herbicides were found to injure the rice plant:

M & B-13992 (WP) and VCS-438 (G) applied 14 DAS at 3 and 1.5 kg/ha a.i., respectively; swep (EC) at 3 and 6 kg/ha a.i. (14 DAS); mixtures of propanil/bromoxynil or propanil/ioxynil applied 14 DAS at 2/0.25 and 2/0.5 kg/ha a.i., respectively. The toxicities of the EC formulations may have been caused by their solvents, since swep W was toxic at 6 but not at 3 kg/ha a.i., and EC formulations of propanil, bromoxynil, and ioxynil applied separately at 14 DAS were not toxic at 0.5, and 1 kg/ha a.i., respectively. The poor stands of the rice plants before treatment with propanil/CHCH or molinate EC, rather than toxicity, account for the poor stands at 42 DAS. Only transient solvent-injury symptoms appeared after propanil/CHCH applications, and molinate caused no visible injury.

Bromoxynil and ioxynil are of particular interest because they have recently been used successfully for early post-emergence broadleaf weed control in barley and wheat and they appear

Table 48. Preliminary evaluation of some promising pre- and post-emergence herbicides in broadcast-seeded flooded IR5. IRR1, 1968 wet season.

Herbicides	Application		Visual ratings* at 42 DAS				Grain yield** by rank (kg/ha)
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAS)	(R)	(G)	(B)	(S)	
1. Ioxynil (240 g/1 EC) †	0.5	14	9	7	2	10	3907
2. El-119 (1.8% G)	0.8	7	9	8	1	1	3876
fb MCPA-K (WSL)	0.8	43					
3. Nitrofen (8% limestone G)	4.0	3	9	9	5	9	3832
4. Propanil (10% G)	6.0	14	7	6	6	10	3805
fb MCPA-EE (25% WP)	0.8	43					
5. Molinate/bromoxynil † (720/240 g/1 EC)	2.0/0.25	14	8	9	9	10	3748
6. Nitrofen (9% clay G)	2.0	3	9	9	5	9	3690
7. El-119 (1.8% G)	0.4	7	9	7	1	1	3666
fb MCPA-K (WSL)	0.8	43					
8. Propanil/CHCH (350/175 g/1 EC) fb MCPA-EE (25% WP)	4.0/2.0	14	7	10	1	10	3636
	0.8	43					
9. Nitrofen (7% bentonite G)	2.0	3	9	9	5	10	3620
10. Propanil/CHCH †† (350/175 g/1 EC) fb MCPA-EE (25% WP)	2.0/1.0	14	5	9	1	10	3617
		43					
11. Bromoxynil (240 g/1 EC) †	0.5	14	9	8	9	10	3511
12. Molinate (720 g/1 EC)	6.0	14	5	10	1	1	3509
fb 2,4-D-EE (25% WP)	0.8	43					
13. Untreated control	—	—	6	1	1	1	2076

*Estimates of rice stand (R), on a scale of 10 (very good) to 1 (very poor), and weed control with respect to grasses (G), broadleaved weeds (B) and sedges (S), on a scale of 1 (no control) to 10 (complete control) Note that these ratings were made the day before the indicated applications of MCPA or 2,4-D which satisfactorily controlled sedges and broadleaved weeds in all instances.

**Based on weight at 14% moisture.

† Ioxynil and bromoxynil ester of octanoic acid were used.

†† CHCH is 2-(1-cyclohexenyl) cyclohexane.

much safer than 2,4-D or MCPA in seedling rice as well. In combinations with molinate, these herbicides increased the weed control spectrum and enhanced the grass-controlling activity of this herbicide at two-thirds its minimum effective rate when used alone. Similar results were obtained by combinations of C-6989 with bromoxynil or ioxynil, although these combinations were probably applied too late (14 DAS) for maximum efficacy.

The addition of 2-(1-cyclohexenyl) cyclohexane (CHCH) to propanil is claimed by its formulator to enhance penetration and reduce crystalline propanil deposits on leaf surfaces and thus make propanil more effective at lower rates. Propanil/

CHCH performed better at 2 kg/ha a.i. of propanil than a 360 g/1 EC formulation of propanil alone, and the combinations appeared safe to rice at twice this rate. Granular propanil also appeared promising for direct-seeded rice because it gave selective control of annual grasses and sedges and partial control of the main broadleaved weed *Monochoria vaginalis*. Another advantage of granular propanil is that it does not require drainage before application and is thus more convenient to apply than liquid propanil.

Granular EL-119 gave good grass control only at 0.4 kg/ha a.i. and appeared selective at twice that rate when applied at the 1- to 2-leaf stage of *E. crusgalli* (7 DAS). A WP formulation of EL-119 did not seem to be as effective as the G form. This

new accession deserves further evaluation because of its effectiveness at low rates and its early post-emergence performance.

The similarities in performance between the Philippine clay and the imported bentonite formulations of nitrofen in this experiment suggest the possibility of reducing the cost of this herbicide by local granulation.

Another preliminary experiment was conducted to evaluate two new methods of obtaining herbicide selectivity in direct-seeded flooded rice: 1) the application of pre-emergence herbicides several days before seeding to allow time for them to affect germinating weeds and to dissipate to levels sublethal to rice, and 2) the protection of rice seeds from preplanting applications of pre-emergence herbicides by means of activated-charcoal coatings. The experimental procedures used were the same as in the previous test except that *E. crusgalli* seeds soaked for 24 hours were sown and incorporated into the soil at 6 kg/ha, and all herbicides were applied in 2 to 3 cm of standing water which was then allowed to subside for 3 days before pre-germinated IR5 seeds were sown at 100 kg/ha onto the water-saturated soil. The plots were not flooded again until 3 DAS after which 2 to 3 cm of water was maintained until crop maturity. An untreated plot served as a control as did plots in which an Institute-developed portable power weeder was used to cut rows through the broadcast rice at 20 DAS. These plots were then handweeded at 30 DAS as a kind of non-chemical standard treatment comparable to handweeded transplanted rice.

This experiment was not allowed to reach the harvest stage, since it was conducted only to give preliminary indications of the kinds of herbicides that might act quickly on weeds and then dissipate rapidly or against which a charcoal coating would provide protection. Chemicals that permitted medium to good rice stand establishments included nitrofen on local limestone and clay and on imported bentonite granules, each at 2 and 4 kg/ha a.i. and dichlobenil (2.5% G) at 0.75 kg/ha a.i. Only fair weed control, however, was given by nitrofen (bentonite G) at 4 kg/ha a.i. and the dichlobenil treatment. The other nitrofen applications provided very poor weed control, indicating that they may have dissipated too soon to affect germinating weed seeds. All the other herbicides,

including dichlobenil (G) at 1.5, CNP (5% G) at 1.5 and 3, nitralin (5% G) at 0.5 and 1, nitralin/chlorthiamid (1.7/1 % G) at 0.5/0.3 and 1/0.6, NC-5024 (200 g/l EC) at 0.75 and 1.5, OCS-21693/21799 at 6/1 and pyriclor (180 g/l WSL) at 0.2 kg/ha a.i. were toxic to the rice plant. Since all of these applications gave fair to good weed control, especially at their higher rates, it appears that these herbicides persisted in amounts lethal to both weeds and rice plants for at least 3 days.

The most interesting aspect of this experiment was the remarkable protection given by the activated-charcoal coatings against the lethal effects of CNP at 3, dichlobenil at 1.5, NC-5024 at 1.5, and pyriclor at 0.2 kg/ha a.i., respectively. The uncoated rice seeds died or failed to make good stands after being broadcast into halves of plots treated with these chemicals, while the charcoal-coated rice sown into the other halves survived and made excellent stands in all instances. Moreover, subsequent invasion by weeds into the halves with vacant spaces where the rice failed to grow led to apparent losses in weed control, but good weed control was maintained in the halves of plots sown to charcoal-treated rice.

The stands in the power-weeded plots gave the impression of having been row-seeded, but they became very weedy before handweeding.

An intermediate evaluation of weed control treatments found promising in previous direct-seeded experiments was begun on August 20, 1968. This experiment included two rice varieties, IR5 and IR8, and 11 weed control treatments arranged in a quadruplicate, randomized, split-plot design with varieties as the main plots and weed control treatments as the sub-plots. It was managed in the same way as the second preliminary experiment, except that only 4 kg/ha of soaked *E. crusgalli* seeds were sown and soil-incorporated at 5 DBS and the water levels were adjusted to 2 to 3 cm before the 4-DBS treatments and allowed to subside to soil saturation before seeding. The plots receiving propanil (EC) were drained before the application and reflooded the next day, but all other plots were undrained. Although the site was fertilized with only 60 kg/ha N, most of the IR5 plots lodged before harvest and gave very poor yields; hence, only IR8 yield data are reported here (Table 49).

A very dense infestation of *Echinochloa crus-*

galli resulted, probably because of the care taken to insure good weed stands among the plots and the long interval between weed-seeding and the initiation of continuous water-level management. Consequently, all plots of this experiment were weedy, and only those that received the most effective treatments were relatively weed-free until harvest time. This weediness may explain the rather low grain yields obtained even with the best weed control treatments.

Dichlobenil G, applied before sowing activated-charcoal-coated rice seeds, gave outstanding weed control and compared favorably with the standard molinate G to MCPA treatment. The rice plants appeared slightly retarded in the dichlobenil-treated plots for several weeks, which indicated that the rice plant was affected by this herbicide although it was protected by the charcoal during initial stand establishment. The rather severe toxicities of pyriclor and propanil EC caused the poor rice stands observed after applications of these chemicals. Both formulations of propanil were probably applied too early for best performance. As observed in the previous experiment, but not

before this experiment was initiated, nitrofen G gave very poor weed control when applied before seeding. Probably, it had dissipated to sublethal amounts by the time the weed seeds germinated, which may account for its low toxicity as well.

Still another direct-seeded experiment was initiated in the middle of the 1968 wet season to evaluate promising combinations of molinate or C-6989 with bromoxynil, 2,4-D or MCPA and to investigate further activated-charcoal protection of rice seeds. The experiment included 11 post-seeding treatments and 7 pre-emergence herbicide formulations. Pre-germinated IR5 rice seeds were remoistened and coated with as much powdered activated charcoal as would adhere (ca. 20 g per 100 g of seeds) and then sown into the pretreated plots of three replicate blocks. Uncoated seeds were sown at 100 kg/ha into corresponding plots of the fourth replication to evaluate the toxicities of these treatments to unprotected seeds. As in previous experiments, soaked *E. crusgalli* seeds were sown and incorporated into the soil at 4 DBS, and the water level was such that all herbicide applications were made into 2 to 3 cm of

Table 49. Performance of selected weed-control treatments in broadcast-seeded flooded IR8. IRR1, 1968 wet season.

Weed-control treatment*	Treatment		Rating at 40 DAS		Grain yield by rank (kg/ha)	Statistical significance** (5% level)
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time	Weed control (1-10)	Rice stand (10-1)		
1. Dichlobenil (2.5% G)†	1.5	4 DBS	7	6	4009	
2. Molinate (5% G)	3.0	9 DAS	7	7	3782	
3. Propanil (10% G)	3.0	9 DAS	3	6	3226	
4. Propanil (360 g/l EC)	3.0	9 DAS	6	4	3184	
5. Propanil (10% G)	6.0	9 DAS	4	6	3155	
6. Nitrofen (8% limestone G)	2.0	4 DBS	2	6	3145	
7. Molinate/bromoxynil (720/240 g/l EC)	2.0/0.25	9 DAS	6	7	3001	
8. Portable power-weeder fb 1 handweeding	—	20 DAS 35 DAS	6	9	2938	
9. Pyriclor (180 g/l WSL)	0.05	3 DAS	2	4	2842	
10. Nitrofen (8% limestone G)	4.0	4 DAS	2	6	2823	
11. Untreated control	—	—	1	8	2456	
12. Pyriclor (180 g/l WSL)	0.1	3 DAS	3	4	2236	

* All treatments except numbers 7, 8 and 11 included MCPA-K (WSL) applied at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. for post-emergence (20 DAS) control of surviving sedges and broadleaved weeds.

** Any two grain yield means opposite the same line were not significantly different at the 5% level.

† Pre-germinated rice seeds were coated with activated charcoal before broadcasting into dichlobenil-treated plots.

standing water and rice seeds were sown into water-saturated soil.

Figure 25 shows at 13 and 68 DAS the plots treated 3 DAS with EPTC/MCPA (G) at 1.75/0.7 kg/ha a.i. in which activated-charcoal coatings protected the rice in the background plot while uncoated rice in the foreground plot was killed. The charcoal-coated rice survived and made good stands in all other plots pre-treated with EPTC/MCPA (G) as well as with trifluralin/MCPA (G) at 0.7/0.4, nitrofen (G) + MCPA-AE (G) at 2 + 0.5, CNP (GD) + 2,4-D-EE (G) at 2 + 0.5, EL-119 (G) + MCPA-EE (G) at 0.5 + 0.5, PCP/MCPA-AE (G) at 5.6/0.5, and 2,4-D-IPE (G) at 1 kg/ha a.i., respectively. Uncoated rice was completely killed by all chemicals except the applications of nitrofen + MCPA and PCP/MCPA. Very good weed control was also given by all 3-DBS treatments except in the plots where uncoated rice failed to make good stands. Weeds invaded the vacant spaces in those plots within 3 to 4 weeks after application.

One disadvantage of the charcoal coating is that the method requires rather precise land-leveling and water-level management. If the charcoal-coated seedlings are submerged too soon, or if they are sown into areas with standing water, they may be killed by certain chemicals which persist in solution and affect young rice shoots which emerge through the charcoal layer. Vertically leachable herbicides may also affect the roots of rice as they penetrate below the soil surface. Further studies will involve the use of adhesives for the charcoal coatings and other means (e.g., pelleting) of overcoming these problems.

The survival of uncoated rice and the good algae and weed control observed after the PCP/MCPA treatment suggest its use as a dual-purpose pre-planting herbicide for direct-seeded rice.

Figure 26 shows the performances of molinate/bromoxynil (EC) and C-6989/bromoxynil (EC) mixtures applied 8 DAS at 1.5/0.25 and 2/0.25 kg/ha a.i., respectively. These combinations did not injure the rice plant and they gave substantially complete control of annual weeds. At higher rates of molinate or C-6989 these mixtures were safe, but they did not give any better control. Excellent weed control was also given by molinate/2,4-D-IPE (EC) and C-6989/2,4-D-IPE (EC) mixtures applied 8 DAS at 1.5/0.5 and 2/0.5 kg/ha

a.i., respectively, but these combinations caused some transient leaf-rolling symptoms of 2,4-D injury to the rice plant. Other selective and effective applications at 8 DAS were molinate (G) + MCPA-EE (G) at 1.5 + 0.5 kg/ha a.i. (but not at 2.5 + 0.5 kg/ha a.i. which injured the rice plant) and propanil (G) + MCPA-EE (G) at 2 + 0.5 kg/ha a.i. Most of these early post-emergence treatments were less toxic to the rice plant and gave better weed control than the standard treatment of propanil (EC) at 3 kg/ha a.i. (15 DAS) fb MCPA-K (WSL) at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. (20 DAS).

Herbicide evaluation in drill-seeded nonflooded rice

Direct-seeded, nonflooded (upland-rainfed) rice culture has weed problems similar to those of direct-seeded, flooded rice culture - difficulties in weed control by either mechanical or chemical methods - but under fertile, nonflooded conditions there are more kinds of weeds and with greater population densities than under flooded conditions. Nonflooded rice also commonly becomes infested with perennial weeds (e.g., *Cyperus rotundus* and *Paspalum dilatatum*) which are more difficult to control than the annual weeds found in flooded rice. Consequently, weed-caused yield losses up to 100% (too weedy to harvest) can easily occur under nonflooded conditions. Flooding alone controls many kinds of weeds and therefore weed losses are usually not as high under flooded as under nonflooded conditions.

When climatic conditions were good and weeds were controlled, nonflooded improved rice varieties yielded more than 6,000 kg/ha with good management (1967 Annual Report). If weeds can be controlled efficiently, the possibilities of such high yields and the opportunities for mechanization make nonflooded rice much more attractive than thought previously in areas where rainfall patterns and other conditions are favorable. Among the various chemical weed control methods that have been tested previously (1964-1967 Annual Reports), the use of selective pre- and post-emergence herbicides in drill-seeded, nonflooded rice may be most practical. Pre-emergence herbicides are likely to be more selective than post-emergence ones in drill-seeded rice because the seeds are placed below the treated soil surface. Moreover, they can be applied with a

Fig. 25. Appearance of plots 16 (top) and 71 (bottom) days after applications of EPTC/MCPA (G) at 1.75/0.7 kg/ha a.i. 3 days before broadcasting IR5 seeds coated with activated charcoal (background plot) and uncoated seeds (foreground). The charcoal coatings protected the rice from injury by this and 9 other pre-emergence herbicides applied 3 or 4 days before seeding. Weeds invaded the vacant spaces where uncoated rice seeds failed to grow, while good weed control was maintained in the stands made by charcoal-protected seeds. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

spray boom mounted behind the seed drill to save time and operation costs. Post-emergence selective herbicides such as propanil, 2,4-D, and MCPA (the only ones now commercially available for non-flooded rice) would be safer and more effective than direct applications of contact herbicides.

A preliminary experiment was conducted to evaluate 37 herbicides in drill-seeded IR5 rice under nonflooded conditions. Most of these herbicides were new and experimental with little information available about them, so each was applied at five different rates and at two times, pre-emergence at 4 DAS (3-4 days before rice emergence) and post-emergence at 14 DAS, to obtain data on their best rates and times of application.

A special Half-Dose Sprayer (Fig. 27) was built to enable each herbicide to be applied rapidly at 5 successively decreasing half-dose rates to adjacent 1 x 3 m subplots within duplicate 3 x 6 m main plots. Measured amounts of herbicide and water carrier were placed in the spraytank (a liter stainless-steel jar with a 240-ml plastic baby-bottle liner) and, after the first swath was applied using only 120 ml of spray, the tank was opened and 120 ml of water was added so that the next swath was applied at half the concentration of the preceding one and so on until five applications at 4, 2, 1, 0.5, and 0.25 kg/ha a.i. of herbicide, respectively, had each been made at the same spray volume of 333 liter/ha. This procedure took about a minute per subplot, and some main plots were sprayed at five rates in less than 4 minutes. The hand-held sprayer (Fig. 27) has since been

Fig. 26. Appearance of plots of flooded IR5 rice 8 weeks after molinate/bromoxynil (top) and C-6989/bromoxynil (bottom) were applied at 1.5/0.25 and 2/0.25 kg/ha a.i., respectively, 8 days after broadcast-seeding. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

mounted on a nylon-wheel bracket suspended from a 3.5-m traverse-curtain channel ("Monorail Half-Dose Sprayer"), so that the tank and nozzle system can be moved across the plots more accurately without an operator having to walk in them or to use a wooden grid as a guide. The half-dose sprayer gives distinctly different application rates among the adjacent subplots which makes it easier to evaluate herbicide performance than in plots treated by a logarithmic sprayer, which gives continuously variable rates of application from start to finish in each plot.

Visual ratings of the selectivity and performance of the herbicides were made 22 days after the pre-emergence and 12 days after the post-emergence applications. On the basis of these observations, the following herbicides were selected for further evaluation:

Herbicide	Selective range kg/ha a.i.	Control spectrum
Pre-emergence		
AC-72141 (EC)	1 - 3	B>G*
CP-53619 (EC)	2 - 4	B>G
Linuron (WP)	1 - 2	G (only)
M & B - 13992 (WP)	1 - 2	G>B
NC-5024 (EC)	1 - 2	G - B
OCS-21693 (EC)	8 ± 2 (?)	G (only)
OCS-21799 (WSP)	0.5 - 2	G = B
Prometryne (WP)	2 - 4	G>B
VCS-438 (EC)	1 - 2	B>G
Post-emergence		
Bromoxynil (EC)	0.25 - 0.5	B>G
C-6989 (EC)	2 - 4	G - B
Ioxynil (WSL)	0.5 - 1	B>G
M&B-13992 (WP)	2 - 4	G>B
M&B-14255 (WP)	0.5 - 1	G = B
OCS 21799 (WSP)	1 - 2	B>G
Propanil/CHCH (EC)	2 - 4	G = B
Phenmediphan	1 - 2	B>G
Swep (WP)	2 - 4	G = B
VCS 438 (EC)	0.5 - 1	B>G

* B=annual broadleaved weeds; G = annual grasses.

Shortly after the preliminary test was initiated, an "advanced" herbicide-evaluation experiment was begun in an adjacent nonflooded field to obtain further information on sprayable formulations of DCPA, EPTC/MCPA, nitralin, pyriclor, propachlor, and trifluralin/MCPA, which were previously found promising at the Institute. The new accession OCS-21693 was also included. All were compared at the best estimated rates and times of application with an untreated control and

Fig. 27. A post-emergence herbicide application being made to a 3 x 6 m plot of drill-seeded upland rainfed rice (IR5) at succeeding half-dosages with the IRRI Half-dose Sprayer. The wooden grid was used as a guide for the adjacent applications at decreasing rates to the 1 x 3 m subplots. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

the standard treatments of two hand-weedings and propanil-fb-MCPA herbicide applications. The improved varieties IR5 and IR8, Milfor-6(2), and the tall upland variety Palawan were chosen to determine the effect of the herbicides on these representative plant types. The varieties were drill-seeded at 100 kg/ha in 30-cm rows on the day after final rotovation. Rainfall during the first month after seeding (June 14 to July 14) was adequate for good emergence (7-8 DAS) and initial crop growth, but was inadequate during the critical stages in the development of this crop. Since the resulting yields were poor and unreliable as indicators of herbicide performance, only visual ratings of herbicide selectivity and weed weights are reported.

Acceptable rice injury ratings (7 or higher) and weed weights (less than 100 g/sq m of any two kinds) were given only by pre-emergence applications of nitralin at 2 kg/ha a.i. fb MCPA-K at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. 27 DAS, handweeding at 15 and 35 DAS, and the standard post-emergence propanil fb MCPA-K applications (Table 50). Fair-to-good early annual grass control with good selectivity was obtained by applications 4-DAS of OCS-21693 at 5.6, DCPA at 7, and propachlor at 3 kg/ha a.i., respectively, but plots receiving these treatments had high populations of *Ipomea triloba* and other broadleaved weeds before the MCPA-K applications killed them. The high grass-weed weights after these treatments reflect the low com-

Table 50. Selectivity and performance of promising herbicides in four drill-seeded rice varieties (IR8, IR5, Palawan and Milfor-6(2)) under upland rainfed conditions. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Herbicide or treatment (by arbitrary rank)	Treatment		Rice injury rating*				Weed weights** among varieties		
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAS)	IR8	IR5	Palawan	Milfor	(G)	(B)	(S)
1. Nitralin (75% WP)	2.0	4	8	8	8	7	17	4	128
fb MCPA-K (480 g/1 WSL)	0.8	27							
2. Handweeded	—	15	8	7	7	7	29	8	9
fb same	—	35							
3. Propanil (360 g/1 EC)	3.0	12	7	7	5	7	51	4	40
fb MCPA-K	0.8	27							
4. OCS-21693 (120 g/1 EC)	5.6	4	8	8	8	8	138	1	85
fb MCPA-K	0.8	35							
5. DCPA (75% WP)	7.0	4	8	8	7	7	159	1	109
fb MCPA-K	0.8	27							
6. Propachlor (65% WO)	3.0	4	8	7	7	7	202	1	26
fb MCPA-K	0.8	27							
Untreated control	—	—	8	8	8	8	204	75	117

* Visual estimates of rice injury made at 33 DAS on a scale of 10 (no injury) to 1 (complete kill). Values 7 or higher are acceptable.

** Mean dry weights (g/sq m) of grasses (G), broadleaved weeds (B) and sedges (S) sampled 88 DAS.

petition offered by the grasses. The main annual grasses were *Echinochloa colonum*, *Eleusine indica*, *Digitaria* sp. and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, with scattered infestations of the perennial *Paspalum dilatatum*. There was no evidence of *P. dilatatum* control by any treatment. The perennial sedge *Cyperus rotundus*, which accounted for the high sedge weights in most plots, was controlled by two handweedings and by the applications of pyriclor 12-DAS at 0.1 and 0.2 kg/ha a.i.

The post-emergence applications of pyriclor were highly toxic to all rice varieties, and only IR8 survived pyriclor when applied at the pre-emergence stage at 0.4 kg/ha a.i. As shown in Table 50, Milfor-6 (2) and Palawan were generally more susceptible to herbicide injury than IR8 and IR5. An important exception was the severe solvent injury to Palawan by the propanil application, which suggests the cautious need for use of this herbicide on tall, leafy, upland varieties. The order of susceptibility to the various herbicides illustrates yet another advantage of the improved rice varieties - that of resistance to injury by otherwise useful herbicides.

Two additional experiments were conducted in adjacent nonflooded fields in which IR5 rice was drill-seeded on July 16 at 100 kg/ha in 30-cm

rows. These fields received 30 kg/ha N as ammonium sulfate during maximum tillering and again at panicle initiation, giving a total of 60 kg/ha N. Standard procedures of insect control by granular diazinon, gamma-BHC, and methyl parathion applications at appropriate rates and times were followed. Promising pre-emergence herbicides were evaluated at selected rates at three different application times (2, 4 and 6 DAS) in one experiment, and the same procedure was followed for promising post-emergence herbicides and herbicide-mixture, but at different application times (14, 21, and 28 DAS). The rice emerged between 5 and 6 DAS, so the 6-DAS applications were actually at rice-emergence time, though mainly pre-emergence to the weeds. Each experiment was conducted in a randomized complete block design with treatments applied to quadruplicate (pre-emergence) or triplicate (post-emergence) 3 x 6 m plots.

Since inadequate rainfall limited the grain yields, only performance ratings and weed weights are reported for the pre-emergence herbicide evaluation experiment (Table 51). The yields of the other experiments were also poor, but since they were somewhat better correlated with weed-control data, they are included, only as indications

Table 51. Selectivity and performance of pre-emergence herbicides applied at different times after drill-seeding upland rainfed IR5. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Herbicide (by arbitrary rank)	Application		Visual ratings* at 47 DAS				Weed weight** (g/sq m)
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAS)	(R)	(G)	(B)	(S)	
1. Handweeded twice	—	15 & 35	10	7	8	7	91
2. CP-53619 (480 g/1 EC)	3.0	4	10	7	9	9	192
3. CP-53619	3.0	2	10	7	7	8	302
4. Prometryne (50% WP)	4.0	2	8	7	9	8	324
5. CP-53619	3.0	6	9	6	8	8	154
6. OCS-21693 (240 g/1 EC)	6.0	6	10	8	4	7	143
7. DCPA (75% WP)	8.0	4	10	7	5	8	173
8. DCPA	8.0	2	10	7	5	7	304
9. OCS-21693	6.0	2	10	7	4	7	246
10. M&B-14255 (50% WP)	3.0	4	10	5	8	6	260
11. M&B-14255	3.0	6	10	4	9	8	324
12. OCS-21693	6.0	4	9	6	5	7	214
13. AC-72141 (240 g/1 EC)	3.0	2	9	4	8	7	386
14. Propachlor (65% WP)	3.0	2	9	4	6	8	261
15. M&B-14255	3.0	2	9	3	7	6	264
16. OCS-21799 (80% WSP)	1.5	4	9	3	7	6	321
17. Nitralin (75% WP)	3.0	4	7	6	4	8	434
18. DCPA	8.0	6	8	5	4	8	311
19. NC-5024 (200 g/1 EC)	1.0	4	7	3	8	7	521
20. Nitralin	3.0	2	6	6	6	8	432
21. Untreated control	—	—	9	3	4	3	427

*Estimates of rice stand (R), on a scale of 10 (very good) to 1 (very poor), and weed control with respect to grasses (G), broadleaved weeds (B) and sedges (S), on a scale of 1 (no control) to 10 (complete control).

** Sampled at the heading time of the grassy weeds (47 DAS).

of post-emergence herbicide performance (Table 52).

The most outstanding new pre-emergence herbicide was 2-chloro-2', 6' -diethyl-N-(butoxy-methyl)-acetanilide (CP 53619). This analog of propachlor gave good annual grass, broadleaved weed, and sedge control after single applications 2, 4, or 6 DAS at 3 kg/ha a.i. with apparently greater safety to rice than propachlor. Prometryne may not be as versatile in nonflooded rice as other herbicides, because at later times of application and at rates higher than 4 kg/ha a.i. it injured the rice. Methyl-2,3,5,6-tetrachloro-N-methoxy-N-methylterephthalamate (OCS 21693) gave slightly better grass control at 6 kg/ha a.i. than did its analog DCPA at 8 kg/ha a.i. and showed similar selectivity and lack of broadleaved weed control. The selective broadleaved-weed killers AC-72141,

M&B-14255, and OCS-21799, although more costly than 2,4-D or MCPA, may be mixed with pre-emergence grass killers like DCPA or OCS-21693 to widen their weed-control spectra. M&B-14255 was inadvertently used at pre-emergence rather than at post-emergence, and vice versa for M&B-13992, which may account for their poor performance.

The selectivity, weed-control, and grain yield data in Table 52 show that mixtures of propanil with bromoxynil or ioxynil are highly promising as one-application post-emergence herbicides at either 8 or 15 days after rice emergence (14-21 DAS). These mixtures caused transient solvent-injury symptoms typical of propanil applications, but the injuries did not appear to affect subsequent rice growth. The lower amount of propanil (2 kg/ha a.i.) is likely to make these treatments less

costly than the standard post-emergence applications of propanil at 3 kg/ha a.i. fb MCPA or 2,4-D, at 0.8 kg/ha a.i. Bromoxynil and ioxynil are not yet available in Asia, but if not too costly they should be useful for early sedge and broadleaved weed control in direct-seeded flooded and non-flooded rice in lieu of the more hazardous chlorophenoxy acid herbicides.

The good performance of the 28-DAS treatments was unexpected since it rained immediately after these applications. The propanil/ 2,4-D ester mixtures were included to determine whether or not they could be combined safely as one-application treatments, but the rainfall prevented a reliable evaluation of their effects.

Propanil/CHCH applied either 14 or 21 DAS at 3 kg/ha a.i. with respect to propanil gave significantly higher grain yields than the two other propanil formulations at equivalent rates. Temperature and sunlight intensity after application were not high enough to cause the solvent injuries often seen after propanil applications, hence, it was impossible to compare the injurious effects of these different formulations.

The sugar-beet herbicide 3-methoxycarbonylaminophenyl-N-(3'-methylphenyl) carbamate (phenmedipham) gave good total weed control when applied alone at 1.5 kg/ha a.i. This new accession deserves further evaluation because of the low rate at which it was effective and its early

Table 52. Performance of post-emergence herbicide formulations applied at different times after drill-seeding upland rainfed IR5. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Herbicide formulation	Application		Visual ratings* at 37 DAS				Grain yield** by rank (kg/ha)	Statistical significance†
	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Time (DAS)	(R)	(G)	(B)	(S)		
1. Propanil/bromoxynil (360/240 g/1 EC)	2.0/0.25	21	8	9	9	9	3644	
2. Propanil/ioxynil (360/240 g/1 EC)	2.0/0.5	21	9	8	8	8	3565	
3. Propanil/2,4-D-BEE (360/480 g/1 EC)	3.0/1.0	28	8	8	8	8	3013	
4. Propanil/bromoxynil	2.0/0.25	14	9	8	8	8	2948	
5. Propanil/ioxynil	2.0/0.5	14	9	9	9	9	2910	
6. Handweeded twice	—	15 & 35	10	7	8	7	2798	
7. Propanil/CHCH (350/175 g/1 EC)	3.0/1.5	21	7	6	9	7	2568	
8. Phemedipham (162 g/1 EC)	1.5	14	8	7	9	7	2565	
9. Propanil/CHCH	3.0/1.5	14	9	8	9	8	2561	
10. Propanil/bromoxynil	2.0/0.25	28	8	8	8	8	2488	
11. Propanil (360 g/1 EC)	3.0	21	10	10	10	9	2379	
12. Propanil (480 g/1 EC)	3.0	21	9	10	10	9	2297	
13. Swep (80% WP)	3.0	21	8	9	10	9	2260	
14. Propanil/2,4-D-IPE (360/400 g/1 EC)	3.0/1.0	28	8	7	7	7	2206	
15. Propanil/2,4-D-OPDA (360/480 g/1 EC)	3.0/1.0	28	8	6	7	7	2106	
16. Propanil/ioxynil	2.0/0.5	28	8	8	8	8	2041	
17. MCPA-K (480 g/1 WSL)	0.8	14	8	4	7	7	2033	
18. Propanil (360 g/1 EC)	3.0	28	7	7	7	2	1985	
19. Sesone (90% WSP)	4.0	14	8	9	6	7	1976	
20. M&B-13992 (50% WP)	2.0	14	8	9	10	7	1946	
21. Untreated control	—	—	8	1	1	1	1194	

*Estimates of rice injury (R), on a scale of 10 (no injury) to 1 (complete kill), and weed control with respect to grasses (G), broadleaved weeds (B) and sedges (S), on a scale of 1 (no control) to 10 (complete control).

** Based on weight at 14% moisture.

† Any two grain yield means opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level.

post-emergence selectivity. The acceptable performance of swep in this experiment suggests its usefulness in nonflooded rice since it is available again from Japan and the United States. Grain yields after applications of C-6989 at 3 kg/ha a.i. were not sufficient to place it among the 20 best treatments, but its selectivity and weed control at 14 or 21 DAS were good. C-6989 gave partial post-emergence control of *Cyperus rotundus* in non-flooded rice and of the perennial *Scirpus maritimus* in flooded direct-seeded rice, and these important effects deserve further investigation.

Effect of Water Management Practices on the Growth Characteristics and Grain Yield of Rice

In many parts of tropical Asia, rice plants suffer from either too much or too little water because of irregular rainfall and poor management of available water. Good water management includes the control of water for optimum crop yield and makes the best use of limited supplies. It makes irrigation possible during the dry season, when yields are generally high due to high solar radiation, thereby increasing annual rice production and allowing crop diversification.

To study the relative effects of various water management practices on the growth and yield of IR8, field experiments on Maahas clay soil were continued during the 1968 crop season at the Institute. The water management practices tested in 1968 differed from those reported earlier (1966 and 1967 Annual Reports).

Dry season

The water management treatments used during 1968 dry season are as follows:

1) Deep continuous flooding (DCF): 15 cm of water were maintained in the plots from 4 days after transplanting to the late dough stage.

2) Deep continuous flooding + drainage at maximum tillering (DCF + DMT): 15 cm of water were maintained in the paddies from 4 days after transplanting, drained for 8 days at maximum tillering, and reflooded until the late dough stage.

3) Deep continuous flooding + drainage at maximum tillering + drainage at panicle initiation (DCF + DMT + DPI): treatment (2) was followed

with an additional drainage period of 8 days extending to the period of panicle initiation.

4) Intermediate continuous flooding (ICF): 7.5 cm of water were maintained in the plots from 4 days after transplanting to the late dough stage.

5) Intermediate continuous flooding + continuous soil saturation (ICF + CSS): 7.5 cm of water were maintained in the plots up to the end of maximum tillering; thereafter, the water level was lowered to soil saturation until the late dough stage.

6) Shallow continuous flooding (SCF): 2.5 cm of water were maintained in the paddies until the late dough stage.

7) Continuous soil saturation + flooding at panicle initiation (CSS + F): the paddies were maintained at soil saturation until panicle initiation at which time the water level was raised to 7.5 cm and maintained until the late dough stage.

8) Continuous soil saturation (CSS): 1 cm of water was kept in the paddies until the late dough stage.

In this season the treatments were tested under naturally drained conditions and in tanks with bottoms.

As observed in the previous year's experiment, higher depths of standing water promoted plant height.

Deep standing water caused a reduction in the tiller number, but the degree of reduction of unproductive tillers was less in plants in deep water than in those in shallower water.

The grain yields from the treatments in plots without bottoms indicate that there were no significant differences among ICF, SCF, ICF + CSS, CSS + F, DCF + DMT, and CSS (Table 53). Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) gave yields comparable to the above treatments, except intermediate flooding (7.5 cm) which gave a higher yield. Draining the deep-flooded plots at the maximum tillering stage resulted in only a slight nonsignificant increase in grain yield over the continuously deep-flooded plots. Paddies drained for 8 days during panicle initiation yielded over 1 ton of rough rice less than the shallow-flooded plots and the plots under 7.5 cm of water. The percentage of unfilled grains was highest in the plots drained during panicle initiation.

The grain yields from the treatments in plots with bottoms (Table 54) showed the same trend as

Table 53. Effect of water management practices on the grain yield and efficiency of water use for IR8. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Water management treatment	Plots with drainage			Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical analysis (5% level)
	Total water use, 91 days (mm)	Index (%)	Efficiency (g/liter)		
1. Intermediate continuous flooding (ICF) (7.5 cm)	850	60	1.14	9720	
2. Shallow continuous flooding (SCF) (2.5 cm)	805	57	1.19	9548	
3. Intermediate continuous flooding + continuous soil saturation (ICF + CSS) (7.5 cm + 1.0 cm)	800	56	1.17	9385	
4. Continuous soil saturation + flooding at panicle initiation (CSS + F) (1.0 cm + 7.5 cm)	780	55	1.17	9142	
5. Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering (DCF + DMT)	1344	95	0.68	9123	
6. Continuous soil saturation (CSS) (1.0 cm)	647	46	1.39	9025	
7. Deep continuous flooding (DCF) (15 cm)	1418	100	0.63	8964	
8. Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering + drainage at p.i. (DCF + DMT + DPI)	1240	87	0.69	8538	
Evaporation	- 378 mm (91 days)	Crop duration (days):	126		
Evapotranspiration	- 589 mm (91 days)	Irrigation started:	28 January 1968		
Rainfall	- 29.5 mm (91 days)	Irrigation stopped:	27 April, 1968 (91 days)		

Means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level. CV(X) = 3.4%

those in plots without bottoms, except for the treatment in which water was drained at panicle initiation, which did not show a significant yield reduction. This similarity may be attributed to the fact that although the plots were surface-drained, there was enough water inside the tanks to satisfy the requirements of the plants before the plots were reflooded. The loss in grain yield in plots with water-saturated soil was attributed to weed competition (Fig. 28).

With deep-flooded treatments (15 cm), the plants flowered and the grains ripened earlier than with treatments using shallower depths of standing water. The plants subjected to 15 cm of water flowered at 93 to 94 days after seeding, while those subjected to lower water depths (i.e., 7.5 to 1.0 cm) flowered at 98 to 99 days after seeding.

The data on total water use and efficiency from the tanks without bottoms (Table 53) under various water management treatments were highly variable probably because of water losses through causes other than evapotranspiration, such as percolation.

The water use and efficiency data collected from the tanks with bottoms however were more reliable.

The amounts of water lost by evapotranspiration in the tanks with bottoms under the three continuous flooding conditions – DCF (15.0 cm), ICF (7.5 cm), and SCF (2.5 cm) – were almost identical, thus indicating that evapotranspiration losses appear to be equal regardless of the depth of continuous standing water in the paddies. In a water-saturated soil, the water losses were greater, due to higher soil temperatures at the soil surface. In the tanks with bottoms, the efficiency of water use was higher in plots with deeper standing water than in those where the soil was only saturated, with no standing water.

Environmental factors and water losses. Solar radiation and temperature readings from the nearby (about 180 meters away) meteorological station were correlated with evapotranspiration and evaporation losses in the experimental field. The data indicate that solar radiation and temperature are correlated with evapotranspiration (ET)

Fig. 28. Effect of depths of water on weed population in rice field at 28 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

and evaporation (E) losses (Fig. 29). The average of 10-day readings of solar radiation showed a significant correlation with evapotranspiration ($r = 0.81^{**}$) and evaporation ($r = 0.78^*$). Temperature readings ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) also showed a significant correlation with evapotranspiration ($r = 0.91^{**}$) and evaporation ($r = 0.70^*$).

Mean atmospheric humidity observations at 10-day intervals showed a negative relationship with evapotranspiration ($r = 0.67^*$) and evaporation ($r = 0.70^*$). When the humidity was low, evapotranspiration and evaporation losses were high (data not presented here).

Environmental factors directly affecting evaporation and evapotranspiration losses were solar radiation, atmospheric temperature, and humidity.

One of the effects of deep, continuous flooding in paddies is the suppression of weeds. Figure 28 shows the more common types of weeds and the effect of water depth on their populations. Under continuous soil saturation and shallow continuous

flooding (2.5 cm), sedges predominate over broad-leaved weeds and grasses. From 7.5 to 15 cm of standing water, grasses and sedges seem to be almost entirely suppressed, although at a water depth of 7.5 cm, some broadleaves and sedges are still visible. These findings indicate that weeds are a major factor contributing to low yields when the soil is saturated but no flooding is practiced.

Supplementary experiment. Four of the treatments discussed earlier were tested in larger areas in an adjacent experiment, using two varieties, IR8 and H-4. These treatments were:

- 1) Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) (DCF).
- 2) Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering (DCF + DMT + F).
- 3) Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering + drainage at panicle initiation (DF + DMT + DPI).
- 4) Shallow continuous flooding (2.5 cm) (SCF).

The effect of these water management practices on the yields of these two varieties is shown in Table 55. There were no over-all significant yield differences among treatments, but their effects on the varieties were statistically significant (1%). The practice of draining the plot during the first week of panicle initiation slightly reduced the yield of IR8 (400-600 kg/ha), but the reduction of the yield of H-4 was higher (278-1,381 kg/ha), although this variety yielded less than IR8. All H-4 plots lodged before harvest.

Evapotranspiration and evaporation ratio. The ratios of the evapotranspiration:evaporation values during these experiments were determined as follows:

$$1966 \text{ wet season} = \frac{\text{Evapotranspiration } 396}{\text{Evaporation } 308} = 1.29$$

$$1967 \text{ dry season} = \frac{\text{Evapotranspiration } 441}{\text{Evaporation } 285} = 1.55$$

$$1968 \text{ dry season} = \frac{\text{Evapotranspiration } 589}{\text{Evaporation } 378} = 1.56$$

These ratios clearly indicate that the evapotranspiration : evaporation ratio during the dry seasons appears to be consistent and higher than that during the rainy, cloudy season.

The results of the 1968 dry season experiments are summarized as follows:

Table 54. Effect of water management practices on the grain yield and efficiency of water use for IR8. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Water management treatment	Plots without drainage			Statistical analysis (5% level) **
	Total water use, 91 days* (mm)	Index (%)	Efficiency (g/liter)	
1. Intermediate continuous flooding (ICF) (7.5 cm)	602	100	1.89	1498
2. Deep continuous flooding (DCF) (15 cm)	605	100	1.79	1411
3. Shallow continuous flooding (SCF) (2.5 cm)	607	100	1.77	1401
4. Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering (DCF + DMT)	585	97	1.82	1384
5. Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering + drainage at p.i. (DCF+DMT+DPI)	549	91	1.94	1384
6. Intermediate continuous flooding + continuous soil saturation (iCF + CSS) (7.5 cm + 1.0 cm)	649	107	1.59	1345
7. Continuous soil saturation + flooding at panicle initiation (CSS + F) (1.0 cm + 7.5 cm)	595	98	1.68	1300
8. Continuous soil saturation (CSS) (1.0 cm)	639	106	1.42	1180

* Evapotranspiration only.

** Means falling opposite the same line are not significantly different at the 5% level. CV(X) = 7.5%

Evaporation	- 378 mm (91 days)
Rainfall	- 29.5 mm (91 days)
Crop duration (days)	- 126
Irrigation started	- 28 January 1968
Irrigation stopped	- 27 April 1968 (91 days)

1) Deep flooding slightly increased the height of IR8, but decreased the number of tillers. The reduction of non-productive tillers of plants under the deep-flooded treatment was smaller than that of plants subjected to low levels of irrigation water. Deep flooding decreased the grain yield of H-4 through lodging.

2) Plants under flowing irrigation and deep flooding flowered earlier, and the grains ripened earlier, than plants under low levels of water.

3) Draining the deep-flooded IR8 plots (in Maahas clay) for a week at maximum tillering did not significantly increase the grain yield. However, when the plots were drained for a week during panicle initiation, the yield was reduced by 13 percent.

4) Yields following weekly applications of 5 cm of water or intermittent drainage (in Maahas clay) were less than those with continuous flooding.

5) When the rice plants were subjected to mois-

ture stress from the tillering phase to the reproductive phase, there was a considerable (62%) grain yield decrease.

6) The efficiency of water use (grains per liter of water applied) was generally higher with shallow than with deep water. Shallow continuous flooding (2.5 cm) gave consistently better grain yield, good weed control, and a lower water loss. Moreover, fertilizers and herbicides may be applied under this condition without draining the irrigation water.

7) Weed growth and infestation varied with the depth of standing water. The predominant weeds in shallow flooded to deep flooded conditions were: sedges > broadleaves > grasses. Under deep flooded conditions (10-15 cm), grassy weeds were practically eliminated.

8) The water loss due to evapotranspiration appeared to be the same regardless of the depth of standing water. Other water losses, including percolation, varied with the depth of standing water.

Fig. 29. Relationship between temperature, evaporation, and evapotranspiration, and between solar radiation, evaporation, and evapotranspiration. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

9) The water lost due to evapotranspiration was higher in the dry season than in the wet season. The $\frac{ET}{E}$ ratios were higher (1.55 - 1.56) in the dry season than in the wet season (1.29).

Wet season

The water management treatments were the same as those in the 1968 dry-season experiment except in the deep continuous flooding treatment, where 16, instead of 15 cm, of water was maintained. Data on grain yield and water use were recorded (Tables 56 and 57).

The different water depths (1, 2.5, 7.5, and 16 cm) including mid-season drainage, did not significantly influence the grain yield of IR8 in the tanks without bottoms (Table 56). The total water use for the season (97 days), which included evapotranspiration, percolation, and other losses, was between 754 and 972 mm. Comparatively higher values of the total water use were recorded from

the tanks with 16 cm of water. A comparison of these data with the evapotranspiration data recorded from the same treatments in the tanks with bottoms indicates that the increased total water use under the 16-cm water depth in tanks without bottoms was mostly due to increased percolation and other losses. Water use efficiency was highest in the tanks which had 1-cm-deep water until panicle initiation and were then flooded with 7.5 cm of water until maturity (Table 56).

The grain yield of IR8 was significantly influenced by the water management treatments in the tanks with bottoms (Table 57). The tanks subjected to 1, 2.5, and 7.5 cm depths of water yielded significantly more grain per square meter than those which were subjected to a 16-cm depth of water. Since these tanks with bottoms had no natural drainage, soil conditions differed from

Table 55. Effect of water management practices on the grain yield of IR8 and H-4 under natural paddy conditions. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Water management practice	Grain yield (kg/ha)	
	IR8	H-4
1. Deep continuous flooding (DCF) (15 cm)	9430	6145
2. Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering (DCF + DMT)	9602	6512
3. Deep continuous flooding (15 cm) + drainage at maximum tillering + drainage at panicle initiation (DCF + DMT + DPI)	9001	5867
4. Shallow continuous flooding (2.5 cm) (SCF)	9406	7248

CV(X) = 19.3%

	IR8
DCF + DMT	9602
DCF	9430
SCF	9406
DCF + DMT + DPI	9001

	H-4
SCF	7248
DCF + DMT	6512
DCF	6145
DCF + DMT + DPI	5867

Statistical analysis (5%)

* Grain yield falling opposite the same line are not statistically significant at the 5% level.

Table 56. Effect of water management practices on the grain yield of IR8 and on water use efficiency. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Water management treatment	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Index (%)	Tanks without bottoms			Water use efficiency (g/liter)
			Statistical significance* (5%)	Total water use, 97 days (mm)	Index (%)	
DCF + DMT + F	6714	100		923	100	0.73
CSS + FAPI	6565	97		754	82	0.87
DCF	6489	96		972	105	0.67
ICF + CSS	6469	96		854	92	0.76
CSS	6381	95		791	86	0.81
ICF	6212	92		775	84	0.80
SCF	5993	89		796	86	0.75
DCF + DMT + DPI + F	5863	87		875	95	0.67

* Any two means falling opposite the same line are not statistically significant at the 5% level. CV(X) = 6%

Table 57. Effect of water management practices on the grain yield of IR8 and on water use efficiency. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Water management treatment	Grain yield (g/sq m)	Index (%)	Tanks with bottoms			Water use efficiency (g/liter)
			Statistical significance* (5%)	Total water use, 97 days (mm)	Index (%)	
ICF	624	100		459	100	1.36
ICF + CSS	610	98		469	102	1.30
SCF	599	96		430	94	1.39
CSS + FAPI	598	96		429	93	1.39
CSS	576	92		446	97	1.29
DCF + DMT + F	549	88		407	89	1.35
DCF	532	85		433	94	1.23
DCF + DMT + DPI + F	522	84		364	79	1.43

* Any two means falling opposite the same line are not statistically significant at the 5% level. CV(X) = 7%

those in the bottomless tanks.

The total water use (evapotranspiration) in tanks with bottoms did not vary greatly among water management treatments except for those which were drained completely and not flooded for 5 and 14 days (Table 57). The water use efficiency order in this procedure was highest in the tanks which were subjected to continuous mid-season drainage for 14 days starting at the maximum tillering stage.

Supplementary experiment. In addition to the two above experiments (tanks with and without bottoms), four selected treatments were included in a larger plot, simulating natural paddy conditions. IR8 and H-4, each representing a distinct plant type, were used as the test varieties. The treatments used were as follows:

1. Rainfed (RF)
2. Shallow continuous flooding (SCF - 2.5 cm)
3. Deep continuous flooding (DCF - 20 cm)

Table 58. Grain yield of IR8 and H-4 under different water management practices. IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Variety, treatment	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Statistical significance* (5%)
IR8		
RF	6025	
DCF	6008	
SAT - F.C.	6003	
SCF	5609	
H-4		
RF	4350	
SAT F.C.	4074	
SCF	2776	
DCF	2107	

* Any two means falling opposite the same line are not statistically significant at 5% level.

4. Saturation to field capacity

In the last treatment, the soil moisture during rainless days was not permitted to go below field capacity and during rainy days, water was not allowed to stand in the plots. Hence, the soil moisture content in these plots fluctuated between saturation and field capacity.

The effect of the interaction of water management treatments and varieties with grain yield was significant (Table 58). IR8 yielded significantly more grain per hectare than H-4 under all the water management treatments. Although the water management treatments did not significantly affect the grain yield of IR8, it influenced the grain yield of H-4. The later variety lodged earlier under shallow and deep, continuous flooding treatment, and hence yielded significantly less than when rainfed and when the soil water content was between saturation and field capacity.

Entomology

The warm and humid climate of tropical Asia is conducive to the proliferation of many insect species. Of these, the stem borers, leafhoppers, and planthoppers are particularly damaging.

The entomology research program at the Institute seeks the effective, economical, and long-lasting control of these pests. The primary objective is to develop immediate control measures by using insecticides and to investigate such other possibilities as varietal resistance, biological control, and the use of sex attractants and chemosterilants. It is hoped that these various aspects can be integrated to make for a more effective and long-lasting pest control.

About 50 newer insecticides were screened in laboratory and field experiments to determine their effectiveness in controlling common rice pests. The compounds S6626 and dursban were highly effective in controlling stem borers but not planthoppers. High rice yields have been obtained in plots treated with such insecticidal mixtures as dol-mix and γ -BHC + unden which combine stem borer and planthopper control. Foliar sprays of azodrin have been highly effective against brown planthoppers.

*Several crosses involving the variety TKM-6 have consistently shown good resistance against the striped borer, *Chilo suppressalis*. A promising selection, IR532E576, has been found resistant to borers and tolerant to green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers. Also it possesses some resistance to bacterial blight, bacterial streak, the tungro virus, and blast. The selection generally has the same yield performance as IR8 but possesses better quality grains.*

*Several varieties have been found to possess a very high level of resistance to the green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, and the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*. The effects of these varieties on the insects and the possible bases of insect resistance were investigated. When used in a hybridization program, these varieties have resulted in some progenies, now in the F_3 stage, which carry high resistance to both green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers and generally resemble IR8 in plant type. The level of resistance of these plants to the green planthoppers and brown planthoppers is so high that, except under epidemic infestations, the use of insecticides on these lines may not be necessary.*

Varietal Resistance to Rice Stem Borers

From a field screening of about 10,000 rice varieties for stem borer resistance and the retesting of the selected lines in greenhouse experiments, 30 varieties were selected as highly resistant to stem borers. However, several of these varieties were susceptible to other insect pests and diseases and were frequently heavily damaged in field experiments. An exception was TKM-6 which, besides being resistant to stem borers, was in repeated field experiments also found to be comparatively resistant to leafhoppers, planthoppers, bacterial leaf blight, and the tungro virus disease. In collaboration with the Institute's plant breeders, this variety was used in a hybridization program to

combine high yield potential with resistance to diseases and insects, particularly to stem borers. One such cross, IR532, involving TKM-6 and Peta₃ x Taichung (Native) 1, has resulted in selections that possess good plant types and are resistant to several insects and diseases. Under severe insect infestations, several of these selections outyielded IR8 by 30 to 50 percent (1967 Annual Report). In 1968, intensive studies were conducted on these selections and on another cross, TKM-6 x IR8, which has also shown some promise.

Further studies on IR532

Seeds from 1,792 IR532 plants selected from the F₅ population were planted in two-row plots in two replications. In one replication, these were

Table 1. Yield potentials and resistance of IR532 lines to the rice stem borer and the bacterial streak. IRRI, January to June, 1968.

Line	Flowering (days after seedling)	Stem borer damage		Bacterial streak *	Yield** (kg/ha)
		Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)		
IR532-E413-1168	91	3.84	3.24	MS†	10,732.50
IR532-E202-651	87	5.00	2.88	R	9,180.00
IR532-E164-582	89	2.85	3.96	R	9,022.50
IR532-E110-437	84	1.68	7.41	R	9,150.00
IR532-E369-1067	95	4.32	1.40	MR	9,157.50
IR532-E518-1506	82	2.50	3.48	S	9,027.50
IR532-E149-560	93	6.39	0.98	R	8,605.00
IR532-E208-675	89	2.88	0.56	MR	8,405.00
IR532-E66-276	95	4.86	2.76	R	8,675.00
IR532-E90-395	95	4.00	1.26	R	8,272.50
IR532-E303-927	95	4.83	3.04	S	8,515.00
IR532-E568-1638	91	3.95	0.95	MS	8,617.50
IR532-E257-780	95	9.46	1.12	MR	7,932.50
IR532-E576-1678	95	7.90	5.40	MR	7,585.00
IR8	91	12.60	3.39	MR	7,826.88
TKM-6	74	8.78	5.64	R	6,268.75
Taichung (Native) 1	89	7.99	5.60	MR	8,080.63
Rexoro	102	46.75	12.41	R	1,564.37

* Readings from seedling inoculation obtained by Plant Pathology and Entomology staff.

** Protected from insect infestations. Yield estimate based on 2-row plots only.

† MS - moderately susceptible, MR - moderately resistant, R - resistant, S - susceptible.

Table 2. Yield and stem borer resistance of IR532 lines. IRR1, July to December, 1968.

Line	Stem borer damage		Yield (kg/ha)	
	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Unprotected plots	Protected plots
IR532-E66-276	19.75	11.68	4,680.53	6,038.40
IR532-E86-366	18.72	7.37	4,564.80	6,062.40
IR532-E90-395	24.19	7.81	4,030.00	5,939.20
IR532-E110-437	11.46	7.23	4,345.60	6,049.60
IR532-E164-581	24.22	12.91	3,380.80	5,691.73
IR532-E202-651	19.87	7.49	4,282.13	5,960.00
IR532-E208-675	14.01	5.35	4,701.86	6,375.46
IR532-E239-748	26.93	7.58	4,347.20	6,172.26
IR532-E303-927	16.37	5.88	4,628.80	6,435.20
IR532-E309-944	16.70	5.40	4,789.86	6,348.80
IR532-E369-1069	17.43	6.45	4,617.06	6,724.27
IR532-E413-1168	16.50	4.60	4,636.60	6,398.93
IR532-E420-1183	24.76	4.28	4,060.80	6,404.26
IR532-E568-1634	24.96	10.55	4,125.86	6,494.86
IR532-E568-1638	24.44	9.26	4,451.73	6,175.46
IR532-E570-1648	27.34	9.91	4,214.93	6,907.20
IR532-E576-1678	15.82	8.78	4,602.13	5,934.40
IR8	20.74	8.48	3,910.40	6,477.87
Rexoro	50.59	13.69	349.86	2,033.25
TKM-6	13.82	4.03	3,015.46	3,141.33
Reta ₃ x T(N)1	22.67	4.55	4,349.06	6,317.86
Taichung (Native)1	32.21	3.32	2,490.66	4,981.33

exposed to natural insect infestation to evaluate their resistance to insects while in the other, they were protected from insect damage to record their yield potentials. In cooperation with the Institute's plant pathologists, observations were also made on the natural incidence of bacterial blight on these lines and on their resistance to bacterial streak by inoculating seedlings in the field. The performance of some of the selected lines is shown in Table 1. As is evident from this table, several selections had much lower dead heart and white head incidence, both of which are manifestations of borer damage, had resistance to bacterial streak, and produced high yields.

From the above experiment, 51 lines showing low dead heart, white head, and disease incidence and high yields were selected for further studies. These were each planted in 2 m x 5 m field plots

in six replications. Three of the replications were protected from insect damage by applying diazinon in the paddy water while the other three were exposed to natural insect infestation. IR8, Taichung (Native) 1, TKM-6, and Peta₃ x Taichung (Native) 1 were used as checks.

The incidence of stem borers during this experiment was high and 50 percent of the tillers of the susceptible check, Rexoro, showed dead heart damage. However, the dead heart incidence in most of the selections was low. In the protected plots, the grain yields of most of these lines were almost identical with that of IR8 but in the unprotected plots, most of them gave higher yields than IR8 (Table 2). Thus their higher yields over IR8 in the later treatment are attributable to their resistance to insects. The insect resistance of these selections is significant, because being a built-in

plant character, it is operative at all levels of insect infestation. Although the level of resistance of these selections is not sufficiently high to bring about stem borer control by itself, it can supplement the use of insecticides for better insect control.

Further studies on IR580 (TKM-6 x IR8)

During the dry season, 500 individual IR580 plant selections at the F₅ stage were tested in two-row plots. In one replication, these were exposed to natural insect infestation while in another, they were protected from insect pests by diazinon

Table 3. Yield potentials, insect and disease reactions of F₅ selections from IR580 (IR8 x TKM-6). IRRI December, 1967 to April, 1968.

Line	Stem borer damage			Planthopper*		Blight**	Yield† (kg/ha)
	Flowering (days after seeding)	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Population	Hopper burn		
IR580-478-421	83	3.50	1.00	1	0	3	11,267.12
IR580-470-375	83	3.50	0.32	1	0	2-3	10,014.80
IR580-462-328	83	2.16	1.40	2	2	2-3	10,139.20
IR580-460-315	83	2.00	0.68	1	3	3	10,283.44
IR580-448-201	105	2.30	1.80	1	0	-	10,195.44
IR580-453-263	86	3.24	1.98	0	0	3-4	9,762.72
IR580-439-112	94	3.55	nil	1	1	3	9,542.56
IR580-436-87	110	2.47	0.72	3	0	-	9,812.80
IR580-460-332	83	1.98	nil	3	1	3	9,516.88
IR580-470-372	83	3.50	0.80	3	1	3	9,560.72
IR580-470-376	86	4.38	2.94	1	0	3	9,658.96
IR8 (40)	86	4.79	1.03	2	0	3-4	9,130.83
Rexoro	102	9.08	8.33	1	0	-	6,742.40
TKM-6	74	2.86	1.18	1	0	3	6,249.60
Taichung (Native) 1	94	6.37	1.40	4	1	4-5	9,735.65

* Grading Scale population

1
2
3
4
5

No. of insects per hill (approx.)

<100
100-200
201-300
301-400
>400

hopper burn

0
1
2
3
4

Area of plot damaged

none
<¼
¼ - ½
½ - ¾
>¾ - 1

** Readings from flag leaf inoculation (cooperative data from the IRRI Varietal Improvement, Plant Pathology and Entomology Department.

† From plots partially protected with insecticide.

applied to the paddy water to record their yield potentials. The incidence of stem borers during the experiment was moderately high but most of the lines tested were much less affected than the susceptible checks (Table 3). The brown planthopper population was severe but several lines had low infestations and produced high yields. From these tests, 1,800 individual plants were selected for further studies. Consequently several lines were selected which possessed resistance to stem borers, tolerance to leafhoppers, resistance to bacterial blight, and good yield potentials (Table 4). The major drawback to this cross is that the grains of the selections had white belly. However, a few showed clear-textured grains.

Ovipositional preference of striped borer moths on resistant and susceptible rice varieties

A series of field experiments has revealed that stem borer-susceptible varieties such as Rexoro, Sapan Kwai, and CP231 x SL017 generally receive several times more egg masses of striped borer moths than the resistant variety TKM-6. Further studies were conducted in the laboratory to determine the consistency of preference or non-preference of these moths and to find out the causes for this difference. The most susceptible variety, Rexoro, and the most resistant variety, TKM-6, were used. One plant of each of these varieties was grown in a 6-inch-diameter clay pot. At 50 days after transplanting, the number of tillers was reduced such that each plant contained 20 leaves. Three clay pots with these plants were then caged in a 50 cm x 50 cm x 1 m screen cage containing 40 pairs of newly emerged striped borer moths. Seven days later, when most of the moths had died, the number of egg masses laid on each plant was recorded. Also, the egg masses were incubated at 29 C to determine the number of eggs in each of them when they had reached the blackhead stage.

Rexoro was found to have consistently received about 30 percent more egg masses than TKM-6. Also, the egg masses laid on Rexoro were generally larger than those laid on TKM-6. These differences in the number and size of egg masses when added meant that Rexoro had about 50 percent more eggs than TKM-6 (Table 5). Since both the resistant and susceptible plants contained the same

number of leaves which intermingled within the cage in these tests, it can be concluded that the moths definitely preferred Rexoro leaves for oviposition.

This preference for one variety over the other could be due to differences in the morphological or chemical characters of the plant. As a first step in finding the answer, the role of morphological factors is being investigated. One factor studied was the possible role of the differences in hairiness of these two varieties, i.e., the leaf surface of TKM-6 is hairy while that of Rexoro is glabrous. In the test, the hairs of TKM-6 leaves were rubbed off using a wet cloth. It was found that this did not alter the ovipositional preference of the moths for Rexoro (Table 5), suggesting that hairiness of plant leaves does not determine the ovipositional preference of the striped borer moths.

Varietal Resistance to Leafhoppers and Planthoppers

Screening varieties for resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper

During the year, about 1,000 varieties and selections were screened for their resistance to the rice green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, and to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*. The selections included those that were screened as stem borer-resistant from the world collection of 10,000 varieties and from the promising breeding materials from the Institute's Varietal Improvement Department. The screening procedure used was that described for *N. lugens* in the 1967 Annual Report, with one modification – each row contained 20 seedlings of a variety which was tested in two replications. Taichung (Native) 1 was used as a susceptible check for both insect species, while Pankhari 203 and Mudgo served as resistant checks for the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper, respectively (Fig. 1).

About 10 percent of the varieties tested showed moderately high levels of resistance to either the rice green leafhopper or the brown planthopper. A few varieties reacted as highly resistant to one but not to the other while most were susceptible to both species. The resistance of the varieties could have been due to one or more of the following factors: 1) These varieties were not preferred by

Fig. 1. In the mass-screening experiments on leafhopper or planthopper resistance, susceptible varieties were frequently completely killed while resistant lines showed little plant damage. IRR1, 1968.

the insect (non-preference), 2) They might possess high tolerance to insect damage (tolerance), and 3) The plants contained factors which prevented the insects from feeding on them or were toxic to the insects (antibiosis).

Generally, it is the third type of resistance, commonly known as "antibiosis", which is most desirable since in the absence of preferred hosts, the insects can infest those that are non-preferred and heavy populations can damage the tolerant plants. In these tests, therefore, emphasis is being placed on identifying those varieties that possess the "antibiosis" type of resistance. This is done by caging a uniform number of insects (either adults or nymphs) on 20-day-old individually potted plants of varieties which show the least damage in the mass screening tests. The varieties which bring about the least survival of the insects are classified as truly resistant and are used in future

experiments.

Effect of plant age on brown planthopper and green leafhopper resistance

Based on the above studies four varieties were selected to determine the consistency of their resistance at different stages of growth. These varieties were Mudgo – resistant to the brown planthopper but susceptible to the green leafhopper, Pankhari 203 and IR8 – resistant to the green leafhopper but susceptible to the brown planthopper, and Taichung (Native) 1 – susceptible to both species.

Ten first-instar nymphs were caged on individually potted plants of these varieties and their survival and growth were recorded at frequent intervals until all of them died or became adults. A series of experiments was conducted using 15-, 30-, 60- and 90-day-old plants. The results of the study using 60-day-old plants are shown in Fig. 2. In the case of the brown planthoppers, at 5 days after caging, only 2 percent of the nymphs were living on Mudgo plants while more than 90 percent were still alive on Pankhari 203 and Taichung (Native) 1. All the nymphs on Mudgo died during the next 5 days while about 90 percent of those on Pankhari 203 and Taichung (Native) 1 survived to later become adults (Fig. 2, A). The nymphs had a similar survival rate when caged on plants of different ages ranging from the seedling stage to maturity.

The green leafhopper nymphs had a high survival rate on Mudgo and Taichung (Native) 1 but not on Pankhari 203. On the latter variety, only 20 percent of the caged nymphs reached the adult stage in contrast to about 70 percent on Taichung (Native) 1 and Mudgo (Fig. 2, B). The age of the plants of these varieties at the time of caging did not alter their susceptibility to this insect. Also, corollary experiments revealed low survival of the green leafhopper on IR8, as was the case on Pankhari 203 (Fig. 3).

Effect of different temperatures on the brown planthopper on Mudgo plants

Whether or not temperature will affect the resistance of Mudgo to the brown planthopper was investigated by caging first-instar nymphs on 15-day-old seedlings at 24, 29, and 33 C. Taichung

Table 4. Stem borer incidence of some selected IR580 lines (F₆). IIRRI, August to December, 1968.

Line	Stem borer damage		Flowering (days after seeding)	Yield* (kg/ha)
	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)		
IR580-E459-304-733	1.36	6.82	101	4,793.60
IR580-E472-383-958	2.28	6.90	93	5,584.00
IR580-E420-5-12	1.05	6.84	92	4,835.20
IR580-E443-145-386	3.07	4.32	104	6,248.00
IR580-E443-145-390	4.96	8.47	101	6,078.40
IR580-E430-29-79	4.00	9.36	88	5,065.60
IR580-E478-421-1020	5.76	6.40	96	4,681.60
IR580-E443-148-397	7.04	7.68	93	6,347.20
IR580-E450-232-1333	9.49	9.00	101	6,052.80
TKM-6	4.31	6.95	73	3,417.07
Rexoro	17.41	34.33	107	1,338.67
IR8	12.04	23.04	96	3,729.60
Taichung (Native) 1	17.01	20.94	85	4,203.20

* Yield estimate obtained from two-row plots protected from insect infestation.

Table 5. Differences in ovipositional preference of striped borer moths, *Chilo suppressalis*, between two rice varieties*. IIRRI, 1968.

Variety	No. egg masses/repl.			Total egg masses	No. eggs/repl.			Total eggs
	I	II	III		I	II	III	
Rexoro (susceptible)	50	51	102	203	2417	2410	5956	10,783
TKM-6 (resistant)	36	29	85	150	1612	1501	3873	6,995
After removing hairs from the leaves of TKM**								
Rexoro**	88	93	122	303	2402	5677	6030	15,909
TKM-6**	70	76	93	239	2772	4022	4232	11,026

* In both experiments, all egg masses on TKM-6 were found on the undersurface of the leaves except for three which were found on the upper surface.

** Test conducted at a later date.

Fig. 2. Survival and development of first instar *Nilaparvata lugens* (A) and *Nephotettix impicticeps* (B) nymphs on 60-day-old plants of resistant and susceptible varieties. (A similar difference in insect survival on these varieties was also recorded in experiments using 15-, 45-, and 90-day-old plants.) IRR, 1968.

(Native) 1 seedlings grown at each of these temperatures were used as susceptible checks. A plant of each variety was infested with five newly hatched nymphs, the survival and development of which was recorded at 2-day intervals. The surviving insects were transferred every sixth day to fresh seedlings of the same variety.

On susceptible variety Taichung (Native) 1, the nymphs had high survival at 24 and 29 C, about 90 percent of them becoming adults within 20 days from caging, but had very low survival and a prolonged nymphal period at 33 C (Fig. 4). The deleterious effects of 33 C temperature on the brown planthopper nymphs have also been recorded in earlier experiments. The nymphs caged on Mudgo plants at all of the three temperatures died within the first 10 days of caging. Thus, the resistance of Mudgo to the brown planthopper was not altered when the plants were grown at different temperatures.

Damage by green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers on resistant and susceptible varieties

The above results have shown that Pankhari 203 and Mudgo caused the low survival of *N. impicticeps* and *N. lugens* caged on them, respectively. The extent of damage on these varieties by these respective insects was further evaluated by

caging 50, 100, and 200 first instar nymphs on individual plants of these varieties. The plants were at the 15 to 20 days after transplanting stage. They were individually graded for extent of damage using the following standard:

Grade	<i>N. impicticeps</i>	<i>N. lugens</i>
0	No visible damage	No visible damage
1	¼ of plant leaves turning yellow	Lower leaves turning yellow
2	1/3 of plant leaves turning yellow with some stunting of plants	Lower leaves turning brownish
3	½ of plant leaves yellow, more pronounced stunting	½ of plant leaves brown, more pronounced stunting
4	All except the central leaf yellow, some plants wilting	All leaves brown, some plants wilting
5	50 percent of test plants killed	50 percent of test plants killed
6	All plants killed	All plants killed

An infestation of 50 *N. impicticeps* nymphs on Pankhari 203 and 50 *N. lugens* nymphs on Mudgo plants caused barely noticeable symptoms of damage. The susceptible varieties, however, were heavily damaged. A population of 100 nymphs per plant caused only yellowing of the lower leaves of resistant varieties 10 to 15 days after infestation; in contrast, all plants of Taichung (Native) 1, which is susceptible to both *N. impicticeps* and *N.*

lugens, were killed (Fig. 5). There was no further increase in damage to the resistant varieties as most of the insects on them had died. The comparative damage to resistant and susceptible varieties remained the same when 200 nymphs per plant were used, although the extent of damage somewhat increased on each variety (Fig. 6). Such level of insect infestation in the field during the seedling stage of the crop is rare and thus, it is unlikely that, in nature, these varieties will be significantly damaged by the insects to which they are resistant.

Feeding punctures and termination of the salivary sheaths on resistant and susceptible varieties

The possible role of a mechanical barrier to brown planthopper feeding on Mudgo plants was investigated by studying the frequency and location of feeding punctures and the termination of the salivary sheaths in tissues of Mudgo and Taichung

Fig. 3. Survival and growth of rice green leafhopper first-instar nymphs on resistant and susceptible rice varieties. (Average of 20 replications each consisting of 15 first instar nymphs caged on a 25-day-old plant.) IRRI, 1968.

Fig. 4. Survival and development of freshly hatched brown planthopper nymphs on 15-day-old Mudgo and Taichung (Native) 1 plants at three temperatures. (Average of 10 replications, each using five brown planthopper nymphs on 12-day-old seedlings.) IRRI, 1968.

(Native) 1 plants. The salivary sheath is a tube formed by a coagulable secretion by a sucking insect around its mouth parts while punctured in the plant tissues. This tube remains in the plant even after the insect has withdrawn its mouth parts and is therefore used to determine the feeding site of the insect.

These studies were conducted by caging 10 brown planthopper adults (5 males and 5 females) for 48 hours on leaf sheaths near the base of Mudgo and Taichung (Native) 1 plants. The infested plant parts were then cut into 5 μ -thick cross sections using a microtome and the sections were stained with safranin 0 and fast green solutions. The safranin 0 stained the salivary sheaths as bright red in contrast to the fast green plant tissues.

The results showed that on the susceptible variety Taichung (Native) 1, 70 percent of the stylet punctures were made through the parenchyma and only 10 percent through the fibers (Table 6). The distribution of punctures is what would be logically expected since the fiber tissues of the plant are harder than the parenchyma.

Fig. 5. Damage to resistant and susceptible rice varieties by the first-instar brown planthopper and green leafhopper nymphs in 15 days. IRRI, 1968.

However, in the resistant variety Mudgo, most of the punctures were made through the fiber tissues, indicating that these tissues did not offer a mechanical barrier to planthopper feeding. Furthermore, since the vascular bundles are located beneath the fibers, it is highly probable that punctures made through fibers would end up in the vascular bundles more than punctures made through other tissues. That the insects could easily locate their feeding sites on Mudgo was also evident in the larger numbers of stylet sheaths having only one branch and ending up in vascular bundles in Mudgo than in Taichung (Native) 1 plants (Table 6). The branches of salivary sheaths are considered as different probes which the insect makes to locate the proper feeding sites. Therefore, the differences in the susceptibility of these two varieties is not attributable to the presence of mechanical barriers to feeding.

Feeding ability of the insect on resistant varieties

The foregoing discussion has shown that the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper had low survival on and caused little damage to varieties that are resistant to them. To investigate

the bases of resistance of these varieties, the ability of the insects to feed on them was studied. This was done by using the following two procedures.

1. *Change in insects' body weights.* Unmated female brown planthoppers were kept without food for 48 hours and then caged on plants of resistant and susceptible varieties for another 48 hours. The differences in their body weights before and after caging on the plants indicated their ability to feed on these plants. The insects gained weight on all the three susceptible varieties tested (IR8, Taichung (Native) 1, and Pankhari 203) but lost weight on the resistant variety Mudgo (Fig. 7). This showed that they did very little feeding, if any, on Mudgo plants. Among the susceptible varieties, maximum feeding was indicated on Pankhari 203.

2. *Amount of honeydew excreted on resistant and susceptible plants* Like most other sucking insects, the leafhoppers and planthoppers have a special structure in their alimentary canal called the filter chamber which is designed to remove the excess fluid of the plant sap on which they feed. This excessive fluid is absorbed by the filter chamber just before the plant sap enters the intestines and is excreted as honeydew. Thus, the amount of honeydew excreted can be used as a criterion for the quantitative feeding by the insect.

The arrangement used for collecting the honeydew is shown in Fig. 8, A. The honeydew drops onto and is absorbed by the filter paper at the bottom of the cage. The dried honeydew on the filter paper is not visible to the naked eye but has a light pink color under ultraviolet light. Also, since the honeydew contains amino acid, its presence can be easily determined by treatment with ninhydrin (Fig. 8, B). A quantitative estimate of the honeydew excreted on different varieties was also made by dissolving the filter paper in H_2SO_4 and determining its color absorbance in a spectrophotometer. Filter paper which was not exposed to honeydew constituted the controls. The values obtained refer to the total organic matter contained in honeydew.

The methods used revealed that the brown planthoppers did much less feeding on the resistant variety Mudgo than on the susceptible varieties IR8, Taichung (Native) 1, and Pankhari 203 (Fig. 8, B and 9). Also, most of the feeding was done by female insects which exhibited maxi-

Fig. 6. Damage (see text for guide to grades) caused by caging 100 first-instar nymphs on resistant and susceptible varieties. IIRI, 1968.

Table 6. Sites of feeding punctures and termination of brown planthopper salivary sheaths on susceptible and resistant rice varieties. IIRI, 1968.

Salivary sheaths	Taichung (Native)1 (susceptible)	Mudgo (resistant)
Total no. of salivary sheaths observed	425	457
Stylet penetration (%) through:		
Fibers	10	45
Just beside fibers	13	18
Parenchyma	77	38
Salivary sheaths with different no. of branches (%)		
1	23	42
2	24	21
3	28	20
4	16	10
5	9	6
Termination of salivary sheaths (%)		
Considering each branch as a separate probe:		
Phloem	21	38
Xylem	10	6
Parenchyma	40	48
Air space	26	5
Others	3	2
Termination of at least one branch of the salivary sheath in:		
Phloem	38	68
Xylem	17	4
Phloem and xylem (at least 1 branch)	11	7
All ending in non-vascular tissues	4	21

Fig. 7. Rate of change in body weights of female brown planthoppers in 48 hours on different rice varieties. The insects were kept without food for 48 hours before they were caged on these plants. IRRI, 1968.

imum differences in feeding on different varieties by excreting 30 to 50 times more honeydew on the three susceptible varieties than on the resistant variety Mudgo. The male insects did much less feeding on all varieties and the differences in total honeydew excreted on resistant and susceptible varieties were not distinct. The highest value of the feeding by brown planthopper females on Pankhari 203 offers an explanation for the insects' greater weight gain on it than on other susceptible varieties (Fig. 7).

Studies on the rice green leafhopper showed that although the insect excreted lesser amounts of honeydew on the resistant varieties Pankhari 203 and IR8 than on the susceptible variety Taichung (Native) 1, the differences were not as distinct as in the case of the brown planthopper (Fig. 10). Furthermore, unlike the brown planthopper, both male and female green leafhoppers excreted almost the same amount of honeydew, suggesting identical feeding quantities. As previously discussed, there have been no mechanical barriers to the feeding of brown planthoppers on the varieties studied (Table 6). Since both these insect species possess the same general type of mouth parts and have almost the same body size, it is unlikely that mechanical barriers exist in these varieties, even to green leafhopper feeding. This has been confirmed for Pankhari 203 (1967 Annual Report, Plant Pathology section).

Therefore, the highest amount of feeding by the brown planthopper on Pankhari 203 but the least amount of feeding by the green leafhopper on the same variety indicate basic differences in the food preference of these insects. The inability of the brown planthopper to feed on Mudgo plants

indicates that this variety possesses either a strong repellent or a toxin against the insect while the varieties resistant to *N. impicticeps* seem to either possess toxic materials or lack vital nutritional elements as the insects do some feeding but still suffer high mortality on them.

A
B

Fig. 8. To assess the quantitative feeding of brown planthoppers, honeydew excreted by planthoppers is collected on a filter paper at the bottom of the cage (A). When the filter paper is dipped in a ninhydrin solution, the honeydew stains as bright pink spots (B). F stands for female and M, for male brown planthoppers. IRRI, 1968.

Inheritance of leafhopper and planthopper resistance

It is evident from the foregoing discussions that Mudgo is highly resistant to the brown planthopper but is susceptible to the green leafhopper. On the other hand, IR8 and Pankhari 203 are resistant to the green leafhopper and susceptible to the brown planthopper. The availability of these sources of resistance, therefore, offers the possibility of developing plants that are resistant to both the green leafhopper and brown planthopper. The resistance of IR8 is particularly significant since its hybridization with Mudgo may yield segregants combining resistance to the green leafhopper and brown planthopper with a desirable plant type.

The studies on the inheritance of the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper in rice varieties are being conducted in collaboration with one of the geneticists of the Institute. F_1 and F_2 generations of the following three crosses were investigated: Mudgo x IR8, Mudgo x Pankhari 203, and Mudgo x Taichung (Native) 1. The F_1 plants were grown individually in clay pots in the greenhouse. At 30 days after transplanting, 15 green leafhopper and 10 brown planthopper first-instar nymphs were caged separately on each of these plants. The survival of the nymphs was recorded at frequent intervals and the experiment was terminated when most of the surviving nymphs became adults. Fifteen F_1 plants of each cross and parent were used. The results showed that resistance to the brown planthopper as well as to the green leafhopper was dominant and the F_1 's of crosses between Mudgo and IR8 or Pankhari 203 possessed resistance to both insects as illustrated by their low survival on these plants (Fig. 11).

Random populations of F_2 seedlings of these crosses were tested in the greenhouse for their reaction to the insects using mass screening techniques. This method has been discussed earlier in this report. The reaction to the brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers was determined by infesting the test plants with each of these species in separate experiments.

The F_2 segregation for reaction to the brown planthopper was relatively more clear-cut than that for reaction to the green leafhopper. Additional information about the green leafhopper is

Fig. 9. Qualitative assessment of the *Nilaparvata lugens* honeydew excreted by five adults for 24 hours on different rice varieties by measuring their light interference in a spectrophotometer. IRR1, 1968.

necessary before any hypothesis can be made to explain the mode of inheritance of resistance to this insect. However, the available F_2 data on segregation for reaction to the brown planthopper indicate that the resistance is simply inherited (Table 7).

All the seedlings of the susceptible parents (IR8, Taichung (Native)1 and Pankhari 203) were killed by the brown planthoppers on the 14th or 16th day after infestation while none of the seedlings of the resistant parent (Mudgo) wilted or died up to the 18th day. Considering the reaction of the F_2 populations and parents, it appears that the resistant and susceptible segregates would be best discriminated on the basis of their reactions on the 18th day after infestation. In F_2 populations of 936 plants of Mudgo x IR8, 176 plants of Mudgo x Taichung (Native) 1, and 218 plants of Mudgo x Pankhari 203, 25.8, 26.9 and 22.3 percent of the plants, respectively, were either dead or badly wilted on the 18th day after infestation. Although the results will be confirmed by studying

Fig. 10. Quantitative assessments of the honeydew excreted by the five *N. impicticeps* adults feeding for 24 hours on different rice varieties by measuring their light interference in a spectrophotometer. IRRI, 1968.

F_3 breeding behavior, the present data agree with a 3:1 ratio and strongly indicate that the resistance of Mudgo to the brown planthopper is dependent upon a single genetic factor.

Table 7. F_2 reactions of different crosses and parents to the brown planthopper on the 18th day of infestation. IRRI, 1968.

Parent or cross	Reaction (% plants)*					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Taichung (Native)1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100
IR8	0.00	1.57	6.29	46.45	38.58	7.08
Pankhari 203	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100
Mudgo	1.16	34.38	30.23	33.72	0.00	0.00
Mudgo x IR8	2.69	22.89	22.78	25.92	2.91	22.78
Mudgo x Pankhari	0.00	27.72	20.45	29.54	1.81	20.45
Mudgo x Taichung (N)1	3.06	4.59	13.26	52.04	3.57	23.46

With a view to determining the pattern of segregation of field reaction to the brown planthopper, 800 F_2 seedlings of each of the three crosses were planted in 5-meter rows at a spacing of 50 cm x 50 cm using one seedling per hill. A row following every five rows of the F_2 material was in turn planted to one of the parent varieties. The insect infestation was very high with most of the susceptible parent lines being killed while the resistant parent Mudgo and about three-fourths of the F_2 population remained unaffected (Fig. 12). Of the unaffected plants in the cross between Mudgo and IR8, several possessed the general plant type of IR8.

Still in another experiment, 200 F_2 plants from each cross are being tested individually in the greenhouse for their resistance to the brown planthopper by caging 10 first-instar nymphs on them. The data obtained so far generally indicated the same pattern of segregation as obtained by the mass screening technique.

Insecticides

Screening of insecticides in greenhouse and field experiments

To identify newer and more effective insecticides for rice pest control, a large number of compounds were screened during the year. These studies emphasized particularly the control of the brown planthopper which has lately become more abundant in many areas. In 1968, 50 insecticides were evaluated for their effectiveness against this insect on topical application and about 17 selected

Table 8. Parasitization of black bug *Scotinophara coarctata* eggs in the laboratory using test tubes and mylar cages with and without a female bug guarding the egg mass. Palawan, Philippines, 1986.

Parasitoid	Parasitization ^a (%)			
	Test tube		Mylar cage	
	Egg mass	Egg	Egg mass	Egg
<i>T. triptus</i> alone	95.0	77.0	13.3	3.8
<i>T. triptus</i> + female black bug	95.0	76.0	66.6	23.0

^a Av of 20 replications.

T. chloropus) into mylar cages with potted plants bearing one egg mass guarded by a female black bug. After 24 h, the egg masses were removed and held until the parasites emerged. *T. triptus* parasitized over 90% of the eggs, followed by *T. cyrus* and the other species, which parasitized <10%.

Effect of location of *Scotinophara latiuscula* egg masses on the host-finding ability of egg parasitoids. *S. latiuscula* egg masses (6 eggs/mass) were glued at the bottom of the stem, in the middle, and at the upper portion of rice plants. The plants were then enclosed in mylar film cages, and one gravid female of each of four species of parasitoids was released inside the cage. After 24 h, egg masses were removed and placed individually in tubes until parasite emergence (n = 202).

No significant differences in the degree of parasitization occurred among locations of egg masses on the plant. However, *T. cyrus* parasitized more eggs at all locations than did the other parasitoid species. *Psix lacunatus* was next in abundance. These two species are indigenous parasites of *S. latiuscula* black bugs in Laguna, Philippines.

Natural parasitization of black bug *Scotinophara coarctata* eggs in Palawan, Philippines. Egg masses of black bug were collected from October 1984 to December 1986 in heavily infested rice-fields in Aborlan and Narra, southern Palawan, and in Roxas, northern Palawan. The egg masses were placed individually in glass tubes plugged with cotton and brought to the laboratory for parasite emergence.

A total of 68,753 eggs (1,746 egg masses) were collected in Aborlan and Narra. Egg parasitization was 23.4%, but 62.3% of the egg masses were parasitized.

Collection in December 1986 in Roxas yielded 447 egg masses with 20,864 eggs. Parasitization of egg masses was 86%; that of eggs was 27%.

Biological control-resistant plant interaction. A greenhouse study was conducted to determine the effect of the combined action of resistant plants and the predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on BPH survival. The mortality of first-instar BPH biotype 3 nymphs on susceptible TN1 and resistant Mudgo varieties with and without predators was measured. Without the predator, mortality was 9% for the susceptible variety and 15% for the resistant. When *C. lividipennis* was added, mortality increased to about 37% on the susceptible variety and 41% on the resistant.

Insect pathogens. Collections and cultures. Several new and rare fungi were collected and isolated from rice insects, and epizootics in pest populations were observed. Fungi isolates are preserved in the IRRI Entomology Department's "Collection of Pathogens of Rice Insects." The new collections include *Metarhizium flavoviride* Gams and Rozsypal, which, with *M. anisopliae* (Metschn.) Sorokin and the common species *Hirsutella citrififormis* Speare, is predominant on BPH and other rice hoppers in the Philippines. The new fungus *M. flavoviride* var. *minus* Rombach, Humber, and Roberts was introduced.

Also, the rare fungus *Metarhizium album* Petch was collected from planthoppers and leafhoppers. *M. album* is becoming common on GLH in the Philippines. In Indonesia, it was collected from *Cofana spectra* on Sulawesi.

New *Hirsutella* and *Cordyceps* species were collected from leafhoppers in Indonesia and from BPH in Korea. *Aphanocladium* sp. was predominant on BPH and the smaller BPH in Korea. During recent years, *Hirsutella strigosa* Petch commonly occurred on GLH and BPH in the IRRI insectary and on the IRRI farm. The mycoparasite *Calcarisporium ovalisporum* Petch was collected on *H. citrififormis* in the Solomon Islands.

Cultures of all established species and varieties are in the IRRI collection.

Dry mycelium of entomogenous Hyphomycetes was mass produced in the laboratory. The mycelium, which was applied in the field, sporulated on the rice plant and the conidia

Table 8. Rice green leafhopper and brown planthopper control effectivity of selected insecticides applied to the irrigation water of potted plants at 2 kg/ha. IRRRI, 1968.

Insecticide		Insect mortality (%) * at indicated days after treatment							
		<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>				<i>Nephotettix impicticeps</i>			
		1	5	10	15	1	5	10	15
γ -BHC	6G	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Dol-mix	6:3	84.6	41.8	22.4	7.7	100.0	40.8	47.0	47.3
γ -Bassa	9G	30.6	12.3	10.2	5.5	76.5	25.5	12.0	0.0
Unden + γ -BHC	8G	84.6	43.8	23.4	13.3	86.7	23.4	10.0	0.0
γ -Mipcin **	6.4	54.0	2.0	2.0	—	**			
Sevidol	8G	5.1	15.3	10.2	—	68.3	3.0	2.0	
Sevin	10G	23.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	89.7	3.0	2.0	
Mipcin	4G	91.8	33.6	20.4	11.1	100.0	71.4	57.0	49.0
Solvigam **	10G	5.1	7.0	2.0					
Diazinon	10G	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	33.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
Tsumacide	25G	28.5	0.0	0.0		100.0	3.0	0.0	
S6626	5G	0.0	0.0	0.0		0.0	5.1	5.0	
Furadan **	10G	100.0	30.0	2.0		**			
Landrin **	10G	3.0	0.0	0.0		**			
Meobal **	10G	18.3	7.0	5.0		**			
S4150 **	10G	25.5	2.0	0.0		**			

* Mortality recorded at 48 hours after caging adult insects on treated plants. Values adjusted using Abbott's formula.

** Not tested for *N. impicticeps*.

the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper was tested in the greenhouse. Each of the insecticides was applied to the standing water in potted plants at the rate of 2 kg/ha. Ten young adults of each insect species were caged separately on the treated plants at different intervals after treatment and their mortality was recorded at 24 and 48 hours after caging.

Several of the insecticides tested were effective for controlling either the brown planthopper or the green leafhopper but dol-mix, unden + BHC, and Mipcin controlled both insects (Table 8). None of the materials tested, however, had significant residual effectivity for controlling the brown planthoppers beyond 10 days after treatment except dol-mix and Mipcin which caused about 50 percent mortality of the green leafhopper at 15 days after treatment.

In another experiment, nine promising compounds were evaluated for green leafhopper, brown planthopper, and striped borer control. Their effectivity as systemics was investigated by applying them at the rate of 2 kg/ha a.i. to the soil surface of porcelain pots containing IR8 plants. The effectivity of the treatment was bioassayed by caging 10 adults of *N. impicticeps* and *N. lugens* in separate cages on the plants and by caging 10 first-instar *C. suppressalis* larvae on a 4-inch stem piece obtained from the basal part of the plant inside a test tube. Insect mortality was recorded at 48 hours after caging. The experiment was conducted twice, with eight replications in the first test and six in the second.

Diazinon treatments caused more than 50 percent mortality of striped borer larvae up to 10 days from treatment, but this declined to 35.8 percent at 15 days after treatment (Table 9).

Table 9. Insect mortality on plants treated with paddy water application of different insecticides at 2 kg/ha a.i.*. IIRI, 1968.

Insecticide	Insect mortality at indicated days after treatment (%)								
	<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>			<i>Nephotettix impicticeps</i>			<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>		
	5	10	15	5	10	15	5	10	15
Lebaycid	0.0	1.04	14.5	11.99	5.62	3.57	42.47	27.15	9.04
UC30044	42.37	0.00	8.38	4.83	3.12	1.25	33.62	24.61	0.82
Terracur	18.12	6.39	11.19	9.33	22.17	5.00	67.25	74.66	49.99
Uden	3.08	1.62	23.12	90.33	67.34	46.65	55.14	51.42	36.99
Temik	1.09	15.50	26.68	54.50	16.44	4.37	80.40	52.46	19.16
Diazinon	55.73	68.61	35.83	0.83	1.87	12.44	10.15	5.46	0.00
Dursban	0.32	9.94	15.24	8.49	4.37	2.14	11.71	5.76	32.32
Birlane	10.30	11.42	7.56	2.66	5.00	0.00	10.15	20.76	10.55
Gusathion	3.20	5.93	11.62	4.16	1.25	3.47	17.19	14.99	11.66

* Mortality at 24 hours after caging. All other data were taken at 48 hours after caging. Values adjusted using Abbott's formula.

Table 10. Effect of different rates and frequencies* of γ -BHC and diazinon applied to the paddy water. IIRI, January to May, 1968.

Insecticide (kg/ha)	Whorl maggot damage scale						Dead hearts (%)			White heads (%)			Grain yield (kg/ha)		
	40 DAT			50 DAT			50 DAT			104 DAT			110 DAT		
	20*	30*	40*	20*	30*	40*	20*	30*	40*	20*	30*	40*	20*	30*	40*
γ -BHC															
0.5	2.1	4.8	4.1	0.5	4.7	4.8	1.47	1.51	5.74	0.74	0.46	1.12	7703	7087	7281
1.0	2.5	4.2	4.1	0.0	4.7	4.8	0.45	1.26	3.54	0.25	0.34	0.62	7905	8045	7562
1.5	2.2	4.1	4.0	0.0	4.1	4.7	1.14	1.58	2.80	0.28	0.35	0.36	7784	8061	7459
2.0	0.8	3.5	3.8	0.0	4.2	4.5	1.05	1.27	5.08	0.31	0.27	0.50	9015	8659	8053
Diazinon															
0.5	2.0	4.3	3.5	0.5	4.7	4.2	1.69	2.22	6.28	0.85	1.37	0.89	7670	7745	7618
1.0	2.1	3.6	3.6	0.1	4.0	4.2	1.05	1.10	5.59	0.44	0.56	1.24	8372	8026	7980
1.5	0.3	2.8	3.1	0.0	3.0	4.1	0.13	1.24	6.30	0.32	0.79	2.95	8314	8466	8228
2.0	0.6	1.2	1.0	0.1	1.6	3.3	2.24	0.50	5.81	0.63	1.04	1.05	8523	9246	8503
Control	4.6			4.7			4.73			1.34			6844		
LSD							0.07			0.12					
Transformation used							$\sqrt{x+0.5}$			$\sqrt{x+0.5}$					

* The insecticidal application in separate treatments was repeated at 20-, 30- and 40-day intervals.

Other insecticides were comparatively ineffective except UC30044 which caused 42 percent larval mortality at 5 days after treatment. Subsequent observations, however, showed this insecticide to have short residual effectivity.

Of all the insecticides tested, unden provided the most effective control of the brown planthopper. It caused 90, 73, and 46 percent mortality of the adult brown planthoppers at 5, 10, and 15 days after treatment, respectively. Except for the 54.5 percent insect mortality in the temik-treated plots at 5 days after treatment, all the other insecticides were comparatively ineffective in controlling the brown planthopper. Also, at the rate of 2 kg/ha, terracur, unden, and temik provided the most effective control of the green leafhopper. Terracur caused more than 50 percent mortality of insects caged on plants at 15 days after the insecticidal application, at which time the mortality in the unden- and temik-treated plots were 37 and 19, respectively.

It is clear from these data that of all the insecticides tested, the following were the most effective: diazinon against the stem borers, unden against the brown planthoppers, and terracur against the green leafhoppers. Unden also proved effective in controlling the green leafhoppers. Since the brown planthoppers have been particularly abundant during the recent crop seasons, unden appears to be a very promising insecticide for rice insect pest control. However, as it is not effective in controlling *C. suppressalis*, it should be used in combination with diazinon or other insecticides effective against borers.

Effectivity of Paddy Water Application of Insecticides in Field Experiments

Different rates and frequencies of γ -BHC and diazinon treatments in greenhouse and laboratory experiments conducted in 1967 showed that applying diazinon in paddy water at even as low a rate as 1 kg/ha provided effective control of stem borer larvae. Even in field experiments this rate provided highly significant stem borer control and protected the crop from virus infection, resulting in high yields. Since lower rates of diazinon, if found effective, will be more economical than the usual 2 kg/ha, an experiment similar to the earlier ones was conducted during the 1968 dry season.

In separate tests, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2 kg/ha rates of diazinon and γ -BHC were applied at 20-, 30-, and 40-day intervals. The experiment was conducted in four replications in a randomized complete block design.

Observations made at 50 days after transplanting showed that at all rates tested both γ -BHC and diazinon were highly effective in protecting the crop from dead heart damage if they were applied every 20 or 30 days. However, none of the rates provided effective control when the insecticides were used at 40-day intervals. A similar trend was also evident in protecting the crop from white head damage. γ -BHC generally was more effective in controlling the stem borers than diazinon at all rates tested.

The first observation on whorl maggot damage made at 40 days after transplanting showed that the maggot incidence was low in all plots treated at 20-day intervals. Since at the time of this observation the plots given the 20-, 30-, and 40-day interval treatments were at 12, 22, and 32 days after the first insecticidal application, respectively, the maggot incidence indicated the residual property of the treatments. Thus, only the 2 kg/ha γ -BHC rate had some residual effects at 22 and 32 days after treatment; the other plots were damaged to the same extent as the untreated control plots. However, diazinon at 2 kg/ha controlled the maggots effectively even up to 22 and 32 days after treatment. Subsequent observations revealed that for cumulative maggot control both the interval from insecticidal treatment to the time of observation and the frequency of treatment were important.

This became more evident 50 days after transplanting when the maggot damage in all γ -BHC and diazinon plots treated at 20-day intervals was almost negligible as compared to the untreated controls and most of the other treated plots (Table 10). At the time of this observation, the plots treated at 20- and 40-day intervals were at only 2 days after the last treatment while the 30-day-interval plots had been treated 18 days earlier. Since 2 days is too short a period to show the effect of insect control on plant damage, for all practical purposes, the 20- and 40-day-interval plots were at 22 and 42 days after the last insecticidal treatment.

Table 11. Effect on the brown planthopper population of different rates and frequencies of γ -BHC and diazinon applied to the paddy water, IRR1, January to May, 1968.

Insecticide (kg/ha)	Mean number of brown planthoppers per two sampling rows											
	20-day intervals*				30-day intervals*				40-day intervals*			
	87**	Nymphs	Adults	98**	87**	Nymphs	Adults	107**	87**	Nymphs	Adults	98**
γ -BHC	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs
0.5	28.25	40.00	51.25	17.00	72.00	27.00	142.00	17.75	74.50	11.00	137.25	89.50
1.0	37.50	5.50	24.50	3.50	72.00	9.00	158.75	29.75	64.75	7.50	61.00	14.00
1.5	29.00	4.75	7.75	1.25	50.00	5.25	15.55	15.25	35.00	5.75	60.25	3.50
2.0	33.25	7.25	34.25	1.75	37.25	1.00	77.00	3.00	44.75	7.25	168.50	109.50
Diazinon	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs
0.5	20.25	4.25	4.50	0.50	17.25	2.25	28.25	3.25	30.25	10.00	20.00	4.00
1.0	12.50	23.25	6.00	1.25	16.50	0.75	26.50	3.00	23.50	9.25	19.75	3.00
1.5	14.50	0.72	5.25	0.75	13.20	0.50	5.50	2.00	21.75	4.25	16.00	1.75
2.0	17.00	1.50	8.00	1.50	16.25	1.00	4.75	0.75	16.75	2.25	19.25	2.25
Control	17.25	10.00	68.50	7.25								

* Days after transplanting.

** The two planthopper samples for each treatment were made at 1 day before and 10 days after the last insecticidal application.

All the diazinon-treated plots produced significantly higher yields than the untreated controls (Table 10). However, in γ -BHC treatments, increased yields were obtained at all rates tested when applied at 20-day intervals, but only with rates of 1 kg/ha or higher and 2 kg/ha when applied at 30- and 40-day intervals, respectively. Highest yields in both insecticide treatments were obtained when they were used at 2 kg/ha at 20- to 30-day intervals. Although both diazinon and γ -BHC were equally effective against borers, the γ -BHC plots had high brown planthopper populations (Table 11).

Tests with newer compounds

Based on the results of previous experiments conducted to determine the systemic effectivity of various compounds, eight insecticides were selected for further evaluation. Each of these was tested during the 1968 dry-season crop at the rate of 2 kg/ha applied to the paddy water every 20 days. Plots treated with diazinon at the same rate and those receiving no insecticidal treatments constituted the treated and untreated checks, respectively.

Each plot measured 5 m x 9 m and the experiment was conducted in four replications in a completely randomized block design. Twenty-day-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted using a single seedling per hill at a 25 cm x 25 cm planting space. The insecticide granules were broadcast by hand on the paddy water. The first application was made at 7 days after transplanting and the succeeding applications at 20-day intervals.

Whorl maggot damage was recorded by visually grading the plots on a scale of from 0 (no damage) to 5 (severe damage). Virus incidence was taken by counting the number of infected hills in a 2 m x 5 m predetermined sample area in each plot. The same area was also observed for dead hearts and white heads and was later harvested for grain yield. The sampling for leafhoppers and planthoppers was done with a motor-driven insect suction net by sweeping along the sides of two rows within the sampling area. Also, 10 randomly selected hills were sampled individually using a special attachment to the machine. This attachment, which fits into the base of the plant, is pulled up gently toward the top and in the process sucks insects

infesting the plant.

All the treated plots had lower whorl maggot damage than the controls. However, unden and salithion were much less effective than the others. The most effective insecticides for maggot control were dursban, dol-mix, terracur, and No.47470. The virus incidence was low and did not differ significantly in various treatments. Except for unden, all treatments had significantly fewer dead hearts than the control plots. However, the differences among these treatments were not significant, indicating that they were equally effective for borer control (Table 12). White head incidence in all plots was too low to be of economic significance.

The leafhopper and planthopper samples revealed that the heaviest infestation was with *Nilaparvata lugens*. The population of this insect was low on the young crop but it built up beyond 70 days after transplanting. Observations made 90 days after treatment showed high populations in the control and in the No.47470-treated plots, and much lower populations in the other treatments. Of these latter treatments, the salithion and birlane-treated plots had significantly more insects than the plots treated with other insecticides. Subsequent observations at 109 and 114 days after treatment showed that the planthopper populations in the salithion birlane, and No.47470-treated plots caused severe "hopper burn" but remained low in the other treated plots. Also, the crop treated with No.47470 developed brownish spots at the leaf tips, indicating some phytotoxic effects. The 0.1 to 1.2 percent "hopper burn" areas in the terracur, dol-mix, and S6626-treated plots represented damage only to the border rows caused by insects migrating from adjoining heavily infested plots.

The treatments which reduced the damage by the whorl maggot, stem borer, and brown planthopper produced high yields which were in excess of 5,000 kg/ha over the control plots (Table 12). The brown planthopper appeared to be the major factor of yield loss, and all plots that did not suffer from "hopper burn" yielded about twice as much rice as the untreated control plots.

These results show that the compounds terracur, S6626, dol-mix, and dursban appear promising for controlling common rice pests. Unden,

Table 12. Effect of paddy water application of selected insecticides at 2 kg/ha every 20 days on insect pest control, variety IR8. IRRRI, December 1967 to April, 1968.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage	Virus-infected hills (%)	Dead heart tillers (%)	White head tillers (%)	Planthopper population per two rows	Hopper-burn damage	Grain yield (kg/ha)	
	39*	72*	69*	109*	90*	109*	114*	120*
Terracur	1.7	2.5	0.0	0.05	4.5	0.1	0.1	9465
S6626	2.7	1.5	0.4	0.20	4.7	0.1	1.2	9245
Dol-mix	1.5	2.6	0.6	0.18	11.5	0.0	0.1	9061
Dursban	1.5	2.5	2.9	0.33	6.2	0.0	0.0	8983
Diazinon	2.2	1.7	2.2	0.67	6.5	0.0	0.0	8545
Uden	3.2	2.3	12.7	0.42	5.5	0.0	0.0	8183
Salithion	3.7	3.4	1.5	0.29	22.7	11.5	41.2	6855
Birlane	2.7	2.1	0.6	0.00	74.5	28.7	75.0	6026
No.47470	1.0	3.9	2.0	0.01	552.0	56.2	92.5	5289
Control	5.0	2.6	12.7	0.68	875.5	42.5	80.0	4116
LSD			0.84**	0.24	8.44			1176
			$\sqrt{x+0.5}$	$\sqrt{x+0.5}$	$\sqrt{x}$			

* Days after transplanting.

** Percentage of total plot area showing hopper burn.

although highly effective against the brown planthoppers, did not control the borers. Similarly, birlane, No.47470, and salithion controlled effectively the borers but not the brown planthoppers. A treatment combining these insecticides may prove more practical.

Effectivity of birlane, dursban, and S6626 used at different rates

Dursban and S6626 were further tested at 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2 kg/ha applied to the paddy water at 20-day intervals. The effectiveness of these treatments was compared with those of diazinon and birlane.

Birlane, dursban, and S6626 at the 1 kg/ha rate or lower were relatively ineffective in controlling whorl maggots but were equally effective at higher rates. There was a heavy stem borer incidence during the dead heart stage, as evidenced by the 22-percent dead heart-damaged tillers in the control plot, but all treatments protected the crop from borers quite effectively (Table 13). The effectiveness of the test compounds even at as low

as 0.5 and 1.0 kg/ha rates is particularly encouraging. Similar results have been obtained with diazinon in earlier experiments. However, at these lower rates diazinon was not effective in protecting the crop from white heads. Dursban was not effective in preventing the occurrence of white heads at all rates tested while birlane, S6626 (at rates of 1.5 and 2 kg/ha) and diazinon were effective.

The most abundant stem borer species during the experiment was *Tryporyza incertulas*. The late infestation of this species generally starts from the apical parts of the plant where the larvae hatching from the eggs on the flag leaf start feeding. Thus, often with very little feeding, white heads are caused although the larvae may later be killed by the insecticides applied to the paddy water. This explains why many insecticides which were effective against dead hearts failed to control white heads adequately. Furthermore, compounds which have strong fumigation effects kill the moths before they can lay eggs, thereby preventing the occurrence of white heads.

Table 13. Effect of insecticides applied to the paddy water at different rates on rice insect pest control. IRRI, July to November, 1968.

Insecticide	Rate of application (kg/ha)	Dead heart tillers (%)		Whorl maggot damage (%)		Hopper burn area (%)	White head (%)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
		43*	65*	30*	43*			
Birlane	(1)	0.00	0.04	2.0	2.18	15.0	1.30	3716
Birlane	(2)	0.00	0.01	0.0	0.50	0.0	0.95	4536
Dursban	(0.5)	0.24	2.16	3.7	3.50	17.5	5.91	2172
Dursban	(1.0)	0.02	0.43	3.0	2.30	23.7	5.05	3488
Dursban	(1.5)	0.01	0.06	1.2	0.60	0.0	4.36	5003
Dursban	(2.0)	0.07	0.12	0.8	0.50	5.0	5.44	4969
S6626	(0.5)	0.49	4.18	3.7	4.50	5.0	6.11	2959
S6626	(1.0)	0.05	1.15	2.5	3.20	7.5	4.48	3755
S6626	(1.5)	0.01	0.21	0.7	1.00	0.0	2.29	4630
S6626	(2.0)	0.04	1.52	0.6	2.00	0.0	3.12	4740
Diazinon	(2.0)	0.00	0.01	0.0	0.10	0.0	2.99	5671
Control		5.02	21.73	4.7	4.80	17.5	5.88	2294

* Days after transplanting.

** The insecticide granules were hand-broadcast to the paddy water at 17, 37, 57, and 97 days after transplanting.

The plots treated with diazinon produced the highest grain yield, indicating that this insecticide provided the best insect control. The plots treated with dursban and S6626 at 1.5 and 2 kg/ha respectively, and those treated with birlane at 2 kg/ha produced significantly higher yields than the untreated controls, but their yields were lower than those of the plots treated with diazinon. Thus, dursban or S6626 alone was not as effective as diazinon in controlling insects. Although dursban, diazinon, and S6626 were equally effective against stem borers, the differences in their overall effectiveness, as indicated by the differences in rice yields, were primarily the result of variations in their ability to control the brown planthoppers (Fig. 13).

Paddy water application of insecticidal mixtures formulated as granules

In another experiment, the effectivity of several insecticide mixtures were compared with those of diazinon and sevidol by applying them to the paddy water at 2 kg/ha every 20 days.

The formulations were developed to combine stem borer and planthopper control. As expected all insecticidal mixtures provided highly effective insect control which resulted in high rice yields. Some of these insecticide mixtures even performed better than diazinon.

All insecticides used were highly effective in reducing dead heart incidence which was 26 percent in the controls as compared to less than 0.2 in all the treated plots (Table 14). Also, all insecticides protected the crop effectively from whorl maggot and white head damage. Brown planthopper infestation during the experiment was particularly severe but all the treatments, except sevidol, effectively protected the crop from this insect (Fig. 14). More than 55 percent of the area in the sevidol-treated and the untreated control plots suffered from "hopper burn". The stem borer larval population, as recovered by dissecting 10 infested tillers from each plot, was lower in all the treated than in the untreated control plots. This population in the control plots consisted of *Tryporyza incertulas*, *Chilotrea polychrysa*,

Fig. 13. Brown planthopper population before and after insecticide application (Refer to Table 13).

Fig. 14. Brown planthopper population before and after insecticide application.

Table 14. The effect of different insecticidal mixtures applied to the paddy water on rice pest control*. IIRI, July to November, 1968

Treatment	Dead heart tillers (%)		Whorl maggot damage**		Hopper burn area (%)		No. of borer larvae/ 10 tillers	Species recovered (%)				White heads (%)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
	43†	65†	33†	43†	82†	112†		<i>C. poly- chrysa</i>	<i>C. suppress- salis</i>	<i>T. incer- tulas</i>	<i>S. infe- rens</i>		
γ-BHC+Bassa	0.02	0.04	0.33	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.00	50.00	50.00	0.92	6374
γ-BHC+Uندن	0.09	0.07	1.12	0.75	0.00	0.00	0.86	0.00	13.95	13.95	72.09	0.88	6208
Sevidol	0.01	0.06	0.12	1.12	33.70	57.50	0.50	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.14	2961
Dol-mix	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.49	24.48	0.00	0.00	75.51	0.68	6704
Diazinon	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.36	0.00	33.33	33.33	33.33	1.44	5854
Control	5.22	26.33	5.00	5.00	30.00	56.20	2.48	13.30	26.61	33.46	26.61	6.63	1078

* The insecticides were applied at 12, 32, 52, and 79 days after transplanting.

** On a scale of 1 to 5. Larger numbers mean greater damage.

† Days after transplanting.

Fig. 15. Plots treated with γ -BHC + unden granules remained comparatively insect-free and produced high grain yields while adjacent plots were heavily damaged by insects. The whitish patches show "hopper burn" damage. IIRI, 1968.

Sesamia inferens, and *Chilo suppressalis* in descending order of abundance. However, the larval population in the treated plots was too low to indicate the selective effectivity of various insecticides.

The plots treated with γ -BHC + Bassa, γ -BHC + unden and dol-mix produced the highest yields – even higher than that obtained in the diazinon-treated plots (Table 14 and Fig. 15). The yields resulting from these treatments and from diazinon were higher than those obtained in the untreated controls. The 2,961 kg/ha yield of the sevidol-treated plots, although significantly higher than those of the controls, was much lower than those of the above treatments, primarily because of "hopper burn" damage.

It is evident from these experiments that insecticide mixtures which combine good stem borer control with good planthopper control offer more promise than any single insecticide presently being used. Also, in all the insecticide mixtures used in this test, γ -BHC was used for borer control. This insecticide has been used at the Institute farm for almost 5 years now, and it is possible that strains that are resistant to it may develop. Therefore, it would be advantageous if other compounds such as dursban, S6626, and birlane, which are highly

effective for borer control, are used in formulating insecticide mixtures in future experiments.

Effectivity of Insecticides When Used as Seed Treatments

Laboratory and greenhouse experiments

The control of insect pests infesting the seedbed or young seedlings in direct-seeded rice crop by insecticidal treatments of the seeds can be a very practical and convenient method of insect control. The feasibility of this method was determined by testing promising insecticides selected from exploratory experiments reported earlier (1967 Annual Report). In a greenhouse experiment the effectiveness of these selected compounds was bioassayed by using 2- to 4-day-old *N. impicticeps* adults as test insects. These were caged on seedlings at different intervals after the sowing of treated seeds in clay pots. Also, 100 seeds from each of different treatments were germinated on moistened filter paper in petri dishes to record their germination and any phytotoxic effects.

Except for terracur and birlane, the insecticides used did not affect the germination of the seeds but several treatments caused a definite stunting of the roots and the plumule (Table 15). However, in

Table 15. Effect of different insecticides used as seed treatments on seed germination and seedling growth. IRRI, January to March, 1968.

Insecticide (@ 2 kg/100 kg of seeds)	Germination (%) 8*	Length (mm) 13*		Remarks
		Roots	Plumule	
Terracur	25.60	0.02	0.76	Whitish brown discoloration on tip of leaves
UC30044	92.60	0.81	1.57	Slight discoloration on tip of leaves
Temik	86.80	0.05	0.46	Slight discoloration on tip of leaves
Diazinon	86.20	3.77	0.99	Slight discoloration on tip of leaves
Birlane	79.80	0.50	0.42	Seedlings malformed
Unden	91.40	0.20	2.08	Whitish brown discoloration on tip of leaves
Dursban	94.20	2.53	1.04	Normal
Lebaycid	90.40	2.82	0.80	Normal
Gusathion	97.20	2.70	0.95	Normal
Control	92.40	3.85	1.88	Normal

* Days after seeding.

field experiments, the same treatments did not show any apparent phytotoxic effect.

Except for dursban, all insecticides caused high mortality of adult *N. impicticeps* caged on seedlings up to 18 days after sowing. This effectivity is significant since seedlings generally are kept in the seedbed for a period of 20 to 25 days after seeding. Even at 30 days after sowing, high insect mortality was recorded in the lebaycid, terracur, unden, birlane, and gusathion treatments. Terracur was most effective and caused 89 percent insect mortality up to 60 days after sowing (Table 16).

Whether or not the effectivity of the seed treatment is carried over to the transplanted crop was investigated by bioassaying seedlings transplanted 20 days after the treated seeds were sown. At 15 days after transplanting, 20 to 35 percent mortality of *N. impicticeps* adults was recorded in the terracur, unden, gusathion, and birlane treatments. The other compounds caused less than 10

percent insect mortality. Thus, although a few insecticides showed good insect control even after transplanting when used as seed treatments, better insect control was obtained on seedlings that were not transplanted. It is likely that a portion of the insecticides sticking to the seed surface is transferred to the soil around the seeds and thus remains available to the seedlings *in situ*.

Field experiments

In a field experiment, the effectiveness of these treatments for insect control was evaluated in a row-seeded crop. Each of the insecticides was used at 2 kg a.i. per 100 kg of seed, and at a 100 kg/ha seeding rate. Each plot measured 5 m x 10 m and was replicated four times in a completely randomized block design.

The plots treated with terracur, temik, dursban, unden, lebaycid, and gusathion had the best

germination although, unlike in the laboratory experiment, good seed germination was obtained in all treatments and the seedlings did not show distinct phytotoxic effects. The only exception to this was the birlane treatment which caused some dwarfing of the plants with slight necrosis, but the symptoms were much less pronounced than in the petri dish experiments.

All the treated plots (except those treated with temik and lebaycid) had lower dead heart and whorl maggot incidence than the untreated control. The visual differences in these plots were distinct, with the plots treated with diazinon, dursban, terracur, lebaycid, and gusathion having luxuriant and vigorous plants as compared to the other treatments. Most of these differences were apparently due to differences in whorl maggot damage (Table 17), but other insects also appeared

Table 16. Toxicity of different insecticides used as seed treatments at 2 kg a.i./100 kg of seeds to *N. impicticeps* caged on seedlings. IRRI, January to March, 1968.

Treatment	Insect mortality at indicated days after sowing (%) [*]		
	18	30	60
Lebaycid	96.0	33.8	5.6
UC30044	92.5	12.2	0.0
Terracur	100	73.5	88.9
Uden	91.7	20.4	6.7
Temik	60.0	1.0	5.6
Diazinon	56.3	2.0	0.0
Dursban	0.0	1.0	0.0
Birlane	67.5	31.6	17.8
Gusathion (E)	67.5	22.4	5.6

^{*} Values adjusted using Abbott's formula.

Table 17. Effect of seed treatments with and followed by paddy water application of different insecticides on rice pest control, variety IR8. IRRI, February to June, 1968.

Insecticide (@ 2 kg/100 kg seed)	Germination (%)	No. of seedlings/ 3-meter row	Dead heart tillers (%)	Whorl maggot damage		Planthopper density/25 sq m		Hopper- burn area (%)	White head tillers (%)	Grain Yield (kg/ha)	
				35*	47*	93*	104*			125*	125*
Temik	80.6	224.5	1.1	4.00	2.12	0.12	0.00	0.0	2.01	9386	8806
Diazinon	61.7	173.0	0.6	0.75	0.00	0.25	0.12	0.0	1.77	9067	9609
Dursban	85.9	219.0	2.6	1.00	0.37	0.75	0.00	0.0	1.32	8748	9033
Uden	80.9	200.7	2.4	0.62	0.25	0.25	0.12	1.2	1.67	8296	9576
Terracur	80.3	239.0	1.0	2.12	1.00	5.12	2.12	81.2	0.73	7833	8938
Lebaycid	87.0	280.2	2.1	4.00	2.25	1.50	5.87	71.2	1.18	7707	9725
UC30044	75.4	181.0	2.0	2.87	2.25	2.25	2.37	33.7	1.77	7157	9218
Birlane	61.8	155.8	1.6	0.25	0.00	13.72	7.37	90.0	0.75	5104	9556
Gusathion (E)	88.9	242.0	1.6	0.75	0.37	16.62	10.25	95.0	2.02	4481	9603
Control	65.7	144.7	4.8	4.50	3.75	15.75	12.50	50.0	1.91	3252	9260
LSD	11.6	2.08				1.00	1.24		0.32	1560	
Transformation used		$\sqrt{x}$				$\sqrt{x+0.5}$	$\sqrt{x+0.5}$		$\sqrt{0.32}$		

^{*} Days after seeding. All data on insect infestation beyond 35 days after seeding are from plots A.

[†] At 35 days after sowing each plot measuring 5 x 10 meters was divided into 5 x 5 meter plots. One of these (A) was treated with the same insecticide used for seed treatment by applying it to the paddy water @ 2 kg/ha every 20 days while the other (B) was treated with diazinon @ 2 kg/ha every 20 days.

Fig. 16. Brown planthopper population before and after insecticide application.

established that at 1 kg/ha, diazinon did not effectively control the borers.

The plots treated with azodrin produced the highest yield. The accothon-treated plots, which were also comparatively less affected by "hopper burn," yielded about 1,000 kg/ha less apparently due to their higher borer and maggot incidence as compared to the azodrin-treated plots.

Briefly then, except for accothon ULVC and azodrin 0.04 percent sprays, no treatment proved effective in controlling the brown planthoppers. These treatments, however, were much less effective in controlling the stem borers than paddy water application of γ -BHC and diazinon.

Effectivity of varying volumes of sprays and active ingredients of azodrin on rice insect pest control

Since Institute research has shown that insecticide application to the paddy water is more effective in controlling insect pests than the foliar sprays, studies on the latter have been scanty. There is no information from other sources about this method

of application on rice, particularly regarding the standard volume of spray material or the quantity of insecticides to be used per hectare. Generally, 250 to 350 gallons of spray per hectare are required to adequately cover the rice crop. The amount needed at the seedling stage is lower and increases as the crop grows denser. However, the amount used in actual practice by farmers varies from 150 to 400 gal/ha. An experiment was therefore designed to determine the effect of variations in the total spray material and in the total active ingredient of the insecticide used in the control of rice pests. The details of these treatments are shown in Table 20.

All the treatments provided significant and equally effective protection to the crop from dead heart damage, whorl maggots and brown planthoppers (Fig. 17) and resulted in high yields. In these treatments, the total active ingredient used ranged from 1.5 to 3.6 kg/ha but the differences in yield of the various treatments were not significant. The high effectivity of azodrin even at a lower concentration was attributable to the some-

what systematic effectivity of the insecticide against the brown planthopper and its long residual effects (Fig. 18). Further experiments will be conducted to confirm these results.

Sex Pheromones in Striped Borer Moths

Results of basic studies on the mating behavior of common rice stem borer moths and the existence of sex attraction in the female striped borer moths have been reported in the 1965 and 1966 Annual Reports. Further studies on the activity of the sex attractant factor (sex pheromone), the feasibility of extracting it from the female moths, and the male moths' reception of the sex pheromones were conducted in 1968.

Bioassay studies using newly emerged males revealed that 91 and 84 percent, respectively, of the newly emerged and 1-day-old females possessed attractant stimuli for the male moths. The attraction occurred mostly between 6 and 8 p.m. on newly emerged female moths. Of the several extraction procedures tested, that which provided

best results consisted of clipping off the last two to three abdominal segments of the live female moths and transferring the tips immediately to a bottle containing ether. These tips were then macerated with a glass rod, and the solids were filtered off while the solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator at room temperature. The resulting extract, a yellowish waxy substance, was stored at 5 C.

The sex attraction activity of the extract was determined by passing air current from it for 1 minute to a 12-inch x 24-inch glass jar containing newly emerged male moths. The positive reactions of the moths included the vibration of the antennae, wing fluttering, and the up-curving of the abdomen while crawling. Air current drawn from clean empty glass jars constituted the controls.

To determine the site of pheromone release by the female moths, separate extracts were obtained from the abdominal tips, bodies of the moths without tips, and from the whole moths. The male moths showed a strong positive reaction to the

Fig. 17. Brown planthopper population before and after insecticide application (refer to Table 20).

to be involved. At 35 days after seeding, when, based on earlier experiments, it was thought that the residual effectivity of most of the insecticides had already diminished, each plot was divided into two 5 m x 5 m subplots and one of these was treated every 20 days with 2 kg/ha a.i. of the same insecticide used as seed treatment, while the other was treated with diazinon at 2 kg/ha every 20 days until harvest. The uniform treatment with diazinon of one-half of all the plots was aimed at determining the effects of differences in general crop growth during the seedling stage due to seed treatment. On the other hand, the continued use of the same insecticide used for seed treatment was aimed at obtaining data on the effectiveness of the insecticide in controlling insects at the later stages of crop growth.

Differences in general crop stand and maggot damage during the first 35 days after seeding were not evident in the yield of the crop if protected with diazinon beyond 35 days from seeding (Table 17). This demonstrates the ability of the crop to compensate for the insect damage during the seedling stage and agrees with the results of earlier Institute experiments which showed that, except under exceptionally high insect infestations, protecting the crop from insect pests during the first 7 weeks of growth did not contribute significantly to rice yields (1964, 1965 Annual Reports). In the test in which the same insecticide used for seed treatment was applied to the paddy water, all the treatments, except gusathion, yielded significantly more rice than the untreated control plots. The yields of several of these treatments were almost three times more than those of the control plots (Table 17). Most of these differences appeared to result from differences in the ability of the treatments to control brown planthoppers.

To summarize, seed treatment with diazinon, dursban, unden, terracur, birlane, and gusathion provided effective control of pests infesting the crop during the seedling stage of the crop, but birlane, gusathion, and terracur were not effective later in controlling brown planthoppers. Also, the effect of pest control during the seedling stage did not show up in the grain yields if the crop was protected beyond 35 days from seeding. However, the results might have been different if there was significant virus incidence during the experiment.

Field Experiments with Foliar Sprays

Comparative effectivity of high and ultra-low volume foliar sprays with paddy water application of insecticides

The paddy water application of insecticides has several advantages over the conventional foliar sprays in controlling many rice pests. However, under certain situations, e.g., with rice plants grown in deep-water, upland rice culture, the control of surface-feeding insects such as cutworms, armyworms, and rice bugs, contact insecticides used as sprays or dusts should provide better control than those applied to the paddy water. Greenhouse, laboratory, and field evaluations of newer insecticides as topical and foliar treatments have been conducted regularly. These insecticides are tested as sprays and not as dusts since the latter, when applied in the tropics, are subject to irregular distribution on frequently wet rice foliage and to washing off by rains. The effectiveness of several of these compounds has been discussed in previous annual reports.

From the experiments on foliar sprays, several promising compounds were selected to compare their effectiveness with that of the paddy water application of diazinon. The foliar spray treatments consisted of spraying the crop with insecticides at 0.04 percent concentration every 15 days from transplanting to harvest. In separate treatments diazinon was applied to the paddy water at 15- to 20-day intervals at 1 kg/ha a.i. This 1 kg/ha rate is one-half the generally recommended rate, but was used to emphasize the difference in the effectiveness of the two methods since, at this rate, almost identical quantities of the two insecticides were used.

Except for the dimethoate and phosphamidon treatments, all the treated plots had significantly lower maggot damage than the control plots. Diazinon and accothon controlled the maggots best. The incidence of stem borers in these plots was too low to account for the yield differences of various plots. Brown planthopper infestation was high in several treated plots and appeared to be the major factor causing the yield reduction (Table 18). The population of this insect was so high in the parathion- or accothon-treated plots that 30 and 58 percent, respectively, of the plot area in these treatments suffered from "hopper burn."

Table 18. Comparative insect control effectivity of selected insecticides used as foliar sprays, and diazinon granules applied to the paddy water, variety IR8, IRR1, February to June, 1968.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage * 30**	Dead heart tillers (%) 55**	White head tillers (%) 120**	Hopper burn area (%) 121**	Grain yield (kg/ha)
Azodrin †	2.3	0.9	0.5	0.0	6496
Phosphamidon †	3.1	0.8	1.4	0.0	5917
Lebaycid †	2.5	2.1	1.4	0.0	5913
Endosulfan †	3.0	1.1	1.1	0.0	5606
Accothion (LVC)	1.0	2.4	1.4	58.3	5213
Parathion M †	2.8	1.6	1.0	30.0	4914
Dimethoate †	3.6	2.7	1.9	0.0	4818
Diazinon 1 kg/ha every 15 days	0.0	1.5	0.6	0.0	7392
Diazinon 1 kg/ha every 20 days	0.1	1.8	0.7	0.0	6559
Control	4.3	2.6	2.0	0.0	4941
LSD	1.2	NS	0.34		821
Transformation used			$\sqrt{x + 0.5}$		

* On a scale of 1 to 5. Smaller number indicates low infestation.

** Days after transplanting.

† Applied as 0.04% foliar spray every 15 days.

Since this condition developed when the crop was already nearing harvest, the yield losses attributed to it were not very large. It is significant that, even at this low rate and regardless of whether it was used every 15 or 20 days, diazinon provided better insect pest control and consequently, higher rice yields, than any of the foliar sprays.

Among the foliar treatments, azodrin was the most effective. It was therefore selected for further tests, and its effectiveness was compared with that of the ultra-low volume concentrate (ULVC) formulations of phosphamidon, malathion, accothion (sumithion), and a mixture of malathion and accothion. The ULVC formulations were sprayed at 400 to 500 cc per hectare using a motorized back-pack type mist blower with a special nozzle. Azodrin was used as 0.04 percent spray, at the rate of 250 to 350 gallons of the spray material per hectare.

The most effective stem borer and whorl

maggot control was obtained with the paddy water application of γ -BHC and diazinon (Table 19). Observations made at 34 and 43 days after transplanting did not indicate effective control of maggots by any of the foliar sprays used. Similarly, except for azodrin, the foliar sprays were relatively ineffective in protecting the crop from stem borer damage in the form of dead hearts. Brown planthopper infestation was particularly severe, with several of the treatments showing "hopper burn" as early as 82 days after transplanting (Fig. 16). At this stage, accothion, malathion + accothion, and azodrin provided the most effective planthopper control. In subsequent observations, however, malathion + accothion-treated plots were also severely damaged. This may be explained by the fact that malathion itself did not control the brown planthopper and the plots treated with accothion + malathion (1:1 mixture) received only half as much accothion as the plots treated with accothion alone. These data also

Fig. 18. Plots sprayed with 0.04% azodrin every 20 days were not damaged by "hopper burn" while most of the adjacent plots were heavily damaged. IRR, 1968.

Table 19. Effect of foliar sprays every 20 days and compounds applied to the paddy water on rice pest control. The insecticidal application was started at 17 days after transplanting and repeated every 20 days until 15 days before harvest. IRR, July to November, 1968.

Insecticide	Rate of application	Dead heart tillers (%)	Whorl maggot damage *		Hopper burn area/plot (%)		Grain yield (kg/ha)
			64**	34** 43**	82** 112**	112**	
Phosphamidon ULVC	500 cc/ha	17.6	0.75	3.12	31.2	37.5	2499
Malathion ULVC	400 cc/ha	10.30	2.50	3.00	25.1	46.2	†
Accothion ULVC	400 cc/ha	12.48	1.12	3.37	2.6	7.5	†
Malathion + Accothion ULVC	400 cc/ha	11.57	1.25	2.75	11.2	38.7	†
Azodrin spray	(0.04%)	7.95	1.75	2.87	0.12	0.12	4529
γ-BHC	1 kg/15 days	1.69	0.12	1.37	36.2	97.5	†
γ-BHC	1 kg/20 days	1.30	0.37	1.62	53.7	100.0	†
Diazinon	1 kg/15 days	0.97	0.12	1.12	36.3	63.7	3995
Diazinon	1 kg/20 days	1.78	0.25	1.00	27.5	48.7	†
Control		23.43	1.75	3.37	60.0	75.0	†

* On a scale of 1 to 5. Smaller number indicates low infestation.

** Days after transplanting.

† Yield data not available due to hopper burn.

Table 20. Effect of varying spray volumes and active ingredients of azodrin on rice insect pest control. IRRI, July - November 1968.

	Volume* of spray and amount of insecticide per hectare					Total a.i./ha	Dead tillers (%)	Whorl maggot damage (%)	Hopper burn area (%)	Whitehead (%)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
	A	B	C	D	E**						
I.	250	300	350	400	400 - 400 gal	3.6	2.76	1.50	0	1.64	5660
	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.7 - 0.7 kg						
II.	250	250	250	250	250 - 250 gal	3.6	1.00	1.10	0	1.42	5678
	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.7 - 0.7 kg						
III.	250	250	250	250	250 - 250 gal	2.4	1.52	1.62	0	2.13	5062
	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4 - 0.4 kg						
IV.	150 gal/ha at 0.05% spray					1.5	1.55	1.25	0	2.27	5191
V.	150 gal/ha at 0.1% spray					2.8	1.45	1.25	0	1.33	5397
VI.	Control						3.53	18.40	1.5	4.96	2640

*Days after transplanting.

**ABCDE refer to the different treatments of the same insecticide.

Except in treatment V all sprays contained 0.05% azodrin.

Table 21. Attraction of newly emerged striped borer male moths to either extracts of female moths. IRRI, 1968.

Extracts* Source	Number of moths showing positive response										Total males showing response	Percentage
	Replications**											
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X		
Whole body	4	3	4	4	2	3	4	4	4	3	35	70
Abdominal tips	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	46	92
Body without tips	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	4	8

* A total of 200 newly emerged female moths was used for each extract.

** Five newly emerged males were used in each replication.

Fig. 19. Response of male moths exposed to extracts of newly emerged females collected at different times of the day. IRRI, 1968.

extracts from the whole body of the female moths or from the abdominal tips only but did not show

a distinct response to the extracts from the bodies without the abdominal tips (Table 21). No attraction was recorded in the control. These indicate that the sex attractant or the pheromone is contained in the abdominal tips of the female moths. The stronger attraction of the male moths (92%) to the abdominal tip extracts in contrast to that to the whole body (70%) could have been due to a more efficient extraction of the sex pheromone from the tips than from comparatively bulkier samples.

Male moths with amputated antennae did not show the typical attraction response to either the live females or their extracts. However, moths with intact antennae but with their eyes painted black with India ink showed the typical response, indicating that their antennae contain the perception organ for the sex stimuli. Also, it was recorded through a series of experiments using live females as well as extracts from their abdominal tips that the attraction of the male moths occurred mostly during the evenings when mating usually occurs. The reactions of male moths to the extracts of females obtained at different hours of the day are shown in Fig. 19. Eighty-five percent of the male moths tested reacted positively to the extracts obtained at 8 p.m. while the response to the extracts obtained at 4 p.m. or 2 p.m. was much weaker. No moths were attracted to the extracts obtained at 8 a.m. Further studies using the most active extracts also showed that the male moths exhibited a strong attraction only between 6 and 8 p.m. Thus, both male and female striped borer

Fig. 20. Responsiveness of male moths of different ages to extracts of newly emerged females. IRRI, 1968.

moths exhibit sex attraction activity during the evenings only.

Newly emerged 1-day-old male moths showed maximum response to the sex pheromones extracted from the female moths but 2-day-old or older moths exhibited weaker response (Fig. 20). Similarly, the abdominal tip extracts from newly emerged and 1-day-old female moths gave the maximum stimuli to the male moths but the male moths showed less response to the extracts obtained from 2-day-old or older females. Also, a weak attraction of the male moths to the abdominal tip extracts from the female pupae was recorded, indicating that some pheromone excretion starts even during the pupal stage (Fig. 21).

These studies confirm the occurrence of the sex attractant factor in the female moths. This factor is excreted by the females at night and can be extracted by using ethyl ether and other organic

solvents. The male moths showed a strong attraction to this extract in laboratory experiments but only in the evenings. The attraction of male moths to the extracts is generally identical to their response to the live females.

Biological Control of Stem Borers

As discussed in earlier annual reports, intensive samplings at eight selected sites on Luzon Island in the Philippines revealed less than 10 percent parasitization of the stem borer larvae. To strengthen this rather low parasitization, efforts are underway to introduce newer parasites into the Philippines, and also, to standardize the procedures of biological control study which can later be used in the international research programs. So far, two dipterous parasites, *Sturmiopsis inferens* Townsend and *Metagonistylum minense* Townsend, have been introduced. Since its introduction, *S. inferens* has been investigated for its parasitic potential and has been mass-reared and field-

Fig. 21. Percentage of male moths showing typical sexual response to abdominal tip extracts from females of different ages. IRRI, 1968.

Fig. 22. Laboratory inoculations of *Sturmiopsis inferens* Towns. IRRI, December 1967 to October 1968.

released. The presently available rearing techniques for *M. minense* are not satisfactory and its maggots, although artificially inoculated on borer larvae, showed less than 2 percent survival. Moreover, at the end of the second generation, all the survivors were males. Further studies on this parasite have been deferred.

Sturmiopsis inferens

Maintenance of culture. In 1968, the fly was continuously reared in the laboratory using the techniques described in the 1967 Annual Report. A total of 4,994 larvae was inoculated in 20 batches. Of these, 1,928 larvae were parasitized, giving an overall parasitization of 42 percent (Fig. 22) as contrasted to 48.87 percent by this fly in 1967, although all experimental procedures followed were the same. Also, during the earlier generations, the female-to-male ratio was generally 1:1 but

later became about 1:1.8. Furthermore, the fertility of a female fly was also considerably reduced and the female flies often died without reaching maturity or before completing their gestation periods. These caused a cumulative reduction in the fly population. To find out whether these effects were due to the continuous inbreeding of the flies, another batch of flies has been obtained from the Commonwealth Institute of Biological Control, Bangalore, India.

Field releases. The details of field release of gravid females and the recovery of the parasitized larvae were described in the 1967 Annual Report. During 1968, 155 gravid females were released at three sites on Luzon Island. Subsequently, 2,675 stem borer larvae were collected from the release sites but no parasitized borer larva was recovered. In earlier field releases, parasitized borer larvae were recovered up to 30 days after the release of adult flies, indicating that the flies completed one generation in nature. The failure of flies in 1968 to parasitize borers in the paddy field could have been due to the weakness of fly cultures as discussed above. This is being further followed up by using more vigorous females from the new culture and making repeated releases in a given area over a period of several months.

Parasitization of host larvae of different ages

An experiment was conducted to determine if the flies can parasitize striped borer larvae of all ages or whether a certain larval stage was most suitable. The larvae used were at 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 days after hatching and were inoculated individually by placing a fly maggot on their lateral segments. The larvae were then reared on rice stem pieces until the pupation of the maggots.

The maggots failed to parasitize 5- to 15-day-old striped borer larvae but a low parasitization of 5.2 percent was recorded for 20-day-old larvae. In the same experiment, the parasitization of 25-day-old larvae averaged 42 percent. These latter larvae used were in their fifth and sixth instars of development. It is thus evident that the maggots need the last instar larvae for optimum parasitization.

Agricultural Engineering

Agricultural machinery research and development activities continued to receive major attention from the Department. This selective approach to mechanization research gained considerable momentum and has started to produce results. A highlight of these activities was the release of the drum-type power thresher for commercial production in the Philippines. The applied machinery research program, aimed at assisting others in the development of new machinery for rice cultivation, is well underway.

Studies on the economics of mechanization were continued with increased emphasis on the performance of commercially available and newly designed agricultural equipment for rice production in the developing countries.

The activities of the Department were directed primarily toward the development of power-operated machinery for rice cultivation in the tropical countries under a contract between the Institute and the United States Agency for International Development. Considerable effort was exerted in testing and evaluating the design of the drum-type power thresher developed in 1967. In November 1968 the thresher was released to three manufacturers for commercial production in the Philippines, and one of them has started the regular manufacture of this machine. A few commercially produced drum-type threshers have been shipped to other tropical countries for testing and evaluation.

The major technical problems encountered with the table-type thresher design were solved in 1968, and a second prototype of the machine was completed and tested. The design is undergoing additional refinements and it is hoped that the table thresher will be ready for commercial production by the end of 1969.

A tractor tillage and mobility study indicated that specially designed rotary tillers could improve tractor mobility under soft wetland conditions. A second experimental machine has been built and will be tested soon.

Designs of power weeders consisting of three and five rows were completed. The performance of the three-row weeder was compared to other weeding methods. A few commercial companies have shown interest in this machine and the design is being forwarded to them.

The development of a paddy stripper combine was initiated. An experimental machine is being built and will be field-tested in the 1969 dry season.

A total of 11 research and development projects were undertaken during 1968. These are described below.

Drum-Type Power Thresher

The development of a second prototype drum thresher has been discussed in the 1967 Annual Report. Based on field tests of this thresher (Fig. 1) in the provinces of Laguna and Isabela, Philippines, some design modifications were made on the separating mechanism. The design of the rotary screen separator was considerably improved

by spiral baffles (Fig. 2) which control the movement of the grain and chaff in the separator.

Two sets of baffles move the material in the separator to two sets of tumbling pockets which elevate and drop the material onto a grain-spreading chute located above the air stream. Mixed grain and straw from the threshing drum are delivered into the wide end of the rotary screen separator where the first set of baffles collects and delivers the material to the initial elevating pocket. As the separator rotates, the material is elevated and dropped onto the grain-spreading chute, which is fitted with guide rails which direct the threshed material into the air stream. As the material goes through the air stream, the relatively light straw is blown out through the rear straw outlet. The heavier grain falls onto the rotary screen and is carried out of the separator. The grain-straw separation is not thorough in the rear portion of the separator. The second set of baffles collects the material from this part of the separator and transfers it to the elevating pockets for a second pass through the air stream.

The first prototype machine was designed on the assumption that the grain could be collected satisfactorily by laying a canvas underneath the rotary separator. Field experience and comments from observers indicated the necessity of elevating the threshed grain for direct delivery into a sack or container. Since the limitations on costs excluded the possibility of using a separate mechanism for elevation and delivery, a simple semi-circular sheet metal trough was fitted under the rotary separator. Three rubber flaps were attached to the rotary separator to sweep and elevate the grain from the trough to the height of a suitable container.

Another premise of this thresher design was that the market will accept a thresher which could thoroughly thresh both dry and wet paddy rice, even though it may only do a reasonable degree of grain-straw separation. The machine has demonstrated excellent threshing performance on both dry (14% m.c.) and freshly harvested (over 30% m.c.) paddy rice. The grain-straw separation is excellent under wet and high-moisture crop conditions. However, under dry conditions, some amount of chaff and dust is present with the grain. Observers have occasionally commented about the desirability of thorough winnowing and cleaning of the grain. Generally, the threshed paddy rice is

Fig. 1. Second prototype drum-type power thresher.

Fig. 2. Schematic drawing showing details of rotary screen separator.

dried to a safe moisture level before it is stored, and better winnowing is performed after the grain has been dried. Nevertheless, it is felt that increased emphasis should be placed on improving the winnowing of the grain in the machine.

Testing and evaluating the drum-type thresher

The thresher was subjected to a series of tests to establish its performance. Its recovery of grain was

better than that of the manual threshing method on a threshing board.

The grain left on the panicles after threshing is the non-recoverable threshing loss. This loss was evaluated for this thresher by carefully hand-stripping all grain left on the panicles and recording the quantity as a percentage of the total amount of grain threshed by the machine. Four 10-minute trials were conducted with two men simultaneously feeding bundles of IR8 paddy at 20 percent grain m.c. The average unrecoverable threshing loss obtained during these tests was 0.97 percent.

The method of feeding and the number of men using the machine have a significant effect on the total machine output and the output per man.

Fig. 3. Three basic methods of feeding the drum-type power thresher.

Tests were conducted to establish the most efficient feeding method and number of men required for threshing with this machine. Figure 3 shows three basic methods of feeding the paddy bundles to the thresher.

Method I is the pick-thresh method in which the men stand at fixed locations near the thresher, pick handfuls of paddy rice from a stack, and then turn and feed the bundles to the threshing drum. The number of men that can conveniently feed a machine is restricted by the length of the drum. Experience has shown that a feeding space of 20

inches per man is required for convenient feeding. During the tests with this method, the number of men was varied from one to five.

Method II is the pick-walk-thresh method in which the men walk continuously in a circular pattern, picking up the paddy bundles and threshing them while walking beside the threshing drum. There is no specific limit to the number of men that can simultaneously thresh by this method. The threshing drum should be long enough to completely thresh the paddy before the men reach the end of the drum. A longer drum would result

Table 1. Drum-type power thresher output using different feeding methods and numbers of men for short-duration threshing trials.*

Method	Threshing method	Number of men in team**	Total or machine output † (kg)	Output per man** (kg)
I	1 man pick-thresh	1	24.9	24.9
I	2 men pick-thresh	2	41.8	20.9
III	1 man pick-transfer and 1 man thresh	2	33.8	16.9
II	2 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	2	32.1	16.1
I	3 men pick-thresh	3	52.5	17.5
III	1 man pick-transfer and 2 men thresh	3	39.5	13.1
II	3 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	3	36.1	12.0
I	4 men pick-thresh	4	61.9	15.5
III	2 men pick-transfer and 2 men thresh	4	54.3	13.6
II	4 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	4	42.2	10.5
I	5 men pick-thresh	5	59.7	11.9
III	2 men pick-transfer and 3 men thresh	5	77.5	15.5
II	5 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	5	54.1	10.8
III	3 men pick-transfer and 3 men thresh	6	86.3	14.4
III	2 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh	6	89.2	14.8
II	6 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	6	61.7	10.2
III	3 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh	7	96.2	13.8
III	2 men pick-transfer and 5 men thresh	7	66.8	9.5
II	7 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	7	64.1	9.2
III	3 men pick-transfer and 5 men thresh	8	76.5	9.6
III	4 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh	8	108.4	13.6
II	8 men pick-walk-thresh, cyclic	8	61.4	7.7

* Test conducted at Bay and Calauan, Laguna, on May 8-10, 1968. Variety — Intan; grain yield per hectare = 4,270 kg at 14% m.c. (average of 3 samples).

** No. of men in the team does not include 1 man who collects and sacks the grain.

† Clean grain threshed per 15 minutes at 14% m.c. (average of 3 trials).

Table 2. Drum-type power thresher output for number of men and method of threshing. 1-hour trials.*

Method no.	Threshing method	Number of men in team**	Total or machine output † (kg/hr)	Output per man † (kg/hr)
III	2 men pick-transfer and 3 men thresh	5	316.2 (79.0)	63.2 (15.8)
III	2 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh	6	358.5 (89.6)	59.7 (14.9)
III	3 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh	7	415.4 (103.8)	59.3 (14.8)
III	4 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh	8	459.6 (114.9)	57.4 (14.4)

* Tests were conducted on May 14-15, 1968. Variety—IR8-68; Grain yield per hectare—7185 kg (14% m.c.).

** Kg of clean threshed grain at 14% m.c.

† Figures in parentheses are computed output values per 15 minutes.

Fig. 4. Threshing performance of the drum-type power thresher using different methods and number of men for feeding.

in ineffective use of the extra threshing surface. During tests, the number of men was varied from two to eight.

Method III is the pick-transfer-thresh method in which the men are split into two groups. Men from the first group, located close to the paddy rice stacks, pick up and pass convenient-sized paddy stalk bundles to the men of the second group, who are located close to the threshing drum and who do the actual threshing. All men are stationed at fixed locations. There is no definite limit to the total number of men which can be used. However, the number of men at the threshing drum is restricted by the length of the drum. In tests with this method, the number of men in each group was varied from one to four.

Table 1 and Fig. 4 show the results of short-duration (15 minutes) tests, each with three replications, conducted at Bay and Calauan, Laguna, in the Philippines on May 8-10, 1968. A total of 22 different combinations of men and methods were tested for threshing output. The rice variety Intan which gave yields of 4,300 kg/ha at 14% m.c. was used in these tests.

For a labor force of up to four men, method I (pick-thresh) gave the highest threshing output. However, with five or more men, method III

Fig. 5. Drum-type thresher produced commercially by local manufacturer A.

Fig. 6. Commercial prototype drum-type thresher by local manufacturer B.

Fig. 7. Commercial prototype drum-type thresher by local manufacturer C.

(pick-transfer-thresh) gave a better output. Method II (pick-walk-thresh) consistently gave a poor output.

Trials of longer duration with methods which had given encouraging results in the short-duration tests were repeated with the high-yielding IR8 variety (yields of 7,200 kg/ha) at 14% m.c. Table 2 and Fig. 4 show the results of the continuous 1-hour test using four combinations of men and methods. The results consistently indicated a slightly higher output than the 15-minute trials, perhaps because a higher yielding variety was used.

The testing and evaluation phase of the drum-type power thresher was completed during the year. A number of manufacturers have indicated their interest in manufacturing this thresher in the Philippines, and the design was released to three of them before the end of the year. Quotations were invited for the supply of threshers for field evaluation in other tropical rice-producing countries.

The three Philippine manufacturers built their own prototype threshers to suit their manufacturing facilities, i.e., the machines were patterned after the IRRI thresher but differed in structural details. One of the manufacturers has successfully developed the thresher (Fig. 5) and has completed the jigs, dies, and other tooling required for regular manufacture. Ten of these threshers are being tested and evaluated in the Philippines and in other tropical countries. The other two manufacturers have completed, and are further testing and improving, their first prototype machines (Figs. 6 and 7).

The first prototype machines of these manufacturers have also been tested and evaluated at the Institute, and the recommendations for necessary modifications have been made. The testing of these machines had to be repeated several times to evaluate the modifications made.

The first commercially produced thresher is an all-steel single shell type construction and weighs 500 kg. One machine was sent to West Pakistan in November 1968 for field trials, and initial reports from that country indicate that an output of 500 lb/hour was achieved. Several manufacturers in West Pakistan have shown interest in building this thresher, so that arrangements are now being made to release the design in West Pakistan. Machines also are being shipped to India, Ceylon, East

Pakistan, Vietnam, Taiwan and Thailand for testing and evaluation. As soon as satisfactory test results are obtained, local companies in the tropical countries will be encouraged to manufacture the machine. Information about and drawings of this thresher are available to interested manufacturers.

Table-type Power Thresher

The design of a table-type power thresher was described in the 1967 Annual Report. The machine originally utilized a one-unit flat circular threshing surface with an integral radial fan and a circular comb-like wire screen. Three major problems, however, were encountered: 1) Long paddy rice stems were caught in the U-shaped wire loops and tended to clog the flat threshing surface, 2) The wire screen was ineffective in achieving grain-straw separation at the high threshing surface and screen velocities, and 3) Excessive grain was lost from the top of the machine during the feeding of the paddy bundles for threshing.

After several failures, the integral thresher-fan-screen approach was scrapped, and a new table thresher was built (Fig. 8) which differed basically from the original concept in three respects.

1. The wire loops were replaced by flat iron pieces, somewhat similar in shape to the loops, to prevent clogging.

2. The threshing surface and the screen were built in separate units and rotated at different speeds. The screen rotated in the same direction but at a slower speed than the threshing surface. The threshed material was easier to separate because of the smaller relative velocity between the screen openings and the moving material on top of the screen.

3. A sheet metal cover with four feeding spouts and an air intake with a control baffle at the center was designed for the machine. This cover reduced the scattering of the grain by guiding the shooting grain back into the machine.

Figure 9 shows a schematic drawing of the new thresher. During threshing, the grain and chaff are thrown at the periphery of the top cover walls. The grain and chaff then fall onto the rotating flat circular screen. The grain passes through the screen openings and the straw is pushed out radially by the two spring steel wire prongs mounted on the

Fig. 8. Second IRRI prototype table thresher in operation.

Fig. 9. Schematic drawing of second IRRI prototype table thresher.

threshing surface. Fan blades, mounted on the underside of the threshing surface, blow a radial air stream just below the screen. The material falling through the screen is winnowed by blowing out the chaff, dirt, and straw through the peripheral opening. Clean grain drops onto a stationary circular pan where it is swept to the delivery spout by two rubber flaps attached to the underside of the screen.

The new machine is simple in design with only two major rotating components. It is relatively lighter and would be cheaper to manufacture than the drum-type thresher. This type of thresher, however, requires more ground area for threshing than the drum-type thresher because of the radial

Table 3. Output and loss test of IRRI table-type paddy thresher powered by a 4.2-hp (gasoline) engine.*

Item	Duration (minutes)								Average
	Output test					Loss test			
	60	27.5	15	15	17.5	5	5	5	
Weight of threshed grain at threshing, kg	228.90	131.65	68.97	56.56	84.04	18.35	16.70	29.10	
Average m.c. (%) at threshing	32	32	19.3	19.3	19.3	20.5	20.5	20.5	
Weight of threshed grain at 14% m.c.	181.78	104.96	63.91	52.41	77.88	16.96	15.44	26.90	
Thresher output (kg/hr)	181.78	229.08	255.64	209.64	167.00	203.52	185.28	322.80	231.84
Fuel consumption (liter/hr)	0.54	0.488	0.97						0.67
Variety	IR5	IR5	IR5	IR5	IR5	IR8	IR8	IR8	
Grain yield, kg/ha	5456	5456	5456	5456	5456				
Grain loss									
a. Threshing loss (unthreshed grain on panicles after threshing)						1.164	3.128	4.27	2.85
Threshing loss (%)						0.567	1.660	1.305	1.18
Threshing efficiency (%)						99.43	98.31	98.68	98.81
b. Cleaning efficiency, (%)									
Chaff and empty grains that go with the threshed grain (percentage by weight of the total grain threshed)						6.27	2.99	4.81	4.6

* Method of feeding: 4 men pick-thresh

arrangement of the paddy stacks and the radial location of the thresher operators.

The machine was field-tested at the Institute Farm in December 1968. Table 3 shows the preliminary test results on two rice varieties and includes data on the machine output and the non-recoverable threshing loss. The average output for four operators was 228.80 kg/hr. The non-recoverable threshing loss was 1.18 percent of the machine output. The average fuel consumption of the table-type thresher was 0.67 liter/hour, which is about two-thirds of the consumption of the drum-type thresher. Since both machines are equipped with identical 4.2-hp engines, the test indicates a lower power consumption for the table-type thresher. Trials with a smaller engine will be conducted to further reduce the cost of this thresher. Additional design work is planned to

deliver the chaff and straw to a single location rather than at the periphery of the machine.

The machine has demonstrated excellent performance during the initial trials and because of the simple design and lower costs, it offers possibilities of wider acceptance than the drum-type thresher. Extensive field trials in the Philippines and in other tropical countries will be undertaken after the completion of the final prototype machine. It is hoped that the machine will be released for commercial production by the end of 1969.

Tractor Tillage and Mobility Studies

An experimental wetland rotary tiller was fabricated following the design reported in the 1967 Annual Report, and was subjected to a series of tests under submerged wetland conditions.

Figure 10 shows the rotary tiller (henceforth referred to as the IRRRI rotary tiller) being operated under wetland conditions. The effect of tillage at the low and high tiller blade velocities of 2.10 m/sec and 3.77 m/sec, respectively, when the tractor was traveling in the II speed (0.75 m/sec), is illustrated in Fig. 11. An objective of these tests was to study the pushing behavior of the tiller on the tractor under relatively hard and soft wetland conditions. Tests comparing the IRRRI rotary tiller with a commercially available conventional rotary tiller of similar weight and width were also conducted.

A 55-hp conventional four-wheel rubber-tired tractor equipped with a standard 540 rpm PTO and a standard Category II three-point linkage was used in comparing the two tillers. Four rubber-tipped crown-type lug wheels (Fig. 10), one on each side of the two rear wheels, were fitted to improve the field mobility of the tractor. Table 4 lists the specifications of the tractor and its accessories, while Table 5 lists the specifications of the two rotary tillers used in the tests.

The average slippage of the two tractor drive wheels was used to indicate the pushing reaction from the tiller to the tractor. High wheel slippage indicated lower pushing reaction for a specific combination of tractor speed and tiller blade velocity. The distance travelled by the two rear wheels in two complete revolutions was measured on the ground with stakes by two men walking beside the tractor rear wheels as shown in Fig. 10. The average wheel travel distance in two wheel

Fig. 10. Experimental rotary tiller being tested under wetland conditions.

A

B

Fig. 11. Effect of tillage at II tractor travel speed (0.75 m/sec) and (A) low tiller blade velocity of 2.10 m/sec; (B) high tiller blade velocity of 3.77 m/sec.

revolutions was computed. A limited slip differential lock was used in all the tests to avoid excessive slippage on any one wheel. The percentage of wheel slippage was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Percentage of wheel slippage} = \frac{\text{Travel distance of rear wheel per 2 revolutions on concrete} - \text{Measured rear wheel travel distance per 2 wheel revolutions during test}}{\text{Travel distance of rear wheel per 2 revolutions on concrete}} \times 100$$

Table 4. Specifications of the tractor and attached accessories.

Maximum engine horsepower:	55 hp	Total front frame ballast:	112.8	kg
Maximum PTO horsepower:	47.5 hp	Total front wheel ballast:	40.4	kg
Weight:	1882.4 kg	Total weight of rubber-tipped crown-type lug wheels attached to both sides of rear wheels:	476.0	kg
Tractor travel speed based on zero slippage at 1800 engine rpm:	1st 0.48 m/sec			
	2nd 0.75 m/sec			
	3rd 1.27 m/sec			
	4th 1.73 m/sec			
Total tractor weight with accessories			2511.6	kg

Table 5. Specifications of rotary tillers.

Specification	IRRI experimental wetland rotary tiller	Conventional rotary tiller
Tilling width	1.6 m (A 30-cm length in the middle of the rotary tiller has no blade)	1.6 m
Number of blades	48	36
Shape of blades	30 cm long, 13 cm wide, flat blades	Conventional Japanese spading blades
Blade arrangement	Alternate arrangement of 12 blades, 6 for tilling and 6 for support, in 4 sections	Each set of 4 blades is mounted spirally at 18-cm spacing
Outside diameter of rotary tiller	100 cm	50 cm
Drive method of tilling shaft	Left side chain drive	Left side chain drive
Weight	450 kg	430 kg
Peripheral tiller blade velocity at 1800 engine rpm	1st 2.10 m/sec (40 rpm) 2nd 2.66 m/sec (51 rpm) 3rd 3.00 m/sec (57 rpm) 4th 3.77 m/sec (72 rpm)	1st 2.78 m/sec (106 rpm) 2nd 4.07 m/sec (155 rpm) 3rd 5.56 m/sec (213 rpm)

The tillage depth was fixed at 12 cm by the depth control lever on the tractor hydraulic system. However, there were unavoidable variations due to the uneven ground and wheel sinkage. To reduce the effect of these variations, the

working depth was measured with a measuring stick at three spots after every test run. The depth at certain fixed soil penetrating resistances was measured by a soil penetrometer with a 30° cone and a 3.2-sq-cm base area. Five penetrometer

depth readings at a soil resistance of 35 psi and 70 psi were taken before every test in an area just ahead of the tractor.

The IRRI rotary tiller had provisions for four peripheral blade velocities while the conventional tiller had three blade velocities. Four forward tractor travel speeds were used, thus providing 16 combinations of tractor travel speeds and tiller blade velocities for the IRRI rotary tiller and 12 combinations for the conventional rotary tiller. Tests were also made to determine the rear wheel slippage at different tractor speeds while the power take-off drive to the tiller was disengaged. These tests indicated the wheel slippage when the tractor was towing a free-rolling tiller. Finally, tests were conducted to establish the tractor wheel slippage without the rotary tiller in the four forward tractor travel speeds. To minimize errors due to variations in the soil conditions, each test was conducted on an undisturbed part of the field.

Experimental data from three tests, (1) IRRI rotary tiller on relatively harder soil conditions, (2) conventional rotary tiller on relatively harder wetland conditions, and (3) IRRI rotary tiller on relatively softer wetland conditions, are presented in Tables 6, 7 and 8 and plotted in Figs. 12, 13 and 14, respectively.

Figure 12 and Table 6 show the relationship between the tractor travel speed and rear wheel slippage at different blade velocities of the IRRI rotary tiller under relatively harder wetland conditions. The pushing effect of the IRRI rotary tiller was indicated by the substantial reduction in wheel slippage whenever the tiller was powered from the tractor PTO. The pushing effect of the IRRI rotary tiller, under relatively harder soil condition, was so pronounced that the tractor rear wheels sometimes registered negative slippage.

Results of a comparison between the pushing reaction of the IRRI rotary tiller and that of a conventional rotary tiller, conducted under similar soil conditions, are shown in Tables 6 and 7 and Figs. 12 and 13. The specifications of the conventional rotary tiller used are listed in Table 5. Figures 12 and 13 show apparent differences in rear wheel slippage between the IRRI rotary tiller and the conventional rotary tiller, with the former having less rear wheel slippage than the latter. At the same peripheral blade velocity, the tractor wheel slippage of the IRRI rotary tiller was con-

Fig. 12. Tractor rear wheel slippage at different tractor forward travel speeds and different IRRI rotary tiller drive conditions under harder wetland conditions.

Fig. 13. Tractor rear wheel slippage at different tractor forward speeds and different conventional rotary-tiller drive conditions.

siderably lower. One reason for this is the increased soil reaction of the IRRI rotary tiller due to the 30 cm by 13 cm flat blades. The sharp conventional spading blades give good tillage, but cannot provide enough soil reaction under soft wetland conditions. The larger diameter of the IRRI rotary tiller also provides an increased

Fig. 14. Tractor rear wheel slippage at different tractor forward travel speeds and different IRR rotary-tiller drive conditions under softer wetland conditions.

Fig. 15. Schematic drawing of rotary tiller blade motion.

horizontal component from the soil reaction.

In comparison to the conventional rotary tiller, a wider variation in tractor wheel slippage was observed when the blade velocity of the IRR rotary tiller was changed. The wider shaded bands in Figs. 12 and 14 indicate this increased variation in wheel slippage. This shows that the pushing force of the IRR rotary tiller is influenced more by the

peripheral blade velocity, indicating that the pushing force could be varied by changing the tiller blade velocity.

Figure 14 plots the results of tests with the IRR rotary tiller under softer soil conditions. The rear wheel slippage of the tractor without the tiller

Fig. 16. Tractor rear wheel slippage at different tractor forward travel speeds and different IRR rotary tiller drive conditions under very soft wetland conditions. Tiller with support blades only.

Fig. 17. Tractor rear wheel slippage at three constant tractor travel speeds and different IRR rotary tiller blade velocities. Rotary tiller with support blades only.

was excessively high under these soil conditions than under harder soil conditions (Fig. 12). However, with the IRRI rotary tiller, the tractor rear wheel slippage was still lower than with the conventional rotary tiller under relatively harder soil conditions (Fig. 13). This indicates that the IRRI rotary tiller is more effective in reducing tractor rear wheel slippage under softer soil conditions.

The study indicated that slower tiller blade peripheral velocity or higher tractor travel speed decreases the tractor rear wheel slippage under both soft and hard soil conditions. An increase in the tilling pitch (Fig. 15) increases the pushing reaction and results in decreased tractor rear wheel slippage.

It is generally known that the sharp tilling blades cut the soil with less soil reaction, thus providing the tractor with less flotation and pushing force. The machine used in the earlier tests consisted of six alternate tilling and supporting blades spaced 12 cm apart on the four sections of the rotor. To increase the horizontal and upward soil reaction, all the six tilling blades from each section of the IRRI rotary tiller were removed, thus doubling the pitch of cut for the same tiller blade velocity and tractor travel speed. The increased spacing between the blades helped to remove the mud from the rotor and reduced rotor clogging.

The machine was tested under extremely soft soil conditions with only six supporting blades in each section of the rotor. To simplify the tests, the second travel speed of the tractor and the second gear of the rotary tiller were not used. The experimental field conditions and the test results are recorded in Table 9 and Figs. 16 and 17. The field used was plowed and puddled 40 days before the test was conducted. At the time of the test the field was flooded to a 5-cm depth in contrast with the previous tests in which the fields were flooded without any tillage. The soil during this test, therefore, was much softer than during the previous tests, resulting in increased tractor wheel sinkage and tilling depth. The difference in soil condition is indicated by the 100-percent tractor wheel slippage in the operation of the trailed rotary tiller although the penetrometer depth did not indicate too much difference from the previous tests.

Figure 16 shows the relationship between the

tractor travel speed and rear wheel slippage of the tiller under various conditions of operation. The slippage on the rear wheels was excessively high throughout the tests, reaching 100 percent whenever the PTO was disengaged. A reason for this seems to be the high rolling resistance of the wheels due to excessive sinkage under the softer soil conditions. Another possible explanation is that, in spite of the larger pitch of cut, the supporting blades did not provide a sufficient horizontal pushing force, perhaps because the supporting blades make a small rake angle (Fig. 15) with the ground and slip on the soil surface without biting the soil the way tilling blades do. It seems that a relatively large blade rake angle is more appropriate for improving pushing reaction under extremely soft soil conditions.

The wheel slippage increased whenever the tractor speed was increased (Fig. 16). As this result contradicted those of earlier tests, further studies are necessary to clear the discrepancy.

Figure 17 shows the relation between the tiller blade velocity and the rear wheel slippage under different tractor travel speeds. The slower blade velocity decreased the slippage when the tractor was traveling in the first and third gear speeds. However, when the tractor was in the fourth gear, the tiller blade velocity had no significant effect on the rear wheel slippage. This result shows that with relatively slower tractor travel speeds, increasing the pitch of cut by decreasing the peripheral blade velocity will improve the pushing force even under very soft soil conditions. It suggests the possibility of further reducing the blade velocity to bring it closer to the tractor travel speed in the low gear to achieve maximum mobility.

The salient points of the above study are:

1. The IRRI rotary tiller decreases the tractor wheel slippage to a greater degree than a conventional rotary tiller.
2. With the IRRI rotary tiller there was a significant reduction in wheel slippage when the tractor speed was increased under the soft soil conditions as compared to a conventional rotary tiller. The results differed, however, under extremely soft soil conditions.
3. A slower peripheral blade velocity for the IRRI rotary tiller seems desirable for increased tractor mobility under all soil conditions.

Table 6. IRRI experimental wetland rotary tiller test* under relatively harder soil conditions.

Test no.	Tractor travel speed based on zero slippage		Peripheral tiller blade velocity		Tilling depth** (cm)	Rear wheel travel distance per 2 revolutions† (m)	Cone penetrometer depth cm at ††		Slippage of rear wheels %	
	m/sec	gear	m/sec	gear			35 psi	70 psi		
1	0.48	1st	2.10	1st	10.7	8.96	18.2	22.4	2.8	
2	0.75	2nd	2.10	1st	7.9	9.01	16.8	23.2	2.3	
3	1.27	3rd	2.10	1st	9.9	9.19	17.2	20.8	0.3	
4	1.73	4th	2.10	1st	9.4	9.09	13.2	18.4	1.4	
5	0.48	1st	2.66	2nd	11.2	8.72	16.2	20.0	5.4	
6	0.75	2nd	2.66	2nd	10.8	8.94	15.0	19.2	3.0	
7	1.27	3rd	2.66	2nd	12.2	9.28	13.4	21.0	-0.7	
8	1.73	4th	2.66	2nd	12.6	9.17	14.4	23.4	0.5	
9	0.48	1st	3.00	3rd	10.9	8.87	16.0	21.4	3.8	
10	0.75	2nd	3.00	3rd	8.6	8.94	14.2	20.8	3.0	
11	1.27	3rd	3.00	3rd	10.3	9.06	14.2	21.4	1.7	
12	1.73	4th	3.00	3rd	9.9	9.24	16.8	20.8	-0.7	
13	0.48	1st	3.77	4th	12.4	8.87	14.0	21.2	3.8	
14	0.75	2nd	3.77	4th	10.7	8.99	15.8	23.4	2.5	
15	1.27	3rd	3.77	4th	10.3	8.96	13.8	23.4	2.8	
16	1.73	4th	3.77	4th	8.6	9.23	13.6	20.8	-0.1	
17	0.48	1st	With rotary tiller trailed,				7.81	17.2	21.8	15.3
18	0.75	2nd	PTO disengaged.				7.98	16.4	22.4	13.4
19	1.27	3rd					8.07	16.2	21.2	12.5
20	1.73	4th					8.02	15.4	21.0	13.0
21	0.48	1st	Tractor only,				7.95	15.6	21.0	13.8
22	0.75	2nd	rotary tiller removed.				8.01	17.6	22.0	13.1
23	1.27	3rd					8.07	15.0	20.2	12.5
24	1.73	4th					8.22	14.2	18.6	10.8

* Tractor used: Ford 4000 (55 hp)
 Tractor engine speed: 1800 rpm
 No-slip travel distance of tractor rear wheel per 2 revolutions on concrete: 9.22 m

Field condition: Loamy soil flooded to 5 cm for 24 hrs and covered with rice stubble and harvested straw.
 Average depth of cone penetrometer: 15.4 cm at 35 psi
 21.4 cm at 70 psi

** Average of three readings.

† Average of both rear wheels.

†† Average of five readings.

Since the blade angle of the rotary tiller was fixed at 45° from the tangent in previous tests, the effect of blade angle on the pushing force was not studied in this experiment. A new IRRI rotary tiller was fabricated (Fig. 18) with eight adjustable blade angles in five sections. The tiller rotor has a 0.85 m diameter and 1.6 m tilling width, and the

machine weighs 450 kg. The blades consist of 12 x 6½ x 1/8 inch flat steel plates reinforced with 3/4 x 1/8 inch angle iron on the tilling edges. The angle of the blades can be changed by selecting the proper bolt hole positions, permitting four angle positions (10°, 30°, 50°, and 70° from the rotor radius.) This IRRI rotary tiller with adjustable

Table 7. Conventional rotary tiller test* under relatively harder soil conditions.

Test no.	Tractor travel speed based on zero slippage		Peripheral tiller blade velocity		Tilling depth** (cm)	Rear wheel travel distance per 2 revolutions † (m)	Cone penetrometer depth cm at ††		Slippage of rear wheels (%)	
	m/sec	gear	m/sec	gear			35 psi	70 psi		
1	0.48	1st	2.78	1st	12.0	8.21	15.2	21.6	11.0	
2	0.75	2nd	2.78	1st	11.9	8.37	12.0	18.8	9.2	
3	1.27	3rd	2.78	1st	11.9	8.53	12.8	24.4	7.5	
4	1.73	4th	2.78	1st	9.0	8.44	11.0	18.0	8.5	
5	0.48	1st	4.07	2nd	11.7	8.17	12.8	19.2	11.4	
6	0.75	2nd	4.07	2nd	12.3	8.32	14.0	20.0	9.8	
7	1.27	3rd	4.07	2nd	11.0	8.47	12.2	20.6	8.1	
8	1.73	4th	4.07	2nd	9.0	8.65	12.4	21.4	6.2	
9	0.48	1st	5.56	3rd	11.8	8.26	13.4	21.0	10.4	
10	0.75	2nd	5.56	3rd	11.3	8.45	13.4	21.2	8.4	
11	1.27	3rd	5.56	3rd	11.8	8.46	12.0	20.8	8.2	
12	1.73	4th	5.56	3rd	12.8	8.47	11.6	21.4	8.1	
13	0.48	1st	With rotary				7.48	11.6	21.4	18.9
14	0.75	2nd	tiller trailed,				7.69	13.2	20.6	16.6
15	1.27	3rd	PTO disengaged.				7.65	11.0	20.6	17.0
16	1.73	4th					7.56	13.8	22.4	18.0
17	0.48	1st	Tractor only,				7.77	12.0	20.6	15.7
18	0.75	2nd	rotary tiller				7.83	13.4	22.4	15.1
19	1.27	3rd	removed.				7.88	14.4	22.2	14.5
20	1.73	4th					7.66	14.6	23.4	16.9

* Tractor used: Ford 4000 (55 hp)
 Tractor engine speed: 1800 rpm
 No-slip travel distance of tractor rear wheel per 2 revolutions on concrete: 9.22 m

Field condition: Loamy soil flooded to 10 cm for 6 hrs and covered with rice stubble and harvested straw.
 Average depth of cone penetrometer: 12.8 cm at 35 psi
 21.2 cm at 70 psi

** Average of both rear wheels.

† Average of both rear wheels.

†† Average of five readings.

Table 8. IRRI experimental wetland rotary tiller test under relatively softer soil conditions.

Test no.	Tractor travel speed based on zero slippage		Peripheral tiller blade velocity		Tilling depth ** (cm)	Rear wheel travel distance per 2 revolutions † (m)	Cone penetrometer depth cm at ††		Slippage of rear wheels (%)
	m/sec	gear	m/sec	gear			35 psi	70 psi	
1	0.48	1st	2.10	1st	13.0	8.67	20.6	30.4	6.0
2	0.75	2nd	2.10	1st	10.3	8.75	33.4	39.0	5.1
3	1.27	3rd	2.10	1st	13.2	8.85	27.2	31.4	4.0
4	1.73	4th	2.10	1st	9.5	8.81	18.6	29.0	4.4
5	0.48	1st	2.66	2nd	9.3	8.52	17.8	27.6	7.6
6	0.75	2nd	2.66	2nd	10.0	8.71	19.2	31.4	5.5
7	1.27	3rd	2.66	2nd	10.2	8.70	17.2	32.4	5.6
8	1.73	4th	2.66	2nd	10.3	8.96	18.8	32.4	2.8
9	0.48	1st	3.00	3rd	11.7	8.62	16.0	25.4	6.5
10	0.75	2nd	3.00	3rd	10.7	8.58	15.4	33.6	6.9
11	1.27	3rd	3.00	3rd	9.7	8.70	16.6	29.0	5.6
12	1.73	4th	3.00	3rd	10.3	8.86	17.0	34.0	3.9
13	0.48	1st	3.77	4th	12.5	8.34	16.2	26.8	9.5
14	0.75	2nd	3.77	4th	11.5	8.44	17.6	28.4	8.5
15	1.27	3rd	3.77	4th	8.9	8.66	13.2	24.0	6.1
16	1.73	4th	3.77	4th	9.3	8.90	13.0	27.4	3.5
17	0.48	1st	With rotary			6.27	14.0	32.2	32.0
18	0.75	2nd	tiller trailed,			7.00	17.2	28.4	24.1
19	1.27	3rd	PTO disengaged,			6.94	19.0	25.8	24.7
20	1.73	4th				6.96	18.0	27.8	24.5
21	0.48	1st	Tractor only,			7.02	21.2	29.6	23.9
22	0.75	2nd	rotary tiller			7.26	18.6	27.6	21.3
23	1.27	3rd	removed.			7.35	16.4	24.6	20.3
24	1.73	4th				7.46	17.0	26.8	19.1

* Tractor used: Ford 4000 (55 hp)
 Tractor engine speed: 1800 rpm
 No-slip travel distance of tractor rear wheel per 2 revolutions on concrete: 9.22 m

Field condition: Loamy soil flooded to 5 cm for 5 days and covered with rice stubble and harvested straw.
 Average depth of cone penetrometer: 18.3 cm at 35 psi
 29.4 cm at 70 psi

** Average of three readings.

† Average of both rear wheels.

†† Average of five readings.

Table 9. IRRI experimental wetland rotary tiller test* under extremely soft soil conditions.

Test no.	Tractor travel speed based on zero slippage		Peripheral tiller blade velocity		Tilling depth** (cm)	Rear wheel travel distance per 2 revs† (m)	Cone penetrometer depth cm at ††		Slippage of rear wheels (%)
	m/sec	gear	m/sec	gear			35 psi	70 psi	
1	0.48	1st	2.10	1st	29.3	3.55	22.8	27.6	61.5
2	1.27	3rd	2.10	1st	28.7	2.85	22.0	29.8	69.1
3	1.73	4th	2.10	1st	30.0	1.15	21.4	30.8	87.5
4	0.48	1st	3.00	3rd	29.0	1.80	20.6	31.6	80.5
5	1.27	3rd	3.00	3rd	30.8	1.57	19.4	28.6	83.0
6	1.73	4th	3.00	3rd	30.7	1.36	20.5	36.0	85.2
7	0.48	1st	3.77	4th	27.7	1.39	23.7	29.3	84.9
8	1.27	3rd	3.77	4th	32.7	1.39	25.4	29.5	84.9
9	1.73	4th	3.77	4th	27.5	1.08	23.0	29.8	88.3
10	0.48	1st	With rotary tiller			0	23.0	29.8	100.0
11	1.27	3rd	trailed PTO			0	23.0	29.8	100.0
12	1.73	4th	disengaged			0	23.0	29.8	100.0
13	0.48	1st	Without rotary tiller,			0.75	23.4	30.2	91.9
14	1.27	3rd	tractor only			0	23.4	30.2	100.0
15	1.73	4th				0	23.4	30.2	100.0

* Tractor used: Ford 4000 (55 hp) equipped with rubber-tipped crown-type lug wheels

Implement used: 1.6 m long, 1 m diameter IRRI experimental wetland rotary tiller with supporting blades only

Tractor engine speed: 1800 rpm

No-slip travel distance of tractor rear wheel per 2 revolutions on concrete: 9.22 m

** Average of three readings.

† Average of both rear wheels.

†† Average of five readings.

Field condition: Loamy soil puddled 40 days before the test, flooded to 5 cm for 1 week, covered with heavy weeds

Average depth of cone penetrometer: 22.5 cm at 35 psi
30.2 cm at 70 psi

Fig. 18. Second IIRRI experimental wetland rotary tiller with adjustable blades.

angle blade will be field-tested to determine the optimum blade angle and optimum peripheral blade velocity for maximum forward and upward reactions under soft soil conditions.

Use of Mechanical Power for Rotary Weeding

The design of a three-row prototype power weeder using a portable rotary power saw engine was described in the 1967 Annual Report. The machine used a back-mounted, 50-cc, two-stroke, high-speed gasoline engine equipped with a centrifugal clutch. The power from the engine was transferred through a partly flexible shaft to a 40:1 reduction worm gear box. Three weeding rotors were mounted on the worm gear shaft which rotated at speeds of 110 to 130 rpm. The worm gear box offered high speed reduction with minimum addition of weight.

The main objective of this project was to use a rather light-weight machine to achieve maximum field coverage at a shallow practical weeding depth. The weeder blades were further tested and modified to provide self-cleaning action, adequate ground support, and enough cutting-scraping action for proper weeding. The blades were designed to provide adequate ground reaction and avoid excessive machine sinkage. The cutting and scraping edges of the blades were designed for shallow working depths of 2 to 3 cm (Fig. 19), since a greater depth would consume power with-

out any additional benefit. Rotor blades and spokes were designed in such a way as to prevent weeds and mud from clinging to them. The 12½-inch diameter rotors equipped with six blades provided good slippage with minimum traction and shallow soil working ability.

In their early growth stages, rice plants are flexible and can be safely bent to a 3- to 4-inch height. A 12½-inch diameter rotor provides enough axle clearance for the plants in the rows to bend and pass under during weeding. In some field trials at IIRRI, 18-inch tall rice plants were weeded with this machine. The plants were able to again stand erect after weeding without any adverse effects. Guide-shields have been attached to the machine to direct the rows of rice plants into the space between the rotors. These shields also prevent the plants from getting caught by the edges of the rotor blades. Two blade-mounting arrangements were built for easy adjustment to suit the considerable variation found in row spacing. The minimum clearance between two rotors for one row of plants is 9 cm. In crops planted at 25-cm row spacing, a width of 16 cm is available for each weeding blade. It seems difficult to maintain the minimum 9-cm spacing for rows if fixed-width blades are used for all row spacings. Blades of variable width may have to be designed to meet the variations in row spacing.

Efforts were also made to reduce operator fatigue by reducing the weight of the machine and

Fig. 19. Exploded view of the three-row IIRRI experimental power weeder with improved shields for guiding plants in rows and sliding hitch.

by studying its various suspension and mounting arrangements. The flexible shaft arrangement of the first experimental machine permitted the strapping of the engine on the operator's back. During weeding only 12 kg out of the total weight of 24 kg was supported by the operator. However, at the end of the row, the operator had to lift the weeding rotor weighing 12 kg which was located at the end of a 1.2-m-long shaft. Considerable effort was required to do this.

It was felt that an alternate design in which the engine weight could be balanced against the rotor weight would result in reduced lifting effort at the ends of the rows. A second machine was designed (Fig. 20,A) in which the engine and weeding rotor were connected by an enclosed rigid shaft. A sliding hitch suspension enabled the operator to balance the engine weight against the rotor when turning at the end of the rows. This arrangement has been preferred by most of the operators who have used this weeder. As the engine and worm reduction gear box of the first experimental machine were heavy, a smaller 32.5-cc engine and a lighter worm reduction gear box (35:1) were used in the second experimental machine.

During the preliminary trials, problems were encountered with the plant guide shields. Lighter but rigid guide shields (Fig. 19) were later developed for this three-row weeder. The weeder with the new guide shields weighed 19 kg, a reduction of 5 kg from the earlier design.

A new five-row power weeder (Fig. 20,B) weighing 27 kg was also designed using a 50-cc engine and the new type of plant guide shields. During the preliminary trials, the engine was found to have sufficient power to operate the five-row weeder; however, the machine was too heavy and difficult to operate. The tests, therefore, were concentrated on the three-row machine.

IRRI power weeder test

During the 1968 dry season, the portable three-row IRRI power weeder (Fig. 20,A) was tested on rice plants at different growth stages to determine whether the 5-inch rotor axle clearance was sufficient for the plants to bend and pass under the axle without any significant damage.

Table 10 lists the age and height of the plants, the rate of weeding, fuel consumption, and the number of hills damaged during one weeding

Fig. 20. IRRI experimental power weeders operating in the field. (A) 3-row (B) 5-row.

operation. The machine required an average of 15.84 man-hours to weed a hectare and consumed 0.70 liter of fuel per hour (11.09 liters/ha). The ideal time to weed, to avoid physical damage to the plants during weeding is from 22 to 38 days after transplanting.

Comparative evaluation of IRRI power weeder

An experiment was conducted in the 1968 wet season to compare the performance of the IRRI three-row power weeder with the commonly practiced and recommended weeding methods under low-land conditions. The effects of the weeders on rice yields, weed growth, and plant damage were evaluated. Chianung 242 and IR8-68 were transplanted in a field that was subdivided

Fig. 21. Effect of different weeding methods on weed population and tiller number per square meter of IR8-68 at 45 days after transplanting, IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Note: The bars in each group are superimposed and each should be read from the bottom of the scale, or 0. Example: In the first grouped bar, the number of tillers per square meter should read 236; broadleaves 48; grasses 12; and sedges 0.

into plots with a 1-meter strip between them to facilitate power weeding. The plots treated with herbicides were enclosed by levees to prevent the diffusion of the chemicals to adjacent plots. The field was fertilized with 70 kg of ammonium sulfate during the last harrowing. Grass was seeded 2 days after the fertilizer was applied. Standard water management and optimum pest control were practiced during the test.

Only a few grass seeds germinated in the control plots. It seems that the broadleaf, *Monochoria vaginalis* (L) Presl., outgrew grass due to its early stand.

Figures 21 and 22 show the effects of different weeding methods on tiller and weed counts at 45 days after transplanting. A highly significant difference in weed population was observed

between the control and the treated plots. The experiment indicated that the mechanically treated plots (1 to 8) showed more weeds than those treated with herbicides. There was no significant difference among the non-chemical methods of weeding (manual weeding, manual rotary weeding, and power weeding). There was a fairly uniform number of tillers per square meter, indicating that the number of tillers damaged during weeding was minimal.

Rice yields, weed weights at harvest, and other data are shown in Table 11. Plots treated with MCPA and then weeded using the IRRI power weeder gave the highest yield and the highest net increase in rough rice. The most expensive weed control treatments were hand weeding and manual rotary weeding.

Fig. 22. Effect of different weeding methods on weed population and tiller number per square meter of Chianung 242 at 45 days after transplanting, IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Note: The bars in each group are superimposed and each should be read from the bottom of the scale, or 0. Example: In the first grouped bar, the number of tillers per square meter should read 136; broadleaves 84; grasses 32; and sedges 20.

Table 10. Performance of IRRI power weeder on plants of different height.*

Plot	Plant age (DAT)**	Plant height (cm)	Rate of machine (man-hr/ha)	Fuel consumption (liter/hr)	Hills damaged/ha	Remarks
1	18	10-20	18.5	0.72	666	Hills buried in soft mud which did not recover as inspected 10 days after weeding.
	18	10-20	20.8	0.71	832	
2	22	20-25	16.4	0.74	0	Fairly good performance: damaged hills were mostly those not in a straight row.
	22	20-25	13.9	0.75	56	
3	24	25-30	13.8	0.70	83	
	24	25-30	12.4	0.66	50	
4	26	30-35	16.7	0.69	33	
5	38	41-50	12.0	0.66	0	Plants that had been bent during weeding were found to have recovered, as inspected 10 days after weeding.
	38	41-50	13.9	0.62	0	
6	50	60 ⁺	20.0	0.75	400	Bent and broken tillers; sprouts seen growing as inspected 10 days after weeding.
Average			15.84	0.70		

* Data taken from results of 30-minute trials.

** Days after transplanting.

Manufacturers of portable rotary power saws have shown interest in the design of this machine, and drawings and reports of tests are being forwarded to them. It is felt that a light-weight portable power unit with a number of quick-change attachments for weeding, harvesting and spraying can find a substantial market in the tropical rice-growing countries.

Application of Anhydrous Ammonia with Small Tractors

Previous experiments by the Agronomy and Agricultural Engineering Departments of the Institute have established that anhydrous ammonia (82% N)

is a promising fertilizer material for flooded rice fields. However, suitable equipment for applying it are not available. The growing popularity of small tractors for tropical rice production prompted the initiation of a feasibility study on using small tractors for anhydrous ammonia application.

An anhydrous ammonia applicator (Fig. 23) which can be easily attached or detached by two pins was fabricated for a small walking tractor. The applicator was patterned after a standard tractor comb harrow and is 125 cm wide with six 14-inch long applicator shanks spaced 25 cm apart. The shanks are of the back-swept type to minimize the accumulation of trash. The pressure regulator, flow distributor, and control valve are mounted

Table 11. A comparative evaluation of weeding methods in flooded rice, IRR1, 1968 wet season.

Weeding method	IR8		Chianung 242		Yield means** (kg/ha)	Labor (man-hr/ha)	Evaluation of weeding returns kg/ha rough rice)			
	Number of Weeds per sq m	Weed weight at 45 DAT* (g/sq m)	Weeds at 45 DAT per sq m	Weed weight at harvest (g/sq m)			Rice earned per man-hr	Cost of labor†	Cost of chemical and gasoline††	increased net return
1. Rotary weeding 2x	84	56.33	196	320.00	2416 ^b	200	350	0	862	
2. Hand weeding 2x	58	24.67	122	110.00	2966 ^{ab}	500	875	0	887	
3. IRR1 power weeder 2x	106	23.33	177	133.67	2939 ^{ab}	50	88	85	1562	
4. Rotary weeding fb hand weeding	149	13.33	120	35.33	2827 ^{ab}	310	542	0	1081	
5. IRR1 power weeder fb hand weeding	93	7.33	133	150.67	2779 ^{ab}	320	560	37	978	
6. Rotary weeding 1x	96	139.33	214	242.33	2426 ^b	90	158	0	1064	
7. Hand weeding 1x	44	26.33	117	202.00	3604 ^a	240	420	0	1980	
8. IRR1 power weeder 1x	94	129.00	145	340.67	2328 ^b	25	44	42	1038	
9. MCPA fb rotary weeding	18	20.33	57	32.33	3180 ^{ab}	104	182	35	2193	
10. MCPA fb hand weeding	2	2.67	9	25.00	3084 ^{ab}	260	455	35	1390	
11. MCPA fb IRR1 power weeder	9	0	10	38.33	3657 ^a	36	63	73	2317	
12. Trifluralin + MCPA (G)	6	7.67	8	16.33	3546 ^a	8	14	256	2072	
13. Nitrofen + 2,4D IPE (G)	0	0	0	8.67	3285 ^{ab}	11	19	266	1796	
14. EPTC + MCPA (G)	0	0	1	12.33	2777 ^{ab}	8	14	266	1293	
15. No weeding (control)	385	214.67	339	550.00	1204 ^c					

CV (b) = 24.6%

* Days after transplanting.

** Any 2 means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by the Duncan multiple range test.

† Cost of labor — P 0.50/man-hr @ 1.75 kg rough rice.

†† Cost of chemical: Trifluralin + MCPA (.7 + .4 kg/ha a.i.) = P 73.
 Nitrofen + 2,4D IPE (G) (2.0 + .8 kg/ha a.i.) = P 76.
 EPTC + MCPA (1.75 + .7 kg/ha a.i.) = P 76.
 MCPA (0.8 kg/ha a.i.) = P 10.

(b) gasoline consumption per hectare = P 12.

Fig. 23. Experimental anhydrous ammonia applicator for small walking tractors.

directly on the comb applicator for easy attachment to and detachment from the tractor.

A 1,000-cubic inch tank with an 8.5-kg ammonia capacity is mounted with a tubular bracket on the front end of the tractor. This position of the tank counterbalances the rear-mounted applicator assembly and improves the tractor balance. A flexible 3/8-inch rubber hose from the ammonia tank is connected to the pressure regulator assembly on the comb applicator. The applicator attachment was calibrated in late December 1968 for use in experimental work by the Agronomy Department during the 1969 dry season.

Physical Properties of the Rice Plant and Paddy

Basic information on the physical properties of paddy and the rice plant is needed in the development of harvesting and threshing equipment for use in tropical countries. A study, therefore, was initiated to find the forces required to: (a) separate paddy from the panicle, (b) separate the panicles from the stalk, (c) pull the individual tillers from the ground, and (d) pull the whole plant from the ground.

Eight rice varieties (IR8, Bluebonnet 50, C₄-63, T(N)1, 81B-25, IR5, BPI-76, and ADT-27) were transplanted at staggered dates in June and July 1968 to mature simultaneously on October 7,

1968. ADT-27 was later eliminated as it matured much earlier than the others. Tests were conducted on seven dates, September 26, 30, October 3, 7, 11, 14 and 19, 1968 to assess the effect of plant maturity and moisture content.

The paddy is detached from the panicle when the applied force exceeds the restraining force. This detaching force was applied by rapidly accelerating the panicle along a circular path. An experimental non-impulsive centrifugal threshing device was built to thresh 10 panicles at a time (Fig. 24). The device consisted of a circular metal disc, mounted horizontally on a vertical shaft. The circular disc was fitted with 10 clamps for holding individual panicles. The shaft and the disc were driven by a 1-hp electric motor through a variable speed drive. The disc could be rotated at a speed of from 1,000 to 3,500 rpm. A circular flexible plastic shroud was hung around the disc to catch the paddy which was detached and thrown from the panicle. An inclined sheet metal pan was fitted below the shroud for continuous collection of threshed paddy during the test.

Ten panicles of each variety were clamped to the rotary disc for each test. The panicles extended to an average radii (m) of 0.31785 (IR8), 0.35335 (Bluebonnet 50), 0.31620 (C₄-63), 0.31905 (T[N]1), 0.33150 (81B-25), 0.31810 (IR5), and 0.32690 (BPI-76). The samples were rotated at speeds of 1,000, 1,500, 2,000, 2,500, 3,000 and 3,500 rpm, subjecting the paddy grains

Fig. 24. Experimental non-impulsive centrifugal threshing device.

Fig. 25. Tripod-mounted rice plant pulling device.

to accelerations of 364, 820, 1,458, 2,278, 3,281 and 4,466 g, respectively. The grain threshed at each speed increment was collected and the following data were recorded: (a) total weight of threshed paddy, (b) number of individual paddy grains, and (c) moisture content of paddy as determined by oven drying.

The percentage of paddy threshed at each speed increment was determined based on the total weight of the sample. The threshing force was determined by the equation,

$$F = 3.99433 W_g R N_c^2$$

which is a metric equivalent of the one developed by B. J. Lamp, Jr. and W. F. Buchele* where

F = threshing force, kg

W_g = grain weight, kg

R = average radius of panicle, m

N_c = revolutions of disc per second.

A study was also undertaken to determine the force required to pull the rice panicle tiller and plant.

A simple tripod-mounted crank and pulley device with a spring-scale-fitted flexible wire (Fig. 25) was used to pull the individual panicles, tillers and entire plants, and a piece of string (or rope) with a noose was attached to the scale to firmly hold them. The crank was turned manually at a steady rate during the tests.

Normal panicles and corresponding tillers from 10 plants and 10 additional plants of each variety were pulled at the rate of 0.45 m/sec. This pulling rate was used because it is the approximate forward speed of a stripper-harvester combine being developed in the Department. Individual values and their corresponding averages were recorded.

Results and conclusions

Separation of paddy from panicle. Figures 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31 and 32 show the relationship between threshing force and paddy threshed for the different varieties tested at seven stages of

Fig. 26. Relation between threshing force and threshing for IR8 at seven grain moisture levels.

* Lamp, B.J. and W.E. Buchele, "Centrifugal Threshing of Small Grains," Transactions of the ASAE, Vol. 3, No. 2 1960

Fig. 27. Relation between threshing force and threshing for Bluebonnet 50 at seven grain moisture levels.

Fig. 28. Relation between threshing force and threshing for C4-63 at seven grain moisture levels.

maturity and moisture levels. As expected, within a variety, the high-moisture-content paddy required a larger threshing force. The upper moisture limits and the force required to thresh 98 percent

Table 12. Maximum paddy moisture levels with corresponding minimum force required to thresh 98 percent of paddy for seven rice varieties.

Variety	Maximum permissible paddy moisture content (% d.b.)	Minimum threshing force (kg)
IR8	32.5	0.058
Bluebonnet 50	34.6	0.052
C ₄ -63	28.4	0.062
T(N)1	31.5	0.069
81B-25	30.1	0.049
IR5	31.8	0.075
BPI-76	29.6	0.073

Fig. 29. Relation between threshing force and threshing for T(N)1 at seven grain moisture levels.

Fig. 30. Relation between threshing force and threshing for 81B-25 at seven grain moisture levels.

Fig. 32. Relation between threshing force and threshing for BPI-76 at seven grain moisture levels.

Fig. 31. Relation between threshing force and threshing for IR5 at seven grain moisture levels.

Fig. 33. Relation between paddy weight and germination for IR8.

of paddy for the varieties tested are shown in Table 12.

There was a marked difference in threshability among the varieties tested, the order being: 81B-25> Bluebonnet 50> IR8> C₄-63> T(N)1> BPI-76> IR5.

Even at about the same grain moisture level, the forces required for threshing varied among varie-

ties. Panicle breakage often occurred in the case of T(N)1, indicating a relatively weak straw.

A force of 0.075 kg was found sufficient to thresh 98 percent of paddy under all typical harvesting conditions for these varieties.

There is evidence of paddy selection by weight in a centrifugal threshing device. The heavier and more mature kernels were threshed at the lower

Table 13. Germination of centrifugally-threshed IR8 paddy compared with hand-threshed check samples at seven levels of maturity (10 panicles per test).

Plant age (days from seeding)	Hand- threshed paddy	Centrifugally - threshed paddy (rpm)						Paddy left on panicle	Total paddy
		1000	1500	2000	2500	3000	3500		
105 a*	.0290	.0310	.0303	.0294	.0288	.0275	.0270	.0268	.0291
b**	86	95	92	87	70	39	21	5	85
109 a	.0287	.0309	.0301	.0294	.0287	.0279	.0269	.0266	.0286
b	92	96	94	90	70	47	30	8	90
112 a	.0286	.0306	.0298	.0290	.0285	.0277	.0269	.0264	.0285
b	92	98	95	88	67	46	33	4	91
116 a	.0284	.0301	.0296	.0289	.0282	.0275	.0268	—	.0284
b	89	97	96	88	66	47	29	—	90
120 a	.0283	.0297	.0292	.0284	.0276	.0273	—	—	.0281
b	85	96	94	76	59	38	—	—	83
123 a	.0281	.0294	.0286	.0281	.0274	—	—	—	.0280
b	83	92	86	71	59	—	—	—	82
128 a	.0279	.0290	.0282	.0275	—	—	—	—	.0278
b	78	82	78	66	—	—	—	—	78

* Average paddy weight (grams).

** Germination percentage (%).

Table 14. Average panicle pulling force in kilograms at a constant pulling speed of 0.45 meter per second.

Test date	Variety						
	IR8	Bbt. 50	C ₄ -63	T(N)1	81B-25	IR5	BPI-76
9-26-68	2.91	3.08	3.20	2.05	3.14	2.57	4.01
9-30-68	2.94	3.42	3.28	2.10	3.18	2.59	4.11
10-03-68	2.99	3.49	3.27	2.07	3.19	2.60	4.10
10-07-68	3.05	3.56	3.30	2.09	3.20	2.61	4.22
10-11-68	3.02	3.48	3.25	2.06	3.20	2.61	4.10
10-14-68	2.97	3.37	3.19	2.05	3.17	2.59	3.95
10-19-68	2.93	3.20	3.18	2.07	3.18	2.53	2.98

Table 15. Average tiller pulling force in kilograms at a constant pulling speed of 0.45 per second.

Test date	Variety						
	IR8	Bbt. 50	C ₄ -63	T(N)1	81B-25	IR5	BPI-76
9-26-68	6.00	8.41	5.09	3.79	6.95	7.20	6.29
9-30-68	6.12	8.57	5.60	3.92	7.19	7.69	6.38
10-03-68	6.12	8.60	5.60	3.97	7.35	7.67	6.38
10-07-68	6.15	8.66	5.62	3.97	7.37	7.70	6.40
10-11-68	6.13	8.58	5.61	3.95	7.36	6.71	6.34
10-14-68	6.10	8.56	5.56	3.88	7.31	7.60	6.35
10-19-68	6.03	8.37	5.12	3.84	7.08	7.20	6.31

Table 16. Average plant pulling force in kilograms at a pulling speed of 0.45 meter per second.

Test date	Variety						
	IR8	Bbt. 50	C ₄ -63	T(N)1	81B-25	IR5	BPI-76
9-26-68	41.6	52.9	43.3	19.8	63.9	56.2	54.2
9-30-68	43.3	61.5	42.6	20.4	65.6	55.3	50.7
10-03-68	45.2	58.1	43.5	22.7	64.9	54.7	56.8
10-07-68	45.6	60.1	44.9	22.8	65.6	55.4	56.6
10-11-68	43.5	57.7	41.7	20.6	63.3	56.3	55.5
10-14-68	44.7	57.3	40.5	18.1	60.4	53.9	52.2
10-19-68	39.3	51.6	38.8	17.5	57.2	51.8	49.3

speeds, i.e., at lesser forces. In a germination test conducted on IR8, the heavier kernels threshed at lesser forces exhibited higher viability as compared to the lighter kernels which were threshed at higher forces and the hand-threshed check. Table 13 and Fig. 33 show the relationship between grain weight and germination. This observation indicates that a centrifugal threshing device may be more useful for threshing seed than the conventional machines.

Panicle, tiller and plant strength. Straw with extreme moisture levels were more susceptible to breakage (Tables 14, 15 and 16). There were varietal differences in straw strength. The varieties were in the following order as regard: *Panicle strength* – BPI-76 > Bluebonnet 50 > C₄-63 > 81B-25 > IR8 > IR5 > T(N)1, *Tiller strength* – Bluebonnet 50 > 81B-25 > IR5 > BPI-76 > IR8 > C₄-63 > T(N)1, and *Whole plant uprooting force* – Bluebonnet 50 > 81B-25 > BPI-76 > IR5 > IR8 > C₄-63 > T(N)1.

Regardless of variety, nearly 50 percent of the plants pulled on September 26 were completely uprooted without their roots being severed from the plant. However, of the plants pulled on October 19, nearly 10 percent were uprooted while the rest were severed at the base, leaving the stumps in the ground. The progressive hardening of the soil and the change in straw strength due to the lateness of the test seem to have contributed to this difference.

The pulling force was the maximum for the panicle, tiller, and whole plant on the same date (October 7, 1968). Thus, the maximum pulling force was recorded on the 107th day for Bluebonnet 50, 112th day for T(N)1, 116th day for IR8, 122nd day for BPI-76 and C₄-63, and 129th day for IR5 and 81B-25. The experiment indicated the difference in the physical properties of paddy rice and its plant among the varieties studied. It seems that there is scope for plant breeders to develop varieties more adaptable for threshing,

combining, and stripping operations. The mechanical harvester operation not only requires non-lodging varieties with uniform panicle heights but also requires uniform grain maturity in each panicle and among plants to avoid excessive grain scatter losses in the field. A high pedicle strength is desirable and can be tolerated for mechanical threshing, whereas it would be undesirable for manual threshing. For manual threshing varieties uniform grain maturity within a panicle with relatively medium pedicle strength for easier threshing would be desirable.

Paddy Stripper Combine Development

The development of a stripper combine for paddy was initiated during the year. Efficient handling of paddy from the field to the storage has always intrigued engineers. It was felt that the current practice of harvesting and then threshing creates many difficulties for the tropical farmer and results in excessive grain losses.

The use of conventional combine harvesters have not been widely accepted in the tropical areas. The large conventional combines are too expensive for the small farmers and the weight of such machines creates severe mobility problems in the wet paddy fields. The smaller conventional-type combines introduced by the Japanese manufacturers also encounter similar problems.

A conventional combine consists of four sections – a cutterbar, an elevator mechanism, a threshing cylinder, and a grain-straw separating

Fig. 34. Schematic drawing of IRRI experimental paddy stripper mounted on a walking tractor.

Fig. 35. Schematic drawing of IRRI paddy stripper.

section. A stripper combine which would thresh directly from standing crop could dispense with the cutterbar and the elevator mechanism. Such a design will permit light-weight, low-cost machines which could be better suited for harvesting rice in the wet tropical countries.

Attempts have been made in many countries, notably in the United States, Great Britain, Australia, Japan, and Taiwan, to design stripper harvesters for rice and other crops. Serious field scattering losses have been a major problem in these experiments. The concept being used at the Institute in the development of a stripper combine is particularly directed toward solving this problem.

The first experimental machine (Fig. 34) is offset-mounted on a 6-hp walking tractor. Figure 35 shows a schematic drawing of the stripper in operation. The experimental machine is designed to first bend the plants backward for stripping the grain on a threshing belt. During the forward motion of the machine the plants would continually unwind out of the machine after the grain stripping action.

The machine differs basically from other experimental stripper designs in this action of gently bending the plant before threshing. This feature can improve the collection of threshed grain and reduce the problem of grain scatter loss. The first experimental machine has no straw-grain cleaning system. A rotary screen cleaner will be added to the machine after a satisfactory stripper mechanism has been developed. A self-propelled

stripper combine will eventually be developed. There is a widespread interest among manufacturers in the industrialized countries in a stripper combine not only for rice but also for other crops. If a successful stripper combine could be developed for rice, the techniques learned could be applied in developing combine harvesters for other crops.

Rotary Harrow for Small Tractors

The use of small walking tractors with comb harrow (Fig. 36) is gaining popularity among the rice-growing farmers in the tropics. A comb harrow, however, causes excessive resistance to the tractor movement in the field due to the collection of vegetative matter on the spikes. It has also been observed that the comb harrow can only produce a scratching-type action without sufficient burying effect.

A project was initiated to study the use of a rotary harrow in place of a comb harrow for faster harrowing and better incorporation of vegetative matter into the soil. An experimental rotary harrow (Fig. 37) which can be attached to a small walking tractor was fabricated to evaluate this possibility. The rotary harrow is similar to a conventional cage wheel used with small tractors. It has 12 flat bars, 15 cm wide and 0.4 cm thick, welded to three circular structural members at a 45° angle from the tangent. The total weight of

Fig. 36. Walking tractor with comb-harrow.

Fig. 37. Experimental IRRI rotary harrow attached to a walking tractor.

the rotary harrow is 38 kg as compared to 11 kg for a conventional comb harrow.

Preliminary field trials revealed that the rotary harrow could puddle and bury the weeds well into the flooded fields. The field was puddled about 2 weeks before the tests. The average WES cone penetrometer (30° angle cone with 3.2 sq cm base area) readings were 20 cm at 35 psi and 25 cm at 70 psi. Table 17 shows the results of tests comparing the rotary harrow and the conventional comb harrow. While the time required to till a certain land area did not significantly differ, the fuel consumption of the rotary harrow was less than that of the comb harrow.

In trials under softer soil conditions, where the average WES cone penetrometer readings were 40 cm at 35 psi and 50 cm at 70 psi, the rotary harrow failed to perform well due to excessive bogging.

It was felt that a rotary harrow with a hollow drum would increase flotation and reduce bogging. A 110-cm long, 33-cm diameter hollow sheet metal drum with a 94.1-liter volume was placed inside the rotary harrow. This added 18 kg to the total weight of the rotary harrow. When tried in a puddled field with 10 cm water, the rotary harrow equipped with the drum exhibited adequate flotation to keep the tractor from bogging.

The rotary harrow with the drum was then compared to the conventional comb harrow in two 1/8-ha plots (25 m x 50 m rectangular plots); the results are shown in Table 18. The harrowing

Table 17. Performance test* of rotary and conventional comb harrow.

Test no.	Penetrometer depth** at		Vegetative condition	Implement used	Time requirement per 1/16 ha		Fuel consumption per 1/16 ha	
	35 psi (cm)	70 psi (cm)			1st pass (min)	2nd pass (min)	1st pass (ml)	2nd pass (ml)
	1	20.4			25.0	Slight	Comb harrow	15.5
2	17.4	23.0	Heavy	Comb harrow	14.0	12.5	405	442
3	18.2	24.6	Slight	Rotary harrow	16.5	15.5	216	268
4	19.6	26.4	Heavy	Rotary harrow	13.5	14.5	228	162

* Tractor used: 6-hp walking tractor
 Implement used: 127-cm wide rotary harrow, and 127-cm wide comb harrow
 Field condition: Loamy soil flooded to 5 cm, harrowed 2 weeks before this test, covered with vegetation.

** Average of five readings.

Table 18. Performance test* of rotary harrow with drum and conventional comb harrow.

Test no.	Implement used	No. of passes needed for transplanting	Time requirement per 1/8 ha (min)	Fuel consumption per 1/8 ha (ml)	Harrowing depth (cm)
1	Rotary harrow with drum	4	82	2167	10.8
2	Comb harrow	4	79	1547	9.0
3	Rotary harrow with drum	4	102	1490	9.0
4	Comb harrow	4	96	1518	11.2

* Tractor used: 6-hp walking tractor
 Implement used: 127-cm wide rotary harrow with drum and 127-cm wide comb harrow
 Field condition: Loamy soil with 10 cm rice stubble, plowed 3 weeks before the test, and flooded to 5 cm 3 days before the test.

depth was 10 cm for both implements. Both harrows required four passes to achieve adequate soil conditions for transplanting. The rotary harrow with the drum consumed more fuel and required more time than did the comb harrow. It was observed, however, that with the rotary

harrow with the drum, the downward pushing effect of the rotating blades buried the weeds better than the comb harrow. The comb harrow, on the other hand, was better at soil breaking due to the scratching operation of the spikes. Under a uniform soil condition the rotary harrow with the

drum was easier to operate than the comb harrow since the operator did not have to support the handles to counteract the axle torque reaction.

The rotary harrow exhibited some advantages under certain field conditions; however, its economy and performance did not clearly justify its higher cost. More tests and further design modifications may be necessary.

Power Distribution for Rotary Tiller and Tractor Rear Axle

The 30-60 hp tractor PTO-driven rotary tillers are becoming popular in the tropical countries for wetland preparation on larger holdings. These machines offer several advantages for wetland operation. Since most of the power is transmitted

directly to the soil through the tractor PTO rather than through the drawbar, power loss due to poor traction is minimized. The rotary tiller operation produces excellent soil breakage and puddling effect in clayey soils and results in fewer passes during land preparation. Tractor PTO shaft failures have frequently been encountered during the operation of the rotary tiller in rice paddies. A knowledge of the power transmitted through the tractor PTO shaft during rotary tiller operations under tropical conditions is essential to tractor design engineers.

A study was therefore initiated to determine the power requirement for land preparation using rotary tillers under dry and wet field conditions at the Institute. This project was also aimed at studying the relative power distribution between soil tillage and tractor mobility by measuring simultaneously the power transmitted through the PTO to the rotary tiller and through the tractor rear axles. This information could be useful for the proper selection and design of tractors and rotary tillers for paddy cultivation.

A 2.8-m wide rotary tiller, fabricated at the Institute with Japanese-type rotary tiller blades, was used. The rotary tiller was mounted on a 65-hp conventional tractor equipped with a hydrostatic transmission to the rear wheels. The first portion of the test was conducted under upland field conditions to establish the PTO torque under the most severe operating conditions. The soil was so hard and dry that the WES cone penetrometer failed to penetrate it at 70 psi. The PTO torque and tractor rear axle torque were recorded simultaneously by a two-channel strip recorder (Fig. 38,A) mounted on the tractor. Bi-axial strain gages (90°) were mounted on the female portion of the PTO shaft for sensing the torque. The signal was transmitted to the recorder through a slip ring assembly (Fig. 38B).

A strain gage pressure transducer was used to record the input-output differential pressure of the hydraulic motor powering the tractor rear wheels. The calibration curve was drawn from tests conducted to establish torque-pressure relationship. The pressure was converted into rear wheel torque by the calibration curve. The PTO rpm was calculated from the indicated rpm on the engine speed indicator. During the field tests, the three-point linkage-mounted rotary tiller was gradually

A

B

Fig. 38. Measuring equipment used for power requirement studies: (A) Two-channel recorder and accessories, and (B) conventional-type IRRRI rotary tiller with strain gauge and slip ring assembly for PTO torque measurement.

Fig. 39. Sample dynograph recorder tracings of tractor rear axle hydrostatic drive-pressure and tractor PTO torque to drive the rotary tiller.

lowered into the ground only after the tractor forward travel speed had stabilized. Attempts were made to maintain tilling depths of 12 cm to 15 cm by controlling the hydraulic lift lever. The tilling depths had to be reduced in the very hard portions of the fields due to the power limitations of the engine.

Figure 39 shows a typical recorder chart. The upper line indicates the rear axle drive pressure and the lower line, the PTO torque for driving the rotary tiller. The recording chart speed was 5 mm/sec. Before the tilling operation, the chart indicated some torque on the rear axles which was consumed in moving the tractor across the field and no torque on the rotary tiller. When the rotary tiller was lowered and came in contact with the soil, the rear axle torque decreased while the PTO torque increased rapidly. The torque fluctuation on the PTO shaft was of relatively high frequency.

The torque and power requirements for tilling and traveling are shown in Table 19 under several operating conditions. The average torque of the PTO shaft varied from 43.8 kg-m to 62.3 kg-m depending on the tilling condition. The highest PTO torque of 62.3 kg-m and power requirement of 47.0 hp were recorded at the highest tractor travel speed and at 540 PTO rpm. On the other hand, the lowest PTO torque was observed at the slowest tractor speed and high PTO speed (540

rpm). For the same PTO speed of 540 rpm, a change in the tractor forward travel speed of 177 percent resulted in a 139 percent change in power requirement at the PTO, indicating that faster tractor travel speeds or increased tilling pitch reduced power requirement. It was also noted that for the same tractor travel speed (treatments 1 and 2) the PTO torque was higher when the rotary tiller speed was slow, even though the tilling depth was 1 cm less in treatment 2. This shows that torque was increased by an increase in the pitch of cut.

The large tilling pitch increased the soil reaction on the machine, resulting in an increased torque, whereas the power requirement was reduced by an increase in the pitch of cut. These phenomena indicate that an increased pitch of cut results in higher torque but lower power consumption. The rear axle torque for tractor travel without using the rotary tiller varied from 330 kg-m to 460 kg-m, and the power requirement ranged from 2.5 hp to 5.1 hp. Whenever the rotary tiller was used on hard soil, the torque on the tractor rear axles was reduced to a range of 0.6 hp to 1.4 hp due to the pushing effect of the rotary tiller.

The following can be summarized from this experiment:

1. During the rotary tiller operation under hard soil conditions, most of the power of the tractor

Table 19. Power distribution between tractor axle and PTO during rotary tiller operation*.

Treatment no.	Tractor travel speed		Rotary tiller condition	PTO speed (rpm)	Rotary tiller speed (rpm)	Tilling depth (cm)	Tilling degree	Average torque		Power requirement	
	(m/sec)	Rear wheel (rpm)						PTO (kg-m)	Rear axle	Rotary tiller (hp)	Rear axle
1	0.44	5.46	raised	540	196	—	—	negligible	330	—	2.5
	0.44	5.46	tilling	540	196	14.3	fine	43.8	120	33.8	0.9
2	0.44	5.46	raised	364	132	—	—	negligible	380	—	2.9
	0.44	5.46	tilling	364	132	13.6	medium	54.0	85	27.4	0.6
3	0.53	6.56	raised	270	98	—	—	negligible	460	—	4.2
	0.53	6.56	tilling	270	98	8.9	coarse	60.4	120	22.8	1.1
4	0.67	8.20	raised	364	132	—	—	negligible	410	—	4.7
	0.67	8.20	tilling	364	132	13.0	coarse	50.6	125	25.7	1.4
5	0.78	9.56	raised	540	196	—	—	negligible	380	—	5.1
	0.78	9.56	tilling	540	196	7.0	medium	62.3	70	47.0	0.9

* Tractor used: International Harvester Farmall 656 Hydrostatic Drive Tractor (65 B.H.P.)
 Rotary tiller: IRR1-designed 2.8-meter wide rotary tiller with conventional blades
 Field condition: Dry sandy loam covered with heavy vegetation.

engine was transmitted through the PTO shaft and a small torque appeared on the tractor rear axle.

2. Considerably high torque was indicated on the PTO shaft during tilling. Generally, increased tilling pitch resulted in high torque and lower power consumption but it also produced coarser tillage.

Further tests under soft soil conditions will be made in the future.

Row Seeder for Lowland Rice

Transplanting is widely practiced in most tropical countries. However, in countries with large farm holdings and high labor costs, direct seeding of paddy in rows would be preferable over transplanting. Direct seeding in rows reduces the cost of planting lowland rice as it eliminates the costs involved in growing, pulling and transplanting the seedlings. Generally, direct-seeded rice matures 7 to 10 days earlier than transplanted rice. However, equipment for direct seeding of paddy in rows under lowland conditions is not available. Hence, a

study was initiated to investigate the possibility of developing such equipment for lowland paddy cultivation.

A major problem with direct-seeded rice is that, unlike transplanted rice, it does not have enough of a headstart to outgrow the weeds. To overcome this problem, pre-germinated rice is seeded by hand broadcast methods in some tropical rice-growing regions. To facilitate this operation, it was decided to develop a mechanical row seeder for pre-germinated paddy under lowland conditions.

A seeder has two basic functions: meter the seed from a bulk supply, and convey and place the metered seed at a desirable location in the soil. The metering of pre-germinated paddy seeds poses considerable problems due to their susceptibility to mechanical damage. Excessive agitation and high seed pressure in the hopper can destroy the growing embryo of the pre-germinated seed. The seed hopper should have a minimum of moving parts to provide only the minimum agitation for the continuous flow of the seeds. The hopper should not be so large as to build up excessive

Table 20. Dry-run test of 8-row portable seeder.

Range of seeds dropped per hill	Row							
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th
0 - 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2 - 3	4	2	3	5	3	5	4	2
4 - 5	14	17	10	12	12	11	20	14
6 - 7	14	20	15	18	18	18	19	16
8 - 9	14	7	12	14	9	14	7	11
10 - 11	5	6	12	5	13	6	6	6
12 - 13	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	4
14 - 15	4	2	3	2	0	1	0	4
16 - 17	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1
18 - 19	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
20	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	470.00	454.00	506.5	434.0	458.0	438.0	596.0	490.0
Mean	7.83	7.57	8.44	7.23	7.63	7.30	6.60	8.17
Duncan's Test at 5% level:								
Rows	3rd	8th	1st	5th	2nd	6th	4th	7th
Means	8.44	8.17	7.83	7.63	7.57	7.30	7.23	6.60

Note: All the means are not statistically different at 5% level.

Table 21. Rate of seeding based on "Stand Establishment Applied Research Trial," Applied Research, IRRI, 1968.

Rate of seeding (kg/ha)	IR8		IR5	
	Broadcast seeds/sq m	Planted seeds/hill*	Broadcast seeds/sq m	Planted seeds /hill*
30	117.0	7.3	106.0	6.6
45	175.5	11.0	159.0	9.9
60	234.0	14.6	212.0	13.2
75	292.5	18.3	265.0	16.6
90	351.0	21.9	318.0	19.9
105	409.5	25.6	371.0	23.2
120	468.0	29.2	424.0	26.5

* Based on 25 x 25 cm hill spacing.

pressure between the seeds and the hopper walls. The metering mechanism should be adjustable for different seeding rates and should distribute the seeds evenly into the individual seed tubes. Present seed metering mechanisms for non-germinated seeds do not meet the special requirements of pre-germinated seeds.

The placement of seeds under lowland conditions also poses challenging problems. To avoid seed damage from pre-emergence herbicide application, rats, birds, algae and other pests, it is desirable to imbed the seed in the mud just below the surface. The clogging of seed tubes under lowland conditions and the covering of the seed after placement are both serious problems which need special attention. A large conventional tractor-mounted seeder will create problems of uneven seedbed due to wheel tracks and uneven rows due to wave action. It would also require handland for turning at the end of the fields. For these reasons the initial work was done on a

portable row seeder which would simplify many of the placement problems of the tractor-mounted seeder.

An eight-row portable seeder was built to study the seeding of lowland rice. The manually operated metering device used showed little difference in seed distribution within a row and between rows. The seeding rate ranged from 30 to 40 kg/ha (Tables 20 and 21) and it required 40 to 45 man-hours/ha when sowing at 25-cm row spacing with hills spaced 25 cm apart.

A second prototype seeder with additional features for greater accuracy in seed metering and adjustable row spacing is being developed.

Counterflow Drying

The construction of a laboratory model counterflow dryer (Fig. 40) consisting of a blower, air-measuring duct, heating chamber, grain-holding bin, plenum chamber, hopper and discharge mechanism was reported in the 1967 Annual

Fig. 40. Schematic drawing of the experimental counterflow dryer.

Report. During its operation, the blower forced the ambient air through the measuring duct to the heating chamber. The air heated by the electric coils in the heating chamber passed through the plenum chamber and up through the grain layer. The discharge mechanism continually moved the grain down the bin in a direction opposite the air movement. The grain flow from the hopper maintained a constant grain depth above the plenum chamber.

Preliminary tests were conducted with IR8 at a discharge rate of 3 cavans per hour and a drying air temperature of 160 F. A 3-percent and 5-percent dry basis moisture reduction per pass was found at air flow rates of 100 and 200 cfm per square foot and heat requirements of 1,260 and 1,400 BTU per pound of water, respectively. The tests resulted in a 69-percent milling and 60-percent

head grain yields. A second experiment was conducted to establish the interactions among airflow rate, discharge rate, and drying air temperature. A split-split randomized complete block design was used with: (a) airflow rate as the main plot (levels: 100, 150 and 200 cfm per sq ft), (b) discharge rate as the subplot (levels 2, 3 and 4 cavans per hour), and (c) drying air temperatures as the sub-subplot (levels 120, 140, 160 and 180 F).

The results are being analyzed and will be reported later.

Performance and Economics of Power Units

The analysis of the performance and economics of current and newly designed farm machinery was continued. Attempts in market research to better understand the specifications of new machinery

Table 22. Hand tractor survey data. Laguna, 1967.

Age of machines	No. of machines	Hiring fee		Area worked on own farm		No. of days hired per year	
		P/day	No. of machines	ha/machine	No. of machines	Days	No. of machines
1 month	11	7	1	0.7	1	1- 5	4
				1.0	10	6-10	22
2-5 "	54	25	69	1.5	16	11-15	41
				2.0	54	16-20	48
6-12 "	34	30	191	2.5	22	21-25	8
				3.0	55	26-30	55
1 year	93	35	13	3.5	28	31-35	11
				4.0	75	36-40	33
2 "	88	40	10	4.5	11	41-45	26
				5.0	37	46-50	13
3 "	55	45	1	5.5	3	51-55	2
				6.0	23	56-60	15
4 "	35	50	2	6.5	2	61-65	3
				7.0	12	76-80	2
5 "	33	55	1	8.0	13	81-85	1
				8.5	3	86-90	5
6 "	12	60	6	9.0	4	91-120	2
				10	16	121-160	1
7 "	4	65	1	11	4	*	89
				12	5	**	62
8 "	4	70	5	13	2		
				14	3		
10 "	1	75	1	18	3		
				19	1		
12 "	1	80	5	19.5	3		
				20	2		
13 "	1	90	9	21	1		
				24	2		
14 "	2	120	5	*	19		
				**	4		
*	3	*	28				
New	3	**	51				
		†	35				
Total	434		434		434		434

* No data.

** No idea.

† Machine not hired.

Table 23. Comparative data on plowing and harrowing with the carabao and hand tractor (6hp)*.

Operation, implement	Mean time (hr/ha)		Actual range (hr/ha)
	Efc **	Actual	
Plow: Carabao	72.5	36.3	28.8 - 41.2
Tractor	32.2	12.9	11.2 - 14.6
Harrow: Carabao	73.3	83.4	55.5 - 109.5
Tractor	14.7	13.9	11.3 - 16.6
Cost comparisons			
Average cost (P)			
Plow: Carabao	96.67	48.33	
Tractor	141.04	56.50	
Harrow: Carabao	97.70	110.94	
Tractor	64.39	60.88	
Total cost/ha (P)			
Land Preparation:			
Carabao	194.37	159.27	
Tractor	205.43	117.38	

* Tests conducted on IRR1 soils. Plowing – one pass. Harrowing – judged to be “adequate” at 9-13 passes of the carabao and 3-4 passes of the tractor.

Contract rates: Tractor, P35 per 8-hour day, or P4.38/hr.
Carabao, P8 per 6-hour day, or P1.33/hr.

** The efc times are computed to provide a relative indication of the time to prepare a field fully. During actual land preparation, considerable undertilling is noted.

revealed the inadequacy of existing test data. Therefore, testing programs were started on the two main types of farm power equipment—for land preparation and for harvesting-threshing. The tests also involved weeding and planting equipment. Since the testing program can proceed only during those short periods when the operations are underway, only preliminary data are presented here. Each operation is discussed separately.

Some preliminary general statements can be made about Philippine agricultural machinery based on recent survey data. In the cultivation of 2 million hectares of lowland rice, a total of about 3.5 million carabaos plus several thousand tractors (roughly estimated, between 7,500 and 10,000 standard-sized tractors, and over 5,000 hand tractors) are used in the Philippines. However, relatively few of the large tractors are used on rice farms. Sales of hand tractors are localized,

especially to relatively small farmers who have irrigated 2-crop farms, i.e., those with repayment capacity, and in areas of difficult mobility conditions for standard-sized tractors.

Data from interviews with hand tractor owners in Laguna Province are presented in Table 22. This province has the largest number of hand tractors, mostly of the 4 and 6 hp type. Recent sales figures indicate that the larger power tiller (with PTO) is gaining in popularity. The data in Table 22 reflect the increasing use of the hand tractors; of 434 machines reported, roughly two-third were 3 years old or less. The machines were used primarily for land preparation, either on the owner's farm or for contract work. The owner typically reported 4 hectares of owned land, prepared twice a year. In addition, the machine was used about 30 days per year on contract hire. The hiring fee for the 4-6 hp tractors with operator is about P35 (including

meals) a day*. For the larger hand tractor with power tiller, a typical rate is ₱60 a day.

The replacement of the carabao by the small 4-6 hp hand tractor is physically almost 1:1 for the size of the moldboard plow and the comb harrow used by the carabao and by the tractor are about the same. The tractor, however, gains advantage in speed, endurance, and by the tillage effect of cage wheels. The larger power tiller uses the rototiller to replace both plowing and some of the harrowings. Land preparation with the small tiller involves typically one plowing followed by three to five harrowings. The final harrowing may be done a week after the others to bury germinating weed seeds. For the power tillers, the rotovation may be done once or twice, followed a week later by two to three harrowings. The contract cost per plowing is ₱75-₱115; for each harrowing, ₱10-₱17, for each rotovation, ₱32-₱65.

Tests were conducted at the Institute farm to compare the time required for carabao and hand tractor plowing and harrowing. The contract costs for these operations are presented in Table 23. Further field testing revealed that many of the farmers using hand tractors had firmer field than those in the controlled experiment.

To compare the time spent in the controlled experiment with that used by the farmer on the firmer soils, the effective field capacity (efc)* was computed for the experimental fields. The farmers' plowing-harrowing time was much closer to the computed time based on the efc for one complete coverage than was the case in the experiment.

The efc in the case of the plowing operation indicates that the carabao and tractor were turning over only half the soil in the experimental fields. In the case of the harrowing operations, however, the coverage was more complete.

A contract-hire cost can now be attached to the efc times as a likely indication of the cost of preparing firm fields. These theoretical figures would indicate a similar total land preparation cost for the 4-6 hp tractor and the carabao.

The number of days required to prepare 1 hectare then is:

tractor (8-hr day): actual, 3.4 days; efc, 5.9 days.

carabao (6-hr day): actual, 20.0 days; efc, 24.3 days.

The total capacity of each of the above methods during the crop year can then be estimated. This is done by assuming a 60-day period of land preparation for each crop, for the crop requires 120 days, or about 4 months, to mature; for 2 crops, the total is 8 months. Two land preparations of 60 days each, or 4 months, complete the year.

For the carabao, at 20 to 25 days per hectare, the maximum area that can be covered is 2.5 to 3.0 hectares per season. One can compare this with the table on farm size and the average number of carabaos. For the hand tractor, at 3.5 to 6 days per hectare, the maximum area per 60 days is 10 to 17 hectares per season. The interview data on hand tractors indicate a median of 4.0 hectares own land and 30 days contract hire. This is roughly $4 + 6 = 10$ hectares, and compares favorably with the study assumptions.

Several large and medium-sized tractors were tested in Isabela Province where soils are firmer than at the Institute. The data obtained are shown in Table 24.

Three large diesel tractors of 55-70 hp, three medium-sized tractors of 11-14 hp, and one power tiller of 8.5 hp were tested during rotavation. One of the 55-70 hp tractors in second gear (high speed) gave the highest efc. It rototilled 1.07 hectares in 1 hour with a fuel consumption of 6.38 liters of diesel fuel. However, the engine overheated at this high speed so that the operation was impractical. The other two large tractors registered an almost identical efc of 0.71 ha/hr with a fuel consumption of 11.34 liters/hectare for one and 8.45 liters/hectare for the other. Wheel slippages were 24.38, 12.19, and 3.36 percent.

The medium-sized tractors had an efc of 0.22, 0.19, and 0.12 ha/hr. The least fuel consumption was 9.24 liters of diesel per hectare. The other tractors consumed 14.65 liters (diesel) and 50.76 liters (gasoline) of fuel. It can be noted in Table 24

* ₱3.90 equals US\$1.00.

** Effective field capacity is a measure of the time needed to perform a field operation on a particular sized field. The equation is $efc (sq.m./hr) = 60 \times 25 \times N.L. / W/t$, where $2 =$ number of trips per round; $N =$ number of rounds.

Table 24. Performance of large and medium-sized tractors: Land preparation in the rice fields of Isabela Province, Cagayan Valley, Philippines, 1968.

Code	Rhp	Age of tractor/ attach- ment	Speed combination used during operation	Type of tractive device, cm (W x diam)	Slip- page (%)	Width of attach- ment (m)	Effective field capacity	
							(sq m /hr)	(sq m/ Rhp-hr)
1. Rotavation								
I-A	55-70	T - 8 mo R - 1 yr	Engine - 2nd (H) Rotor - (L)	Paddy Wheel (51 x 141)	12.19	1.66	10705.75	194.65
I-B	55-70	T - 3 yr R - 1 yr	Engine- 1st (H) Rotor - (H)	Paddy Wheel (51 x 141)	24.38	1.52	7116.96	121.66
I-C	55-70	T - 8 mo R - 1 yr	Engine - 2nd (H) Rotor - (L)	Paddy Wheel (51 x 142)	3.36	1.52	7095.30	113.52
I-D*	14.0	T & R-7 mo	Engine - 2nd (L) Rotor - 1st (L)	Paddy Wheel (17 x 84)	20.58	1.00	2178.43	115.60
I-E*	11.0	T & R-3 yr	Engine - 2nd (L) Rotor - 2nd (L)	Paddy Wheel (20.5 x 74.5)	10.54	0.94	1229.42	111.77
I-F*	12.0	T & R-2 yr	Engine - 2nd (L) Rotor - (H)	Paddy Wheel (36 x 69)	7.38	1.03	1928.12	160.68
2. Harrowing								
II-G	55-70	T & H - 2.5 yr	Engine - 4th (L)	Ara Wheels (61 x 145)	3.36	Home-made comb 2.51	8243.89	122.13
II-C	35-45	T & H - 1.25"	Engine - 3rd (L)	Cage Wheels (61 x 126)	25.34	Home-made comb 2.97	6166.99	158.13
II-G	35-45	T & H - 15 yr	Engine - 2nd (L)	Ara Wheels (61 x 149.5)		Two-way disc 2.00	6523.76	144.97
II-G	55-70	T & H < 1 yr	Engine - 1st (H)	Pneumatic tires (33 x 155)	13.21	Pegtooth 2.04	10054.28	148.95
II-C	55-70	T & H - 2 yr	Engine - 2nd (L)	Cage Wheels (61 x 140)	19.02	Home-made 2.90	10308.37	187.42
3. ARA-Wheeling**								
III-G	55-70	T - 2.5yr	Engine - 4th (L)	Ara Wheels (61 x 145)	2.49		5676.39	84.09
4. Plowing								
IV-A*	28 BHp	T & P-1.5 yr	Engine - 3rd (L)	Pneumatic tires (28 x 140)	16.15	2 - disc 0.80	2074.84	74.10
IV-H*	55-70	T & P-1.66"	Engine - 3rd (L)	Ditto (40 x 140)	13.42	4 - disc 1.40	6075.30	110.46
IV-G*	55-70	T & P < 1 yr	Engine - 4th (L)	Ditto (33 x 155)	16.56	4 - disc 1.22	4152.50	61.52
IV-C	35-45	T & P-3 yr	Engine - 2nd (L)	Ditto (28 x 140)	16.83	3 - disc 1.07	3036.01	84.33
IV-B	55-70	T & P-3 yr		Ditto (33 x 158)	14.04	4 - disc 1.40	5003.34	85.53

Table 24. continuation

Code	Fuel consumption (liter/ha)	Unrototilled/unplowed/not harrowed (sq m)	Overlap (sq m)	Depth of tillage (cm)	Soil type	Soil depth at resistance before the operation (psi)		Soil condition on day of operation	Duration of flooding of (days before operation)	Depth of water (cm)	Years experience of operator
						35	70				
1. Rotavation											
I-A	6.38		684.48	14.5	Sandy clay loam	12	18	Flooded	7.0	14.8	3.0
I-B	11.34	11.45		10.3	- do -	12	17	- do -	4.0	9.4	2.0
I-C	8.45	1779.40		14.8	- do -	12	15	- do -	1.0	7.8	2.0
I-D*	9.24		64.80	14.0	Silt loam	5	22	Saturated	0	0	2.0
I-E*	14.65	75.22		16.4	- do -	21	24	Flooded	1.0	1.0	2.0
I-F*	50.76		7.66	17.0	- do -	21	24	Saturated	0	0	1.0
2. Harrowing											
II-G	5.10	17.58		15.4	- do -	16	20	Flooded	0	11.7	5.0
II-C	6.32		546.12	13.5	- do -	13	15	- do -	1.0	13.2	5.0
II-G	9.37		4132.80	9.0	- do -	2	4	- do -	3.0	10.3	2.0
II-G	5.14		86.14	12.0	- do -	4	6	dry			4.0
II-C	5.71		545.95	12.1	- do -	14	17	Flooded	0	3.0	4.0
3. ARA-Wheeling**											
III-G	8.23	45.30		16.1	- do -	18	23	Flooded	0	9.6	5.0
4. Plowing											
IV-A*	14.76	124.95		18.0	- do -	2	4	dry		- 09	5.0
IV-H*	9.63		551.88	18.0	- do -	2	3	dry		- 10	5.0
IV-G*	17.89		79.24	20.7	- do -	3	5	dry		- 09	10.0
IV-C	6.53	1097.36		15.0	- do -	2	4	dry		- 05	< 1
IV-B	8.01		82.19	14.8	- do -	1	3	dry		- 05	4.0

* Tractor demonstration at San Mateo, Isabela.

** ARA-Wheeling: land preparation by cage wheels only.

that the depths of cut were slightly deeper for the medium-sized tractors than for the large tractors; this is because the areas where the former had worked were previously plowed while the areas for the latter were not.

Four makes of large diesel tractors were tested for harrowing. One tractor with a 2.90-meter wide comb harrow which had about 19 percent slippage on its cage wheels harrowed 1.03 hectares in 1 hour using 5.71 liters of fuel. Another harrowed a hectare of dry clay loam soil with a 2.04-meter peg-tooth harrow in 1 hour and consumed 5.14 liters of diesel fuel. In another field which was flooded and which had a silt loam texture, the same kind of tractor trailing a 2.50-meter comb harrow had an efc of 0.82 ha/hr. A 15-year-old tractor was also tested. It harrowed only 0.65 hectare in 1 hour and had a high fuel consumption of 9.37 liters per hectare. Another tractor had an efc of 0.62 ha/hr and a fuel consumption of 6.32 liters per hectare. It had a very high slippage of 25.34 percent.

Tests on plowing were conducted using five kinds of large diesel tractors. The efc varied from 0.21 ha/hr to 0.61 ha/hr; fuel consumption varied from 6.53 to 17.89 liters/ha. The slippage varied from 13.42 to 16 percent. All the tractors were equipped with pneumatic tires.

In another type of land preparation only cage wheels are used. The tractor uses no tillage attachment and pulverizes with its cage wheels the area which had been previously plowed. With a 55-70 hp diesel tractor, an efc of 0.57 ha/hr was obtained, consuming 8.23 liters per hectare. Wheel traction was fairly good and allowed only 2.49 percent slippage during the operation. The operator drives around until he finally reaches and ends at the center of the field. This operation requires that he make three complete rounds before starting on a new pass.

Methods of land preparation in Isabela Province:

	Unit cost/ha	Total cost/ha
First method: 1 pass rotovator	P65	P65
2 passes harrow drawn by tractor with leveling board	80	160
Final harrowing + leveling with carabao	-	-

Second method: Dry plowing	P40	P40
2 passes harrow drawn by tractor with leveling board	80	160
Final harrowing + leveling with carabao	-	-

Note: After plowing, the area is idle for 2-4 weeks before the next operation is made, granting that the operator has the time.

	Unit cost/ha	Total cost/ha
Third method: Dry plowing	P40	P40
1 pass rotovator	45	45
4 passes harrow drawn by carabao	-	-

All operations are done under flooded conditions unless otherwise stated.

All charges are on a contract basis. There are usually two operators for one tractor who are paid P5 to P6 each per day.

Performance and Economics of Harvesting-Threshing Machines

The testing of threshing equipment was limited to two types of stationary threshers: the IRRI experimental paddy thresher and the Japanese automatic thresher. The test results of the IRRI thresher are given in a later part of this report.

Since Japanese automatic machines are similar, brand names have been omitted. The thresher uses the drum with wire loops to thresh the grains. When the rice is harvested, the stalks are laid on a table attached to the thresher. The grain is handled gradually into a chain drive which carries the panicles under the drum. The stalks are carried past the threshing drum to the other side of the machine and fall to the floor. The grain is winnowed in the machine, and then delivered through a pipe for sacking (Fig. 41).

The tests reported here were conducted in March, 1968 in the municipality of Biñan, Laguna.

The machine did not operate as well as expected, particularly in threshing wet stalks and grain. Further tests will be conducted on other makes of threshers. In conducting the tests, the analysis was divided into three categories — a slow feeding rate when threshing wet grain, an average speed, and as fast as possible. A three-man crew was used — one man to feed in the stalks, another to prepare rice stalks on the adjoining table, and the third to sack the rice and watch the machine (Fig. 41).

Fig. 41. Japanese automatic thresher.

The results of the trials indicate an average output of 100 kg/hr for a slow feeding rate, 200 kg/hr for average feeding, and 400 kg/hr for maximum feeding. Because of wet stalks, much of the rice harvested under rainy conditions would be at the minimum rate.

The large rice-growing areas in the Philippines currently rely on the large McCormick stationary threshers for threshing the major part of the crop. In Isabela Province, northeastern Luzon, data were obtained from farmers about their reaction to the machines. The procedure is to harvest the rice by hand, bundle the rice, and place these in small stacks (called mandalas) to dry, later to be restacked in large mandalas for threshing. The threshers operate on a contract basis; 5 percent of the threshed crop is usually sufficient for paying their own crew and the large-hp tractor that tows the thresher through the paddies. The farmers interviewed in Isabela indicated that they were able to get their crop threshed within 1 to 4 weeks after harvest, depending on the availability of a threshing machine. Only a few indicated an unduly long wait before threshing. They did indicate that they thought that the threshing charge was too high. The harvesting and threshing operations were not paid for together. The operator contracted and paid for the harvesters separately. A common practice is to pay a specific price per head per day.

The most commonly mentioned price was ₱2.50 per day.

Thus, where the threshing was mechanized, the harvesting and threshing crews were separate. In contrast, in Laguna, harvesting and threshing are still done by hand, and the practice is to pay a crew for both operations.

Agronomic-Engineering Surveys of Major Rice Areas and Farm Management Interviews

These data were collected to examine the technical relationships involved in growing rice in the major rice-producing regions in the Philippines in order to assess the extent of and potential for mechanization. Mechanization potential in this case is being viewed both from an over-all (macro) approach and from the view of the individual farmer (micro).

In assessing the potential for mechanization in an area, we have looked at farm sizes and the type and number of equipment already being used. Further, we have found a correlation between hand tractor owners and irrigated two-crop farms. Irrigation and the income provided by two crops is an important factor in mechanization. Mechanization cannot proceed without the means to pay for the equipment.

What other factors are indicative of an area that will mechanize? Firstly, a reliance on hired labor, and therefore a cash cost, can indicate a possible potential for change. Secondly, high seasonal labor demands may be accompanied by labor shortages, indicating production bottlenecks.

Hired labor is commonly used in the Central Luzon areas for transplanting, harvesting, and to some extent, weeding. Threshing is done by custom operation, so it, too, is "hired" service. The other cultural operations are typically performed by the family. When asked about labor shortages, however, the farmers consistently answered that this occurred only during land preparation. Thus, while most of these farms are of the "subsistence" type, several of the key operations are performed by hired labor, thus constituting a cash or "in kind" cost. If an operation is already a cash cost, the operator may be interested in minimizing his outlay, and may turn to mechanical power. If there is a production

Table 25. Indications of a labor shortage, taken from interview data, 1968.*

Operation	Yes				No				No answer
	All hired labor	Some hired labor	No hired labor	Total	All hired labor	Some hired labor	No hired labor	Total	
(1) Tacurong – 63 farms									
Plowing – harrowing		8	2	10	5	40	6	51	2
Pulling seedling and transplanting/plant	12	1		13	17	9	22	48	2
Weeding and/or cultivation	3		5	8	5	6	42	53	2
Hiring more weeders				7				54	2
Harvesting and threshing	2		1	3	16	22	20	58	2
(2) Midsayap – 45 farms									
Plowing–harrowing	1		3	4	1	13	27	41	
Pulling seedlings and transplant/planting	2	2	1	5	12	22	6	40	
Weeding and/or cultivation			4	4	2	3	36	41	
Hiring more weeders				6				36	3
Harvesting and threshing			1	1	17	17	10	44	
(3) Isabela – 124 farms									
Plowing–harrowing	3	22	37	62	1	30	31	62	
Pulling seedlings and transplanting or planting	22	14	4	40	36	42	6	84	
Weeding and/or cultivation	1		25	26	3	16	79	98	
Hiring more weeders				24				59	41
Harvesting and threshing	6	23	4	33	15	72	4	91	

* Farmers' responses are listed under the category of whether the farmer used hired labor for that operation, some or no hired labor.

bottleneck, this happens during land preparation. Lastly, threshing is already mechanized in many of the rice areas.

Table 25 indicates the response of farmers in Isabela and Cotabato provinces to queries about labor shortages. The Tacurong and Midsayap, Cotabato farmers indicated no serious labor-hiring difficulties. However, in Isabela, 50 percent of the farmers encountered difficulty in hiring labor for

land preparation. Further, there was some labor shortage in each farm operation. Of the three major rice areas, Isabela may suffer a serious labor shortage.

Varieties planted are indicative of the change taking place in a region. A change in cultural practices may well indicate a propensity to change toward mechanization. Tables 26 and 27 list the varieties planted in Central Luzon and in the

Laguna and Isabela provinces. For Central Luzon and Laguna one-crop farms, which are usually rainfall-dependent, no sampled farm grew an improved variety. For the two-crop farms, 26 of 41 farms in Laguna grew an improved variety in the wet season, and 13 of 27 farms in the dry season. For Central Luzon two-crop farms, six of 24 in the wet season and all of four in the dry season grew improved varieties. This indicates that changes are taking place in the irrigated farms, but not in the rainfall-dependent farms. For Isabela Province, 24 of 104 farms, or about 20 percent, indicated that they were growing an improved variety.

Rice yields were obtained by harvesting 4 sq m plots. The yields for Central Luzon are summarized in Table 28. Data on factors affecting these

yields have also been collected and will be presented in a later report. These data, however, do not accurately reflect the yield realized by the farmer as several factors are left out. One is the usual field loss during harvesting and threshing. Another is an upward bias in the yield estimate due to the sampling method. Also, the levees and unproductive areas were not included in the samples.

In the 1967 Annual Report, the estimated yields as gathered from interview data averaged 25 percent less than the harvested samples. Considering this reduction, the yields are not high. It is interesting to note that the improved varieties had distinctly higher over-all yields than the more traditional varieties.

Table 26. Rice varieties planted in Laguna and Central Luzon, 1967-1968 cropping season.*

Variety	One-crop farm		Two-crop farm				Total
			1st crop	1st crop	2nd crop	2nd crop	
	Laguna	C. Luzon	Laguna	C. Luzon	Laguna	C. Luzon	
	No. of farms						
Tjeremas		15		1			16
Intan		13	1	1	12		27
Ramajah		7					7
BE-3		5					5
BPI-121		3					3
Raminad		2					2
Peta		1	1				2
Binato		1		14			15
Darrah		1					1
Piling Baybay	1		1				2
(Not listed)	3	3					6
IR5**			2				2
IR8**			22	6	13	4	45
Glutinous			9		1		10
BPI-76**			1				1
C ₄ -63**			1				1
Wagway			1		1		2
Thailand			1	1			2
Milagrosa				1			1
Cotabato			1				1
Total	4	51	41	24	27	4	151

* Sample of farms.

** Improved varieties.

Table 27. Rice varieties planted in Isabela province, 1967 wet-season crop.

Variety	No. of farms grown
Intan	19
IR8*	17
Raminad	12
Wagway	8
Ramadja (Ramajah)	6
BPI-76*	5
Los Baños	4
Magsaysay	3
Ketchel (Seraup Ketchel)	4
Glutinous	2
Besar	2
Magralia	2
Peta	2
Milfor	2
Buenketan	2
IR5*	1
BPI-121	1
F-76	1
Milagrosa	1
Binato	1
Tjeremas	1
C-4*	1
Bicol Selection	1
Majrasia	1
Miniranda	1
Zero	1
London	1
Binuldozer	1
Squad	1
Total	104

* Improved varieties.

Analysis of Soil Penetrating Resistance

The study on soil resistance and trafficability was aimed at obtaining quantitative data on soil characteristics, i.e., what percent of the lowland rice-growing areas have soils too soft to support power equipment? Perhaps a future objective will be to look more into tractor mobility indices for specific power units.

The soil trafficability study was and is being conducted in two major rice areas in the Philip-

pinos – Central Luzon and Cagayan Valley in north-eastern Luzon. Rice soils in these areas are generally clayey, varying from sandy clay loam to heavy clay. The randomly selected fields were either non-irrigated (one-crop) or irrigated (two or more crops a year).

Two instruments were used: the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers WES Cone Penetrometer and the self-recording Japanese-made penetro-shear graph called Soil Values Meter TN-4.

Measurements with the WES cone penetrometer were made on 145 rice fields in Central Luzon in 1966-67 and have been reported earlier. The results demonstrated that the irrigated two-crop fields were, on the average, considerably softer than the one-crop fields (Fig. 42). Furthermore, the analysis showed that, on the average, the soils of Laguna Province were softer than those of Central Luzon. Based on a rule of thumb that a

Table 28. Central Luzon: mean yields from sampled 4-sq m plots, 1967-68 crop year.*

Variety	Fields sampled	First crop (kg/ha rough rice)
IR8	28	4882.04
IR5	2	4865.50
C4	1	4619.00
BPI-76	1	4548.00
Glutinous (Malagkit)	9	4132.67
Piling Baybay	1	3706.00
Darra	1	3698.00
Thailand	2	3336.50
Binato	15	3148.93
BE-3	5	3136.60
Ramajah	7	3126.57
Raminad	2	3115.50
Cotabato	1	3055.00
Tjeremas	16	2987.81
Intan	14	2972.93
Peta	2	2827.00
Wagway	1	2326.00
BPI-121 (Macapagal)	3	2142.00
Milagrosa	1	1758.00

* Sample of field.

critical index is reached at a depth of 30 cm (12 inches) under a pressure of 70 psi where a 50-hp standard tractor can expect to encounter bogging problems, 62 percent of the fields measured in Central Luzon were firmer than the 30-cm depth; for Laguna Province only 42 percent of the fields were as firm at plowing and 30 percent at harrowing time. In northeastern Luzon (Isabela Province) the majority of the fields measured apparently offer no bogging problems to large equipment (Fig. 43).

Measurements with the Soil Values Meter TN-4 were taken recently in the Central Luzon area at three stages of operation: immediately before land preparation, during final harrowing, and just after harvest. Similarly, these measurements demonstrated that the irrigated two-crop fields and the Laguna soils are softer than those in Central Luzon (Figs. 44, 45 and 46).

In Isabela Province, measurements with the TN-4 meter at different stages of the cropping season (Fig. 47) showed that, on the average, the two-crop rice soils are softest during the harrowing stage and firmest at harvest. Furthermore, the graph confirms the result of the test with the WES cone penetrometer that the soils in the area apparently offer no bogging problems to large

equipment.

To examine some fields that are continuously under water, a test was conducted on some continuously cropped fields (three crops a year) at the Institute. The results (Fig. 48) showed that at

Fig. 42. Cumulative frequency of various mean soil depths (cm) during plowing or harrowing at which a U.S. Army Corps of Engineers WES Cone Penetrometer had a resistance of 70 psi. Central Luzon and Laguna Provinces, Philippines (1966-67).

Fig. 43. Cumulative frequency of various mean soil depths (cm) during the plowing, harrowing, transplanting, vegetative, or reproductive stages at which a U.S. Army Corps of Engineers WES Cone Penetrometer had a resistance of 70 psi. Isabela, Philippines (October 23, 1967-January 13, 1968).

Fig. 44. Mean soil resistances at different depths (cone index) measured just before land preparation with the Soil Values Meter TN-4. The numbers of measured sites are enclosed in parentheses. Laguna and Central Luzon Provinces (1967-68).

Fig. 45. Mean soil resistances at different depths (cone index) measured during final harrowing with the Soil Values Meter TN-4. The numbers of measured sites are enclosed in parentheses. Laguna and Central Luzon, Philippines (1967-68).

penetrating resistances of 35 psi (2.464 kg/sq cm) and 70 psi (4.928 kg/sq cm), the average soil depths were 39 and 57 cm, respectively. Under these conditions, the standard tractor is not able to work. The soil resistance of a water-logged area in Isabela was measured and the results are presented in Fig. 49. The average soil depths at 35 psi and 70 psi were 44 cm and 48 cm, respectively.

Two tests on cone index measurements with respect to time were done using the TN-4 meter. The first case (Fig. 50) was to measure the change in soil resistance from a dry state to a condition

after it had been continuously flooded for a time. This was done to establish the optimum time for land preparation and to avoid work in excessively softened flooded soils. In this experiment the

Fig. 46. Mean soil resistances at different depths (cone index) measured just after harvest with the Soil Values Meter TN-4. The numbers of measured sites are enclosed in parentheses. Central Luzon and Laguna Provinces, Philippines (1967).

Fig. 47. Mean soil resistances at different soil depths (cone index) measured at different stages during the cropping season of two-crop fields with the Soil Values Meter TN-4. The numbers of measured sites are enclosed in parentheses. Isabela Province, Philippines (1968).

Fig. 48. Actual measurements recorded by the Soil Values Meter TN-4 on one of IRRI's Maximum Production Plots (3 crops per year), Laguna Province, Philippines (1967).

Fig. 49. Actual measurements recorded by the Soil Values Meter TN-4 on a water-logged area. An ISEKI KF-850 was tested on this field and bogged down. Isabela Province, Philippines (1968).

change in penetrometer reading was abrupt after the first 5 hours, and then decreased until it became insignificant with respect to time. This particular field, one of the Institute's maximum production plots, will not be workable by a standard tractor after it has been flooded for 5 hours. The cone index at the time was 70 psi at a depth of 30 cm. However, further tests are needed, at the TN-4 meter indicated that the sub-soil was already soft, although hard on top.

The second case (Fig. 51) was a change from the harvesting stage to a dry state. The change in soil resistance was more or less gradual with respect to time. This field, also a maximum production plot but in another location, could be prepared for the next crop with a standard tractor

Fig. 50. Change in soil resistance from an idle dry state to a condition after soil has been flooded for a time. Measurements made with Soil Values Meter TN-4. IRRI, Laguna Province, Philippines (1968).

Fig. 51. Change in soil resistance from harvesting to a dry state measured with Soil Values Meter TN-4. IRRI, Laguna Province, Philippines (1968).

about 3 days (70 hours) after harvesting. The soil at the time had a unit resistance of 70 psi at 30 cm depth.

Economics of Use of Different threshers

Mechanically powered threshers are gaining popularity in the tropical rice-growing regions. Because their cost is an important item in producing farm products, farmers are often faced with the choice of buying or hiring a threshing machine. The shortage of labor during the harvest season may induce some of the farmers to purchase their own power threshers. Most farmers would be interested in the relative cost of threshing by other methods (like hand threshing, using pedal thresher, trampling by animals, etc.) before making the purchase. They would like to know the number of hectares or hours of use needed to make the machine pay. The various types of threshers available in the market and the availability of custom threshing make it increasingly difficult to select the best machine and method of threshing.

This study was undertaken to obtain information on the average costs of owning and operating some of the threshers currently available in the Philippines. Such information would help farmers in choosing the right thresher and thresher designers in developing new threshing machines. The following analysis is primarily based on data gathered at the Institute from performance tests conducted on several threshers.

	Make of thresher	Output per hour	
		cavans	kilograms
1. IRRI drum-type paddy thresher			
	<u>Feeding method</u>		
a. Four-man method (2 men pick-transfer and 2 men thresh)		4.02	176.88
b. Five-man method (2 men pick-transfer and 3 men thresh)		5.70	250.80
c. Six-man method (2 men pick-transfer and 4 men thresh)		7.15	314.60
2. Japanese automatic thresher, 3 men		4.40	193.60
3. Locally made threshers			
a. Make I (4 men)		2.66	117.04
b. Make II (3 men)		3.60	158.40

Thresher costs

Two groups of factors affect the cost of using a thresher: (1) those related to machine ownership and (2) those related to machine operation. The costs associated with the first group of factors are referred to as fixed costs and those associated with the second group are called variable costs.

Fixed costs result from mere ownership and will be incurred whether the thresher is used or not. In determining the fixed cost associated with thresher ownership, only the depreciation and interest on investment were considered.

Depreciation is a typical cost item. It consists of: (1) depreciation due to use, i.e., loss of service capacity due to wear, and (2) time depreciation which is independent of use and is usually due to obsolescence, rust, decay, and other factors. The

Table 29. Hourly operating cost of different threshers.

Item	IRRI paddy power thresher			Japanese automatic thresher 3 men	Locally-made thresher	
	4 men	5 men	6 men		Make I 4 men	Make II 3 men
	(pesos/hr)					
Labor	1.75	2.19	2.62	1.31	1.75	1.31
Fuel	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.51	0.45	0.70
Oil	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.012	0.015	0.009
Repairs	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.66	0.63	0.46
Total	2.66	3.10	3.53	2.60	2.98	2.48

Table 30. Total cost of using different threshers.

Item	IRRI drum-type paddy thresher	Japanese automatic thresher	Locally-made thresher	
			Make I	Make II
Initial cost (₱)	2500	3500	6750	2464
Estimated service life* (hr)	3200 (5 yrs)	3200 (5 yrs)	6400 (10 yrs)	3200 (5 yrs)
Fixed cost (cost of ownership) (₱)				
Depreciation (assuming a trade-in value 10% of initial cost)	2250	3150	6075	2217.60
Interest (12% a year)	555	777	2814.75	547
Total	2805	3927	8889.75	2764.60
Variable cost (cost of operation) (₱)				
Repairs (60% of initial cost)	1500	2100	4050	1478.40
Fuels (₱0.286/liter)	1372.80	1625.57	2928.64	2242.24
Oil (₱1.50/liter)	30	40	100	30
Labor				
3 men		4200		4200
4 men	5600		11200	
5 men	7000			
6 men	8400			
Total				
3 men		7965.57		7950.64
4 men	8502.80		18278.64	
5 men	9902.80			
6 men	11302.80			
Total cost (₱)				
3 men		11892.57		10715.24
4 men	11307.80			
5 men	12707.80			
6 men	14107.80			

* Except for the locally-made thresher (Make I), an estimated service life of 3200 hours (5 years) was assumed for all the thresher studies. This, therefore, becomes one of the limitations of the analysis because, certainly, the service capacities of the threshers are not the same, much less their make and the materials they are made of. Thus, caution should be exercised in using these data.

common practice is to handle all depreciation as a fixed cost. In our analyses, the straight-line method of computing depreciation was used. In this method, the service life of the machine is assumed, thus the yearly depreciation is:

$$\text{Depreciation} = \frac{\text{Original cost} - \text{trade-in value}}{\text{expected life}}$$

Annual interest costs were computed on average investment at the rate of 12 percent per annum. Average investment is half the sum of the purchase price and the resale value. Thus the interest cost for a year is:

$$\text{Interest cost} = \frac{\text{Value of machine for the year in question} + \text{trade-in value}}{2} \times 0.12$$

As stated earlier, the fixed ownership costs are based upon the investment in the machine and would vary with its price.

Variable cost is directly related to machine use and includes maintenance, repairs, fuel, lubricants, and labor. No wage data for threshing operations are available because the common practice in the Philippines is to pay for the threshing in kind on the basis of the weight of the paddy threshed during the day. Therefore, the institutional agricultural wage rate of ₱3.50 per man-day was used in estimating labor cost. It was found that the labor cost for the IRRI drum-type paddy thresher for the four-man, five-man, and six-man methods of feeding would be ₱1.75, ₱2.19, and ₱2.62 per hour, respectively (Table 29). Table 29 also shown the hourly operating cost of the other threshers.

Total costs were calculated for an assumed number of hours of use over the estimated life of the machines. The fixed, variable and total costs for the threshers are shown in Table 30. The hourly operating costs are shown in Table 31 for a wide range of hours of use.

To establish the economic feasibility of use of each machine, the break-even point for the number of hours of operation was calculated by the following formula:

$$B/E = \frac{FC}{TR - TVC}$$

where

- B/E = number of hours of operation to break even with current threshing practices
 FC = fixed cost

Fig. 52. Average cost curves, IRRI drum-type paddy thresher.

- TR = total returns ("custom rate" which is 5% of output times price per cavan)
 TVC = total variable cost (hourly operating cost)

The results are given below:

Machine	Break-even (hours)
A. IRRI paddy thresher	
1. Four-man method	2062
2. Five-man method	1612
3. Six-man method	1104
B. Japanese automatic thresher	3445

The break-even point computations show that, on the average, the choice of thresher will greatly depend upon utilization. To elucidate this point, let us turn to the IRRI drum-type paddy thresher. The average total cost per hour curves on the IRRI drum-type thresher are shown in Fig. 52. Assuming that the custom rate for threshing is 5 percent of the threshing output (which is a typical threshing rate in the Philippines), the break-even point for the four-man, five-man, and six-man feeding methods would be 2,962, 1,612, and 1,104 hours, respectively. This is based on a ₱17 per cavan (44 kg) price of paddy (rough rice). The price of paddy would have a marked influence on the break-even point and it may be attained earlier or later depending on the direction of change in the price of paddy. Although the cost per hour increases considerably with the number of men used for feeding, the increase is sufficiently justified by the higher returns.

Table 31. Average cost of using different threshers.

Working hours	IRRI paddy power thresher			Japanese automatic thresher 3 men	Locally-made thresher	
	4 men	5 men	6 men		Make I 4 men	Make II 3 men
	(pesos/ hr)					
500	8.27	8.71	9.14	10.34		8.01
1000	5.46	5.90	6.33	6.42	11.73	5.24
1500	4.53	4.97	5.40	5.11		4.32
2000	4.06	4.50	4.93	4.46	7.29	3.86
2500	3.78	4.22	4.65	4.06		3.58
3000	3.59	4.03	4.46	3.80	5.81	3.40
3200	3.54	3.98	4.40	3.72		3.34
4000					5.07	
5000					4.62	
6000					4.33	

Table 32. Specifications of different threshers.

Thresher model	Dimensions			Cylinder		Type of threshing cylinder	Engine		Weight of machine including engine (kg)
	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Height (mm)	Width x dia. (mm)	Rpm		Make	HP	
IRRI drum-type	3570	830	870	500 x 2270	300	U-shaped wire loop	Honda	4.2	500
IRRI table-type	1550	1550	1080	1117*	130	U-shaped wire loop	Honda	4.2	175
Japanese automatic	1100	530	1020	500 x 460	450	U-shaped wire loop	Honda	4.2	150
Locally made Thresher I				500 x 485	750	U-shaped wire loop	Ditter	10.0**	975
Locally made Thresher II				925 x 400	500	U-shaped wire loop	Kawasaki	4.0	
TURNER "Economy"	3400	765	1560	705 x 330	680	Rasp bar	Wisconsin	10.0	820
GARVIE type DA	3962	1575	2083	470 x 508	1450	Rasp bar	Hosch	12.0**	545
Vogel	1820	754	1830	504 x 300	800	Spike tooth	Wisconsin	10.0	

* Diameter of the thresher table.

** Diesel engine.

Table 33. Comparative output of different threshers.

Thresher model	Thresher output (14% m.c.)				Fuel (gas) consumption (l/hr)	Method of feeding*	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Variety
	Low (kg/hr)	m.c. (%)	Average (kg/hr)	m.c. (%)				
IRRI drum-type	46.48	32.0	127.53	24.90	326.16	18.0	2624	Mixed
IRRI drum-type (Clinton)	80.76	25.4	147.0	21.80	249.80	26.0	3300	Mixed
IRRI drum-type (GAMI)	160.76	18.2	212.68	18.20	252.16	18.6	2772	Mixed
IRRI table-type	181.78	32.0	228.86	24.38	267.00	19.3	5280	IR5
Japanese automatic D2L	86.64	31.0	89.73	30.37	95.28	30.0	3300	IR8
Japanese automatic TF50	123.92	26.0	195.52	21.80	261.60	19.6	5280	IR5
Locally made Thresher I	27.56	24.0	117.13	20.77	186.28	19.5	2200	C63
Locally made Thresher II	131.54	18.5	158.50	18.0	181.65	17.0	Unknown	mixed
TURNER "Economy"	163.68	32.0	171.14	31.30	180.72	30.0	3080	C63
GARVIE Type DA	143.92	32.0	163.28	32.00	204.00	32.0	5280	IR5
Vogel	103.00	32.0	118.76	32.00	130.00	32.0	Unknown	mixed
Pedal	61.35	19.8	89.19	19.80	117.04	19.8	Unknown	IR5

* Method of feeding: (1) 4 men pick-thresh; (2) 2 men pick-thresh; (3) 2 men pick-transfer and 1 man thresh; (4) 1 man pick-transfer and 1 man thresh.

** Grain moisture content during threshing.

† Diesel fuel.

A wage rate of ₱3.50 per man-day has been assumed; however, wages may be lower in some areas than in others (Fig. 52). With a custom threshing rate of ₱4.84 per hour, the break-even point for the five-man method is 1,612 hours. In other words, at this number of hours of use the threshing cost is the same by either method – owning the paddy thresher or custom threshing. Thus, with the five-man method, the least cost alternative is custom threshing up to 1,612 hours. To generalize the analysis, various wage rates were substituted into the equation,

$$C = F/A + V + L$$

where

- C = custom rate per hour
- F = fixed cost
- A = break-even point in hours
- V = operating costs per hour
- L = labor cost per hour.

Figure 53 shows the various combinations of labor wage and hours of use for the five-man method. The curve separates the zones for which it costs less to custom hire or to own the paddy thresher. For all combinations of labor cost and hours of use to the right and below the line, it costs less to own the paddy thresher. The competitive position of custom hiring is, therefore, greater at higher wage rates and more hours of use are required to justify ownership of the machine.

Comparative threshing equipment performance

A study was undertaken to establish the performance of the different threshers available in the Philippines. This was necessitated by the recent introduction of the power-operated drum-type paddy thresher. The following threshers were evaluated:

1. IRRI drum-type paddy thresher powered by

Fig. 53. Zones of cost advantage: custom hiring vs. owning IRRI paddy thresher using five-man method.

Table 34. Comparative performance of selected rice threshers.

Thresher model	Machine performance			Power performance			Labor performance			Economic performance			
	kg/hr	ha/hr*	Rat- ing	Eng. hp	Hp-hr/ 44 kg	Rat- ing	No. of men**	Man-hr/ ha*	Grain output/ man-hr (kg)	Rat- ing	Machine cost (₱)	Thresh- ing cost/44kg (₱)	Rat- ing
IRRI drum-type													
Low feed	160.60	0.0365	4.2	1.095	5	136.98	32.12	2500	1.392				
Average feed	216.04	0.0491	4.2	0.855	2	101.83	43.21	2500	1.035	4			
High feed	252.12	0.05373	4.2	0.695	5	87.26	50.42	2500	0.887				
IRRI table-type	228.80	0.0520	4.2	0.807	1	96.17	45.76	1800	0.657	1			
Japanese automatic	195.36	0.0444	4.2	0.946	3	67.56	65.12	3500	.765	2			
Locally made thresher I	117.04	0.0266	8	12.5	4.700	7	172.94	29.26	10	6750	1.512	5	
Locally made thresher II	158.40	0.0360	5	4.0	1.333	4	83.33	52.80	2	2464	0.930	3	
TURNER "Economy"	170.72	0.0288	4	10.0	2.577	5	120.00	39.60	7				
GARVIE Type DA	163.24	0.0371	6	17.5	4.717	8	107.85	40.79	6				
Vogel Nursery	126.72	0.0288	7	10.0	3.473	6	138.81	31.68	9				
Pedal	68.64	0.0156	10			2	128.20	34.32	8				

* Based on 4,400 kg/ha yield.

** Number of men includes one man who collects and sacks the grain.

a 4.2-hp gasoline engine

2. IIRI table-type paddy thresher powered by a 4.2-hp gasoline engine

3. A Japanese automatic thresher powered by a 4.2-hp gasoline engine

4. Locally made thresher Make I powered by a 10-hp diesel engine

5. Locally made thresher Make II powered by a 4.0-hp gasoline engine

6. TURNER "Economy" thresher powered by a 10-hp gasoline engine

7. Vogel thresher powered by a 10-hp gasoline engine

8. GARVIE Type DA thresher powered by a 12-hp diesel engine

9. Pedal thresher, manually operated

The specifications of the threshers are listed in Table 32, and the performance of each thresher is given in Table 33. The IIRI drum-type thresher was tested simultaneously with threshers of other makes in the same field and with the same paddy variety. The paddy used in the tests was freshly harvested, with a grain moisture content varying from 18 percent to over 30 percent. The method of feeding differed for each machine. In the case of the IIRI drum-type paddy thresher, the 4-men pick-thresh method was employed since in earlier tests with this machine good results were obtained by this method. The method of feeding for each machine is shown in Table 33.

The tests were conducted in Laguna and Isabela. Their durations ranged from 15 minutes to 1 hour for every trial. The data were analyzed into three categories: (1) low output when threshing

very wet grain; (2) average output: and (3) high output when feeding at the maximum possible rate. The data shown in Table 33, particularly the thresher output, grain moisture content, and fuel consumption, are the average results of 5 to 10 tests. The thresher output (kg/hr) was adjusted to 14 percent m.c. level.

Table 34 lists the machine, power, labor and economic performance of the different threshers tested at the Institute. Both the IIRI drum-type and table-type threshers indicated excellent performance in almost all categories. The test showed that the IIRI threshers could thresh an average of 216.04 and 228.80 kg of palay per hour, respectively. The IIRI table-type thresher indicated the top machine, power and economic performance in the whole test. A Japanese automatic thresher indicated best labor performance efficiency of 65.12 kg per man-hour during the test. The IIRI drum thresher held the second, second, fifth and fourth positions in machine, power, labor, and economic performance categories respectively.

The Japanese thresher could not perform well at moisture content levels of above 20 percent. However, both the IIRI drum and table threshers did not indicate any moisture level limitations in threshing. The locally made thresher Make I performed without clogging when threshing wet rice but the output was considerably reduced. With all the threshers of other makes severe clogging problems with paddy of above 20 percent m.c. level were encountered.

Agricultural Economics

A major portion of this report is devoted to research concerned with the adoption of new rice varieties at the farm level. Information regarding the rate of acceptance of new varieties throughout tropical Asia is also presented, although most of the estimates at the national level are not as yet supported by official government surveys.

The report is divided into three sections: (1) The results of surveys showing changes taking place on the farm and the analysis of experiments in fertilizer response and irrigation, (2) The growth of the Philippine fertilizer industry – the second in a series of studies relating to the input requirements for rice production, and (3) An analysis of the response of consumers to changes in income and price, to complement the earlier work on rice supply response in the Philippines. International trends in production and price are discussed in the final section.

Productivity and Efficiency in Rice Production

The objectives of research in productivity and efficiency are to report the change taking place on the farm, to identify the factors influencing change, and to determine the optimum cultural practices to be used in rice production. This section is concerned with the economic aspects of the introduction of new rice varieties and reports on results of experiments conducted to identify the effect of water application below the flooding level on rice yield, a basic issue in water management and irrigation policy.

A case study in the adoption pattern of new rice varieties

Since 1966, a group of 155 farms located in the towns of Biñan, Cabuyao, and Calamba, all in Laguna province, have been surveyed annually to observe the changes taking place with the introduction of new, high-yielding rice varieties. These farms are not typical of those in the Philippines. Although 90 percent of their operators are tenants, both the level of management and the resource input of these farms are higher than would be found in many other regions. Laguna has relatively good irrigation facilities, and its rice yields are well above the national average. Being one of the first provinces to be exposed to the new rice varieties, the data obtained from its farms have provided useful information with respect to the adoption pattern.

Figure 1 shows the trend in adoption by crop season over a 3-year period. Farms are classified by the symbols as full adopters (circle), partial adopters (triangle), and non-adopters (rectangle). A full adopter planted all of his rice land to the improved varieties—IR8, IR5, BPI-76, and/or C4-63. The most commonly planted variety was IR8. During the 1968 wet season only 12 of the 127 adopters were planting new varieties other than IR8.

The small symbols just above the symbol for each season indicate the farm category in the previous season. Thus, for example, of the nine full adopters in the 1967 dry season, one had been a full adopter, one a partial adopter, and seven non-adopters during the 1966 wet season.

The major adoption of the new varieties occurred in the 1967 wet season, which was the first time that a large quantity of seed became available. By the end of 1968, 146 of the 155 farmers had tried the new varieties for at least one season. The land planted to the new varieties reached a maximum of 75 percent in the 1968 wet season. However, a pronounced seasonal pattern was observed, with more being planted to new varieties in the wet than in the dry season. Notice, for example, that during the 1968 dry season 35 of the 56 non-adopters had planted the improved varieties during the previous wet season, and in the 1969 dry season 35 of the 43 non-adopters had planted the improved varieties during the previous wet season.

The reason for this shift between varieties is related to the price differentials. Some local varieties currently sell at a price at least 20 percent more than IR8. Local varieties will respond to medium input levels of nitrogen during the dry season without lodging. This strategy of choosing separate wet- and dry-season varieties was common even before the introduction of the improved varieties, and seems particularly appropriate on those farms with uncertain or limited dry season water resources.

Tables 1 and 2 show some of the physical, economic, and sociological factors associated with the rate and level of adoption. In Table 1, farms were divided into groups based upon the time period in which they first adopted the new varieties. In Table 2, farms were classified according to the level of adoption. Of the 155 farms studied, 60 (40 percent) were classified as full adopters, 48 (31 percent) as partial adopters, and 47 (30 percent) as non-adopters in the 1967 wet season. Partial adopters planted an average of 50 percent of their rice land to the new varieties.

Physical factors. The most important of the physical factors is the irrigation facility. In the wet season farms were classified as either irrigated or rainfed. Both the early adopters (Table 1) and the full adopters (Table 2) had predominantly irrigated farms. The larger farms tended to be operated by late adopters probably because rainfed farms tend to be larger than irrigated farms in this province.

The 1966 wet season yield levels indicate the performance of the various farm groups prior to

Table 1. Physical, economic, and sociological factors related to the time of adoption of new rice varieties among 155 farmers in Laguna, 1966 to 1968.

Factors	Time of first adoption				
	1966	1967		1968	
	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season
No. of new adopters	6	17	88	20	15
Physical factors (wet season)					
Farms irrigated (%)	100	92	80	45	67
Area planted - 1967 (ha)	1.8	2.0	2.4	2.5	2.6
Area new varieties- 1967 (ha)	1.2	1.5	1.8	0	0
Yield-1966 - actual (kg/ha rough rice)	2860	2816	2464	1936	2376
Yield-1967 - expected (kg/ha rough rice)	4884	4928	4092	3256	3124
- actual (kg/ha rough rice)	4532	4356	3300	2200	2200
Yield-1968 - expected (kg/ha rough rice)	4356	4136	3740	3168	2948
- actual (kg/ha rough rice)	3652	3696	3380	2332	2640
Economic factors (wet season)					
Variable costs* - 1966 (P/ha)	347	314	259	239	260
Variable costs* - 1967 (P/ha)	515	472	379	290	314
Price rough rice - 1966 (P/ha)	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.39
Price rough rice - 1967 (P/kg)	0.39	0.41	0.39	0.50	0.50
Price rough rice - 1968 (P/kg)	0.36	0.41	0.34	0.34	0.32
Return to variable costs - 1966 (P/ha)	826	841	751	555	667
Return to variable costs - 1967 (P/ha)	1253	1314	908	810	786
Sociological factors					
Contact with extension (no.)	11	9	4	2	5
Education (grades)	5	4	4	2	2
Age (years)	48	53	44	49	48

* Variable costs include cash costs plus harvester's share and amount withheld for seed. \$1.00=P3.90.

Time of Adoption	Number of farmers belonging to each category			Planted to new varieties	
	Full adopter	Partial adopter	Non adopter	Area(%)	Farms (%)
Wet Season, 1966	①	△5	□149	1.0	3.9
Previous Season	① △ 7	△ 2 □ 10	△ 2 □ 132	8.1	13.6
Dry Season, 1967	⑨	△ 12	□ 134		
Previous Season	⑧ △ 4 □ 48	△ 6 □ 42	① △ 2 □ 42	54.5	69.7
Wet Season, 1967	⑥0	△ 48	□ 47		
Previous Season	④1 △ 8 □ 13	⑤ △ 15 □ 9	⑬3 △ 22 □ 21	53.4	61.9
Dry Season, 1968 *	⑥2	△ 23	□ 56		
Previous Season	④8 △ 12 □ 23	⑧ △ 14 □ 22	④ △ 2 □ 10	74.7	87.0
Wet Season, 1968 **	⑧3	△ 44	□ 19 ***		
Previous Season	④7 △ 11 □ 5	⑥ △ 25 □ 1	⑲7 △ 8 □ 8	66.5	68.8
Dry Season, 1969 *	⑥3	△ 32	□ 43		

Fig. 1. Adoption trend of new rice varieties among 155 farmers. Laguna, Philippines, 1966-1969

* Eight farmers did not plant rice in dry season.

** Nine farmers stopped rice farming.

*** Three farmers did not plant rice in the previous season.

the introduction of the new varieties. The earliest adopters, shown in Table 1, were already planting the new varieties in 1966, but only to a small percentage of their total land. Those that adopted later showed significantly lower yields prior to adoption. However, the differences between the yields of the partial and full adopters (Table 2) were not significant in this pre-adoption period.

The average farm yields in the 1967 wet season declined in accordance with the level of adoption. However, the trend in the period of adoption declined not only in the absolute levels of yield gain over 1966, but also in the percentage of gain. Questions regarding expected yield were asked *ex post*. The early adopters more nearly approached their expected 1967 yield than the late adopters. The same can be said for the full adopters vs the non-adopters.

Economic factors. Yield performance is closely related to irrigation facilities, as previously discussed, and to the level of variable inputs such as fertilizers, insecticides, and labor. The average variable cost per farm for the 1966 and 1967 wet seasons is shown in Table 3. The costs were higher on those farms that switched to the new varieties, but appear to have increased somewhat even for the non-adopters. The increase in expenditure for specific inputs in the 1967 wet season were itemized in the 1967 Annual Report and those in the 1968 wet season are shown in Table 3 of this report.

The early adopters were able to maintain a relatively high and stable price for their rice primarily by switching some land back to one of the group of local glutinous varieties which are known as Malagkit. The price of Malagkit has been

Table 2. Physical, economic, and sociological factors related to the degree of adoption of new varieties among 155 farmers in Laguna, 1967 wet season.

Factors	Full adopters (100%)	Partial adopters (48%)	Non-adopters (0%)
No. of farms	60	48	47
Physical factors			
Farms irrigated (%)	93	79	69
Area planted (ha)	2.4	2.4	2.4
Area new varieties (ha)	2.4	1.2	0
Yield 1966 - actual (kg/ha rough rice)	2684	2552	2288
Yield 1967 - expected (kg/ha rough rice)	4796	4048	3212
- actual (kg/ha rough rice)	4224	3256	2112
Yield 1968 - expected (kg/ha rough rice)	3916	3564	3344
- actual (kg/ha rough rice)	3476	3520	2772
Economic factors			
Variable costs - 1966 (P/ha) *	296	261	253
Variable costs - 1967 (P/ha) *	440	418	313
Price rough rice - 1966 (P/kg)	0.41	0.41	0.41
Price rough rice - 1967 (P/kg)	0.32	0.41	0.48
Price rough rice - 1968 (P/kg)	0.34	0.34	0.36
Return to variable costs - 1966 (P/ha)	804	785	685
Return to variable costs - 1967 (P/ha)	912	917	701
Sociological factors			
Contact with extension (no.)	6	3	3
Education (grades)	5	4	2
Age (years)	44	45	44

* Variable costs include cash costs plus harvesters share and amount withheld for seed. US\$1.00=P3.90.

nearly double that of IR8 for the past two years because of its demand for special uses. Late adopters who switched land out of such varieties in 1968 experienced a large decline in average prices received for their rice. A comparison of costs and returns between IR8 and the glutinous varieties or Malagkit is shown in the following section.

Sociological factors. Over 50 percent of the farmers surveyed reported that the extension worker was the major source of their information regarding new varieties. The second most important information source was the neighboring farmers. Neighbors played an important role in

two other respects. Eighty-six percent of those interviewed first saw the new varieties in neighbors' fields, and neighbors provided the source of 60 percent of the seed. The early adopters and the full adopters generally received more assistance from extension personnel. Radio appears to have been a more important source of information than printed material. Seventy-three percent of those interviewed indicated that they had read no publications regarding the new varieties.

Implication of the analysis. The analysis indicates that yield gains decline sharply with the increase in the number of adopters. Early adopters have the resources needed to achieve the high yield

Table 3. Returns and costs per hectare of rough rice for IR8 and glutinous rice varieties on 60 farms in Laguna, 1968 wet season.

Items	Full adopters	Non-adopters	Partial adopters	
	IR8	glutinous rice	IR8	glutinous rice
No. of farms	30	15	15	15
Physical inputs				
Average area of varieties (ha/farm)	2.4	1.6	1.0	1.0
Nitrogen (kg/ha)	78	56	79	68
Labor (man-days/ha)				
Cash costs				
Fertilizer expenses (P/ha)	92	63	95	76
Insecticides expenses (P/ha)	24	11	25	11
Weedicides expenses (P/ha)	10	7	10	8
Yield of rough rice in:				
Kg/ha	3696	2816	4004	2904
Cavans/ha	84	64	91	68
Standard deviation (cavans/ha)	17	19	17	23
Price of rough rice				
P/kg	0.28	0.53	0.28	0.53
P/cavan	12.50	23.50	12.50	23.50
Variable costs (P/ha)	475	458	494	484
Return over variable costs (P/ha)	575	1046	644	1114

potential of the new varieties. It appears that the delay in acceptance of and the decision not to plant the new varieties are related to the availability of irrigation facilities, the level of inputs used, and the extent of extension support. However, the causal relationships among these factors have not been specifically determined. Not only the difference in water resources but also the current price differential between new and local varieties have caused a complex pattern of shift between varieties from season to season.

Cost and returns of selected varieties in the provinces of Laguna and Rizal

Although Laguna and Rizal are neighboring provinces, they differ in the pattern of adoption of new rice varieties. In Laguna, the predominant

new rice variety in the municipalities surveyed has been IR8. The local glutinous varieties (or Malagkit) have also gained in popularity due to the high prices received. In Rizal, a large number of farmers switched from IR8 to C4-63 in the 1968 dry season. This is a new variety developed by the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines. It is similar in plant type to IR5, but has a better grain quality and commands a higher price. The glutinous varieties are not grown in Rizal. Among the local varieties, Intan and BE-3 are the most popular in the wet season and Binato (or Thailand) in the dry season.

Laguna Province. Sixty farm records from the 1968 survey were selected to compare the costs and returns for IR8 and the glutinous varieties.

The results are summarized in Table 3. (This table is organized in the same manner as Table 3 in the 1967 Annual Report, and the reader may wish to compare the results for the two years).

The input levels and the yields were significantly higher for IR8 than for the glutinous varieties. The input levels for IR8 in 1967 and 1968 were about the same although the yields for 1968 were somewhat lower. The quantity of inputs used for the glutinous varieties, however, was significantly higher than that used for local varieties in 1967. For example, for those growing only the glutinous varieties, 56 kg/ha N were

applied, while in 1967, for those growing only local varieties, 20 kg/ha N were used. As a consequence of this generally higher input level, the yield differences between IR8 and the glutinous varieties were less pronounced than those between IR8 and local varieties reported in the previous year.

The cash inputs used for IR8 were higher than those for the glutinous varieties. However, the variable costs for the two kinds of varieties were about the same. This similarity is due to the higher value of glutinous rice which is traded in kind for

Table 4. Returns and costs per hectare of rough rice for selected varieties, Rizal, 1967 wet season.*

Items	IR8	BPI-76	Intan
No. of farms	102	26	38
Physical inputs			
Average area of variety (ha/farm)	0.82	0.80	1.07
Cash costs and costs in kind			
Fertilizer (P/ha)	62	20	26
Chemicals (P/ha)	15	3	6
Others costs (P/ha)			
Land preparation	52	58	30
Pulling of seedlings	26	16	25
Transplanting	43	38	45
Weeding	16	25	7
Harvesting, threshing and seeds	303	165	192
Total	517	325	331
Yield of rough rice in:			
Kg/ha	3608	2772	2820
Cavans/ha	82	63	64
Standard duration (cavans/ha)	57	42	32
Price of rough rice **			
P/kg	0.28	0.35	0.35
P/cavans	12.34	15.43	15.43
Return over variable cost (P/ha)	495	647	657

* These data are summarized from records provided by the Agricultural Development Council of Rizal.

** Prices used are based upon Bureau of Agricultural Economics prices received by farmers for ordinary rough rice, November-December, 1967. Price of IR8 is reduced by 20 percent.

Table 5. Returns and costs per hectare of rough rice for selected varieties, Rizal, 1968 dry season.*

Items	IR8	IR5	C ₄ -63	Binato
No. of farms	179	16	93	40
Physical inputs				
Average area of variety (ha/farm)	.70	.60	.80	.60
Cash costs and costs in kind				
Fertilizer (P/ha)	89	138	103	35
Chemicals (P/ha)	18	28	25	14
Other cash costs (P/ha)				
Land preparation	50	45	56	26
Pulling of seedlings	23	13	21	14
Weeding	31	11	23	9
Transplanting	49	46	52	34
Harvesting, threshing, and seeds	267	347	274	210
Total	527	628	554	342
Yield of rough rice in:				
Kg/ha	4660	7130	4310	3920
Cavans/ha	106	162	98	89
Standard deviation (cavan/ha)	71	86	60	40
Price of rough rice **				
P/kg	0.29	0.33	0.36	0.29
P/cavan	12.83	14.44	16.04	12.83
Return over variable cost (P/ha)	833	1711	1018	800

* These data are summarized from survey records provided by the Agricultural Development Council of Rizal.

** Prices used are based upon Bureau of Agricultural Economics prices received by farmers for ordinary rough rice, March-April, 1968. Price of IR5 is reduced by 10 percent, and price of IR8 and Binato by 20 percent.

the harvester's share, thus offsetting the lower cash expenses.

The returns over variable costs were nearly twice as high for the glutinous varieties as for IR8. However, the wide price differential between these two varieties is likely to be a temporary phenomenon. The total hectareage planted to the glutinous varieties in the Philippines is extremely small. In 1967 the price per cavan (44 kg) of rough rice of these varieties approached P30,* but now has already fallen substantially from this level.

Rizal Province. Again this year, through the courtesy of the Agricultural Development Council

of Rizal (ADCR) and Agricultural Executives Inc. who conducted the initial surveys, an analysis was made of costs and returns for selected varieties in the 1967 wet season and in the 1968 dry season. Data were collected from a 10-percent sample of lowland rice farms in Rizal (with a minimum of 2 farms per municipality). The results are shown in Tables 4 and 5. (For easy comparison, these tables are organized in the same manner as Table 2 in the 1967 Annual Report).

* US\$1 = P3.90

The 166 farms growing IR8, BPI-76, and Intan during the 1967 wet season represented about 60 percent of the total number of farms surveyed. The yield and input levels were higher for IR8 than for the other two varieties (Table 4). However, as observed in the Laguna surveys, the gap between the yields of IR8 and other varieties has been substantially reduced as IR8 has become more widely accepted. The price received for rough rice is not available from the Rizal surveys. Many farms in this province sell rice for seed at prices well above the normal level (P30 to P35 vs P12 to P17 per cavan of 44 kilograms). The price used to compute gross returns was the average farm price in the Philippines for the 1967 November-December main harvest period. The price of IR8 was reduced 20 percent below this level, since both BPI-76 and Intan are reputed to have superior grain quality. Had the price of IR8 been equal to those of the other varieties, the return over variable costs would have exceeded that of Intan.

The first major planting in Rizal of two additional new varieties, IR5 and C4-63, was made in the 1968 dry season. Those who adopted these two varieties appear to have been the leading farmers. The growers of IR5 were a group especially selected by the ADCR for seed multiplication. Their input and yield levels were exceedingly high. The yields and inputs for C4-63 slightly exceeded the levels for IR8. The local variety, Binato, performed well with a per hectare production cost considerably lower than those of the new varieties. Of the four varieties (which were planted on 95 percent of the surveyed farms), C4-63 currently commands the highest price. The price of IR5 was assumed to be 10 percent below that of C4-63 and the prices of IR8 and Binato were reduced by 20 percent in computing the returns to variable costs.

Implications of the analysis. In the Philippines, the current farm price support is about P0.40 per kilogram of rough rice. However, the government lacks the finances to purchase more than a small fraction of the total production. The recent increase in production has pushed the open market price well below the support level. At the same time there is a price differential of approximately 20 percent between the average- and the better-quality rice varieties. Under the existing market

price differentials, IR8, the most widely disseminated of the new varieties, is receiving strong competition from high-priced local varieties such as the glutinous ones and Intan. Farmers reflect their sensitivity to these price differentials by switching back and forth between varieties, looking for the combination of price and yield potentials that will give the highest profits. As a consequence, progressive producers are still finding it profitable in some cases to plant local varieties. Efforts to improve grain quality are being continued at IRRI and in the many country breeding programs in Asia. It will be possible in the near future to select from a wide range of high-yielding varieties the one which best suits the particular farm situation. No one can say at this time which of the new varieties will become the most popular. However, these economic studies of farm costs and returns in the Philippines suggest that IR8, the best known and most widely planted of the new varieties, may soon be replaced by others of superior grain quality.

Optimum level of fertilizer application under uncertain situations

Annual variability in yield performance and price have an important bearing not only on the acceptance of new varieties but also on the level of inputs used with these varieties. Under normal conditions, the yield response and price for a given year cannot be known in advance. For these situations of uncertainty, decision-making rules have been developed. A study was conducted to determine the optimum level of nitrogen that should be applied using specified decision-making criteria.

The analysis was based on 3 years of experimental data on the yield response of IR8 and Peta to nitrogen. The experiments were conducted at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Nueva Ecija under the supervision of the Agronomy Department, IRRI, in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry. IR8 and Peta were chosen because they were representative of two plant types – the new, short-stemmed indica, and the traditional, tall indica, respectively. The results from the Maligaya center were used because this station is located in Central Luzon, the largest rice-producing area in the Philippines.

Fig. 2. Variability in optimum level of nitrogen and yield output due to yield effect. Maligaya, 1966, 1967, and 1968 dry seasons.

The analysis involved a single location and a period of 3 years. However, the data illustrate the basic problem of decision-making when both weather and price cannot be predicted with certainty.

Annual variability in yield response. The response functions in each of the 3 years for the wet and the dry seasons are shown in Figs. 2,A and 2,B, respectively. Annual variability is particularly marked during the wet season, the main rice-growing period throughout the tropics, because of frequent typhoons, floods and drought. The contrast between these two figures suggests that the relative advantage enjoyed by regions of dry climate production is due not only to the high yield potential, but also to the relatively low variability in the response functions.

During the 1966 wet season at the Maligaya Center, there was no crop damage by unusually bad weather. However, the 1967 wet-season crop was severely damaged by a strong typhoon (which caused Peta to lodge severely) and a subsequent attack of bacterial leaf blight. The 1968 wet season was also unusual in that Central Luzon experienced a serious drought. For the many farmers who could not avail themselves of irrigation water, this resulted in losses in yields and in fertilizer investments. However, at the Maligaya

Center, where the water supply was adequate, the best yields were achieved by both IR8 and Peta at the highest level of fertilizer input, 150 kg/ha N.

Decision-making under certainty. The first step in the analysis is to determine the levels of nitrogen that would be used if one could know in advance the price and the response function that would occur in a given year. The optimum is based upon a profit maximizing point where the marginal return from the output is equal to the marginal cost of the input ($MR = MC$). That is to say, the peso return due to the increase in rice yield from the last bag of fertilizer equals the cost of the bag of fertilizer. Computations of maximum profit for Peta are based upon the price of ordinary rice at the farm level as reported by the Philippine Bureau of Agricultural Economics, while the price of IR8 is set 20 percent below this level. The prices used are the average in November-December, the main wet season harvest months, and in March-April, the main dry season harvest months. The price is ₱1.18 per kilogram of elemental nitrogen in the form of urea, with 10 percent added for interest. The output is reduced by one-sixth to allow for the normal harvester's share. The optimum input-output levels for fertilizer and rice are shown in Fig. 2. The optimum

Fig. 3. Variability in optimum level of nitrogen and yield output level due to price effect. Maligaya, 1966, 1967, and 1968 wet and dry seasons. Observations combined.

point is marked with a circle on each function.

Decision-making under uncertainty. In comparing the fertilizer response potential of two rice varieties, a common procedure is to compute an average function using the data available from several years' experiments. This procedure was followed in the 1967 Report with only 2 years of observation. Allowance was made for uncertainty by computing the optimum level of fertilizer input at a benefit-cost ratio of 2½ to 1. This ratio was based on the observed marginal returns to capital on irrigated Philippine rice farms.

The same procedure is followed in the computation of Fig. 3. The optimum levels of fertilizer input are shown for three price levels: ₱0.24, ₱0.32, and ₱0.40 per kilogram of rough rice. The high level is the approximate government support price, and the low level is the approximate open market farm price for rough rice in Central Luzon during the early part of the 1968 harvest season. The optimum amount of fertilizer to be used does not change greatly over this wide range of price variation.

The procedure of averaging functions is similar but not identical to the La Place decision-making criterion based upon the "principle of insufficient reason." The decision problem in uncertainty is treated as a risk problem with each of the response functions being assigned an equal probability. This procedure is appropriate if (as in the case of the dry season) the variance of outcomes is rather small. It is also appropriate for an individual planning over the long run who has sufficient financial resources so that his operation will not be threatened by loss in a single year.

Decision-making with respect to the level of fertilizer to use is frequently in the hands of tenant-farmers or small land owners with limited finances. Many of these farmers would assign a low value or utility to the outcome represented by the 1967 wet season, particularly if it meant the possible inability to repay fertilizer loans or obtain credit for fertilizer in the following crop season. Based on the *Wold minimax criterion*, which is appropriate in this situation, the strategy is to assume that the most unfavorable outcome will prevail, and to maximize utility assuming this outcome. In this case, for the wet season, one assumes the 1967 function (see Fig. 2,A) and determines the level of fertilizer that will maxi-

Table 6. Level of nitrogen input using three decision-making strategies for IR8 and Peta at varying prices, based on experiments at Maligaya, 1966, 1967 and 1968 wet and dry seasons.

Price (₱)	Decision-making criterion		
	Average of functions (kg elemental nitrogen)	<i>Wald minimax</i>	<i>Savage regret</i>
Wet season			
IR8			
0.24	60	0	90
0.32	60	0	90
0.40	90	30	90
Peta			
0.24	0	0	30
0.32	0	0	30
0.40	0	0	30
Dry season			
IR8			
0.24	90	150	180
0.32	120	150	180
0.40	120	180	180
Peta			
0.24	0	0	30
0.32	0	0	30
0.40	30	0	30

mize profits in this least favorable year.

Still another decision-making strategy is known as the *Savage regret criterion*. The objective here is not to minimize the chances of loss, but rather to minimize the chances of foregoing a big profit. The criterion is less conservative than the *minimax* and is appropriate when there is a large gain to be realized if the most favorable situation is comparatively small. Examining Fig. 2,A, this appears to describe the situation represented by the three IR8 functions. By comparison, the magnitude of the yield loss is greater and that of the potential yield gain smaller for Peta than for IR8.

Table 7. Return above fertilizer cost per hectare for three different decision-making strategies and for perfect knowledge, based on experiments at Maligaya, 1966, 1967, and 1968 wet and dry season.*

Year	Average of function		Wald minimax		Savage regret		Perfect knowledge	
	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Returns (₱/ha)	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Returns (₱/ha)	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Returns (₱/ha)	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Returns (₱/ha)
Wet season								
IR8								
1966	60	574	0	0	90	690	104	698
1967	60	-31	0	0	90	100	8	1
1968	60	178	0	0	90	227	128	251
Total		721		0		817		950
Peta								
1966	0	0	0	0	30	211	65	296
1967	0	0	0	0	30	107	0	0
1968	0	0	0	0	30	7	0	0
Total		0		0		97		296
Dry season								
IR8								
1966	120	499	150	532	180	492	162	534
1967	120	662	150	696	180	678	155	696
1968	120	346	150	364	180	355	157	365
Total		1507		1592		1525		1595
Peta								
1966	0	0	0	0	30	14	29	16
1967	0	0	0	0	30	110	51	132
1968	0	0	0	0	30	70	48	81
Total		0		0		194		229

* Assumed price ₱ per kilogram of rough rice:

	Wet		Dry	
	IR8	Peta	IR8	Peta
1966	0.26	0.32	0.25	0.31
1967	0.23	0.29	0.26	0.33
1968	0.22	0.27	0.24	0.30

Application of decision-making criteria. This analysis was conducted in two steps and the results are summarized in Tables 6 and 7. The first step was to determine the optimum level of fertilizer to be used under each of the decision-making rules just described. Table 6 lists these rules. The

optimum level was determined for each season and variety assuming three different price levels. The results are expressed to the nearest 30 kg of elemental nitrogen.

Regardless of the variety or the decision-making rule chosen, shifts in rice price from a high of P0.40 per kilogram (P17.60 per cavan) to a low of P0.24 per kilogram (P10.56 per cavan) change the optimum fertilizer level by not more than 30 kg. For Peta, it never pays to apply more than 30 kg/ha of fertilizer. The choice of decision-making rule, however, makes a considerable difference as to the optimum fertilizer input. Particularly for the wet season, the variability in the functions themselves result in a wide gap between the pessimistic *Wold* strategy and the optimistic *Savage* strategy. The price ratio for the average of functions has been discounted to approximate the marginal return to capital observed among farmers who irrigate their rice, and as a consequence this model may more nearly approximate the actual practice of farmers.

In the dry season the annual variance in the IR8 response functions is very small; consequently, there is little contrast between the *Wold* and the *Savage* strategies. The procedure of discounting price for the average function becomes the most conservative decision-making rule. All the rules indicate, however, that a substantially higher amount of fertilizer should be used in the dry than in the wet season. Not only is the yield response greater, but the chance of loss is less.

In practice, farmers do not appear to apply fertilizer to the new varieties at much different rates for the two seasons. This is evident in Tables 4 and 5, which compare the average fertilizer inputs for IR8 in the wet and dry seasons in Rizal province. However, it is difficult to conclude that the fertilizer levels should be increased in the dry season unless a dependable irrigation system exists. Even for many of the so-called irrigated farms in the Philippines, the supply of water is uncertain and fluctuates with rainfall.

The second step in the application of decision-making criteria was to determine what incomes would have been obtained if each of the criteria had been adopted for the period 1966 to 1968. These returns are shown in Table 7. They were computed in the following manner: (1) The fertilizer input to be used was obtained from Table

6 assuming a price expectation of P0.32 for rough rice. (2) Yield was determined for each variety and season by referring to the fertilizer response functions shown graphically in Fig. 2 and applying the fertilizer indicated in Table 6. (3) The yield without fertilizer was subtracted from the total yield to determine the yield due to fertilizer. (4) The yield due to fertilizer was reduced by one-sixth to account for harvesting costs, and the result was multiplied by the price received for rice in that year. The average November-December price was used in the wet season and the average March-April price in the dry season. The farm prices for ordinary rough rice in Central Luzon as reported by the Bureau of Agricultural Economics were used. For IR8, the price was reduced by 20 percent to reflect current differentials. The prices used are shown in Table 7. (5) The cost of fertilizer plus 10 percent interest was subtracted from the gross return for rice. The price of fertilizer was assumed to be constant for the 3-year period at P1.18 per kilogram of elemental nitrogen.

Table 7 also shows the income that would have been realized if one could have known beforehand in each year the price and the yield response function for that specific crop. This optimum yield level is the same as reported in Fig. 2. The difference between the income under *perfect knowledge* and the resulting income using one of the other decision-making criteria is the cost paid for the unpredictable year-to-year variation in yield and price. This cost is greatest when the most conservative criterion is adopted. However, even using the least conservative of the decision-making rules, there is still a cost due to uncertainty. Where profit is the goal, a major function of management is to determine how to minimize this cost.

The results in Table 7 show why so many farmers have chosen to apply substantial amounts of fertilizer with the new varieties. For example, observe the profits and losses using the least conservative of the criteria, the *Savage regret*. The highest return per hectare is P677 while the largest loss is only P101. For Peta, on the other hand, the gains are small and the application of any fertilizer could be said to be "hardly worth the risk."

Implications of the analysis. For fertilizer-responsive varieties such as IR8, high yields can be achieved in the "good" years while the loss in the

Table 8. Grain yield, tiller number, and panicle number of IR8 under six levels of water supply treatment. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Water supply treatment * (mm/day)	Tiller no./sq m	Panicle no./sq m	Grain yield (g/sq m)
Flood	521 (a)	353 (a)	726
6	452 (b,c)	336 (b,c)	614
5	481 (a,b,c)	342 (a,b,c)	613
3	490 (a,b)	351 (a,b)	601
4	423 (c)	330 (c)	591
2	457 (b,c)	337 (b,c)	567
F	3.36**	3.72**	18.55 †
CV (X) %	7.85	2.77	4.17

* Applied at ear initiation of the crop.

** Significant at 1% level.

† Significant at 5% level.

Note: The Duncan's new multiple range test at 5% level of significance was applied on tiller number, panicle number and grain yield. Interpretation is as follows:

1. Values on tiller number and panicle number marked by identical letter either singly or in combination with other letters are not significantly different.

2. Values on grain yield that are within the vertical bar shown at the right are not significantly different.

“poor” years would be very small. The combination of these two factors – potential high gain and potential small loss – has been instrumental in the acceptance of the new varieties. Yield variability is least in the dry season which undoubtedly explains also the high success from the introduction of the new varieties in adequately irrigated, dry-climate regions such as West Pakistan.

Uncertainty due to yield variability has a potentially greater impact on the level of input use and yields than uncertainty due to price. Yield variability can be expected to increase from the irrigated situation at the Maligaya Center, which

forms the basis of this study, toward the rainfed paddy, which represents the majority of the rice land in tropical Asia. Where a rapid increase in rice production per hectare is an essential policy objective, measures to reduce uncertainty due to yield, such as crop insurance, might be more effective in encouraging fertilizer use than government price supports or price subsidies. However, due to a shortage of capital, lack of credit, or high interest rates many Asian farmers cannot follow an optimization pattern as suggested here. Thus, a price subsidy or support (or conversely a tax) may have considerably more impact on input use than

Table 9. Relationship between solar radiation (X_1), evaporation (X_2), and evapotranspiration plus losses (X_3) for IR8(68), IRRI, dry and wet seasons, 1968.

Relationship	Regression equation	Days	r
Experiment 1 (Dry season)			
I. $X_2 = a + bX_1$			
(A) Vegetative stage *	$X_2 = 0.16 + 0.011 X_1$	60	0.8400 **
(B) Reproductive stage †	$= -1.72 + 0.0154 X_1$	50	0.8514 **
(C) Whole crop season ††	$= -0.64 + 0.0127 X_1$	110	0.8460 **
II. $X_3 = a + bX_1$			
(A) Vegetative stage	$X_3 = -0.05 + 0.0188 X_1$	18	0.8600 **
(B) Reproductive stage	$= -6.13 + 0.0429 X_1$	49	0.6414 **
(C) Whole crop season	$= -1.25 + 0.0284 X_1$	67	0.4750 **
III. $X_3 = a + bX_2$			
(A) Vegetative stage	$X_3 = 0.085 + 1.621 X_2$	18	0.982 **
(B) Reproductive stage	$= -0.15 + 2.517 X_2$	49	0.679 **
(C) Whole crop season	$= 1.17 + 1.985 X_2$	67	0.554 **
Experiment 2 (Wet season)			
I. $X_2 = a + bX_1$			
(A) Vegetative stage ⌘	$X_2 = -0.15 + 0.011 X_1$	41	0.8304 **
(B) Reproductive stage †	$= -0.34 + 0.010 X_1$	47	0.7611 **
(C) Whole crop season Δ	$= 0.26 + 0.0105 X_1$	88	0.7798 **
II. $X_3 = a + bX_1$			
(A) Vegetative stage	$X_3 = -1.20 + 0.0211 X_1$	41	0.7993 **
(B) Reproductive stage	$= 2.30 + 0.0126 X_1$	47	0.5992 **
(C) Whole crop season	$= 0.46 + 0.0172 X_1$	88	0.7022 **
III. $X_3 = a + bX_2$			
(A) Vegetative stage	$X_3 = -0.32 + 1.737 X_2$	41	0.8788 **
(B) Reproductive stage	$= 2.51 + 1.334 X_2$	47	0.8249 **
(C) Whole crop season	$= 1.54 + 1.425 X_2$	88	0.7800 **

Note: Notation of variables:

X_1 = solar radiation ($\text{g-cal cm}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$)

X_2 = sunken pan evaporation (mm/day)

X_3 = evapotranspiration plus losses (mm/day)

Three crops were planted at monthly intervals during the wet season but only the first was considered in these calculations.

* From 0 to 59 DAT period inclusive.

** Significant at the 1-percent level.

† From 60 to 109 DAT period inclusive.

†† From 0 to 109 DAT period inclusive.

⌘ From 0 to 57 DAT period inclusive.

† From 58 to 109 DAT period inclusive.

Δ From 0 to 109 DAT period inclusive.

Fig. 4. Two possible hypotheses on the functional relationship between rice yield and irrigation water.

suggested by this analysis, particularly among the smaller farmers. Pricing policies must normally take into consideration equity as well as productivity.

Transition from rainfed to irrigated production

The importance of adequate water control (including irrigation, drainage, and flood control) is well understood. Tables 8 and 9 of the Agricultural Economics section of the 1966 Annual Report showed how potential yields, farm income, and labor productivity are closely linked with the availability of irrigation facilities. Tables 1 and 2 of this report indicate the important relationship between irrigation and the acceptance of new varieties. In most of the tropical rice-growing countries, the expansion or improvement of irrigation facilities is a basic step toward increasing labor productivity in the face of growing population pressures on the land.

Even if there is general agreement regarding the need for extension of adequate irrigation and water control, there are a whole range of questions from the purely technical to the social and organizational aspects that must be answered if irrigation systems constructed in the future and those already in existence are to function properly and achieve the objectives sought. Of fundamental importance to the design and operation of an irrigation system is the way in which rice yield responds to water. The work already accomplished by the Agronomy Department answers this question adequately for additional amounts of water beyond flooding. However, throughout most of tropical Asia, the supply of water available from

irrigation systems depends very much on rainfall. Gravity systems lack storage facilities and the low-lift, suction-type pumps draw water from streams or underground sources at a depth of only 20 feet or less below the point of pump installation. The key issue not only at the farm but also at the national level is how to distribute the water, particularly during periods of shortage. Related to this is the question of the design of the irrigation distribution system. Whether the goals of irrigation emphasize production, economic efficiency, or social equity, the problem of optimum water distribution can be solved *only* if one understands the nature of the rice yield response to water levels below flooding. The need for this information is demonstrated by an explanation of two possible hypotheses (Fig. 4) regarding the shape of the response relationship.

Figure 4,A shows a response in which the rice yields obtained with additional amounts of water diminish from the outset. Under this type of function the maximum amount of rice can be produced by spreading water over a large area. Depending upon the cost of such water distribution, the conflict among economic, social, and productivity goals may be relatively small.

Figure 4,B differs from 4,A in that there is an initial very low yield followed by a rather narrow range of increasing returns to water input and sharply increasing yields. Both from an economic and agronomic viewpoint the maximum yield for a limited amount of water is achieved by insuring that any irrigated hectare received at least the amount of water represented by the increasing returns range. In Figure 4,B this minimum water level (water applied plus rainfall) is assumed to be 40 to 60 cm in 100 irrigation days.

This latter hypothesis suggests that a difference in the physiological nature of the rice plant and/or the difference in lowland vs upland conditions makes the rice plant grown in flooded fields more sensitive to drought. In other words the drop in water below a certain level causes a severe yield decline. The physiological characteristics of the rice plant that affect water use at these lower levels are not well understood. However, there is some evidence that rice leaves are narrower when the same variety is grown under upland conditions, and that rice plants surviving early-season water stress will be more resistant to drought later in the

season.

The primary objective of the research in irrigation conducted thus far has been to identify the response relationship of yield to water. That is to say, which of the two hypotheses suggested in Fig. 4 is more nearly correct?

The experiment conducted in the 1968 dry season unfortunately did not produce the desired results. The design and procedures have consequently been revised for the 1969 dry season. However, the 1968 results are reported because the information obtained and the problems encountered should be of value to others working in this general area. Also an experiment was conducted in the 1968 wet season to establish the benefits of supplemental irrigation by measuring yield performance under irrigated and rainfed conditions.

Design of dry-season experiment. A total of 24 plots, each 2 m x 2 m, were planted using a split-plot design with two replications. The main block was fertilized with the levels set at 50 and 100 kg/ha for elemental nitrogen. The blocks were oriented across the general land slope and were randomized within two replications. Six water-supply levels were assigned randomly to each replication. One consisted of flooding at a depth of 5 cm; the other five ranged from 2 to 6 mm of water per day.

The experiment was designed and constructed with the intent of minimizing the losses due to seepage and thus permitting the measurement of consumptive use (evaporation plus transpiration). Each plot was bounded by 20 gauge G.I. sheet metal buried to a depth of one meter. The experimental plots were "open bottomed". Percolation losses were measured before transplanting, and these were low, averaging about 0.6 mm per day. A sunken evaporation pan (closed bottom) was installed at one edge of the experimental area. The pan, equipped with a Belfort water level recorder and time clock mechanism, was used to record evaporation and rainfall data. A still well was sunk in the corner of each plot to permit the daily recording of water levels with the use of a hook gauge.

The decision was made to maintain a flooded condition at 5 cm in all plots until panicle initiation took place and then to vary the supply of water according to the treatments described,

applying water once every 5 days. This period was considered short enough so that any stress upon the plant would not be the result of the interval between applications of water, but rather of the low total level of water received.

Results of dry-season experiment. In the conduct of the experiment two problems were encountered which had considerable influence upon the final results obtained. First, in spite of the low level of some of the water treatments, the moisture in the soil did not reach a level low enough to critically affect yields. Second, the open-bottom system did not effectively control water losses due to seepage and percolation, making it impossible to accurately measure consumptive use.

Table 8 and Fig. 5 illustrate the first problem. The yields in Table 8 are the average of the two replications plus the two fertilizer treatments. While the high fertilizer treatments yielded about 70 g/sq m more than the low-input ones, on the average, the yield functions plotted against water supply treatments ran parallel to each other, showing no interaction between different levels of fertilizer and water.

Fig. 5. Pattern of soil moisture behavior at different growth stages for five different water supply treatments on IR8 (68). IRRI, 1968 dry season.

Table 10. Grain yield, plant height, tiller number, and panicle number of IR8 under rainfed and irrigated lowland culture (July 14, August 14, and September 14 transplanting) IRRI, 1968 wet season.

Variable, culture	Date of Transplanting			Average
	July 14	Aug. 14	Sept. 14	
A. Yield				
1. Rainfed	452	423	411	428.7
2. Irrigated:				
(a) 5 cm	539	635	505	560.0
(b) 1 cm	-	554	548	551.0
Average	495.5	537.3	488.0	
B. Plant height				
1. Rainfed	88.9	73.6	77.6	80.0
2. Irrigated:				
(a) 5 cm	91.3	87.0	82.7	87.0
(b) 1 cm	-	81.4	81.4	81.4
Average	90.1	80.7	80.6	
C. Tiller no.				
1. Rainfed	264	295	298	286
2. Irrigated:				
(a) 5 cm	245	319	276	280
(b) 1 cm	-	280	330	305
Average	254.5	298	301.3	
D. Panicle no.				
1. Rainfed	223	273	255	250
2. Irrigated:				
(a) 5 cm	233	300	229	254
(b) 1 cm	-	271	318	294
Average	228	281	267	

Yields for the five water supply treatments were all significantly below that at flooding. Considering the wide range of difference in the range of water applied (represented by the 6 and 2 mm/day treatments), the decline in yield over this range is extremely small. Figure 5 shows the change in the moisture content of the soil determined by oven-drying samples taken from the plots. With the beginning of the treatments, the moisture content of the soil declined rapidly at first and then more gradually reached a minimum of about 50 percent of field capacity. The decline in soil moisture content may have been halted by rains late in the growing season. However, of much greater significance is the failure of the treatments

to show an appreciable difference in soil moisture content even before the rains. This suggests that underground water movement and possible capillary action may be preventing the occurrence of differences that might be expected in soil moisture content between treatments. This being the case, the amount of water supplied in the treatments may have no relation to the amount of water actually used by the plant.

The problems encountered in measuring consumptive use in the designed system are illustrated in Fig. 6, which shows plotted daily observations of: (1) evapotranspiration plus losses on the 5-cm flooded plots, (2) potential evaporation, (3) sunken pan evaporation, and (4) rainfall. Potential

evaporation is determined by making a linear conversion of the measured amount of solar energy. Excluding the modifying effects of other climatic elements, it represents the maximum possible evaporation that could take place from evaporation surfaces due to the heating effect of solar energy, and thus represents an upper limit for consumptive use. If losses due to seepage and percolation were at a minimum, the evapotranspiration plus losses should not greatly exceed the potential evaporation. Early in the season these two move closely together (Fig. 6). Beginning at panicle initiation, however, a wide divergence exists and, just before harvest, the two lines converge again. The reason for the divergence is not clear. One hypothesis is that the development of the plant roots increased percolation and, with the decay of the root system late in the season, the lines converged again. The late-season convergence may also be related to the rainfall which decreases evapotranspiration.

The relationships among evapotranspiration plus losses, sunken pan evaporation, and solar radiation are summarized in Table 9. Since the relationship between solar radiation and potential evaporation is expressed by a constant, the use of either one would result in the same value for the correlation coefficient. Correlations relating evapotranspiration plus losses with evaporation are somewhat higher than with solar radiation. This is logical since evaporation occurs as a result of solar energy and other climatic variables.

Design of wet-season experiment. The equipment used in the dry season was also used in the 1968 wet season. The 24 plots were divided into three groups according to planting date, and these groups were transplanted a month apart on July 14, August 14, and September 14. For each planting date half of the eight plots were rainfed and the other half, irrigated. Water was maintained at a 5-cm depth in the irrigated plots of the July planting. For the other two plantings half of the

Table 11. Solar radiation and rainfall at different crop growth stages for three planting dates of IR8(68), IRR1, 1968 wet season.

Period	Number days per period	Date of transplanting		
		July 14	Aug. 14	Sept. 14
Solar radiation (g-cal cm ⁻² day ⁻¹)				
Booting to flower	15	4293	4784	3512
Early booting to flower	20	5729	5954	4448
Flower to harvest	30	9088	7313	6738**
Booting to harvest	45	13381	12097	10250**
Early booting to harvest	50	14817	13267	11186**
Rainfall* (mm)				
Transplanting to panicle initiation	56	335.5†	314.2	251.1
Early booting to flower	20	108.1	94.4	65.5
Booting to harvest	45	220.5	74.5	58.7
Panicle initiation to maturity	50	280.5	160.4	89.2

* Includes records up to 6 days before harvest.

** Values for five-day period before harvest are computed values.

† Six days' records during about maximum tiller stage were not included due to breakdown of Belfort time clock mechanism.

Fig. 6. Rainfall, evaporation, potential evaporation and evapotranspiration plus losses (ET + L) for irrigated (5 cm depth) IR8 (68) at different growth stages. IRRI, 1968 dry season.

plots were irrigated at 5- and 1-cm depths. In the rainfed treatments, supplemental water was allowed for land preparation. At transplanting about 2 cm of standing water was allowed in each plot. Thereafter the water supply for the crop was derived entirely from rainfall. During heavy rains the plot water depth exceeded the level normally found in a paddy because of the high sheet metal sidings in each plot. In such cases the water level was lowered to 5 cm during early vegetative growth and to 7.5 cm thereafter.

As with the dry-season experiment, evapotranspiration and other losses, evaporation, and rainfall data were recorded throughout the crop season, except for a period of 6 days during which the Belfort water level recorder was broken. The water depth of the rainfed plots was also recorded whenever standing water was present.

Results of wet-season experiment. The results of the wet-season experiment are summarized in Table 10 and the rainfall levels and solar radiation at different periods of crop growth are shown in Table 11.

The yield of the 5-cm flooded plots was highest for the August 14 planting, and was about 1,000 kilograms lower for the other two planting dates. Unexpectedly the yields were not related to the amount of solar radiation for the periods either 30 or 45 days before harvest. However, the yield levels were closely reflected by the amount of solar radiation in the period from 15 to 20 days before flowering.

The 1-cm and rainfed plots show a mixed relationship among yield, rainfall, and solar energy which can be described only in general terms. An abundance of solar radiation accompanied by a

shortage of rainfall during the critical period following booting should result in the widest differences between irrigated and rainfed plots. This appears to describe the situation for the second planting. Both water and solar energy were low in the third harvest period. The reduction in yield and solar energy in the third planting was in keeping with the normal seasonal pattern. There is no explanation as to why the highest yield was obtained in the 1-cm, flooded plot during this last period.

The term "rainfed", as used here, must be interpreted with some caution. Although the moisture content of the soil was not measured throughout this experiment, it is apparent that moisture levels did not fall below field capacity. It is again possible that underground water movement set a floor to the decline in moisture content and that, under true rainfed conditions, the yield reduction for some of the plantings would have been more severe. The same note of caution would apply to other experiments being conducted on the Institute experimental farm which assume upland or rainfed conditions.

Finally, the yield response for rainfed vs irrigated situations should ideally be observed over a period of years in order to be able to relate yields to weather variability in a context of statistical probability. A more direct approach to identifying possible yield variability is represented by the initial dry-season experiment. Another alternative is to measure yields cross-sectionally in a given season for situations from the very dry to the adequately irrigated.

Fertilizer Supply and Distribution

The 1967 Annual Report described the seed multiplication and distribution system in the Philippines and the changes that occurred following the introduction of the new rice varieties. In April 1968 the Seed Growers Association of the Philippines Inc. (SEEDPHIL), an association of private seed producers, was formed to meet the growing demand for certified seeds throughout the country and abroad. The shift to the private sector of the responsibility for producing and distributing certified seeds opened up a new chapter in the Philippine seed program. The purpose of this section is to describe the supply and distribution

system for a second important input – *fertilizer*.

As with certified seed, so also with fertilizer; the Philippine government played an instrumental role in the early development, and then gradually turned over major responsibility to the private sector. The following discussion is divided into two parts: (1) growth of imports and domestic production, and (2) growth of the distribution system.

Growth of imports and domestic production

Since 1950 the chemical fertilizer consumption of the Philippines has been growing at an annual rate of about 9 percent based on the quantity of fertilizer imported and produced locally (Fig. 7). This rate understates the true growth since the composition of fertilizer has changed over the period. In 1950 the bulk of the fertilizer was ammonium sulfate. At present, mixed fertilizers and urea make up a considerable share of the total. The nutrient content of a ton of fertilizer may have increased by as much as 30 percent. This would indicate a growth of about 10 percent over the 17-year period based on nutrients consumed.

Government activity. From the period 1950 to 1954, US\$10 million worth of fertilizer was imported under the Economic and Technical Cooperation Agreement between the Philippine and United States governments. Importation declined in 1954, but increased in the following year with the beginning of imports by the Sugar Producers Cooperative and Marketing Association (SPCMA). Under Republic Act 1609 the Agricultural Credit Administration (ACA, then the ACCFA) appropriated P45,513,000 for the purchase and distribution of fertilizer over a period of 7 crop years (1956/57 to 1962/63). Purchases were made principally from domestic producers and distributed at subsidized prices through the farmers' cooperatives. The subsidy represented more than 50 percent of the commercial retail price. Republic Act 2084 provided for the distribution of fertilizer specifically to rice and corn farmers at a 50-percent subsidy. Between 1958/59 and 1963/64 a total of P44,541,000 worth of fertilizer was distributed under this program. However, it is estimated that more than 50 percent of the fertilizer intended for rice and corn producers was diverted or resold for use on sugar cane

Fig. 7. Total imports plus domestic production of inorganic fertilizer. Philippines, 1950-1967

or other crops. Another difficulty with the program was the disproportionate acquisition of mixed vs nitrogenous fertilizers relative to local farm demand. In 1964 the ACA terminated its fertilizer subsidy program, but it continues to sell fertilizer through cooperatives at rates slightly below the current commercial level. The passage of Republic Act 3050 in June 1961 removed import duties on fertilizer for farmers' cooperatives. This tariff, which amounts to 20 percent of the C&F value (cost plus freight to the Philippines), was reinstated for cooperatives in 1965, but imports by cooperatives are currently exempted from the

7 percent advanced sales tax required of all private importation and domestic production.

Domestic production. The fertilizer industry in the Philippines is at present composed of four inorganic fertilizer plants, three organic plants, and several small importer-compounder plants. The four inorganic plants which make up 90 percent of total fertilizer production, are:

- (1) Maria Cristina Fertilizer Corporation (subsidiary of Marcelo Steel Corporation)
Location: Iligan, Mindanao
Start-up date: July 1951

Productive capacity: 125,000 metric ton ammonium sulfate

(2) Chemical Industries of the Philippines Inc. (Chemphil)

Location: Rizal, Luzon

Start-up date: 1952

Productive capacity: 30,000 metric tons ammonium sulfate
35,000 metric tons superphosphate
9,000 metric tons mixed

(3) Atlas Fertilizer Corporation

Location: Cebu, Visayas

Start-up date: April 1958

Productive capacity: 90,000 metric tons ammonium sulfate
27,200 metric tons superphosphate
96,400 metric tons mixed

(4) Esso Standard Fertilizer and Agricultural Chemicals Co. Inc. (ESFAC)

Location: Bataan, Luzon

Start-up date: mid-1966

Productive capacity: 67,650 metric tons urea
17,500 metric tons diammonium phosphate
301,000 metric tons mixed

The first of the local plants to begin operation, the Maria Cristina, was operated under the National Power Corporation from 1951 until 1960, at which time it was purchased by the Marcelo Steel Corporation. The initial domestic production was oriented toward the demands of the sugar industry. A 1964 survey by the Market Research Division of the San Miguel Corporation showed that 144,000 m.t. of fertilizer or 49 percent of the fertilizer was being used on the approximately 300,000 hectares of sugar cane land while 79,000 m.t. or 27 percent of consumption was being used on 3 million hectares of rice. Of course, most of this hectareage planted to rice received no fertilizer.

In spite of government activities, which were sometimes in conflict with the development of private local production and distribution, the domestic fertilizer industry continued to grow. However, until recently, the Philippine government has been the main supplier of fertilizer to the rice industry. A major shift came with the end of the government subsidy program in 1964 and the opening of the ESFAC plant in mid-1966. The latter event coincided fortuitously with the initial Institute release of 50 tons of IR8 seed to the Philippine government.

In 1967 the domestic production of 286,000

Table 12. Distribution of fertilizer dealers by region and company, Philippines, 1968.*

Region	ESFAC	Atlas	Ma. Cristina	Chempbil	ACA	Total
Ilocos	23	35	31	11	7	107
Cagayan	32	13	13	20	6	84
Central Luzon	89	123	103	15	44	374
Southern Tagalog	61	75	99	9	19	263
Bicol	36	33	6	-	5	80
E. Visayas	24	86	4	-	11	125
W. Visayas	47	32	14	2	11	106
N & E Mindanao	38	36	11	1	12	98
S & W Mindanao	53	71	24	2	15	165
Total	403	504	305	60	130	1,402

Total private fertilizer dealers: 1,272

* Source of basic data: Fertilizer Institute of the Philippines.

m.t. represented 63.5 percent of the total production plus imports, but this was less than 50 percent of industry capacity. This low utilization of domestic capacity was due to: (1) continued competition from direct imports, particularly in the sugar industry and from government sales (government fertilizer is imported under the Japanese reparations agreement), and (2) the failure of plant capacity to match, product by product, the local demand. In this latter connection, the industries' mixed fertilizer capacity is well in excess of demand for the foreseeable future.

The distribution system

The fertilizer distribution system in the Philippines can be characterized only by describing the way in which fertilizer is transferred from the company to the farmer. The methods employed by each company and by the government differ considerably.

For the first three companies to enter the fertilizer business – Maria Cristina, Chemphil, and Atlas – the relationship between the company and the farmer has been passive. Fertilizer is sold by the company to distributors or outlets; beyond this point the company has no direct interest. Distributors may in turn sell their fertilizer to retail dealers of their own choosing who in turn sell to farmers. Consider, for example, the system employed by Atlas. It delivers fertilizer to its 14 regional distributors located throughout the Philippines. The regional distributors in turn select their dealers, who are for the most part store owners engaged in selling a wide range of other products. There are about 500 retail stores handling Atlas fertilizer products (Table 12).

The system adopted by ESFAC is based upon a more direct relationship among company, retail dealer, and farmer. A dealer is selected by the company and undergoes 6 months of training in the technical aspects of fertilizer use, and in business management and salesmanship. At the end of the training period he is awarded a 1-year contract to sell only ESFAC products, and is referred to as an Agroservice dealer. There were more than 400 such dealers in the Philippines in 1968 (Table 12). The company employs a trade name for its products, ENGRO, and carries on aggressive nationwide sales and advertising campaign to encourage farmers to use more fertilizer in general and its products in particular.

Fig. 8. Growth of fertilizer dealers in 12 major rice-producing provinces, Philippines, 1949-1968.

The ACA has 155 local warehouses. About 130 district fertilizer agents serve as liaison officers between the farmers' cooperatives (FACOMAS) and the district warehouses. However, because of the lack of field personnel, the district farmer agents are more often salesmen than liaison officers. Each is assigned a number of towns. Where there are no active farmers' cooperatives, outlets are designated by the ACA branch office. Fertilizer stocks are normally kept in warehouses of the no longer active cooperatives and assigned for distribution during certain days of the week.

Growth of the system. A survey was made of retail dealers or outlets in 12 leading rice-producing provinces in the Philippines to learn more about the nature and development of the fertilizer distribution system at the farm level. The provinces surveyed were: Bulacan, Pampanga, Nueva Ecija, Pangasinan, and Tarlac in Central Luzon; Laguna, in the Southern Tagalog region; Albay in Bicol; Ilocos Sur and Cagayan in Northern Luzon; Iloilo and Leyte in the Visayas; and Cotabato in Mindanao.

The survey consisted of a "long form" containing rather detailed questions and a "short form" of only two pages. The long form was used for 20 dealers in the Central Luzon provinces, the original intent being to interview one retail dealer from each company in each of the five provinces. The short form interview was used for a random sample of the remaining 20 percent of the dealers in these Central Luzon provinces, plus 20 percent of all dealers in the other seven provinces. A total of 122 retail dealers were interviewed in the 12 provinces.

Table 13. Average price per bag paid by farmers for fertilizer purchased from private and government sources in 12 leading rice provinces, Philippines, 1968.*

Province	Ammonium		12-12-12 (P)
	sulfate (P)	Urea (P)	
Central Luzon			
Bulacan	13.80	24.40	16.20
Pampanga	12.00	21.90	17.00
Nueva Ecija	13.50	23.80	17.15
Tarlac	14.90	23.90	17.50
Pangasinan	14.10	24.45	17.25
Other			
Laguna	13.80	24.40	18.50
Cagayan	16.50	27.50	22.50
Ilocos Sur	14.40	25.16	20.75
Albay	16.50	26.50	18.25
Iloilo	13.20	22.50	17.00
Leyte	15.00	23.25	19.00
Cotabato	15.30	26.60	19.00
Government **			
ACA	12.50	—	15.00

* Ammonium sulfate and 12-12-12 are in 45-kg bags whereas urea is in 50-kg bags.

** Government prices are uniform throughout.

Based on the survey, a chart (Fig. 8) was drawn to indicate the rate of growth of the retail fertilizer outlets in the major rice-producing areas. There was no evidence to show that growth had been more rapid in any particular region; thus, all provinces are combined in the graph. In developing the chart the survey was weighted to adjust for the fact that the sample did not reflect accurately the percentage of dealers represented by a given company in a given province. This adjustment was essential because the time at which a company dealer began to sell fertilizer was closely related to the start-up date of the company's fertilizer plant. Thus, one can observe an increase in the number of retail outlets after 1958 with the opening of the Atlas Fertilizer plant, and an even greater increase from 1966 with the opening of the ESFAC plant.

The figure is only a rough approximation of the situation since there have been many unrecorded

changes. Many dealers have gone out of business; others started selling, stopped temporarily, then resumed selling. Of the original sample drawn, 13 percent were not operating at the time of the interview, 6 percent were non-existent, and 4 percent had never been fertilizer dealers.

Other factors. The majority of the dealers provide credit to a selected number of their customers although the fertilizer companies themselves do not extend credit to the dealers. The ESFAC dealers in particular do soil testing and to a lesser extent run demonstration farms. Nearly all dealers make recommendations on the type and amount of fertilizer to apply. The majority also make recommendations on time of application. The source of information or basis for these recommendations varies, but the most important is the company itself through company publications and technical fertilizer recommendations. Apparently, dealers rely very little on extension workers for information.

The price of fertilizer. The price per bag of fertilizer paid by farmers, as reported by the dealers interviewed, is shown in Table 13. The price is highest in those areas with the longest overland haul, Cagayan and Albay. It is lowest for ammonium sulfate and urea in Pampanga, which is a major sugar-producing area in Central Luzon. Some of the fertilizer purchased through the sugar cooperatives undoubtedly finds its way to rice paddies. Farmers pay about one-third more per kilogram of elemental nitrogen in the form of ammonium sulfate vs urea.

The domestic price of fertilizer is related to the import cost. The example below indicates how the import cost is calculated for ammonium sulfate and urea delivered to the Philippines from Japan at approximately US\$45 and US\$75 per metric ton (C & F) respectively:

	Imported fertilizer	
	Ammonium sulfate	Urea
C & F value per metric tone	P 175.50	P 292.50
duty	35.10	14.60
other charges	17.50	17.50
advanced sales tax	16.00	22.70
	<u>P 244.10</u>	<u>P 347.30</u>
Price per bag-cooperatives	P 10.25	P 16.25
Price per bag-private	P 11.00	P 17.35

The duty is 20 percent for ammonium sulfate and 5 percent for urea. The advanced sales tax of 7 percent does not apply if the fertilizer is sold through cooperatives. The difference between the price landed port and the retail price shown in Table 13 represents the cost of transportation to the warehouse, warehousing, transportation to the dealer, and markups. For the rice provinces studied, this cost varies from 20 to 35 percent of the retail price due principally to differences in transportation costs.

It was not possible to determine the profit margins of local producers. However, in an industry where the economies of plant size are very large, the comparatively small size of three of the Philippine fertilizer plants by international standards plus the under-utilization of existing capacity suggests that even with the 20-percent tariff the domestic profit margins are probably not large. As a consequence, farmers do not stand to benefit from the existence of a local industry through a lower price.

Implications. The fertilizer industry of the Philippines has undergone a dramatic change in the past decade. Fertilizer production and distribution started as a government monopoly but has gradually shifted to the private sector. Private sector distribution was at first concentrated on the sugar industry but has now spread to rice and corn. The aggressive sales policy of the ESFAC has added a new dimension to the industry.

The growth of the domestic industry raises some interesting questions regarding the future structure of the industry. Farmers have benefited from the industries' development of the local distribution system. Considering the services provided and the cost of transportation and marketing, farm fertilizer prices are currently well in line with those of other Asian countries. At the same time, it may be difficult for Philippine farmers to benefit from recent technological advances in fertilizer manufacture which have reduced the farm price of fertilizer in the United States and in many other parts of the world. This problem, which is not unique to the Philippines but is being faced by many other developing countries, deserves further explanation.

Unlike the production of farm crops, the production of fertilizer requires the use of inputs which are not divisible. Whether in advanced or in

developing countries, cheap fertilizer is produced in large plants which can take advantage of substantial economies of size. Most developing countries do not have the initial local demand for fertilizer to warrant the construction of large-scale plants which can operate close to capacity. Over the short run, plants of smaller capacity are frequently constructed in line with the policy objective of creating a local industry. The economies of size, however, continue to point in the direction of concentration of world fertilizer production in large plants. Therefore, in an industry structure such as exists in the Philippines (where three of the four local plants must be considered small by international standards) there are three alternatives for the future:

(1) maintain the local industry by the continuance or perhaps even the eventual increase of the current tariff levels.

(2) allow competition from imports to force up costs and erode the profit margins of local plants, and eventually force closure.

(3) follow step (1) above but subsidize the price of fertilizer to farmers.

None of these alternatives are palatable. It is largely a matter of deciding who should bear the cost.

Rice Supply, Demand, and Price Behavior

The first half of this section consists of a broad overview of the changes taking place in rice production in several Asian countries and in the world price of rice traded in the international market. Information is now available which gives some indication of the land area being planted to the new rice varieties. The impact on national production and yield is going to be difficult to assess because of changes in weather, prices, and other factors which influence both production and consumption. However, there has not been sufficient time yet for the increased production (due to the new varieties) to have had a major influence on the world rice price. The recent decline in this price from the 1967-68 high to more normal levels appears to be principally the result of other factors.

The rapid changes occurring in rice production emphasize the importance of understanding the relationships among the quantity of rice supplied,

the price and income levels, and the quantity of rice consumed. In more technical terms, the following need to be identified: (1) *elasticity of supply* – the effect of a change in price upon the quantity supplied, (2) *marketed surplus* – changes in the quantity being marketed as a result of changes in production, (3) *price elasticity of demand* – the relationship between a change in price and a change in the quantity consumed, and (4) *income elasticity of demand* – the relationship between a change in income and a change in quantity consumed. These relationships should be identified as a first step toward improving national estimates of changes in production and consumption.

Research has been undertaken to estimate all four of the above relationships in the Philippine rice economy. The results of the analysis of supply response and marketable surplus were summarized in the 1966 Annual Report. The effect of increased production on marketed surplus and income elasticity of demand, resulting from the adoption of new varieties, is discussed in the current report in connection with a small farm survey. The first results of the research initiated this year to estimate income elasticity of demand

at the national level are presented in the final sub-section.

Spread of new rice varieties in the tropics

The amount of land planted to the new varieties during the crop year 1968/69 will probably exceed 5 million hectares or 6 percent of the total rice land in South and Southeast Asia. The spread of the new varieties has been rapid but not uniform. The rate of diffusion differs among countries, among regions within a country, and among farms within a region. Factors influencing adoption at the farm level have been discussed in the first section of this report. The section is concerned with the acceptance of new varieties at the national level.

The starting point for the spread of new varieties is taken here as the crop season 1965/66 which marked the introduction into India of the semidwarf Taichung (Native) 1. Varieties of medium to short stature with high yield potential introduced in the tropics after this date are categorized here as *new*. It is difficult to define precisely a *new* or *high-yielding* rice variety. To date the principal new varieties in terms of planted hectareage are IR8 and IR5. A number of varieties

Table 14. Seed of new varieties distributed by The International Rice Research Institute, by country of destination, to January 1, 1969 in metric tons. *

Country	1966	1967		1968		
	IR8	IR8	IR5 (metric tons)	IR8	IR5	IR-253
Burma	0.1			**	**	
Ceylon		0.5				
India		10.0				
Laos	0.1					1.0
Malaysia	3.0	3.0				
Nepal					**	
Philippines	55.3	5.2	0.9	0.1	18.1	
Saudi Arabia				**		
Vietnam (South)		**	**			
Total	58.5	18.7	0.9	0.1	18.1	1.0

* In 1965, 1 metric ton of Taichung (Native) 1 was sold to the Indian government.

** Less than 0.1 metric ton.

Table 15. Seed of new varieties exported from the Philippines by country of destination, to January 1, 1969 in metric tons. *

Country	1967	1968 (6 months)				
	IR8	IR8	IR5	IR-253**	C4-63**	C4-113**
Burma	200					
Ceylon		210				
Ecuador			†			
Ghana					2	
Indonesia					1	
Iran		†				
Israel	100	198				
Laos			2	2		
Liberia		1	1		1	
Pakistan	3600					
Panama	10		†			†
Spain		12				
UAR	100					
Venezuela		10				
Vietnam (South)		1807	205			
West Germany		†				
Total	4010	2238	208	2	4	

* Source: Rice and Corn Administration, Philippine Government.

** C4-63 and C4-113 are varieties developed at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, IR-253 is not an official IRRI variety, but a selection. It is a glutinous rice bred specifically to suit taste preference in the Upper Mekong River Basin.

† Less than 1 metric ton.

recently developed through various country research programs, such as C4-63 and BPI-76 in the Philippines, are also included in the list of new varieties. ADT-27, which has been spreading rapidly in the Tanjore District of India, although developed several years ago, is included in the list. H-4 and H-8, which account for more than 50 percent of the rice grown in Ceylon, are omitted since their dissemination occurred well before 1965/66.

Where the varieties are being grown. Until now the Philippines has been the major source of seed for the new varieties. Some of the seed was multiplied and distributed by the Institute (Table 14). However, most of the estimated 6,500 tons of exported seed was produced by private growers and shipped through private or government channels. Table 15 shows the quantity of seed

exported from the Philippines by year and by country of destination.

Seed exports give a rough indication of where the new varieties are being grown and where the expansion is likely to take place in the immediate future. One ton of seed will plant 20 to 25 hectares. Allowing for a 50-percent loss in the production and distribution channels, the expansion per crop season would be about fifty-fold (1,000 hectares at the end of the first season, 50,000 hectares at the end of the second season). Thus, in two crop seasons, a relatively modest amount of seed can be multiplied into a quantity sufficient to meet local demand.

Table 16* shows the estimates of hectareage

* The table was compiled in cooperation with Dr. Dana G. Dalrymple, International Agricultural Development Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture.

planted to new varieties by country and by crop year beginning in 1965/66. Most of these figures are either projections of government plans or predictions unsupported as yet by official government surveys. Making allowance for gross inaccuracies, the figures, nevertheless, are revealing. The most rapid dissemination has occurred in India, West Pakistan, and the Philippines. One of the major rice-exporting countries, Thailand, does not appear in the table at all. The factors which have contributed to this varied rate of acceptance among countries are discussed below.

Factors influencing the dissemination of new varieties. The new varieties represent a potential for increased output per unit of input, and can thus be viewed as a technological improvement. The extent to which a technological change at the experiment station is transmitted to the farm is determined by a multitude of factors. These factors can be thought of as a series of potential obstacles, a certain number of which must be overcome at one time if the diffusion of technology is to occur. However, the initial expansion of production may create new problems which must be solved if sustained growth is to be achieved. For example, the existing marketing structure may be adequate for a small increase in production. However, a large and rapid expansion may overtax the system, both from the viewpoint of delivering the necessary inputs and processing the increased production. It would be difficult to make out a complete list of factors or to indicate for any given situation how these numerous factors have interacted to encourage or retard the acceptance of new varieties. One unusual feature relating to the initial acceptance has been the initiative and apparently successful promotional efforts undertaken by a number of governments which, in the past, have shown relatively little interest in agriculture. Recognizing the high degree of oversimplification, five factors have been used as a basis for subjectively determining which countries appear to have *more favorable, average, and less favorable* conditions for adoption. The analysis is presented in Table 17. For a given country, each of the factors is identified in one of three categories from favorable to unfavorable. Those factors which appear particularly important in influencing the initial acceptance in a given

country are underlined.

The contrast between the more and less favorable situations can be seen by comparing West Pakistan and East Pakistan. The factors which favor West Pakistan — high and comparatively stable yield response due to the dry climate (Fig. 2), water control, and a minimum of disease and insect problems — are the major handicaps in East Pakistan. Much of East Pakistan's rice-growing area

Table 16. Estimates and projections of hectareage of new rice varieties planted in Southeast and South Asia by country and year, December, 1968.*

Country and crop year	Total rice hectareage 1965/66 (1000)	Hectares planted to new varieties (1000)	Percent 1965/66 riceland
Southeast Asia			
Burma	4856		
1968/69		324	6.7
Indonesia	7348		
1968/69		271	3.7
1969/70		809	11.0
Laos	648		
1967/68		1	**
Malaysia	480		
1966/67		4.5	**
1967/68		30	6.3
Philippines	3109		
1966/67		75	2.4
1967/68		447 †	14.4
South Vietnam	2450		
1967/68		.9	**
1968/69		44	1.8
1969/70		200	8.7
South Asia			
Ceylon	492		
1968/69		10	2.0
India	35274		
1965/66		6	**
1966/67		379	1.1
1967/68		2024	5.7
1968/69		3077	8.7

Continued next page

Table 16. Continuation

East Pakistan	8900		
1966/67		.2	**
1967/68		81	**
1968/69		242	2.7
West Pakistan	1393		
1967/68		4	**
1968/69		344	24.7
1969/70		405	29.1
Total	80,678 ††		
1966/67		454	0.6
1967/68		2,588	3.2
1968/69	℥	4,790	5.9

* Detailed description of data sources may be obtained through IRRI or through Dr. Dana Dalrymple, International Agricultural Development Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture. The word *new* in this table refers principally to varieties disseminated since 1965/66 and excludes H-4 and H-8 in Ceylon and BPI-76 in the Philippines although hectareage of both varieties has been increasing.

** Less than 1 percent.

† Based on official government survey.

†† Includes all non-communist countries in South & Southeast Asia.

℥ Where data are not available, 1967/68 estimates are repeated.

becomes flooded during the annual monsoons. Disease and insect problems have made it virtually impossible to grow IR8 during the main crop season.

That the spread has been more rapid than initially anticipated by many observers seems to point to the advantage of the new plant type over existing indica varieties throughout a wide geographical area in the tropics. Research is already being undertaken at many localities to improve disease and insect resistance and grain quality. It appears likely that these obstacles will be overcome in a comparatively short time in most areas. However, development of adequate irrigation and drainage facilities will require a longer period of time and a considerable capital investment. Thus,

many observers consider water control to be the major factor that will limit the initial adoption of the new technology.

Implications of the analysis. The rapid expansion of rice production as a consequence of the introduction of new rice varieties will lead to a whole series of new problems. In the short run, there are problems relating specifically to the rice industry involving principally the supply and distribution of inputs and the improvement of processing and marketing facilities. However, of greater concern in the long run is the implication of the increase in food grain production for the whole process of development. Included in this category are three issues: (1) the food-population race, (2) the alternatives to rice production, and (3) the disparity in income distribution. These issues are discussed below.

The initial thrust of the new technology has been far more rapid than any previous historical experience. In many areas, the level of adoption has exceeded even the most optimistic predictions. There is thus no question that a "breathing spell" has been gained in the food-population race. This can be illustrated as follows. Assume a yield increase of one-half a metric ton of milled rice equivalent on 5 million hectares planted to new varieties during the 1968/69 crop season (a conservative estimate). The increase in rice production for South and Southeast Asia would equal 2.5 million metric tons. Given a population growth of 2.5 percent per annum and an annual per capita consumption of 80 kilograms, this production increase would be matched by a growth in demand of 1.75 million metric tons.

However, it remains to be seen how these initial gains in rice production will be translated into sustained growth. Much of this will depend on the solution of marketing and production problems outside the area of plant breeding and varietal improvement. There is the danger that the pendulum of thinking may swing too far and too fast from the recent fear of scarcity to a fear of surplus.

As the same time, it also must be recognized that many regions of Asia will experience surpluses as a consequence of the new technology. The demand for rice is very inelastic in the short run. The existence of an inadequate marketing system

Table 17. Countries which appear to be in a more favorable or less favorable situation with respect to five factors influencing dissemination of new indica varieties in South and Southeast Asia, 1968.*

Condition	Factor				
	Water control	Availability of inputs	Yield advantage over existing varieties	Disease resistance	Quality acceptability of new rice grain
More favorable					
India	Average	Good	<u>High</u>	Average	Average
Malaysia	<u>Good</u>	Good	<u>High</u>	High	Poor
Philippines	Average	Good	<u>High</u>	Average	Average
West Pakistan	Good	Good	<u>High</u>	High	Average
Vietnam	Average	Average	<u>High</u>	Average	Average
Average					
Ceylon	Good	Good	Low	Average	Average
Indonesia	Average	Poor	Medium	Average	Average
Less favorable					
Burma	Poor	Poor	High	Average	Poor
East Pakistan	<u>Poor</u>	Average	High	<u>Low</u>	Average
Thailand	<u>Poor</u>	Average	Medium	Average	<u>Poor</u>

* Those factors thought to be particularly important in influencing the initial rapid or slow rate of adoption are underlined.

* Those factors thought to be particularly important in influencing the initial rapid or slow rate of adoption are underlined.

as well as the decline of export opportunities resulting from the drive for self-sufficiency may further reduce the capacity of the market to absorb surpluses without a sharp price decline.

If continued technological progress can lead to a sustained increase in rice yield per hectare, it should be possible to divert resources from the production of rice to other agricultural products. Irrespective of the rate of industrial expansion, existing rates of population growth preclude for most Asian countries the possibility of reducing the amount of labor on the land in the near future. This suggests the necessity of examining the alternatives to rice at the farm level. The objective will be to create a more flexible agriculture which can respond to relative changes in prices. Toward this end, more research will be needed in multiple cropping and crop rotations as well as in water management. However, substantial effort will also be necessary to develop and expand both the

domestic and export markets for these alternatives to create the demand necessary to encourage expansion of production.

Finally, the spread of the new varieties will alter the comparative advantage of production both within and between regions. Those farmers with adequate irrigation will be the initial beneficiaries of the new technology. This factor is more important than farm size, since at current wage rates, there are no major economies of scale in rice production that give advantage to the large farmer. It would be difficult to forecast the consequences of a widening gap in the income distribution. The degree of advantage may be eroded over time by expanding production and declining rice prices. Ideally, in the development process, the mechanism should be created for using the gains of one segment to broaden the base of economic growth. This would mean taxing some of the profits of the beneficiaries to provide funds for expanding the

Fig. 9. The Thai export price of rice, 5% broken and white broken A.I Super, F.O.B. Bangkok.

infrastructure in the relatively disadvantaged areas.

Trends in the international rice price

The world export market for rice is a "thin" market. Only about 7 million metric tons or less than 2 percent of the total world production is traded internationally. Thus, there is a potential for a wide price fluctuation. The introduction of new technology and the drive for self-sufficiency on the part of a number of countries suggest that the international export market for rice will likely be more competitive in the near future.

Recent trends in the international rice price are examined in this section. The F.O.B. Bangkok price is taken as indicative of the international market price since Bangkok is one of the world's major export centers. Figure 9 shows the trend in price from 1956 to 1968 of two popular Thai export grades: *White Rice 5%* and *White Broken Rice A.I Super*. The first of these is a high quality grade consisting of 76 percent head rice, 15 to 17 percent big broken, and 5 to 7 percent broken. The second is the most common of the Thai 100 percent broken grades, and normally sells about 30 percent below the former in price. In 1966, approximately 23 percent of the rice milled for export in Thailand sold at or above the price for

White Rice 5%. Another 19 percent of the rice sold as *A.I Super*. About 50 percent, including the parboiled grades, sold somewhere between these two prices, and the remaining 8 percent sold below the price for *A.I Super*.

The price of rice rose sharply in 1967 reaching an unprecedented peak in early 1968. A number of factors contributed to this rise including: (1) the severe drought in India during the 1965/66 and 1966/67 crop years, (2) a decline in exports from Burma which were reported at 1,348,000 metric tons in 1965 and only 650,000 in 1967, and (3) the increase in imports of South Vietnam which between 1964 and 1967 moved from a net exporter to a major world importer of 750,000 m.t. Therefore, the rise in price can be attributed to a combination of unfavorable weather plus internal government problems.

The price rise of 1967 was largely retraced in 1968. Prices at the beginning of 1969 stand approximately where they were in January 1967. A major reason for the decline is explained in Fig. 10, which shows the trend in the ratio of the price of rice to the price of another major world food grain, wheat. With the rice price rising relative to wheat, the major producers of rice and consumers of wheat, such as Mainland China, could profit by exporting rice and importing wheat. In 1966,

Mainland China increased its rice exports by 400,000 m.t. to over a million metric tons and thus became the world's third largest rice exporter.

Another factor contributing to the recent decline was the increase in U.S. production in 1968. This expansion was due principally to the decision of the U.S. government to raise acreage allotments by 20 percent during the 1968 season. The United States became the world's largest rice exporter in 1967 with a total of 1,800,000 m.t. or 25 percent of the total.

It seems unlikely that increased production as a result of new varieties has yet influenced the world price trends to any significant degree. The Philippines, which was a net importer of 187,000 m.t. of rice in 1967, exported a total of 37,000 in 1968. How much of India's recent production increase was due to weather and how much to new varieties cannot be determined, but favorable weather certainly was the dominant factor. West Pakistan harvested 344,000 hectares of IR8 in late 1968. Other countries have not yet harvested a major hectareage planted to new varieties.

What impact will the new rice technology have upon future world price trends? This question is important for countries who are now approaching self-sufficiency and are looking to the world market as a possible source of export earnings. For

the short run the situation is not optimistic. The rapid expansion of the hectareage planted to new varieties is likely to produce a surplus of the coarser grades of rice. It will be difficult for countries entering the export market to produce a large volume of high-quality rice. This is due not only to the quality defects in the new rice varieties such as IR8 and IR5, but also to inadequate processing and milling facilities. New rice exporters will have difficulty winning away the markets of the traditional exporters, and the surplus is likely to create a downward price pressure particularly for the lower grades.

Predicting the long-run trend in the market depends on the conclusions one reaches with respect to the production-population race mentioned earlier. However, the market will continue to be volatile and influenced strongly from year to year by weather and other temporary conditions. Due to the generally low elasticity of demand for rice and the low volume traded on the world market, the export of rice (and other food grains as well) will continue to offer a high risk.

Changes in consumption and marketed surplus as a result of increased production

Two important policy questions relate to the disposition of increased rice production. First,

Fig. 10. Ratio of price to rice (Thai broken A.1 Super) to price of wheat (American #2 hard winter) C.I.F. United Kingdom.

$$\frac{P_r}{P_w} = \text{Ratio of rice price to wheat price}$$

how much of the increase is consumed on the farm and how much enters the commercial market channel? Second, what share of the increase is added to the income of the farm operator?

The first question is important because the marketed surplus affects market price. The rate at which marketed surplus is increased determines when a country reaches self-sufficiency (an adequate market supply of rice relative to demand that will maintain the rice price at a desired level). Two factors which influence the amount of rice consumed or marketed are farm price and farm income. When income increases as a consequence of greater rice production, as has occurred recently on many farms in the Philippines, this may have a very different effect on marketed surplus than when income increases as a consequence of a rise in rice price. In the former case, where the increase in income is synonymous with increase in production, it is impossible to separate out the income effect on consumption. In the latter case, the change in the relative prices between rice and substitutes for rice (such as corn) may result in a reduction in the amount of rice consumed if the price or substitution effect outweighs the income effect.

The second question is concerned with the issue of who benefits from the increase in production. Does the operator maintain the same share or is there a relative increase in the claim against his share by the landlord, moneylenders, or others?

Disappearance of farm operator's share. A survey was made of 106 Luzon farmers in 1966 and 1967 to obtain information with respect to both of these questions. The survey was conducted in cooperation with the Engineering Department as part of a joint study dealing principally with mechanization. The farms selected for interview were those whose land lay adjacent to the kilometer posts along the main highway. The route started in Pila, Laguna, south of Manila and ran north making a loop in Central Luzon. Thus, the survey route had the shape of a lasso. Of the farms surveyed, 36 were rainfed, 36 had irrigation for one crop, and 34 had irrigation for two crops. Seventy-five percent of the farmers were share tenants.

Farm operators were asked to report total production for the previous year and to indicate how the produce was distributed. They were asked

the amount and time of sales and of purchases. There are limitations to this procedure since it relies heavily upon memory for details.

Table 18 shows the disappearance of the farm operator's share of the total rice production. Using the same classification employed in Table 2, farmers were categorized as full adopters, partial adopters, and non-adopters based upon their level of acceptance of new high-yielding varieties in 1967. The purpose was to group together those farms that were likely to have experienced a major increase in production.

The operator's share is the residual after the harvester's share, the landlord's share, and other nominal amounts such as rice for seed have been removed. The landlord's and harvester's shares remained unchanged with the introduction of new varieties. Percentage changes in the division of the operator's share are shown in the table.

Both the full and partial adopters showed gains in gross income. However, the full adopters reduced sharply the hectareage they planted to rice during the dry season by diverting land to other crops. The non-adopters also reduced the total hectareage but by a lesser amount. The partial adopters, on the average, planted more than three-fourths of their land to new varieties but increased the total acreage they planted to rice. The reasons for this shift in land use unfortunately cannot be answered from the information obtained in this year's survey. But plans are being made to pursue this question in more detail in a subsequent survey of the same group of farmers.

The production increase on the farms planting new varieties (full and partial adopters) due to increased yield and shift in land use was 32 percent. More than 90 percent of this increase seems to have initially entered the marketing channel. However, after repurchases 80 percent could be attributed to net marketed surplus and 20 percent to net home use.

Although the net home use increased substantially in absolute amount on those farms planting new varieties, it is very difficult to say what proportion of this increase resulted in an increase in consumption. A recent Bureau of Census survey in the Philippines indicated that rice stocks on farms increased substantially between the 1966/67 and 1967/68 crop seasons.

Income elasticity of demand. To understand

Table 18. Disappearance of farm operator's share of rice production on 106 Luzon farms, 1966 and 1967.

Item	Full adopters		Non-adopters		Partial adopters			All 1967
	Local 1966	New 1967	Local 1966	Local 1967	Local 1966	New 1967	Local 1967	
No. of farms	8	8	77	77	21	21	21	21
Area planted rice (ha)	4.95	3.36	3.46	2.88	4.83	4.32	1.28	5.60
Yield/ha rice (kg)	2020	2980	2120	2320	1910	2050	3680	2420
Total production (kg)	9980	10010	7330	6680	9240	8860	4710	13570
Gross income from rice (₱)	2130	1900	1600	1470	2140	1980	940	2920
Total gross income (₱)	4240	5050	2720	2750	3280	-	-	4850
Kilograms per farm								
Operator's share	5060	5210	3810	3480	5100	4710	2590	7300
Less: home use	1830	1740	1800	1430	2120	1290	1000	2290
Marketable supply	3230	3470	2020	2050	2980	3420	1590	5010
Less: crops to creditor expense in kind	1130	850	400	720	590	300	340	640
Marketed surplus	1880	2480	1450	1190	2320	3060	1160	4220
Less: purchase	150	440	130	450	140	-	-	340
Net marketed surplus	1730	2030	1320	740	2180	-	-	3880
Net home use	1980	2180	1930	1880	2260	-	-	2630
Percent of operator's share								
Operator's share	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Less: home use	36	33	47	41	42	27	39	31
Marketable supply	64	67	53	51	58	73	61	69
Less: crops to creditor expense in kind	23	16	10	21	12	6	13	9
Marketed surplus	37	48	38	34	45	65	45	58
Less: purchase	3	9	3	13	3	—	—	5
Net marketed surplus	34	39	35	21	43	—	—	53
Net home use	39	42	50	54	45	—	—	36

more clearly the nature of the consumption response due to increased income, an analysis was made of the income elasticity of demand using standard regression techniques.

The model is based upon a cross-sectional analysis of the 106 farms surveyed in 1967; it estimates consumption response as a function of the difference in the level of income from farm to farm. It is hypothesized that wealthy farmers will consume more rice than poor farmers. The objective is to determine how the percentage of rice consumption will change for a given percentage

change in income as the level of farm income increases.

The log form of the equation was used to estimate consumption as a function of income and family size as follows:

$$\log C = 0.5130 + 0.2170 \log I + 0.4110 \log S \quad R^2 = 0.40$$

(0.0449) (0.0811)

where:

- C = rice for home use 1967 (cavans per household)
- I = gross income from all sources (₱ per household)
- S = family size (persons)

Table 19. Percentage of household, percent income spent on rice, per capita rice expenditure per year, average size of household by income groups, Philippines, 1965.*

Item	500 & below	500-999	1000-1499	1500-1999	2000-2499	2500-2999	3000-3999	4000-4999	5000-5999	6000-6999	7000-7999	8000-8999	9000-9999	10000 & above
Number of observation	289	514	584	511	454	365	459	250	178	100	65	68	50	216
Percent income spent on rice	110	58	38	27	23	20	17	14	13	11	9	7	7	3
Per capita rice expenditure per year (P)	68	69	71	68	71	71	75	70	62	75	72	70	69	73
Rice expenditure per household per year (P)	357	440	464	480	521	535	582	618	646	585	666	614	672	655
Average size of household (No. of persons)	5.22	6.34	6.49	7.05	7.33	7.52	7.74	8.76	10.48	7.85	9.21	8.75	9.80	8.95

* Source of basic data: Bureau of Census, Philippine Household Survey, May 1966.

Fig. 11. Engel cruve for rice expenditure. Philippines, 1965.

The coefficient of the income variable is the income elasticity. This income elasticity reading directly from the equation is 0.217.

Income elasticity of demand for the Philippines

A study was initiated to determine the income elasticity of demand for rice in the Philippines, the preliminary results of which are reported in this section. The study made use of data from the Philippine Statistical Survey of Households conducted by the Bureau of the Census in May 1966. This survey consisted of an 0.087-percent sample of households throughout the Philippines. Respondents were asked a wide range of questions, a portion of which dealt with income expenditure patterns. At the request of the Institute, the Bureau of the Census provided clerical assistance to draw from its records information pertaining specifically to the expenditure for rice. The following information was obtained: (1) annual household income, (2) size of household, (3) whether the household was located in an urban or a rural area, (4) whether or not the household was engaged in rice production, and (5) the expenditure for rice during the week in which the survey was made.

Some of the basic information has been summarized and classified by size of income in Table 19. The *Engel curve* in Fig. 11 is based upon data from this table and shows the change in the percentage of the household income spent for rice with an increase in income. This figure suggests that income elasticity is likely to be related to size of income, with the low-income groups showing a much larger change in consumption with a change in income. However, the lower income brackets tend to have a smaller size of household, and the relationship between income and percentage of income spent for rice is not well defined when put on a per capita basis.

A procedure used in the past in the Philippines in comparing income elasticities is to divide households into three groups: (1) rural, (2) urban, and (3) Manila. In the case of rice, classification according to rice producers and non-rice producers would seem to be more meaningful for the reasons discussed in the previous section. The following two equations show the estimated income elasticities of demand for each of these groups using the log form of the model. The semi-log form was also used with essentially the same result.

- (1) $\log C = 1.12 + 0.139 \log I - 0.221 \log S$
 (0.015) (0.027)
 $R^2 = 0.13$ rice producers
- (2) $\log C = 0.32 + 0.087 \log I - 0.231 \log S$
 (0.012) (0.020)
 $R^2 = 0.10$ non-rice producers

where:

C = *Rice expenditure per capita* or rice expenditure per household $\div$ size of household. Rice expenditure per household is the value of rice, including glutinous rice, taken by members of the family including servants. The value includes purchases, own produce, and those obtained from other sources by the household. The value excludes the amount taken by boarders and guests.

I = *Income per capita* or income per household $\div$ size of household. Income per household refers to net profits before taxes. This excludes the earnings of servants and other boarders living in the sampled household.

S = *Size of household* or the number of persons living with the household regardless of age. The data, however, exclude the number of servants.

The R^2 values for the two equations are low as is customary with this type of data. However, the coefficients for income and size of household are both significant at the 1-percent level and the signs and values appear to be logical and consistent.

Reading directly from the equations, the coefficients for income indicate an income elasticity of 0.14 for rice producers and 0.09 for non-rice producers. The negative sign associated with the household-size variable indicates that per capita rice consumption declines with an increase in size of household.

Further analysis is being conducted to estimate the income elasticity of demand for different levels of income and for different geographical regions in the Philippines. In this latter context it is hypothesized that the income elasticities will vary according to differences in cropping pattern between regions (e.g., rice-producing areas vs corn-producing areas). The results obtained thus far, based upon Bureau of the Census classification of regions, indicate that, for the most part, income elasticities of demand are significant and positive. Of 19 elasticity estimates made in the 10 Census regions, 14 fall between 0.04 and 0.17. For the Philippines as a whole, the income elasticity of demand for rice appears to be extremely low, i.e., the bulk of the population will change the quantity of rice eaten very little with a change in income.

Statistics

The Department of Statistics placed its major effort on improving field plot techniques in rice research. Various field experiments were conducted in cooperation with the Agronomy Department.

The development of statistical techniques for analyzing and interpreting rice experimental data and for collecting rice statistics from farmer's fields was continued. Consultation and analytical services also were rendered to research workers in other departments.

Biases in Rice Production Statistics

Interview method

Previous findings (1966 and 1967 Annual Reports) have indicated the possible underestimation of rice production by the interview method due to the failure of farmers to report certain components of production. The unreported components—harvester's share, heaping, gleaning, amount given to relatives and friends, and other expenses paid in palay—accounted for about 22 percent of the total rice production in Laguna province. In 1968, a survey was undertaken in the same province to determine the accuracy of assessing these unreported components by further interviews with farmers.

Of the components considered, only those involving amount given to relatives and friends and expenses paid in palay seemed to have been adequately obtained by the interviews. The responses of farmers regarding the harvester's share were in terms of the sharing system in use; in the survey, the farmer-harvester sharing ratios found were 4:1, 5:1, 17:3 and 7:1. Based on the sharing

system reported, the harvester's share was computed for each farm, and the value was compared to the actual harvester's share measured during harvest. An average underestimation of 18 percent was found. One of the reasons for this underestimation was the common practice known as "heaping," where only the harvester's container is filled to overflowing during the sharing process. This practice, however, was not followed in the 17:3 sharing system. Actual measurements from each sample farm during the harvest period showed that each harvester obtained an average of 14 percent more grain than what he would have received if heaping were not practiced.

The farmers generally were not able to estimate accurately their losses from gleaning. Sampling procedures for estimating this component are being devised.

Crop-cutting survey

To examine the possibility of utilizing the crop-cutting method as an objective procedure for estimating average rice production, 31 farms in Laguna were selected from those involved in the

Table 1. Estimated average yield and percentage of overestimation for different sizes and shapes of sampling cuts.

Size and shape of cut (mxm)	Dry season	Wet season	
	Estimated average yield (kg/ha)	Estimated average yield (kg/ha)	Percent overestimation*
1x1	—	4008	16
1x2	—	3845	12
1x3	4208	3852	12
1x4	4239	3767	10
2x2	4515	3864	12
1x5	4395	3871	12
2x3	—	3875	12
2x4	4237	3780	10
3x3	4319	3880	13
3x4	4291	3896	13
4x4	4249	3834	11
4x5	4271	3834	11
5x5	4307	3841	11

$$* \text{ Percent overestimation} = \left[\frac{\text{Estimated average yield} - \text{"Actual" average yield}}{\text{"Actual" average yield}} \right] 100$$

Fig. 1. Patterns and sizes of sampling cuts used in the crop-cutting experiments, 1968 dry and wet seasons.

1967 survey. Two randomly chosen paddies were selected from each sample farm. From each paddy a randomly located 5 x 5 sq m area was harvested according to the patterns and sizes shown in Fig. 1. Table 1 shows the estimated average yield in kilograms per hectare for different sizes and shapes of cuts for the dry and wet seasons. In both seasons, no significant yield differences were detected from cuts ranging from 3 sq m to 25 sq m. In the wet season, where smaller cut sizes were included, the 1 sq m cut gave a slightly higher estimate while the 2 sq m cut did not differ significantly from the others. These results thus indicate that at least in Laguna where rice is planted evenly, cut sizes ranging from 2 sq m to 25 sq m do not seem to affect appreciably the estimated yield.

A proper test of bias must compare yield estimates from sampling cuts of different sizes with that obtained from the entire field. This was not feasible in our study. In the wet season, however, all components of rice production during the harvesting processes were measured in the attempt to estimate, as accurately as possible, the "actual" rice production of each sample farm. This value

was then divided by the actual planted area to obtain the "actual" average yield per hectare. The estimated average yields from the sampling cuts were then compared with the "actual" average yield. The percentages of overestimation for the different cut sizes are shown in Table 1. The 1 x 1 sq m cut gave the highest overestimation of 16 percent while the figures for the remaining cuts ranged from 10 to 13 percent.

It should be noted, however, that the "actual" average yield per hectare used in the comparisons did not include certain losses due to harvesting, transporting, threshing, and drying which would be expected to be larger than those involved in crop-cuts. If the crop-cutting procedure is to be used in estimating average rice production, these losses should be determined.

Combined Analysis of Rice Experimental Data

The evaluation of the validity and uses of combined analyses of data over locations and seasons, which was started in 1966, was continued. Emphasis was given to the validity of the com-

Table 2. Estimates of the effects of variety x location interaction for six rice varieties at 16 locations.

Location	Variety					
	IR8	IR5	IR52- 18-2	IR14- 149-8	T(N)1	BPI- 76
Ilocos Norte	-612*	325	-585*	642*	646*	-417
Isabela	-753*	88	-155	561	-79	338
Bulacan	594*	61	-738*	169	192	-278
Pampanga	1976**	1437**	-1725**	-643*	-1665**	629*
Or. Mindoro (1)	-945**	-28	-263	124	742*	369
Or. Mindoro (2)	-314	-276	-160	238	628*	-116
Albay	-227	-191	-84	1218**	-160	-554
Camarines Sur	317	-1187**	451	351	803**	-734*
Sorsogon	379	199	-595*	404	-526	140
Capiz	-292	530	675*	-1509**	450	147
Iloilo	-1879**	1047**	1536**	-166	-1894**	1358**
Negros Occidental	100	1375	79	-64	-706*	-786**
Leyte del Norte	1226**	-1684**	-204	497	400	759*
Or. Misamis	858**	-540	160	982**	802**	-297
Zamboana del Norte	-537	77	570	330	68	-510
Palawan	109	-1232**	1040**	-174	298	-40

* Significant at the 5% probability level.

** Significant at the 1% probability level.

bined analysis of variance with respect to the underlying assumptions required. Data from the Uniform Rice Variety Trials (URVART)*, Co-operative Uniform Rice Fertilization Applied Research projects (CURFAR)*, and Maximum Yield Experiments** were used.

The difficulties encountered in constructing a combined analysis of variance were the heterogeneities of the error variances and of some of the components of interaction. These problems arose not only in combining data through both locations and seasons but also through either locations or seasons. This heterogeneity vitiated the usual F-tests to a certain extent. In all the cases considered, however, when the error variances were found heterogeneous, the F-statistics were either sizable or very small. Thus no modification of the test was deemed necessary, although the exact significance level of the F-test was no longer known. When the variances of the interaction components were not homogeneous, each treatment comparison was tested against its own interaction component.

Treatment x environment interactions were present in most cases, indicating that the effects of the different treatments (i.e., varieties, fertilizers, and methods of planting) were not the same under different environments. Several approaches for investigating the nature of the interactions were evaluated and the following procedures were found effective:

(1) Estimation of the individual interaction effects. Table 2 shows the estimates of variety x location interaction effects obtained by combining URVART 1966 wet season data involving six rice varieties over 16 locations. Negative or positive signs indicate that the observed mean yields were lower or higher, respectively, than those expected when no interaction was assumed. Significant interaction effects were detected for all varieties and in all locations except Zamboanga del Norte.

* Cooperative project between the Agricultural-Productivity Commission (APC) and The International Rice Research Institute, 1966-67.

** Department of Agronomy, IRRI, 1964-66.

Fig. 2. Linear regression between the mean yield of a variety and the mean yields of all varieties at different locations, by variety. Regressions with the same type of line are not significantly different.

(2) Regression of treatment means to environments. The linear relationships between the average yield of a variety and the average yield of all the varieties at each location (taken as a measure of the environmental condition) for the URVART wet season data are shown in Fig. 2. The six varieties did not respond similarly to the different environments.

In conducting a series of experiments, the optimum combination of the number of replications, locations, and seasons to attain a specified degree of precision needs to be known. An analysis utilizing variance component estimates obtained from the combined analysis of variance of the URVART data showed that for such a series of rice varietal trials in the Philippines, the use of additional seasons, locations, or replications in that order was most effective in reducing the variance of the treatment mean.

Data Transformation in Rice Research

The analysis of variance is one of the most useful and common statistical tools in rice research. Its application, however, is valid only when the data conform to the required assumptions.* When certain types of experimental data deviate from the assumptions, a remedy is needed to allow for an analysis of variance that is free from disturbances. This study was conducted to investigate the assumptions generally invalidated by certain rice data and to evaluate procedures necessary for

handling the situations. Existing data from different departments of the Institute were used. For each set of data, Bartlett's test for homogeneity of variances, Tukey's test for additivity, and the test of significance for the correlation between the treatment means and the within-treatment variances were applied simultaneously to check if the data conform to the required assumptions. Many types of data from rice experiments violated one or more of the assumptions. From this study, however, no general rule can yet be formulated regarding the specific assumptions violated by certain types of data.

Based on the departures from the underlying assumptions as indicated by the statistical tests, specific transformations were applied. It was found that many of the difficulties encountered could be handled by utilizing suitable transformations. As an example, data on the number of living larvae/20 hills are presented in Table 3. The data showed departures from all the three assumptions tested, namely, homogeneity of variance, additivity, and normality. As in most of the cases examined, heterogeneity of variance was due to some degree of association between the variance and the treatment mean. For this specific case, the relationship between treatment mean ($\bar{x}$) and the within-treatment variance (s^2) was found to be linear with a highly significant correlation coefficient of 0.87. Based on the derived relationship, a logarithmic transformation** was made. Various tests to check the validity of the assumptions were then applied to the transformed data. The results indicated that the chosen transformation succeeded in remedying the situation (Table 3). It corrected not only the dependence of the variance on the treatment mean but also the other disturbances.

Field Plot Technique Studies in Rice

In cooperation with the Department of Agronomy, a series of field experiments was con-

*The analysis of variance requires that the experimental errors be independently and normally distributed with a common variance, and that the scale of measurement be one for which the linear additive model holds.

** Since some of the original observations were zeros and many of the values were small, the transformation $\log(X+1)$ was used.

Table 3. Effects of data transformation on the number of living larvae/20 hills.*

Treatment**	Original data (X)				Transformed data [$\log(X+1)$]							
	Replication				Replication							
	I	II	III	IV	I	II	III	IV				
	Treatment mean ($\bar{x}$)	Within-treatment variance (s^2)	Treatment mean ($\bar{x}$)	Within-treatment variance (s^2)	Treatment mean ($\bar{x}$)	Within-treatment variance (s^2)	Treatment mean ($\bar{x}$)	Within-treatment variance (s^2)				
Diazinon (4)	9	12	0	1	5.5	35.00	1.0000	1.1139	0.0000	0.3010	0.6037	0.29114
Diazinon (3)	4	8	5	1	4.5	8.33	0.6990	0.9542	0.7782	0.3010	0.6831	0.07626
Diazinon (2)	6	15	6	2	7.2	30.25	0.8451	1.2041	0.8451	0.4771	0.8428	0.08809
Diazinon (1)	9	6	4	5	6.0	4.67	1.0000	0.8451	0.6990	0.7782	0.8306	0.01632
Diazinon (2) + MLVC (2)	27	17	10	10	16.0	64.67	1.4472	1.2553	1.0414	1.0414	1.1963	0.03813
Diazinon (2) +MLVC+SLVC(2)	35	28	2	15	20.0	212.67	1.5563	1.4624	0.4771	1.2041	1.1750	0.23862
Diazinon (1) + Gusathion (3)	6	15	6	2	7.2	30.25	0.8451	1.2041	0.8451	0.4771	0.8428	0.08809
Diazinon (1) at 15% DH infestation	1	0	0	0	0.2	0.25	0.3010	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0752	0.02265
Diazinon (1) at 20% DH infestation	10	0	2	1	3.2	20.92	1.0414	0.0000	0.4771	0.2361	0.4387	0.19939
Control	4	10	15	5	8.5	25.67	0.6990	1.0414	1.2041	0.7782	0.9307	0.05464

Bartlett's test for

homogeneity of variances: $\chi^2 = 24.67^\dagger$

$\chi^2 = 11.50^{ns}$

Tukey's test for

non-additivity: $F = 11.85^\dagger$

$F = 3.10^{ns}$

Correlation between $\bar{x}$ and s^2 : $r = 0.87^\dagger$

$r = 0.03^{ns}$

* Source of data: Timing of diazinon application and combination with low volume concentrated and conventional sprays, Department of Entomology, IRR1, October 1966-February 1967.

** Numbers in parentheses refer to number of times of application of the chemicals.

† Significant at the 1% probability level.

ns not significant.

Fig. 3. Coefficient of variation for different plot sizes, from four sets of uniformity data.

ducted to collect information that might be useful in improving field plot techniques in rice experimentation.

Uniformity Trials

Four rice uniformity trials involving IR8 and IR5 and two levels of nitrogen – 0 and 120 kg/ha – were carried out in the 1968 dry season. Each trial covered a 25 x 50 sq m area, and the planting distance was 20 x 20 cm. The standard cultural practices recommended by the Agronomy Department were followed uniformly. From the center of each of the three trials, 648 basic unit plots of 1 x 1 sq m size were harvested, while 900 basic unit plots of 0.4 x 2 sq m size were harvested from the fourth trial. Data on grain yield, plant height, and number of panicles were collected.

By combining the unit plots, variations were computed for plots of different shapes and sizes which exactly fitted into the whole area. While the shape of the plot did not seem to have any appreciable effect upon plot variability, a progressive decrease in the coefficient of variation as the plot size increased was observed for the three characters considered (Fig. 3). The rate of decrease, however, was not proportional to the increase in plot size. A slower rate of decline was evident as plot sizes became larger. In general, no sizable reduction in the coefficient of variation was observed for plots larger than 10 sq m. Of the three characters considered, plant height gave the lowest variation. The rate of decrease in the coefficient of variation as the plot size increased was fastest for the panicle number, especially in the plots ranging in size from 1 to 10 sq m.

In all cases investigated, efficiency due to blocking was sizable for most plot sizes considered. Block efficiency gradually decreased with the increase in block size and varied greatly with block shape. This result indicated the importance of selecting a suitable orientation of blocks.

The soil variability of the four experimental fields were examined by constructing fertility contour maps and by computing Smith's indexes of soil heterogeneity. The heterogeneity of the areas appeared to differ. Two maps (Figs. 4 and 5) exhibited strong fertility gradients in both areas but one was uni-directional while the other was two-directional. Using double logarithmic paper,

Table 4. Relative efficiencies of the simple lattice, triple lattice, and lattice square as compared with the randomized complete block design in plots 2 x 3, 2 x 5, and 3 x 5 sq m in size, calculated from uniformity yield data.

Lattice design	No. of treatments	No. of replications	No. of trials	Size and shape		Relative efficiency (%)	
				Incomplete block (m x m)	Replicate (m x m)	Mean	Range
2 x 3 sq m							
Simple	9	2	6	2 x 9	6 x 9	107.0	96.0 - 119.1
				6 x 3	18 x 3	113.8	94.2 - 144.4
	16	2	3	4 x 6	16 x 6	112.5	90.2 - 135.0
				8 x 3	32 x 3	319.3	210.2 - 393.7
36	2	1	6 x 6	12 x 18	135.4	- - -	
			12 x 3	12 x 18	137.2	- - -	
Triple	9	3	4	2 x 9	6 x 9	112.5	100.0 - 147.8
				6 x 3	18 x 3	126.8	100.0 - 187.4
	16	3	2	4 x 6	16 x 6	141.1	100.3 - 174.5
				8 x 3	32 x 3	381.1	294.9 - 467.3
	36	3	1	6 x 6	12 x 18	154.7	- - -
				12 x 3	12 x 18	167.1	- - -
Square	9	2	6	-	6 x 9	258.8	102.2 - 675.7
				-	18 x 3	163.4	100.6 - 352.9
	16	5	1	-	32 x 3	484.3	- - 352.9
				2 x 5 sq m			
Simple	9	2	3	2 x 15	6 x 15	169.6	106.3 - 279.2
				6 x 5	18 x 5	121.0	98.1 - 134.8
	16	2	2*	8 x 5	32 x 5	413.2	345.5 - 480.9
				4 x 10	8 x 20	142.6	135.2 - 150.0
36	2	1*	6 x 10	36 x 10	299.5	- - -	
			3 x 5 sq m				
Triple	9	3	2	2 x 15	6 x 15	116.4	111.0 - 121.9
				6 x 5	18 x 5	127.0	102.2 - 151.8
	16	3	1	8 x 5	32 x 5	468.1	- - -
				3 x 5 sq m			
Square	9	2	3	-	6 x 15	191.2	144.0 - 269.8
				-	18 x 5	204.9	167.8 - 253.7
Simple	9	2	2	3 x 15	9 x 15	140.0	100.3 - 179.7
				9 x 5	27 x 5	395.0	290.6 - 499.5
	16	2	1*	6 x 10	12 x 20	132.3	- - -
				3 x 20	12 x 20	105.3	- - -
	9	3	1	3 x 15	9 x 15	115.5	- - -
				9 x 5	27 x 5	625.8	- - -
16	3	1*	6 x 10	12 x 20	176.4	- - -	
			3 x 5 sq m				
Square	9	2	2	9 x 15	236.8	167.4 - 306.3	
			2*	27 x 5	1042.3	360.9 - 1486.9	

* Yields from a few plots were used twice to obtain complete replicates.

obtained, only the results for grain yield and panicle number per square meter are presented (Table 5). A marked increase in both grain yield and panicle number of the outermost row (R_1), as compared to the five innermost rows, was observed in both varieties (IR8 and IR5) as well as levels of nitrogen (0 and 120 kg/ha). The increases ranged from 62 to 164 percent for yield and 45 to 118 percent for panicle number. It was further observed that, in many cases, the grain yield of the second outermost row (R_2) tended to be comparatively low. However, statistical tests could not establish any significant differences between R_2 and the center rows.

To further evaluate the border effects, data from a large number of replicates were collected in the wet season from five outermost rows of blocks planted to IR8 and which received 0 and 60 kg/ha N. The data on grain yield, plant height and panicle number per square meter are shown in Table 6. In both trials, highly significant border effects on the outermost row were obtained for all the three characteristics. For yield, R_2 was also found to be significantly lower than the center rows for both nitrogen levels. That is, border effects on yield, from the 1.5-meter bare alley surrounding the plots, were not confined to the outermost row. The succeeding row was also affected. The results seem to indicate that when the increase in the yield of the outermost row is large, the yield of the adjacent row may be reduced, possibly due to competition among plants for light and nutrients.

Averaged over two levels of nitrogen, over-estimations in yield, plant height, and panicle number when no border row was removed were 23, 1, and 17.5 percent, respectively. Furthermore, while estimates for the two other characters were adequate when only one outermost row from each side of the plot was removed, the yield was underestimated by about 3 percent. Thus, while the removal of the outermost row seemed to be sufficient for plant height and panicle number it may be necessary to exclude not only one but two outermost rows in measuring plot yield.

Differential response of varieties to the effects of unplanted alley between plots. Two experiments – one without added nitrogen and the other with 120 kg/ha N – were conducted in the 1968 dry season using IR8 and IR5 and a selection,

Table 5. Effects of unplanted sides on grain yield and number of panicles/sq m, 1968 dry season.

Row position	Grain yield (kg/ha)						No. of panicles/sq m					
	0 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N				0 kg/ha N		120 kg/ha N			
	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5	IR8	IR5
R_1	12180 (162)*	11320 (200)	16530 (205)	14960 (264)	525 (145)	531 (166)	625 (159)	706 (218)	388 (107)	294 (92)	419 (106)	450 (139)
R_2	6200 (82)	5500 (97)	7370 (92)	5920 (105)	356 (98)	331 (103)	369 (94)	375 (116)	7980 (99)	5530 (98)	5820 (103)	5970 (105)
R_3	7220 (96)	5790 (102)	7980 (99)	5820 (103)	8140 (101)	5970 (105)	394 (100)	375 (116)	8240 (102)	8048 (100)	394 (100)	425 (131)
R_4	7340 (98)	5820 (103)	8140 (101)	5970 (105)	8240 (102)	8048 (100)	394 (100)	324 (100)	7850 (104)	6000 (106)	394 (100)	425 (131)
R_5	7850 (104)	6000 (106)	8240 (102)	5970 (105)	8240 (102)	8048 (100)	394 (100)	324 (100)	7522 (100)	5664 (100)	394 (100)	324 (100)
R_C	7522 (100)	5664 (100)	8048 (100)	5662 (100)	8048 (100)	5662 (100)	394 (100)	324 (100)	17.5	9.9	15.1	19.4
cv(%)			11.2	10.0	15.3	16.4	15.1	19.4				

* Figures in () are percentages of R_C which is the average of the 5 innermost rows.

the relationship between yield variance per unit area and plot size was found to be linear for all the four sets of uniformity data investigated (Fig. 6). The estimate of Smith's index of soil heterogeneity, b' , for each of the four areas was obtained from the regression coefficient of the respective

regression line. The b' values ranged from 0.1142 to 0.3321. The fairly low b' values obtained indicate that there was a high correlation between the yields of adjacent plots and that the possibility of utilizing relatively small plot sizes should be considered. Further studies will be undertaken to

Fig. 4. Fertility contour map based on uniformity yield data, variety IR8, 0 kg/ha N. IRRI experimental farm, 1968 dry season.

Fig. 5. Fertility contour map based on uniformity yield data, variety IR8, 120 kg/ha N. IRRI experimental farm, 1968 dry season.

obtain estimates of soil heterogeneity over a wider range of environmental conditions which, together with estimates of the costs involved, can be used in estimating the optimum plot size for rice field experiments.

Complex Designs in Rice Field Experiments

A salient feature of the present method of experimentation with rice is the inclusion of many treatments or varieties in a test. It is common in rice research to have several dozen fertilizer treatments or several hundred rice selections in one experiment. An experimental design which can effectively cope with the increased soil heterogeneity encountered in large experimental fields is an important asset for attaining the experimental precision required.

The objective of this study was to investigate, from rice uniformity data, the efficiencies of certain incomplete block designs relative to randomized complete blocks. Three of the more commonly used incomplete block designs, namely, simple lattice, triple lattice, and lattice square were examined. The precision of these designs, relative to the randomized complete blocks, were computed for different plot sizes. Only the results from one uniformity trial, involving IR8 at 120 kg/ha N, are presented and discussed in this report (Table 4). The index of soil heterogeneity for this particular field was small ($b' = 0.149$), indicating that adjacent plots were highly correlated or that strong fertility gradients existed. Given such conditions, one would logically anticipate some gains in precision from the more complex designs. This was the case for the lattice designs considered. Sizable gains in precision* over the randomized complete blocks were exhibited in almost all the cases considered. Furthermore, relative efficiencies varied greatly over the field, reflecting the large differences in fertility patterns from one part of the field to another. The shape of the replication affected the relative efficiency although there was no indication of the superiority of the square replicates over the oblong ones.

Of the three lattices considered, the square lattice seemed to give gains in precision more consistently. This could be explained by the fertility contour map which showed a two-

directional fertility trend in most parts of the field (Fig. 5).

Within the realm of designs and plot sizes investigated, breaking the replication into sub-blocks when the number of entries in the experiment is large seems desirable especially on fields as variable as the one used in this study. As indicated by the present results, it should be realized, however, that while lattice designs may give large gains in precision in some locations, small gains may be expected in others. This implies that each experiment station will have to determine locally what gains may be expected from the use of lattice designs as compared to randomized complete blocks. As a continuation of this study, more uniformity and actual field experimental data will be utilized.

Effects of Interplot Competition

To minimize or eliminate the extraneous effects caused by the contiguity of plots to other varieties, treatments, or interspaces, it is common in rice field experiments to exclude the outermost rows and terminal hills in determining grain yield and other agronomic characters. Whether or not this procedure is sufficient to achieve its purpose is not generally known. Moreover, the extent and magnitude of these effects of interplot competition have not been determined experimentally. This investigation was therefore conducted to evaluate the following effects of interplot competition in transplanted rice: a) the effects of unplanted sides, and b) the effects of nitrogen competition - effects of differences in nitrogen fertilization on adjacent plots.

The effects of unplanted sides

Performance of rows adjacent to unplanted alley.

In the 1968 dry season, data on grain yield, plant height, and panicle number were collected from the 25 center hills of each of 10 successive rows starting from the unplanted sides of the four uniformity trials previously described. Since no significant border effects on plant height were

*The precision of the lattices given in Table 4 was computed without the recovery of inter-block information which explains why there were few cases showing slight losses in precision over the randomized complete blocks.

Table 6. Effects of unplanted sides on grain yield, plant height, and number of panicles/sq m for two nitrogen levels, variety IR8, 1968 wet season.

Row position	0 kg/ha N			60 kg/ha N		
	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Plant height (cm)	No. of panicles/sq m	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Plant height (cm)	No. of panicles/sq m
R ₁	11204 (213)*	100 (104)	390 (182)	12598 (243)	106 (102)	458 (187)
R ₂	4689 (89)	96 (100)	221 (103)	4492 (86)	104 (100)	260 (106)
R ₃	5128	96	206	4902	105	259
R ₄	5170 } (100)	96 } (100)	219 } (100)	4925 } (100)	103 } (100)	239 } (100)
R ₅	5502 } (100)	96 } (100)	219 } (100)	5743 } (100)	103 } (100)	236 } (100)
cv(%)	17.6	4.4	42.5	13.8	6.3	26.5

* Figures in () are percentages of the average of the 3 innermost rows

IR400-5-12-10-2. Each test plot consisted of eight rows 4 m long and 20 cm apart. Adjacent plots were separated by an unplanted alley of 1 meter. Data on grain yield and panicle number were taken from each row. The results are presented by row position, each as the mean of two rows equidistant from the center of the plots (Table 7). The outermost row consistently gave higher yield and more panicles than the center rows, the differences being highly significant in both experiments. The largest increase in yield was exhibited by IR8 plots with 120 kg/ha N. Furthermore, there was an indication in these plots of border effects reaching the second outermost row although in the reverse direction, as shown by the significantly lower yield of R₂ as compared to the center rows. It seems that border effects on the second outermost row become important only when the increase in the yield of the outermost row is extremely large. There are indications that such situations may be expected with heavily fertilized plots planted to varieties capable of efficiently using the advantage offered by the unplanted border. For these cases, it would seem necessary to exclude not one but two outermost rows in measuring plot yields.

Highly significant border effect x variety interactions were observed at both nitrogen levels, indicating that some varieties were influenced more than others by the 1-meter alley between

Fig. 6. Relationship between variance of yield per unit area and plot size on double logarithmic paper, for four uniformity trials.

plots. Based on yield, IR400-5-12-10-2 seemed to be the least affected while IR8 and IR5 were able to make better use of the advantage afforded by the unplanted border.

The result showed also that the increments in yield and panicle number of the outermost row over the center rows tended to be larger at higher nitrogen levels. This was especially true for IR8 where the yield of the outermost row was about 110 percent higher than that of the center rows at 0 N but was 139 percent higher at 120 N. The same trend was shown by IR5, although at a lower magnitude.

Effects of distances between plots on the performance of border rows. Using IR8 as the indicator variety, two experiments – one at 0 and another at 60 kg/ha N – were conducted in the 1968 wet season. A randomized complete block design with five replications and five spacings between plots, namely 40, 60, 100, 140 cm, and control*, were used. Data on grain yield, plant height, and panicle number were collected from each of the 16 rows in each plot. Only the averages of the two trials are presented since the combined analyses of variance, for all characteristics, showed no significant interactions between trials and all other factors. Table 8 shows the average performance of the outermost row (R_1), the second outermost row (R_2), and the center rows (R_C) for the different sizes of unplanted borders. The outermost rows gave significantly higher values for yield, plant height, and panicle number than did the center rows at all spacings, except of course

the control (20 cm). However, the differences became greater as the distance between plots was widened. The distance between plots beyond 100 cm, however, did not result in any further increase in the values of the outermost row.

Effects of nitrogen competition

Fertilized and unfertilized plots were arranged systematically in an alternating series, and adjacent plots were separated by a 40-cm unplanted alley. The dry season experiment involved two rice varieties, IR8 and IR5, and two nitrogen levels, 0 and 120 kg/ha N. In the wet season only IR8 was planted using 60 kg/ha N instead of 120. The results on grain yield and number of panicles per square meter are presented in Tables 9 and 10.

In all cases, the grain yield of the outermost

*The distance between plots was 20 cm which was the same as the spacings between rows within plots.

Table 7. Mean grain yield (kg/ha) and number of panicles/sq m (average of 5 replicates) of the 4 row positions for three rice varieties at two nitrogen levels, 1968 dry season.

Variety or selection	Row position	Grain yield		No. of panicles/sq m	
		0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N	0 kg/ha N	120 kg/ha N
IR8	R_1	10650 (210)*	18250 (239)	472 (145)	635 (184)
	R_2	5275 (104)	6975 (78)	314 (97)	370 (107)
	R_3	5375 (106)	7888 (103)	282 (87)	395 (114)
	R_4	5062 (100)	7638 (100)	324 (100)	346 (100)
IR5	R_1	11750 (218)	14000 (228)	591 (187)	706 (201)
	R_2	5538 (103)	5738 (94)	331 (105)	399 (114)
	R_3	5275 (98)	6675 (109)	320 (102)	382 (109)
	R_4	5388 (100)	6125 (100)	316 (100)	351 (100)
IR400-5-12-10-2	R_1	10300 (196)	14488 (198)	666 (186)	914 (187)
	R_2	5550 (106)	7350 (101)	364 (101)	488 (100)
	R_3	5375 (102)	7650 (105)	350 (97)	498 (102)
	R_4	5250 (100)	7312 (100)	359 (100)	489 (100)
	LSD (.05)	561	698	51	71
	LSD (.01)	752	936	68	93

* Figures in () are percentages of R_4 .

Table 8. Mean grain yield, plant height and number of panicles/sq m (average of 10 replicates) of border rows adjacent to varying widths of unplanted alley between plots, 1968 wet season.

Distance between plots (cm)	Grain yield (kg/ha)			Plant height (cm)			No. of panicles/sq m		
	R ₁	R ₂	R _C	R ₁	R ₂	R _C	R ₁	R ₂	R _C
20 (Control)	5241	5411	5416	92	92	93	247	250	246
40	7920	5491	5576	95	95	94	327	271	264
60	9264	5488	5394	97	94	93	354	266	242
100	11117	5436	5654	97	95	95	428	278	253
140	10897	5288	5461	94	92	93	408	257	250

Table 9. Mean grain yield and number of panicles per square meter for plots receiving no nitrogen when bordered by plots receiving high rates* of nitrogen (averages of 13 and 8 replicates for the dry and wet seasons, respectively).

Row position	Dry season, 1968				Wet season, 1968	
	IR8		IR5		IR8	
	Grain yield (kg/ha)	No. of panicles/sq m	Grain yield (kg/ha)	No. of panicles/sq m	Grain yield (kg/ha)	No. of panicles/sq m
R ₁	10,422	406	10,042	486	7167	218
R ₂	5,766	292	6,043	325	5133	208
R ₃	5,910	286	6,124	332	4900	210
R ₄	6,128	306	6,090	348	4800	208
R ₅	6,183	292	5,998	325	4850	210
R ₆	6,322	315	6,232	335	4800	209
R ₇	6,397	298	6,101	331	4733	208
cv(%)	12.1	12.4	8.5	12.0	6.7	6.2

* The rates of 120 and 60 kg/ha N were used in the dry and wet season, respectively.

row was significantly higher than that of the center rows. This was true for the fertilized plots although the surrounding areas had lower fertility levels. Apparently, the effect of the unplanted alley between plots was more than enough to offset the reduction in productivity due to nitrogen deficiency in adjacent areas. For the panicle number, a similar effect on the outermost row was obtained in the dry season. In the wet season, however, no border effects on panicle number were detected. Furthermore, even the second outermost row of IR8 in the fertilized plots gave significantly lower yield and panicle number than

the center rows in the dry season (Table 10). It thus seems that the very productive outermost row could adversely affect not only the yield but also the panicle number of the adjacent row.

In the study of the effects of nitrogen competition, two questions need to be answered: a) Are the effects of competition due mainly to the 40-cm unplanted space or to the different nitrogen levels between adjacent plots? b) Are the differences in performance among row positions sufficient to characterize the effect of nitrogen competition? It should be noted that if the entire plot was affected by the differential nitrogen

application, the effects of competition would not have been detected by merely comparing the different row positions.

The wet season experiment was, therefore, slightly modified in an attempt to answer the above questions. A 14-row plot was bordered on one side by plots of the same nitrogen level, and on the other side by plots of a different level. The nitrogen levels used were 0 and 60 kg/ha. The average yields from eight replicates each consisting of two rows are shown in Fig. 7 by their respective row positions in the plots.

As expected, the yields of the outermost rows in all plots were consistently higher than those of their respective center rows. However, the increase was higher in the outermost rows adjacent to the highly fertilized plots than those adjacent to the unfertilized plots. This result holds for both the unfertilized and fertilized plots. It seems, therefore, that the effects of competition on the outermost rows were not only due to the 40-cm unplanted alley but also to the differences in nitrogen level on the adjacent plots.

It was found also that the effects of widely different nitrogen levels on adjacent plots were not confined only to one or two border rows; they were evident even up to the fourth or fifth row (80 or 100 cm) from the edge of the plot. For the no-nitrogen plots, the average yield of the half-plot adjacent to the plot receiving 60 kg/ha N was significantly higher than that of the half-plot next to the unfertilized plot. On the other hand, the yield of the 60 kg/ha N half-plot adjacent to the no-nitrogen plot was significantly lower than that adjacent to the plot similarly fertilized. The results also indicate that even when the outermost row is discarded, the average yield could be over-estimated by 7 percent for a no-nitrogen plot bordered by a highly fertilized one or under-estimated by 6 percent for a 60 kg/ha N plot bordered by a no-nitrogen one.

Effects of missing hills

For rice field experiments, the occurrence of missing hills within experimental plots can not be totally avoided. A common practice is to make adjustments in plot yield by assuming that a missing hill has a value equivalent to the average of the living hills. This adjustment would be correct only if the absence of a hill does not in any way

affect the performance of the neighboring plants. However, since the vacant hill does not compete with the adjacent plants for such growth factors as soil moisture, light, nutrients, etc., there is reason to doubt this assumption. Therefore, an experiment was conducted during the 1968 wet season to evaluate the effects of various types of missing

Fig. 7. Mean grain yields of different row positions in fertilized and unfertilized plots adjacent to plots receiving the same and different nitrogen levels, 1968 wet season. Figures in () refer to the percentages of the average of the four center rows.

Table 10. Mean grain yield and number of panicles per square meter by row position for highly fertilized* plots when bordered by plots receiving no nitrogen (averages of 13 and 8 replicates for the dry and wet seasons, respectively).

Row position	Dry Season, 1968				Wet Season, 1968	
	IR8		IR5		IR8	
	Grain yield (kg/ha)	No. of panicles/sq m	Grain yield (kg/ha)	No. of panicles/sq m	Grain yield (kg/ha)	No. of panicles/sq m
R ₁	10214	429	10353	462	7767	255
R ₂	6881	309	6373	346	7100	252
R ₃	7577	356	6697	352	5133	253
R ₄	7696	350	6598	346	5067	254
R ₅	7397	369	6618	342	5267	256
R ₆	7520	346	6433	336	5100	257
R ₇	7594	346	6120	348	5417	261
cv (%)	10.1	17.3	8.9	12.0	9.9	1.0

* The rates of 120 and 60 kg/ha N were used in the dry and wet seasons, respectively.

Table 11. Effects of different types of missing hill(s) on plot yields (kg/ha), for four sizes of harvested area, 1968 wet season.

No. of hills harvested	Treatment	IR8	IR154-61-1	Average	Percentage of control	
2 hills	T ₁	5980	4173	5076	110	
	T ₂	6200	4700	5450**	118	
	T ₃	6510	4725	5618**	121	
	C	5575	3697	4636	100	
4 hills	T ₁	5172	4144	4658	100	
	T ₂	5755	4522	5139	111	
	T ₃	6512	4182	5347**	115	
	C	5361	3932	4646	100	
14 hills	T ₁	5078	4151	4614	104	
	T ₂	4982	4161	4572	103	
	T ₃	5625	4540	5082*	115	
	C	4979	3897	4438	100	
5 sq m area:						
	99 hills	T ₁	5454	4097	4776	101
	98 hills	T ₂	5158	3971	4564	96
	98 hills	T ₃	5413	4401	4907	104
100 hills	C	5327	4157	4742	100	

* Significantly different from the control at the 5% probability level.

** Significantly different from the control at the 1% probability level.

hills on the performance of adjacent hills in rice experimental plots. At 1 week after transplanting, three missing-hill conditions were established: one missing hill (T_1), two adjacent missing hills (T_2), and two missing hills with one standing hill in-between (T_3). A condition in which no hill was missing (C) was used as the control. IR8, a high-tillering variety and IR154-61-1, a relatively low-tillering selection, were used. For each plot, grain yields were taken from the two hills, the four hills and the fourteen hills immediately surrounding the missing hill(s), and also from the 5-sq-m area* covering the missing hill(s). The results are shown in Table 11.

When only two hills were harvested, both T_2 and T_3 gave grain yields that were significantly higher than the control. On the four- and fourteen-hill bases, however, only T_3 yielded significantly better than the control. These results seem to indicate the following:

(1) that aside from the number, the position of the

missing hills in a plot is also important in determining grain yield, and

(2) that the effect of a missing hill on plot yield determination tends to decrease with the increase in the size of the harvested area.

The mean yields of the 5-sq-m area containing some vacant hill(s) were not significantly different from those of the control. It should be noted that the yield of the 5-sq-m area had not been adjusted for the missing hill(s). This points out the possible overestimation of the plot yield if the usual adjustment of equalizing the number of hills per plot is made. The similarity of the unadjusted yields to that of the control indicated that the loss in the total number of hills was at least partially compensated for by higher yields of the hills surrounding the missing ones. Further studies are needed to establish appropriate adjustment procedures for determining yields of plots with various types of missing hills.

*The area per plot commonly harvested in IRRI's field experiments.

Experimental Farm

The Experimental Farm continued to perform its important functions of providing a field labor force for the other departments of the Institute, controlling pests and weeds on the station, and multiplying seeds of promising new varieties.

As in previous years, the area assigned to the Experimental Farm was planted to IRRI selections for seed multiplication and for cooking quality tests. A total of 24 and 27 selections were grown in the dry and wet seasons, respectively.

In the dry season, 1.18 hectares were planted to the glutinous selection, IR253-16-1-2, with the bulk of the harvested grain being sent to Laos and the remainder sold to farmers interested in growing the selection. In the wet season, IR532E576, one of the most promising Institute selections, was grown on 1.14 hectares of land for seed multiplication. From the harvest obtained, 100 cavans were distributed to the Seed Growers Association of the

Philippines, to agricultural and fertilizer companies, and to cooperating agencies abroad.

The irrigation system of the Farm was improved by drilling a new deepwell and equipping it with a 15-horsepower pump and motor. To distribute the water in all parts of the field, several new irrigation pipelines were laid during the year.

In September and October, the experimental fields were heavily infested with brown plant-hoppers, but these were controlled by insecticide applications (sevin, azodrin, and dimecron, used alternately).

Field damage by rats was minimized by the extensive rat control measures adopted by the Farm, including the heavy dusting of rat burrows in the experimental areas and in surrounding farmer's fields. The total number of rats killed by the electric fence during the year was 9,968 as compared with 15,093 killed in the previous year.

Library and Documentation Center

International Bibliography

In 1968 the 5-year cumulative index to the 1961-1965 supplements of the *International Bibliography of Rice Research* was published. This 143-page volume contains the cumulative author, subject, and geographic indexes to the world literature on rice reported in five separate supplements from 1961 through 1965.

The 1967 supplement to the *International Bibliography of Rice Research* was also prepared in 1968, and will appear in printed form in early 1969. Consisting of 353 pages including a list of rice literature translations and indexes, the supplement contains 2,780 bibliographic citations on technical rice literature, which is an increase of about 20 percent over the number for the previous issue. This increase is attributed to the greater rice literature output and the inclusion of references published in 1961-1966 which were not in the previous supplements. An additional 101 serial titles were scanned for the compilation. The bibliography is arranged according to subject matter with author and keyword indexes.

The 1963 supplement was reprinted to fill pending and future requests. The demand for the rice bibliography has increased considerably as more requests continue to come from the rice-producing areas of the world.

Reference and Circulation

There was a marked increase in the number of reference inquiries received, particularly from Malaysia, India and the Philippines. Rice breeding and genetics outranked all other subject requests, followed by general works and pathology. Many of the requests were for Japanese literature.

Requests for short bibliographies on specific subjects, and for information on library problems dealing with organization, administration, and information retrieval were also received.

Circulation statistics within the Institute totalled 22,812. As the library operates an open stack system, no direct-library-use figures are available.

Library Holdings

The monographic collection (books, pamphlets, reprints, and translations) now totals 22,463 volumes. Other library materials acquired were maps and theses on microfilm. Some 16,000 cards were added to the card catalogue in 1968, bringing the card total to 140,000.

As in previous years, current and back issues of periodicals and journals were obtained through purchase or exchange or as gifts. The number of serial titles reached a maximum of 1,667, but a few of them were excluded by the end of the year.

Other Library Activities

The monthly distribution of the library list of new literature acquisitions and the routing of tables of contents of journals to the departments concerned were continued to keep the scientists informed of the latest publications about rice.

The library continued to send copies of translations of foreign language rice literature to the National Agricultural Library of the U.S. Department of Agriculture, which in turn lists these in the *Bibliography of Agriculture* to make them readily accessible to rice scientists.

Bindery

The bindery output during the year was as follows: periodicals, 356 volumes, theses, 92 volumes; field books, 85 volumes, IRRI Annual Report, 36 volumes, reprint file boxes, 98 pieces, slide boxes, 6 pieces, folders, 104 pieces, *International Bibliography of Rice Research* Cumulative index, 900 volumes, book repair, 50 volumes; IRRI Technical Bulletin, 250 volumes, mounting maps, 12 pieces, and name tags, 200 pieces.

Office of Communication

The overall organization, functions and activities within the Office of Communication remained essentially the same as in previous years except for a quickening pace in some phases of work and certain personnel changes. An effort was made to identify homogeneous types of activities within the Office and to separate them into two distinct sections.

At the end of the year plans were being made to realign the functions presently being managed by the Office and to form two distinct programs: the Office of Information Services to include editorial, photographic, art, reproduction, visitor and display functions, and the Office of Rice Production Training and Research which would include the training of rice production specialists and the so-called applied research program of the Institute.

Thirty-four trainees from nine countries participated in the fourth class in the Rice Production Training Program conducted from June to December. Like the trainees of previous classes, they spent half of their training time in the paddies, developing their skills in producing rice in the monsoon tropics with the tools and implements available to average farmers throughout Asia; the other half they spent in the classroom discussing with a member of the Institute's senior staff the scientific aspects of rice technology. They attended a 3-week course of instruction in selected agricultural engineering subjects, given special emphasis for the first time in the 1968 RPTP, because of the growing trend in Asia toward labor-saving devices.

Follow-up visits during 1968 on the 1967 Institute-trained rice production specialists found the 1967 graduates of the RPTP, particularly those from Indonesia, Ceylon, the Philippines, West Pakistan, East Pakistan, and the United States, conducting their own training programs for hundreds of their countrymen, a clear indication that the RPTP graduates are putting to effective use their rice production training at the Institute.

Dissemination of Information

Publications

As usual, the Annual Report of over 300 pages was the principal publication effort. The editing, illustrating, lay-out work, proofreading and supervision of the typesetting in Australia and printing in Hongkong of the Report required the attention of the editorial staff throughout the year. Investigations into alternate possibilities for typesetting and printing were begun in order to advance the date of publication of this Report in future years.

Many individual projects and experiments of Institute scientists are published in scientific professional journals throughout the world. The Office of Communication continued to provide editorial, graphic and illustrative processing for the increasing number of these journal articles. Reprints of these articles were purchased for distribution to interested scientists and institutions. Similar services were provided for non-journal articles such as papers to be presented in seminars and conferences and reports to agencies funding specific projects.

The Virus Diseases of the Rice Plant, a book reporting the proceedings of a symposium held at the Institute, was processed in cooperation with the Johns Hopkins Press, which is publishing the book. Work proceeded on schedule and it should be released by March 1969.

The eighth in a series of Institute technical bulletins, *Market Relationships for Rice and Corn in the Philippines*, was edited, illustrated and turned over to a Manila publishing house for printing. This bulletin of over 250 pages is expected to become available by May 1969.

Because of an increasingly heavy work load and changes in personnel, only three issues of *The IRRI Reporter* were published in 1968. The usual six issues of this semi-technical publication will be printed in 1969. The original size of *The IRRI Reporter* mailing list (2,000 names in 1965) has doubled to a present 4,000 names.

Revisions of Institute publications were made for the purpose of updating them and ordering an adequate supply for distribution. These publications included: 1) The general information booklet, describing the general nature and program of the Institute, 2) The Training Program, a 19-page

booklet describing all aspects of the Institute's international research training program, and 3) General Leaflet I, "Cultural Practices for Profitable Rice Production," which contains recommendations for growing the new, short, stiff-strawed varieties such as IR8 and IR5.

Informational activities

The soundtrack of the Office of Communication's 13-minute film "Changing the 'Change Agent'" which describes approaches to rice production training was revised and rerecorded. Prints of this film have been sent to Pakistan, Ceylon, India, and Hawaii.

Requests for copies of the Institute's film, "Harvest of Energy" increased this year. Copies were sold to private business, foundations or government agencies in 10 countries. In addition, there were requests for permission to use parts of this film in movies being produced to illustrate economic or agricultural advancement.

A growing number of requests have been received for Institute photographs of new rice varieties, cultural recommendations and insects or diseases for use in educational programs, commercial literature, foundation publications or technical journals. Additionally, several publications throughout the world have sent reporters and/or photographers to the Institute to prepare major articles for their use.

During the year, the editor and the rice production specialist met with personnel from the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines to plan and implement a major revision of the Rice Production Manual.

At the invitation of the Philippine National Science Development Board, a photographic and essay exhibit on two NSDB-sponsored Institute research projects was prepared in June and formed part of the NSDB exhibits put up last year in connection with the Board's anniversary celebration.

Visitors

Briefing for visitors to the Institute continue to be one of the most effective means of communicating to the general public the activities of the Institute. Various trainees and professionals visited the Institute in increasing numbers, although as in previous years, most visitors consisted of school

groups, tourists, and farmers (both local and foreign). During the past year the Institute has hosted visitors engaged in medicine, education, agricultural production, government, private foundations, private enterprise, administration, commerce, military functions, labor, banking, sociology, extension, trade, public relations, missionary activities, and international affairs. Nationalities and specific interests of the visitors are highly varied, but every effort is made to satisfy the individual needs of each group by arranging discussions, movie and slide presentations, and visits to field plots, as appropriate.

To relieve staff members of the burden of attending to the bulk of these visitors – students, farmers, and civic groups – a rice information assistant was hired in November. He is a graduate of the Institute's first rice production training program and is qualified to answer questions on rice production as well as on general information about the Institute.

The plots near the entrance to the Institute grounds were maintained to serve as high visual impact exhibits for illustrating the benefits of new cultural recommendations or rice varieties to the Institute's non-professional visitors.

Training in Rice Production and Communication

The Rice Production Training Program (RPTP) was started in June 1964 when it became obvious that rice researchers soon would develop new varieties and new cultural practices which could result in dramatic yield increases if properly applied at the farm level. It was clear that the average farmer could be taught the new technology by "change agents" within existing governmental and private agricultural organizations by the normal means of meetings, displays and field demonstrations. Those engaged in the extension phase of agriculture (the "change agents") are essentially communicators and to elicit a positive attitude and a directed response from farmers with respect to the use of the new rice technology, the communicators first must understand the new information thoroughly and must have practiced it themselves before attempting to teach or demonstrate its application. The general purpose and nature of the Rice Production Training has been

described in previous annual reports and in other publications, so it will not be repeated here.

During the past 5 years, 108 persons have undergone training in rice production at the Institute in programs of 6-month or 12-month duration. Over 200 others have been trained in short courses of from 1 to 2 weeks. Table 1 shows the countries of origin of these trainees.

A practical examination involving the identification of specimens of the important insects, diseases and weeds associated with rice production is used to assess the level of knowledge of topics which a trainee has upon entering the course and again upon completing the training, regardless of the duration of the course. Trainees selected for participation in the 6-month RPTP are usually recommended by their home institutions as being qualified agriculturists with a reasonable amount of experience in the field of rice research or extension. Every effort is made to arrange a personal interview with the candidates to be conducted by a professional agriculturist qualified to judge the adequacy of the individual's academic background and experience. The majority of participants hold at least the degree of Bachelor of Science in Agriculture, while a number hold the M.S. or Ph.D. degree.

Participants' performance data show clearly that "change agents," regardless of their country of origin or academic attainment, can benefit from instruction offered in the 6-month or 12-month courses which stresses the development in the individual of the ability to accurately diagnose a paddy production problem, a mastery of the skills and the science of rice production, and a working knowledge of the fundamentals of effective communication. It will be noted that all trainees distinctly improved their diagnostic skills during the training program, as measured by the practical examination results shown in Table 2.

The same pattern of performance is apparent in the practical examination scores of "change agents" who underwent rice production training at locations other than the Institute, but under instructors who had been graduated from one of the Institute's 6- or 12-month courses.

In Table 3, note that results of the practical examination show that the duration of the training program can be as short as 1 or 2 weeks and still produce the desired change in diagnostic skills.

Table 1. Countries of origin of rice production trainees.

Course	Country	No. of trainees
6-month or 12 month course	Philippines	56
	India	11
	Indonesia	9
	United States	7
	Ceylon	6
	East Pakistan	4
	West Pakistan	4
	Malaysia	3
	Laos	2
	Nigeria	1
	Sudan	1
	Total	108
1-month course	Malagasy Republic	1
1-week or 2-week course	United States	104
	Philippines	80
	East Pakistan	11
	West Pakistan	2
	India	2
	Indonesia	1
	Total	200
GRAND TOTAL		309

From the data in Tables 1 to 3, it is clear that the persons participating in rice training programs during the past 5 years, before training were generally inadequately prepared to help farmers identify production problems correctly and apply effective economic control measures. In fact the average percentage of correct answers for 861 trainees who took the practical examination was only 28 percent.

Mounting evidence in the form of performance scores of "change agents" in rice training programs, and in the continuing comments of farmers with respect to the inability of "change agents" to help solve their rice production problems, supports the thesis that rice farmers, to a large degree, are resisting the ill-equipped "change agents" as much as, or more than, they are resisting change in technology itself. If this is the case, then immediate strenuous and widespread efforts are re-

quired in rice-producing countries to produce as many qualified "change agents" as possible as experts in the new rice technology and thus minimize or eliminate one of the existing barriers to the rapid technological advancement needed to bring about food sufficiency in developing countries.

Of particular interest are the practical examination scores obtained by two groups of Filipino farmers who participated in 2-week rice production training programs conducted at the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines in July and August 1968 by graduates of the Institute RPTP. While the sample is small (19), the participants represent reasonably well the general farmer population of Laguna province. Only one individual had undergone 2 years of college study, while one could not even read and write.

Table 2. Rice production diagnostic and identification skills of trainees from different countries before and after 6 months or 12 months of training at IRRI.

Country	No. of trainees	Percentage of correct answers	
		First test	Final test
Philippines	29	39	89
India	11	22	85
Indonesia	9	26	78
United States	7	22	87
Ceylon	6	28	90
East Pakistan	4	17	83
West Pakistan	4	54**	86
Vietnam	4	10	85
Malaysia	3	40	80
Laos	2	36	89
Nigeria	1	No exam.*	100
Sudan	1	7	No exam.*
Total (81)*			
Average		27	87

* The 1964-65 class of trainees (11 in number) did not take the test. Sixteen trainees in class No. 2 arrived late and did not take the test.

** High opening score reflects prior 2-week training in West Pakistan in 1967 before entering training at IRRI in June 1967.

Table 3. Practical examination scores of "change agents" in rice production training at locations other than IRRI (November 1967-December 1968).

Country where trained	No. of trainees	Duration of course	Percentage of correct answers	
			First day	Last day
Indonesia	29	3 months	33	67
Hawaii	21	2 weeks	16	85
Ceylon	24	2 weeks	38	No data
East Pakistan	81	2 weeks	32	83
West Pakistan	301	2 weeks	31	68
Philippines*	405	2 weeks	15	71
Total	861	Average	28	75

* Training conducted at the Baybay National Agricultural School, Siniloan, Laguna, and at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, College, Laguna.

Comparing the average practical examination scores for "change agents" (Tables 2 and 3) with those for Filipino farmers (Table 4), it can be noted that some of the farmers from Laguna performed at least as well as the "change agents" during rice production training short courses.

Once trained and qualified in the rice production skills and science required to meaningfully assist farmers, the rice "change agents" must be supported in their work by their parent agencies if dedication and performance are to be expected of them.

While marked progress is being made to upgrade the rice production skills and knowledge of "change agents," a dire need still exists to (1) multiply the numbers of truly qualified individuals who can communicate effectively with farmers to introduce meaningful new technology by their actions rather than by their words - to show how, rather than to tell how, (2) to organize the trained rice specialists within a country into a functioning national communication system which will permit the rapid and continuous flow of technical information between research workers and farmers, and (3) to professionally challenge and stimulate the trained individuals and to reward excellence in performance.

If farmers are to accept new technology and apply it with reasonable assurance that it will

Table 4. Practical examination scores of selected farmer-leaders in rice production training at UPCA, Laguna. July to August, 1968.

Class No.	Duration of training	No. of trainees	Percentage of correct answers	
			First day	Last day
1	2 weeks	6	43	78
2	2 weeks	13	37	72
	Total	19		
	Average	40		

benefit them personally and produce more food for the increasing population, they must have available to them the services of a professional and technically competent "change agent" who can gain and hold their confidence and respect based on what he can accomplish in a rice paddy.

The 1968 rice production training program

The fourth class in the Institute-based Rice Production Training Program was conducted from June to December, 1968.

The class of 34 trainees included 10 Indians, 5 Indonesians, 4 Vietnamese, 3 Malaysians, 3 Filipinos, 2 Laotians, 2 Ceylonese, 2 East Pakistanis, 2 U. S. Peace Corps volunteers, and 1 American from the private sector. The educational

attainment of the participants ranged from the B. S. degree to the doctorate. As in previous classes, strong emphasis was placed on developing trainee competence in the skills required to produce rice in the monsoon tropics using the tools and implements which are available to average farmers throughout Asia. Additionally, a senior staff member of the Institute met daily with the class to discuss the scientific aspects of rice technology and to delineate the objectives of and progress in their respective research programs. The class of 34 trainees was organized into five operational groups each consisting of at least one member of each nationality in the program. Each group was supervised by a staff member of the Office of Communication and was responsible for carrying out one or more applied research projects during the 6-month period.

Trainees plowed their paddies with animals and native plows, grew their own seedlings, measured and laid out their randomized and replicated plots, transplanted, made quantitative measurements of pertinent plant characteristics, harvested and threshed, and reported their results to the class both during the crop season and at the conclusion of the program. Approximately half of their time was spent in the paddies and half in the classroom.

An "International Rice Variety" display was planted by the trainees. It contained the leading rice variety of each country represented in the training program. Trainees from a given country specified the cultural practices for their variety and managed the planting throughout the season. The display enabled all participants and staff to observe a typical variety from each of the nine countries and to compare its performance with those from other countries.

Also included in the training were quantitative studies involving three methods of stand establishment (transplanting, broadcasting and row sowing), spacing trials using three spacings and two varieties, herbicide trials to evaluate several of the new granular herbicides in comparison with hand-weeding, a fertilizer trial using a new selection IR532E208 and 10 combinations or levels of N-P-K, with and without diazinon, tests of a deep water selection (IR442), production fields (transplanted and broadcast), and trials of direct seeding into 4-inch-deep water.

Dr. Francis C. Byrnes, former head of the Office of Communication, returned to the Institute in September from his assignment in Colombia, to organize and present 4 weeks of intensive training in the fundamentals of communication for the RPTP participants.

If graduates of the RPTP are to exert a positive influence within their home organizations upon completion of technical training, they will need an effective communication channel for conveying new ideas and stimulating their associates. It would appear that well-designed and carefully executed rice field days presented shortly after the return of the RPTP graduate might afford the needed communication channel for the technically competent rice specialist to demonstrate to various audiences both his own capabilities to grow rice and the effectiveness of the newest rice technology. If the technician is to succeed in his efforts to change attitudes and behavior with respect to rice production in his own country, the technology itself must be perceived as highly meaningful by various audiences in both the public and private sectors of agriculture. Should the new technology under demonstration fail to stimulate a given audience to positive and directed action, both the technology and the rice specialist will find difficulty in gaining acceptance within the agricultural community. With competence in the fundamentals of the communication process and in the use of rice technology as a communication channel, the rice specialist should be able to demonstrate simultaneously his own credibility and the efficacy of the technology. Practice in a well-organized field day was given the trainees by having them go through this exercise at a Saturday seminar.

Agricultural engineering subjects were given special emphasis in the 1968 rice production training program for the first time because of the presently growing trend in Asian countries toward labor-saving devices such as two-wheel tractors, motor-driven threshers, heated-air driers, and pumps. As rice yields and associated net profits increase, more and more rice farmers are investing in motorized equipment and are finding need for technical guidance in its selection and use. To prepare the present group of trainees for practical service to rice farmers in subjects related to machinery, a 3-week intensive course of instruc-

tion in selected agricultural engineering topics was presented by members of the Agricultural Engineering Department of the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines. In lecture and laboratory sessions the trainees studied a number of subjects from small tractors for soil preparation on average-sized farms to self-propelled combines for large-scale commercial harvest operations. Considerable emphasis was placed on rice drying by use of heated air in batch-type (horizontal) or continuous flow-type (vertical) driers. The Manila-based rice milling expert of the Food and Agriculture Organization assisted in providing detailed instruction concerning rice milling equipment and the milling process. This type of training is urgently needed for rice specialists in every rice-producing country if "change agents" are to become qualified to help rice millers produce a quality of rice which is saleable on the world market.

As in previous classes, classroom instruction was given in the theory, use, and management of agricultural aircraft in tropical rice production so that graduates of the training program will be prepared to make rational judgments concerning the use of this technique in their own countries when the need arises. The 2-hectare field of a nearby farmer served as a practical laboratory where trainees gained actual experience in organizing and supervising the aerial application of both fertilizers and pre-germinated seeds. In this process, they individually calculated application rates, calibrated the aircraft distribution equipment, loaded the aircraft and served as flagmen at the rice paddy during the application phase.

In the fourth month of the program, trainees in groups of 5 to 6 persons, accompanied by a training staff member, spent a week traveling in rural areas throughout the Philippines to acquaint themselves with national agricultural organizations, practical on-farm production practices and problems, rice production problems, and farmer attitudes. Upon their return to the Institute, a spokesman for each group reported their observation to the entire class.

Applied research as a medium for continued training

Fundamental concepts. In recent years, Institute scientists have been distributing to other scientists

around the world small samples of seed of new rice selections for trial. The senior staff has also been quick to circulate internationally through publications the newly developed rice technology. Once received in another country, the new technology must be evaluated carefully under local environmental conditions before it can be confidently recommended for farmer use. In some areas, this process of applied research, or field evaluation, has been slow. One of the reasons for this is the shortage of trained rice scientists to carry out the testing under varying environmental conditions.

Having received training in the process of quantitative evaluation of rice technology, graduates of the Institute-based RPTP are technically competent to contribute to the field evaluation of new rice technology within their home countries, regardless of whether their home organization is a research center, an extension agency, or an educational institution. Experience gained in the Philippines over the past 4 years shows that graduates of 6-month courses can be utilized effectively in nationwide programs of applied research involving new rice varieties, insecticides, cultural practices and fertilizer usage if the organization and support for such a program is sound.

As graduates of a training program return to their agencies, they are in need of a project which will challenge them in their new roles and which will allow them to continually keep abreast of changing technology. Such activities may be viewed as a continuation of training or post-graduate training for the graduates of an organized RPTP. Additionally, the competent rice specialist, regardless of the nature of his parent organization, becomes another set of eyes, hands, and legs for the rice researcher when the graduate involves himself in unified cooperative applied research field trials.

In general, there are too few rice research scientists available in most countries to personally undertake the necessary field evaluation trials away from their laboratories, but each year more trained extension rice specialists are becoming available who can be (and in some countries are already being) integrated into a national system of field evaluation. Overall guidance, planning, implementation, support and data processing nor-

mally would be undertaken by the agency having the primary responsibility for rice research. Rapid progress in translating rice research findings into farm practices will be made when technically competent rice specialists, regardless of their administrative organization, are fitted into nationwide systems of applied research and field evaluation. Such a system has been functioning in the Philippines in recent years and similar programs are being started or are underway in Indonesia, Vietnam and Ceylon where a number of Institute-trained rice specialists are participating in both training and applied research programs.

Follow-up of Institute-trained rice production specialists

Viewed as "alumni" of the Institute, graduates of the RPTP are kept informed at all times of new developments in the field of rice technology through correspondence, *The IRRI Reporter*, and other literature.

Emphasis is being placed on selecting candidates for rice production training whose governments have planned for their participation in a specific action program upon completion of training. In the past, some individuals completed 6 months of training at the Institute, but failed to find a productive function upon returning home. With increasing demands for rice production training, it is becoming more and more important to select the best qualified candidates, and only those whose role upon completion of training is well defined. Assurance must be given for continued support for conducting training and applied research programs.

Graduates of the 1967 RPTP returned to their homes or duty stations in December 1967, and in 1968 they began working to establish rice production training centers which would serve to train hundreds of their countrymen in the new rice technology.

The four Indonesian graduates of the Institute program conducted a 3-month rice production training program at the Central Agricultural Research Institute, Bogor, from February through April 1968 in which 30 extension workers and 5 researchers received both theoretical and practical training in the new technology. One member of the Office of Communication spent 2 weeks in Indonesia helping the trainers establish their pro-

gram. He again went to that country in late April to assist in the final phases of this training and to help design a series of insecticide applied research trials for graduates of the Bagor training program. By June 1968 the 30 extension men were back at their duty stations instructing farmers on how to increase their rice yields with the new varieties and proper management. Thirteen selected graduates of the Bagor training program supervised insecticide applied research trials. By the end of 1968, 115 trainees had graduated from the Bogor Rice Production Training Center, and yields of IR5 (Peta Baru 5) and IR8 (Peta Baru 8) in excess of 7,000 kg/ha were reported from several locations.

In Ceylon, the four 1967 Institute graduates began two extension teaching programs shortly after returning home. At Peradeniya, two of the men were assigned to the In-service Training Center, where they presented a series of 2-week rice production short courses for district agriculturists. The two other graduates were assigned to the Colombo area and conducted a large number of short training programs in different villages for local rice farmers. In all, several hundred Ceylonese government agriculturists and farmers received rice training during 1968 from the four graduates of the 1967 RPTP at the Institute. One member of the staff of the Office of Communication spent 3 weeks in Ceylon assisting the general development of the short course program in Peradeniya.

Two Filipinos from the Presidential Arm on Community Development and two U.S. Peace Corps volunteers participated in the 1967 RPTP at the Institute and upon graduation established in cooperation with the Bureau of Vocational Education a series of 2-week courses in rice production at the Baybay National Agricultural School at Siniloan, Laguna, Philippines. During 1968, members of numerous governmental and private organizations underwent training in rice production at Siniloan under the guidance of these four 1967 Institute graduates.

Upon graduating from the Institute program in December 1967, four Filipino members of the staff of the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines (UPCA) began teaching in the UPCA Rice Production Training Program. During 1968 they offered short courses in rice

production to 269 persons representing government agriculturists, community development workers, religious groups, military personnel, and farmers from the Philippines plus 39 Americans from the U.S. AID and International Volunteer Service organizations. Information concerning the UPCA rice production short courses spread quickly, and during the year a number of foreign trainees were admitted for training. In the second half of 1968, the UPCA rice production instructors began a 6-month RPTP with participants from several colleges of agriculture in the Philippines.

In West Pakistan, two rice production training centers were established in 1968 at Dokri and Kala Shah Kaku, and the four West Pakistani graduates of the Institute's 1967 RPTP began conducting short courses in rice production by April. Several hundred government agriculturists and farmers underwent training and immediately applied their new knowledge to bring about dramatic increases in rice yields during the 1968 crop season. At the request of the Government of Pakistan and the Ford Foundation in Pakistan, a member of the Office of Communication and a member of the IRRI experimental farm spent 3 weeks at each training site assisting the IRRI graduates in conducting their first training programs.

Two East Pakistani graduates of the 1967 RPTP established a series of 2-week courses in rice production at the Tejgon Farm near Dacca in April 1968 and trained a total of 201 agriculturists. The participants were from the Thana, Sub-Division, District and Deputy Director levels of organization. One member of the Office of Communication staff and one member of the UPCA staff (a graduate of the 1967 RPTP) were requested by the Pakistan government and the Ford Foundation in Pakistan to assist for 4 weeks at the Tejgon Farm training Center.

One American representing the University of Hawaii completed the Institute RPTP in November 1967 and returned home to establish a Rice Production Training Center near Kapaa on the island of Kauai, Hawaii, where persons (primarily Americans) going abroad on agricultural assignments could receive 2 weeks of training under conditions similar to those encountered in most of the rice-producing areas of the monsoon tropics.

Seed of nine rice varieties with divergent growth characteristics were obtained from the U.S. Department of Agriculture in Maryland and planted in observational plots at the Kauai Center to enable trainees to acquaint themselves with the different plant types of rice commonly encountered in the rice-producing areas of the world. The first 2-week training program began in March 1968 and included as trainees a group of Vietnamese agricultural officials and American representatives of the U. S. AID in Vietnam. Both field work and classroom discussions were used to teach production techniques and diagnostic skills. A water buffalo was furnished to permit participants to learn how soil is cultivated by the majority of farmers in Asia. Rice plants at all stages of growth from seedlings to mature plants ready for harvest were available in paddy-size plots as a result of regular plantings made every 2 weeks from November, 1967 to March, 1968. Trainees were able to practice all cultural operations from plowing to threshing during the 2-week course as a result of the timed plantings. During 1968 several other groups of trainees underwent rice production training at the Kauai Center, including American agricultural advisors enroute to their assignments with U.S. AID in Vietnam, American missionaries, Peace Corps Volunteers, and American agriculturists from the private sector. At the request of the University of Hawaii one member of the Office of Communication spent 4 weeks in Hawaii assisting in the establishment of the Center and was followed by one member of the Philippine Government's Agricultural Productivity Commission who had completed 12 months of training at the Institute in 1965.

Four of the Filipino trainees in the 1967 RPTP came from three Philippine colleges of agriculture. Upon graduation they returned to their institutions and organized short courses in rice production for staff members and students at their colleges or for farmers in nearby communities.

To furnish professional stimulation and an opportunity to engage in a rice project immediately upon return to their home organizations, the Institute provided the trainees from each of the colleges of agriculture with all the inputs required for the production of one-fourth hectare of IR8.

International Activities

This section briefly summarizes various activities of the Institute which are intended in one way or another to stimulate or to assist in rice research in other countries or regions. Increasingly, such activities have focused on research centers in other countries and while the work in progress is cooperative in one degree or another, the actual results are appropriately reported elsewhere. The intention here is to indicate the nature of the Institute's involvement and in some cases to cite high points of the results being obtained.

Presently the Institute participates in national research activities in several countries through a number of separate agreements which involve the country and a grant-making agency, with the Institute serving as a contractor or back-stopping agency responsible for various planning, staffing, training, and purchasing activities. As will be detailed later, such arrangements exist with Pakistan (both East and West), India and Ceylon. In addition, during 1968 the Institute was the recipient of two grants for carrying out similar activities in countries where more comprehensive formal agreements have not been entered into and where only short-term visits of IRRI staff are involved. The Institute also has been the direct recipient of a separate grant to enable it to undertake cooperative projects with various agencies in the Philippines, and it is specified as a principal collaborator in a grant for regional studies of the bacterial blight disease.

While the specific activities entered into vary from country to country, they generally include (a) training of young rice scientists at the Institute's research center or elsewhere, (b) research projects in which Institute staff cooperate as advisers or participants, (c) scientific conferences or symposia, and (d) travel of Institute staff as consultants to projects in the host country or as participants in conferences in the host country or elsewhere. In addition, the Institute is expected in certain instances to obtain the services of consultants not on its staff, to act as purchasing agent for certain items of scientific equipment, to assist in the planning and construction of research facilities, and to distribute rice literature to rice research workers.

For clarity in this summary, each grant or contract will be described in separate sections, but those activities which are thoroughly integrated regardless of source of funding or country of origin of the participants will be grouped together. The grants or contracts are listed in the time sequence in which they were undertaken. They are followed by descriptions of the more or less integrated activities of conferences and staff travel. Training, a separate integrated activity, is treated in detail elsewhere in this Annual Report.

East Pakistan

The first direct involvement of the Institute in a continuing program headquartered away from its Los Baños research center was established in East Pakistan in March, 1966. The Government of East Pakistan had decided to establish an accelerated rice research project which would be interdisciplinary in nature and which would undertake the research necessary for the rapid increase of rice production in the province. It was anticipated that particular attention would be given to a team approach in which varietal improvement, plant pathology, entomology, and agronomy would focus on factors limiting rice production and on means of modifying these factors. It was also expected that the accelerated rice project would establish linkages with the extension service and would promote the application of research results as soon as feasible. The Government of East Pakistan asked the Ford Foundation to assist them in this undertaking, and this led to the Ford Foundation grant which involved the Institute as the technical back-stopping agency.

East Pakistan has had a long history of rice research. In recent years, however, the research effort had been considerably reduced by the absence of an adequate research farm. In 1963 the main research station at Dacca was taken over as the site of the second capital of the nation and it was not possible to replace it with new land until 1967. In that year, however, the Government purchased an excellent area at Joydevpur, about 20 miles from the city of Dacca, and drew up general plans for the long-term development of the

The grant was specifically to provide training opportunities for young rice scientists, to test in Pakistan rice research results of the Institute, and to reinforce the local research facilities by the importation of certain equipment and supplies not locally available. Provisions were made for an Institute-employed scientist to be stationed in East Pakistan as an adviser to this project. The immediate objectives included the testing of varieties and advanced breeding selections of the Institute. The central theme of the Institute's involvement, however, was to assist in stimulating East Pakistan's own research efforts to meet the local needs as rapidly as possible.

site as a center for agricultural research with rice as one of its principal areas of investigation.

The first fields at the new Joydevpur site to become available for experimental purposes were released to the rice research group in January, 1968. At that time there were no buildings on the land, but it was possible for the rice research team to establish some provisional experimental plots. First to be planted at the Joydevpur site were breeding lines which had been tested earlier in nearby provisional experimental fields. This was in the dry season, locally known as the "boro" season. Inadequate water supply prevented extensive planting, however, until the main rainy season ("aman" season) which starts in June. During that season a large number of plantings were made. Also, during the boro season it was possible to continue experiments at some of the sub-stations and new breeding lines were tested, particularly at the Comilla sub-station.

East Pakistan is undoubtedly faced with some of the most challenging rice research problems encountered any place in tropical Asia. The climate is characterized by extremes in water availability. During the winter season, from about November until May, essentially no rain falls while during the period from June to November, the rainfall amounts to 60 to 70 inches. In addition to rain which falls directly in the rice-growing regions of East Pakistan, the inflow from rivers draining the rest of the province and more remote areas brings a large amount of water into the area. Consequently, flooding is a major problem. Water depths of 2 to 20 feet may affect as much as 60 percent of the rice-growing area in the aman season.

Unofficial estimates indicate that water control in East Pakistan may be adequate to permit the growing of short, stiff-strawed, highly responsive varieties on perhaps 7 million out of the 23 million acres planted to rice in East Pakistan. During the rainy season, varieties for the remaining acreage will have to be modified to adapt to the water situation.

In addition to creating problems of water control, the high humidity arising from this general climatic pattern is conducive to a build-up of insect pests and diseases. At present, bacterial blight and a tungro-like virus with a *Nephotettix*

vector present major problems in the introduction of an improved variety for the aman season.

In addition to major fluctuations in rainfall, the climate of East Pakistan is characterized by relatively extreme temperatures for a location of this latitude. The months of November, December and January are cool with night-time minimum temperatures in the low 50's being common and with temperatures in the 40's encountered occasionally. By contrast, temperatures in May range from the 70's at night to the 90's in the daytime. Both of these extremes, but particularly the low temperatures that may occur in the winter, create special problems for some varieties. Quite possibly, the crossing of locally adapted, cold-resistant lines with high-yielding types from abroad may be required before optimum results can be obtained.

The three-way agreement among the Government of East Pakistan, the Ford Foundation and the Institute was modified in 1968 to call for a second rice adviser. It continued along the same lines as far as training, short-term consultancies, study tours for officials, and the procurement of supplies and equipment were concerned.

The principal rice adviser posted in East Pakistan by the Institute is trained in agronomy and the decision was made for the second adviser to be an entomologist. The entomologist reported for regular duty in September, 1968.

In November, 1967 the Ford Foundation made a separate grant to the Institute to assist over a 2 year period in developing rice research facilities at the Joydevpur farm which, as mentioned earlier, had been purchased by the Government of Pakistan as a major research center. The grant provides principally for the purchase of equipment, supplies and materials not available in East Pakistan, plus certain architectural and engineering services. Plans were fully drawn for these developments during the first half of 1968 and by the end of the year most of the projected building was in progress. When completed these facilities should provide a very efficient physical unit for rice research.

A number of short-term consultancies were provided during 1968. These included brief visits (detailed elsewhere) by the director, the associate director, the plant breeder, the plant physiologist, and visiting plant physiologist. Two assignments,

each of 2 months duration, were made in the area of rice production training wherein an assistant rice production specialist of the Institute staff worked directly with the rice production training program of East Pakistan for 2 months, followed by Mr. Diosdado Castro from the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, whose services were engaged by the Institute. The virus disease problems were given special attention by a 3-month assignment of an assistant plant pathologist of the Institute staff and another 3-month assignment of Dr. Guillermo Galvez, virus specialist from the Instituto Colombiano Agropecuario.

During 1968 a total of 12 East Pakistan rice technicians studied at the Institute for varying periods. The subject matter areas involved included plant pathology, entomology, agronomy, farm management, rice production training and field experimentation with rice. Several persons participated in a general workshop on rice research techniques. In addition, one East Pakistan scientist continued to study for the Ph.D. degree in the United States.

A number of agricultural officials from East Pakistan made official study visits to the research center at Los Baños, as follows: Dr. Amirul Islam, Director of Agriculture, East Pakistan and Dr. A. Alim, Chief Economic Botanist, East Pakistan Directorate of Agriculture, attended the rice research conference held at the Institute on April 8-11. In early July, Mr. A. M. Anisuzzaman, TPK, C.S.P., Director, E.P.A.D.C.; Mr. Enam Ahmed Chowdhury, C.S.P., Deputy Chief, Agriculture Planning Department; Mr. K. G. Mohiuddin, Deputy Director of Agriculture; and Mr. A. Samand, Deputy Director of Agriculture, Rajahahi, observed the work of the Institute and called on Philippine national agencies. Later in the same month Mr. A.K.M. Ahsan, C.S.P., Chairman, E.P.A.D.C.; Mr. A. M. Chowdhury, Additional Director of Agriculture (Training); Mr. Syed Serajul Islam, Deputy Director of Agriculture, Khulna Division; and Mr. I. H. Khan, Additional Director of Agriculture (Research), made similar visits. In November Mr. Karim Iqbal, Secretary of Agriculture, East Pakistan, visited the Institute for an intensive series of conferences on rice research and development.

West Pakistan

In September, 1966 an agreement was reached among the Government of West Pakistan, the Ford Foundation and the Institute to undertake a co-operative rice research project in West Pakistan. The general objectives of this project were similar to those of the project established somewhat earlier in East Pakistan, namely, (1) to assist in the training of young rice scientists, (2) to advise in the development of the research project through the resident adviser, (3) to procure equipment and supplies not available in West Pakistan, (4) to provide short-term consultancies from the staff of the Institute or other places, and (5) to arrange study tours of the Institute for West Pakistan officials.

Rice is not the predominant cereal in West Pakistan that it is in East Pakistan, but nevertheless it is an important part of the overall agricultural output of the province. Some 3.5 million acres are planted to rice each year in West Pakistan. Of these, about 2.6 million acres are planted to the so-called coarse rices and the remainder is planted to the Basmati type. For years West Pakistan has exported significant quantities of Basmati rice and usually has had a modest surplus of coarse rices. Basmati rice has been shipped primarily to the markets in the Middle East while the small quantity of coarse rice has been sold in East Pakistan.

The climatic conditions in West Pakistan are extremely different from those in East Pakistan. The Central Region of West Pakistan receives an annual rainfall of 20 to 22 inches, while the Southern Region receives only 2 to 3 inches. Water for rice-growing comes primarily from the Indus River and the complex pattern of irrigation facilities which it provides. Because of its northerly location, only one crop of rice a year can be grown in West Pakistan. The conditions under which this crop is grown, however, are extremely favorable for high yield. Specific data are not available, but sunlight intensity is very high and, during the ripening period, the crop is exposed to almost cloud-free weather. While traditionally rice yields have not been high in West Pakistan, the physical environment for high yields exists and with appropriate, properly-handled varieties, world record yields may be produced.

The primary focus of the Institute's agreement with the Ford Foundation in West Pakistan has been upon assisting in the development of the rice research organization and facilities of the province. As part of its overall drive to increase food supply, however, the Government in 1966 asked the research group to take a close look at IRRI varieties and selections to determine if they could be of some immediate use. Basically, because of the good environmental conditions, these early trials of IRRI varieties and selections in West Pakistan were highly successful, with some very good yields being obtained. In 1967 some 76 tons of IR8 seed were imported from the Philippines and 14 tons were obtained from East Pakistan. This seed was distributed to a large number of cultivators throughout West Pakistan to test the variety and to increase seed. This variety was grown on some 10,000 acres, and the average yield was 63 maunds per acre as compared to about 27 maunds traditionally obtained. In 1968 the Government of West Pakistan named IR8 "IRRI-Pak" and a target of one million acres of this variety was set. While this target was not achieved, it is estimated that 850,000 acres were actually planted to IR8 in the province in 1968, one of the most dramatic increases in varietal usage that have been recorded. In three seasons (1966-1968) this variety moved from test plots to something more than 25 percent of the total rice acreage in West Pakistan.

When it became evident that the results would justify moving directly with the introduction of IR8, considerable emphasis was placed upon the training of rice production specialists in West Pakistan. In the first instance this training was done cooperatively by IRRI staff who went to West Pakistan to work with local authorities. Several of the local extension staff were then brought to IRRI for rice production training in the 6-month class held in 1967. In 1968 they were back on the job in West Pakistan and offered refresher courses and short courses to practically all of the field extension workers known locally as "agricultural assistants" and "field assistants." Nearly 1,000 extension workers thus received training in the use and management of high-yielding rice varieties.

In planning for the acceleration of rice research in West Pakistan the Government officials have

decided to focus upon two principal rice research stations, one at Kala-Shah Kaku near Lahore and the other near Dokri in the southern region.

Because of its dry, sunny climate, disease problems in West Pakistan are far less acute than in most other rice-growing regions. Historically there have been occasional serious outbreaks of the rice blast disease but other than that, the disease picture looks extremely favorable.

The principal insect problem in West Pakistan is the rice stem borers. These insects can at times cause devastating damage and are a serious threat throughout the province and during the entire rice-growing season.

Some salinity problems are encountered in the rice-growing regions of West Pakistan. Other soils problems are also found, e.g., nitrogen response, which is almost universal. Zinc deficiency has recently been identified in cooperative work under this project and sizable field responses have been obtained.

While the environmental conditions of West Pakistan favor rapid progress and permit the direct introduction of varieties which might not be so easily used in less favored regions, the need for a strong local rice research effort cannot be over-emphasized. As West Pakistan moves into a strongly surplus position in rice supply, it will be looking toward export markets. The world trade in rice is a highly competitive business and only through careful attention to highly efficient production can consistently good returns be expected. Special rices such as Basmati will require special breeding which cannot be done elsewhere because of interactions of Basmati quality and climate.

During 1968 the rice adviser from the Institute staff who had been on assignment in West Pakistan since the beginning of the agreement accepted a position with the Ford Foundation in Indonesia and a replacement was obtained. The present rice adviser went on duty in August. His training is in soil science and he is expected to be particularly useful in helping solve some of the soil problems of West Pakistan.

During the year, 10 West Pakistan trainees studied at the research center in Los Baños and one continued to work toward the Ph.D. degree in soil chemistry in the United States. The fields of specialization of the IRRI trainees were entomology, plant pathology, varietal improvement,

agronomy, and general rice experimentation techniques. West Pakistan had more participants than any other area in the rice experimentation workshop held at the Institute in 1968. Five members of the Dokri and Kala-Shah Kaku staff participated in this course.

During 1968 officials from the agricultural agencies of West Pakistan visited the Institute under the auspices of this project. Mr. Ch. Mohammad Shafi, Rice Botanist, Kala-Shah Kaku Rice Station, attended the rice research conference held in April. Three agricultural directors from West Pakistan, Messrs. Shafi Gil, Mohamed Sharif, and Malik Fazeldad Khan familiarized themselves with the Institute's program. On November 11 and 12 the Central Minister of Agriculture, Mr. A. H. M. Shamsud Doha, together with the Secretary of Agriculture, Mr. Yamin Qureshi, observed the research activities at IRRI and discussed plans for research throughout Pakistan.

India

Participation of the Institute in cooperative rice research activities in India involves a three-way agreement with the Government of India and the United States Agency for International Development (U.S. AID). The All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) serves as the focal point for Institute cooperation. The AICRIP is an Indian agency founded in 1965 by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) to coordinate rice research throughout the nation. It is so constituted that it can potentially bring together research workers throughout India and in all of the various agencies within the country which are in one way or the other responsible for rice research. It is also ideally situated to serve as a coordination center for testing materials from abroad or in otherwise entering into international cooperative work. The Rockefeller Foundation has participated in the work of the AICRIP since its inception and one of its staff members has been named by the ICAR as joint coordinator of the AICRIP.

While the Institute had a number of informal ties with the AICRIP earlier, it was not until July, 1967 that a formal agreement was reached for IRRI to participate on a continuing basis. This

participation was made possible by an agreement between the Government of India and the U.S. AID wherein the latter would undertake to contract with the Institute to provide certain services. Through this contract the Institute has been able to employ four senior staff members for long-term assignment in India. It is also funded to provide up to 12 man-months per year of short-term consultancies. These may be members of the Institute staff from its research center in the Philippines or persons from other centers engaged for specific assignment to India. To assist in the implementation of this contract, The Rockefeller Foundation assigned to the Institute its staff member who is joint coordinator of the AICRIP and he now acts as the team leader for the Institute's group of scientists and consultants.

Training of young rice scientists is an integral part of the agreement between the Institute and the AICRIP. Provisions have been made wherein as much as 6 man-years of training can be given each year to individuals selected from the AICRIP group of cooperators within India. This training is to be given at the Los Baños center of the Institute and can cover all of the research fields in which the Institute is engaged. The project agreement also provides for certain equipment and supplies and for the temporary employment of new Indian staff members of the AICRIP. For items to be purchased in India under this agreement the team leader and joint coordinator is principally responsible, while for purchases of equipment and supplies abroad, the Institute is to act as the purchasing agent. The agreement also calls for the Government of India to construct certain minimal facilities for the research activities at the coordination center in India.

The four IRRI staff scientists who work full time under the AICRIP are in the fields of agronomy, plant pathology, plant physiology and entomology. They have participated as active members of the AICRIP research team and the results of their work are presented in the fully integrated AICRIP semi-annual reports.

Only three training participants have so far been sent to the Philippines under the AICRIP/IRRI/U.S. AID agreement, but funds provided to the Institute by The Rockefeller and Ford Foundations have made it possible to train Indian scientists both from the AICRIP and other

agencies. Training has been provided, not only in research fields, but also in the area of rice production, training and extension. During 1968 a total of 21 Indian students participated in various training programs at the Institute for a total of 11 man-years.

India under the project in 1967 returned for a 2-week period in October-November 1968 to study virus problems in West Bengal and to assess the research programs underway on insects and diseases.

In April, Dr. S. V. S. Shastry, coordinator of the AICRIP, and Dr. S. Y. Padmanabhan, director of the CRRRI, came to the Institute to attend the international meetings. They reviewed the work of their respective agencies. The joint coordinator and team leader in India also attended this meeting to review team activities and to participate in the overall program. In September the consultant bacteriologist who had been in India for 2 months stayed at the Institute for a week together with the plant pathologist member of the IRRI/AICRIP team.

Consultants sent by the Institute to India during 1968 included Dr. Masao Goto, a rice bacteriologist who spent 8 weeks in August-September in active research on problems associated with bacterial leaf blight. The Institute's virologist and its entomologist who were members of the disease-insect survey team which went to

Philippines

Most of the research of the Institute has some degree of application in the Philippines. The overall objectives, of course, are to investigate the problems of increasing rice production on a world-wide basis rather than to concentrate on the factors limiting production in the Philippines. Because of its location, however, it is possible for the staff of the Institute to work rather more directly in activities of the national research and extension agencies of the Philippines than they can do in other countries. In May, 1967 a grant was received from the Ford Foundation to assist in the implementation of such cooperative work in the Philippines. As in other country programs of the Institute, training represented a major portion of the undertaking. In addition, however, emphasis was placed on cooperative research at the national

research centers and in farmer's fields.

Cooperative experiments were conducted at the research centers with long-term responsibility for rice research. In many instances the cooperator at the national agency was a former Institute scholar or had participated in cooperative activities with the Institute. Generally, it was possible to enter into these cooperative tests with little formality. Likewise, it was possible for Institute staff members at all levels to engage directly in the execution of various phases of the work. The results are summarized in other sections of the annual report, but general areas of activities are mentioned in the following paragraphs.

In 1968 cooperative experiments in agronomy were conducted at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Central Luzon, at the Bicol Rice and Corn Experiment Station in Camarines Sur, at the Visayas Rice Experiment Station in Iloilo City, and at Central Mindanao University in Musuan, Mindanao. These experiments tested the growth characteristics, disease and lodging susceptibility, and yield potential of promising Institute selections under high levels of nitrogen, and evaluated herbicides for transplanted rice under a wide range of soil and climatic conditions. In other experiments, the sources of fertilizer phosphorus for flooded rice were evaluated.

In varietal improvement, promising Institute selections were grown at the Maligaya center and at the Bicol station. Entries from the program of the Bureau of Plant Industry, new lines as well as standard checks such as Peta and BPI-76, were included. Materials of different growth duration were given attention in some of these tests. In the 1968 wet season a nursery of breeding lines under specific test for bacterial leaf blight disease was grown in cooperative tests in the Philippines.

Experiments in entomology were conducted at the Maligaya center and at the Visayas station. Besides differing in geographic location and climatic conditions, these sites have the advantage of making possible the testing of materials against rice stem borers species that differ from those found at the Los Baños research center. The predominant species at the Maligaya center is the yellow rice stem borer, *Tryporyza incertulas*; at the Institute's research center, the striped borer, *Chilo suppressalis*; and in Iloilo, the white stem borer, *Tryporyza innotata*. Thus, the experimental

results obtained at these two stations of the Bureau of Plant Industry strongly supplemented the results obtained at the Institute. Entomological tests included comparisons of insecticides and of varietal resistance to stem borers.

At a somewhat different level from the established research center, there is a need to conduct cooperative trials to test the validity of a new practice or material under farmer's field conditions throughout the region in which they may be used. As a part of its cooperative work in the Philippines, the Institute established such applied research trials in cooperation with the Agricultural Productivity Commission (the Philippine extension service) and the Bureau of Plant Industry. Other agencies such as the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture and other colleges of agriculture participated in various ways, either in the actual execution of the work or in its coordination. Private agri-business and private rice producers made significant contributions.

In this project, in advance of a given crop season, meetings are held with the staff scientists responsible for the original experimentation which is to be tested in farmer's fields. Plans are drawn up for the inclusion of appropriate treatments in the tests, and materials to be evaluated are selected. A written plan is then prepared for each separate project. Once coordinated with the Institute's scientific staff and officials of cooperating Philippine agencies, detailed instructions for participating personnel are drawn up. The plan is mimeographed and distributed to the persons conducting the trials. This write-up serves as a guide for the uniform collection of data from uniformly conducted experiments.

Based on the agreed-upon experimental plan the required seeds, fertilizers, insecticides, herbicides, and other materials are packaged in plastic containers in the exact amounts needed for an individual trial. These materials are then shipped to the cooperators throughout the country.

The kinds of data to be collected are specified in the uniform plan and printed data collection forms are furnished in kits containing fertilizers and other materials. At the end of the season a copy of the data sheet is sent to the Institute for statistical analysis. Another copy remains with the cooperator for ready reference. After the statistical analysis, the results are studied by the

Institute scientist whose field is concerned in the particular project and by scientists in the same discipline in the cooperating agency.

Several hundred tests of this type are carried out each year. These have included studies of fertilizers, varieties, insecticides, herbicides and stand establishment, and have involved at least 10 cooperating agencies. IR8 was grown in uniform variety trials in nine provinces, and IR5 in 20 provinces over four seasons before they were named as varieties.

Results have contributed to a better understanding of the rates of fertilizer required, and the returns which may be expected by the farmer. In the 1967 dry season, for example, tests showed that maximum yields of IR8 were obtained when 100 kg/ha N were used. At this level a benefit-cost ratio of 7 to 1 was obtained.

Insecticide trials have tended to support the results obtained in the Institute fields as regard the use of diazinon and lindane. In the 1968 trials the average yield losses resulting from failure to control insects amounted to about 1,500 kg/ha.

At the end of 1968 the Institute and the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture were joining forces in the planning and supervision of an expanded nationwide network of trials under this program. The Agricultural Productivity Commission, the Bureau of Plant Industry, the Bureau of Soils, the Bureau of Prisons, and private rice growers are all cooperating in this series.

During 1968 there were nine Philippine participants in the 6-month-long rice production training course. In the same year 19 research scholars and fellows spent 12 man-years in research training. The numbers involved in rice production training in 1968 were sharply down from those in earlier classes. This was due to the establishment of a training center at the UPCA which is specifically designed to provide continuing training of this type for Philippine participants. The development of these facilities permitted the Institute to expand the number of trainees accepted from other countries in 1968.

Ceylon

In mid-1967 discussions among the Government of Ceylon, the Ford Foundation, and the Institute

resulted in an agreement wherein the Foundation would provide a grant in support of rice research in Ceylon. Under this grant the Institute is the back-stopping agency and is responsible for working out training programs, providing advice on the development of research activities, and obtaining certain equipment not available in Ceylon. Under this agreement a research adviser is to be provided by the Institute for residence in Ceylon.

To fill the requirement for a resident consultant, the agronomist from the Institute's regular staff undertook a 2-year assignment in Ceylon beginning in September, 1967. To familiarize himself with Ceylon conditions he started almost immediately on a program of field research in agronomy in cooperation with the Ceylon Agricultural Research Institute at Peradeniya where he makes his headquarters. Most of the studies undertaken were simple experiments with the objective of examining the yield potential of short, lodging-resistant varieties under Ceylon conditions. Others dealt with insects and weed control procedures with particular regard to the new varieties. This orientation was established at the request of the Deputy Director of Research of the Ceylon Ministry of Agriculture, who expressed a desire to have the new varietal type tested under the direction of a person experienced with it.

Results of these tests are more appropriately reported elsewhere and will not be given here. It should be indicated, however, that generally promising results were obtained with these introductions. As might be expected, results were considerably more favorable in certain parts of the country than in others. Thus, in four dry zone test locations, IR8 averaged over 6,000 kg/ha at the top level of fertilization. Because of a complexity of soil, disease and insect factors, results at the **two wet zone stations were considerably lower** with an average yield of 3,600 kg/ha. The data indicate that IR8, which is highly nitrogen responsive elsewhere, was likewise more responsive to fertilization under Ceylon conditions than the standard local varieties. At all locations IR8 yielded about 20 percent more than H-4, a Ceylon standard. The superiority of IR8 over H-4 was noted at all nitrogen levels. IR8 was superior to IR5 in both wet and dry zone locations. As a result of these data the Ceylon Agricultural

Research Institute recommended that IR8 be added to the list of varieties to be used by Ceylon farmers in the dry zone.

By the end of 1968, which corresponded approximately with the first year of the resident consultant's stay in Ceylon, equipment and other research needs at key rice stations in Ceylon had been identified and significant amounts of these had been ordered under the project. It was also possible at this point to start preparation of plans for longer range participation and to identify areas in which the Institute can help Ceylon in its program to attain full rice self-sufficiency. Such assistance may take the form of participation in extension training activities as well as in the research phases.

Returned graduates from the Institute's rice production training program have offered short courses in modern rice technology, several of which were considered to be outstandingly successful. The rice farmers and government technicians who attended these courses quickly picked up the new information and appear to be making good use of it.

On the research side it appears that the Institute's participation should focus most strongly on those regions of the country where soil and climatic conditions tend to favor high rice yields and major responses to increased inputs.

In general, there appeared to be ready acceptance of new varieties and new techniques of obtaining high yields. Provided appropriate incentives are available and practices are adjusted to meet local requirements, there seems good likelihood that Ceylon rice cultivators can be counted on to obtain significantly higher yields over the next few years.

During the first year of implementation of the project, 16 persons from Ceylon were sent abroad under the grant on either training or travel awards. Three of these were candidates for the Bachelor of Science degree at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture. Four officers completed the rice production training program and one was sent to the University of the Philippines and the Institute for course work and research leading to the M.S. degree. Two graduate programs are underway in the United States. Two junior research officers of the Directorate of Agriculture attended the short course on field experimentation with rice

held at the Institute in 1968. The Deputy Director (Research) and the botanist of the Ceylon Agricultural Research Institute attended the international project reviews held in the Philippines in April, 1968. Later in the year, the Deputy Director (Extension) and the Director of Agriculture visited the Institute in connection with the implementation of the grant, and to observe the program of the Institute.

Thailand

The Institute does not have a formal agreement with the Government of Thailand on cooperative rice research but has conducted informal cooperative investigations almost since its founding. In recent years, such undertakings have benefited from an agreement between the Thai Government's Rice Department and The Rockefeller Foundation wherein the latter has stationed a staff scientist in Thailand to participate actively in rice research, particularly varietal improvement. The exchange of materials and ideas has been facilitated by this action and it has been possible to identify areas of mutual interest more rapidly. The selection of candidates for training has also been facilitated.

Thailand is, of course, a rice surplus nation and as such gains considerable foreign exchange through rice exports. The need to focus on rice quality of the type Thailand's export trade is known for places certain special restrictions on the rice breeder. He cannot accept a high-yielding strain of divergent grain quality quite as easily as the breeder who has only his local market preferences to assess. Deep water problems in certain areas and seasons also prevent the Thai farmers from accepting new short-statured strains which might be otherwise suitable.

In spite of these limitations, the Thailand Rice Department is moving strongly ahead with varietal improvement as well as with work in the supporting fields of agronomy, plant pathology, and entomology. Attention is given to breeding high-yielding rices of traditional Thai quality and also special-purpose ones such as the glutinous types. Disease and insect resistance is receiving special attention and efforts are being made to shorten

the growth duration of varieties to be used in parts of the country which have lower rainfall. Many of these tests include materials from the Institute's breeding program and valuable information about their performance is being obtained.

Colombia

The Rockefeller Foundation has assigned a senior plant breeder to the Centro Interamericano de Agricultura Tropical in Colombia (CIAT) to take leadership in its inter-American rice improvement program. This serves as the principal direct liaison between the Institute and Latin American rice research programs. Exchange of breeding materials has been encouraged, but equally important has been the interchange of ideas. Currently one of the most serious problems of rice growing in some parts of Latin America appears to be the rice blast disease. A world-wide effort to evaluate the potential of developing field resistance to this disease has been proposed as an approach to solving the problem. This proposal, arising with the CIAT rice breeder, would mobilize cooperative studies throughout the world and typifies the sort of activity that can be fostered by international cooperation, properly focused.

Indonesia

Late in 1968 the Ford Foundation placed an experienced rice scientist on its staff to serve as an adviser on rice research affairs and to act as liaison contact with the Institute and Indonesian research centers. Indonesia is presently mounting an intensive drive for national self-sufficiency in rice. Sustained activity in this direction will require a strong and continuing research effort and it is hoped that the Institute will be able to increase its contribution in this regard.

Other Countries

Separate grants from the Ford and Rockefeller foundations were available in 1968 in support of activities in countries in which no specific agreement on cooperative work existed either directly with the Institute or with either foundation. In general these funds made some degree of cooperative activities possible in essentially any developing rice-growing country or with any

interested institution within these countries.

Training was again an important component of this activity. Under this program a total of 49 trainees, scholars and fellows from 12 countries came to the Institute and received a total of 21 man-years of training. The details of these awards are given in the training section of this report.

Cooperative research in non-project countries was fostered through modest funds provided under these grants. Among these activities was the continuation of a survey of nutritional disturbance of the rice plant in Asia, centered at Hokkaido University. Certain equipment were supplied to a plant pathology laboratory, of Shizuoka University, Japan, in support of bacterial leaf blight studies throughout Asia, and other items were provided to the virus laboratory of Hokkaido University which has contributed materially to the characterization of tungro and other virus diseases of Southeast Asia. Modest funds were provided in support of electron microscope studies of the blast disease of Academia Sinica, Taiwan. Cooperative testing in Taiwan, India and Thailand of the mechanical drum thresher developed at the Institute was partially supported by funds from this grant. A preliminary cooperative study was initiated in Indonesia on varietal resistance to the rice gall midge.

Major support to technical conferences was provided by funds from these two grants. The Mekong Conference was fully funded from this source and all observers from non-project countries at the Institute's international project reviews were sponsored in this way. Both of these conferences are described elsewhere in this report.

Rice literature was supplied to scientists throughout the rice-growing world using funds provided in these two general grants. Publication of a general text on rice diseases was supported by the grant through purchase of copies of the text for similar distribution to key rice research centers in developing countries.

International Conferences

Two international conferences were held at the Institute in 1968. These were not symposia of the type held in earlier years and which involved specialists in closely defined subject matter areas; rather they brought together workers from a

number of fields and from various countries to discuss current rice research on a rather broad basis. Funding for both meetings was provided by the Ford and Rockefeller Foundation grants in support of international activities and by the country projects described earlier.

The first conference was held in April and focused on international cooperation. It was viewed as the first of a continuing series of meetings which would periodically bring together key staff of the various cooperative projects plus observers from other rice research centers to exchange ideas and draw plans for future work. The participants came from Ceylon, Colombia, Pakistan (East and West), India, Thailand, and the Philippines, and the observers were from Australia, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Taiwan, India, Malaysia and the Philippines.

These meetings, called "International Rice Research Project Reviews", covered the Institute's own research, and Institute scientists reviewed their work in all fields. The participants from other countries also reviewed their work although in less detail, and some of the observers summarized the research interests and activities in their countries. The meetings were very useful in providing new avenues for exchange of information and ideas. It was felt, however, that more attention to problems of particular importance would be preferred to such broad general coverage. It was decided that a second meeting with the same general base of participation would be held in 1969, but that there would be no attempt to review all activities in depth; instead the focus would be on four or five major topics. In general, these would include varietal improvement plus reviews of two or three major insect pests and diseases. Review of activities and prospects of breeding for disease and insect resistance would receive equal attention in the next series of meetings with breeding for production capacity and quality. Participating plant pathologists and entomologists would be asked to review both basic and applied aspects of the particular problem being brought up for discussion. Lesser attention would be given to other areas of science related to the rice plant and its environment, but similar attention in depth would be planned for these subjects in future years.

In October, the Institute cooperated with the

Mekong Committee of the Economic Commission for Asia and the Far East (ECAFE) in holding a conference on rice production with special emphasis on the riparian countries of the Mekong basin. The objectives were to review the research findings of the Institute and of riparian countries, to consider procedures for instituting a basin-wide applied rice research program, to enable riparian technicians to observe progressive rice production practices, and to consider means of introducing research findings to extension workers and farmers.

The participants came from Laos, Vietnam and Thailand and observers were present from Burma. Reviews of Institute research were presented by appropriate staff scientists and special topics were discussed by FAO experts and University of the Philippines College of Agriculture staff. Participants from the riparian countries and co-operating FAO personnel reviewed rice research activities and needs, and described plans for increasing rice production in the region.

International Travel

Travel of the senior staff to other rice-growing countries continues to be an important means of keeping the Institute in close contact with developments in the rice-growing regions of the world. Information is obtained on problems encountered in other regions, on work in progress, and on needs for further action. Research scholars are identified and interviewed on these trips, and follow-up assistance may be provided to them following their return. Cooperative projects may be established or serviced by visits of Institute staff or they may act as consultants to national programs. Increasingly, requests have been received for Institute staff to review for other agencies the steps followed in organizing the Institute's research efforts as well as to describe the results obtained.

In April the associate agronomist went to Indonesia to visit the cooperative soil fertility experiments. In August he attended the Ninth International Soil Science Congress in Adelaide where he presented a paper entitled, "Efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen (N^{15} -labelled) for flooded rice." On the same trip he visited the Coastal Plains Research Station near Darwin and the

Kimberley Research Station in Kunnunura, Western Australia, to review the rice research program in tropical Australia. Later, he visited the CSIRO headquarters in Canberra to review his observations on rice research with the officials concerned. Part of his visit was sponsored by the CSIRO Australia.

In November the visiting weed scientist went to South Vietnam to advise on weed control problems there.

The chemist attended the Joint Meeting of the American Association of Cereal Chemists and the American Oil Chemists Society on March 31 to April 4 in Washington, D. C., U. S. A. and presented a paper on the protein screening of the IRRI world collection and another on rice starch. He visited the Western Regional Research Laboratory at Albany, California, enroute to this meeting. He then took study leave from April to December at the Plant Research Laboratory, Michigan State University, and did research on enzymic degradation of starch in germinating pea cotyledons with Dr. Joseph E. Varner. He later visited the Southern Regional Research Laboratory in New Orleans, Instituto de Nutricion de Centro America y Panama (INCAP) in Guatemala City, and the Protein Quality Laboratory, Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maiz y Trigo (CIMMYT) in Chapingo, Mexico, enroute to Manila.

The entomologist went to Indonesia in April for 1 week to acquaint himself with research on rice entomology and to observe the general rice insect pest problem in the country. In October he acted as consultant to the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project in a survey of insect infestations of the rice crop.

The plant pathologist attended the First International Congress of Plant Pathology held in London in July. In November he visited Thailand to discuss rice disease problems.

The associate pathologist went to London in July to attend the First International Congress of Plant Pathology. In October, at the request of the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, he visited New Delhi, Calcutta, Chinsurah, Barasat, Gaighata, Bongaon, Ranaghat, Cuttack and Rajendranagar to observe the incidence of virus diseases of rice in India and to consult on research related to these diseases.

In February the economist visited Thailand and Malaysia to confer with professional colleagues at Kasetsart University and the University of Malaya. In June he attended the meetings of the FAO Regional Commission on Farm Management for Asia and the Far East held in Thailand, and in August and September he attended the annual meeting of the American Agricultural Economics Association in Bozeman, Montana and the International Seminar on Change in Agriculture in Reading, England.

In February the principal rice breeder went to East Pakistan to observe cold injury and virus infection in breeding lines supplied by the Institute. In March he went to Thailand to discuss rice breeding methods at a conference held by the Rice Breeding Section of the Thailand Rice Department. In August and September he went to Ceylon, Indonesia and Malaysia to confer with rice research personnel, to review breeding objectives, and to arrange to send IRRI breeding lines to these countries in support of their breeding program. In September he went to Korea and East Pakistan to observe breeding lines sent there and to observe the severe virus infections found in East Pakistan. In October he travelled to both the West and East provinces of Pakistan to examine the IRRI breeding lines being grown at the Dokri and Kala Shah Kaku stations in West Pakistan and at the Comilla and Joydevpur stations in East Pakistan. In November he presented a paper on rice breeding progress at the American Society of Agronomy in New Orleans and attended a protein conference held in New York by The Rockefeller Foundation.

In August the second plant breeder attended the Fourth FAO/IAEA Coordinated Program in the Use of Induced Mutations in Rice Breeding at Hiratsuka, Japan, and the International Genetics Congress held in Tokyo. In September to October, in connection with his home leave, he visited rice growing areas and rice experiment stations in South India and, in December, he went to Thailand to take notes on Institute breeding materials and to visit the rice experiment stations of the country.

In March the geneticist participated in the 12th meeting of the U. S. Rice Technical Working Group held at New Orleans, Louisiana. In August he attended the 12th International Congress of Genetics in Tokyo. He also attended the annual

meeting of the American Society of Agronomy held in New Orleans in November while on study leave at the North Carolina State University at Raleigh.

During 1968 the rice production specialist and the rice production technician spent 2 weeks in South Vietnam studying rice production matters in the country at the request of the Vietnamese Minister of Agriculture and Land Reform and the U.S. AID. In May he again visited Vietnam briefly to interview candidates for the rice production training program (RPTP) and selected two men and two women as participants. In November he returned to Vietnam to discuss working assignments for the four trainees after completion of their training. In January and February he visited Ceylon to meet with the four Ceylonese graduates of the 1967 Institute rice production training program and to observe rice production in that country. In March he attended the meetings of the Rice Technical Working Group in New Orleans and visited briefly with officials of the University of Hawaii Rice Production Training Center on plans for establishing a 2-week rice production training program. During a visit to Indonesia in April he consulted with the four Indonesian graduates of the 1967 RPTP about their work and conferred with officers of the Indonesian Air Force on the use of agricultural aircraft in rice production. In October he travelled to Laos to discuss the proposed utilization of two trainees from Laos in the 1968 RPTP following completion of their training. He attended the annual meetings of the American Society of Agronomy in New Orleans in November where he presented two papers, and stopped briefly in Hawaii to discuss recent developments within the University of Hawaii Rice Production Training Center.

Rice production technicians and rice production specialists of the Office of Communication during the first half of the year travelled to Hawaii, Ceylon, Indonesia, East Pakistan, and West Pakistan in support of rice production training programs being conducted by graduates of the IRRI-based RPTP.

The associate statistician attended the Second Session of the FAO Asia and Far East Commission on Agricultural Statistics held in New Delhi, India in December.

The plant physiologist attended the annual

meeting of the Society of the Science of Soil and Manure in Japan in early April. In July-August he spent 30 days in West Pakistan, Thailand, Malaysia and India to observe nutritional disorders of the rice plant. In September he attended the Eleventh Session of the FAO IRC Working Party on Rice Soils, Water and Fertilizer Practices held in Ceylon. In October he returned to West Pakistan to attend a rice seminar at the Kala Shah Kaku Rice Experiment Station near Lahore and to report on his studies of soil problems encountered there.

The associate plant physiologist was on study leave at the University of California Davis, during most of 1968. During his stay in the United States he attended the meeting of the American Institute of Biological Sciences at College Station, Texas (August 23-September 4, 1967), and the meeting of the Rice Technical Working Group in New Orleans, Louisiana (March 4-March 8, 1968.) At the latter meeting he presented a paper entitled "Effect of high night temperature on the developing leaves and panicle."

In April the agricultural engineer travelled to Japan to present a paper before the Japan Society of Agricultural Machinery and to visit agricultural machinery research institutions. In September he went to Ceylon to give a paper at the International Rice Commission meeting and while enroute he visited several rice research centers in India and Thailand. He went to the United States in December to present a paper before the American Society of Agricultural Engineers and to confer with U.S. AID on the farm mechanization contract.

The visiting agricultural economist on mechanization presented a paper at the Society of Agricultural Machinery held in Japan in April. In August he went to Thailand and Malaysia to obtain information on the rice economies of Southeast Asia as regard the costs of production of types of equipment now being used, government policies on mechanization, the extent and potential for local fabrication of farm equipment and the present organization and objectives of local engineering and economic research on mechanization, and to explain the mechanization project of the Institute and how it might relate to their programs.

A trip was made by the associate farm super-

intendent to Taiwan in June to observe rice culture with reference to seedbed preparation, planting methods, pest and disease control, fertilizer application, farm mechanization and the general cultural practices followed by the experiment stations and farmers.

The treasurer visited Ceylon, East Pakistan and India in May to discuss fiscal matters with Institute staff members posted in those countries.

The executive officer visited Dacca, East Pakistan, in April, June, July and November on matters related to the construction of the laboratory and service buildings of the East Pakistan Accelerated Rice Research Institute (EPARRI). He was acting officer of the Institute on architectural and engineering services in the EPARRI buildings and in purchasing and handling imported materials for the buildings.

In March the librarian visited the Rice Archives at the University of Southwestern Louisiana and observed the operations of the Project URBANDOC at the Research Foundation of the City University of New York, the bibliographical services of the Engineering Societies in New York, and the information retrieval system at the Parkinson's Disease Information and Research Center of Columbia University.

The assistant director travelled to India in early January to deliver the presidential address to the Indian Society of Genetics, to attend meetings of the Indian Science Congress, and to assist in the selection of the professor of plant breeding in Punjab Agriculture University. In August he attended the International Genetic Congress in Tokyo and briefly visited the Crop Experiment Station in Suwon to observe rice research and interview candidates for training at the Institute. In October he travelled to several centers in India and Malaysia to visit rice research stations and observe extension programs. In November he went to Australia to visit the Coastal Plain Research Station near Darwin and the University of Queensland in Australia.

The associate director travelled to East Pakistan in February to observe cold injury and virus problems in commercial plantings of IR8 and to consult with government officials on the implementation of plans to develop the Joydevpur rice research farm. In March he went to Ceylon to review progress and plans for the cooperative

project started there between the Institute and the Ceylon Ministry of Agriculture. Extending the same trip, he visited the coordination center of the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project to review cooperative activities and the Tanjore and West Godavari districts to become acquainted with rice research and production in these important regions. Before returning to the Philippines he visited Thailand briefly to review the Institute's research program at the annual meetings of the Thailand Rice Department. In May he spent a week in Kenya at the request of the Minister of Agriculture to advise on the rice work in progress there and to identify possible areas of cooperation. In June, in connection with home leave, he spent several days in Washington, D.C. working on grant and contract matters through which the U.S. AID contributes to various aspects of the Institute's program. In September he went to Korea to discuss possible cooperative undertakings with the Office of Rural Development, Suwon, and to review previous results. In October he visited West Pakistan briefly to appear on the program of a seminar planned to bring the rice researchers of all of the provinces together to review their work and to plan new activities. In November he was in East Pakistan again to work on the implementation of project affairs with particular reference to the construction of the new physical plant of the rice research center and also to consult with Government officials on staffing and training aspects. Following this he stopped in Burma to discuss rice research and development with officials of the Ministry of Agriculture. In December he travelled again to Ceylon to discuss extension of the Ford Foundation-supported project. Continuing this trip he went to Washington, D.C. to confer with U.S. AID officials on progress and plans in the mechanization project.

In February and March the director travelled to Pakistan to look at agricultural research in both provinces and to make recommendations to the Ford Foundation regarding its future participation in such activities. Later in March and extending into April he travelled to the United States to see the experimental work of Dr. Carl N. Hodges and associates, to attend the symposium on "Strategy for the Conquest of Hunger" held at the Rockefeller University in New York, where he presented

a paper entitled "Accelerating agricultural output: The case for research." On the same trip he gave a lecture on "Rice at the Asia House" at the Asia Society in New York and later met with the U.S. Secretary of Agriculture, Orville Freeman, and his staff in Washington to discuss the Institute's program. He also visited the Environmental Research Laboratory at the University of Arizona. In late April and early May he attended the meeting of the Indian Council of Agricultural Researchers Scientific Advisory Committee (Rice), of which he is a member. He also attended the All-India Rice Workshop Meeting on the same trip and then spent a few days in Burma to review the rice research activities in that country. In May he visited the Coastal Plains Research Station, Australia, to become better acquainted with its rice research activities and consider with CSIRO's executive officers and scientists the course which rice research program should take. In late May he attended a meeting in Djakarta, Indonesia, jointly sponsored by the National Academy of Sciences

and its Indonesian counterpart to discuss food and nutrition research in Indonesia. In connection with home leave, he visited Nigeria, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Sierra Leone, and Senegal to advise with local authorities on rice research and development, and attended the International Seminar on Agricultural Change at the University of Reading, England. At these meetings he presented a joint paper with the Institute's economist on "The Spread of IRRI Varieties in Southeast Asia and the Indian Sub-Continent." In October he spent a week in India to review rice research work in the state of Punjab together with the assistant director. In late October he conferred with Rockefeller and Ford Foundation officers in New York on the budgetary plans of the Institute for 1969. In December the director travelled to Pakistan to receive an award known as "Sitaria-I-Imtiaz" from the President of Pakistan, Field Marshall Mohammad Ayub Khan. On the return trip he visited briefly in Thailand to observe rice research activities there.

Staff in International Program

WAYNE H. FREEMAN, Ph.D., Plant Breeder, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India.
HILLENIUS ten HAVE, D.Sc., Agronomist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India
HAROLD D. KAUFFMAN, Ph.D., Plant Pathologist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India.
PAUL C. LIPPOLD, Ph.D., Assistant Rice Advisor, The Ford Foundation, East Pakistan.

JOHN A. LOWE, Ph.D., Entomologist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India.
GORDON McLEAN, Ph.D., Rice Advisor, The Ford Foundation, West Pakistan.
JAMES C. MOOMAW, Ph.D., Agronomist, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Ceylon.
RUFUS K. WALKER, M.S., Rice Advisor, The Ford Foundation, East Pakistan.

Training Programs

The training of rice workers from different countries has always been an important activity of the Institute. The training programs are designed to enable participants to obtain experience and training in different areas of rice research and in rice production technology. Generally, the training periods range from 6 months to about 2 years, with one cropping season being considered as the minimum period of residence. Those staying at the Institute for 2 years would in most cases be candidates for the Master of Science degree from the College of Agriculture of the University of the Philippines. They enroll for course work at the College and carry out their thesis research at the Institute, with Institute scientists as their major advisors. Others with shorter periods of stay pursue a non-degree training program in different research areas.

The research trainees are designated as research scholars or research fellows. While a research scholar holds the Bachelor of Science degree, a research fellow is a relatively more experienced or a better qualified individual with the Master of Science or an equivalent degree. Post-doctoral fellows also participate in the Institute's research programs, usually by undertaking a specific research project of mutual interest. They contribute substantially to the research programs of the Institute and may not be considered as trainees in the strictest sense. The post-doctoral fellows get an opportunity to familiarize themselves with some special field of study and to conduct investigations using facilities and equipment often not available in their home institutions. In many instances they bring to the Institute special skills and experience that are particularly useful.

Persons admitted for training in rice production participate in a 6-month Rice Production Training Program which is oriented primarily to prepare and qualify individuals as rice production specialists. The rice production trainees usually hold at least the Bachelor of Science degree; in 1968 three of them possessed the Ph. D. degree. They are selected carefully from institutions concerned with the training of rice extension workers. The major objective of the rice production training program has been to train the trainers and to assist other institutions in establishing similar training programs for a large number of local extension workers engaged in educating the rice farmers. In 1968 graduates of previous rice production training programs organized several similar programs in the Philippines, Pakistan, Ceylon, Indonesia and Vietnam. Ten trainees from India who returned home in December, 1968 are expected to handle similar programs in their country. Quite obviously these training programs are having a great impact on rice production efforts in many countries. A more complete description of this activity can be found in the report of the Office of Communication.

By special arrangement, individuals may come to the Institute for periods of less than 6 months to acquire skills in specific techniques, to observe a small aspect of the Institute's program, or to review research results and techniques of potential value in their countries.

For the first time a 6 week workshop on field

experimentation with rice was organized in which 20 rice research workers from Pakistan, Thailand, India, Ceylon, and the Philippines participated. The workshop was aimed at assisting the scientists of rice research stations in improving (1) the design and execution of conventional field experiments, (2) the management of experimental plots, (3) the use of equipment in field experiments, and (4) the recording, analysis, interpretation and reporting of experimental data. The program included lectures on basic principles of field experiments and on different research areas related to rice technology as well as field and laboratory practices in various research areas.

The research scholars and trainees belong to educational and research institutions concerned with rice. Although the underdeveloped countries of South and Southeast Asia have received primary attention, occasionally candidates from other regions including some developed countries of Europe and America have been accepted for special reasons. A significant feature of the selection procedure is that the candidate must be sponsored by his employing institution which should give him an assurance of a position on his return. As almost all of the trainees return to work in their home institutions, they are able to utilize effectively the training that they receive at the Institute. This is what has made the training program a most successful and gratifying experience.

During 1968 a total of 125 scholars, 7 of them females, studied and worked at the Institute for part or all of the year. The number varied during the year but the total man-years in residence amounted to 62.5, the maximum number of scholars at any one time during the year being 79. The scholars came from Ceylon, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Pakistan, the Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Laos, Malaysia, Nepal, Nigeria, Vietnam, the United States, Germany, and Switzerland. Two Peace Corps volunteers and one U. S. Agency for International Development employee who were assigned to work in Asia comprised the trainees from the United States. They attended the 6-month rice production training course. A scholar from Germany and a fellow from Switzerland conducted basic research on certain aspects of the bacterial leaf streak disease of rice and on carbohydrate chemistry, respectively.

Research scholars from Thailand and Korea and the Institute plant pathologist examine cultures of bacteria causing the leaf blight disease of rice.

Research scholars from different countries consult rice literature in the Institute library.

Research scholars from Japan and Taiwan conduct greenhouse experiments on the brown planthopper.

A Filipino research scholar replaces the graph in an instrument which records changes in water level in a field experiment designed for an economic analysis of the rice yield response to irrigation.

The major fields of interest of the scholars covered all research areas in which the Institute was engaged, but relatively more applications were received from different countries in the areas of agronomy, varietal improvement, entomology, plant pathology and plant physiology. The number of applications actually received in each area was much larger than the number finally accepted; the competition facilitated the selection of the most suitable candidates. Apart from working on a particular research project, the research scholars get an opportunity to become generally acquainted with programs and results in related areas through departmental and Institute seminars. Every attempt is made to assign a scholar to a research project which would be of special benefit to rice programs in his country. For example, a Korean scholar working in the department of soil chemistry or soil microbiology would be encouraged to take up a research project involving investigations on a problem soil from Korea. Similarly, the research project of a scholar working in the department of plant pathology or entomology may pertain to an insect pest or a disease of serious economic importance in his country. The scholars receiving training in the varietal improvement department are encouraged to make crosses between selected parents, grow the F_1 generation at the Institute experimental farm, and take back material for studies at their home stations.

There is an increasing trend among the scholars to apply for a training program which leads to a degree, as this improves their qualifications and prospects for professional advancement. More than half of the research scholars worked toward the M. S. degree. As the basic qualifications of rice scientists in underdeveloped countries gradually improve, many inquiries are received from young workers for training leading to the Ph. D. degree. At present, there is no provision for such a training program but the Institute is looking into the possibility of making a modest beginning in this direction by developing arrangements with selected universities to have a scholar carry out his Ph. D. thesis research at the Institute.

Cereal chemistry, soil chemistry and agricultural engineering continue to be the fields receiving relatively fewer applications. The increased emphasis on rice mechanization in rice-

growing countries in recent years and the progress being made in the design and development of rice machinery at the Institute may result in more trainees in this area in the future. In the case of cereal chemistry and soil chemistry, the problem is one of identifying a qualified individual with a good basic knowledge of chemistry. It might be necessary to consider candidates from universities in addition to rice experiment stations to get persons who would be better qualified in the basic sciences and can profit by participating in the research programs of these two departments.

The training programs provide the Institute with an important means of developing informal contacts with institutions in other countries that are concerned with rice. With some countries, cooperative arrangements have been established for accelerating their rice research work. Although during the first few years a large proportion of the scholars came from the Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand and Japan, the numbers from such important rice-growing countries as India, Pakistan and Indonesia have gradually increased. To ensure the effectiveness of the Institute's effort to assist in rice research and production, relatively more candidates have been accommodated from those countries which have cooperative research projects with IRRI. Recently, considerable interest has been shown by some of the rice-growing countries of Africa and South America in having their rice workers trained at the Institute. A limited number of scholars from these countries will be accepted for training.

Five persons came to the Institute for short periods of training and/or to learn specific techniques, as described below:

SYED HARIS AHMED, mechanized cultivation officer, East Pakistan Agricultural Development Corporation, spent 3 months at the Institute to gain part-time on-the-job training in agricultural engineering and farm operations.

RAHERIZO ANDRIAMIALLY, assistant to the regional agricultural delegate for production, Ministry of Agriculture, Tananarive, Malagasy Republic, received a month of training in certain aspects of rice production technology.

MUHAMMAD IBRAHIM, assistant plant pathologist, Government Rice Farm, Kala-Shah-Kaku, West Pakistan completed one-and-a-half month of training in the technique of growing a rice blast nursery in the department of plant pathology.

SOTERO M. SORILLA, plant protection specialist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines, completed a month of training in the technique of growing a rice blast nursery in the department of plant pathology.

TAN BOCK THIAM, assistant lecturer, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, received training in certain aspects of rice production and agricultural economics during a 3-week visit.

The following 20 persons participated in the 6-week rice field experimentation workshop:

MEENHON K. ABBASI, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan.

CH. BASHIR AHMAD, research assistant, Government Rice Farm, Kala-Shah-Kaku, West Pakistan.

WEERASINGHE N. ALWIS, experimental officer, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

MANOON ANECKACHAI, chief, Kuan Gut Rice Experiment Station, Phatthalung, Thailand.

DAMKHEONG CHANDRAPANYA, second grade officer, Khonkaen Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

M. A. CHOUDHURY, assistant economic botanist, Agricultural Research Institute, Rice Division, East Pakistan.

MD. ABDUL HAMID, assistant botanist, Directorate of Agriculture, East Pakistan.

WAHIDUL ISLAM, project director, East Pakistan Soil Fertility and Soil Testing Institute, Dacca, East Pakistan.

PONGVUTTI KLUNCHAROEN, technician, Hantra Rice Experiment Station, Ayudhya, Thailand.

ALLAH DITTA MASTOI, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan.

S.C. MODGAL, associate professor, U. P. Agricultural University, Pantnagar, India.

ZOLLO QUISMORIO, agronomist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines.

MODEKURT V. RAO, research officer in agronomy, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

SOMPOTE SEKHANAN, Chief, Koksamrong Rice Experiment Station, Lopburi, Thailand.

GHULAM R. SOLANGI, research assistant, Agricultural Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan.

ARBAB ALI SOOMRO, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan.

MUHAMMAD JALALUDDIN TALUKDAR, mycologist, Agricultural Research Institute, Directorate of Agriculture, East Pakistan.

WILFREDO VARGAS, agronomist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines.

UTHAI WONGVISES, second grade officer, Breeding Division, Rice Department, Bangkok, Thailand.

V. YOGARATNAM, experimental officer, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon.

Rice Production Trainees

Thirty-four participants completed 6 months of training in rice production, applied research, and communication, as follows:

RAFIUDDIN AHMED, instructor, National Development Training Institute, East Pakistan.

ROMULO P. ALCALA, vocational agriculture teacher, Baybay National Agriculture and Vocational School, Philippines.

PATURI AMMIRAJU, plant protection specialist, Intensive Agricultural District Program, Andhra Pradesh, India.

GADICHERLA BABURAO, superintendent, Agricultural Research Station, Andhra Pradesh, India.

MD. ABDUL HAQ BHUIYAN, principal, Agricultural Extension Training Institute, East Pakistan.

SUDHAMOY BISWAS, Kalyani University, West Bengal, India.

CHARLES T. BRACKNEY, soils advisor, U.S. Agency for International Development, Saigon, Vietnam.

SIMMA CHAREUNSOUK, supervisor, Rice Seed Distribution Program, Vientiane, Laos.

BISHWA N. CHATTERJEE, agronomist, Kalyani University, West Bengal, India.

MAHABIR S. CHAUDHRY, irrigation agronomist, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

TRAN-THI-LE-CHI, plant pathologist, Directorate of Research, Saigon, South Vietnam.

PHANG CHENG CHONG, agricultural assistant, Department of Agriculture, West Malaysia.

NGUYEN-MINH DUC, Directorate of Agricultural Affairs, Saigon, Vietnam.

THOMAS J. ELLIS, Peace Corps volunteer, Philippines.

P. HANUMAPPA, extension leader, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, India.

ROBERT M. HOLLISTER, Peace Corps volunteer, Philippines.

JAYANTHE JAYATILAKE, agricultural extension officer, Department of Agriculture, Peradeniya, Ceylon.

JAGIR SINGH KHARA, assistant professor of extension, Punjab Agricultural University, India.

ZACHARIUS S. MAWUNTU, head of plant protection, Sang Hjang Seri, Subang, Indonesia.

PHAM THI TO NGA, Directorate of Agricultural Affairs, South Vietnam.

NOORDIN BIN OSMAN, agricultural assistant, Department of Agriculture, Kedah, Malaysia.

CHATRABHUJ R. PADALIA, research officer, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

RATMO, Directorate of Agricultural Education, Djakarta, Indonesia.

MUHAMAD SIDIK, chief of rice section, Directorate of Agriculture, Djakarta, Indonesia.

RAMON L. SIMBULAN, secondary school teacher, Pampanga National Agricultural School, Philippines.

R. SIMHADRI, assistant crop specialist, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, India.

KHAMPHA SIRISOMPHONE, assistant chief of agricultural research, Directorate of Agriculture, Vientiane, Laos.

J. SOEPRIAMAN, Agriculture Research Center, Bogor, Indonesia.

FELIPE SUARIN, assistant farm superintendent, Siliman University, Philippines.

A. SUBRAMANIAM, crop specialist, Regional Research Station, Madras, India.

BASIMAN TAMPUBOLON, assistant plant breeding instructor, Bogor Institute of Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia.

KANDIAH THEVATHASAN, agricultural extension officer, Department of Agriculture, Peradeniya, Ceylon.

NGUYEN DINH TOAN, 4-T section deputy chief, Directorate of Agricultural Affairs, Saigon, Vietnam.

MOI SOONG WOOL, agricultural assistant, State Agricultural Office, Perak, West Malaysia.

The following six individuals completed the 6 month rice production training course in 1967 and received on-the-job training for a further period of about 6 months in different areas, as follows:

APOLINAR ASENCION, Philippines	(rice production)
RUBEN S. BORJA, Philippines	(agronomy)
AGAPITO GONZALVO, JR., Philippines	(varietal improvement)
WILHELMINO HERRERA, Philippines	(multiple cropping)
FLORENCIO MACAPUGAY, Philippines	(rice production)
SESINANDO MASAJO, Philippines	(rice production)

Research Scholars

A total of 46 research scholars studied at the Institute in 1968 and 29 of them were enrolled for the Master of Science degree. Sixteen research scholars completed their training during the year, 11 with the M.S. degree. Their names, home institutions, and major research were as follows:

Agronomy

MANZUR AHMAD, research assistant, Government Rice Farm, Kala-Shah-Kaku, West Pakistan. Major research: Water management and efficacy of granular herbicides in flooded rice.

PIYA DUANGPATRA,** junior instructor and researcher, Agronomy Department, Kasetsart University, Thailand. Major research: Phosphorus fertilizers and soil fertility.

SAMSON O. FAGADE, research officer, Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria. Major research: Effect of plant density and fertilization on the growth characteristics and grain yield of flooded rice.

JAMES E. HAWES,* agronomy advisor, U.S. Agency for International Development, Laos. Major research: Establishment of direct seeded rice and Age and nutrition of seedlings for transplanted rice.

JIN KOO PARK, junior agronomist, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Major research: Weed control and effect of management levels on the grain yield of two varietal types of rice.

ERASMO G. SAGARAL,** vocational agriculture teacher, Central Mindanao University, Philippines. Major research: Herbicides for upland rice.

VISHNU PRASAD SHARMA,** assistant manager, Department of Agriculture, Nepal. Major research: Rice fertilizers and fertilizer response.

AKIN WILLIAMS,** rice agronomist, Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria. Major research: Water management and environmental influences in flooded rice.

PONNAMPALAM YOGARATNAM, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ceylon. Major research: Minimum tillage in direct seeded and transplanted flooded rice.

Chemistry

NATIVIDAD B. RAMOS,** instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Varietal differences in physico-chemical properties of caryopsis and starch of glutinous rice.

Communication

DIOSDADO V. CASTRO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Not selected.

CORAZÓN V. MENDOZA, editorial assistant, The International Rice Research Institute, Philippines. Major research: Not selected.

SOSIMO PABLICO, Philippines. Major research: Evaluation of the "Mini-Kit" in an applied research program.

Agricultural Economics

NARCISO DEOMAMPO,** instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: An economic analysis of the effect of tillage, weeding and nitrogen interaction on the yield of rice.

SHENG-HUI LIAO, graduate research fellow, UP-Cornell Exchange Program, Taiwan. Major research: Factors affecting the spread of new rice varieties.

CARL MONTAÑO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Economics of insecticide use.

DIBJO PRABOWO, instructor, Gadjah Mada University, Jogjakarta, Indonesia. Major research: Sources of out-plant growth in Indonesian rice production.

* Completed training.

** Completed Master of Science degree.

- RODOLFO D. REYES, research assistant, Agricultural Engineering Department, The International Rice Research Institute, Philippines. Major research: Economic analysis of water utilization in rice.
- REYNALDO DE SAGUN, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Income elasticity of demand for rice in the Philippines.
- MOISES L. SARDIDO, instructor, University Research Center, University of Eastern Philippines. Major research: Rice production systems and multiple cropping.

Agricultural Engineering

- ANTERO MANALO,** research assistant, The International Rice Research Institute, Philippines. Major research: Design of a laboratory type counterflow rice dryer.

Entomology

- CHING-HUAN CHENG, junior entomologist, Department of Plant Protection Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan. Major research: Varietal resistance to green leafhopper (*Nephotettix impicticeps*) in rice.
- IJAZ AHMAD DAR, research assistant in charge, Government Rice Farm, West Pakistan. Major research: Life history and control of pink stem borer, *Sesamia inferens*.
- T. YESU DAS research assistant, Agricultural University of Andhra Pradesh, India. Major research: Varietal resistance to rice stem borers.
- MARGARITA FORTUNO,* plant pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Varietal resistance to the brown planthoppers.
- A.N.M. REZAUL KARIM, research assistant, Department of Agriculture, East Pakistan. Major research: Bionomics of rice leaf whorl maggot, *Hydrellia philippina*, chemical control and varietal resistance.
- CAESAR PURA, teacher, Bureau of Public Schools, Philippines. Major research: Varietal resistance to brown planthoppers.
- CARLOS R. VEGA,** research assistant, The International Rice Research Institute, Philippines. Major research: Sex attraction studies in stripe borer moths, *Chilo suppressalis*.

Experiment Station Management

- MUHAMMAD ABDUS SALAM, farm superintendent, Directorate of Agriculture, Dacca, Pakistan. Major field: Experiment station management.

Plant Pathology

- SUNETRA EAMCHIT second grade officer, Rice Pathology Branch, Rice Department, Bangkok, Thailand. Major research: Seed transmission of *Xanthomonas oryzae*.
- GERD FRANCK,* assistant, Laboratory of Phytopathology, Hohenheim, Germany. Major research: Bacterial leaf streak disease of rice.
- SOON HYUNG LEE, junior researcher, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Suwon

Korea. Major research: Virus transmission and serological tests.

- MD. QUAMARUZZAMAN,** research assistant, Division of Mycology and Plant Pathology, East Pakistan Agricultural Research Institute. Major research: Seasonal changes of the pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae*.
- LEONARDO SANTOS, plant entomologist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Major research: Variability of *Rhizoctonia oryzae* strains in the Philippines.

Plant Physiology

- ANNAPANTULA BHADRACHALAM, senior scientific assistant, Agricultural Chemistry Division, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India. Major research: Factors affecting the uptake of zinc in soils.
- MANUEL PALADA, instructor, Central Philippine University, Philippines. Major research: Submergence and survival of rice plants.

Soil Chemistry

- DAE YOUNG CHO, assistant soil chemist, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea. Major research: Influence of soil temperature on the chemical kinetics of flooded soil and the growth of rice plant.
- TZE-SHUN LEE,** junior specialist, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Taiwan. Major research: Influence of calcium carbonate, presubmergence and phosphate on the chemical changes and the growth of rice in a flooded acid latosolic soil.

Soil Microbiology

- SANG KYU LEE, assistant to soil microbiologist, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea. Major research: Transformation and determination of organic acids in paddy soils.
- IRENEO MANGUIAT, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Microbial transformation of nitrogen in flooded soils.

Statistics

- K.M. PALANISWAMY, statistical officer, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Coimbatore, India. Major research: Experimental statistics.
- SUTJIHNO,** assistant-in-charge, Statistical Division, Coordinated Bureau for Research Institutes, Indonesia. Major research: Multivariate methods in rice research.

Varietal Improvement

- SUNG HO HONG, research assistant, Crop Experiment Station, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea. Major research: IRRI-Korea cooperative rice breeding program.
- TOMAS MASAJO, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Major research: Breeding behavior of white belly in rice grain and its relationship to amylose content and gelatinization temperature.
- SOON JAI PARK,* junior agronomist, Crop Experiment Station, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea.

Major research: Improving plant type of Korean rice using japonica x indica crosses.

M.S. QURESHI,* assistant botanist (rice), Government Rice Farm, Kala-Shah-Kaku, West Pakistan. Major research: General rice breeding.

Research Fellows

Fifteen research fellows conducted investigations in the general areas of agronomy, plant physiology, entomology, rice breeding, cereal chemistry, and agricultural engineering. Four of them were post-doctoral fellows.

HANS ALBERT GREMLI, Institute of Agricultural Chemistry, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich, Switzerland, is engaged in chemical investigations on hemicelluloses of rice bran.

JIRO HARADA,* graduate student, Department of Agronomy, Faculty of Agriculture, Tohoku University, Japan, carried out biochemical studies on the internode elongation of the rice plant.

YOSHIHIKO HAYAKAWA,* graduate student, Hokkaido University, Hokkaido, Japan, studied the effect of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on the photosynthetic activity of the active center leaf of various rice varieties.

MAKOTO HOKI,* graduate student, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan, completed studies of dynamic relationship between tractors and their implements on the wet land.

K.I. JAMES,* assistant rice research officer, Central Rice Research Station, Pattambi, India, participated in the Institute rice breeding programs.

M. SALEH KHOKAR, research assistant, Government Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan, is studying general rice breeding.

V.A. KULKARNI, assistant botanist, Agricultural Research Institute, Bihar, India, is studying general rice breeding.

ABDUL MAJID, assistant economic botanist (cereals), Directorate of Agriculture, Dacca, East Pakistan, is studying the effect of split application of N on grain yield and the effect of some growth regulators on the tillering of rice plant.

S.C. MODGAL,* associate professor of agronomy, Uttar Pradesh Agricultural University, Pantnagar, India, worked on water use and management in transplanted rice.

S.N. RAGHAVENDRA RAO,* senior scientific assistant, Central Food Technology Research Institute, Mysore, India, studied changes in the physicochemical properties of rice during parboiling.

D.V. SESHU,* assistant botanist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, India, participated in the Institute rice breeding programs.

NAMBRATTIL SETHUNATHAN,* senior fellow, University Botany Laboratory, Madras-5, India, worked on pesticide residues.

KAZUSHIGE SOGAWA, research associate, Laboratory of Applied Entomology and Nematology, Faculty of Agriculture, Nagoya University, Japan, is studying the feeding behavior of brown planthoppers on susceptible and resistant rice varieties.

HIDEO WATANABE, technical officer, Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo, Japan, is studying varietal difference in photosynthetic rate of the rice plant.

MD. ABU YUSSOUF, research assistant, Directorate of Agriculture, Dacca, East Pakistan, is working on variety, method of planting and fertilizer management in flooded rice.

Advanced Study in the United States

Financial support was provided to promising individuals for advanced studies. Grantees were either from the Institute's junior staff and from other institutions in the Philippines or from the rice research staff of Pakistan and Ceylon because funds were available specifically for this purpose in the country projects concerned. Their names, along with the subject of specialty and the institutions attended were as follows:

SHAMSUL ALAM, East Pakistan, entomology, Cornell University.

GLORIA B. CAGAMPANG,* Philippines, biochemistry, Purdue University.

NAGAMUTTU DEVASUNDRARAJAH, Ceylon, agronomy, Cornell University.

WILFREDO G. ESPADA,** Philippines, agronomy, Ohio State University.

PANAMBARAGE SAMUEL YESUDAS FERNANDO, Ceylon, plant pathology, University of Hawaii.

LETICIA R. MENDIOLA,** Philippines, biochemistry, Rutgers University.

LUCILA PARIAL,* Philippines, cereal chemistry, Texas A&M University.

MUHAMMAD EHSAN UL HAQ TUSNEEM, West Pakistan, soils, Louisiana State University.

Short-Term Visitors

The following rice research and extension workers from different countries came to the Institute to become acquainted with a particular aspect of the Institute's activity or to review results of research in their areas of interest.

MICHEL ARRAUDEAU, chief of plant breeding division, Institut de Recherches Agronomiques a Madagascar, Tananarive, Malagasy Republic, spent 3 weeks at the Institute to become acquainted with the research work in the varietal improvement department.

* Completed Master of Science degree

** Completed Ph. D. degree.

- R. CHABROLIN, Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrieres, Paris, spent 1 week at the Institute to familiarize himself with research work pertaining to nutrition of the rice plant.
- WILLIE COOK, extension advisor in rice, U.S. Agency for International Development, Indonesia, spent 2 weeks at the Institute to become fully informed regarding the content of the IRRI rice production training course, teaching methodology and practical training.
- RUBEN DAYRIT, rice agronomist, Marianas Islands, U.S. Trust Territory, reviewed recent results of rice research in agronomy during a 2-week visit.
- M.L. JERATH, principal research officer, Entomologist, Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria, spent a week at the Institute to become acquainted with the latest advances in entomological research in rice.
- SHYAM SUNDER MISRA, assistant economic botanist, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, India, studied the Institute varietal improvement program during a 2-week visit.
- SIVASAMBO NATESAN, agricultural officer (extension), Department of Agriculture, Colombo 7, Ceylon, spent 3 weeks at the Institute to study its extension-oriented activities.
- SORASITH VACHAROTAYAN, head, Soils Department, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand, spent 4 months at the Institute to become familiar with the research in the soil chemistry department and to review literature on soil fertility and the chemistry of flooded soils.

Publications and Seminars

Staff Publications

Plant Physiology

- LAMIN, J.B. and B.S. VERGARA. 1968. Seasonal variations in the growth duration of some Malayan rice varieties. *Malaysian Agr. J.* 46: 298-315.
- TANAKA, A. and B.S. VERGARA. 1967. Growth habit and ripening of rice plants in relation to the environmental conditions in the Far East. *Intern. Rice Comm. Newslet. (Special Issue 1967.)* p. 26-42.
- VERGARA, B.S. and R. LILIS. 1967. Response to photoperiod of reported long-day and intermediate varieties of rice. *Nature* 216: 168.
- VERGARA, B.S., R. LILIS, A. BUENO and R. DONATO. 1967. Adaptability to cultural conditions of Raminad Strain 3. *Phil. Agriculturist* 51: 253-267.

Cereal Chemistry

- BRIONES, V.P., L.G. MAGBANUA, and B.O. JULIANO. 1968. Changes in physicochemical properties of starch of developing rice grain. *Cereal Chem.* 45: 351-357.
- IGNACIO, C.C., and B.O. JULIANO. 1968. Physicochemical properties of brown rice from *Oryza* species and hybrids. *J. Agr. Food Chem.* 16: 125-127.
- JULIANO, B.O. 1968. Relation of some properties of rice starch and protein to eating quality preferences for milled rice in Asia. *Getreide Mehl* 18: 82-84. (in German)
- JULIANO, B.O., A.V. CARTAÑO, and A.J. VIDAL. 1968. Note on a limitation of the starch-iodine blue test for milled rice amylose. *Cereal Chem.* 45: 63-65.
- JULIANO, B.O., C.C. IGNACIO, V.M. PANGANIBAN, and C.M. PEREZ. 1968. Screening for high protein rice varieties from the IRRI world collection. *Cereal Sci. Today* 13: 299-301, 313.
- PALMIANO, E.P., A.M. ALMAZAN, and B.O. JULIANO. 1968. Physicochemical properties of protein of developing and mature rice grain. *Cereal Chem.* 45: 1-12.
- ROSARIO, A.R. del, V.P. BRIONES, A.J. VIDAL, and B.O. JULIANO. 1968. Composition and endosperm structure of developing and mature rice kernel. *Cereal Chem.* 45: 225-235.

Varietal Improvement

- MUN HEU, T. T. CHANG and H. M. BEACHELL. 1968. The inheritance of culm length, panicle length, duration to heading and bacterial leaf blight reaction in a rice cross Sigadis x Taichung (Native) I. *Jap. J. Breed.* 18: 7-11.
- CHANG, T. T. and C. C. LI. 1968. Component analysis of vegetative growth duration in rice. *Agron. Abst. Amer. Soc. Agron.* 5.
- CHANG, T. T. and C. C. LI. 1968. Component analysis of heading date in rice. *Proc. 12th Intern. Congr. Genetics, Tokyo, Japan.* 1: 256.

Plant Pathology

- LING, K. C. and V. M. AGUIERO. 1967. Breeding for efficient transmitting colony of *Nilaparvata lugens*, vector of rice grassy stunt virus. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 6.
- LING, K. C. and M. K. PALOMAR. 1967. Preliminary studies on the feeding habits of *Nephotettix impicticeps*. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 6.
- LING, K. C. 1968. Virus diseases of the rice plant. Bulletin, The Intern. Rice Res. Inst., Los Baños, Laguna, 52 pp.
- OU, S. H. and M. R. AYAD. 1967. Physiologic races of *Piricularia oryzae* from single blast lesion. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 10.
- OU, S. H., F. L. NUQUE, T. T. EBRON, JR. and C. VON CHONG. 1967. Further studies on physiologic races of *Piricularia oryzae* in the Philippines. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 11.
- OU, S. H., F. L. NUQUE and J. P. SILVA. 1967. Resistance of IRRI world collection and Philippine seedboard rice varieties to bacterial leaf blight. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 10.
- OU, S. H., F. L. NUQUE and J. P. SILVA. 1967. Pathogenicity patterns of 50 strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae*. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 12.
- OU, S. H., F. L. NUQUE, J. P. SILVA and S. T. HSU. 1967. Effect of nitrogen and temperatures on the development of bacterial blight lesions in rice. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 11.
- OU, S. H. and P. C. SANCHEZ. 1967. Variation in pathogenicity of *Piricularia oryzae* in pure culture. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 13.
- OU, S. H. and P. C. SANCHEZ. 1967. Preliminary study on the effect of toxins produced by *Piricularia oryzae*. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 13.
- OU, S. H., P. C. SANCHEZ and H. T. HSU. 1967. The relation of reducing sugar and total nitrogen ratio to rice blast. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 14.
- PALOMAR, M.K. and C.T. RIVERA. 1967. Yellow dwarf of rice in the Philippines. *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 27-34; Abstract: *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 16.
- QUAMARUZZAMAN, MD. 1968. Seasonal changes of the pathogenic races of *Piricularia oryzae* Cav. at the IRRI blast nursery. M.S. Thesis. Univ. of the Phil. Coll. Agric., 62 pp.
- RIVERA, C.T. and S.H. OU. 1967. Strains of rice tungro virus. (Abstract.) *Phil. Phytopath.* 3(1 & 2): 19.
- RIVERA, C.T., S.H. OU and T.D.M. TANTERE. 1968. Tungro disease of rice in Indonesia. *Plant Dis. Repr.* 52(2): 122-124.

Agronomy

- MOOMAW, J. C. and D. S. KIM. 1968. Selectivity of 2,3,5-trichloro-4-pyridinol as a herbicide for flooded rice. *Weed Research* 8(3):

RACHO, V. V. and S. K. DE DATTA. 1968. Nitrogen economy of cropped and uncropped rice soils under field conditions. *Soil Sci. 105*: 419-427.

DE DATTA, S.K., C. P. MAGNAYE and J. C. MOOMAW. 1968. Efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen (N^{15} -labelled) for flooded rice. *Proc. 9th Intern. Soil Sci. Congr. Adelaide IV*: 67-76.

MOOMAW, J. C., S. K. DE DATTA, D. E. SEAMAN and P. YOGARATNAM. 1968. New directions in weed control research for tropical rice. *Proc. 9th British Weed Control Conference, Brighton, U.K. 2*: 675-681.

MOOMAW, J. C. and S. K. DE DATTA. 1968. The response of high-yielding variety in improved management practices. *IRC Working Party Meetings, Kandy, Ceylon*. Sept. 2-14: 1968. IRC/PP - C8/VIII/8.

DE DATTA, S. K., A. C. TAURO and S. N. BALAOING. 1968. Effect of plant type and nitrogen level on the growth characteristics and grain yield of indica rice in the tropics. *Agronomy J. 60*: 643-

Entomology

KAMRAN, M.A. and E.S. RAROS. 1968. Seasonal fluctuations in abundance of various rice stem borers on Luzon Island, Philippines. *J. Econ. Entom. 61*(3): 650-656.

PATHAK, M.D. 1968. Ecology of common insect pests. *Ann. Rev. Entom. 13*: 257-294.

PATHAK, M.D. 1968. Control of major rice pests. *Intern. Pest Control*. December, 1968.

PATHAK, M.D. 1968. Application of insecticides to paddy water for more effective rice pest control. *Intern. Pest Control* November- December, 1968.

Soil Microbiology

MACRAE, I.C., R.R. ANCAJAS, and S. SALANDANAN. 1968. The fate of nitrate nitrogen in some tropical soils following submergence. *Soil Sci. 105*(5): 327-334.

Agricultural Economics

BARKER, R. and A. SOOTHIPAN. 1968. Economic efficiency and profitability of rice farming in the Philippines and Thailand. *Farm Management Notes 4*(1): 8-14.

BARKER, R. and E. U. QUINTANA. 1967. Farm management studies of costs and returns in rice production. *The Seminar-workshop on the Economics of Rice Production*. Paper presented at a Conference, IRRI, Dec. 8-9, 1967. 48 pp.

BARKER, R. and S. K. DE DATTA. Management practices and economic analysis of experimental results in rice production. *The Seminar-workshop on the Economics of Rice Production*. Paper presented at a Conference, IRRI, December 8-9, 1967. 38 pp.

Seminars

The following topics were the subjects of seminars held at the Institute during 1968. Unless otherwise stated the speakers were staff members.

- “Miracle rice” as “produced” by the press. *Dr. Gelia Tagumpay-Castillo*, associate professor, UPCA.
- Progress of the IRRI rice breeding program. *Mr. Beachell*.
- The story of hybrid bajra (pearl millet). *Dr. Athwal*.
- A review of the international activities of the Institute. *Dr. McClung*.
- Rice cultivation in Thailand. *Dr. Sala Dasananda*, director general, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Thailand.
- The problems of the Philippine sugar industry, *Dr. Thomas R. McHale*, president, Victorias Milling Co., Inc., Victorias, Occidental Negros.
- Reflections on Asian agricultural development, *Dr. David Hopper*, agricultural economist, Indian Agricultural Program of The Rockefeller Foundation.
- Breeding potatoes for improved yield. *Dr. Robert Plaisted*, head, Department of Plant Breeding, Cornell University.
- Inorganic nitrogen metabolism of soil microorganisms. *Dr. T. Yoshida*.
- An integrated approach on the problem of rice quality. *Dr. Juliano*.
- Administration's rice and corn self-sufficiency program. *Mr. Teofilo Azada*, director, RCPC.
- Impact of modernization on attitudes and values. *Dr. George Guthrie*, Pennsylvania State University.
- Irrigation program in the Philippines. *Mr. Alfredo L. Juinio*, administrator, National Irrigation Administration.
- Rice weed problems in Thailand. *Dr. D. E. Seaman*, visiting weed scientist, IRRI.
- The Asian Development Bank – progress and prospects. *Amb. Bernard Zagorin*, U.S. representative to the Board of Governors of the Asian Development Bank.
- Some observations of rice growing in Arkansas, *Dr. Reeshon Feuer*, visiting professor in crops and soil extension, UPCO.
- Fertility of lowland rice soils in some southern Asian countries. *Dr. Keizaburo Kawaguchi*, professor of soils, Kyoto University.
- The Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture. *Dr. Gil S. Saguiguit*, assistant director, SEAMES.
- Rice Production in California, *Dr. D. S. Mikkelsen*, visiting scientist, IRRI.
- Observations on rice production in Australia, Burma, India and Pakistan. *Dr. Chandler*.
- The role of the Comilla Academy in Pakistan's development, *Dr. Nicolaas Luykx*, senior advisor, Michigan State University, Pakistan Project on Rural Development, Comilla, East Pakistan.
- Immuno-genetics of self-incompatibility in cabbage. *Dr. Don Wallace*, visiting professor, UP-Cornell Program.
- Weed control in rice (current results). *Dr. De Datta*.
- The UPCA corn program. *Dr. Virgilio Carañgal*, Plant Breeding Division, Agronomy Department, UPCA.
- Problems of soil management and manuring in Equatorial Africa. *Dr. E. W. Russell*, Department of Soil Science, The University, Reading, England.
- Agricultural data collection in the Philippines. *Dr. Leonardo Paulino*, director, Bureau of Agricultural Economics.
- Status of Agricultural Statistics in Asia and the Far East. *Dr. Burton T. Oñate*, statistician, Asian Development Bank.
- The world export market for rice and Philippine self-sufficiency. *Dr. Barker*.
- Wheat breeding in Kansas. *Dr. E. G. Heyne*, Department of Agronomy, Kansas State University.
- Agricultural aircraft in rice production. *Mr. Golden*.
- Organization and activities of Esso Fertilizer in the Philippines. *Dr. J. G. Davide*, acting marketing operations manager, Esso Standard Fertilizer & Agricultural Chemicals Co., Inc.
- What I didn't know about growing rice. *Dr. Orlando J. Sacay*, president, The Agricultural Executives, Inc.
- The organization and operation in other banks in the Philippines. *Mr. Tirso V. Antiporda*, associate director, Department of Rural Banks, Central Bank of the Philippines.
- Soil organic compounds as plant growth promoters and inhibitors. *Dr. Thomas S. C. Wang*, visiting professor, Department of Soils, UPCA.
- Rice drying in the Philippines. *Dr. Dante de Padua*, chairman, Department of Agricultural Engineering, UPCA.
- The international center for tropical agriculture – a report on development. *Dr. Francis C. Byrnes*, CIAT, Colombia.
- Recent studies on varietal resistance to rice stem borers, leafhoppers and planthoppers. *Dr. Pathak*.
- Economics of mechanization of rice. *Dr. S. Johnson*.
- Some Problems of Agricultural Development in Asia. *Dr. W. Klatt*, O.B.E., formerly economic advisor, Foreign Office, The United Kingdom.
- Seed Growers Association of the Philippines – a new enterprise. *Mr. Abel L. Silva*, president, Seed Growers Association of the Philippines, Inc.
- Some observations on rice research and production in West Africa. *Dr. Chandler*.
- IR8 rice production with CO² enrichment. *Dr. James Riley*, Environmental Research Laboratory of the University of Arizona.
- Rice production in Indonesia. *Dr. Leon Mears*, University of the Philippines Program in Development Economics.
- Radiation damage, mutation and repair of the gene. *Dr. Baldomero M. Olivera*, research associate professor, Department of Biochemistry, College of Medicine, University of the Philippines.
- The use of calcium silicate on sugar cane in Hawaii. *Dr. D. L. Plucknett*, University of Hawaii.

